

Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000

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Abstract

*This paper brings natural numbers from 11112 to 20000 written in **ascending** and **descending** orders of 1 to 9. Most of the numbers are obtained by using basic operations, except few. It is revised version of author's previous work [41], where for the missing numbers **factorial** and **square-root** are used. In this work, only **factorial** is used for missing numbers. The representations for the numbers 20001 to 30000 are given in the next work. The representations from 0 to 11111 author's previous work [18]. In the previous work, all the numbers are written with basic operations except one, i.e., 10958 (in the increasing case). For more details and comments refer [19].*

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1 Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers

In this section natural numbers are represented in three different types.

1.1 Increasing and Decreasing

In 2013-2014, author [18] wrote natural numbers in increasing and decreasing orders of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1. See below some examples:

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$$\begin{aligned}
100 &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 \times 9 = 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
101 &:= 1 + 2 + 34 + 5 + 6 \times 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
102 &:= 12 + 3 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\
103 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 34 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4 + 3 + 21 \\
104 &:= 1 + 23 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 65 + 4 \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\
105 &:= 1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4 + 56 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
106 &:= 12 + 3 + 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
107 &:= 1 \times 23 + 4 + 56 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 \times 1 \\
108 &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 78 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1.
\end{aligned}$$

<http://bit.ly/2wnZq6g>

$$\begin{aligned}
786 &:= 1 + 23 + 4 + 56 + 78 \times 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 \times 4 \times 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
999 &:= 12 \times 3 \times (4 + 5) + (67 + 8) \times 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 654 + 321 \\
2535 &:= 1 + 2345 + (6 + 7 + 8) \times 9 = 9 + 87 \times (6 + 5 \times 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
2607 &:= 123 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + (7 + 8) \times 9 = 987 + 6 \times 54 \times (3 + 2) \times 1 \\
10483 &:= 1 + 23 \times 456 - 7 - 8 + 9 = (9 \times 87 \times 6 + 543) \times 2 + 1 \\
10549 &:= 1^2 \times 34 \times 5 \times (6 + 7 \times 8) + 9 = 9 + (87 \times 6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3 + 2) \times 1 \\
10550 &:= 1^2 + 34 \times 5 \times (6 + 7 \times 8) + 9 = 9 + (87 \times 6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3 + 2) + 1 \\
10553 &:= 1 \times 23 \times 456 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times 5 \times 43 + 21) \\
10554 &:= 1 + 23 \times 456 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) \times 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\
11807 &:= 1 \times 234 \times (5 + 6 \times 7) + 89 = -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)^2 \times 1.
\end{aligned}$$

<http://bit.ly/2wnZq6g>

For more details refer author's complete work [18, 19].

1.2 Comments and Discussions

This work has been considered as "**Improbable Research**". For details see the link:

- (i) <http://www.improbable.com/2013/02/12/lots-of-numbers-plain-and-almost-simple/> - [1];
- (ii) <http://www.improbable.com/2013/06/08/lots-more-numbers-deemed-crazy-sequential/> - [2].

Also refer [9, 10] for more comments. We observe that the number 10958 is the only number among 0 to 11111 that is not possible to write in terms of 1 to 9 in the increasing case. We need to use extra operations such as **square-root** and/or **factorial** to write it. See below:

$$10958 := 1 + 2 + 3!! + (-4 + 5! + 6 - 7) \times 89.$$

Recently, **Numberphile** produced two videos on **YouTube** using **concatenation** as an extra operation to bring representation of number 10958 in increasing order. See below both the links [11, 12]:

- (i) **The 10,958 Problem - Numberphile;**
- (ii) **A 10,958 Solution - Numberphile.**

Also this number has become a question of discussion at various web-sites. See the links below:

- (i) http://www.primepuzzles.net/puzzles/puzz_864.htm - [16];
- (ii) <https://www.futilitycloset.com/?s=10958> - [8];
- (iii) <https://puzzling.stackexchange.com/questions/51129/the-10-958-problem> - [13];
- (iv) <https://puzzling.stackexchange.com/questions/47923/rendering-the-number-10-958-with-the-string-1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9>; - [14]
- (v) https://www.reddit.com/r/mathematics/comments/6hooq2/the_10958_problem/; - [15]
- (vi) <http://digg.com/video/10958-math-problem>;
- (vii) <http://wssrmnn.net/index.php/2017/04/20/the-10958-problem/>;
- (viii) <https://twitter.com/aap03102/status/854319054173220864>;
- (ix) <https://inderjtaneja.com/2017/12/02/10958-problem-1-5-millions-views/>.

Extensions of above work to higher numbers refer to Ames [3, 4], and A.E. Bras and V.H.J. van der Veiden [5, 6]. For different bases A.E. Bras and V.H.J. van der Veiden refer to link [19]. Also extension to small bases refer Wylie [17].

For more studies on representations of numbers in different ways refer to author's work [18]-[41].

2 Crazy Representations From 11112 to 20000

Below are representations of natural numbers from 11112 to 20000 in ascending and descending orders of 1 to 9. Most of the results are with operations, except few. For these numbers, the idea of **factorial** is applied. These results are divided in two subsections. One is numbers with **factorial**, and another a complete list giving all the numbers.

Remark 2.1. Most of the results are with **excess of brackets**. After simplifications, these **extra brackets** can easily be removed. Moreover, the expressions of type " $\times - a$ " etc. requires more attention for simplifications.

2.1 Representations by Use of Factorial

Below are numbers represented by use of **factorial**. These numbers are divided in two subsections. One on ascending order and another in descending order of 1 to 9.

2.1.1 Ascending Order of 1 to 9

$$11149 := 1^2 \times (-3! + 4^5) \times 6 + 7! - 8 + 9$$

$$11192 := 1 + 2 + 3! + 4^5 \times 6 + 7! + 8 - 9$$

$$11488 := (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times 4 \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$11632 := 1 \times 2^{3!} / 4 \times (5! \times 6 - 7 \times (8 - 9))$$

$$11642 := 1 \times 2 \times (3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$11852 := -(1 + 2) \times 3!! + (4 + 5!) \times (-6 + 7 \times (8 + 9))$$

$$11884 := (1 + 2^{3!} \times 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9$$

$$11948 := -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + (6! + 7) \times 8 - 9$$

$$12820 := (1 + 2) \times ((3!! - 4 - 5) \times 6 + 7) - 8 + 9$$

$$13964 := (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times 5! / 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$14540 := (1 + 2 + 3!! + 4) \times 5 \times (-6 - 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$14611 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!)^4 - 5! \times 6 / (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$14612 := (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 + 5!) - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$14648 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!)^4 + (5 + 6 - 7)! - 8 - 9$$

$$14666 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!)^4 - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$14764 := (1 + 2) \times ((3 + 4)! - 5!) - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$14798 := (1 + 2) \times (3 + 4 - 5! + 6! \times 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$15971 := (-1 + 2) \times 3!! \times 4! - (5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9)$$

$$16004 := (1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (-4 + 5!) + 6! \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$16612 := -1 \times (2 + 3)! + 4 \times (-5! - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$17312 := -1 - 2 + 3!! \times 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$17707 := (1 + 2) \times 3! \times 4! - 5 + 6! \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$17726 := (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4! - 5 + 6!) + 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$17771 := -1 + 2 \times 3! + (4 \times 5 + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$17773 := (1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4) + 5^6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$17779 := (1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4 + 5^6 + 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$17780 := (1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!) - 5!) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$17789 := -1 + (2 + 3) \times (-4! + 5 \times (6! - 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$17795 := (1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 \times (5! - 6! + 7!) + 8 + 9$$

$$17843 := -1 - 2 \times 3! + (4 + 5!) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$17923 := (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times 4! - 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$17971 := -1 \times 2 - 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$17996 := (1 \times 2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 \times 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$18014 := (1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4!) - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$18058 := (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times 4! + 5! + 6! - 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$18266 := -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + (6! - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$18536 := -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5^6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$18812 := (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) + (6! + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$18878 := 1 - 2 + (-3 + 4!) \times ((5! + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$19084 := -1 + 2 + 3 \times ((4 + 5) \times 6! - 7 \times (8 + 9))$$

$$19165 := (1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4! + 5) + 6! \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$19166 := -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$19861 := -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 - 5) + 6! \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$19867 := 1 \times 2 \times 3!^4 - 5 + 6! \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$19886 := (1 \times 2^{3!} \times 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$19994 := 1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4 \times (56 - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$19996 := (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (-4! + (-5 + 6) \times 7! - 8 - 9)$$

Remark 2.2. In our representations, the fractional part and negative powers are not considered. If we allow the representations with fractional parts and/or negative powers (see [6]), then some of the above numbers can be replaced by **basic operations**. See below:

$$11149 := 1^2 \times (-3! + 4^5) \times 6 + 7! - 8 + 9$$

$$= -1 + (-2/3 + 4) \times 5 \times (678 - 9)$$

$$11192 := 1 + 2 + 3! + 4^5 \times 6 + 7! + 8 - 9$$

$$= -1 + 234 \times (5/6 + 7 \times 8 - 9)$$

$$11488 := (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times 4 \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$= (-1 + 2/3 + 4 \times 5 \times 6) \times (7 + 89)$$

$$11632 := 1 \times 2^{3!} / 4 \times (5! \times 6 - 7 \times (8 - 9))$$

$$= -1 - 2 + 3/4 \times (5^6 + 7) - 89$$

$$11642 := 1 \times 2 \times (3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$= 1 \times 2/3 \times (4 \times 56 \times 78 - 9)$$

$$11852 := -(1 + 2) \times 3!! + (4 + 5!) \times (-6 + 7 \times (8 + 9)) = 1/2 \times (34 + 5 \times 6 \times 789)$$

$$11884 := (1 + 2^{3!} \times 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9$$

$$= (-1/(2 + 3) + 4) \times 5^{6+7-8} + 9$$

$$11948 := -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + (6! + 7) \times 8 - 9$$

$$= 12 \times 3 \times (-4 + 5 \times 67 + 8/9)$$

$$12820 := (1 + 2) \times ((3!! - 4 - 5) \times 6 + 7) - 8 + 9$$

$$= 1^2 + (3 + (4^5/6 + 7) \times 8) \times 9$$

$$16612 := -1 \times (2 + 3)! + 4 \times (-5! - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$= 1 + (2 + 3 + 4^5) \times (-6/7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$17726 := (-1 + 2 + 3)! \times (4! - 5 + 6!) + 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$= (-1/2 + 3) \times (4^5 - 6) \times 7 - 89$$

$$17771 := -1 + 2 \times 3! + (4 \times 5 + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$= (-12 + (3/4 + 5^6)/7) \times 8 + 9$$

$$17773 := (1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4) + 5^6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$= (1/2 + 3) \times (-4^5 + 678 \times 9)$$

$$17789 := -1 + (2 + 3) \times (-4! + 5 \times (6! - 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$= -(-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4^5 \times (67/8 + 9)$$

$$17795 := (1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 \times (5! - 6! + 7!) + 8 + 9$$

$$= 1 + (-2^{-3} + 4) \times 56 \times (-7 + 89)$$

$$17843 := -1 - 2 \times 3! + (4 + 5!) \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$= (-1 - 2 + (3/4 + 5^6)/7) \times 8 + 9$$

$$17996 := (1 \times 2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 \times 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$= (-1/2 + 3) \times ((4^5 + 6) \times 7 - 8) - 9$$

$$18014 := (1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4!) - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$= 1/2 \times (3 + 4^5 + 6^7/8 + 9)$$

$$18226 := (1 - 2 + 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$= (-1 + 23 + 4) \times (5 - 6 + 78 \times 9)$$

$$18818 := 1 \times 2 + (3!^4 - 5!) \times (6 - 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$= 1 \times 23 \times 4^5 - 6 \times 789$$

$$18878 := 1 - 2 + (-3 + 4!) \times ((5! + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$= -1 + (-2^{-3} + 4) \times 56 \times (78 + 9)$$

$$19861 := 1 + (-2/3 + 4) \times (-5 + 67 \times 89)$$

$$= 1 + (-2/3 + 4) \times (-5 + 67 \times 89)$$

$$19867 := 1 + (2/3 + 4) \times (5 + 6 \times 78) \times 9$$

$$= 1 + (2/3 + 4) \times (5 + 6 \times 78) \times 9$$

For more work by B. Ames and by A.E. Bras and V.H.J. van der Veiden see the link [19].

2.1.2 Descending Order of 1 to 9

$$14187 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$14317 := (9 + 8) \times (7!/6 - 5 + 4 + 3) + 2 + 1$$

$$14324 := (9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + 5) \times (-4 + 3!!) + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$17060 := -9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 - 5 + 4! \times (-3! + (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$17188 := -9 \times 8 + (7! - 6! - 5) \times 4! / (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$17797 := (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) \times (-5 + (4! + 3!!) \times 2) + 1$$

$$17806 := (98/7 + 6! - 5!) \times (4! + 3 + 2 \times 1)$$

$$17890 := 9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5! + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$18022 := (9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - 5 + 4! + 3 + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$18493 := 98 + 765 \times 4! + 3!^2 - 1$$

$$18517 := (9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 + 5) + 4! \times (-3 + (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$18860 := (-9 + 8 + 7! - 6!/5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$18995 := (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$19042 := 9 \times 8 + 7 - 6! + ((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1}$$

$$19078 := -(9 + 8) \times 7 + (6! - 5 - 4) \times 3^{2+1}$$

$$19085 := (-9 \times 8 + 7 - 6) \times 5 + (4! + 3) \times (2 + 1)!!$$

$$19102 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times (-6 + 5!) \times 4! - 32 - 1$$

$$19157 := -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5!) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$19301 := 9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5) \times 4 - 3!! \times (2 - 1)$$

$$19820 := 9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5 + (4! + 3)^{2+1}$$

$$19931 := (9 + 8! + 7 + 6 - 5! \times 4) / (3! / (2 + 1))$$

Remark 2.3. In our representations, the fractional part and negative powers are not considered. If we allow the representations with fractional parts and/or negative powers (see [6]), then some of the above numbers can be replaced by **basic operations**. See below:

$$14187 := -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1) = (9 \times 8 / 7 \times 65 + 4 + 3) \times 21$$

$$14317 := (9 + 8) \times (7!/6 - 5 + 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 = 9 + (-8 + (7 + 6 - 5)^4) \times (3 + 2^{-1})$$

$$17060 := -9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 - 5 + 4! \times (-3! + (2 + 1)!!) = 9 \times (8 \times 7 / 6 \times 5 + 43^2) - 1$$

$$17890 := 9 + 8 - 7 + 6! - 5! + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)! = (9 + 8 / 7 \times (6^5 + 43)) \times 2 \times 1$$

$$18022 := (9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - 5 + 4! + 3 + (2 + 1)!! = -9 + 876 \times (-5 / (4 \times 3) + 21)$$

$$18517 := (9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 + 5) + 4! \times (-3 + (2 + 1)!!) = 9 - 8 \times (-7 - 654) \times (3 + 2^{-1})$$

$$18860 := (-9 + 8 + 7! - 6!/5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! = 9 + 87 \times 65 \times (4/3 + 2) + 1$$

$$19042 := 9 \times 8 + 7 - 6! + ((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1} = (9 + 8) / 7 \times (6^5 + 4^3) + 2 \times 1$$

$$19078 := -(9 + 8) \times 7 + (6! - 5 - 4) \times 3^{2+1} = -9^{-8+7+6} + 5^{4+3} + 2 \times 1$$

$$19157 := -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5!) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 = -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (-6 + 5 \times 4)^3 + 21$$

$$19301 := 9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5) \times 4 - 3!! \times (2 - 1) = 9 \times 8 - (7 / (6 - 5 \times 4))^{-3} - 21$$

$$19931 := (9 + 8) \times 7! / 6 + 5 + (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)! = (-9/8 - 7 + 6 + 5^4) \times 32 - 1$$

For more work by B. Ames and by A.E. Bras and V.H.J. van der Veiden see the link [19].

2.2 Complete List

The numbers below are the representations in ascending and descending orders of 1 to 9 using basic operations. The numbers given in subsection 2.1 using **factorial** are written again to have a complete the list. There are total 10000 numbers from 20001 to 30000.

$$11112 := (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 - ((4 + 5) \times (6 - (7 \times 89))))))$$

$$11113 := (1 - (2 \times -(3 - ((4 + 5) \times (6 - (7 \times 89))))))$$

$$11114 := (1 - (((2 + (3^4)) \times -(56 + 78)) + 9))$$

$$11115 := ((1 + (((2 \times 3) + 4)^5) + ((6 \times 7) - 8)) / 9)$$

$$11112 := 9 - 8 - 7 + 6 \times (5 + 43^2 - 1)$$

$$11113 := 9 + (87 + 65 \times 4) \times 32 \times 1$$

$$11114 := -9 - 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5 + 43^2 \times 1)$$

$$11115 := (9 - 8 \times (7 + 6)) \times ((5 - 4^3) \times 2 + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11116 &:= (1 - ((23 - 4) \times -((5 + 67) \times 8) + 9)) \\
11117 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times -67) + (8 \times 9)) \\
11118 &:= (1 \times -((((2 \times 3) + 4)^5) + (6 + (7 \times 8)) / -9) \\
11119 &:= (1 - (((((2 \times 3) + 4)^5) + (6 + (7 \times 8))) / -9)) \\
11120 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^4)) \times -(5 - (6 \times (7 + (8 + 9)))))) \\
11121 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3) + 4)^5) + (6 \times (7 + 8))) / -9) \\
11122 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3^4)) \times -((5 - 67) - (8 \times 9)))) \\
11123 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times -((5 - 67) - (8 \times 9)))) \\
11124 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3+4}) \times 5) - ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times -9) \\
11125 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times (5 \times -((6 - 7) \times 89))) \\
11126 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times (((4 + 56) \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\
11127 &:= (1 + (2 + (3 \times (((4 + 56) \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\
11128 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 \times (4 \times (5 + 6))) - 7) \times -89)) \\
11129 &:= (((12^3) \times 4) + 5) - (6 \times -(78 \times 9)) \\
11130 &:= ((12 + 3) \times ((4^5) - (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
11131 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (3^4)) \times -(56 + 78)) - 9)) \\
11132 &:= ((1 - 2) + ((3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))))) \times -9) \\
11133 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))))) \times -9) \\
11134 &:= (((-1 - 234) \times -(5 + (6 \times 7))) + 89) \\
11135 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - 45))) \times -((6 \times -7) - 89)) \\
11136 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))))) \times -9) \\
11137 &:= ((1 + (2 + 34)) \times -((5 \times -(6 + (7 \times 8))) + 9)) \\
11138 &:= ((1 - 23) - (4 \times -(5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
11139 &:= (12 - ((34 \times -((5 \times 67) - 8)) - 9)) \\
11140 &:= (-1 + (2 + ((3 \times 45) + 6) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
11141 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times (((456 + 7) \times 8) + 9)))) \\
11142 &:= ((1 - ((2 + 3^4) - 5)) \times (6 - (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
11143 &:= (1 - (((234 - 56) \times 7) - 8) \times -9) \\
11144 &:= (((-1 - ((2^3) \times 4)) \times -(5 \times 67)) + 89) \\
11145 &:= (12 + ((3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))))) \times -9) \\
11146 &:= (1 - (((2 + ((3 \times 45) + 6)) \times -78) + 9)) \\
11147 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times -((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
11148 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times -((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
11149 &:= 1^2 \times (-3! + 4^5) \times 6 + 7! - 8 + 9 \\
11150 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 34) \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))))) - 9) \\
11151 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3^4) - 56)) \times ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
11152 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 34) \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))))) - 9) \\
11153 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(((3 \times 4) + 56) \times (7 - 89)))) \\
11154 &:= ((1 - 23) \times -((4 \times -5) + ((67 \times 8) - 9))) \\
11155 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -(4 + ((56 \times 7) + 89)))) \\
11156 &:= ((1 - 2) - (3 - (4 \times (5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11116 &:= (9 - 8) \times (-7 + 6 \times (5 + 43^2) - 1) \\
11117 &:= (9 - 8) \times (-7 + 6 \times (5 + 43^2 \times 1)) \\
11118 &:= (9 - 8 \times 7 \times 6) \times (-5 \times (4 + 3) + 2 - 1) \\
11119 &:= 9 + (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4 + 3)^2 + 1 \\
11120 &:= 9 + (8 + 7 \times 65) \times 4 \times 3 \times 2 - 1 \\
11121 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 \times -(6^5)) + (4^{3^2-1}))) \\
11122 &:= (98 + (((7 \times ((6 - (5 - 4)) \times 3))^2) - 1)) \\
11123 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) \times -1)) \\
11124 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - 6) \times ((5^4) - ((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\
11125 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -((6 \times -(5 + (43^2)))) - 1) \\
11126 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - ((6 \times -(5 + (43^2)))) - 1) \\
11127 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (6 \times (5 \times 43)))) + 21) \\
11128 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) + ((6 \times (5 - (43^2)))) + 1)) \\
11129 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(7 - ((6 + 5) \times ((4 \times 32) - 1)))))) \\
11130 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
11131 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + (6 \times (5 + (43^2)))) \times -1)) \\
11132 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 + (6 \times (5 + (43^2)))) \times -1)) \\
11133 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 + ((6 \times (5 + (43^2)))) + 1)) \\
11134 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 - ((6 + 5) \times (4^3)))))) \times (2 \times -1) \\
11135 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) + (6 \times (5 - ((43^2) + 1)))))) \\
11136 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times -3) - (2 - 1))) \\
11137 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 - 65) \times -((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
11138 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) - (6 \times -(5 + ((43^2) + 1)))) \\
11139 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (6 - ((5 + 4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
11140 &:= (9 + ((8 - 7) + (6 \times (5 + ((43^2) + 1)))))) \\
11141 &:= (-9 + (87 - ((6 \times (5 - (43^2)))) + 1)) \\
11142 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times -((6 - (5^4)) \times -(3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
11143 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - ((6 - (5^4)) \times -(3 - 21))) \\
11144 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -((6 - 5) \times (4 \times 32))) + 1)) \\
11145 &:= (9 - (87 \times -((6 - 5) \times (4 \times (32 \times 1)))))) \\
11146 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -((6 - 5) \times (4 \times 32))) - 1)) \\
11147 &:= (((98 + 7) - ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3)) + 2)) \times -1) \\
11148 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times -3) + (2 - 1))) \\
11149 &:= (9 - ((8 \times 7) - (6 \times (((5^4) - 3) \times (2 + 1)))))) \\
11150 &:= (9 + (((87 - ((6^5)/4)) \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
11151 &:= ((9 - 87) - ((6 \times -(5^4) \times 3)) + 21) \\
11152 &:= ((98 + ((7 - (6 - 5))^4)) \times ((3^2) - 1)) \\
11153 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 - 65) \times -((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
11154 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) - (2 \times 1))) \\
11155 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7 + 6)) - ((5^4) \times (3 - 21)))) \\
11156 &:= (98 - ((7 + (6 \times (5 - (43^2)))) - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11157 &:= ((1-2) \times (3 - (4 \times (5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8) \times 9)))))) \\
11158 &:= ((1 - ((2+3) \times (4 - (5^6)))) / (7 \times -(8-9))) \\
11159 &:= (1 \times ((2-3) + (4 \times (5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8) \times 9)))))) \\
11160 &:= (1 + ((2-3) + (4 \times (5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8) \times 9)))))) \\
11161 &:= (1 \times -(((2+3)^4) \times -(5 + (6+7))) + 89) \\
11162 &:= (1 - (((2+3)^4) \times -(5 + (6+7))) + 89) \\
11163 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3) + 4)^5) + (6 \times 78)) / -9) \\
11164 &:= ((1 + ((2 + ((3 \times 45) + 6)) \times 78)) + 9) \\
11165 &:= (1 \times ((2+3) + (4 \times (5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8) \times 9)))))) \\
11166 &:= ((1+2) + (3 + (4 \times (5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8) \times 9)))))) \\
11167 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(3 \times ((4 \times (5 - (6 \times 78))) - 9)))) \\
11168 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) + (4 \times (5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8) \times 9)))))) \\
11169 &:= (1 + ((2^3) + (4 \times (5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8) \times 9)))))) \\
11170 &:= (1 \times -(2 + (3 \times (4 \times (5 - ((6+7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
11171 &:= (1 - (2 + (3 \times (4 \times (5 - ((6+7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
11172 &:= (12 \times ((3-4) \times (5 - ((6+7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
11173 &:= (((1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times 67)) - 8) - 9) \\
11174 &:= (1 \times (2 - (3 \times (4 \times (5 - ((6+7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
11175 &:= (1 + (2 - (3 \times (4 \times (5 - ((6+7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
11176 &:= ((1-23) \times (4 - (((5 \times 6) / (7+8))^9))) \\
11177 &:= (1 + (2 \times -((3^4) - (5678 - 9)))) \\
11178 &:= (((1 + ((2+3)^4) - 5) \times -(6 - (7 + (8+9)))) \\
11179 &:= ((1 + (((2+3)^4) \times (5 + (6+7))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
11180 &:= (1 \times -((2 - ((34-5) \times 6)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9))) \\
11181 &:= ((1+2) \times (3 - (4 \times (5 - ((6+7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
11182 &:= (1 + (((2 - (3 \times 45)) \times -(6+78)) + 9) \\
11183 &:= (1 \times (23 + (4 \times (5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8) \times 9)))))) \\
11184 &:= (12 + (3 \times -(4 \times (5 - ((6+7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
11185 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (34 \times 5)) \times 67)) + (8 \times -9)) \\
11186 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((3 + (4 \times (5+6))) \times (7 \times (8+9)))) \\
11187 &:= (((1+2)^3) - (4 \times -(5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8) \times 9)))) \\
11188 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times -67) - (8 - 9)) \\
11189 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times 67) + 8) - 9) \\
11190 &:= ((1 - ((2+3) \times (4 \times 56))) \times (7 - (8+9))) \\
11191 &:= (((1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times 67)) - 8) + 9) \\
11192 &:= 1 + 2 + 3! + 4^5 \times 6 + 7! + 8 - 9 \\
11193 &:= ((1+2) \times ((3 \times -4) + (5 + (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\
11194 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3+4)^5) \times 6) - 78) / 9) \\
11195 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3+4)^5) \times 6) - 78) / 9) \\
11196 &:= ((1+2) \times -(3 \times -(4 \times (5 + (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))) \\
11197 &:= ((1 + (((2 - ((3+4)^5)) \times 6) + (7 \times 8))) / -9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11157 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 - ((6+5) \times 43)))) \times -(2+1)) \\
11158 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) + ((6-543) \times -21)) \\
11159 &:= (9 - (87 - ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3) - 2)) - 1)) \\
11160 &:= ((9-87) - (6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) - (2 \times 1)))) \\
11161 &:= ((9-87) - ((6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) - 2)) - 1)) \\
11162 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 - (65 \times 43))) / -2) + 1)) \\
11163 &:= (9 - (87 - (((6 \times (5^4)) - 3) \times (2+1)))) \\
11164 &:= (((9 - (87 \times 65)) + (4^3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
11165 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5)) \times -((4 \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\
11166 &:= ((9 - (8+7)) \times (((6 \times 5) \times -((4^3) - 2)) - 1)) \\
11167 &:= (((-9-8) \times -((7+6) + (5^4))) + 321) \\
11168 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6+5))) \times 4)) \times -(32 \times -1)) \\
11169 &:= ((9-87) - ((6 \times -((5^4) \times 3)) + (2+1))) \\
11170 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6+5) \times (4^3)))) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
11171 &:= (9 - (87 - ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3)) - (2-1)))) \\
11172 &:= (9 + ((87 - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times -(2-1))) \\
11173 &:= ((9-87) - ((6 \times -((5^4) \times 3)) - (2-1))) \\
11174 &:= (9 + ((87 - ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3)) + 2)) \times -1)) \\
11175 &:= ((9-8) \times ((7 - (6 \times ((5^4) - 3))) \times -(2+1))) \\
11176 &:= ((9-8) + ((7 - (6 \times ((5^4) - 3))) \times -(2+1))) \\
11177 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (((76 + (5^4)) - 3) \times 2))) \times 1) \\
11178 &:= (((9 + (8+7)) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 \times -(2-1))) \\
11179 &:= (98 - (7 \times -(((6+5) \times ((4 \times 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
11180 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (76-5))) \times -(4 \times ((3+2) \times 1))) \\
11181 &:= ((9-87) - (((6 \times (5^4)) + 3) \times -(2+1))) \\
11182 &:= ((9+8) - ((7 \times (6+5)) \times -(((4 \times 3)^2) + 1))) \\
11183 &:= ((9-87) - ((6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) + 2)) + 1)) \\
11184 &:= ((9 - (((8 - (7-6))^5) - 4) / 3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
11185 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) - (2+1)))) \\
11186 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(((6 \times 5) + 4) \times ((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\
11187 &:= (98 - (((7 \times (6+5)) \times -((4 \times 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
11188 &:= (9 - (((8 \times ((7+6) \times (5 \times 43))) / -2) + 1)) \\
11189 &:= ((9-8) \times -(7 - (6 \times (((5^4) - 3) \times (2+1)))) \\
11190 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) - 2)) + 1)) \\
11191 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) - (2 \times 1)))) \\
11192 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) - 2)) - 1)) \\
11193 &:= ((9-8) \times -(7 \times -(((6 \times (5 \times 4)) / 3)^2) - 1)) \\
11194 &:= ((9-8) - (7 \times -(((6 \times (5 \times 4)) / 3)^2) - 1)) \\
11195 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - (6 \times (5 + ((43^2) + 1)))) \\
11196 &:= (((9 + (8+7)) - 6) \times -(((5^4) - 3) \times -(2-1))) \\
11197 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (((5^4) \times 3) - (2-1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11198 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3^4) - ((5 - 67) \times 89))) \\
11199 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 + 4)^5) \times 6) - 78) / -9) \\
11200 &:= ((1 + (((2^{3+4}) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) \times 8) - 9) \\
11201 &:= (1 \times -(23 \times -(((4 \times 5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9))) \\
11202 &:= (1 - (23 \times -(((4 \times 5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9))) \\
11203 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((34 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8))) - 9))) \\
11204 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^4) - 5678)) + 9) \\
11205 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + 4)^5)) / ((6 \times (7 - 8)) + 9)) \\
11206 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 + 4)^5) \times 6) - (7 + 8)) / -9) \\
11207 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times 67) + 8)) + 9) \\
11208 &:= ((12^3) - (4 \times -(5 \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
11209 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times ((4 - 5) + (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\
11210 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4 \times 56))) \times -(7 - (8 + 9))) \\
11211 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 + (456 + 7)) \times -8) - 9)) \\
11212 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (34 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8)))))) - 9) \\
11213 &:= (((1 + 2) - (((3 + 4)^5) \times 6) + 78)) / -9) \\
11214 &:= (1 + (2 + (3 \times ((4 - 5) + (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\
11215 &:= (12 - (((3 + 4)^5) \times 6) - (7 + 8)) / -9) \\
11216 &:= (1 - ((23 \times -((4 \times 5) + (6 \times 78))) + 9)) \\
11217 &:= ((1 + ((2^3) \times (4^5))) - (6 \times -(7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
11218 &:= ((1 + (((2^{3+4}) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) \times 8) + 9) \\
11219 &:= (1 \times (2 - (3 \times ((4 - 5) - (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\
11220 &:= (1 + (2 - (3 \times ((4 - 5) - (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\
11221 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 \times 45) - 6) \times (78 + 9))) \\
11222 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 \times 45) - 6) \times (78 + 9))) \\
11223 &:= ((1 + (2^{3+4})) \times -((5 - 6) \times (78 + 9))) \\
11224 &:= ((1 - (234 \times ((5 \times 6) - 78))) - 9) \\
11225 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -((4 \times (567 - 8)) + 9))) \\
11226 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 - (4 - 5)) + (6 \times (7 \times 89)))) \\
11227 &:= ((-123 \times -(4 \times ((5 \times 6) - 7))) - 89) \\
11228 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((3 + 4) + ((56 + 7) \times 89)))) \\
11229 &:= (1 \times -((2 - (3 - 4)) \times -(5 + (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\
11230 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) \times -(4 + (5 \times ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))))) \\
11231 &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times -(4 + (5 \times ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))))) \\
11232 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -4) \times -(5 + ((6 \times (7 + 8)) + 9)) \\
11233 &:= ((1 - 2) - (((3^4) + 56) \times (7 - 89))) \\
11234 &:= (((1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times ((5 \times -(6 + 7)) - (8 \times 9))) \\
11235 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times -4) + (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\
11236 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(345 - (67 \times 89)))) \\
11237 &:= ((1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - (5 - (6 \times 7)))) \times -(8 + 9)) \\
11238 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(34 - (5 \times ((6 + 78) \times 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11198 &:= (98 - ((7 - (6 - 5)) \times -((43^2) + 1))) \\
11199 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6 \times (5 \times 4)) / 3)^2)) + 1)) \\
11200 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) \times -((4^3) / -(2 \times 1))) \\
11201 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
11202 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -(((6 \times (5 \times 4)) / 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
11203 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -7) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 \times (2 - 1)))))) \\
11204 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6 \times -((5^4) \times 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
11205 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
11206 &:= (9 - ((8 \times 7) - ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3)) + (2 + 1)))) \\
11207 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6 \times (5 \times 4)) / 3)^2) + 1))) \\
11208 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 \times -(((6 \times (5 \times 4)) / 3)^2) + 1)) \\
11209 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) + (2 - 1)))) \\
11210 &:= (9 - (((((8 - (7 - 6))^5) - 4) / 3) \times -2) + 1) \\
11211 &:= ((98 + (7 + 6)) \times -(((54 - 3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
11212 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -7) + (((6 \times (5^4)) + 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
11213 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) - (2 - 1)) \\
11214 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) + 2)) + 1)) \\
11215 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
11216 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times -(((6 \times (5 \times 4)) / 3)^2) + 1)) \\
11217 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 \times -(((6 \times (5 \times 4)) / 3)^2 \times 1))) \\
11218 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times -(((6 \times (5 \times 4)) / 3)^2) - 1)) \\
11219 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (76 + (5^4))) - 3) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
11220 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 \times -(2 - 1)) \\
11221 &:= (9 - ((8 \times 7) - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
11222 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 - ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3)) - 21))) \\
11223 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5 + (4^{3+2-1}))) \\
11224 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 \times -(((6 \times (5 \times 4)) / 3)^2) + 1)) \\
11225 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3) - (2 + 1)))))) \\
11226 &:= (((9 - (8 - 7)) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
11227 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) - (2 \times 1))) \\
11228 &:= (((9 - 8) - ((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
11229 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) - (2 - 1))) \\
11230 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) + (2 - 1))) \\
11231 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
11232 &:= (((9 - 8) - ((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
11233 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) - ((6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) - 2)) - 1)) \\
11234 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 - (((6 \times (5^4)) - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
11235 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - (((6 \times (5^4)) - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
11236 &:= (9 + (((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 54)) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\
11237 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3) - 2) - 1)) \\
11238 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3) - 2) - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11239 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (34 \times 5)) \times -67) - (8 + 9))) \\
11240 &:= (1 + (((2 - (34 \times 5)) \times -67) - (8 + 9))) \\
11241 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3+4}) \times 5) - (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times -9) \\
11242 &:= ((1 - 23) \times -((4 \times -5) + ((67 - 8) \times 9))) \\
11243 &:= (1 \times -(2 + ((34 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9))) \\
11244 &:= (1 - (2 + ((34 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9))) \\
11245 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(3 - (45 \times (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9))))))) \\
11246 &:= (12 + (((3^4) + 56) \times -(7 - 89))) \\
11247 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times -((5 - 6) \times (78 - 9))) \\
11248 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((34 \times -(5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\
11249 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3)^4) \times -(5 + (6 + 7))) - (8 - 9)) \\
11250 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 + (6 + 7))) + 8) - 9) \\
11251 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 + (6 + 7)))) \times -(8 - 9)) \\
11252 &:= (((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 + (6 + 7)))) - 8) + 9) \\
11253 &:= (1 + (2 - (((34 \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) + 8) \times 9))) \\
11254 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3)^4) - (5 - (6 \times 7))) \times -(8 + 9)) \\
11255 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - (5 - (6 \times 7))) \times -(8 + 9)) \\
11256 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 + 6))) \times -(7 - (8 - 9))) \\
11257 &:= (12 + ((34 \times -(5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\
11258 &:= (1 + (((2 - (34 \times 5)) \times -67) - (8 - 9))) \\
11259 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -(((4 \times (5 + 6)) + 7) \times -8) - 9) \\
11260 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 - ((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
11261 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times -67) - (8 \times 9)) \\
11262 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3+4}) \times 5) - ((6 \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9) \\
11263 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((34 \times -(5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9)) \\
11264 &:= (((12^3) - (4^5)) \times (6 - (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\
11265 &:= ((1 - 2) + (((3^4) + 5) \times ((6 \times 7) + 89))) \\
11266 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((34 \times -(5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9)) \\
11267 &:= (1 \times ((23 - 4) \times -((5 \times 6) - (7 \times 89)))) \\
11268 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 + (6 + 7))) + 8) + 9) \\
11269 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3^4) + 5) \times -((6 \times 7) + 89))) \\
11270 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times -(5 \times ((6 + 7) - (8 - 9)))) \\
11271 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times -((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
11272 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
11273 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times ((4 \times 5) + (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\
11274 &:= (1 + (((2 - (34 \times 5)) \times -67) + (8 + 9))) \\
11275 &:= (12 + ((34 \times -(5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9)) \\
11276 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times ((4 \times 5) + (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\
11277 &:= ((1 - ((2 + 34) \times 5)) \times -((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9)) \\
11278 &:= (12 - (((3^4) + 5) \times -((6 \times 7) + 89))) \\
11279 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times -67) - 89)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11239 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -((6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) - 2)) - 1)) \\
11240 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - ((6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) - 2)) - 1)) \\
11241 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 \times 4))) \times -(3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
11242 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 - ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3)) - (2 - 1)))) \\
11243 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
11244 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -6) \times (((5^4) \times -3) + (2 - 1)) \\
11245 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 - ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3)) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
11246 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 + ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3) - 2)) + 1)) \\
11247 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 + ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3) - 2)) + 1)) \\
11248 &:= ((9 - (8 - (7 - 6))) \times -(((5^4) \times -3) + 1)) \\
11249 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) + (2 \times -1) \\
11250 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
11251 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -((6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
11252 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
11253 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) - (2 \times -1) \\
11254 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 - ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3) + 2)) - 1)) \\
11255 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3) + 2)) - 1)) \\
11256 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) - (2 \times 1))) \\
11257 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) - ((6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3)) + (2 - 1))) \\
11258 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 + ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3)) + (2 - 1)))) \\
11259 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 + ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3)) + (2 - 1)))) \\
11260 &:= ((9 + (((8 - 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
11261 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3) + 2)) - 1) \\
11262 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3) + 2)) - 1 \\
11263 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3) + 2)) \times 1 \\
11264 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3) + 2)) + 1 \\
11265 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -(((6 + 5) \times -(4^{3+2})) - 1)) \\
11266 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) - (6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) + (2 - 1)))) \\
11267 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 + (((6 \times (5^4)) + 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
11268 &:= (((9 - (8 + 7)) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
11269 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
11270 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5)) \times ((4 \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\
11271 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 - ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3) + 2)) - 1)) \\
11272 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) - (2 - 1))) \\
11273 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) - (2 \times 1))) \\
11274 &:= (((9 - 8) + ((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
11275 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3)) + (2 - 1)))) \\
11276 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 + ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3)) + 2)) \times -1)) \\
11277 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3)) + (2 + 1)))) \\
11278 &:= (9 + ((8 - 7) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
11279 &:= (9 + (8 + (((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) - 3) \times (2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11280 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -(((4^5) \times -6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 11280 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 \times -(2 - 1)) \\
11281 &:= (1 + (((2 + 3) - 45) \times -(6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) & 11281 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 + ((6 \times (5^4) + 3)) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
11282 &:= (((12 + 3)^4)/5) - ((6 + 7) \times -89) & 11282 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 + ((6 + 5) \times ((4^{3+2}) + 1)))) \\
11283 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 \times ((45 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8))) + 9)) & 11283 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 + ((6 + 5) \times ((4^{3+2}) + 1)))) \\
11284 &:= ((1 - (23 \times 4)) \times ((5 + 6) - ((7 + 8) \times 9))) & 11284 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 - (6 \times ((5^4) + 3))) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
11285 &:= ((1 + (2 + 34)) \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times -8) + 9) & 11285 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times (((5^4) \times 3) - 2))) \times -1) \\
11286 &:= ((1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5))) \times ((6 \times -7) - (8 \times 9))) & 11286 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
11287 &:= (1 - (((234 \times 5) + (6 + 78)) \times -9)) & 11287 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 + ((6 + 5) \times (4^{3+2}))) - 1)) \\
11288 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) + 5)) \times -(67 - (8 - 9))) & 11288 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 + ((6 + 5) \times (4^{3+2}))) \times -1)) \\
11289 &:= ((1 + ((2 - 34) \times 5)) \times -((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9))) & 11289 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) - (2 - 1))) \\
11290 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times (4 \times (5 + ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 11290 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) - (2 \times 1))) \\
11291 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (4 \times (5 + ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 11291 &:= (9 + (8 + (((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
11292 &:= (12 \times -((34 \times -(5 \times 6)) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 11292 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times -(6 + (((5^4) \times 3) + (2 - 1)))) \\
11293 &:= (1 \times (23 \times -((4 - 567) + (8 \times 9)))) & 11293 &:= (((9 - 8) + ((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3)) + 21) \\
11294 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times (4 \times (5 + ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 11294 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 65) - (4 \times 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
11295 &:= (1 + (2 + (3 \times (4 \times (5 + ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 11295 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3)) + 21))) \\
11296 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -((4 \times (5 \times 67)) + (8 \times 9))) & 11296 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 65) - (4 \times 3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
11297 &:= (1 - ((2^3) \times -((4 \times (5 \times 67)) + (8 \times 9))) & 11297 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 - (6 \times (((5^4) + 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
11298 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 45))) \times -(6 \times -(7 \times (8 - 9)))) & 11298 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (((6 \times ((5^4) + 3))/ -2) + 1)) \\
11299 &:= (1 + (2 \times (3 \times ((4 \times (5 + (6 \times 78))) - 9)))) & 11299 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + ((6 + 5) \times ((4^{3+2}) + 1)))) \\
11300 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) \times -(4 \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 11300 &:= (9 + (8 - ((7 - (6 \times ((5^4) + 3))) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
11301 &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times -(4 \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 11301 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) + (2 + 1)) \\
11302 &:= (1 \times ((23 \times -(45 - (67 \times 8))) + 9)) & 11302 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) + (2 \times 1)) \\
11303 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 - (((4 \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times 89))) & 11303 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) + (2 - 1)) \\
11304 &:= (12 - (3 \times -(4 \times (5 + ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 11304 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - 6) \times -(((5^4) + 3) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
11305 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times 5)) - (67 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 11305 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times -((5 \times (4 \times (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\
11306 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times (34 - (5678 + 9)))) & 11306 &:= ((98 - ((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3)) - 21) \\
11307 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((34 \times 5) - (6 + 7)) \times -(8 \times 9))) & 11307 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + (6 \times ((5^4) + 3))) \times (2 + 1) \\
11308 &:= (1 \times -(2 + ((34 - 5) \times (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 11308 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) - (543 \times -21)) \\
11309 &:= (1 - (2 + ((34 - 5) \times (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 11309 &:= (9 - (((8 \times -7) + 6) + ((5^4) \times (3 - 21)))) \\
11310 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) \times -((4 \times 567) - 8)) - 9)) & 11310 &:= ((98 + 76) \times -(5 \times -(4 + (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
11311 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) + (((4 \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times 89))) & 11311 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 + (6 \times (((5^4) + 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
11312 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -((4^5) - (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 11312 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 + (6 \times (((5^4) + 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
11313 &:= (1 - ((2^3) \times -((4^5) - (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 11313 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 + 54))) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\
11314 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((3 \times 4) - (5678 - 9)))) & 11314 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) - 6) \times -(((5^4) + 3) \times 2)) - 1) \\
11315 &:= (((1 + 2) - 34) \times -5 \times -((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9))) & 11315 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 \times (2 - 1)))))) \\
11316 &:= (((1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times ((5 \times -(6 \times 7)) + (8 \times 9))) & 11316 &:= ((9 + ((87 \times (65 \times 4)) + 3))/ - (2 \times -1)) \\
11317 &:= (12 - (((3 \times (4 \times 56)) - 7) \times -(8 + 9))) & 11317 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 65) - (4 - 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
11318 &:= (12 + (3 + (((4 \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times 89))) & 11318 &:= (98 + ((7 - ((6 \times (5^4)) - 3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
11319 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 + 4) \times -5) - (6 \times (7 \times 89)))) & 11319 &:= ((98 - ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})) \\
11320 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -(4 \times ((567 + 8) - 9)))) & 11320 &:= (98 - (7 - ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3)) - 21)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11321 &:= (((1+2) + (34 \times (5 \times 67))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
11322 &:= ((1 - ((2+3)^4) + 5)) \times (6 - (7 + (8+9))) \\
11323 &:= (((1+2) - (3 \times ((4^5) - ((6^7)/8))))/9) \\
11324 &:= ((12 - (3 \times ((4^5) - ((6^7)/8))))/9) \\
11325 &:= (((1+2)^{3+4}) \times 5) + (6 \times -(7 - (8 \times 9))) \\
11326 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3^4) \times 5))) \times -((6+7) - (8-9))) \\
11327 &:= (1 \times ((2 - (3^{4-5+6})) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
11328 &:= (1 + ((2 - (3^{4-5+6})) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
11329 &:= (1 \times (((2^{3+4}) \times (5+6)) + 7) \times 8) + 9) \\
11330 &:= ((1 + (((2^{3+4}) \times (5+6)) + 7) \times 8)) + 9) \\
11331 &:= (1 + (2 - (3 \times (4 - (5 \times ((6+78) \times 9)))))) \\
11332 &:= ((-1+2) - ((3 \times -(45 \times (6+78))) + 9)) \\
11333 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times (45 \times 6)))) \times -(7 \times -(8-9))) \\
11334 &:= ((1+2) \times -(((3+4) \times -(5 + (67 \times 8))) + 9)) \\
11335 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 \times (4 \times (5 + (6 \times 78)))) - 9))) \\
11336 &:= (((12^3) \times 4) - (56 \times -(7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
11337 &:= ((1+2) \times ((3-4) + (5 \times ((6+78) \times 9)))) \\
11338 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((3-4) \times (5678-9)))) \\
11339 &:= (1 \times -(((2+3) \times -(4 \times 567)) - (8-9))) \\
11340 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times -4) \times -((5 \times -6) + ((7+8) \times 9)) \\
11341 &:= ((1 + ((2+3) \times (4 \times 567))) \times -(8-9)) \\
11342 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((3 \times (45 \times (6 \times 7))) - (8-9)))) \\
11343 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 \times (45 \times (6 \times 7))) - (8-9)))) \\
11344 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(3 \times (4 \times (5 + (6 \times 78)))) + 9)) \\
11345 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 - (4 - 5678))) + 9)) \\
11346 &:= (((1+2) - 34) \times ((5 \times -(67+8)) + 9)) \\
11347 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times (45 \times 6)))) \times (7 \times -(8-9))) \\
11348 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -((3-4) \times 5678)) - 9)) \\
11349 &:= (((1+2)^{3+4}) \times 5) - (6 \times -(78-9)) \\
11350 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times -5 - ((6 \times 78) - 9)) \\
11351 &:= (((12^3) - (4 \times ((5+6) \times 7))) \times 8) - 9) \\
11352 &:= ((1-23) \times -(4 + ((5 \times 6)/(7+8))^9)) \\
11353 &:= (-1 - (2 - (34 \times ((5 \times 67) + (8-9)))))) \\
11354 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times 5))) \times ((6+7) - (8-9))) \\
11355 &:= ((1+2) \times -((((3^4) \times 5) + 67) \times -8) - 9) \\
11356 &:= (((-1+23) - 4) \times -5678) / -9) \\
11357 &:= (1 \times -(((2+3) \times -(4 \times 567)) - (8+9))) \\
11358 &:= ((1 + (((2+3)^4) + 5)) \times -(6 - (7 + (8+9)))) \\
11359 &:= (1 - (2 \times (((3^4) \times (5 - (67+8))) - 9))) \\
11360 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((3+4) - (5678+9)))) \\
11361 &:= ((1+2) \times ((3+4) + (5 \times ((6+78) \times 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11321 &:= ((9 + (((87 \times 65) + (4-3)) \times 2)) \times 1) \\
11322 &:= (((9 + (8+7)) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 \times -(2-1))) \\
11323 &:= (98 - (7 - (6 \times (((5^4) \times 3) - (2+1)))))) \\
11324 &:= (9 + ((8 \times 7) + (((6 \times (5^4)) + 3) \times (2+1)))) \\
11325 &:= ((98 - ((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
11326 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) + (6 \times (((5^4) \times 3) + 2))) - 1)) \\
11327 &:= (98 + ((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 \times (2-1)))) \\
11328 &:= ((9+8) + (7 + (6 \times (((5^4) + 3) \times (2+1)))))) \\
11329 &:= ((98 - ((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
11330 &:= ((98-7) - ((6 \times -((5^4) \times 3) - 2)) - 1) \\
11331 &:= ((9 + ((876-5) \times (4 + (3^2)))) - 1) \\
11332 &:= (98 - (7 - (((6 \times (5^4)) - 3) \times (2+1)))) \\
11333 &:= ((9+87) - ((6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) - 2)) + 1)) \\
11334 &:= ((9+87) - (6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) - (2 \times 1)))) \\
11335 &:= ((98-7) + (6 \times (((5^4) \times 3) - (2-1)))) \\
11336 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (((5+4)^3) \times 2)))) - 1) \\
11337 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (((5+4)^3) \times 2)))) \times 1) \\
11338 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -((7 \times 6) - (((5+4)^3) \times 2))) + 1)) \\
11339 &:= (98 + ((7 - ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3)) - 2)) \times -1)) \\
11340 &:= (((9 + (8+7)) - 6) \times -(((5^4) + (3+2)) \times -1)) \\
11341 &:= (98 + ((7 - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times -(2-1))) \\
11342 &:= (98 + ((7 + (6 \times (((5^4) \times 3) - 2))) - 1)) \\
11343 &:= (98 - (7 - ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3)) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
11344 &:= (98 + (7 + ((6 \times (((5^4) \times 3) - 2)) + 1))) \\
11345 &:= (9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (((5+4)^3) \times 2) + 1))) \\
11346 &:= ((98+7) - (((6 \times (5^4)) - 3) \times -(2+1))) \\
11347 &:= ((98-7) - (6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) + (2-1)))) \\
11348 &:= (((9+87) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
11349 &:= ((98 - (7-6)) \times -(((5 - (4^3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\
11350 &:= (((9+8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (((4+3)^2) + 1)) \\
11351 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((76-5) \times (4 \times (3+2)))))) \times -1) \\
11352 &:= ((9 - (8+7)) \times (((6 + (5^4)) \times -3) + (2-1))) \\
11353 &:= (98 + ((7 + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) - (2 \times 1))) \\
11354 &:= (98 + ((7 + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) - (2-1))) \\
11355 &:= ((98+7) - (6 \times -((5^4) \times (3 \times (2-1)))))) \\
11356 &:= (98 + (7 + ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3)) + (2-1)))) \\
11357 &:= (98 - ((7 + ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3)) + 2)) \times -1)) \\
11358 &:= ((9 - (8+7)) \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times -(3 \times (2-1)))) \\
11359 &:= (98 - (7 - (6 \times (((5^4) \times 3) + (2+1)))))) \\
11360 &:= (98 - (((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) - 3) \times -(2+1))) \\
11361 &:= ((98+7) - (6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) + (2-1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11362 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((3 \times 4) + (5678 - 9)))) \\
11363 &:= (((12^3) - 4) - (567 \times -(8 + 9))) \\
11364 &:= (12 - (3 \times -(4 + (5 \times ((6 + 78) \times 9)))) \\
11365 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -((3 - 4) \times 5678)) + 9)) \\
11366 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((3 \times 4) - (5 \times (67 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
11367 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -(((4 + 56) \times -7) + (8 - 9))) \\
11368 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times 8))) - 9) \\
11369 &:= (((12^3) - (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 7))) \times 8) + 9) \\
11370 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3^4) \times -(5 + (6 \times 7))) + (8 + 9))) \\
11371 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 \times (4 \times (5 + (6 \times 78)))) + 9))) \\
11372 &:= (((1 - 2) + (34 \times (5 \times 67))) - (8 + 9)) \\
11373 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3^4) - 5) \times -(6 - (7 \times 8))) - 9) \\
11374 &:= ((1 - 23) \times -(4 + (((56 + 7) \times 8) + 9))) \\
11375 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times (5 - ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
11376 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times -4) - (5 \times ((6 + 78) \times 9)))) \\
11377 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))))) / -9) \\
11378 &:= ((12 - (34 \times (5 \times 67))) \times (8 - 9)) \\
11379 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3^4) + ((5 + 6) \times 7)) \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
11380 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times (3^4) - 5) - 6) \times 78)) - 9) \\
11381 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) \times -(((4 + 5) - 6)^7 + 89))) \\
11382 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^3) \times (4^5)) - 6) \times -7) / - (8 + 9)) \\
11383 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3^4) - 5) \times (67 + 8)) - 9)) \\
11384 &:= (1 - (((2^{3+4}) \times -(5 + (6 + 78))) + 9)) \\
11385 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times 3)^4) - (5 \times 6)) \times ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
11386 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times 8))) + 9) \\
11387 &:= (((12^3) + (4 + 5)) \times -(67 - 8)) / -9) \\
11388 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - 5)) \times ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\
11389 &:= (((1 - 2) + (34 \times (5 \times 67))) \times -(8 - 9)) \\
11390 &:= (((1 - 2) + (34 \times (5 \times 67))) - (8 - 9)) \\
11391 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 + (4^5)) - (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
11392 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((34 \times (5 \times 67)) + 8)) - 9) \\
11393 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (34 \times (5 \times 67))) - (8 - 9))) \\
11394 &:= ((12^3) - (((4^5) - (6 - (7 \times 8))) \times -9)) \\
11395 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3+4}) - (5^6))) + ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
11396 &:= ((1 - 23) \times -((4 \times 5) - (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
11397 &:= (1 + (2 - (((34 \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) - 8) \times 9))) \\
11398 &:= (((1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
11399 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -(((4 \times 5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) + 9)) \\
11400 &:= (1 - ((23 \times -(((4 \times 5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) + 9)) \\
11401 &:= (1 \times -(((2^{3+4}) \times -(5 + (6 + 78))) - 9)) \\
11402 &:= (1 \times (2 - (3 \times ((4^5) - (67 \times (8 \times 9))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11362 &:= (98 - (7 - ((6 \times ((5^4) \times 3)) + 21))) \\
11363 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 + 6)) + ((5^4) \times (3 - 21)))) \\
11364 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (((6 + (5^4)) \times -3) - (2 - 1))) \\
11365 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 - ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 - 21)))) \\
11366 &:= ((98 + 7) - ((6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) + 2)) + 1)) \\
11367 &:= (98 - (((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
11368 &:= (98 + ((7 + ((6 + 5) \times (4^{3+2}))) - 1)) \\
11369 &:= (98 - ((7 + ((6 + 5) \times (4^{3+2}))) \times -1)) \\
11370 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)))) \times (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
11371 &:= (98 - (((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) - (2 \times 1))) \\
11372 &:= (98 - (((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) - (2 + 1))) \\
11373 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + (6 \times ((5^4) - 3))) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
11374 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + 5) \times -(43 - 21))) \\
11375 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 \times -(65 \times ((4 \times (3 \times 2)) + 1)))) \\
11376 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - 6) \times ((5^4) + ((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\
11377 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times (((4^3) / -2) + 1)) \\
11378 &:= (98 - ((7 + ((6 \times (5^4)) + 3)) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
11379 &:= ((9 + (((87 + 6) - 5) \times 43)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
11380 &:= (98 + (7 + ((6 + 5) \times ((4^{3+2}) + 1)))) \\
11381 &:= (98 + ((7 - (6 \times ((5^4) + 3))) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
11382 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6^5) / 4)) \times -(3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
11383 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 + (6 \times (((5^4) \times 3) + 21)))) \\
11384 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 + (6 \times (((5^4) \times 3) + 21)))) \\
11385 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -((5 - 4) \times -(32 + 1))) \\
11386 &:= (9 - (((8 + 76) - 5) \times -((4 \times 3)^2)) - 1) \\
11387 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) - (6 - (543 \times 21))) \\
11388 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 54))) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
11389 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 54))) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
11390 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 54))) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1)) \\
11391 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
11392 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times (65 \times ((4 \times (3 \times 2)) + 1)))) \\
11393 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(7 - (65 \times (43 - 21)))) \\
11394 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - 6) \times ((5^4) + ((3^2) - 1))) \\
11395 &:= (98 - (7 - (6 \times (((5^4) + 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
11396 &:= ((9 - (8 - 76)) \times ((5 + ((4 \times 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
11397 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 \times -(((6 \times 543) / 2) - 1))) \\
11398 &:= ((9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 543))) / 2)) \times -1) \\
11399 &:= (9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5 \times (4 + (3 \times 21)))) \\
11400 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6 \times (5^4)) + 3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
11401 &:= ((9 - 8) - (76 \times -(5 + (((4 \times 3)^2) + 1)))) \\
11402 &:= (9 - (((8 + (76 + 5)) \times -(4 \times 32)) - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11403 &:= (((1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) - (5 \times 6)) \times -((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
11404 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((3 + 4) + (5 \times (67 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
11405 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 + 4) + (5 \times (67 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
11406 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3^4) + (5 - ((6^7)/(8 \times 9)))))) \\
11407 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((34 + 5678) - 9))) \\
11408 &:= (1 \times -(23 \times -((45 \times (6 + 7)) - 89))) \\
11409 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3+4}) \times 5) - (6 \times -(7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
11410 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times 5 \times ((6 + 7) - (8 - 9))) \\
11411 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))))/ - 9) \\
11412 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 \times ((4 \times (5 \times 67)) - (8 \times 9)))) \\
11413 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4 \times 567))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
11414 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((3 \times 4) + (5 \times (67 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
11415 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -(4 + ((5 - (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9))) \\
11416 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(34 + 5678)) + 9)) \\
11417 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -(((4 \times 5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
11418 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3^4) \times -(5 + (6 \times 7))) - (8 - 9))) \\
11419 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3^4) - 5) \times (67 + 8)) + 9)) \\
11420 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) \times -(4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + 89)))))) \\
11421 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times ((4 + 5) \times -((6 \times 7) - 89))) \\
11422 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (34 \times ((5 \times 67) - (8 - 9)))))) \\
11423 &:= (1 - (2 - (34 \times ((5 \times 67) - (8 - 9)))))) \\
11424 &:= ((1 + 23) \times -(4 \times ((5 - 6) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
11425 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -((4 \times 567) + (8 + 9)))) \\
11426 &:= (1 \times (2 + (34 \times ((5 \times 67) - (8 - 9)))))) \\
11427 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3^4) - 5) \times -(6 - (7 \times 8)) + 9)) \\
11428 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times -(3 \times (45 \times (6 \times 7)))) - 89)) \\
11429 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3) \times -(4 \times 567)) - 89)) \\
11430 &:= (1 \times ((2 - (3 \times (4 + (5 \times (6 + 78)))))) \times -9) \\
11431 &:= (1 + ((2 - (3 \times (4 + (5 \times (6 + 78)))))) \times -9) \\
11432 &:= ((1 - (23 \times (4^5))) - (((6^7)/ - 8) + 9)) \\
11433 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3+4}) \times 5) - 6 - (7 \times -(8 \times 9)) \\
11434 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5^6))) - (7 + 89)) \\
11435 &:= ((12^3) - ((4 + 567) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
11436 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3^4) - (5 + ((6^7)/(8 \times 9)))))) \\
11437 &:= (1 - ((2 + (34 \times 56)) \times -((7 + 8) - 9))) \\
11438 &:= (1 \times -(2 + (((34 \times 5) + 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
11439 &:= (1 - (2 + (((34 \times 5) + 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
11440 &:= ((1 - (23 + 4)) \times (5 \times -(6 - (7 - 89)))) \\
11441 &:= (1 \times (((234 - 5) \times -(6 - (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
11442 &:= (1 + (((234 - 5) \times -(6 - (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
11443 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11403 &:= ((9 + ((87 - 6) \times (5 \times 4))) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
11404 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times (6 \times 543))/ - 2) - 1)) \\
11405 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((76 - 5) \times 4))) \times -((3 + 2) \times -1)) \\
11406 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3)) - 21) \\
11407 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3) - 2)) \times -1) \\
11408 &:= ((98 - (7 - (6 - 5))) \times -(4 \times -(32 - 1))) \\
11409 &:= (98 + (7 + (6 \times (((5^4) + 3) \times (2 + 1)))))) \\
11410 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6 \times 543)/2) + 1))) \\
11411 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3) + 2)) \times -1) \\
11412 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - 6) \times -(((5^4) + (3^2)) \times -1)) \\
11413 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 \times -(((6 \times 543)/2) - 1))) \\
11414 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 + 6)) \times -543) - (2 \times 1))) \\
11415 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times (((6 \times 5) + 4) \times (3 \times 2)))))) \times -1) \\
11416 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) - 2))) - 1) \\
11417 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) - 2))) \times 1) \\
11418 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) - 2))) + 1) \\
11419 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((7 \times (6 \times 543))/2) - 1)) \\
11420 &:= (((9 - (87 \times 65)) - (4^3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
11421 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6^5)/ - ((4^3)/(2 \times 1)))) \\
11422 &:= ((98 + (76 \times (5 + ((4 \times 3)^2)))) \times 1) \\
11423 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 - 21)))) \\
11424 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) + (2 + 1)) \\
11425 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
11426 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) + (2 - 1)) \\
11427 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3)) \times (2 - 1)) \\
11428 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) - (2 - 1)) \\
11429 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
11430 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
11431 &:= (98 + (7 \times -(6 - (5 \times (4 + 321)))))) \\
11432 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times (((6 \times 5) + 4) \times (3 \times 2)))) + 1)) \\
11433 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (((6 \times 5) + 4) \times (3 \times 2)))))) \times 1) \\
11434 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times (((6 \times 5) + 4) \times (3 \times 2)))) - 1)) \\
11435 &:= (-9 - (((8 + (7 + 6)) \times -(543 + 2)) + 1)) \\
11436 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + ((6 \times (5^4)) + 3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
11437 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -(6 \times (54 \times (3 + 2)))) + 1)) \\
11438 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) - ((5 + 4)^3)))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
11439 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 + 4) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
11440 &:= (((9 + 876) - 5) \times -(((4 + 3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
11441 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - (6 \times (((5^4) \times 3) + 21)))) \\
11442 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + (4 \times 3)))))) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
11443 &:= (-9 - (((876 + 5) \times -(4 + (3^2))) + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11444 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8) - 9)))))) \\
11445 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) \times 5) + 6) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
11446 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times ((4 + (5 \times (6 + 78))) \times 9)))) \\
11447 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8) - 9)))))) \\
11448 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8) - 9)))))) \\
11449 &:= (1 \times -((234 \times -(56 - 7)) + (8 + 9))) \\
11450 &:= ((1 - (23 \times (4^5))) - (((6^7) / -8) - 9)) \\
11451 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5^6))) - (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
11452 &:= (12 + (((34 \times 5) + 6) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
11453 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (34 \times 5)) \times 67)) + (8 \times -9)) \\
11454 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 34)) \times (((5 + 6) \times -7) - 89)) \\
11455 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -((4 \times (567 + 8)) - 9))) \\
11456 &:= (1 \times (2 - ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
11457 &:= (1 + (2 - ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
11458 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(34 + (5 \times (67 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
11459 &:= (1 \times (((234 - 5) \times -(6 - (7 \times 8))) + 9)) \\
11460 &:= (12 \times ((34 \times (5 \times 6)) + (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
11461 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times -((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9)))) \\
11462 &:= (1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times -((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9)))) \\
11463 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -((3 - (4^5)) \times 6)) - 789)) \\
11464 &:= (1 \times -((2^{3 \times 4}) - ((5^6) + (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
11465 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - ((5^6) + 7))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
11466 &:= (12 + ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times -(6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
11467 &:= (1 \times -((234 \times -(56 - 7)) + (8 - 9))) \\
11468 &:= (((1 + (234 \times (56 - 7))) - 8) + 9) \\
11469 &:= ((-12 \times (3 - (4^5))) + (6 - 789)) \\
11470 &:= ((123 + (4^5)) \times -((6 \times (7 + 8)) / -9)) \\
11471 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times 45))) \times -(6 \times 7)) + 89) \\
11472 &:= (12 \times -(((3^4) \times -(5 + 6)) + (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
11473 &:= (1 \times -(2 + ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times ((67 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
11474 &:= (1 - (2 + ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times ((67 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
11475 &:= ((1 - (23 \times (4 \times 5))) \times ((6 \times -7) + (8 + 9))) \\
11476 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3^4) - 5))) \times ((6 + 7) - 89)) \\
11477 &:= (1 \times (23 \times ((4 + 567) - (8 \times 9)))) \\
11478 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 \times (((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)))) \\
11479 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 \times (((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)))) \\
11480 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) \times 5) - ((67 \times -8) - 9)) \\
11481 &:= ((1 + (2^{3 \times 4 - 5})) \times -((6 - 7) \times 89)) \\
11482 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (78 + 9)))))) \\
11483 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5^6))) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
11484 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 \times -(((4 - 5) - (6 \times 7)) \times 89))) \\
11485 &:= (-1 - (2 \times -(((3^4) \times (5 + 67)) - 89)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11444 &:= ((9 - ((876 + 5) \times (4 + (3^2)))) \times -1) \\
11445 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -(((54/3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
11446 &:= ((98 - (7 - 6)) \times ((5 - (4^3)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
11447 &:= (9 + (((87 + 6) \times -(5 - (4 \times 32))) - 1)) \\
11448 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (6 \times -((5 \times (4^3)) - (2 \times 1)))) \\
11449 &:= (98 - (7 + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 - 21)))) \\
11450 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) - ((6 + 543) \times -21)) \\
11451 &:= (9 - (87 - ((6 + 543) \times 21))) \\
11452 &:= ((98 + (7 \times (6 \times 543))) / - (2 \times -1)) \\
11453 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 + 6)) \times -(543 + 2)) + 1)) \\
11454 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times -((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)) - 1)) \\
11455 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 + 6)) \times -(543 + 2)) - 1)) \\
11456 &:= ((98 + (76 + 5)) \times -((4^3) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
11457 &:= ((9 - (87 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) \times (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
11458 &:= (9 - (((87 + ((6 + 54)/3))^2) \times -1)) \\
11459 &:= (9 + (((87 + ((6 + 54)/3))^2) + 1)) \\
11460 &:= ((9 - (8 + 765)) \times ((4 \times -3) - (2 + 1))) \\
11461 &:= (9 - (((876 + 5) \times -(4 + (3^2))) + 1)) \\
11462 &:= ((9 + ((876 + 5) \times (4 + (3^2)))) \times 1) \\
11463 &:= (98 + (7 - ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 - 21)))) \\
11464 &:= (9 - (((8 + 76) - 5) \times -(((4 \times 3)^2) + 1))) \\
11465 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(((7 + 6) - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
11466 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 76) - 5) \times -((4 \times (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\
11467 &:= (98 - (7 - (6 \times (((5^4) \times 3) + 21)))) \\
11468 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((65 - 4) \times -((3 + 2) - 1))) \\
11469 &:= (-9 + (((8 - (7654 \times 3)) / -2) + 1)) \\
11470 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -6) - (5 \times 4)) \times (32 - 1)) \\
11471 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + 6)) + ((5^4) \times -(3 - 21))) \\
11472 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (((6^5) / -4) + (32 \times 1))) \\
11473 &:= ((9 - (8 - 76)) \times -((5 + ((4 \times 3)^2)) \times -1)) \\
11474 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) - ((5 + 4)^3)))) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
11475 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) \times -((4 \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
11476 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 76) + 5)) \times ((4 \times -(3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
11477 &:= (9 + (((8 - 7654) \times 3) / -2) - 1) \\
11478 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)))) \times -(3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
11479 &:= (9 + (((8 - 7654) \times 3) / -2) + 1) \\
11480 &:= ((98 + (7 \times 6)) \times (((54 \times 3) / 2) + 1)) \\
11481 &:= (9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (((65 + 4) \times 3) - 2)) - 1))) \\
11482 &:= (((98 - 7) - (((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
11483 &:= (9 + (8 - ((76 - ((5^4) - 3)) \times 21))) \\
11484 &:= (9 - (((87 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) - 3) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
11485 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times -(3 - 21)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11486 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((3^4) \times (5 + 67)) - 89))) \\
11487 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 \times -(4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (78 + 9)))))) \\
11488 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!) \times 4 \times 5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
11489 &:= (((-1 + 234) \times (56 - 7)) - (8 \times -9)) \\
11490 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(((3^4) + 5) \times 67) - (8 + 9)))) \\
11491 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3^4) + 5) \times 67) - (8 + 9)))) \\
11492 &:= (1 \times -((((2 \times 3)^4) + (5 \times 6)) \times 78) / -9) \\
11493 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3+4}) \times 5) - ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times -9) \\
11494 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times (56 + (7 + 8)))))) - 9) \\
11495 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times 5)))) \times -((6 + 7) \times -8) + 9) \\
11496 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) \times -(4 + (5 \times ((6 \times 78) - 9)))))) \\
11497 &:= (1 \times -(23 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 89)))))) \\
11498 &:= (1 - (23 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 89)))))) \\
11499 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (3 \times 45)) \times -(6 + 78)) + 9)) \\
11500 &:= (1 - (((2 + (3 \times 45)) \times -(6 + 78)) + 9)) \\
11501 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3^4) + (5678 - 9)))) \\
11502 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times 5)) \times (6 - (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
11503 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(((34 + 5) - 678) \times 9))) \\
11504 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -((4^5) + (6 \times (78 - 9)))))) \\
11505 &:= (1 - ((2^3) \times -((4^5) + (6 \times (78 - 9)))))) \\
11506 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5^6))) - (7 + (8 + 9))) \\
11507 &:= ((1 + (2 + 34)) \times (5 + (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\
11508 &:= (12 \times -(((3^4) + 56) \times (7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\
11509 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3 \times 45)) \times -(67 + (8 + 9)))) \\
11510 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((3 - ((4^5) + (6 \times 789)))))) \\
11511 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (((3 + 4)^5) + ((6^7) / 8)))) / 9) \\
11512 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times (56 + (7 + 8)))))) + 9) \\
11513 &:= (1 - ((2^3) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 89)))))) \\
11514 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(345 - (678 \times 9)))) \\
11515 &:= (1 \times ((234 + (5 + 6)) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
11516 &:= (1 + ((234 + (5 + 6)) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
11517 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times (((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times -678) - 9)) \\
11518 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3 \times 45)) \times (6 + 78))) + 9) \\
11519 &:= (1 \times -((((234 + 5) \times 6) + 7) \times -8) + 9) \\
11520 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - ((5^6) + 7))) - (8 + 9)) \\
11521 &:= ((1 - (2^{3 \times 4}) - ((5^6) \times (7 - 8)) + 9) \\
11522 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5^6))) - (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
11523 &:= ((1 - (2^{3 \times 4}) - ((5^6) - 7) \times (8 - 9)) \\
11524 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5^6))) - ((7 + 8) - 9)) \\
11525 &:= ((1 + (23 \times (4 \times 5))) \times -((6 \times -7) + (8 + 9))) \\
11526 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 89))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11486 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7654 \times 3)) / - (2 \times 1))) \\
11487 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7654 \times 3)) / - 2) + 1)) \\
11488 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times (((65 + 4) \times 3) - 2))) + 1)) \\
11489 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(7 \times (((65 + 4) \times 3) - (2 \times 1)))))) \\
11490 &:= (((9 + (87 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)))) - 2) - 1) \\
11491 &:= ((9 + (87 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
11492 &:= (((9 + (87 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)))) - 2) + 1) \\
11493 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7654 \times 3)) / - 2) + 1)) \\
11494 &:= ((9 + ((87 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3))) + 2)) - 1) \\
11495 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times ((5 \times -(4 \times (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\
11496 &:= ((9 + ((87 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3))) + 2)) + 1) \\
11497 &:= (9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) - ((5 + (4^3)) \times 21)))) \\
11498 &:= ((9 - ((87 - (((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times 2)) - 1) \\
11499 &:= ((9 - ((87 - (((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times 2)) \times 1) \\
11500 &:= (9 + (((87 - (((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
11501 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times ((5 \times -43) - (2 \times 1))) \\
11502 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (((6 \times 5) \times -(4^3)) + (2 + 1))) \\
11503 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times 2)))) \times -1) \\
11504 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) + (7 - 6)) \times (54 \times 3)) - 2) \times -1) \\
11505 &:= ((9 + 876) \times ((5 \times -4) + (32 + 1))) \\
11506 &:= (-9 + ((8 - (7 + 6)) \times -((5 + 43)^2) - 1)) \\
11507 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times 2) + 1) \\
11508 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (((6 \times 5) \times -(4^3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
11509 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times -(5 \times (43 + (2 + 1)))))) \\
11510 &:= ((98 - ((7 + ((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
11511 &:= ((9 + (87 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) \times -(3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
11512 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times ((7 + 65) \times (4 \times (3 + 2)))) + 1)) \\
11513 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(7 + (((6 - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times 2) + 1)))) \\
11514 &:= (((98 - 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) - 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
11515 &:= ((98 - (7^{(6-5) \times 4})) \times ((3 + 2) \times -1)) \\
11516 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 + 6)) - (543 \times 21))) \\
11517 &:= ((9 - ((8 - 76) \times 5)) \times -((4 \times -3) - 21)) \\
11518 &:= (9 - (((87 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
11519 &:= (9 - (((87 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) + (2 - 1))) \\
11520 &:= ((9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times (5 \times -((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
11521 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 + 65) \times (4 \times (3 + 2))) - 1))) \\
11522 &:= (9 - (((87 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) - (2 \times 1))) \\
11523 &:= (((98 - 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
11524 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 + 6)) \times -((5 + 43)^2) - 1)) \\
11525 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - 6) \times -((5 + 43)^2) + 1) \\
11526 &:= ((9 + (87 + 6)) \times -((54 + 3) \times -2) + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11527 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 + ((4 + 56) \times (7 + 89)))))) \\
11528 &:= (1 \times -((2 + ((3^4) + 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) + 89))) \\
11529 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -((4 \times -(5 + ((6 + 7) \times 8))) + 9)) \\
11530 &:= ((123 + ((4^5) + 6)) \times -(7 - (8 + 9))) \\
11531 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3^4) + 5) \times 67) + 8) + 9)) \\
11532 &:= (12 \times -(3 - ((4^5) + (6 \times (7 - (8 + 9)))))) \\
11533 &:= (1 \times ((23 - 4) \times (((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
11534 &:= (1 \times ((2 - (3^4)) \times -((5 + 6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
11535 &:= (((1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - (5^6) + 7) \times (8 - 9)) \\
11536 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - ((5^6) + 7))) + (8 - 9)) \\
11537 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - ((5^6) + 7))) \times -(8 - 9)) \\
11538 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - ((5^6) + 7))) - (8 - 9)) \\
11539 &:= ((1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) - (((5^6) \times (7 - 8)) - 9)) \\
11540 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5^6))) - (7 - (8 + 9))) \\
11541 &:= (12 + (3 \times -(45 - ((6^7)/(8 \times 9)))))) \\
11542 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(34 \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8))) - 9))) \\
11543 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(34 \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8))) - 9))) \\
11544 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (((3^{-4+5} \times 6) - 7) \times 8))) - 9) \\
11545 &:= ((1 + (2^{3^{4+5-6}})) + (7 \times -89)) \\
11546 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 \times (4 \times 56)) + 7) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
11547 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 3)^4) - (5 - ((6 - 7) \times 8))) \times -9)) \\
11548 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5 - ((6 - 7) \times 8))) \times -9)) \\
11549 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3^4) + 5) \times 67) + 8) - 9)) \\
11550 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -(4 - (((5 \times 6) + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
11551 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(34 \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8)))) + 9)) \\
11552 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(34 \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8)))) + 9)) \\
11553 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(((3^4) - 5) \times ((6 + 7) - 89)))) \\
11554 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - ((5^6) + 7))) + (8 + 9)) \\
11555 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (((4 + 56) \times 7) + 8) \times 9)))) \\
11556 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5 + 6))) \times ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
11557 &:= ((-12 \times (3 - ((4^5) - 6))) + (7 \times -89)) \\
11558 &:= (1 \times (2 \times (((3^4) + 5) \times 67) + (8 + 9))) \\
11559 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 + 4) \times -5) + ((6^7)/(8 \times 9)))) \\
11560 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(34 \times (5 \times (67 - (8 - 9)))))) \\
11561 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3^{-4+5} \times 6) - 7) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
11562 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(((3^{-4+5} \times 6) - 7) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
11563 &:= ((1 + 2) - (34 \times -(5 \times (67 - (8 - 9)))))) \\
11564 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) \times 5) + 6) - (7 \times -89)) \\
11565 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times (((4 + 56) \times 7) + 8) + 9) \\
11566 &:= (1 + ((23 - (4 \times ((5 \times 67) - 8))) \times -9)) \\
11567 &:= ((1 + ((23 - (4^5)) \times ((6 + 7) \times 8)))/ -9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11527 &:= (((-9 - 87) \times -(6 \times (5 \times 4))) - ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
11528 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 + 6)) \times -((5 + 43)^2)) - 1)) \\
11529 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((7 + 65) \times (4 - (3 + 21)))))) \\
11530 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 + 6)) \times -((5 + 43)^2)) + 1)) \\
11531 &:= (((-98 - (7654 \times 3))/ -2) + 1) \\
11532 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (((6 \times 5) \times -(4^3)) - (2 \times 1))) \\
11533 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 - 76)) + 5) \times ((4 \times -(3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
11534 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 + 6)) \times -(((5 + 43)^2) + 1))) \\
11535 &:= ((9 + ((87 - ((6^5) + 4) \times 3))/(2 \times -1)) \\
11536 &:= ((98 - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times -(43 - 2)) - 1)) \\
11537 &:= (9 + (8 \times (((7 + 65) \times (4 \times (3 + 2))) + 1))) \\
11538 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (((6 \times 5) \times -(4^3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
11539 &:= (9 + ((8 - 7) + ((6 + 543) \times 21))) \\
11540 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 - 5))) \times (4 \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
11541 &:= (9 - (((87 + (6 \times 5^4))) \times -3) - 21)) \\
11542 &:= (((((-9 + 87) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times 3)/ -2) + 1) \\
11543 &:= ((98 - (7 - 6)) \times ((5 \times (4 \times (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\
11544 &:= ((9 - ((87 - ((6^5) + 4) \times 3))/ - (2 \times -1)) \\
11545 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((7 \times (6 - (5 \times 43)))) + 21))) \\
11546 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times ((6 + 543) \times (2 + 1)))))) \\
11547 &:= (9 \times ((8/ - ((7 + 6) - 5)) + (4 \times 321))) \\
11548 &:= (-98 - ((7 - 654) \times -(3 - 21))) \\
11549 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (76 \times (54 + 3))))/ - (2 + 1)) \\
11550 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times (((6 \times -5) + (4^3))^2) - 1)) \\
11551 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 76) - (543 \times -21)) \\
11552 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(76 \times -(5 + ((4 + 3) \times 21)))) \\
11553 &:= ((9 - 8) - (76 \times -(5 + ((4 + 3) \times 21)))) \\
11554 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times ((5 \times -43) - (2 + 1))) \\
11555 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 \times (54 + 3))))/ (2 + 1)) \\
11556 &:= ((9 + (87 + (6 + 5))) \times -(4 \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
11557 &:= (((((-98 \times 7) + 6) \times -(5 + (4 \times 3))) - 2) - 1) \\
11558 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + 654)) + 321) \\
11559 &:= (((98 + 7) - ((65 + 43)^2)) \times -1) \\
11560 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 \times -5) + (4^3))^2) \times -1)) \\
11561 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((765 - 43) \times 2))) \times 1) \\
11562 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 \times ((5 + (4 + 32)) \times 1))) \\
11563 &:= (((-9 - 87) - (((6^5) - 4) \times 3)/ -2) - 1)) \\
11564 &:= (98 + ((76 - ((5^4) - 3)) \times -21)) \\
11565 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 65) \times 4))) \times -(3 + 2) \times -1)) \\
11566 &:= (((-9 - 8) - ((76 + 5) \times -((4 \times 3)^2) - 1))) \\
11567 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times -((54 \times -(3 + 2)) + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11568 &:= (1 \times (2 \times ((3-4) + (5 \times ((6+7) \times 89)))))) \\
11569 &:= (1 + (2 \times ((3-4) + (5 \times ((6+7) \times 89)))))) \\
11570 &:= (((((12^3) \times 4) + (5 \times 6)) \times -(7+8)) / -9) \\
11571 &:= ((1+2) \times -((3+4) - (56 \times (78-9)))) \\
11572 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times ((3-4) - (5 \times ((6+7) \times 89)))))) \\
11573 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times ((5 + (67+8)) - 9)) \\
11574 &:= ((1 - (23-4)) \times (5 + ((6-78) \times 9))) \\
11575 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(((3+4) \times 5) - 678) \times 9))) \\
11576 &:= (1 \times (2^3) \times -(((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) \\
11577 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5^6))) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
11578 &:= (1 \times (2 \times ((34 \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8))) + 9))) \\
11579 &:= (1 + (2 \times ((34 \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8))) + 9))) \\
11580 &:= ((12+3) \times -(4 \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - (8+9)))) \\
11581 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6)))) + (78 \times -9)) \\
11582 &:= (1 \times (2 - (3 \times (4 - (56 \times (78-9)))))) \\
11583 &:= (((1+2)^{3+4} \times 5) + ((6-78) \times -9)) \\
11584 &:= (((12^3) - ((4^5) \times (6+7))) \times (8-9)) \\
11585 &:= ((1-2) \times ((34 \times -(5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9)) \\
11586 &:= ((1+2) - ((3^4) \times -(56 + (78+9)))) \\
11587 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (34 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))))) - 9)) \\
11588 &:= (1 + ((2 + (34 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))))) - 9)) \\
11589 &:= ((1+2) \times ((3-4) + (56 \times (78-9)))) \\
11590 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((34 - (5+6)) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
11591 &:= (1 - (2 - ((34 - (5+6)) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
11592 &:= (((12^3) \times -(4 - (5+6))) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
11593 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times (5+67)))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
11594 &:= (1 \times ((23-45) \times -((67 \times 8) - 9))) \\
11595 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - ((5^6) + (7 \times 8)))) + 9) \\
11596 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (34 \times 5)) \times -67) - (8 \times 9))) \\
11597 &:= (12 - ((34 \times -(5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9)) \\
11598 &:= (1 \times -(((2^{3 \times 4}) - ((5^6) + (78-9)))) \\
11599 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3^{(-4+5) \times 6}) - 7) \times -8) + 9)) \\
11600 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3^{(-4+5) \times 6}) - 7) \times -8) + 9)) \\
11601 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((34 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9))) \\
11602 &:= (1 - (2 - ((34 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9))) \\
11603 &:= ((1-2) \times ((34 \times -(5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\
11604 &:= ((12 - (3 \times ((4^5) \times ((6 \times 7) - 8)))) / -9) \\
11605 &:= (((1+2) - (3 \times ((4^5) \times ((6 \times 7) - 8)))) / -9) \\
11606 &:= (1 + (2 + ((34 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9))) \\
11607 &:= ((1 + ((2-34) \times 5)) \times ((6-7) - (8 \times 9))) \\
11608 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3 \times 456) - 78) \times 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11568 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times ((6 - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
11569 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) - (((5 + 4)^3) \times 2)))) \times 1) \\
11570 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times (((6 \times -5) + (4^3))^2 + 1)) \\
11571 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) - (6^5)) / 4) \times (3 \times 2))) \times -1) \\
11572 &:= ((987 + 65) \times -((4 \times -3) + (2 - 1))) \\
11573 &:= (98 - (765 \times -((4 \times 3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
11574 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times -(((65 \times 4) - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
11575 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((76 - ((5^4) + 3)) \times -21)) \\
11576 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 + (5 \times 4)))))) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
11577 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times ((65 + 4) \times 3)) - (2 + 1)))) \\
11578 &:= (98 - (((7654 \times 3) / -2) + 1)) \\
11579 &:= ((9 - 87) - (((((6^5) - 4) \times 3) / -2) + 1)) \\
11580 &:= ((9 - 87) - (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) / - (2 \times 1)) \\
11581 &:= ((9 - 87) - (((((6^5) - 4) \times 3) / -2) - 1)) \\
11582 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) - ((6^5) / 4)) \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1) \\
11583 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) - ((6^5) / 4)) \times -(3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
11584 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((76 + 5) \times -(((4 \times 3)^2) - 1))) \\
11585 &:= ((9 - 87) - (((6^5) / 4) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1) \\
11586 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times -((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)) + 1)) \\
11587 &:= ((9 - 87) - (((6^5) / 4) \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1) \\
11588 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) - (6^5)) / 4) \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1) \\
11589 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) - (6^5)) / 4) \times -(3 + (2 + 1))) \\
11590 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) - (6^5)) / 4) \times -(3 \times 2) + 1) \\
11591 &:= (9 - (87 - (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) / 2) - 1) \\
11592 &:= ((98 - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 + (4^3)) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
11593 &:= ((9 - 87) - (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) / -2) - 1) \\
11594 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((76 - 54) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
11595 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times 6)) + ((5^4) \times (3 - 21)))) \\
11596 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) / -2) + 1) \\
11597 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(76 \times (5 + 4))) - 32) + 1) \\
11598 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times -((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)) - 1)) \\
11599 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - 4))) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
11600 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((76 + 5) \times -(((4 \times 3)^2) - 1))) \\
11601 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) - (6 - 543)) \times -21)) \\
11602 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7 \times (6 - ((5 \times 43) - 2)))) + 1)) \\
11603 &:= (((9 - 8) - (((7 + 6)^5) + 4)) / (32 \times -1)) \\
11604 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) - ((6^5) / 4)) \times (3 \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
11605 &:= (9876 - ((54 \times -32) - 1)) \\
11606 &:= ((-98 / -7) \times -((6 \times -((5 + (4^3)) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
11607 &:= ((-9 + 87) - ((6 + 543) \times -21)) \\
11608 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(6 - (((5 + 4)^3) \times 2) - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11609 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - ((5^6) + 7))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
11610 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times ((4 \times -5) - ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
11611 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - 5) \times (6 - (7 + 8)))) - 9 \\
11612 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5^6))) - (7 - 89)) \\
11613 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4^5)))) \times ((6 \times 7) - 8))/9) \\
11614 &:= (1 - (((2 + (34 \times 5)) \times -67) - 89)) \\
11615 &:= (1 \times -(23 \times -(((4 \times 5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) + 9))) \\
11616 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 - 4))^5)) \times (6 \times -(7 - (8 - 9)))) \\
11617 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3^{(-4+5) \times 6})) - 7) \times -8) - 9)) \\
11618 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3^{(-4+5) \times 6})) - 7) \times -8) - 9)) \\
11619 &:= ((12^3) - (((4^5) + (67 + 8)) \times -9)) \\
11620 &:= ((12 + ((3 \times ((4^5) - (6^7)))/8))/ -9) \\
11621 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 \times ((4^5) - (6^7)))/8)) / -9) \\
11622 &:= (((1 + 2) - (3^4)) \times ((5 \times -6) - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
11623 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times 6))) + (78 \times -9)) \\
11624 &:= (((-123 + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) - 89) \\
11625 &:= ((1 + (23 \times 4)) \times -(5 \times -((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9)))) \\
11626 &:= (1 + (((2 + 3)^4)/5) \times (6 + (78 + 9))) \\
11627 &:= ((-1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - 5) \times (6 - (7 + 8)))) + 9 \\
11628 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3^4) - 5))) \times -((6 + 7) - 89)) \\
11629 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - 5) \times (6 - (7 + 8)))) + 9 \\
11630 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(((3^4) \times (5 + 67)) - (8 + 9)))) \\
11631 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3^4) \times (5 + 67)) - (8 + 9)))) \\
11632 &:= 1 \times 2^{3!} / 4 \times (5! \times 6 - 7 \times (8 - 9)) \\
11633 &:= (-1 - (2 \times -((3 + 4) \times ((56 \times (7 + 8)) - 9)))) \\
11634 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((3 + 4) \times ((56 \times (7 + 8)) - 9)))) \\
11635 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 + 4) \times ((56 \times (7 + 8)) - 9)))) \\
11636 &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times -(4 - ((5 \times (6 \times 78)) - 9)))) \\
11637 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 \times ((4^5) + 6)) + 789)) \\
11638 &:= ((12 - 34) \times ((5 \times -((6 + 7) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
11639 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3^4) \times (5 + 67)) - 8)) + 9)) \\
11640 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 \times -((4 + 5) - ((6^7)/(8 \times 9)))) \\
11641 &:= (1 + (((234 \times 5) - 6) \times -(7 - (8 + 9)))) \\
11642 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3!! + 4 \times (5 + 6) + 7! + 8 + 9) \\
11643 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 \times -4) + 5) + ((6^7)/(8 \times 9)))) \\
11644 &:= (((12^3) - 4) \times 5) - (6 \times -(7 \times (8 \times 9))) \\
11645 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (345 - 6)) + 7) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
11646 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) + (5 - 6))) \times ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
11647 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3^4) \times (5 + 67))) + (8 + 9))) \\
11648 &:= (((1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times (5 + 67)))) - 8) - 9) \\
11649 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5^6))) - (7 \times -(8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11609 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 \times -(5 + (4 + 32))) - 1)) \\
11610 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((((6^5) - 4) \times 3) / -2) + 1)) \\
11611 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -7) + (((((6^5) - 4) \times 3) / (2 \times 1)))) \\
11612 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -7) + (((((6^5) - 4) \times 3) / 2) + 1))) \\
11613 &:= (9 + ((8 - (76 \times (54 - 3))) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
11614 &:= (9 + (((8 + ((7 - ((6^5) / 4)) \times 3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
11615 &:= (9 + ((8 + ((7 - ((6^5) / 4)) \times 3)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
11616 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((((6^5) / 4) \times -3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
11617 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((65 + 43)^2) \times -1)) \\
11618 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((((6^5) / 4) \times -3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
11619 &:= (((9 - 87) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3)) / -2 \times -1) \\
11620 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) \times ((4 \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\
11621 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 - ((6^5) / 4)) \times -3) \times 2) - 1) \\
11622 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((((6^5) + 4) \times 3) / -2) + 1)) \\
11623 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -7) + (((((6^5) + 4) \times 3) / (2 \times 1)))) \\
11624 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -7) + (((((6^5) + 4) \times 3) / 2) + 1))) \\
11625 &:= ((9 + (8 + 76)) \times -((5^4) / -((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
11626 &:= (((-9 \times -((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5 - 43))) - 2) \times 1) \\
11627 &:= (98 - (7 \times -((6 + 543) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
11628 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (6 \times -((54 \times (3 \times 2)) - 1))) \\
11629 &:= (9 - (8 - (76 \times ((54 - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
11630 &:= (((9 + 8) - (((7 + 65) / 4)^3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
11631 &:= (((9 - 8) + (76 \times (54 - 3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
11632 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 - ((6 - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times 2))) + 1)) \\
11633 &:= (9 - (((87 + 6) \times (5^4)) / -3 \times 2) + 1) \\
11634 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) - (6^5)) / 4)) \times -3 \times -2 \times 1)) \\
11635 &:= (9 - (((87 + 6) \times (5^4)) / -3 \times 2) - 1) \\
11636 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(76 \times (5 + 4))) + ((3^2) - 1)) \\
11637 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 - 54)))) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\
11638 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) - (((6^5) - 4) \times 3)) / 2) + 1) \\
11639 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) - (((6^5) - 4) \times 3)) / (2 \times 1))) \\
11640 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) - (((6^5) - 4) \times 3)) / 2) - 1) \\
11641 &:= (9 - (8 \times -7 - (((6 - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times 2) - 1))) \\
11642 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) - (((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
11643 &:= (9 - (((8 - 76) + (5^4)) - 3) \times -21) \\
11644 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) - (((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times (2 \times -1) \\
11645 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((76 \times 54) / -3 \times 2) - 1)) \\
11646 &:= (9 - (((8 - ((7 - ((6^5) / 4)) \times 3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
11647 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((7 - ((6^5) / 4)) \times 3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
11648 &:= (9 - (((8 - ((7 - ((6^5) / 4)) \times 3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
11649 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 - (((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times -2) - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11650 &:= ((1 - 234) \times ((5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))) / -9) \\
11651 &:= (1 \times (2 - ((3 \times (45 - ((6^7)/8)))) / 9)) \\
11652 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 + (((4 + 5) - ((6^7)/8)) / 9))) \\
11653 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 45))) \times -((6 \times -7) + (8 - 9))) \\
11654 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((34 \times -((5 \times 67) + 8)) + 9)) \\
11655 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 \times (4 + 5)) - ((6^7)/8)) / -9)) \\
11656 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^{(-4+5) \times 6}))) \times -(7 - (8 - 9))) \\
11657 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3 \times ((4 \times 5) - ((6^7)/8)))) / -9) \\
11658 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 - (((4 + 5) + ((6^7)/8)) / 9))) \\
11659 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3 \times (4 \times (5 + 6)))) \times -(78 + 9))) \\
11660 &:= (1 \times -(((23^4) + (5 - 6)) / -(7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
11661 &:= (1 - (((23^4) + (5 - 6)) / -(7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
11662 &:= (1 \times (2 \times (((3^4) \times (5 + 67)) + (8 - 9)))) \\
11663 &:= ((12 + (3 \times ((4 \times 5) - (6^7)))) / (8 \times -9)) \\
11664 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 \times ((4 + 5) - ((6^7)/8))) / -9)) \\
11665 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5^6))) - ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
11666 &:= ((1 - 2) - ((3 \times ((4 + 5) + ((6^7)/8))) / -9)) \\
11667 &:= ((1 - 2) \times ((3 \times ((4 + 5) + ((6^7)/8))) / -9)) \\
11668 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(((3^4) + 5) \times 67) + (8 \times 9))) \\
11669 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 \times ((4 + 5) + ((6^7)/8)) / 9))) \\
11670 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3 \times ((4 + 5) + ((6^7)/8)) / 9))) \\
11671 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3 \times ((4 \times 5) + ((6^7)/8)))) / 9) \\
11672 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^{(-4+5) \times 6}))) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
11673 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 \times (4 + 5)) + ((6^7)/8)) / -9)) \\
11674 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((34 \times -((5 \times 67) + 8)) - 9)) \\
11675 &:= (((12^3) - (4 + 56)) \times 7) + (8 - 9) \\
11676 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 + (((4 + 5) + ((6^7)/8)) / 9))) \\
11677 &:= (((((12^3) - (4 + 56)) \times 7) - 8) + 9) \\
11678 &:= (1 - (2 + ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times (678 + 9)))) \\
11679 &:= (12 - ((3 \times ((4 + 5) + ((6^7)/8))) / -9)) \\
11680 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^4)) \times ((5 + 6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
11681 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3^4) \times (5 + 67))) - (8 + 9))) \\
11682 &:= (((1 + ((2 \times 3^4)) - (5 - 6)) \times -((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
11683 &:= (12 - ((34 \times -((5 \times 67) + 8)) - 9)) \\
11684 &:= (((12^3) + 4) \times 5) - (6 \times -(7 \times (8 \times 9))) \\
11685 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 \times -4) + 5) - ((6^7) / (8 \times 9)))) \\
11686 &:= (1 - (((2^{3+4}) - 5) \times -(((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9))) \\
11687 &:= (-1 + (2 \times -(3 \times (4 \times (((5 - 67) \times 8) + 9)))) \\
11688 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^{4-5+6}))) \times (7 + (8 + 9))) \\
11689 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) \times -(4 - (5 \times (6 \times 78)))) + 9)) \\
11690 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(3 - ((4^5) + (67 \times (8 \times 9))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11650 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) - (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) / -2) - 1) \\
11651 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) - (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) / -(2 \times 1))) \\
11652 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 - (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) / 2)) \times -1) \\
11653 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) / 2) + 1) \\
11654 &:= (((9 - (8 - 7)) - (((6^5) - 4) \times 3)) / (2 \times -1)) \\
11655 &:= (((9 - 8) - ((7 - (6 - 5))^4)) \times (3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
11656 &:= (((9 + 8) - ((7 - ((6^5) - 4) \times 3)) / -2) \times -1) \\
11657 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) - (((6^5) / 4) \times -(3 \times 2) + 1)) \\
11658 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) / (2 \times 1)) \\
11659 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -((((6^5) - 4) \times 3) / -2) - 1) \\
11660 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) / -2) - 1) \\
11661 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 7) \times 6) / 5^4) / 3)) / -(2 + 1) \\
11662 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 - (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) / 2) - 1) \\
11663 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) / 2) - 1) \\
11664 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) - (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) / -(2 \times 1)) \\
11665 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) - (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) / -2) + 1) \\
11666 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) / 2) + 1) \\
11667 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) / 2) + 1) \\
11668 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 - (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) / 2)) \times -1) \\
11669 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) - 4)) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
11670 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) / -2) + 1) \\
11671 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) / -(2 \times 1)) \\
11672 &:= (((9 + 8) - ((7 + ((6^5) / 4)) \times 3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
11673 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) - (((6^5) / 4) \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1) \\
11674 &:= (((9 - (8 - 7)) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) / -(2 \times -1)) \\
11675 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) / -(2 \times -1) \\
11676 &:= (9 - (((8 - 7) + (((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
11677 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) / 2)) \times -1) \\
11678 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) / 2)) \times -1) \\
11679 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + (((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
11680 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 + (((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
11681 &:= (((9 - 8) + ((7 + ((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) / -(2 \times -1)) \\
11682 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (((6^5) / -4) - (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
11683 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) / 2) + 1) \\
11684 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) + (((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times -(2 \times -1) \\
11685 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times -((5 - (4 \times 32)) \times -1)) \\
11686 &:= (9 + (((8 + 76) \times -(5 - ((4 \times 3)^2))) + 1) \\
11687 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) - (((6^5) / 4) \times -(3 \times 2) + 1)) \\
11688 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 7) + ((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) / (2 \times -1)) \\
11689 &:= (((9 + 8) + ((7 + ((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) / -2) \times -1) \\
11690 &:= (9 - (((876 \times (5 \times 4)) / 3) \times -2) - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11691 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times -(((4+56) - 7) \times -8) - 9)) \\
11692 &:= (1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4+5))) \times (6 \times 78))) - 9) \\
11693 &:= (((12^3) - (4+56)) \times 7) + (8+9) \\
11694 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times 3) \times -((4 + ((5^6) + 7)/8)) - 9))) \\
11695 &:= (1 - ((2 \times 3) \times -((4 + ((5^6) + 7)/8)) - 9))) \\
11696 &:= ((1 - 2) - ((3 + 4) \times -((5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9))) \\
11697 &:= ((1 - 2) \times ((3 + 4) \times -((5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9))) \\
11698 &:= (1 \times - (2 \times -(((3^4) \times (5 + 67)) + (8 + 9)))) \\
11699 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 + 4) \times ((5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)))) \\
11700 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3 + 4) \times ((5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)))) \\
11701 &:= (((((12^3) - ((4 + 5) \times 6)) \times 7) - 8) - 9) \\
11702 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times 6))) + (7 \times -89)) \\
11703 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - (3 - 4))^5) + 6) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\
11704 &:= (1 - (((2 - (3 - 4))^5) + 6) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\
11705 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times ((3 \times (4 - (5^6))) + 7)) / -8) - 9)) \\
11706 &:= (1 + (((2 \times ((3 \times (4 - (5^6))) + 7)) / -8) - 9)) \\
11707 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 \times ((4^5) + (6^7))) / 8)) / 9) \\
11708 &:= ((12 + ((3 \times ((4^5) + (6^7))) / 8)) / 9) \\
11709 &:= (12 - ((3 + 4) \times -((5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9))) \\
11710 &:= (1 + (((2 - (3 \times (4 + 5))) \times - (6 \times 78)) + 9)) \\
11711 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3) \times - (4 + (5 \times (6 \times 78)))) + 9)) \\
11712 &:= ((1 + ((2 - (3 - 4))^5)) \times - (6 \times - (7 - (8 - 9)))) \\
11713 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3) \times (4 - ((5^6) + 7))) / 8)) - 9) \\
11714 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 345) + (6 - 7)) \times - (8 + 9))) \\
11715 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 \times 4) + 5) + ((6^7) / (8 \times 9)))) \\
11716 &:= (((12^3) - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times 7) + (8 \times -9) \\
11717 &:= (((12^3) - ((4 + 5) \times 6)) \times 7) + (8 - 9) \\
11718 &:= (((12^3) - ((4 + 5) \times 6)) \times -7) \times (8 - 9) \\
11719 &:= (((((12^3) - ((4 + 5) \times 6)) \times 7) - 8) + 9) \\
11720 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) \times -(((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
11721 &:= (1 + ((2^3) \times -(((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
11722 &:= (1 \times - (2 - (3 \times ((4 \times 5) + ((6^7) / (8 \times 9)))))) \\
11723 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times ((4 \times 5) + ((6^7) / (8 \times 9)))))) \\
11724 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3 + 4)) + 5) \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\
11725 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times - (5 - (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
11726 &:= ((1 - 23) \times - (4 + ((5 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8)) + 9))) \\
11727 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 \times - ((4 \times 5) + ((6^7) / (8 \times 9)))))) \\
11728 &:= (1 \times - (2 - ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
11729 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
11730 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3 \times 45)) \times ((6 + 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
11731 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3) \times (4 - ((5^6) + 7))) / 8)) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11691 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 + 54)))) \times (3^{2+1})) \\
11692 &:= (9 + ((8 \times - (7 \times (6 - (5 \times 43)))) - 21)) \\
11693 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) - (((((6^5) + 4) \times 3) / -2) + 1)) \\
11694 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) + (6^5)) / 4)) \times (3 \times - (2 \times 1))) \\
11695 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3)) / - (2 \times 1))) \\
11696 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 + (((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
11697 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 76) \times (5 \times 4))) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
11698 &:= (9 + ((8 \times - ((7 \times (6 - (5 \times 43)))) + 2)) + 1) \\
11699 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((7 + ((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times - (2 \times 1))) \\
11700 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times (65 \times 4)) - 3) \times - (2 + 1)) \\
11701 &:= (-9 - (8 - (7 \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times (32 - 1)))))) \\
11702 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) + (((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
11703 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) + (((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times 2) \times 1) \\
11704 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) + (((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
11705 &:= ((9 - 8) \times - (((7 + ((6^5) / 4)) \times - (3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
11706 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 + ((6^5) / 4)) \times - (3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
11707 &:= ((9 - 8) \times - (((7 + ((6^5) / 4)) \times - (3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
11708 &:= (((9 - 8) + ((7 + ((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times - (2 \times -1)) \\
11709 &:= (((9 - 87) - (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) / (2 \times -1)) \\
11710 &:= (9 + ((8 \times - (7 \times (6 - (5 \times 43)))) - (2 + 1))) \\
11711 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 - (5 \times 43)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
11712 &:= (((9 - (8 - 7)) + ((6^5) / 4)) \times - (3 \times - (2 \times 1))) \\
11713 &:= ((9 + 8) \times - ((7 + 6) \times - ((5 \times 4) + (32 + 1)))) \\
11714 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times (6 - (5 \times 43)))) - 2)) - 1) \\
11715 &:= (((9 + 8) + (((7 - (6 - 5))^4) \times 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
11716 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times (6 - (5 \times 43)))) - 2)) + 1) \\
11717 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) / 2) \times -1) \\
11718 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times (65 \times 4)) + 3) \times - (2 + 1)) \\
11719 &:= (98 + (((7 - ((6^5) / 4)) \times - (3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
11720 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 + (5 \times 4)))) \times ((3^2) - 1)) \\
11721 &:= (98 + (((7 - ((6^5) / 4)) \times - (3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
11722 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) / 2) - 1)) \\
11723 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) / (2 \times 1))) \\
11724 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 + ((6^5) / 4)) \times - (3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
11725 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) + 4)) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
11726 &:= ((9 - (8 - (76 + 5))) \times (((4 \times 3)^2) - 1)) \\
11727 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (65 \times 4))) \times - (3 \times - (2 - 1))) \\
11728 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - (((65 + 43)^2) - 1))) \\
11729 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - ((65 + 43)^2 \times 1))) \\
11730 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times - ((5 \times - (4 + 3)) + (2 - 1))) \\
11731 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((7 + ((6^5) / 4)) \times 3)) \times - (2 \times 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11732 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3^4) + (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times 89)))) & 11732 &:= (9 - (((8 + ((7 + ((6^5)/4) \times 3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
11733 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times -(6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 11733 &:= (((-987 + (6 + 5)) \times -(4 \times 3)) + 21) \\
11734 &:= (((12^3) - (45 - 6)) \times 7) - 89 & 11734 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7 \times (6 - (5 \times 43)))) + 21)) \\
11735 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) \times 8) + 9)) & 11735 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)/(2 \times 1))) \\
11736 &:= (1 - (((2 - ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) \times 8) + 9)) & 11736 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)/2 + 1)) \\
11737 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times (5 + 67)))) - (8 \times -9)) & 11737 &:= ((98 - (7 - 6)) \times -((5 \times -(4 \times (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\
11738 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(((3 \times (4 + (5^6))) - 7)/8) + 9)) & 11738 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times -((65 \times (4 \times 3)) + 2)) + 1)) \\
11739 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3 \times (4 + (5^6))) - 7)/8) + 9)) & 11739 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times -((65 \times (4 \times 3)) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
11740 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (4 + ((5^6) + 7)/8))) - 9) & 11740 &:= (((9 + 8) + ((7 + ((6^5)/4) \times 3)) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
11741 &:= (((12^3) \times 4) + 5) - (67 \times -(8 \times 9)) & 11741 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) - 4) \times -((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\
11742 &:= (12 - ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times -(6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 11742 &:= (9876 - (((5^4) - 3) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
11743 &:= (1 \times -(2 + ((3 - (4 \times ((5 \times 67) - 8))) \times 9)) & 11743 &:= (((-98 \times 7) - 6) \times -(5 + (4 \times 3))) - 21) \\
11744 &:= (1 \times ((2 - 34) \times -(((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9)) & 11744 &:= (9 - (((8 + ((7 - (6 - 5))^4)) \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\
11745 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3+4} \times 5) - (6 \times -((7 + 8) \times 9)) & 11745 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((76 + 5) \times -(((4 \times 3)^2) + 1))) \\
11746 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times (((45 + 6) - 7) \times 89))) & 11746 &:= (9 - (8 - ((76 + 5) \times (((4 \times 3)^2) + 1)))) \\
11747 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 345) - (6 - 7)) \times -(8 + 9)) & 11747 &:= (98 + (((7 - (((6^5)/4) \times 3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
11748 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 - (4 \times ((5 \times 67) - 8))) \times -9)) & 11748 &:= (98 + ((7 - (((6^5)/4) \times 3)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
11749 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times 6))) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9)) & 11749 &:= (98 + ((7 - (((6^5) - 4) \times 3)/2)) \times -1)) \\
11750 &:= ((1 - ((23 - 4) \times 5)) \times -(6 + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 11750 &:= (9 - (((((8 \times 7) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3)/ -2) + 1)) \\
11751 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((34 - 5) + ((6^7)/(8 \times 9))) & 11751 &:= (9 - (((((8 \times 7) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3)/ -2) + 1)) \\
11752 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 3) \times 45)) \times -((6 \times 78)/ -9)) & 11752 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) - 2)) + 1)) \\
11753 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times -((5 + 67) - (8 - 9)) & 11753 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times -((4 \times (3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
11754 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 \times -((4^5) + (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) & 11754 &:= ((98 - 7) - (((6^5)/4) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
11755 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 + ((4 - (5 - 67)) \times 89))) & 11755 &:= ((98 - ((7^6) - (5 - 4)))/ -((3^2) + 1)) \\
11756 &:= (((12^3) - (45 + 6)) \times 7) + (8 + 9) & 11756 &:= (9 - (((((8 \times 7) + (6^5)))/4) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
11757 &:= (12 + ((3 - (4 \times ((5 \times 67) - 8))) \times -9)) & 11757 &:= ((9 + (((((8 \times 7) + (6^5)))/4) \times (3 \times 2))) \times 1) \\
11758 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (4 + ((5^6) + 7)/8))) + 9) & 11758 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5)/4) \times 3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
11759 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3^{(-4+5) \times 6}) + 7) \times 8) - 9)) & 11759 &:= ((9 + 87) - (((6^5)/4) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
11760 &:= ((1 + 23) \times -((4 \times 5) - (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 11760 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -((6 \times 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2 \times 1))) \\
11761 &:= (1 + (((234 \times 5) + 6) \times -(7 - (8 + 9))) & 11761 &:= ((98 - 7) - (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)/ -2) + 1)) \\
11762 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 34) \times ((5 \times 67) - 8))) - 9) & 11762 &:= ((98 - 7) - (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)/ -2) - 1)) \\
11763 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 - (4 \times ((5 + ((6 + 7) \times 8)) \times 9)))) & 11763 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7^6)) - (5 \times 4))/(3^2 + 1)) \\
11764 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((345 - (6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9))) & 11764 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7^6) - (5 + 4))/ -((3^2) + 1))) \\
11765 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -(4 + ((5 \times (6 \times 78)) + 9))) & 11765 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7^6) + (5 - 4))/(3^2 + 1))) \\
11766 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times -(67 + 8)) + 9) & 11766 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((7^6) + (5 - 4))/(3^2 + 1))) \\
11767 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times -(67 + 8)) + 9) & 11767 &:= (((9 - 8) + ((7^6) + (5 \times 4)))/(3^2 + 1)) \\
11768 &:= (1 - ((23 \times -(456 + (7 \times 8))) + 9)) & 11768 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -((6 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))^2)) - 1)) \\
11769 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 + 4) \times -5) - ((6^7)/(8 \times 9))) & 11769 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -((6 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))^2)) - 1)) \\
11770 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times (4 \times ((5 + ((6 + 7) \times 8)) \times 9)))) & 11770 &:= ((98 + 7) - (((6^5)/4) \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
11771 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (4 \times ((5 + ((6 + 7) \times 8)) \times 9)))) & 11771 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
11772 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -4) \times ((5 \times -6) - (7 + (8 \times 9))) & 11772 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))))) - (2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11773 &:= (1 \times -((2-3) - (4 \times (((5 \times 67) - 8) \times 9)))) \\
11774 &:= (1 - ((2-3) - (4 \times (((5 \times 67) - 8) \times 9)))) \\
11775 &:= ((1 + (((2+3) - (4^5)) \times ((6+7) \times 8)))/ -9) \\
11776 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times -((6+78) - 9))) \\
11777 &:= (1 \times ((2+3) + (4 \times (((5 \times 67) - 8) \times 9)))) \\
11778 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -3) - (4 \times (((5 \times 67) - 8) \times 9)))) \\
11779 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6)))) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
11780 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (((4 \times 56) + 7) \times (8+9)))) \\
11781 &:= (12 + (((3+4) \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9)) \\
11782 &:= ((1 + ((2+34) \times ((5 \times 67) - 8))) + 9) \\
11783 &:= (1 \times (((23-45) \times -(67 \times 8)) - 9)) \\
11784 &:= (12 - (3 \times -(4 \times ((5 + ((6+7) \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
11785 &:= ((12^3) - (((4 \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times -89)) \\
11786 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) + 5)) \times -((6-7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
11787 &:= ((1+2) \times -(((3^4) - (5+6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9) \\
11788 &:= (((12^3) - (4 \times (5+6))) \times -7) \times (8-9) \\
11789 &:= (((((12^3) - (4 \times (5+6))) \times 7) - 8) + 9) \\
11790 &:= ((12 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\
11791 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times 6)))) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
11792 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -((4^5) - ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
11793 &:= (1 - ((2^3) \times -((4^5) - ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
11794 &:= (1 \times - (2 \times -(((3^{(-4+5) \times 6}) + 7) \times 8) + 9)) \\
11795 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3^{(-4+5) \times 6}) + 7) \times 8) + 9)) \\
11796 &:= (12 \times -((3 \times -(4 \times (5 \times 6))) - (7 \times 89))) \\
11797 &:= (1 \times - (2 - ((3 + (4 \times ((5 \times 67) - 8))) \times 9)) \\
11798 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 + (4 \times ((5 \times 67) - 8))) \times 9)) \\
11799 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times -(((4+56) \times -7) - (8+9))) \\
11800 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - ((3 - (4^5)) \times (6+7))) \times 8) / -9) \\
11801 &:= (1 - (((2 - ((3 - (4^5)) \times (6+7))) \times 8) / -9) \\
11802 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times 3) \times -(4 + (((5^6) + 7)/8) + 9))) \\
11803 &:= (1 - ((2 \times 3) \times -(4 + (((5^6) + 7)/8) + 9))) \\
11804 &:= (((12^3) + (4 - 56)) \times 7) - (8 \times -9) \\
11805 &:= (((((12^3) - (4 \times (5+6))) \times 7) + 8) + 9) \\
11806 &:= (((((12^3) - (45 - 6)) \times 7) - 8) - 9) \\
11807 &:= (((12^3) - ((4+5) \times 6)) \times 7) + 89 \\
11808 &:= (((1-2) - (3^4)) \times ((56/7) + 8) \times -9) \\
11809 &:= ((((-12 \times 3) - 4) \times -(5 \times (67 - 8))) + 9) \\
11810 &:= (1 \times -((2 + ((3^{4+5}) \times 6))/(7 - (8+9)))) \\
11811 &:= (1 - ((2 + ((3^{4+5}) \times 6))/(7 - (8+9)))) \\
11812 &:= (1 + (((2 + (3^{4+5})) \times 6) / - (7 - (8+9)))) \\
11813 &:= (1 - (23 - ((4 + (5+6)) \times 789)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11773 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((7^6) - (5-4))) / - ((3^2) + 1))) \\
11774 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((7^6) + (5+4))) / - ((3^2) + 1))) \\
11775 &:= (9 - (8 - (7 \times (((6 + (5 \times (4+3)))^2) + 1)))) \\
11776 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7+6) + (((5+4)^3) \times 2))) + 1)) \\
11777 &:= (98 - (((7 + (((6^5)/4) \times 3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
11778 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7+6) + (((5+4)^3) \times 2))) - 1)) \\
11779 &:= ((9-8) \times (7 - (654 \times (3-21)))) \\
11780 &:= ((9-8) \times -((76 \times 5) \times -(4 + (3^{2+1})))) \\
11781 &:= ((9+8) - (((7^6) - (5+4)) / - ((3^2) + 1))) \\
11782 &:= ((9+8) + (((7^6) + (5-4)) / ((3^2) + 1))) \\
11783 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times 5))) \times (4^3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
11784 &:= ((9+8) - (7 \times -((6 + (5 \times (4+3)))^2 \times 1))) \\
11785 &:= ((9+8) - ((7 \times -((6 + (5 \times (4+3)))^2)) - 1)) \\
11786 &:= (9 + (((8 - ((76 \times 5) - 4)) \times -32) + 1)) \\
11787 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times 5))) \times (4^3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
11788 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 - (6 \times 5))) \times -(4^3)) + (2 + 1))) \\
11789 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + (6 \times 54)) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
11790 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4+3)))))) + 21) \\
11791 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times (((6 + (5 \times (4+3)))^2) + 1)))) \\
11792 &:= ((9 + ((87 \times 6) + 5)) \times (43 - 21)) \\
11793 &:= ((9 + (((87 + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3)) / - (2 \times -1)) \\
11794 &:= (9 + ((87 - ((6^5) + (4^{3 \times 2}))) \times -1)) \\
11795 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) - 4) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
11796 &:= ((9 - (87 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4))) \times -((3+2) - 1)) \\
11797 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) + 4) \times -((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\
11798 &:= ((9+8) \times -(((7+6) \times -54) + (3^2)) - 1) \\
11799 &:= ((987 + (6 \times 54)) \times -(3 \times -(2+1))) \\
11800 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)) - 2)) - 1)) \\
11801 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(7 - (((6^5) \times 4) - 3)/21))) \\
11802 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)) - 2)) + 1)) \\
11803 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5)) \times -((4 \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
11804 &:= (((9+8) - (7 \times ((6 + (5+4))^3)) / (2 \times -1)) \\
11805 &:= (98 - (((7 + ((6^5)/4)) \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
11806 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 - (6 \times 5))) \times -(4^3)) + 21)) \\
11807 &:= ((((-9 - 87) \times -((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)) - 2) + 1) \\
11808 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(6 \times -((5 \times ((4+3)^2)) + 1))) \\
11809 &:= ((9 - ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5)) \times (((4+3)^2) \times -1)) \\
11810 &:= ((-98 \times -7) - (6 \times -(5 + (43^2 \times 1)))) \\
11811 &:= (((9-8) + (76 \times 5)) \times -(((4^3) / -2) + 1)) \\
11812 &:= (((9-8) - (7 \times ((6 + (5+4))^3)) / (2 \times -1)) \\
11813 &:= (((9-8) + (7 \times ((6 + (5+4))^3)) / - (2 \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11814 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 + 5)) + (6 \times -(7 \times 89))) \\
11815 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - 45))) \times (67 + (8 \times 9))) \\
11816 &:= (1 - (((2^{3+4}) + 567) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
11817 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 \times -(4 + ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
11818 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times ((5 \times (6 + 7)) + 8)))) - 9) \\
11819 &:= ((1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - ((5 + 6) \times -(78 \times 9))) \\
11820 &:= ((1 + ((2 - (3^4)) \times 5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\
11821 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times 6))) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
11822 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 + 4) \times ((5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9)))) \\
11823 &:= ((1 - 2) \times ((3 + 4) \times -(5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9))) \\
11824 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^4) \times ((5 + 6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
11825 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 + 4) \times ((5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9)))) \\
11826 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3 + 4) \times ((5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9)))) \\
11827 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) - ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times 789))) \\
11828 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3^4) \times ((5 + 6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
11829 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3^4) \times ((5 + 6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
11830 &:= ((1 - (23 + 4)) \times -(5 - ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
11831 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 + 4) \times (56 + 789)))) \\
11832 &:= (12 \times -(((3 \times 45) + 6) \times -7) - (8 - 9)) \\
11833 &:= (1 \times (((2 - 3) - ((4^5) \times ((6 + 7) \times 8))) / -9)) \\
11834 &:= (1 + (((2 - 3) - ((4^5) \times ((6 + 7) \times 8))) / -9)) \\
11835 &:= (12 - ((3 + 4) \times -((5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9))) \\
11836 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times ((5 \times (6 + 7)) + 8)))) + 9) \\
11837 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3 + (4 + 56))) + 7) \times -89)) \\
11838 &:= (12 - ((3^4) \times -((5 + 6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
11839 &:= (1 - (2 \times (3 + (((4 \times 5) - 678) \times 9)))) \\
11840 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -(((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) + 8) / 9)) \\
11841 &:= (1 - ((2^3) \times -(((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) + 8) / 9)) \\
11842 &:= (((12^3) + (4 - (5 \times 6))) \times 7) + (8 \times -9) \\
11843 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) + ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times 789))) \\
11844 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 \times -(4 \times (5 \times 67))) + (8 \times 9)) \\
11845 &:= (1 \times -(23 \times -((4 + (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8))) - 9))) \\
11846 &:= (1 - (23 \times -((4 + (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8))) - 9))) \\
11847 &:= (1 + (2 - ((3 - 45) \times (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
11848 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((34 + 5) - (67 \times 89)))) \\
11849 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times ((3 \times 4^5)) / 6)) / - (7 \times -(8 - 9))) \\
11850 &:= ((12 + 3) \times ((4 \times -5) + (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
11851 &:= (1 - (2 \times -3 - (((4 \times 5) - 678) \times 9))) \\
11852 &:= -(1 + 2) \times 3!! + (4 + 5!) \times (-6 + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
11853 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times ((4 \times -5) + ((6 \times 78) - 9))) \\
11854 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 \times (456 \times 78)) / 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11814 &:= ((98 + (76 + 5)) \times -(((4^3) + 2) \times -1)) \\
11815 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (((7 + 6) \times 54) - ((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\
11816 &:= (98 - (7 \times -(6 \times ((5 + 4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
11817 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times (6 + (5 \times (43 - 2)))) - 1))) \\
11818 &:= (9 - (((((8 + 7) - 6^5) - 4) / - (3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
11819 &:= (9 - ((((((8 + 7) - 6^5) - 4) / - (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\
11820 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(6 \times -(5 + ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
11821 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) / - (2 \times -1)) \\
11822 &:= ((((-9 \times -8) + 7) + (((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
11823 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 76) \times (5 \times 4))) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
11824 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6^5)) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)) \\
11825 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5) + (4^{3 \times 2})) \times -1)) \\
11826 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6^5)) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)) \\
11827 &:= (98 + ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times -(4 - 321))) \\
11828 &:= ((-98 \times -7) - ((6 - (5^4)) \times -(3 - 21))) \\
11829 &:= ((9 - ((87 + (((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
11830 &:= ((98 - 7) \times -(65 \times (4 - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
11831 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 \times 65)) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) \times -1)) \\
11832 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (76 \times 5)) \times 4)) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
11833 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times (6 + (5 \times (43 - 2)))) + 1))) \\
11834 &:= ((98 - (7 - 6)) \times -5 - ((4 \times 32) - 1)) \\
11835 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times 4)) \times (3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
11836 &:= (9 - (((876 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)) / -2) - 1)) \\
11837 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) + (654 \times (3 - 21)))) \\
11838 &:= (((-987 \times 6) + ((5 + 4) / 3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
11839 &:= (((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6) + (5 \times 4)) \times -32) - 1) \\
11840 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1})) \\
11841 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 65) + (4^{3+2})))) \times 1) \\
11842 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times 65) + (4^{3+2}))) - 1)) \\
11843 &:= (98 - ((76 + 5) \times -(((4 \times 3)^2) + 1))) \\
11844 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times -(((65 \times 4) + 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
11845 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (4 \times (3 \times 21)))) \\
11846 &:= (9 - (((87 + (((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
11847 &:= (9 - ((87 + (((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
11848 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6^5) \times 4) - 3) / -21)) \\
11849 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) \times -(32 \times 1))) \\
11850 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (((6^5) / -4) - (32 - 1))) \\
11851 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) + 4)) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
11852 &:= (((-987 \times -6) + (5 - (4 - 3))) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
11853 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (76 - (5 \times 4)))) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\
11854 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(76 + (5^4))) + (3 \times -21))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11855 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 \times (456 \times 78))/9))) & 11855 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times 6)) - (5^4))) - 3) \times 2) - 1) \\
11856 &:= ((1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times -((5 + (6 + 7)) - (8 - 9))) & 11856 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (((6^5)/ -4) - (32 \times 1))) \\
11857 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times -((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9)))) & 11857 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(7 + ((6 - 54) \times (32 - 1)))))) \\
11858 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times -((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9)))) & 11858 &:= (98 - (7 \times -(6 + (54 \times (32 - 1)))))) \\
11859 &:= (((12^3) - (4 + (5 \times 6))) \times 7) - (8 - 9) & 11859 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 - (6 - 54)) \times 3))) - 21) \\
11860 &:= (((12^3) - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times 7) - (8 \times -9) & 11860 &:= ((98 + (((7 + 65)/4)^3)) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
11861 &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times -(4 \times ((5 \times 6) - (7 \times 89)))) & 11861 &:= (9 + (8 + (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (4 \times (3 \times 21)))))) \\
11862 &:= (1 \times -(((2^{3+4}) \times 5) + 678) \times -9) & 11862 &:= (98 - (((7^6) - (5 + 4))/ -((3^2) + 1))) \\
11863 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9) & 11863 &:= (98 + (((7^6) + (5 - 4))/((3^2) + 1))) \\
11864 &:= (1 - (((2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9) & 11864 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 - ((6^5) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)))) \\
11865 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 11865 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 - ((6^5) + (4^{3 \times 2}))) \times -1)) \\
11866 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) + (5 + 67))) \times (8 + 9)) & 11866 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 - ((6^5) + (4^{3 \times 2}))) \times -1)) \\
11867 &:= (-1 - (23 \times -(4 + (((5 \times 6)/(7 + 8))^9)))) & 11867 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - ((6^5) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\
11868 &:= (12 \times -(((3^4) - 5) \times -(6 + 7)) + (8 - 9)) & 11868 &:= ((98 - (7 - (6 - 5))) \times -((4 \times -32) - 1)) \\
11869 &:= (1 \times -((2 + (3^4)) \times -(56 + (78 + 9)))) & 11869 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((76 + (5^4)) - 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
11870 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -(4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) & 11870 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - ((6 + 5) \times (4^3)))) + 21) \\
11871 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) + (4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times -9) & 11871 &:= ((((-9 - 8)^7) \times (6^5)) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)) \\
11872 &:= (1 + (((2 + 3) + (4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times -9) & 11872 &:= ((((-9 - 8)^7) + ((6^5) + (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1) \\
11873 &:= (((1 + 2) - 34) \times ((56 - 7) \times -8) + 9) & 11873 &:= ((((-9 - 8)^7) + ((6^5) + (4^{3 \times 2}))) \times 1) \\
11874 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 \times ((45 \times (6 \times 7)) + 89)))) & 11874 &:= ((((-9 - 8)^7) + ((6^5) + (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1) \\
11875 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times -5) - ((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9) & 11875 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times ((5^4)/ -((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
11876 &:= (1 - ((23 - 4) \times -(5 \times (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 11876 &:= (9 - (8 - ((76 \times (5^4))/(3 + 2) - 1))) \\
11877 &:= (((12^3) - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times 7) + 89 & 11877 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 - ((6 + 5) \times 4)) \times -321)) \\
11878 &:= (1 + ((23 \times -((4 \times 5) - (67 \times 8))) + 9) & 11878 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 + ((6^5) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)))) \\
11879 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (45 \times (6 - (7 - 89)))))) & 11879 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + ((6^5) + (4^{3 \times 2}))) \times -1)) \\
11880 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) - (8 \times 9))) & 11880 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 + ((6^5) + (4^{3 \times 2}))) \times -1)) \\
11881 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9) & 11881 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + (6 \times (5 + (4 \times 3))))^2) \times -1)) \\
11882 &:= (1 - (((2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9) & 11882 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 + (6 \times (5 + (4 \times 3))))^2) \times -1)) \\
11883 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 - (4 - 5))^6) - ((7 + 8) \times 9)) & 11883 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((7 + (6 \times (5 + (4 \times 3))))^2) + 1)) \\
11884 &:= (1 + 2^{3!} \times 4!) \times (5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9 & 11884 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 76) \times (5^4))/ - (32 \times 1))) \\
11885 &:= (-1 - (2 \times -(3 + (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 11885 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 76) \times (5^4))/ - 32) - 1) \\
11886 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((3 + 4) \times (((5 + 6) \times 78) - 9))) & 11886 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (((6 \times 5) \times -((4^3) + 2)) - 1)) \\
11887 &:= (1 \times -(2 + ((3 + (4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))) & 11887 &:= (9 - (8 + (7 \times ((6 \times 5) - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))) \\
11888 &:= (1 - (2 + ((3 + (4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))) & 11888 &:= (((-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times 4) - 3)) - 2) + 1) \\
11889 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 \times -4) + (5 \times (6 + 789)))) & 11889 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 + ((5 - 43) \times 21)))) \\
11890 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times ((3^4) - 5))) - 6) \times -(7 - 89)) & 11890 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -(((5 + (4 \times 3))^2) + 1)) \\
11891 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times (5 - (6 \times (78 + 9)))) & 11891 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((65 \times -4) + ((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\
11892 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 + (4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times -9) & 11892 &:= (9 + (8 + ((76 \times (5^4))/(3 + 2) - 1))) \\
11893 &:= (1 \times -(23 + (4 \times ((5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) & 11893 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -(76 + (5^4))) - 3) - 21) \\
11894 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times (5 + (6 + 7)) - (8 - 9)) & 11894 &:= (9 + (8 - ((7 - ((6 + 5) \times 4)) \times 321))) \\
11895 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(3 \times (4 \times ((5 - 67) \times 8)))) - 9) & 11895 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + ((6^5) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11896 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -(3 \times (4 \times ((5 - 67) \times 8)))) - 9)) \\
11897 &:= (((((12^3) + (4 - (5 \times 6))) \times 7) - 8) - 9) \\
11898 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 - (((45 + 6) \times 78) - 9))) \\
11899 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times -((56/7) \times -8) - 9)) \\
11900 &:= ((123 - 4) \times ((5 + ((6 + 7) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
11901 &:= (12 + ((3 + (4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))))) \times -9)) \\
11902 &:= (((((12^3) - (4 + (5 + 6))) \times 7) - 89) \\
11903 &:= ((1 + 2) - (34 \times -(5 + ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)))) \\
11904 &:= (((12^3) \times -((4 - 5) \times (6 + (7 \times 8))))/9) \\
11905 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) \times -(4 - (5 \times ((6 \times 78) + 9)))) \\
11906 &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times -(4 - (5 \times ((6 \times 78) + 9)))) \\
11907 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3+4}) \times -((56 \times 7)/8)/ -9) \\
11908 &:= ((12^3) + (((4^5) - 6) \times -(7 - (8 + 9)))) \\
11909 &:= (((((12^3) - ((4 \times 5) - 6)) \times 7) - 89) \\
11910 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -3) - (4 \times ((5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\
11911 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -3) - (4 \times ((5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\
11912 &:= (12 - (34 \times -(5 + ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)))) \\
11913 &:= (((((12^3) + (4 - (5 \times 6))) \times 7) + (8 - 9)) \\
11914 &:= (((((12^3) + (4 - (5 \times 6))) \times -7) \times (8 - 9)) \\
11915 &:= (((((12^3) + (4 - (5 \times 6))) \times 7) - 8) + 9) \\
11916 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 + ((45 + 6) \times 78)) - 9)) \\
11917 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^4) + 56) \times (78 + 9))) \\
11918 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) + (4 \times -((5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
11919 &:= (((((12^3) - (4 + (5 + 6))) \times 7) + (8 \times -9)) \\
11920 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^4)) \times -((5 \times -6) - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
11921 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3^4) + 56) \times (78 + 9)))) \\
11922 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3^4) + 56) \times (78 + 9)))) \\
11923 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 \times ((45 + 6) \times 78)) - 9))) \\
11924 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) - (4 \times ((5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\
11925 &:= (1 + ((2^3) - (4 \times ((5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\
11926 &:= (((((12^3) - ((4 \times 5) - 6)) \times 7) + (8 \times -9)) \\
11927 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) \times -((4^5) + (6 \times 78))) + 9)) \\
11928 &:= ((12^3) - (4 \times -(5 \times (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
11929 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 \times (4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 - 89))))))) \\
11930 &:= (((((12^3) - (4 + (5 \times 6))) \times 7) - (8 \times -9)) \\
11931 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 - (4 - 5))^6) - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
11932 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 - ((4 - 5) \times (67 \times 89)))) \\
11933 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 - ((4 - 5) \times (67 \times 89)))) \\
11934 &:= (((1 + 2) - (3^4)) \times (((5 + (6 + 7)) \times -8) - 9)) \\
11935 &:= (((1 + 2) - 34) \times -(((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) + 9)) \\
11936 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((3 - 4) \times (5 + (67 \times 89))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11896 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 + ((6^5) + (4^{3 \times 2}))) \times -1)) \\
11897 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + ((6^5) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\
11898 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((7 + (6 \times (5 + (4 \times 3))))^2)) \times -1)) \\
11899 &:= (9 + (8 + (((7 + (6 \times (5 + (4 \times 3))))^2) + 1))) \\
11900 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times -((4 \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\
11901 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((76 - 5) \times (4 + 3)))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
11902 &:= (98 - ((7 + 6) \times -(5 + (43 \times 21)))) \\
11903 &:= (9 + (8 - (7 \times ((6 \times 5) - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))) \\
11904 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -(((6 + 5) \times -(43 + 2)) - 1)) \\
11905 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((76 \times 5) + 4) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
11906 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((76 + 5) \times -((4 + 3) \times 21))) \\
11907 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) \times (4 - (32 - 1))) \\
11908 &:= (9 - (8 - ((76 + 5) \times ((4 + 3) \times 21)))) \\
11909 &:= (9 + ((8 - 76) \times -(5 \times ((4 + 32) - 1)))) \\
11910 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(6 - ((54 + 3) \times 21))) \\
11911 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -6) + 5) \times (43 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
11912 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((76 \times (5 \times 4)) - 32)) + 1)) \\
11913 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((7 - (65 + 4)) \times (3 + 21)))) \\
11914 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5)) \times ((4 \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
11915 &:= (9 + (8 - ((7 + 654) \times (3 - 21)))) \\
11916 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (6 \times -((5 \times ((4^3) + 2)) + 1))) \\
11917 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((765 - (4^3)) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
11918 &:= (((-987 - 6) \times -(5 + (4 + 3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
11919 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 76) \times 5)) \times (4 - (32 + 1))) \\
11920 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7^{(6-5) \times 4})) \times ((3 + 2) \times -1)) \\
11921 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4))) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
11922 &:= ((98 + (76 \times (54 - 3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
11923 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -(76 + (5^4))) + (3 \times 2)) \times 1) \\
11924 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times -(4 + 32)) + 1)) \\
11925 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times (5 \times -(43 + 2) \times 1)) \\
11926 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times -(4 + 32)) - 1)) \\
11927 &:= (9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -(4 - (3 \times 21)))) \\
11928 &:= ((98 - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times -43) + (2 \times 1))) \\
11929 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + 6) \times 54)) - 3) + (2 \times -1)) \\
11930 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 4))) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\
11931 &:= ((98 - (7 - 6)) \times ((5 - (4 \times 32)) \times -1)) \\
11932 &:= (((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times 6) - 5) \times 43) + 21) \\
11933 &:= (-98 - (((76 \times 5) - 4) \times -32) + 1)) \\
11934 &:= ((9 + (87 + 6)) \times -(((5 - (4^3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\
11935 &:= ((9 - (8 - 76)) \times -(5 \times -(4 + (3^{2+1})))) \\
11936 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - ((6^5) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 11937 &:= ((1+2) + (34 \times -((5 \times (6-78)) + 9))) \\
 11938 &:= ((1 + (((23 \times (4+5)) + 6) \times (7 \times 8))) + 9) \\
 11939 &:= (1 + (2 \times -((3 - (4+5)) - (67 \times 89)))) \\
 11940 &:= ((1+23) + (4 \times -((5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
 11941 &:= (1 \times (((234+5) \times -(6 - (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
 11942 &:= (1 + (((234+5) \times -(6 - (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
 11943 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + (5 \times 6))) \times -((7-8) \times 9)) \\
 11944 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times ((5 + (6+7)) \times 8))) - 9) \\
 11945 &:= (1 \times -((2+3) \times -(4 + (5 \times ((6 \times 78) + 9)))) \\
 11946 &:= ((1-23) \times (((4 + (5 \times (6+7))) \times -8) + 9)) \\
 11947 &:= (((12^3) - (4 \times 5)) \times (6 - (7-8))) - 9) \\
 11948 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + (6! + 7) \times 8 - 9 \\
 11949 &:= (12 - (3 \times -(4 + (5 \times (6 + 789)))) \\
 11950 &:= ((1 + (23 \times (4 - 56))) \times (7 - (8 + 9))) \\
 11951 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 345) + (6 + 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
 11952 &:= ((1+2) \times (3 \times (4 \times ((5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)))) \\
 11953 &:= ((1-2) - (((3^4) + 5) \times -(67 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 11954 &:= ((1-2) \times (((3^4) + 5) \times -(67 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 11955 &:= ((12+3) \times -(4 - ((5 + (6 + 78)) \times 9))) \\
 11956 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3^4) + 5) \times (67 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 11957 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3^4) + 5) \times (67 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 11958 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(3 \times ((4 \times ((5 - 67) \times 8)) - 9)))) \\
 11959 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(3 \times ((4 \times ((5 - 67) \times 8)) - 9)))) \\
 11960 &:= (1 + (((234+5) \times -(6 - (7 \times 8))) + 9)) \\
 11961 &:= (((12^3) \times -(4 - (5 + 6))) + ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
 11962 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times 8))) + 9) \\
 11963 &:= (((12^3) - (((4 + (5^6)) \times 7) - 8)) / -9) \\
 11964 &:= (((1+2)^3) - (4^5)) \times -((6 + (7 + 8)) - 9) \\
 11965 &:= (((12^3) - (4 \times 5)) \times (6 - (7 - 8))) + 9) \\
 11966 &:= (((12^3) + (4 + 5)) \times -(6 + (7 \times 8))) / -9) \\
 11967 &:= (((12^3) - ((4 \times 56) + 7)) \times 8) - 9) \\
 11968 &:= ((12^3) - ((4^5) \times -((6 \times (7 + 8)) / 9))) \\
 11969 &:= ((-1+2) - (34 \times -((5 \times 67) + (8 + 9)))) \\
 11970 &:= ((1+2) \times -((3-45) \times (((6+7) \times 8) - 9))) \\
 11971 &:= ((1+2) - (34 \times -((5 \times 67) + (8 + 9)))) \\
 11972 &:= (((1-2) - (3^4)) \times -((5+6) + ((7+8) \times 9))) \\
 11973 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 + ((4 \times 5) + (67 \times 89)))) \\
 11974 &:= (((((12^3) - (4 + (5 + 6))) \times 7) - 8) - 9) \\
 11975 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 11976 &:= ((1+23) \times -((4 - (5 - 6)) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 11977 &:= (((12^3) \times -(4 - (5 + 6))) + (7 \times -(8 + 9))) \\
 11978 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 3) \times 45)) \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 11937 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 + 65) - (4 - 3)) \times 21))) \\
 11938 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - ((6^5) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\
 11939 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + 6) \times 54)) + 3) - (2 \times -1)) \\
 11940 &:= (((-987 \times -6) + (5 + 43)) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
 11941 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -(76 + (5^4))) + 3) + 21) \\
 11942 &:= (98 - (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times -(4 \times (3 \times 21)))) \\
 11943 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times (4 \times 3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 11944 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times -((4 + 32) - 1))) \\
 11945 &:= ((((-98 + 76) \times -543) - 2) + 1) \\
 11946 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) / 4)) \times (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
 11947 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(76 + ((5^4) + 3))) - 21) \\
 11948 &:= (((-98 + 76) \times -543) - (2 \times -1)) \\
 11949 &:= (((-98 + 7) \times -6) - (543 \times -21)) \\
 11950 &:= ((98 + (76 \times 5)) \times -((4 \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
 11951 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((76 - 54) \times -32) + 1)) \\
 11952 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) \times ((4 + 32) \times -1)) \\
 11953 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)) - 21))) \\
 11954 &:= ((-98 \times ((7 - 65) - (4^3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
 11955 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((76 - 5) \times (4 + 3)))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 11956 &:= (98 \times (((76 + (5 + 43)) - 2) \times 1)) \\
 11957 &:= (-98 + ((7 \times -(6 - (54 \times 32))) + 1)) \\
 11958 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 + 65)) - (4 + 3)) \times -21)) \\
 11959 &:= (-9 - (8 \times -((76 \times (5 \times 4)) - (3 + 21)))) \\
 11960 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times 4))) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
 11961 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + (4 \times 321)))) \\
 11962 &:= (98 - (7 - ((6^5) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)))) \\
 11963 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 \times -(6 - (5 \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))) \\
 11964 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 \times -(6 - (5 \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))) \\
 11965 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + 6) \times 54)) + (32 - 1)) \\
 11966 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + 6) \times 54)) - (32 \times -1)) \\
 11967 &:= (9 + (87 + ((6^5) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)))) \\
 11968 &:= (9 - ((87 + ((6^5) + (4^{3 \times 2}))) \times -1)) \\
 11969 &:= (((9 + 87) + (6^5)) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)) \\
 11970 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((7 \times 65) - 4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
 11971 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 - 6)) \times -((54 \times 3) + 2)) - 1) \\
 11972 &:= (-987 - ((6 \times -(5 \times 432)) + 1)) \\
 11973 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7^{(6-5) \times 4})) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1)) \\
 11974 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7^{(6-5) \times 4})) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
 11975 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
 11976 &:= (98 + (7 + ((6^5) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)))) \\
 11977 &:= (98 - ((7 + ((6^5) + (4^{3 \times 2}))) \times -1)) \\
 11978 &:= (98 + (7 + ((6^5) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
11979 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times 5)))) \times -((6 \times -(7 + 8)) - 9)) & 11979 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times 6) - (5 + 4))^3) / -(2 + 1)) \\
11980 &:= (1 - ((23 + (4 \times ((5 \times 67) - 8))) \times -9)) & 11980 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 \times 6) - (5 + 4))^3) / -(2 + 1)) \\
11981 &:= (((12^3) - ((4 \times 5) - 6) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) & 11981 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times -(6 - (54 \times 32))) - 1)) \\
11982 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -3) + (((4 \times (5 \times 67)) - 8) \times 9))) & 11982 &:= ((9 + ((87 - (6 \times (5 + 4)))^3)) / (2 + 1)) \\
11983 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -3) + (((4 \times (5 \times 67)) - 8) \times 9))) & 11983 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times -(6 - (54 \times 32))) + 1)) \\
11984 &:= (1 - (23 \times -((456 - 7) + (8 \times 9)))) & 11984 &:= (98 + (7 \times -((6 \times 5) - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
11985 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 - ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) & 11985 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times ((6^{(5+4)/3}) - 2)) - 1))) \\
11986 &:= (((12^3) + (4 - (5 \times 6))) \times 7) - (8 \times -9)) & 11986 &:= ((987 - 65) \times -((4 + 3) \times -2) + 1) \\
11987 &:= (1 \times ((2 - 3) + (((4 \times (5 \times 67)) - 8) \times 9))) & 11987 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 + 6) \times 54) + 3)) + 2) \times 1) \\
11988 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -((4 + 56) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 11988 &:= (9 - (((87 - (6 \times (5 + 4)))^3) / -(2 + 1))) \\
11989 &:= (1 \times -((2 - 3) - (((4 \times (5 \times 67)) - 8) \times 9))) & 11989 &:= (((-98 + 76) \times -(543 + 2)) - 1) \\
11990 &:= (((12^3) - (4 + (5 + 6))) \times 7) + (8 - 9)) & 11990 &:= ((98 - 76) \times ((543 + 2) \times 1)) \\
11991 &:= (((12^3) - (4 + (5 + 6))) \times -7) \times (8 - 9)) & 11991 &:= (((-98 + 76) \times -(543 + 2)) + 1) \\
11992 &:= (((((12^3) - (4 + (5 + 6))) \times 7) - 8) + 9) & 11992 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) \times -((6^{(5+4)/3}) - 2)) + 1)) \\
11993 &:= ((1 - (2 \times 34)) \times ((5 \times -((6 \times 7) - 8)) - 9)) & 11993 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times 7) \times ((6^{(5+4)/3}) - 2))) \times 1) \\
11994 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 + (((4 \times (5 \times 67)) - 8) \times 9))) & 11994 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times 7) \times ((6^{(5+4)/3}) - 2))) + 1) \\
11995 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 + 4) \times ((5 + 6) \times 78)) - 9))) & 11995 &:= ((-9 - (876 \times 5)) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
11996 &:= (((12^3) - 4) \times -((5 - 6) \times 7)) + (8 \times -9)) & 11996 &:= (9 + (8 + (((7 \times 6) - (5 + 4))^3) / (2 + 1))) \\
11997 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 \times -((4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9))) & 11997 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times 4) \times -(3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
11998 &:= (((12^3) - ((4 \times 5) - 6) \times -7) \times (8 - 9)) & 11998 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 76)) \times (5 \times 4)) - 3) + 21) \\
11999 &:= (((12^3) - ((4 \times 5) - 6) \times 7) - (8 - 9)) & 11999 &:= (-98 - ((7 \times -(6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 32))) - 1)) \\
12000 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^4)) \times -((5 \times -(6 + (7 + (8 + 9)))))) & 12000 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -((6 \times 5) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) + 1))) \\
12001 &:= (1 + ((2 - 34) \times -((5 \times ((6 + 78) - 9)))) & 12001 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times (65 \times 4)) - 321))) \\
12002 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6))) - 7) \times (8 + 9)))) & 12002 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 \times -(65 + (4 + 32))) + 1)) \\
12003 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6))) - 7) \times (8 + 9)))) & 12003 &:= ((98 - ((7^6) \times 5)) / (((4 + 3)^2) \times -1)) \\
12004 &:= ((12 - (3 \times ((4^5) + ((6^7)/8)))) / -9) & 12004 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7^6)) \times 5)) / (((4 + 3)^2) \times -1)) \\
12005 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((34 + 5) + (67 \times 89)))) & 12005 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) \times (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\
12006 &:= ((12 + 34) \times -(((5 \times 6) + (7 - 8)) \times -9)) & 12006 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7^6)) \times 5)) / -(((4 + 3)^2) \times -1)) \\
12007 &:= ((-12 \times (3 - ((4^5) - (6 + 7)))) - 89) & 12007 &:= ((98 + ((7^6) \times 5)) / -(((4 + 3)^2) \times -1)) \\
12008 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - (((5^6) \times 7) - 8))) / 9) & 12008 &:= (9 - (((87 \times (65 + 4)) - 3) \times -2) + 1) \\
12009 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times -(4 \times (5 \times 67))) + (8 + 9))) & 12009 &:= ((9 + ((87 \times 6) \times (5 + (4^3)))) / (2 + 1)) \\
12010 &:= (1 + (((2 - 34) \times -((5 \times (67 + 8))) + 9)) & 12010 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7^{(6-5) \times 4})) \times -((3 + 2) \times -1)) \\
12011 &:= (1 \times (23 + (((4 \times (5 \times 67)) - 8) \times 9))) & 12011 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 76)) \times (5 \times 4)) + (32 - 1)) \\
12012 &:= (1 \times ((23 - (4^5)) \times -((6 + (7 + 8)) - 9))) & 12012 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -(6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))) + (2 + 1))) \\
12013 &:= (1 + ((23 - (4^5)) \times -((6 + (7 + 8)) - 9))) & 12013 &:= ((9 + (87 \times (6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
12014 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 12014 &:= (9 + ((87 \times -(6 \times ((5 + 4) - 32))) - 1)) \\
12015 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 12015 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 76) - 5) \times 4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times -1)) \\
12016 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times (6 - 78))) - 9) & 12016 &:= ((9 + ((87 \times (6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))) + 2)) - 1) \\
12017 &:= (((12^3) \times -((4 - (5 + 6))) - 7) + (8 \times -9)) & 12017 &:= ((9 + (87 \times (6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
12018 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -(((4^5) \times -6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) & 12018 &:= ((9 + ((87 \times (6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))) + 2)) + 1) \\
12019 &:= (1 \times (((2^{3+4}) \times 5) + 67) \times (8 + 9)) & 12019 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 \times -((6 + 5) - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
12020 &:= (1 + (((2^{3+4}) \times 5) + 67) \times (8 + 9))) & 12020 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 \times -((6 + 5) - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))) \\
12021 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + 45) + (67 \times 89)))) & 12021 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7^{(6-5)^4}) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
12022 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((3 + 45) + (67 \times 89)))) & 12022 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7^{(6-5)^4}) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
12023 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - 34) \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) + 9)) & 12023 &:= (9 + (8 - (((7 \times 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 - 21)))) \\
12024 &:= (((1 - 23) + (4^5)) \times ((6 + (7 + 8)) - 9)) & 12024 &:= (((9 + 8) - (76 \times (5 \times 4))) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
12025 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times -((56 \times -7) - 89)) & 12025 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((76 \times (5 \times 4)) + (3 - 21)))) \\
12026 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) - (5^6)) \times 7) + 8)/9) & 12026 &:= (9 - (8 - ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 321)))) \\
12027 &:= (1 + (2 + (((34 - 5) \times 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9))) & 12027 &:= (((-98 - 76) \times -(5 + (4^3))) + 21) \\
12028 &:= ((12^3) + (((4^5) + 6) \times -(7 - (8 + 9)))) & 12028 &:= (((9 + (87 + 6)) - 5) \times -(4 \times -(32 - 1))) \\
12029 &:= (1 \times (23 \times -((4 - 5) - (6 \times (78 + 9)))))) & 12029 &:= (((-9 - ((87 \times (65 + 4)) + 3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
12030 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -((((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + 8) / -9) & 12030 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times (6 + ((54 + 3) \times 21))) \\
12031 &:= (((((12^3) \times -(4 - (5 + 6))) + 7) + (8 \times -9)) & 12031 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((((76 \times 5) - 4) \times -32) + 1)) \\
12032 &:= (((12^3) - (4 \times 56)) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) & 12032 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (((6 - 54) / -3)^2) \times -1) \\
12033 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) \times -(4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))))) - 9) & 12033 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((((76 \times 5) - 4) \times -32) - 1)) \\
12034 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5^6))) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 12034 &:= (9 - (8 - (((76 \times 5) - 4) \times 32) + 1)) \\
12035 &:= (1 - (2 + ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + (78 \times 9)))))) & 12035 &:= (9876 - ((5 \times -432) + 1)) \\
12036 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(34 \times -((5 - 6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 12036 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 \times -((6 + 5) - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))) \\
12037 &:= (-1 - ((234 \times (5 - (6 \times 78)))/9)) & 12037 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 - (54 \times 32)))) \times -1) \\
12038 &:= (1 \times ((234 \times (5 - (6 \times 78)))/-9)) & 12038 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times -(6 - (54 \times 32))) + 1)) \\
12039 &:= (1 \times -((((2 \times 3)^4) + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times -8) + 9) & 12039 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((765 - (4 \times 3)) \times 2))) \times -1) \\
12040 &:= (1 - (((((2 \times 3)^4) + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times -8) + 9)) & 12040 &:= ((98 - (7 \times 6)) \times -(5 \times -((4^3) - 21))) \\
12041 &:= (1 - (2 + (3 \times ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))) \times 9)))) & 12041 &:= ((9 - ((8 - ((76 \times 5) + 4)) \times 32)) \times 1) \\
12042 &:= (1 + (((2 - 34) \times -((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) + 9)) & 12042 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (((6^5) / -4) - (3 \times 21))) \\
12043 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 34) \times -((5 \times 67)) + (8 + 9))) & 12043 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 76)) \times (5 \times 4)) - (3 \times -21)) \\
12044 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((3 - (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 12044 &:= (-9 - (8 + (7 \times (6 - ((54 \times 32) + 1)))))) \\
12045 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 \times -((4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))) \times 9))) & 12045 &:= (9 - ((8 - 76) \times -((5 - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
12046 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((34 + ((5 - 678) \times 9)))) & 12046 &:= (((9 - (8 - 7)) + (6 \times 5)) \times -(4 - 321)) \\
12047 &:= (((12^3) + (4 - (5 + 6))) \times (7 \times -(8 - 9))) & 12047 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 \times -(6 - ((54 \times 32) - 1)))) \\
12048 &:= (12 + ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times -(6 + (78 \times 9)))) & 12048 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times (6 \times -(5 - (4^{3+2-1})))) \\
12049 &:= (((12^3) \times -(4 - (5 + 6))) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & 12049 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((76 \times 5) - 4) \times -(32 \times 1))) \\
12050 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -(((4^5) \times -6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 12050 &:= ((9 - ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5)) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
12051 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) \times -(4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))))) + 9) & 12051 &:= (9 \times ((8 \times 7) - ((6 - 5) - (4 \times 321)))) \\
12052 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times (3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 + 8))) - 9) & 12052 &:= (987 + ((6 \times -(5 - (43^2))) + 1)) \\
12053 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (345 + 6)) + 7) \times -(8 + 9))) & 12053 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7^{(6-5)^4}) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
12054 &:= (((1 + (((2^{3+4}) - (5^6)) \times 7)) - 8) / -9) & 12054 &:= (9 + ((8 + (7^{(6-5)^4})) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
12055 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 12055 &:= (9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6 - (54 \times 32)))) \times -1)) \\
12056 &:= ((1 - 23) \times (4 \times -((5 \times (6 + 7)) + (8 \times 9)))) & 12056 &:= (9 + ((8 \times ((765 - (4 \times 3)) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
12057 &:= (1 \times -((((2 \times 3)^4) + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times -8) - 9) & 12057 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((765 - (4 \times 3)) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
12058 &:= (1 - (((((2 \times 3)^4) + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times -8) - 9)) & 12058 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((765 - (4 \times 3)) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
12059 &:= (((((12^3) + (4 - (5 - 6))) \times 7) + (8 \times -9)) & 12059 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -6) - (5 - 4)) \times (32 - 1)) \\
12060 &:= (((1 + 2) - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 \times 9))) & 12060 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (6 \times -(5 \times (4 + (3 \times 21))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
12061 &:= (((12^3) - (4 - (5 - 6))) \times (7 \times -(8 - 9))) & 12061 &:= (98 + (7 \times -(6 - (5 \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))))) \\
12062 &:= (((1 + ((2 + 34) \times (5 \times 67))) - 8) + 9) & 12062 &:= (9 - (8 + (7 \times (6 - ((54 \times 32) + 1)))))) \\
12063 &:= (((((12^3) - (4 + (5 + 6))) \times 7) - (8 \times -9)) & 12063 &:= (9876 - (((5 + 4)^3) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
12064 &:= ((1 - (23 + 4)) \times ((56 \times -7) - (8 \times 9))) & 12064 &:= (9 + (8 - (7 \times (6 - ((54 \times 32) - 1)))))) \\
12065 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 34) \times 5)) \times 67) - (8 \times -9)) & 12065 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((765 - (4 \times 3)) \times 2) + 1))) \\
12066 &:= (((((12^3) - ((4 - 5) \times 6)) \times 7) + (8 \times -9)) & 12066 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (765 - (4 \times 3)))) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
12067 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^4) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 + (8 + 9))))))) & 12067 &:= ((((-9 + 876) - 5) \times ((4 + 3) \times 2)) - 1) \\
12068 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^4) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 + (8 + 9))))))) & 12068 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 76) - 5) \times -(4 \times (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\
12069 &:= (((((12^3) - 4) \times -((5 - 6) \times 7)) - (8 - 9)) & 12069 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times -(6 - ((5 - 43) \times 21)))) \\
12070 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times ((3^4) \times 5)) - 6) \times (7 + 8))) + 9) & 12070 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 76) - 5) \times -(4 \times (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\
12071 &:= (1 \times ((23^{4+5-6}) - (7 + 89))) & 12071 &:= (9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 - (54 \times 32)))) \times -1)) \\
12072 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3^4) \times -(5 + (6 \times (7 + (8 + 9)))))) & 12072 &:= (9 - ((8 \times (7 + 6)) - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
12073 &:= (((((12^3) - (4 - (5 + 6))) \times 7) + (8 \times -9)) & 12073 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (7 - ((6^5) + 4321))) \\
12074 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times ((4^{5-6+7}) - (8 \times 9)))))) & 12074 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times 6) + 5) \times -((4 \times 32) - 1)) \\
12075 &:= (1 + (2 + (3 \times ((4^{5-6+7}) - (8 \times 9)))))) & 12075 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times (((54/3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
12076 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 + (4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))))) & 12076 &:= (-98 + (7 + (((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3))^{2+1}))) \\
12077 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 34) \times -(5 \times 67)) - (8 + 9))) & 12077 &:= (98 - (((7 \times 6) - (5 + 4))^3) / -(2 + 1)) \\
12078 &:= ((1 - 2) + (3 - (4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))))) & 12078 &:= (((98 + 7) - 6) \times -(5 - ((4 \times 32) - 1))) \\
12079 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(3 - (4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))))) & 12079 &:= (9 - (((87 - 6) \times -(5 + ((4 \times 3)^2))) - 1)) \\
12080 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) \times -(4^5)) - ((6^7)/(8 \times 9))) & 12080 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 76) + 5)) \times -(4 \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
12081 &:= ((1 + ((2^3) \times (4^5))) - ((6^7) / -(8 \times 9))) & 12081 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(76 + (5 \times (4 - 32)))))) \\
12082 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -3) + (4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))))) & 12082 &:= ((98 + 765) \times ((4 + 3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
12083 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -3) + (4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))))) & 12083 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times 6) \times (5^4))) / -(3^{2+1})) \\
12084 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3^4) - 5) \times -((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9))) & 12084 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(76 \times -((54 \times 3) - (2 + 1)))) \\
12085 &:= (12 - (3 + (4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))))) & 12085 &:= (9 - (8 - (76 \times ((54 \times 3) - (2 + 1)))))) \\
12086 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) - (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 12086 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times -6) + (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
12087 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) - (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 12087 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((7 + 6) \times -54) - (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
12088 &:= (((((12^3) \times -(4 - (5 + 6))) - 7) + (8 - 9)) & 12088 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times (6^{(5+4)/3})) - 2)) + 1)) \\
12089 &:= (((((12^3) \times -(4 - (5 + 6))) - 7) \times -(8 - 9)) & 12089 &:= (9 + (8 \times ((76 \times (5 \times 4)) - ((3^2) + 1)))) \\
12090 &:= (((((12^3) \times -(4 - (5 + 6))) - 7) - (8 - 9)) & 12090 &:= (9 + ((8 \times ((7 \times (6^{(5+4)/3})) - 2)) + 1)) \\
12091 &:= (((1 + 2) - (((3^4) - (5^6)) \times 7) - 8) / 9) & 12091 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(76 - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
12092 &:= ((((((12^3) - ((4 + 5) - 6)) \times 7) + 8) + 9) & 12092 &:= ((9 - 8) - (76 - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
12093 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((34 - 5) \times -(67 + (8 \times 9))) & 12093 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) \times (6^5)) / (4 \times 3))) / -(2 + 1)) \\
12094 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) & 12094 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 765)) + (4^3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
12095 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) & 12095 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) \times (6^5)) / 4)) / (3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
12096 &:= (((12^3) / -(4 + 5)) \times -((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9)) & 12096 &:= (9 + ((8 \times ((76 \times (5 \times 4)) - (3^2))) - 1)) \\
12097 &:= ((-1 + (23^{4+5-6})) - (78 - 9)) & 12097 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) \times (6^5)) / 4)) / -(3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
12098 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times (5 - ((67 - 8) \times 9))) & 12098 &:= (((9 + (87 \times 6)) - 5) \times ((4 \times (3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
12099 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 \times -(((4 \times 5) - (6 \times 78)) \times 9))) & 12099 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) \times (6^5)) / (4 \times 3))) / (2 + 1)) \\
12100 &:= (((((12^3) + ((4 + 5) - 6)) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) & 12100 &:= (-987 - ((6543 \times -2) - 1)) \\
12101 &:= (1 + (2 \times -((3 + 4) + ((5 - 678) \times 9)))) & 12101 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -((6 + 5) + (4 \times 32))) + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
12102 &:= (((12^3) \times -(4 - (5 + 6))) + 7) + (8 - 9) & 12102 &:= (98 - (((7^{(6-5)} \times 4) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
12103 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + (4 \times -(5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 12103 &:= (98 - ((7^{(6-5)} \times 4) \times -(3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
12104 &:= (((12^3) \times -(4 - (5 + 6))) + 7) - (8 - 9) & 12104 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times 4))) \times ((3^2) - 1)) \\
12105 &:= (((12^3) \times -(4 - (5 + 6))) - ((7 - 8) \times 9)) & 12105 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 76) - 5) \times 4)) \times -((3 + 2) \times -1)) \\
12106 &:= (((12^3) \times -(4 - (5 + 6))) - 7) + (8 + 9) & 12106 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 \times -((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 32)) - 1))) \\
12107 &:= (((((12^3) + 4) \times -((5 - 6) \times 7)) - 8) - 9) & 12107 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) \times -6^{(5+4)/3})) - (2 \times 1)) \\
12108 &:= (((12 + 3) - (4^5)) \times -((6 + (7 + 8)) - 9)) & 12108 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) \times -6^{(5+4)/3})) - (2 + 1)) \\
12109 &:= (1 \times ((2 - ((3 + 4) \times ((5^6) - (7 \times 8)))) / -9)) & 12109 &:= (9 - (((87 + ((65 + 4)/3))^2) \times -1)) \\
12110 &:= (1 + ((2 - ((3 + 4) \times ((5^6) - (7 \times 8)))) / -9)) & 12110 &:= ((9 + ((87 + ((65 + 4)/3))^2)) + 1) \\
12111 &:= ((1 - (2 - 34)) \times -(((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times -8) + 9)) & 12111 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times ((4 \times -3) - 21)) \\
12112 &:= ((1 - 2) - (3 - (4 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 12112 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times -(6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 32))) + 1)) \\
12113 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (3 - (4 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 12113 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 \times ((6^5) \times 4)) / - (3 - 21))) \\
12114 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 \times -4) + (5 \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 12114 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (6 - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
12115 &:= (1 \times ((2 - 3) + (4 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 12115 &:= ((-9 \times 876) - (((5^4) \times -32) + 1)) \\
12116 &:= (1 + ((2 - 3) + (4 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 12116 &:= ((-9 \times 876) - ((5^4) \times -(32 \times 1))) \\
12117 &:= (((12^3) + ((4 + 5) - 6)) \times -7) \times (8 - 9) & 12117 &:= (98 + (7 \times -((6 + 5) - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
12118 &:= ((1 - 2) + (3 + (4 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 12118 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) - (32 + 1)) \\
12119 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(3 + (4 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 12119 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) + (32 \times -1)) \\
12120 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) - (8 \times 9)) & 12120 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((65 + 4)/3)^{2+1})) \\
12121 &:= (((((12^3) - ((4 - 5) \times 6)) \times 7) - 8) - 9) & 12121 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 \times -(6 + ((5 + 43) \times 2))) + 1)) \\
12122 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 12122 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 765) - (4^3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
12123 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 12123 &:= (9 \times (((8 \times ((76 \times 5) - 43))/2) - 1)) \\
12124 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -3 - (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 12124 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (76 \times 5))) \times ((4 \times 3) / - (2 + 1))) \\
12125 &:= (1 + (2 \times -3 - (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 12125 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 \times -6) + (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
12126 &:= ((1 - ((23 - 4) \times 5)) \times (6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9)) & 12126 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6 + (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
12127 &:= (1 \times (((((2 - 34) + (5^6)) \times 7) - 8) / 9)) & 12127 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times -(6 - (54 \times 32))) + 1)) \\
12128 &:= (((12^3) - (4 - (5 + 6))) \times 7) - (8 + 9) & 12128 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((76 \times (5 \times 4)) - (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\
12129 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3^4) + 5) \times -(6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) & 12129 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((765 - (4 + 3)) \times 2) - 1))) \\
12130 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -(((4^5) \times -6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 12130 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((76 \times (5 \times 4)) - (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\
12131 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) + (7 \times 8))) + 9)) & 12131 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -7 \times -((6 + (54 \times 32)) - 1)) \\
12132 &:= (1 - ((2 \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) + (7 \times 8))) + 9)) & 12132 &:= (((9 - 87) - ((6^5)/4)) \times (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
12133 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -((3 - (4^5)) \times 6)) - (7 \times (8 + 9))) & 12133 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times -(6 - ((54 \times 32) + 1)))) \\
12134 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times 6))) + (7 \times -(8 + 9))) & 12134 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times -4) - 3) + 21) \\
12135 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3^4) \times 5))) \times ((6 \times (7 - 8)) - 9)) & 12135 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 - (65 \times 4)) \times (3 \times 2)))) \times -1) \\
12136 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) \times 6) - 78)))) + 9) & 12136 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(76 \times (5 \times 4))) + (32 + 1))) \\
12137 &:= (((((12^3) - ((4 - 5) \times 6)) \times 7) + 8) - 9) & 12137 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) + (32 \times -1)) \\
12138 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 - 5)) - 6) \times -(7 \times -(8 - 9)) & 12138 &:= ((9 + (87 + 6)) \times ((5 \times (4 \times (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\
12139 &:= (((((12^3) - ((4 - 5) \times 6)) \times 7) - 8) + 9) & 12139 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times (6 + (54 \times 32)))) \times -1)) \\
12140 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -(4 \times (((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) & 12140 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times (5 + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))) \\
12141 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) \times -(4 \times (((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) & 12141 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (76 + 5))) \times ((4 \times -(3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
12142 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((34 \times 5) + 6) \times (78 - 9)))) & 12142 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 7) \times 6) + 5) \times (4^3)) \times (2 \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 12143 &:= (((1+2)^3) - (4 \times -(5 + (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 12144 &:= (((((12^3) - (4 - (5 + 6))) \times 7) + (8 - 9)) \\
 12145 &:= ((1 - (((2 + (3 + 4)) - (5^6)) \times 7) + 8)) / 9 \\
 12146 &:= (((((12^3) - (4 - (5 + 6))) \times 7) - (8 - 9)) \\
 12147 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((((3 \times (4^5)) / 6) - 7) \times -8) - 9)) \\
 12148 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6)))) + ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
 12149 &:= (1 + (((23 + ((4 - (5^6)) \times 7)) - 8) / -9)) \\
 12150 &:= (12 + ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times -(6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 12151 &:= (1 \times -(((2^{3+4}) \times -(5 + (6 \times (7 + 8)))) + 9)) \\
 12152 &:= (1 - (((2^{3+4}) \times -(5 + (6 \times (7 + 8)))) + 9)) \\
 12153 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 + ((4^5) + (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 12154 &:= (1 \times -((((23 - 4) + ((5^6) \times 7)) - 8) / -9)) \\
 12155 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 + 4) \times ((5^6) + (7 - 8))) / -9)) \\
 12156 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(3 - (4^5) \times 6)) - (7 + 89))) \\
 12157 &:= (1 \times ((23^{4+5-6}) + (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\
 12158 &:= (((((1+2)^3) + (((4 + (5^6)) \times 7) - 8)) / 9) \\
 12159 &:= ((1 + (23^{4+5-6})) + ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
 12160 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times 6)))) + ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
 12161 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 + (((4 + (5^6)) \times 7) - 8) / 9)) \\
 12162 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (3 \times -(4 + (5 \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) \\
 12163 &:= (((-1 + (23 \times (4 + 5))) \times (67 - 8)) + 9) \\
 12164 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 12165 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 12166 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((((3 \times 4) + (5^6)) \times 7) + 8) / -9)) \\
 12167 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times ((5 \times -((6 + 7) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
 12168 &:= (((1 + 2) - (3^4)) \times (((5 + 6) \times -(7 + 8)) + 9)) \\
 12169 &:= (1 \times -(((2^{3+4}) \times -(5 + (6 \times (7 + 8)))) - 9)) \\
 12170 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 + (4 \times 5))^{6 \times (7-8)+9})) \\
 12171 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 + 4) + (5 \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) \\
 12172 &:= (1 - (((2 + (3 \times (45 \times 6))) \times -(7 + 8)) + 9)) \\
 12173 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times 6)) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 12174 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times 6)) + 7)) + (8 \times -9)) \\
 12175 &:= (12 - (((((3 \times 4) + (5^6)) \times 7) + 8) / -9)) \\
 12176 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times 6)))) + (7 \times -(8 + 9)) \\
 12177 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -((4 - 5) + ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
 12178 &:= (1 \times (23 + (((4 + (5^6)) \times 7) - 8) / 9)) \\
 12179 &:= (12 + ((3 + (4 \times 5))^{6 \times (7-8)+9})) \\
 12180 &:= (((1 - 2) - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 12181 &:= (1 + (2 \times -((3 + (4 + 5)) - (678 \times 9)))) \\
 12182 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (((4 + (5^6)) \times 7) - 8) / -9)) \\
 12183 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -((3 - (4^5)) \times 6)) - (78 - 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 12143 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((76 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
 12144 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times -((((6 + (5 + 4)) \times 3)^2) - 1)) \\
 12145 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) - 3) - 21) \\
 12146 &:= (9 + ((8 \times ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times (43 - 2))) + 1)) \\
 12147 &:= ((9 - ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 + 4)^3))) / - (2 + 1)) \\
 12148 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((76 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
 12149 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times (654 - 3)))) / - (2 + 1)) \\
 12150 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (((6 + (5 + 4)) \times 3)^2) \times -1)) \\
 12151 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times (3 / - (2 + 1))) \\
 12152 &:= (((9 - 8) - (76 \times (5 \times 4))) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
 12153 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 + 4)^3))) / (2 + 1)) \\
 12154 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + 6) - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 12155 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) - (6 - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 12156 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times -((((6 + (5 + 4)) \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\
 12157 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4))) + (3 \times 2))) \times -1) \\
 12158 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) - ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
 12159 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) - ((3^2) + 1)) \\
 12160 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) + (3 \times - (2 + 1))) \\
 12161 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) - ((3^2) - 1)) \\
 12162 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - 6) + (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}) \\
 12163 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) + (3 \times - (2 \times 1))) \\
 12164 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) - 3) + (2 \times -1)) \\
 12165 &:= (9 - ((8 \times - (76 \times (5 \times 4))) + ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\
 12166 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 - 6) - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 12167 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times ((4 \times (3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
 12168 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 - 6) \times -(((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 12169 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) - (6 - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 12170 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) - (3 / - (2 + 1))) \\
 12171 &:= ((9 + ((8 - ((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) \times 3)) / (2 \times -1)) \\
 12172 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) - (3 \times - (2 - 1))) \\
 12173 &:= ((9 - 8) \times - (7 \times -((6 + 5) + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))) \\
 12174 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 \times -((6 + 5) + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))) \\
 12175 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) - (3 \times - (2 \times 1))) \\
 12176 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) - ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
 12177 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) + ((3^2) - 1)) \\
 12178 &:= ((9 + (((8 + 7) \times 6) + 5) \times (4^3))) \times - (2 \times -1)) \\
 12179 &:= (((9 + 8) - ((7 + 6) \times ((5^4) \times 3))) / (2 \times -1)) \\
 12180 &:= ((9 - ((8 - ((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) \times 3)) / - (2 \times -1)) \\
 12181 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) + (6 + (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 12182 &:= (9 - (((8 - 7) \times -6) - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 12183 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 - 6)) + (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1})))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
12184 &:= (((12^3) + (4 + (5 + 6))) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) \\
12185 &:= (1 - (((23^4) / -((5 \times 6) - 7)) - (8 + 9))) \\
12186 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) - 6)))) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)) \\
12187 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -((3 - (4^5)) \times 6)) + (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
12188 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times 6)) - 7)) + (8 \times -9)) \\
12189 &:= (1 + (2 \times - (3 - (((4^5) \times 6) - ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
12190 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times 6))) + ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
12191 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3 + ((4^5) \times 6)) - 7)) + 89)) \\
12192 &:= ((1 + 23) \times - (4 - (((5 \times 6) / (7 + 8))^9))) \\
12193 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times 456) + (7 \times -(8 + 9)) \\
12194 &:= (((12^3) + ((4 \times 5) - 6)) \times (7 \times -(8 - 9))) \\
12195 &:= ((12 - ((3 + 4) \times ((5^6) + (7 \times 8)))) / -9) \\
12196 &:= (((1 + 2) - ((3 + 4) \times ((5^6) + (7 \times 8)))) / -9) \\
12197 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) \times 6) - 7)))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
12198 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 \times (4^{5-6+7})) - 89))) \\
12199 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times 6)))) - (7 + 89)) \\
12200 &:= (((12^3) + (4 + (5 + 6))) \times 7) + (8 - 9)) \\
12201 &:= (((12^3) + (4 + (5 + 6))) \times -7) \times (8 - 9)) \\
12202 &:= (((12^3) + (4 + (5 + 6))) \times 7) - (8 - 9)) \\
12203 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times - (3 - ((4^5) \times 6))) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
12204 &:= (1 + ((2 \times - (3 - ((4^5) \times 6))) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
12205 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3 + (4^5)) \times 6)) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
12206 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times 6))) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
12207 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3 + 4) - 5) \times (678 \times 9)))) \\
12208 &:= (((1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times 6)))) - 78) - 9) \\
12209 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 + 4) - 5) + (678 \times 9))) \\
12210 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3 - (4^5))) + 6)) \times -((7 + 8) - 9)) \\
12211 &:= (1 \times - (2 - ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times ((67 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
12212 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times ((67 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
12213 &:= ((1 + 2) \times - (3 \times -((4 \times (5 \times 67)) + (8 + 9)))) \\
12214 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6))) + 78)) + 9) \\
12215 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times - (3 + ((4^5) \times 6))) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
12216 &:= (1 - ((2 \times - (3 + ((4^5) \times 6))) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
12217 &:= (((1 + 2) + (((3^4) + (5^6)) \times 7) + 8)) / 9 \\
12218 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6))) + (7 \times 8))) - 9) \\
12219 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3 \times (4^{5-6+7}))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
12220 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) \times -((4 - 56) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
12221 &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times -((4 - 56) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
12222 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3 - (4^5))) + 6)) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)) \\
12223 &:= ((1 - (((2 + 3)^4) + (((5^6) \times 7) + 8))) / -9) \\
12224 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times - (3 - (((4^5) \times 6) + 7))) - (8 \times 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
12184 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 - 6)) - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
12185 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 - 6) + (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
12186 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((7 \times 65) + 4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
12187 &:= (((9 - 8) - ((7 + 6) \times ((5^4) \times 3))) / (2 \times -1)) \\
12188 &:= (((9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) \times ((5^4) \times 3))) / - (2 \times -1)) \\
12189 &:= (98 - (76 - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
12190 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times ((6 - ((5 \times (4 + 3))^2)) \times -1)) \\
12191 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + (((65 + 4) / 3)^{2+1}))) \\
12192 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times 6) - 5)) \times (4 \times -(3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
12193 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -(6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 32))) + 1)) \\
12194 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((76 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
12195 &:= ((9 - ((8 + ((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) \times 3))) / (2 \times -1)) \\
12196 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) + (3^{2+1})) \\
12197 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) + (6 + (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
12198 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 - (65 \times 4)))) \times -(3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
12199 &:= ((9 + ((87 / - (6 - (5 + 4)))^3)) / - (2 \times -1)) \\
12200 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + (6 \times 5)))) \times -(4 \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
12201 &:= (98 - (7 \times -((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 32)) + 1))) \\
12202 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) + (32 + 1)) \\
12203 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 654) - 3))) / (2 + 1)) \\
12204 &:= ((987 + (6 \times 5)) \times -(4 \times -(3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
12205 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 654))) / (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
12206 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (((7 + 6) - (((5 + 4)^3) + 2)) \times -1)) \\
12207 &:= (((98 - 7) - (65 \times (4^3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
12208 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((76 \times (5 \times 4)) + (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\
12209 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -6) - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
12210 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -6) - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
12211 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 654))) / - (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
12212 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + 4)) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
12213 &:= ((9 + (87 \times 6)) \times -(5 - (4 + (3 + 21)))) \\
12214 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 765) - 4)) \times -(3 - (2 - 1))) \\
12215 &:= ((9 - ((8 - 76) \times 5)) \times -((4 \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\
12216 &:= ((9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times (5 - ((4^{3+2}) - 1))) \\
12217 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times (6 + (5 \times 43))) - 21))) \\
12218 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 654)) + 3) / - (2 + 1))) \\
12219 &:= (987 - (6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) - (2 + 1)))) \\
12220 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(65 \times ((4 + 3) - (2 + 1)))) \\
12221 &:= (9 - ((8 \times ((76 - 5) \times 43)) / - (2 \times 1))) \\
12222 &:= ((98 - (7 - 6)) \times -(((5 + 4) - 3) \times -21)) \\
12223 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times -(5 + ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
12224 &:= (987 - ((6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) - 2)) + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
12225 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -(3 - ((4^5) \times 6) + 7))) - (8 \times 9)) \\
12226 &:= (((1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times 6)))) - 78) + 9) \\
12227 &:= (((12^3) - ((4 - 5) \times 6) \times 7) + 89) \\
12228 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 - ((4^{5-6+7}) - (8 + 9)))) \\
12229 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times 6))) + (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
12230 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) - ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
12231 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) - ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
12232 &:= (1 \times -((2 + ((3^4) + 5)) \times -(67 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
12233 &:= (((1 + (23^{4+5-6})) - 7) - (8 \times -9)) \\
12234 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 + (8 + 9))))) \\
12235 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(3 - ((4^5) \times 6))) - ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
12236 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6)))) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
12237 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) + 7))) \times (8 - 9)) \\
12238 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times 6))) - (78 + 9)) \\
12239 &:= (1 \times -(((23^4) / -((5 \times 6) - 7)) - (8 \times 9))) \\
12240 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\
12241 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) - (7 - 8))) - 9)) \\
12242 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -(((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) - (7 - 8))) - 9)) \\
12243 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((((3^4) + 5) \times 6) - 7) \times -8) - 9) \\
12244 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times 6))) + ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
12245 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) + 7)) + (8 - 9)) \\
12246 &:= (((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times 6))) - 7) + (8 \times -9)) \\
12247 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times 6))) - ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
12248 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times 6)))) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
12249 &:= (1 + ((2^3) + (((4^5) + (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
12250 &:= ((1 + ((23 \times 4) + 5)) \times (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
12251 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times (3 - (((4^5) \times 6) - 7))) + (8 + 9))) \\
12252 &:= (1 - ((2 \times (3 - (((4^5) \times 6) - 7))) + (8 + 9))) \\
12253 &:= (1 \times -(23 - (4 \times ((5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\
12254 &:= (1 - (23 - (4 \times ((5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\
12255 &:= ((1 + (2^{3 \times 4 - 5})) \times -(((6 + 7) \times -8) + 9)) \\
12256 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times 6))) - (78 - 9)) \\
12257 &:= (1 \times -(((23 \times 4) + (5 + 6)) \times -(7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
12258 &:= (((1 + (2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times 6))) - 7) \times (8 - 9)) \\
12259 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) - 7)) + (8 - 9)) \\
12260 &:= (((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times 6))) - (7 \times 8)) - 9) \\
12261 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) - 7)) - (8 - 9)) \\
12262 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times 6))) - ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
12263 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3 + ((4^5) \times 6) - 7)) + (8 + 9))) \\
12264 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -(((4^{5-6+7}) - 8)) / -9) \\
12265 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) - 7)) + (8 - 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
12225 &:= (987 - (6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) - (2 \times 1)))) \\
12226 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times -6) - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
12227 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (76 \times 5))) \times -4) + (32 - 1)) \\
12228 &:= ((9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times -((5 - (4^{3+2})) \times -1)) \\
12229 &:= (98 - (7 \times -((6 + (54 \times 32)) - 1))) \\
12230 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 765) + 4)) \times -(3 - (2 - 1))) \\
12231 &:= (987 + (6 \times (((5^4) \times 3) - (2 - 1)))) \\
12232 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) - (3 \times -21)) \\
12233 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(7 + (((6 - 54) \times 32) + 1)))) \\
12234 &:= (987 - ((6 \times -((5^4) \times 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\
12235 &:= (987 - ((6 \times -((5^4) \times 3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
12236 &:= (987 - ((6 \times -((5^4) \times 3)) + (2 - 1))) \\
12237 &:= (((9 + 8) - (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
12238 &:= (987 - ((6 \times -((5^4) \times 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
12239 &:= (987 - ((6 \times -((5^4) \times 3)) - (2 \times 1))) \\
12240 &:= ((9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times (5 - ((4^{3+2}) + 1))) \\
12241 &:= ((9 - 8) - (765 \times -(4 \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
12242 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (765 - (4 - 3)))) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
12243 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (76 + (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
12244 &:= ((9 - 8) + (76 + (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
12245 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 765) + (4 + 3)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
12246 &:= (987 - (((6 \times (5^4)) + 3) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
12247 &:= ((9 + ((8 - 76) \times 5)) \times ((4 \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
12248 &:= (987 - ((6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) + 2)) + 1)) \\
12249 &:= (987 - (6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
12250 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 \times 6) + 5)) \times -((4 \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\
12251 &:= (987 - ((6 + 5) \times -(4^{3+2} \times 1))) \\
12252 &:= ((98 - 7) - (6 - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
12253 &:= ((9 + (((8 - (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times 3) + 2)) \times -1) \\
12254 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 + 6)) \times (5 - (4^3)))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
12255 &:= (987 - (6 \times -(((5^4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
12256 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times -(4 + (32 + 1)))) \\
12257 &:= ((9 + 87) - (6 - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
12258 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) + 1) \\
12259 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2 \times 1))) \\
12260 &:= ((9 + ((8 - 7)^6)) \times (((5 \times (4 + 3))^2) + 1)) \\
12261 &:= (9 - ((8 \times ((765 \times 4) + 3)) / - (2 \times 1))) \\
12262 &:= (987 - ((6 + 5) \times -((4^{3+2}) + 1))) \\
12263 &:= ((9 + 87) + (((65 + 4) / 3)^{2+1})) \\
12264 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times (4 \times -(3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
12265 &:= (98 - ((7 - 6) \times -(((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1})))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 12266 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) - 7)) + (8 - 9)) \\
 12267 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) + 7))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
 12268 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6) - 7))) + (8 - 9)) \\
 12269 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6) - 7))) \times -(8 - 9)) \\
 12270 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - 5)) \times -((6 \times (7 - 8)) + 9)) \\
 12271 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times 6)))) - (7 + (8 + 9))) \\
 12272 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) + (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\
 12273 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6)))) + (7 - (8 + 9))) \\
 12274 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6)))) + ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
 12275 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6)))) - (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
 12276 &:= (((1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - 5) \times ((6 \times (7 - 8)) + 9)) \\
 12277 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times 6)) - ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 12278 &:= (((1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) + (5^6)) \times 7)) - 8)/9) \\
 12279 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 + ((4^5) \times 6)) - (7 - (8 - 9)))) \\
 12280 &:= (1 - (((2 - 34) \times ((56 \times 7) - 8)) + 9)) \\
 12281 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3 + ((4^5) \times 6)) - 7)) + (8 - 9))) \\
 12282 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -((3 + ((4^5) \times 6)) - 7)) + (8 - 9))) \\
 12283 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) - 7)) + (8 + 9))) \\
 12284 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -(((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) - 7)) + (8 + 9))) \\
 12285 &:= (((1 + 2) - (3 \times (4^{5-6+7}))) \times (8 - 9)) \\
 12286 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times 6)))) + ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
 12287 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times 6)))) - (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
 12288 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times 6)))) - (7 \times -(8 - 9))) \\
 12289 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6)))) + ((7 + 8) - 9)) \\
 12290 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6)))) + (7 \times -(8 - 9))) \\
 12291 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6)))) + (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
 12292 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6)))) - ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
 12293 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) - 7)) + (8 + 9))) \\
 12294 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 \times -((4^{5-6+7}) - (8 - 9)))) \\
 12295 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -((3 - ((4^5) \times 6) + 7))) + (8 - 9))) \\
 12296 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + (((5^6) \times 7) - 8)))/9) \\
 12297 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 + (4^{5-6+7})) \times (8 - 9))) \\
 12298 &:= ((1 - 23) \times ((4 - 5) - ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
 12299 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times 6)) - ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 12300 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times 6))) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
 12301 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times 6))) - (7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\
 12302 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times 6)))) + (7 \times -(8 - 9))) \\
 12303 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times 6)))) + (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
 12304 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times 6)))) - ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
 12305 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times 6)))) - (7 - (8 + 9))) \\
 12306 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + 5)) \times ((6 \times (7 - 8)) + 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 12266 &:= (98 + ((7 - 6) + (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 12267 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5)) + 4) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\
 12268 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 76) + 5) \times (4 \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 12269 &:= ((9 + 87) + (6 + (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 12270 &:= ((9 - (87 \times (6 - (5 \times 4)))) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\
 12271 &:= (9 + (((8 - (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times -3) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 12272 &:= (98 + (7 + (((65 + 4)/3)^{2+1}))) \\
 12273 &:= (9 - (876 \times -((5 \times (4 + 3)) - 21))) \\
 12274 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 765) + (4 \times 3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
 12275 &:= (9 + (((8 - (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times -3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 12276 &:= ((9 - ((87 - 6) \times 5)) \times (((4^3)/ -2) + 1)) \\
 12277 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(765 - 43)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 12278 &:= ((98 + 7) + (6 + (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 12279 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((((7 + 6) - 5)^4) - 3) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 12280 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((((7 + 6) - 5)^4) - 3) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
 12281 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(76 + (54 \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
 12282 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(76 + (((5 + 4)^3) \times 2))) - 1)) \\
 12283 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (65 \times 4)) - (3 \times -21)) \\
 12284 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) \times ((4 \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
 12285 &:= (((9 - 8) - (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
 12286 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times -3) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 12287 &:= (9 + ((8 - (((((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times 3) - 2)) \times -1)) \\
 12288 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 - (5 - (4 + 3)))^{2+1})) \\
 12289 &:= (9 + ((8 - (((76 \times 5) + 4) \times 32)) \times -1)) \\
 12290 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 + 6)) \times (5 - (4^3)))) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
 12291 &:= (9 + ((8 - (((((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times 3) + 2)) \times -1)) \\
 12292 &:= (((9 - 8) + (((((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\
 12293 &:= (-9 + ((8 - ((76 \times (54 \times 3)) - 2)) \times -1)) \\
 12294 &:= (((98 + 7) + ((6^5)/4)) \times -(3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
 12295 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (76 \times 54)) \times 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
 12296 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((((7 + 6) - 5)^4) - 3) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
 12297 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((((7 + 6) - 5)^4) + 3) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 12298 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((((7 + 6) - 5)^4) + 3) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
 12299 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (76 \times 54)) \times 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
 12300 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(6 \times -(5 \times ((43 - 2) \times 1)))) \\
 12301 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 76)) \times (5 \times 4)) + 321) \\
 12302 &:= (((9 + 8) + (((((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times 3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
 12303 &:= (9 - (((8 + (((((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times 3)) - 2) \times -1)) \\
 12304 &:= (((9 + 8) - ((76 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))^2)) \times -1) \\
 12305 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 76) + 5) \times 4)) \times -(3 + 2) \times -1) \\
 12306 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 \times 6) - ((5^4) + 3)) \times -21))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
12307 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) \times 6) + 7))) - (8 - 9))) \\
12308 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) \times 6) + 7))) - (8 - 9))) \\
12309 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) - 7)) - (8 - 9))) \\
12310 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) - 7)) - (8 - 9))) \\
12311 &:= (1 + (2 \times (3 + (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 - (8 - 9))))) \\
12312 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -((4^{5-6+7}) + 8)) / -9 \\
12313 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) \times 6) + 7))) + (8 + 9))) \\
12314 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) \times 6) + 7))) + (8 + 9))) \\
12315 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 - (4 - 5))^6) - ((7 - 8) \times 9))) \\
12316 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times 6))) + ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
12317 &:= (((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times 6))) - 7) + (8 - 9)) \\
12318 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times 6)) + 7)) - (8 \times -9)) \\
12319 &:= (((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times 6))) - 7) - (8 - 9)) \\
12320 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -(4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 - 89))))) \\
12321 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times -(4 \times ((5 \times 67) + 8))) + 9)) \\
12322 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) + 7))) - (8 + 9)) \\
12323 &:= (1 - (2 + (3 \times ((4 - 56) \times (7 + (8 \times 9))))) \\
12324 &:= (12 \times -((34 \times -(5 \times 6)) + (7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\
12325 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times -((5 + 6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
12326 &:= (1 + ((2 \times (3 + (((4^5) \times 6) + 7))) + (8 + 9))) \\
12327 &:= (1 + (2 - (3 \times ((4 - 56) \times (7 + (8 \times 9))))) \\
12328 &:= ((1 - (2 \times 34)) \times (5 - ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9))) \\
12329 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3) \times -(4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\
12330 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6)))) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
12331 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3 + (4^5)) \times 6)) + (7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\
12332 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times 6)) - 7)) - (8 \times -9)) \\
12333 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times 6))) + (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
12334 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times 6))) - ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
12335 &:= (((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times 6))) - 7) + (8 + 9)) \\
12336 &:= (1 \times -((2 + ((3 \times (4^5)) / 6)) \times -(7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
12337 &:= (1 - ((2 + ((3 \times (4^5)) / 6)) \times -(7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
12338 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) + 7))) + (8 - 9)) \\
12339 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) + 7))) \times -(8 - 9)) \\
12340 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) + 7))) - (8 - 9)) \\
12341 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) \times 6) - 7)))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
12342 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times 6)))) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
12343 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) - (4 \times (((5 \times 67) + 8) \times 9)))) \\
12344 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) - (7 - (8 + 9))))) \\
12345 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) - (7 - (8 + 9))))) \\
12346 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) + (7 + 8)))) - 9) \\
12347 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6))) + (7 - (8 \times 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
12307 &:= (((9 + 8) + (((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times 3) - (2 \times -1)) \\
12308 &:= (((9 + 8) + (((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\
12309 &:= (9 - ((8 - (7 - (6 + 5))) \times -((4^{3+2}) + 1))) \\
12310 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 \times 4))) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
12311 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((76 \times (54 \times 3)) - 2)) \times -1)) \\
12312 &:= (9 + (((8 + (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) - 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
12313 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((76 \times -(54 \times 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
12314 &:= (9 + (8 + (((7 + 6) - 5)^4) + 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
12315 &:= (9 - (8 - ((76 \times (54 \times 3)) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
12316 &:= (9 - (8 - ((76 \times (54 \times 3)) + (2 + 1)))) \\
12317 &:= (9 + (((8 - 76) \times 543) / - (2 + 1))) \\
12318 &:= (((9 - 8) - ((76 \times 54) + 3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
12319 &:= (((9 + (87 + 6)) - 5) \times -((4 \times -32) + 1)) \\
12320 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 - ((5^4) - 3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
12321 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((76 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))^2) - 1)) \\
12322 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((76 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))^2)) \times -1)) \\
12323 &:= (9 - (8 - (((76 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))^2) + 1))) \\
12324 &:= ((9 - (87 \times (6 + 5))) \times (((4 + 3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
12325 &:= ((98 + ((7 \times 6) + 5)) \times -((43 \times -2) + 1)) \\
12326 &:= (((9 + 8) + (((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times 3) + 21) \\
12327 &:= (9 - (((8 + (76 \times (54 \times 3))) - 2) \times -1)) \\
12328 &:= ((9 + ((87 \times 6) + 5)) \times ((4 \times (3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
12329 &:= ((9 + 8) + (76 \times -((5 + 4) \times (3 - 21)))) \\
12330 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times (((6 - ((5^4) - 3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
12331 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (4 - (3 \times 21))) \\
12332 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 765) \times 4)) \times -((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
12333 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((76 \times -(54 \times 3)) - 21)) \\
12334 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (765 + (4 + 3)))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
12335 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 765) + 43) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
12336 &:= ((9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times -((5 + (4^{3+2})) - 1)) \\
12337 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((76 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))^2) - 1)) \\
12338 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((76 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))^2)) \times -1)) \\
12339 &:= (((9 + 8) + (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times -(3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
12340 &:= (((-9876 \times 5) / -4) - 3) + (2 \times -1)) \\
12341 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2) - 1))) \\
12342 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 \times -(((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2) - 1))) \\
12343 &:= (9 + ((876 + 5) \times -((4 + 3) - 21))) \\
12344 &:= ((9 - ((8 + (76 \times 5)) \times 4)) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
12345 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 - (((6 - 54) \times 32) + 1)))) \\
12346 &:= (9 - (((8 + (76 \times 54)) \times -3) - (2 - 1))) \\
12347 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2) + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 12348 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6)))) + ((7 \times 8) + 9)) & 12348 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2)) + 1)) \\
 12349 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times 6))) + (7 + (8 + 9))) & 12349 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times ((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2))) \times -1)) \\
 12350 &:= ((1 - (23 + 4)) \times (5 \times -(((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9))) & 12350 &:= (9 - (8 - ((7 \times ((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2)) + 1))) \\
 12351 &:= (((12^3) + (4 + (5 \times 6))) \times 7) + (8 + 9)) & 12351 &:= (((-9876 \times 5) / -4) - (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
 12352 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3 + ((4^5) \times 6)) - 7)) - (8 \times 9))) & 12352 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 - ((6 - 54) \times 32))) + 1)) \\
 12353 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -((3 + ((4^5) \times 6)) - 7)) - (8 \times 9))) & 12353 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((7 \times 6) + (5 \times (4 - 321)))))) \\
 12354 &:= (1 - (((2 + ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times 67)) \times -8) - 9)) & 12354 &:= ((9 - (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times 4)) \times (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
 12355 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -3) - (4 \times (((5 \times 67) + 8) \times 9)))) & 12355 &:= ((9 - 8) \times - (7 \times -(((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2) + 1))) \\
 12356 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) - (7 \times 8)))) - 9) & 12356 &:= (9 - (8 - (7 \times (((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2) + 1)))) \\
 12357 &:= ((1 + 2) \times - (3 \times -((4 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9))) & 12357 &:= (9 \times -((8 \times -(7 + (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)))) - 21)) \\
 12358 &:= (1 \times - (2 - ((3 \times (4^{5-6+7})) + (8 \times 9)))) & 12358 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times (((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2) - 1)))) \\
 12359 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 \times (4^{5-6+7})) + (8 \times 9)))) & 12359 &:= (9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times - (5 - (4 \times (3 \times 21)))))) \\
 12360 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times 6))) + ((7 \times 8) + 9)) & 12360 &:= ((9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times - (5 + ((4^{3+2}) + 1))) \\
 12361 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times - (3 - ((4^5) \times 6))) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 12361 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (6 - ((54 \times (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\
 12362 &:= (1 + ((2 \times - (3 - ((4^5) \times 6))) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 12362 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((765 + (4 + 3)) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
 12363 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3 \times (4^{5-6+7}))) - (8 \times -9)) & 12363 &:= (9 + (87 \times -(((6 - 54) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
 12364 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) + (7 + 8)))) + 9) & 12364 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times -((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2)) + 1)) \\
 12365 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) \times ((4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8))) + 9))) & 12365 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times ((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2))) \times -1)) \\
 12366 &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8))) + 9))) & 12366 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times -((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2)) - 1)) \\
 12367 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + (4 \times - (5 \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))))) & 12367 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 + (5 \times 43)))))) \times - (2 - 1)) \\
 12368 &:= (1 \times - ((2^3) \times - ((4^5) + (6 \times (78 + 9)))))) & 12368 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times (6 + (5 \times 43))) - 2)) + 1)) \\
 12369 &:= (1 - ((2^3) \times - ((4^5) + (6 \times (78 + 9)))))) & 12369 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((765 + (4 + 3)) \times 2) + 1))) \\
 12370 &:= ((1 + 2) + (((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times - (7 \times 8)) - 9)) & 12370 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times - (6 - (((5^4) - 3) \times 2) - 1))) \\
 12371 &:= (1 + (2 \times - (3 + ((4 - 56) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 12371 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 76)) \times - (5 \times 4)) + (32 - 1)) \\
 12372 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times 6))) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & 12372 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 \times -(((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2) + 1))) \\
 12373 &:= (1 \times - (2 - ((3 + (4 \times ((5 \times 67) + 8))) \times 9))) & 12373 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 76)) \times - (5 \times 4)) + (32 + 1)) \\
 12374 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) - (7 \times 8)))) + 9) & 12374 &:= (((((-98 \times (7 \times 6)) - (5 + 4)) \times -3) - 2) + 1) \\
 12375 &:= ((1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5))) \times - (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 12375 &:= (((98 + 7) - 6) \times - ((5^4) / - ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
 12376 &:= ((1 - 2) - ((3 \times - (4^{5-6+7})) - 89)) & 12376 &:= ((98 - 7) \times (((6 \times 5) + 4) \times ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\
 12377 &:= ((1 - 2) \times ((3 \times - (4^{5-6+7})) - 89)) & 12377 &:= (98 - (((((7 + 6) - 5)^4) - 3) \times - (2 + 1))) \\
 12378 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 + (4 \times ((5 \times 67) + 8))) \times -9)) & 12378 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 765) + (4^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
 12379 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 \times (4^{5-6+7})) + 89))) & 12379 &:= (9 - (((87 + 6) \times - (5 + (4 \times 32))) - 1)) \\
 12380 &:= (1 \times - ((2 \times - (3 + (((4^5) \times 6) + 7))) - (8 \times 9))) & 12380 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times - (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
 12381 &:= (1 - ((2 \times - (3 + (((4^5) \times 6) + 7))) - (8 \times 9))) & 12381 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 76) - (54/3)) \times -21)) \\
 12382 &:= (1 - ((2 \times - (3 + ((4^5) \times 6))) - (78 + 9))) & 12382 &:= (9 - ((8 \times - (7 \times (6 + (5 \times 43)))) + (2 + 1))) \\
 12383 &:= (1 \times (((2 - ((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times 7)) \times 8) - 9)) & 12383 &:= ((98 + (((((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 12384 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3^4) + 5) \times (6 \times (7 - (8 - 9)))))) & 12384 &:= ((98 + (((((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
 12385 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times - (4 - 567)) + (8 - 9)) & 12385 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 + (5 \times 43)))))) \times (2 - 1)) \\
 12386 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times ((5 + 6) \times 7)))) - 89) & 12386 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 \times (6 + (5 \times 43)))) + 2)) - 1) \\
 12387 &:= (1 \times - ((2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times 6)) - ((7 + 8) \times 9))) & 12387 &:= ((98 + (((((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times 3) + 2)) - 1) \\
 12388 &:= (1 \times - (2 \times - (3 + (((4^5) \times 6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) & 12388 &:= ((98 + (((((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times 3) + 2)) \times 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
12389 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) \times 6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))))) \\
12390 &:= (((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times 6))) - 7) - (8 \times -9)) \\
12391 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times ((6 \times 78) - 9)))))) \\
12392 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times ((6 \times 78) - 9)))))) \\
12393 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3^4) - 5))) \times ((6 - (7 + 8)) \times -9)) \\
12394 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3 + 4))^5)) - (6^{7+8-9})) \\
12395 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times ((6 \times 78) - 9)))))) \\
12396 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(3 \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times (78 - 9))))))) \\
12397 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times -((5 + 6) \times -(7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\
12398 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) \times 6) + 7))) - 89)) \\
12399 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) - 7)) - 89)) \\
12400 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times 3^4) - 56) \times -(7 - (8 + 9)))) \\
12401 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - ((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times 7)) \times -8) - 9)) \\
12402 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6)))) - (7 \times -(8 + 9))) \\
12403 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3 + (4^5)) \times 6)) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
12404 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -((3 + (4^5)) \times 6)) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
12405 &:= (((12^3) + (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times 7) - (8 - 9)) \\
12406 &:= (((12^3) + (4 + (5 \times 6))) \times 7) - (8 \times -9)) \\
12407 &:= (((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times 6))) - 7) + 89) \\
12408 &:= (((1 - 2) - (((3^4) + 5) \times 6)) \times -(7 + (8 + 9))) \\
12409 &:= (1 + ((2 - (345 \times 6)) \times -(7 + 8) - 9)) \\
12410 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times 6)) + 78)) + 9) \\
12411 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) + 7))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
12412 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times (3 - (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
12413 &:= (1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
12414 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(((3^4) + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
12415 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\
12416 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\
12417 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) - 78)) + 9)) \\
12418 &:= (1 \times (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
12419 &:= (1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
12420 &:= ((1 - ((2 + (3^4)) \times 5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\
12421 &:= (((12^3) + (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times 7) + 8) + 9) \\
12422 &:= (12 + (34 \times -(5 \times ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
12423 &:= (1 \times (((2^3) - 45) \times -(6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
12424 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((3 + ((4^5) \times 6)) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
12425 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 + ((4^5) \times 6)) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
12426 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) - (78 + 9)))) \\
12427 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) - (78 + 9)))) \\
12428 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) + 7))) + 89) \\
12429 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3^4) \times -5) - (6 \times (7 \times 89))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
12389 &:= ((98 + (((((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times 3) + 2)) + 1) \\
12390 &:= ((98 + 7) \times ((6 \times (5 - (4^3)))/ - (2 + 1))) \\
12391 &:= (9 - (8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 - (3 \times 21))))))) \\
12392 &:= (9 - (((8 \times ((7 + 65) \times 43))/ - 2) + 1)) \\
12393 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times 65) + 4) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
12394 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 \times 65) + 4) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
12395 &:= (98 - (((((7 + 6) - 5)^4) + 3) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
12396 &:= (98 - ((7 + 6) \times -((5^4) + 321))) \\
12397 &:= ((9 - (8 - 76)) \times -((54 \times -3) + (2 - 1))) \\
12398 &:= (((-98 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 43))/ - 2) + 1) \\
12399 &:= ((9 - (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times (4 \times (3 \times 2)))) \times -1) \\
12400 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times (6 + (5 \times 43))) + 2)) + 1)) \\
12401 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (6 + (5 \times 43))) + 2))) \times 1) \\
12402 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (6 + (5 \times 43))) + 2))) + 1) \\
12403 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 + 4)^3))/ - 2) + 1)) \\
12404 &:= (98 + (((7 \times 6) - ((5^4) + 3)) \times -21)) \\
12405 &:= (9 + (8 + (76 \times ((54 \times 3) + (2 - 1)))))) \\
12406 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times (6 + (5 \times 43)))) - 21)) \\
12407 &:= (9 + (8 - (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 - (3 \times 21))))))) \\
12408 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (6 \times -((5 \times 4) + (3 + 21)))) \\
12409 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 \times (43 - (2 + 1)))))) \\
12410 &:= (9 + (8 + (((7 \times 65) + 4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
12411 &:= (9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times -6) - (5 + (4 \times 321)))) \\
12412 &:= (98 - ((76 \times -(54 \times 3)) - (2 \times 1))) \\
12413 &:= (98 - ((76 \times -(54 \times 3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
12414 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times -((6 \times ((5 + (4^3)) \times 2)) - 1))) \\
12415 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 - (65 \times (4 \times (3 \times 2)))))) \times -1) \\
12416 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times -(4 \times (3 \times 2))) + 1)) \\
12417 &:= ((9 + (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times (4 \times (3 \times 2)))) \times 1) \\
12418 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times -(4 \times (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\
12419 &:= ((98 + ((76 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))^2) \times 1) \\
12420 &:= (((9 + 87) - 6) \times -((5 + (4^3)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
12421 &:= (((-9 \times (((8 \times (7 - 65)) + 4) \times 3)) + 2) - 1) \\
12422 &:= (((-98 \times -(7 + (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) - 3) - 21) \\
12423 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((765 + (4 \times 3)) \times 2))) \times -1) \\
12424 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((76 \times (5 \times 4)) + 32)) + 1)) \\
12425 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((76 \times (5 \times 4)) + 32))) \times 1) \\
12426 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4)))) \times (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
12427 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 + 4) \times -32) - 1)) \\
12428 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times 6) \times -((5 + (4^3)) \times 2)) + 1)) \\
12429 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 - 65)) + 4) \times -(3^{2+1})))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
12430 &:= (1 \times ((2+3) \times -(4 + (5 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9))))))) & 12430 &:= (((9+8) - 7) \times (((6 - ((5^4) + 3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
12431 &:= (1 + ((2+3) \times -(4 + (5 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9))))))) & 12431 &:= (98 - ((76 \times -(54 \times 3)) - 21)) \\
12432 &:= (12 \times (((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times (7 - 8)) + 9)) & 12432 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5)) \times (((4+3)^2) - 1)) \\
12433 &:= (1 - ((2 + (345 \times 6)) \times -((7+8) - 9))) & 12433 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6^5))) - 4)) / -((3+2) \times -1)) \\
12434 &:= (12345 - ((6 - 7) \times 89)) & 12434 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7 - (65 \times (4 \times (3 \times 2)))))) + 1)) \\
12435 &:= ((12+3) \times -(4 - ((56 - 7) \times (8+9)))) & 12435 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 - ((6^5) + 4)))) / ((3+2) \times -1)) \\
12436 &:= ((((((12^3) + (45+6)) \times 7) - 8) - 9)) & 12436 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 + (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) - ((3^2) + 1)) \\
12437 &:= (((-12 \times -(3 + (4^5))) + ((6+7) \times 8)) + 9) & 12437 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6)))) - 5) \times -4) + 321) \\
12438 &:= (1 \times ((2 - (((3 \times (4+56)) - 7) \times 8)) \times -9)) & 12438 &:= (9 \times -(((8 \times (76+5)) + 43) \times -2 \times 1)) \\
12439 &:= (1 + ((2 - (((3 \times (4+56)) - 7) \times 8)) \times -9)) & 12439 &:= (98 - (7 \times -(((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2) - 1))) \\
12440 &:= (1 \times -((2+3) \times -(4 \times ((5-6) + (7 \times 89)))))) & 12440 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6^5) + 4) / - (3+2) + 1)) \\
12441 &:= (1 - ((2+3) \times -(4 \times ((5-6) + (7 \times 89)))))) & 12441 &:= ((987 - (6 \times 5)) \times -(((4+3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
12442 &:= 1 - 23 + 4 \times (5^{6+7-8} - 9) & 12442 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((765 + (4 \times 3)) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
12443 &:= (((((12^3) - (4 - 56)) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) & 12443 &:= (((((-98/7) - 6) \times -((5^4) - 3)) + 2) + 1) \\
12444 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times 6))) - (7 \times -(8 + 9))) & 12444 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) - (65 \times (4^3))) \times -2 + 1)) \\
12445 &:= (1 \times ((23 - 4) \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) + 89)))) & 12445 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2) + 1)) \\
12446 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 12446 &:= (98 - (7 \times -((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2 \times 1)) \\
12447 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 \times 4) - (5 + (6 \times 78))) \times -9)) & 12447 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2) - 1)) \\
12448 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) \times 6) + 78)))) + 9) & 12448 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6^5) + 4) / -((3+2) \times 1))) \\
12449 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3^4) \times ((5+6) \times 7)) - 8)) + 9)) & 12449 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -4 - (3 \times 21)) \\
12450 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(((3^4) \times ((5+6) \times 7)) - 8)) + 9)) & 12450 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 - ((5^4) + 3)) \times 2) - 1)) \\
12451 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3^4)) \times -(5 \times (6 + (7 + (8 + 9)))))) & 12451 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + (6^5)))) / - (4 + (3 / (2 + 1)))) \\
12452 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3 + (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) & 12452 &:= ((-9 \times -87) - (((((6^5) + 4) \times 3) / -2) + 1)) \\
12453 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 + (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) & 12453 &:= (98 - (7 \times -(((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2) + 1)) \\
12454 &:= (1 \times (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) & 12454 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 - ((6 + 54) \times 3)))) + 2) \times -1) \\
12455 &:= (1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) & 12455 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((65 \times 4) + ((3+2) \times 1)) \\
12456 &:= (((1 + 2) + (((3^4) + 5) \times 6)) \times (7 + (8 + 9))) & 12456 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6^5) + 4) / - (3+2) - 1)) \\
12457 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3^4) \times ((5+6) \times 7))) + (8 + 9))) & 12457 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6 \times -(5 \times 432)) - 1)) \\
12458 &:= (((1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times ((5+6) \times 7)))) - 8) - 9) & 12458 &:= ((-98 \times -7) + (654 \times -(3 - 21))) \\
12459 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 \times (4 + 56)) - 7) \times -(8 \times 9))) & 12459 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 - (65 \times (4^3))) \times -2 + 1)) \\
12460 &:= ((1 - 2) - (3 - (4 \times ((5^{6+7-8}) - 9)))) & 12460 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 + (6^5))) - 4) / (3+2) - 1)) \\
12461 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (3 - (4 \times ((5^{6+7-8}) - 9)))) & 12461 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6^5) + 4)))) / -((3+2) \times -1)) \\
12462 &:= ((1 + (23 \times 4)) \times ((5 - 6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) & 12462 &:= ((9 + (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times 4)) \times -3 \times -2 \times 1)) \\
12463 &:= (1 \times ((2 - 3) + (4 \times ((5^{6+7-8}) - 9)))) & 12463 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((76 \times -((54 \times 3) + 2)) + 1)) \\
12464 &:= (1 + ((2 - 3) + (4 \times ((5^{6+7-8}) - 9)))) & 12464 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 + 6)) \times (5^4))) \times -((3+2) - 1)) \\
12465 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times -((56 \times -(7 + 8)) + 9)) & 12465 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((76 \times -((54 \times 3) + 2)) - 1)) \\
12466 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) - (4 \times -((5^{6+7-8}) - 9))) & 12466 &:= (9 - (8 - ((76 \times ((54 \times 3) + 2)) + 1))) \\
12467 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3^4) \times ((5+6) \times 7)) - 8)) - 9)) & 12467 &:= ((98 - 7) \times -((6 \times ((5 + 4) - 32)) + 1)) \\
12468 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(((3^4) \times ((5+6) \times 7)) - 8)) - 9)) & 12468 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 65))) + 4) \times -3) - 21) \\
12469 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) + (4 \times ((5^{6+7-8}) - 9)))) & 12469 &:= ((((-98/7) - 6) \times -5^4) - (32 - 1)) \\
12470 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -3) - (4 \times ((5^{6+7-8}) - 9)))) & 12470 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (((5 + (4 \times 3))^2) + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
12471 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -3) - (4 \times ((5^{6+7-8}) - 9)))) \\
12472 &:= (1 + (((2 - (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times 6))) \times -78) - 9)) \\
12473 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3^4) \times ((5 + 6) \times 7))) - (8 - 9))) \\
12474 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times ((3^4) \times ((5 + 6) \times 7))) + 8)) - 9) \\
12475 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3^4) \times ((5 + 6) \times 7))) + (8 - 9))) \\
12476 &:= (((1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times ((5 + 6) \times 7)))) - 8) + 9) \\
12477 &:= (1 - (2 - (34 \times (((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9)))) \\
12478 &:= (((-12 \times -(3 + ((4^5) + 6))) - 7) + 89) \\
12479 &:= (12 + (3 + (4 \times ((5^{6+7-8}) - 9)))) \\
12480 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\
12481 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times (5 + 6)))) \times (7 \times -(8 - 9))) \\
12482 &:= (1 \times -((2 - (3 \times (4 - 56))) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
12483 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((((3 \times (4^5))/6) + 7) \times -8) - 9) \\
12484 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -((3^4) \times (5 - (6 - 78)))) - 9)) \\
12485 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times -3) + (4 \times (5^{6+7-8}))) - 9)) \\
12486 &:= (1 + (((2 \times -3) + (4 \times (5^{6+7-8}))) - 9)) \\
12487 &:= ((1 - 23) - ((4 \times -(5^{6+7-8})) - 9)) \\
12488 &:= ((1 + 23) - (4 \times -(5^{6+7-8}) - 9)) \\
12489 &:= (1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) - (7 - 89)))) \\
12490 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
12491 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 - ((4 \times (5^{6+7-8})) - 9))) \\
12492 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times ((3^4) \times ((5 + 6) \times 7))) + 8)) + 9) \\
12493 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3 \times 4) \times (5^6))/(7 + 8))) - 9) \\
12494 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3 \times 4) \times (5^6))/(7 + 8))) - 9) \\
12495 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((34 \times (((5 \times 6) - 7) \times 8)) - 9))) \\
12496 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) + (4 \times (5^{6+7-8}))) - 9)) \\
12497 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 + (4 \times (5^{6+7-8}))) - 9)) \\
12498 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 - 4) - ((5 - (6 \times 78)) \times 9)) \\
12499 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) + ((4 \times (5^{6+7-8})) - 9))) \\
12500 &:= (1 + ((2^3) + ((4 \times (5^{6+7-8})) - 9))) \\
12501 &:= (1 + (((2 \times 3) + 4^5) / -((6 - 78) / 9))) \\
12502 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -3) + (4 \times ((56 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\
12503 &:= (12 - (((3 \times 4) \times (5^6)) / - (7 + 8) + 9)) \\
12504 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times 5)) \times -((6 + 7) - (8 + 9))) \\
12505 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times 3) - (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times -8) + 9) \\
12506 &:= (1 \times (2 \times (3 - ((4 \times (5^6)) / (7 - (8 + 9))))) \\
12507 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 \times -((4^{5-6+7}) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
12508 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 \times 4) \times (5^6)) / (7 + 8) + 9))) \\
12509 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 - ((4 \times (5^{6+7-8})) + 9))) \\
12510 &:= ((12 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\
12511 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3 \times 4) + (5 + 678)) \times 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
12471 &:= (9 - ((87 + 6) \times -(5 + ((4 \times 32) + 1)))) \\
12472 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -((65 \times -(4 \times (3 \times 2))) + 1)) \\
12473 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 - (65 \times ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
12474 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (((65 \times (4^3)) / -2) + 1)) \\
12475 &:= (9 - (8 - (7 \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times (32 + 1))))) \\
12476 &:= (9 + (8 - ((7 - (65 \times (4^3))) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
12477 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (65 \times (4^3))) \times -(2 + 1) \\
12478 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((7 + 6) \times -54) - (32 \times 1))) \\
12479 &:= (9 - ((87 - (6 - 5)) \times -(((4 \times 3)^2) + 1))) \\
12480 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 \times (5^4)) / -3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
12481 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (65 \times -((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
12482 &:= (9 + (8 + ((76 \times ((54 \times 3) + 2)) + 1))) \\
12483 &:= (((9 - (8 - 7))^6) - ((5 - 4)^3)) / 21 \\
12484 &:= (((-987 \times -6) + (5 \times (4^3))) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
12485 &:= (((-987 \times 6) - (5 \times (4^3))) \times -2) + 1 \\
12486 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (((65 \times (4^3)) / -2) - 1)) \\
12487 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 \times -(65 - (43^2))) - 1)) \\
12488 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -((65 \times -(4 \times (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\
12489 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 \times -(65 - (43^2))) + 1)) \\
12490 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 \times 4))) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\
12491 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times (32 + 1))))) \\
12492 &:= (9 - (((8^{7-6+5}) - (4 - 3)) / -21)) \\
12493 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 + (6 \times 54))) \times -(32 - 1)) \\
12494 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times -(65 - ((43^2) + 1)))) \\
12495 &:= ((98 + (7^{(6-5) \times 4})) \times -(3 + 2) \times -1) \\
12496 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (7 \times (6 + ((5 \times 43) + 2)))) - 1)) \\
12497 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 + 6) \times 5) \times -((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
12498 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times (6 + ((5 \times 43) + 2)))) - 1)) \\
12499 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (6 \times 5)) \times -(432 - 1) \\
12500 &:= ((9 - (8 - (7 - 6))) \times -((5^4) \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
12501 &:= ((9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5)) + 4)) \times (3^{2+1})) \\
12502 &:= (9 - (8 - ((7 + (65 \times (4^3))) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
12503 &:= (((-9 - (87 \times (6 - 54))) \times 3) - (2 \times -1)) \\
12504 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) - (65 \times -((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
12505 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (5 \times -((4^3) - (2 + 1)))) \\
12506 &:= (9 + (8 - ((7 \times (65 - (43^2)))) - 1)) \\
12507 &:= (((9 - 8) - (76 \times 5)) \times ((4 \times -3) - 21)) \\
12508 &:= (9 + (((8 - 7) - (6 \times 5)) \times -(432 - 1))) \\
12509 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 + 6)) \times -((5^4) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
12510 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 \times (5^4)) + 3) / - (2 + 1))) \\
12511 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 65))) - 4) \times -3) - 2) \times 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12512 &:= (((-1 + ((2345 \times 6) + 7)) \times -8) / -9) \\ 12513 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times 4) - ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 89))) \\ 12514 &:= ((1 - 23) - (4 \times -((5^{6+7-8}) + 9))) \\ 12515 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -3) - ((4 \times (5^{6+7-8})) + 9))) \\ 12516 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -3) - ((4 \times (5^{6+7-8})) + 9))) \\ 12517 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) + ((4 \times (5^{6+7-8})) + 9))) \\ 12518 &:= (1 + ((2^3) + ((4 \times (5^{6+7-8})) + 9))) \\ 12519 &:= (1 \times -((((2 \times 3)^4) + (5 + (6 \times (7 + 8)))) \times -9)) \\ 12520 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) + (5 + (6 \times (7 + 8)))) \times -9)) \\ 12521 &:= (1 + (2 \times -((3 - (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\ 12522 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 + 4) - ((5 - (6 \times 78)) \times 9))) \\ 12523 &:= (1 + (2 \times -((3 + ((4 + 5) \times (6 - (78 \times 9)))))) \\ 12524 &:= ((12 + 3) - ((4 \times -(5^{6+7-8})) - 9)) \\ 12525 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((((3^4) + 5) \times 6) + 7) \times -8) + 9)) \\ 12526 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -(((4^5) \times -6) - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 12527 &:= (1 - ((23 \times -((4 + 5) + (67 \times 8))) + 9)) \\ 12528 &:= (((12^3) \times -4) - ((5 \times (6^7)) / - (8 \times 9))) \\ 12529 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + 5) \times 6) + (7 \times -89)) \\ 12530 &:= (1 \times (2 - (3 \times (((4 + 5) - 67) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 12531 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) - (4 \times ((5^{6+7-8}) + 9)))) \\ 12532 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) - (4 \times ((5^{6+7-8}) + 9)))) \\ 12533 &:= (1 + (23 + ((4 \times (5^{6+7-8})) + 9))) \\ 12534 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((3 - ((4 + 5) \times (6 - (78 \times 9)))))) \\ 12535 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 - ((4 \times (56 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9))) \\ 12536 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - ((4 \times -(5^{6+7-8})) - 9)) \\ 12537 &:= ((1 - 2) + ((3 + (4 \times (56 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\ 12538 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) - (4 \times -(5^{6+7-8}) + 9)) \\ 12539 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (3 \times -(4 - ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 89)))) \\ 12540 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -(4 \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 - 9)))) \\ 12541 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -3) - ((4 \times (56 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9))) \\ 12542 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -3) - (4 \times ((5^{6+7-8}) + 9)))) \\ 12543 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -3) - (4 \times ((5^{6+7-8}) + 9)))) \\ 12544 &:= (12 - (3 - ((4 \times (56 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9))) \\ 12545 &:= (12 - (3 - (4 \times ((5^{6+7-8}) + 9)))) \\ 12546 &:= (((1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times (((5 + (6 + 7)) \times -8) - 9)) \\ 12547 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times ((5 + 6) \times 7)))) - (8 \times -9)) \\ 12548 &:= (((((12^3) + 4) \times 5) - ((6^7) / - (8 \times 9))) \\ 12549 &:= ((1 - 2) - (3 - ((4 \times (56 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9))) \\ 12550 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (3 - ((4 \times (56 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9))) \\ 12551 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times ((5 + 6) \times -(7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\ 12552 &:= (12 \times (((3^4) + 5) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 \times 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12512 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times 6)) - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 12513 &:= (((9 + (87 + 6)) - 5) \times -((4 \times -32) - 1)) \\ 12514 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 + (((6^5) + 4) / (3 + 2)))) - 1)) \\ 12515 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (7 \times -(6 + (54 \times (32 + 1)))))) \\ 12516 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 \times -(6 + (54 \times (32 + 1)))))) \\ 12517 &:= ((9 + ((87 \times ((6 - 54) \times 3)) + 2)) \times -1) \\ 12518 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times 6) \times (5 - ((4 \times 3)^2)) + 1)) \\ 12519 &:= (9 + ((8 + 7) \times -(6 \times ((5 \times (4 - 32)) + 1)))) \\ 12520 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 \times (5^4)) / -3) - (2 \times 1))) \\ 12521 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(7 + (((6^5) + 4) / (3 + 2)) + 1))) \\ 12522 &:= ((-9 \times -87654) / - (3 \times -21)) \\ 12523 &:= (((-98 \times ((76 \times 5) + 4)) / -3) - 21) \\ 12524 &:= (9 - (((8 - (7 \times 65)) \times -(4 - 32)) + 1)) \\ 12525 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 \times 65)) \times (4 - 32))) \times 1) \\ 12526 &:= ((9 - ((87 + (6 + 5)) \times (4^3))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\ 12527 &:= (((9 + 8) - (((7 \times (6 - 54)) / -3)^2)) \times -1) \\ 12528 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(6 \times -(5 + (4^{3+2-1})))) \\ 12529 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((765 + 4) - 32) \times -1)) \\ 12530 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 \times (5^4)) / -3) - (2 + 1))) \\ 12531 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (765 \times 43))) / -21) \\ 12532 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -(4^3) - 2) - 1)) \\ 12533 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) - 2))) \times 1) \\ 12534 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) - 2))) + 1) \\ 12535 &:= ((9 - (87 \times ((6 - 54) \times 3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\ 12536 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 + 6)) \times (5^4))) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 12537 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\ 12538 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times ((6 - 54) \times 3)) - 2)) - 1) \\ 12539 &:= ((9 - (87 \times ((6 - 54) \times 3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\ 12540 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times ((6 - 54) \times 3)) - 2)) + 1) \\ 12541 &:= (9 - (8 - (76 \times (5 \times ((4 \times 3) + 21)))))) \\ 12542 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -76) + ((5^4) \times -(3 - 21))) \\ 12543 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 \times (6 - 54)) / -3)^2) - 1)) \\ 12544 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (7 + (65 \times (4 \times (3 \times 2)))))) - 1)) \\ 12545 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 \times (6 - 54)) / -3)^2) \times -1)) \\ 12546 &:= ((98 + ((7 - (6 - 5))^4)) \times -(3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\ 12547 &:= (((-98 \times ((76 \times 5) + 4)) / -3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 12548 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7) - (6 \times 5)) \times -(432 + 1))) \\ 12549 &:= ((9 - (87 \times 6)) - (((5^4) - 3) \times -21)) \\ 12550 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 + (5^4)) - 3) \times -2) + 1)) \\ 12551 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 \times -(65 + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))) \\ 12552 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2)) \times -1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
12553 &:= ((1+2) - (3 - ((4 \times (56 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9))) & 12553 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times (6 + (5 \times 43))) + 21))) \\
12554 &:= (1 \times -((2 - 3) - ((4 \times (56 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9))) & 12554 &:= (9 - (((8 + ((76 \times 5) + 4)) \times -32) - 1)) \\
12555 &:= (1 - ((2 - 3) - ((4 \times (56 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9))) & 12555 &:= ((9 + (8 + 76)) \times (5 \times -(4 - (32 - 1)))) \\
12556 &:= (1 \times -((2 + (34 \times 5)) \times ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9)))) & 12556 &:= ((((-9 + (87 \times (6 - 54))) \times -3) + 2) - 1) \\
12557 &:= (1 - ((2 + (34 \times 5)) \times ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9)))) & 12557 &:= (98 + ((7 - (65 \times (4^3))) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
12558 &:= (((1 + 2) - (3^4)) \times ((5 \times -((6 \times 7) - 8)) + 9)) & 12558 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times 6) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) - 21))) \\
12559 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 + ((4 \times (56 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9))) & 12559 &:= (9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times -(5 - (4^{3+2-1})))) \\
12560 &:= ((1 + 23) - (4 \times -((5^{6+7-8}) + 9))) & 12560 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) / -(2 + 1))) \\
12561 &:= (12 + (3 \times -(((4 \times 5) - 67) \times 89))) & 12561 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 \times (6 - 54)) / -3)^2) \times -1) \\
12562 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 12562 &:= ((9 + ((87 + (6 + 5)) \times (4^3))) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
12563 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (4 \times -((5^{6+7-8}) + 9))) & 12563 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((7 + (6 + 5)) \times -(43 - 2)) - 1)) \\
12564 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 \times -(4 + ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 89)))) & 12564 &:= (9 + ((87 + 6) \times -(5 \times (4 - (32 - 1)))) \\
12565 &:= (1 - ((2 + (34 \times (56 - (7 + 8)))) \times -9)) & 12565 &:= (((((-9 - 87) \times 65) - 43) \times -2) - 1) \\
12566 &:= (12345 - ((6 + 7) \times -(8 + 9))) & 12566 &:= (9 + (((8 - 7) - (6 \times 5)) \times -(432 + 1))) \\
12567 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 + (4 \times 5)) - (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) & 12567 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times -((5^4) - (3^{2+1})))) \\
12568 &:= (12 + (3 + ((4 \times (56 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9))) & 12568 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times (65 + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))) \\
12569 &:= ((-12 \times -(3 + ((4^5) + (6 + 7)))) + 89) & 12569 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 43) - 21))) \\
12570 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 + 4) + ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 89))) & 12570 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -((((6 + (5^4)) - 3) \times -2) - 1)) \\
12571 &:= (12 - (((3 + (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times -8) + 9)) & 12571 &:= (98 - (7 - (65 \times ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
12572 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 89)))))) & 12572 &:= (98 - (7 \times -(6 \times ((5 + 4) \times (32 + 1)))) \\
12573 &:= (1 - ((2^3) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 89)))))) & 12573 &:= (((9 - 8) + (76 \times 5)) \times -((4 \times -3) - 21)) \\
12574 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -3) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 89)))))) & 12574 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + (65 \times (4 \times 3)))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
12575 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times ((5 - 6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 12575 &:= (9 + (8 + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - 21)))) \\
12576 &:= ((12 + ((3 \times (4^5)) / 6)) \times (7 + (8 + 9))) & 12576 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -(6 - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
12577 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 + (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times 8) + 9)) & 12577 &:= ((((-9 - 87) \times -(6 + ((5^4) / (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
12578 &:= (1 \times (2 - (3 \times ((4 \times 5) - (6 \times (78 \times 9)))))) & 12578 &:= (98 - (((7 + 6) \times 5) \times -((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
12579 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((((3^4) + 5) \times 6) + 7) \times -8) - 9) & 12579 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 \times 65)) \times 4)) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
12580 &:= ((1 + 2) + (((3 + (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times 8) + 9)) & 12580 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times -((4 \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
12581 &:= (((12 + 3) + (4 \times (5 - (6^7)))) / -89) & 12581 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6543 \times -2) + 1)) \\
12582 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 + 4) - 5) - (6 \times 78)) \times -9) & 12582 &:= ((98 + (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times -(3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
12583 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 3) + (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times -8) + 9) & 12583 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + (65 \times (4 \times 3))) \times 2))) \times -1) \\
12584 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3) + (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times -8) + 9) & 12584 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -((6 + 5) \times -(((4 \times 3)^2) - 1))) \\
12585 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -((4 \times -(5 \times (6 \times 7))) - (8 - 9))) & 12585 &:= ((98 + 7) - (65 \times -((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
12586 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -3) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 89)))))) & 12586 &:= ((98 + (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) \times (32 - 1)) \\
12587 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -3) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 89)))))) & 12587 &:= (98 + ((7 \times -(65 - (43^2))) + 1)) \\
12588 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - 5) \times 6) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 12588 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (7 \times -(6 + (54 \times (32 + 1)))) \\
12589 &:= (1 - ((2 \times 3) \times -(((4 + 5) - 6)^7) - 89))) & 12589 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -76) + (((5^4) + 3) \times 21))) \\
12590 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times (456 + 7)) + 89) & 12590 &:= ((((-98 - 7) \times -(6 \times (5 \times 4))) - ((3^2) + 1)) \\
12591 &:= (1 \times -((2 + ((3 \times (456 + 7)) + 8)) \times -9)) & 12591 &:= (9 \times (((8 + 7) - 65) \times (4 - 32)) - 1) \\
12592 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (34 \times 5)) \times (67 + 8))) - 9) & 12592 &:= ((((-98 - 7) \times -(6 \times (5 \times 4))) - ((3^2) - 1)) \\
12593 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) + (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times 8) + 9) & 12593 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 + (65 \times (4 \times 3))) \times 2) - 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
12594 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 12594 &:= ((9 - (((87 \times 6) + 5) \times 4)) \times (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
12595 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times 6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 12595 &:= ((-9 \times 876) - ((5 \times -(4^{3 \times 2})) + 1)) \\
12596 &:= (((1 - (2 - 3)) - (45 \times 6)) \times ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & 12596 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((65 \times -4) - ((3^2) - 1))) \\
12597 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (34 \times (5 + 6))) - 7) \times -(8 + 9))) & 12597 &:= (((98 + (76 \times 54)) - 3) \times (2 + 1)) \\
12598 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (34 \times (5 + 6))) - 7) \times -(8 + 9))) & 12598 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 + 6) + (54 \times 3)))) - 2) \times 1) \\
12599 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) \times -((4 \times (56 \times 7)) + 8)) + 9)) & 12599 &:= (98 - ((7 + (65 \times (4^3))) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
12600 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 + ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)))) & 12600 &:= ((98 + (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 + 4) \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
12601 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 3) + (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times -8) - 9)) & 12601 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 + (65 \times (4 \times 3))) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
12602 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3) + (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times -8) - 9)) & 12602 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 + (65 \times (4 \times 3))) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
12603 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3^4) - 56) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 12603 &:= (((-987 - 65) \times -(4 \times 3)) - 21) \\
12604 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -(4 \times ((5 \times (6 + 7)) + (8 \times 9)))) & 12604 &:= ((((-98 - (76 \times 54)) \times -3) - 2) \times 1) \\
12605 &:= (1 \times ((2 - (((3 + 4)^5) \times 6)) / - (7 - (8 - 9)))) & 12605 &:= ((((-98 - (76 \times 54)) \times -3) - 2) + 1) \\
12606 &:= (1 + ((2 - (((3 + 4)^5) \times 6)) / - (7 - (8 - 9)))) & 12606 &:= ((98 + (76 \times 54)) \times -(3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
12607 &:= (1 \times (((2^{3 \times 4}) + ((5^6) \times 7) - 8) / 9)) & 12607 &:= (((((-9 - 87) \times 65) - (4^3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
12608 &:= (1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) + ((5^6) \times 7) - 8) / 9)) & 12608 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times -(6 \times (5 \times (4 - 32)))) - 1)) \\
12609 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -(((4 + 5) \times -(6 \times 7)) - 89)) & 12609 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((7 \times (6 \times (5 - 43))) + 21))) \\
12610 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (34 \times 5)) \times (67 + 8))) + 9) & 12610 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times ((6 + (((5^4) + 3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
12611 &:= (1 \times (2 - (3 \times ((4 + 5) - (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) & 12611 &:= (((-9 \times -((8 + ((7 \times 65) + 4)) \times 3)) + 2) \times 1) \\
12612 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + (4^5)) \times ((6 + (7 + 8)) - 9) & 12612 &:= (((-9 - 87) \times 6) - (((5^4) + 3) \times -21)) \\
12613 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + (((3 + 4)^5) \times 6)) - 7) / 8) + 9) & 12613 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + 6) + ((5 + 4)^3))) - 2) + 1) \\
12614 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3 \times (4 \times (5 - 67)))) \times -(8 + 9)) & 12614 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(7 \times -(((65 + 43) - 2) \times 1))) \\
12615 &:= ((12 + 3) \times ((4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) - (8 - 9))) & 12615 &:= ((98 + ((7 \times 6) + 5)) \times -((43 \times -2) - 1)) \\
12616 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(3 \times (((45 \times 6) - 7) \times 8))) + 9)) & 12616 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(765 - 4)) - 321) \\
12617 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) \times -((4 \times (56 \times 7)) + 8)) - 9)) & 12617 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(7 - (((6 + 5) \times ((4 \times 3)^2)) - 1)))) \\
12618 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) \times 6) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9)) & 12618 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((7 \times 65) + 4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
12619 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 + ((4 \times 5) + 678)) \times 9)) & 12619 &:= (9 - (8 + ((76 + (5^4)) \times (3 - 21)))) \\
12620 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (3 - 4)) \times -(5 - (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) & 12620 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 + (5^4)) \times -(3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
12621 &:= (1 \times ((2 - (3 - 4)) \times -(5 - (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) & 12621 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times (65 \times 4))) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
12622 &:= (1 + ((2 - (3 - 4)) \times -(5 - (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) & 12622 &:= ((((-987 - 65) \times -(4 \times 3)) - 2) \times 1) \\
12623 &:= (-1 + (2 \times -(3 \times (4 \times (5 - ((67 - 8) \times 9)))) & 12623 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -((6 - 5) + ((4 \times 3)^2))) + 1)) \\
12624 &:= (12 \times (3 + ((4^5) + ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9)))) & 12624 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6 + 5) \times ((4 \times 3)^2)))) - 1) \\
12625 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times (((5 - 67) \times -8) + 9)) & 12625 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6 + 5) \times ((4 \times 3)^2)))) \times 1) \\
12626 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times 78))) - 9)) & 12626 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6 + 5) \times ((4 \times 3)^2)))) + 1) \\
12627 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 \times (4 - 5)) + (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) & 12627 &:= (9 \times -((((87 \times 6) - 54) \times -3) + (2 - 1))) \\
12628 &:= (((1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times ((5 \times -(6 + 7)) - 89)) & 12628 &:= ((9 - (8 - 76)) \times -((54 \times -3) - (2 \times 1))) \\
12629 &:= (((1 + 2) + (34 \times 5)) \times -((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9)) & 12629 &:= (((-98 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -(43 - 2)) + 1) \\
12630 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 + 4) - 5) - (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) & 12630 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times (6 + (((5^4) + 3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
12631 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times (7 \times 8)))) / - 9) & 12631 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 \times -((65 + 43) - 2)) - 1)) \\
12632 &:= (1 + (((2 \times ((3^4) \times 5)) - 67) \times (8 + 9)) & 12632 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(6 + (5 \times (4 - 32)))) \\
12633 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times -(4^5)) - (67 \times (8 + 9)))) & 12633 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(7 - (((6 + 5) \times ((4 \times 3)^2)) + 1)))) \\
12634 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times (((45 \times 6) - 7) \times 8)))) + 9) & 12634 &:= (-98 + ((7 \times -((6 \times 5) - (43^2))) - 1)) \\
12635 &:= (1 \times -((2 - (3 \times 45)) \times (((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9)) & 12635 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 - (6 \times 54)))) \times ((3 + 2) \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

12636 := $((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - 5)) \times -((6 - (7 + 8)) \times -9))$
12637 := $(1 \times -(2 + (3 \times ((4 - 5) - (6 \times (78 \times 9)))))$
12638 := $(1 - (2 + (3 \times ((4 - 5) - (6 \times (78 \times 9)))))$
12639 := $((1 - 2) \times -(3 \times -((4 - 5) - (6 \times (78 \times 9)))))$
12640 := $(1 \times ((2 - 34) \times -(5 - (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))$
12641 := $(1 + ((2 - 34) \times -(5 - (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))$
12642 := $((1 + ((23 \times 4) + 5)) \times -(6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))$
12643 := $(1 - (2 \times -((3 \times (((45 \times 6) - 7) \times 8)) + 9)))$
12644 := $(1 + (((2 - 3) + (45 \times 6)) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))$
12645 := $((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times (4 - 5)) - (6 \times (78 \times 9))))$
12646 := $(1 \times -(2 + (3 \times (4 \times ((5 - 67) \times (8 + 9)))))$
12647 := $(1 - (2 + (3 \times (4 \times ((5 - 67) \times (8 + 9)))))$
12648 := $((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + 5) \times 6) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))$
12649 := $((((12^3) + (4 \times (5 - (6 \times 7)))) \times 8) + 9)$
12650 := $((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5 \times 6))) \times (7 - (8 + 9)))$
12651 := $(1 - (23 \times -((4^5) - (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))$
12652 := $(1 - ((2 - (3 - 4)) \times -(5 + (6 \times (78 \times 9)))))$
12653 := $(1 - (2 \times -(((3^4) \times ((5 + 6) \times 7)) + 89)))$
12654 := $((1 + 2) \times (3 \times -(4 - (5 \times (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))))$
12655 := $((((12 + 3)^4) - 5) / -((6 + 7) - (8 + 9)))$
12656 := $(1 \times (((2 - (34 \times 5)) \times 678) / -9))$
12657 := $((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times -4) + (5 - (6 \times (78 \times 9)))))$
12658 := $(123 - ((4 \times -(56 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9))$
12659 := $(123 - (4 \times -((5^{6+7-8}) + 9)))$
12660 := $(1 \times (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5 \times 6)) \times -(7 - (8 + 9)))$
12661 := $(1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5 \times 6)) \times -(7 - (8 + 9)))$
12662 := $(1 - (2 - (3 \times ((4 + 5) + (6 \times (78 \times 9)))))$
12663 := $((1 + (2 \times ((3 - (((4^5) - 6) \times 7)) \times 8))) / -9)$
12664 := $((1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 - ((6 + 7) \times 8)))) - 9)$
12665 := $(1 \times -((((2^{3+4}) - 5) \times 6) + 7) \times -(8 + 9))$
12666 := $(1 - (((((2^{3+4}) - 5) \times 6) + 7) \times -(8 + 9)))$
12667 := $(1 \times ((234 + 5) \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9)))$
12668 := $(1 + ((234 + 5) \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9)))$
12669 := $((1 - (2 \times (3 + (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 \times 8))))) / -9)$
12670 := $((((1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) - (5 \times 6)) \times -(7 - (8 + 9)))$
12671 := $(1 \times ((23^{4+5-6}) + (7 \times (8 \times 9))))$
12672 := $((((12^3) \times -(4 \times (5 + 6))) / -((7 + 8) - 9))$
12673 := $(1 \times -(23 \times -((4 \times 5) + ((67 - 8) \times 9))))$
12674 := $(1 \times (2 + (3 \times (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 89)))))$
12675 := $(1 + (2 + (3 \times (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 89)))))$
12676 := $(1 + (((234 \times 5) / 6) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9))))$
12677 := $(-1 - (2 \times -(3 \times (((45 \times 6) - 7) \times 8) + 9)))$

12636 := $(9 \times (((8 - (7 \times (65 + 4))) \times -3) - 21))$
12637 := $(9 - (8 + ((7 + 6) \times (54 \times (3 - 21))))$
12638 := $(98 - (76 \times -(5 \times ((4 \times 3) + 21))))$
12639 := $(9 - ((8 + 7) \times -((((6 \times 5) - (4 - 3)^2) + 1)))$
12640 := $(-9 - (((87 \times 6) + 5) \times -(4 \times (3 \times 2))) - 1)$
12641 := $(98 + (((7 \times (6 - 54)) / -3)^2) - 1)$
12642 := $(98 - (((7 \times (6 - 54)) / -3)^2) \times -1)$
12643 := $((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 \times -(54 - (3^2))) + 1))$
12644 := $(987 - (((((6^5) - 4) \times 3) / -2) + 1))$
12645 := $(987 - (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) / -(2 \times 1))$
12646 := $(987 - (((((6^5) - 4) \times 3) / -2) - 1))$
12647 := $((9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 - 43)) + 2)))) \times -1)$
12648 := $((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -((((65 \times 4) + 3) \times -2) - 1))$
12649 := $(9 - (8 \times -(7 + ((6 + 5) \times (((4 \times 3)^2) - 1))))$
12650 := $(987 - (((6^5) / 4) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1)$
12651 := $(9 - ((8 + 7) - (6 - 5)) \times -(43 \times 21))$
12652 := $(987 - (((6^5) / 4) \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1)$
12653 := $(9 + (8 - ((7 + 6) \times (54 \times (3 - 21))))$
12654 := $((9 - ((87 - 6) \times (5^4))) / -((3 + 2) - 1))$
12655 := $((((-9 \times 8) - (76 \times 5)) \times (4 - 32)) - 1)$
12656 := $(9 - (((87 \times 6) + 5) \times -(4 \times (3 \times 2))) + 1)$
12657 := $(9 - (8 \times -(((7 \times 6) + (5 + 4)) \times (32 - 1))))$
12658 := $(9 - (((87 \times 6) + 5) \times -(4 \times (3 \times 2))) - 1)$
12659 := $(9 + (8 - (7 \times (6 \times ((5 \times 4) - 321))))$
12660 := $((9 + 8) - 7) \times (6 + (5 \times (4 \times (3 \times 21))))$
12661 := $(((-9 - (8 \times 76)) \times -(5 \times 4)) + 321)$
12662 := $(((-9 - 8) \times -765) - ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))$
12663 := $(((-98 - 7) \times -(6 \times (5 \times 4))) - (3 \times -21))$
12664 := $((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6 + 5) \times -((4 \times 3)^2)) + 1))$
12665 := $(9 - (8 \times -(7 + (((6 + 5) + (4^3)) \times 21))))$
12666 := $((9 + (((87 \times 6) + 5) \times (4 \times 3))) \times -(2 \times -1))$
12667 := $((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times -(65 \times (4 - 32))) - 1))$
12668 := $(((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (65 \times (4 - 32)))) \times -1)$
12669 := $(((9 - 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 \times -(4^3) - 2)) + 1)$
12670 := $(((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 + ((5^4) + 3)) \times -2) + 1))$
12671 := $((9 + (8 \times ((7 - (6 \times 54)) \times (3 + 2)))) \times -1)$
12672 := $((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -((6 + 5) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) - 1)))$
12673 := $((9 - 8) - (((76 \times 5) + 4) \times -(32 + 1)))$
12674 := $(((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(65 \times (4 - (3 - 2)))) - 1)$
12675 := $(9 + ((87 \times -6) + (((5^4) + 3) \times 21)))$
12676 := $(((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(65 \times (4 - (3 - 2)))) + 1)$
12677 := $((-98 \times -(7 + 6)) - (543 \times -21))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 12678 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 \times (((45 \times 6) - 7) \times 8) + 9)))) \\
 12679 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 \times (((45 \times 6) - 7) \times 8) + 9)))) \\
 12680 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -(4 \times ((5 + 6) + (7 \times 89)))))) \\
 12681 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 + 6))) \times -((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
 12682 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 - ((6 + 7) \times 8)))) + 9) \\
 12683 &:= (1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4 \times (5 - 67)))) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
 12684 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(3 - (45 \times (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) \\
 12685 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) - (45 \times (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))))) \\
 12686 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) - (45 \times (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))))) \\
 12687 &:= (1 \times (((2 - ((3 + (4 \times 56)) \times 7)) \times -8) - 9)) \\
 12688 &:= (1 + (((2 - ((3 + (4 \times 56)) \times 7)) \times -8) - 9)) \\
 12689 &:= (1 \times ((2 - 3) + (45 \times (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))))) \\
 12690 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times ((4 \times 5) - ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
 12691 &:= (1 \times -((2 - 3) - (45 \times (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))))) \\
 12692 &:= ((1 - 2) + (3 + (45 \times (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))))) \\
 12693 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 - (4 - 5))^6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 12694 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times ((4 \times 5) + (6 \times (78 \times 9)))))) \\
 12695 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) + (45 \times (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))))) \\
 12696 &:= ((1 + ((2 + ((3^4) + 5)) \times 6)) \times (7 + (8 + 9))) \\
 12697 &:= (((12^3) \times 4) - (5 \times -((6 + 7) \times 89))) \\
 12698 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times ((4 \times 5) + (6 \times (78 \times 9)))))) \\
 12699 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 - (4 \times (56 + 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 12700 &:= (1 + ((2 - (3 \times (456 + (7 + 8)))) \times -9)) \\
 12701 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3 + (4 \times 56)) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
 12702 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 + (4 \times 56)) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
 12703 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (((3 + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9)) \\
 12704 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (((3 + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9)) \\
 12705 &:= ((1 - (2 - 34)) \times (((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) + 9)) \\
 12706 &:= ((1 - ((2 - ((3 + (4 \times 56)) \times 7)) \times 8)) + 9) \\
 12707 &:= (1 \times -(((23 \times 4) + 5) \times -((6 \times 7) + 89))) \\
 12708 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 \times ((4 \times (5 \times 67)) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 12709 &:= ((1 - ((2 + 34) \times 5)) \times -((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 12710 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3 \times (45 + 6))) \times -(7 - 89))) \\
 12711 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3 \times (45 + 6))) \times -(7 - 89))) \\
 12712 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3 + 4)) + 5) \times -(678 - 9))) \\
 12713 &:= (1 \times (23 + (45 \times (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))))) \\
 12714 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times -(((5 + 6) \times -7) + (8 - 9))) \\
 12715 &:= (12 - (((3 + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9)) \\
 12716 &:= ((1 - 23) \times ((4 \times -5) - ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
 12717 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -(4 - (5 \times (((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9)))) \\
 12718 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (3 \times -((456 + (7 + 8)) \times 9))) \\
 12719 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times (5 - (67 + (8 + 9))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 12678 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (6 - (((5^4) + 3) \times 21))) \\
 12679 &:= (((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) - (6 + 5))) + 4) \times (32 - 1)) \\
 12680 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 + ((5^4) + 3)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
 12681 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 + 65) \times (43 - 21)))) \\
 12682 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 + 6)) - 5) \times -(4 \times 32)) - 1)) \\
 12683 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times 65) \times -(4 + (3^2))) + 1)) \\
 12684 &:= ((9 - (87 \times ((6 \times 5) + 43))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
 12685 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times 65) \times -(4 + (3^2))) - 1)) \\
 12686 &:= (((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 65) - 4) \times -3) - 2) + 1) \\
 12687 &:= (-9 + (8 \times -((7 \times 6) - (543 \times (2 + 1)))))) \\
 12688 &:= ((987 - (6 + 5)) \times -(((4 + 3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
 12689 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((76 \times 5) + 4) \times -(32 + 1))) \\
 12690 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -((7 - (6 \times 54)) \times (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\
 12691 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5)) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) \times -1)) \\
 12692 &:= (9 - (8 - ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))) \\
 12693 &:= ((9 - (87 \times (6 - (5 \times (4 - 32)))))) \times -1) \\
 12694 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 - 5))) \times (43 - 21)) \\
 12695 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -76) - (543 \times -21)) \\
 12696 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times -(4 \times -(3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 12697 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 - 6) - (5 \times (4 - 321)))))) \\
 12698 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -6) - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 12699 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 65)) \times (4^3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 12700 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times 6) - 5)) \times ((4 \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
 12701 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 \times (43 - 2)))) \times -1) \\
 12702 &:= ((9 + (((87 \times 6) + 5) \times 4)) \times -(3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
 12703 &:= (-987 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2) + 1)) \\
 12704 &:= (((9 + 8) + (76 \times 5)) \times -((4^3) / - (2 \times 1))) \\
 12705 &:= ((98 + (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
 12706 &:= ((-987 \times -(6 + 5)) - ((43^2) \times -1)) \\
 12707 &:= ((-98 \times -(76 + 54)) - (32 + 1)) \\
 12708 &:= (9 + (8 + ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))) \\
 12709 &:= ((-98 \times -(76 + 54)) - (32 - 1)) \\
 12710 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)) \\
 12711 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) \times -1)) \\
 12712 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)) \\
 12713 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 43) - (2 + 1)))) \\
 12714 &:= ((9 - 87) \times ((6 \times -((5 + 4) \times 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
 12715 &:= (-9 - (8 + ((7 \times ((6 \times 5) - (43^2)))) + 1)) \\
 12716 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 43)) + 21)) \\
 12717 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 43)) - 2)) \times -1) \\
 12718 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times -(5 \times (43 - 2))) + 1)) \\
 12719 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 12720 &:= (12 \times -(((3^4) - 5) \times -(6 + 7)) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 12721 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (((3 + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\
 12722 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3^4) - (5 - 6)) \times -78) - 9) \\
 12723 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 3^4) - (5 - 6)) \times -78) - 9) \\
 12724 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 + 4) \times (((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times 9)))) \\
 12725 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 + 4) \times (((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times 9)))) \\
 12726 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 \times -((4^5) - (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 12727 &:= ((123 + (4 \times 5)) \times -((6 - 7) \times 89)) \\
 12728 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -((4 \times ((56 \times 7) + 8)) - 9))) \\
 12729 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 + 4) \times -(((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times 9))) \\
 12730 &:= (1 \times ((23 - 4) \times -(5 - ((67 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
 12731 &:= (1 + ((23 - 4) \times -(5 - ((67 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
 12732 &:= (12 \times ((3 + 4) - ((5 - 67) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 12733 &:= (12 - (((3 + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\
 12734 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 - (67 \times 8)))))) - 9) \\
 12735 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times 4) - ((5 + (6 \times 78)) \times 9))) \\
 12736 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 - (67 \times 8)))))) - 9) \\
 12737 &:= (1 \times -(((23 + (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times -8) - 9)) \\
 12738 &:= (12 - ((3 + 4) \times -(((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times 9))) \\
 12739 &:= (1 + (2 \times -((3 - ((4 + 5) \times (6 + (78 \times 9)))))) \\
 12740 &:= ((1 + ((234 \times 5)/6)) \times ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
 12741 &:= ((1 + (23 \times 4)) \times -((5 \times -(6 + 7)) - (8 \times 9))) \\
 12742 &:= ((12 + 34) \times -(5 - (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
 12743 &:= ((1 - ((2^{(-3+4) \times (5+6)}) \times (7 \times 8)))/ - 9) \\
 12744 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -4) \times -((5 - 6) + (7 \times (8 + 9))) \\
 12745 &:= (((-1 - 2) - ((3 + (4 \times 56)) \times 7)) \times -8) + 9 \\
 12746 &:= (1 \times (2 - (3 \times ((4 - (56 + 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 12747 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 + 4) \times -(((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
 12748 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((34 - ((5 + 67) \times 89)))) \\
 12749 &:= (1 + (2 \times -((34 - ((5 + 67) \times 89)))) \\
 12750 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times -(5 \times -(6 + (7 + 89)))) \\
 12751 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((34 + 5) \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\
 12752 &:= (1 - (2 - ((34 + 5) \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\
 12753 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((34 + 5) + (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\
 12754 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 - (67 \times 8)))))) + 9) \\
 12755 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((34 + 5) \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\
 12756 &:= (1 + (2 + ((34 + 5) \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\
 12757 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times 6))) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
 12758 &:= (1 - (2 - ((34 \times (5 \times (67 + 8))) + 9))) \\
 12759 &:= (12345 - (6 \times -(78 - 9))) \\
 12760 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (((3^4) - 5) \times (6 + 78)))) - 9) \\
 12761 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((34 \times (5 \times (67 + 8))) + 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 12720 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) \times -1)) \\
 12721 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)) \\
 12722 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 43) - 2)) - 1)) \\
 12723 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times (65 \times (4 - 32)))) \times -1) \\
 12724 &:= (-9 - ((8 + (7 \times (65 \times (4 - 32)))) - 1)) \\
 12725 &:= (9 - ((8 - 76) \times -(5 - ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 12726 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 \times -((6 \times 5) - ((43^2) - 1)))) \\
 12727 &:= (9 - (8 + (7 \times ((6 \times 5) - ((43^2) - 1)))) \\
 12728 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times (6 - (5 \times (4 - 321)))) \\
 12729 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(((7 + 6) - 543) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 12730 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times -5 + ((4 \times 32) + 1)) \\
 12731 &:= (((-98 \times (76 + 54)) + (3^2)) \times -1) \\
 12732 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 \times -((6 \times 5) - (43^2))) - 1)) \\
 12733 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times (65 \times 4))) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
 12734 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 \times -((6 \times 5) - (43^2))) + 1)) \\
 12735 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 \times -((6 \times 5) - (43^2))) + 1)) \\
 12736 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 43)) + (2 - 1))) \\
 12737 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 \times -(54 - (3^2))) - 1)) \\
 12738 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 43)) - (2 - 1))) \\
 12739 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 43)) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 12740 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(6 - (5 \times (4^{3+2-1})))) \\
 12741 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 76) \times 5)) \times (((4^3)/ - 2) + 1)) \\
 12742 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times (65 \times (4 - 32)))) - 1)) \\
 12743 &:= (9 + (8 - (7 \times ((6 \times 5) - ((43^2) - 1)))) \\
 12744 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - 6) \times (((5 + 4)^3) - 21)) \\
 12745 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 43) + (2 - 1)))) \\
 12746 &:= (((-98 \times -(76 + 54)) + (3 \times 2)) \times 1) \\
 12747 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times (65 \times 4))) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
 12748 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 \times (65 \times (4 + 3))))/2) - 1)) \\
 12749 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -((4^3) - (2 + 1))) \\
 12750 &:= ((9 + (87 + 6)) \times -((5^4)/ - ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
 12751 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (((5^4) - 3)/ - (2 \times 1))) \\
 12752 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 43) + 2)) + 1)) \\
 12753 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 65))) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
 12754 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 43) + 2)) - 1)) \\
 12755 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 76) + (5^4))) + 3) \times -2) - 1) \\
 12756 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 \times -(65 \times (4 - 32))) - 1)) \\
 12757 &:= (9 - ((8 - (7 \times (65 \times (4 - 32)))) \times -1)) \\
 12758 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 \times -(65 \times (4 - 32))) + 1)) \\
 12759 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times ((65 \times 4) - 32)))) \times -1) \\
 12760 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5)) \times -(4 \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
 12761 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7^6))/ - (5 + 4)) + 321))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
12762 &:= ((1 - (23 - 4)) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 12762 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + (65 \times 4)))) \times (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
12763 &:= (1 - (((23 + 4) \times -(5 + (6 \times 78))) + 9)) & 12763 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times -((5 \times (43 - 2)) + 1))) \\
12764 &:= ((-12/3) \times ((456 \times -7) - (8 - 9))) & 12764 &:= (9 + (8 - (7 \times ((65 \times (4 - 32)) - 1)))) \\
12765 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -(4 - ((5 + (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9))) & 12765 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times (((54/3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
12766 &:= (1 + (23 \times -(((4 - (5 + 6)) \times 78) - 9))) & 12766 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(765 - ((4 + 3) \times 2))) - 1) \\
12767 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (456 \times 7)) + (8 - 9)) & 12767 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((765 - ((4 + 3) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
12768 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 - 4) + ((5 + (6 \times 78)) \times 9))) & 12768 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times 6) \times -((5^4) - 321))) \\
12769 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) \times -4) - 5) \times -(((6 + 7) \times 8) + 9)) & 12769 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times 6) \times -((5^4) - 321))) \\
12770 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -(4 + (5 \times (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9))))))) & 12770 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times -((5 \times 43) - 2)) + 1)) \\
12771 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) \times -(4 + (5 \times (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9))))))) & 12771 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 + 4) \times -(32 + 1))) \\
12772 &:= ((-12/3) \times ((456 \times -7) + (8 - 9))) & 12772 &:= (((-9 \times -(876 + 543)) + 2) - 1) \\
12773 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((34 \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) - 9))) & 12773 &:= (((-9 \times -(876 + 543)) + 2) \times 1) \\
12774 &:= (1 - (2 - ((34 \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) - 9))) & 12774 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7 \times (6 \times (5 - 43)))) - (2 + 1))) \\
12775 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times -((5 \times -((6 + 7) \times 8)) + 9)) & 12775 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times ((4 \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
12776 &:= ((1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - ((5 + 6) \times -789)) & 12776 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times ((65 \times 4) - 32))) + 1)) \\
12777 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3^4) - 5) \times (6 + 78))) - 9)) & 12777 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((65 \times 4) - 32)))) \times 1) \\
12778 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((34 \times -((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) + 9)) & 12778 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 - 43)))) - 2)) - 1) \\
12779 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -((4^5) - (6 \times 78))) + 9)) & 12779 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 - 43)))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
12780 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 \times -(4 \times (5 \times ((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9)))))) & 12780 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (76 + 5))) \times -(4 \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
12781 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((34 \times 5) - 6) \times 78) - 9)) & 12781 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times (6 + 54))) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
12782 &:= (1 \times -((2 + (3^4)) \times -((5 \times (6 + 7)) + 89))) & 12782 &:= ((((-9 - 87) \times -6) + 5) \times (4 - (3 - 21))) \\
12783 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3^4)) \times -((5 \times (6 + 7)) + 89))) & 12783 &:= (((-98 \times -7) + (6^5)) + 4321) \\
12784 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) \times -(4 - ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times 89)))) & 12784 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (((6 \times 5) + 4) \times -((3^2) - 1))) \\
12785 &:= (1 + ((2^3) \times -(4 - ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times 89)))) & 12785 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times ((65 \times 4) - 32)) + 1))) \\
12786 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3+4} - 56) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)) & 12786 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 + ((7 + 6) \times 54))) + 3) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
12787 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6)))) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 12787 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times -((6 + 5) - ((43^2) - 1)))) \\
12788 &:= (1 \times (23 \times -((4 \times 5) - (6 \times (7 + 89)))))) & 12788 &:= (-9 + (8 - (((7 + 6) - ((5^4) - 3)) \times 21))) \\
12789 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -((3^4) \times (5 - (6 + 78)))) - 9)) & 12789 &:= (98 - ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times -((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
12790 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -((3^4) \times (5 - (6 + 78)))) - 9)) & 12790 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times ((6 \times ((5 \times 43) - 2)) + 1)) \\
12791 &:= ((1 + (23^{4+5-6})) - (7 \times -89)) & 12791 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (((7 \times 6) + (5 - (4 + 3)))^2))) \times -1) \\
12792 &:= (((1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times (((5 + 6) \times -(7 + 8)) + 9)) & 12792 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -(((5^4) - 3)/2) + 1)) \\
12793 &:= ((1 - 2) \times ((34 \times -((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) - 9)) & 12793 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 - 43))) - 2))) \times 1) \\
12794 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times ((4 - 56) \times (7 - 89)))))) & 12794 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -((7 \times (6 \times (5 - 43))) - 2)) + 1)) \\
12795 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((34 \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) + 9))) & 12795 &:= (((98 + 7) + (65 \times (4^3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
12796 &:= (1 + (2 + ((34 \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) + 9))) & 12796 &:= ((-98 / -7) \times ((6 + 5) + (43 \times 21))) \\
12797 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -((4^5) - (6 \times 78))) - 9)) & 12797 &:= ((-9 \times -876) + ((5 + (4 \times 3))^{2+1})) \\
12798 &:= (((12^3) \times -(4 - (5 + 6))) - (78 \times -9)) & 12798 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 - 43)))))) + 21) \\
12799 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times 6)))) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 12799 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -(765 - (4 \times 3))) - 2) \times 1) \\
12800 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times (((5 \times 6) / (7 + 8))^9)) & 12800 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -((((6 \times (5 \times 4)) / 3)^2) \times -1)) \\
12801 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 \times -((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) & 12801 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((7 + 6) \times (5 - (4 \times (32 \times 1)))))) \\
12802 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((3 + 4) - ((5 + 67) \times 89)))) & 12802 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -((7 + 6) \times (5 - (4 \times 32)))) + 1)) \\
12803 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((34 \times 5) - 6) \times 78) + 9)) & 12803 &:= ((-98 \times -(76 + 54)) - (3 \times -21))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 12804 &:= ((12 - (((3 + 4)^5 \times 6) / 7) \times 8)) / -9 \\
 12805 &:= (((1 + 2) - (((3 + 4)^5 \times 6) / 7) \times 8)) / -9 \\
 12806 &:= (1 \times -((23 - 4) \times -((5 + 678) - 9))) \\
 12807 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times -4) - ((5 + (6 \times 78)) \times 9))) \\
 12808 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -((3^4) \times (5 - (6 + 78)))) + 9)) \\
 12809 &:= (1 \times (((2 - 34) \times -((56 \times 7) + 8)) + 9)) \\
 12810 &:= (((12^3) / -4) + 5) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 12811 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -((4 - 5) + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
 12812 &:= (1 - (23 \times -((4 - 5) + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
 12813 &:= (123 - (45 \times -((6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
 12814 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3 - 4) + ((5 + 67) \times 89)))) \\
 12815 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3) + (4 \times 56)) \times -((7 \times 8) + 9))) \\
 12816 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) + (4 \times 56)) \times -((7 \times 8) + 9))) \\
 12817 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times (7 \times 8)))))) / -9 \\
 12818 &:= ((1 - (23 + 4)) \times ((5 + 6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 12819 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3^4) + (56 + 7)) \times -89)) \\
 12820 &:= (1 + 2) \times ((3! - 4 - 5) \times 6 + 7) - 8 + 9 \\
 12821 &:= (-1 - (2 \times -((3 + (4 \times ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times 89)))))) \\
 12822 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3 + (4 \times ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times 89)))))) \\
 12823 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 + (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) \times 8))) / -9) \\
 12824 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (45 \times (((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9)))) \\
 12825 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times -((56 + 7) \times -8) - 9) \\
 12826 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 - 4))^5)) \times -((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\
 12827 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times (45 \times (((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9)))) \\
 12828 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3 + (4^5) \times 6)) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 12829 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5) \times 6))) - (7 \times -((8 \times 9))) \\
 12830 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 + (45 \times 6)) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 12831 &:= ((1 - 2) \times ((3 + (45 \times 6)) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 12832 &:= (((12^3) - 4) \times 5) - (6 \times -((78 \times 9))) \\
 12833 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3) + (4 \times 56)) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 12834 &:= ((1 + (23 \times 4)) \times -((5 \times -((6 \times 7)) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 12835 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3^4) - 5))) \times -((6 + 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 12836 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
 12837 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
 12838 &:= ((1 + ((23 \times 4) + 5)) \times -((6 \times -7) - 89)) \\
 12839 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3 \times (45 \times 6)) - 7) \times 8)) + 9)) \\
 12840 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5 + 6))) \times (7 - (8 + 9))) \\
 12841 &:= (((12^3) \times 45) / 6) + (7 \times -((8 + 9))) \\
 12842 &:= (-1 - ((23 \times -((4 + 5) \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\
 12843 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -((4 + 5) \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\
 12844 &:= (1 - ((23 \times -((4 + 5) \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\
 12845 &:= ((1 - (2 + 34)) \times (((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times -8) + 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 12804 &:= (((9 + (87 + 6)) - 5) \times -((4 \times -((32 + 1)))) \\
 12805 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times (65 \times 4))) \times -((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\
 12806 &:= (9 + (8 - (((7 + 6) - ((5^4) - 3)) \times 21))) \\
 12807 &:= (9 \times -((8 \times -((7 + 6) \times 5)) - (43 \times 21))) \\
 12808 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) / 3^2) + 1)) \\
 12809 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (((7 \times 6) + (5 - (4 + 3)))^2))) \times 1) \\
 12810 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(((7 \times 6) + (5 - (4 + 3)))^2)) - 1)) \\
 12811 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 + 5^4))) / ((3^2) - 1)) \\
 12812 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - (7 \times (65 \times (4 - 32)))) \times 1) \\
 12813 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 + 5^4))) / ((3^2) - 1)) \\
 12814 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times -43) \times -((2 \times -1)) \\
 12815 &:= (-9 - (8 \times -(((7 + (65 \times 4)) \times (3 \times 2) + 1))) \\
 12816 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 + (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
 12817 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 + (65 \times 4)) \times (3 \times 2) - 1))) \\
 12818 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 \times -((65 + 43)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 12819 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 76) - (5 - (4 + 3))) \times -21)) \\
 12820 &:= (((-98 / -7) + 6) \times -((5 \times -((4^3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
 12821 &:= ((((-98 / 7) - 6) \times -((5^4) + 321)) \\
 12822 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((765 - (4 \times 3))) + 21) \\
 12823 &:= (-9 - (((87 - 6) \times 5) - 4) \times -((32 \times 1))) \\
 12824 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 + (65 \times 4)) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
 12825 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 + (65 \times 4)) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\
 12826 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 + (65 \times 4)) \times (3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
 12827 &:= (9 + (8 + ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times ((4^3) - (2 + 1)))) \\
 12828 &:= (((-987 \times -((6 - 5) + (4 \times 3))) - 2) - 1) \\
 12829 &:= (((-987 \times -((6 - 5) + (4 \times 3))) - 2) \times 1) \\
 12830 &:= (98 + ((7 \times -((6 \times 5) - (43^2))) - 1)) \\
 12831 &:= ((98 - 7) \times -((6 \times -((5 + 4) \times 3)) + 21)) \\
 12832 &:= (98 + ((7 \times -((6 \times 5) - (43^2))) + 1)) \\
 12833 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (((5^4) + 3) / -2) + 1)) \\
 12834 &:= ((9 + ((87 - 6) \times 5)) \times -(((4^3) / -2) + 1)) \\
 12835 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 \times -((65 + 43)) + (2 - 1))) \\
 12836 &:= (-987 - ((6 \times -((5 + 43)^2)) + 1)) \\
 12837 &:= ((987 - (6 \times ((5 + 43)^2))) \times -1) \\
 12838 &:= (98 \times (((7 + 65) - 4) + (3 \times 21))) \\
 12839 &:= (98 + ((7 \times -((65 \times (4 - 32))) + 1)) \\
 12840 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 - (543 - 2)) \times -1)) \\
 12841 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((7 + ((6 - 543) \times (2 + 1)))))) \\
 12842 &:= (9 - (((87 - 6) \times 5) - 4) \times -32) - 1) \\
 12843 &:= (9 - ((87 + 6) \times -((5 + (4^3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
 12844 &:= (9 - (((87 + 6) \times -((5 + (4^3)) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
 12845 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times ((4 \times -((3^2) + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
12846 &:= (12 - ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times -((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
12847 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3 + (4 + 5)) \times (67 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
12848 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -(4 + ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times 89)))) \\
12849 &:= (1 - ((2^3) \times -(4 + ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times 89)))) \\
12850 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times 3^4) - (5 + 6)) \times -(7 - (8 + 9)))) \\
12851 &:= (1 + (((2 \times 3^4) - (5 + 6)) \times -(7 - (8 + 9)))) \\
12852 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -(4 \times ((5 - 6) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
12853 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (45 \times (6 + 7))) - 8) - 9) \\
12854 &:= ((1 + ((2 + ((3 + 4)^5)) \times (6 + 7)))/(8 + 9)) \\
12855 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 + ((4^5) + 6)) \times (7 \times 8))))/ - 9) \\
12856 &:= (1 - (((23 - (4 - 5)) \times -(67 \times 8)) + 9)) \\
12857 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3 \times (45 \times 6)) - 7) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
12858 &:= (1 \times - (2 \times - (3 + ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))))) \\
12859 &:= (1 - (2 \times - (3 + ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))))) \\
12860 &:= (1 \times ((23 \times -(4 - 567)) - 89)) \\
12861 &:= ((1 + 2) \times - (3 \times - ((4 \times (5 \times 67)) + 89))) \\
12862 &:= (1 - ((234 \times -((56 + 7) - 8)) + 9)) \\
12863 &:= (((12^3)/(4 + 5)) \times 67) + (8 - 9)) \\
12864 &:= (((12^3) - (4 \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
12865 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3 \times (4 \times (5 + 6)))) \times -(7 + 89))) \\
12866 &:= (1 \times - (2 \times - (((3 \times (45 \times 6)) - 7) \times 8) + 9)) \\
12867 &:= (1 - (2 \times - (((3 \times (45 \times 6)) - 7) \times 8) + 9)) \\
12868 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times (3 + 4)) \times (5^6)) + 7))/ - (8 + 9)) \\
12869 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 \times 4) + ((5^6) \times 7))))/ - (8 + 9)) \\
12870 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 \times (4 \times 5)) + 6) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
12871 &:= (1 \times - (((2 \times 3) + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9) \\
12872 &:= (1 \times - ((2^3) \times -((4 \times ((56 \times 7) + 8)) + 9))) \\
12873 &:= ((1 + 2) \times - (((3^4) + 5) \times (6 - (7 \times 8))) + 9) \\
12874 &:= ((1 + ((23 - (4 - 5)) \times (67 \times 8))) + 9) \\
12875 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times ((5 + 6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
12876 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times 6))) - (7 \times -89)) \\
12877 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times -(5 - (67 + (8 + 9)))) \\
12878 &:= (1 \times (2 \times (((3^4) + 56) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
12879 &:= ((1 + ((2 - 34) \times 5)) \times -((6 - (7 + 8)) \times -9)) \\
12880 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^4)) \times -((5 \times -((6 \times 7) - 8)) + 9)) \\
12881 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times ((6 \times 78) + 9)))))) \\
12882 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) \times -4) - 5) \times ((6 \times -7) - (8 \times 9))) \\
12883 &:= (1 - (2 \times - (((3^4) + 5) \times (67 + 8)) - 9)) \\
12884 &:= (1 \times - (2 \times - (34 + ((5 + 67) \times 89)))) \\
12885 &:= ((12 + 3) \times (4 + ((5 + (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9))) \\
12886 &:= (1 \times - ((2 + (3 \times (4 \times (56 + 7)))) \times -(8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
12846 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times (65 + 4))) \times 3)) + 21) \\
12847 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4))/3^2)))) \times -1) \\
12848 &:= (((987 - 6) + (5^4)) \times ((3^2) - 1)) \\
12849 &:= (((98 - 7) - (6 \times ((5 + 4)^3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
12850 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times ((6 - 5) + (4 \times 321))) \\
12851 &:= ((-9 + 8765) + ((4^{3 \times 2} - 1)) \\
12852 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) \times -((4 - 32) \times 1)) \\
12853 &:= (9 - (8 + (7 \times (((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) + 21)))) \\
12854 &:= (-98 - (7 - ((6 \times (5 \times 432)) - 1))) \\
12855 &:= (((98 + 7) - (6 \times (5 \times 432))) \times -1) \\
12856 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - (((6 \times 5^4)/3)))/ - 21) \\
12857 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4))/3^2)) - 1))) \\
12858 &:= ((987 + ((6^5) + (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1) \\
12859 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times (65 \times 4))) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
12860 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times (6 + (5 \times (4^{3+2-1})))) \\
12861 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 + (4^3)))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
12862 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (76 + ((5 + 4)^3)))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
12863 &:= ((-9 - 87) - ((6 \times - (5 \times 432)) + 1)) \\
12864 &:= (9 - ((8 \times - (7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4))/3^2)))) + 1)) \\
12865 &:= (9 + (8 \times - (7 - (6 \times ((54 \times (3 + 2)) - 1)))))) \\
12866 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4))/3^2)))) + 1)) \\
12867 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 76) - 5) \times (4^3)))/(2 + 1)) \\
12868 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times ((6 + 5) - (43^2)))) - 1)) \\
12869 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) + 21))) \\
12870 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - 6) \times - (5 \times -((4 \times 3)^2) - 1)) \\
12871 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) - (2 + 1))) \\
12872 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((7 \times -(((6 - 5) \times 43^2)) - 1)) \\
12873 &:= (((98 + 7) - ((6^5)/4)) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
12874 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (((5^4) + 3)/ - (2 \times 1))) \\
12875 &:= (-98 + (7 + (6 \times ((5 \times 432) + 1)))) \\
12876 &:= (9 + (8 - (7 \times ((6 + 5) - ((43^2) - 1)))))) \\
12877 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -765) + ((4^3) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
12878 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -765) + (((4^3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
12879 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times ((5 + 4) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
12880 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5)) \times (4 \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
12881 &:= ((9 - 87) - ((6 \times - (5 \times 432)) + 1)) \\
12882 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 \times -((6 + 5) - (43^2))) - 1)) \\
12883 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times ((6 + 5) - (43^2)))) \times 1) \\
12884 &:= (9 + (8 - ((7 \times ((6 + 5) - (43^2)))) - 1)) \\
12885 &:= (9 - (87 \times -((6 - 5) + ((4 + 3) \times 21)))) \\
12886 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 \times - (65 + 43)) - (2 \times 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
12887 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3 \times (4 \times (56 + 7)))) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
12888 &:= ((12^3) - (4 \times -(5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
12889 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) - (4^5)) \times -(6 + 7)) + (8 \times -9)) \\
12890 &:= (1 \times (2 - ((3 + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
12891 &:= (1 + (2 - ((3 + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
12892 &:= ((1 - 23) \times (((4 + 5) \times -67) + (8 + 9))) \\
12893 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) - 6789))) \\
12894 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3^4) + (5 + (6 \times (78 \times 9))))) \\
12895 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3 \times (45 \times 6))) - 7) \times -8) + 9) \\
12896 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3 \times (45 \times 6))) - 7) \times -8) + 9) \\
12897 &:= (1 \times -(((234 + 5) \times 6) + (7 - 8)) \times -9) \\
12898 &:= (1 - (((234 + 5) \times 6) + (7 - 8)) \times -9) \\
12899 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times -(4 \times (5 \times (6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9))))) \\
12900 &:= ((1 + (2^{3+4})) \times ((5 + ((6 + 7) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
12901 &:= (1 - ((2 + (34 \times 5)) \times -((6 + 78) - 9))) \\
12902 &:= (1 - ((23 - 4) \times -(56 + (7 \times 89)))) \\
12903 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 - (4^{5+6-7})) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
12904 &:= (1 + (23 \times (((4 \times 5) + (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
12905 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6))) - (7 \times -89)) \\
12906 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6)))) - (7 \times -89)) \\
12907 &:= (1 \times (2 - ((3 + (4 \times (5 - (6 \times 7)))) \times 89))) \\
12908 &:= (1 + (2 - ((3 + (4 \times (5 - (6 \times 7)))) \times 89))) \\
12909 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 + 4) \times -((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8))) + 9)) \\
12910 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 3^4) - 5) \times -((6 \times (7 + 8))/9))) \\
12911 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3^4) - 5) \times -((6 \times (7 + 8))/9))) \\
12912 &:= ((1 + 23) \times -((4 \times 5) - ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
12913 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3 \times (45 \times 6))) - 7) \times -8) - 9) \\
12914 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3 \times (45 \times 6))) - 7) \times -8) - 9) \\
12915 &:= (1 \times -(((234 + 5) \times 6) - (7 - 8)) \times -9) \\
12916 &:= (1 - (((234 + 5) \times 6) - (7 - 8)) \times -9) \\
12917 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 + ((4^5) \times 6))) - (7 \times 89))) \\
12918 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) + ((6^7)/-(8 \times 9))) \\
12919 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 + 4)^5) - ((6^7)/(8 \times 9)))) \\
12920 &:= (((1 + ((2 \times 3^4)) - 5) \times -((6 \times (7 + 8))/ -9)) \\
12921 &:= (1 \times ((2 + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6^7)/(8 \times 9)))) \\
12922 &:= (1 + ((2 + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6^7)/(8 \times 9)))) \\
12923 &:= (1 + (2 - (34 \times (5 \times ((6 + 7) - 89)))) \\
12924 &:= ((1 - ((2^3) \times 45)) \times (6 \times -((7 + 8) - 9))) \\
12925 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times ((5 + 6) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
12926 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) + (45 \times 6)) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
12927 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3^4) + 5) \times -(6 - (7 \times 8))) + 9) \\
12928 &:= (1 - (((((2 + 3) \times 45) + 6) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
12887 &:= (98 + (((7 + 6) - ((5^4) - 3)) \times -21)) \\
12888 &:= ((9 - ((87 - 6) \times (5 \times 4))) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
12889 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 - 43)) - 2)))) \times 1) \\
12890 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 - 43)) - 2)))) + 1) \\
12891 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + (6 + 5)) \times (4^3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
12892 &:= (-9 + ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times -(5 - ((43^2) - 1)))) \\
12893 &:= (((-9 - (87 - 6543)) \times 2) - 1) \\
12894 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (6 - (5 \times (432 - 1)))) \\
12895 &:= (((-9 - (87 - 6543)) \times 2) + 1) \\
12896 &:= (((98 + 7) - (6 - 5)) \times -(4 \times -(32 - 1))) \\
12897 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((7 \times ((6 \times (5 - 43)) - 2)) - 1))) \\
12898 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 + ((5 + 4)^3)))) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
12899 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times (5 - (43^2)))) \times -1) \\
12900 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times ((6 \times 5) \times ((4^3) - 21))) \\
12901 &:= ((9 - ((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times 4)) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
12902 &:= (-9 + (((87 - 6543) \times -2) - 1)) \\
12903 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 76) + ((5 + 4) - 3)) \times -21)) \\
12904 &:= ((98 - (7 + 6543)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
12905 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((7 + 6) - (5 \times (4 + 321)))))) \\
12906 &:= (9 \times ((8 + 7) + ((6 + 5) \times ((4 \times 32) + 1)))) \\
12907 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times -((5 \times 432) - 1))) \\
12908 &:= (98 - ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times -((4^3) - (2 + 1)))) \\
12909 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times (65 + (4 \times 3)))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
12910 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times -(5 - ((43^2) - 1)))) \\
12911 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (765 + 43))) \times 2) + 1) \\
12912 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times (((6 + 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
12913 &:= ((9 - ((8 - 76) \times 5)) \times -((4 \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
12914 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6 \times -(5 \times 432)) - 1)) \\
12915 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (5 \times -((4^3) - (2 - 1)))) \\
12916 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -(4^3)) - 21)) \\
12917 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times -(5 - (43^2 \times 1)))) \\
12918 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 - 6)) \times -(5 - (43^2))) + 1)) \\
12919 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times -((5 \times 432) + 1))) \\
12920 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times -(5 \times 43)) - (2 \times 1))) \\
12921 &:= (9 + ((87 - 6543) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
12922 &:= ((98 - 7) \times (((6 - 54) \times -3) - (2 \times 1))) \\
12923 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 - (6 \times (5 \times (432 - 1)))))) \\
12924 &:= (((9 + (8 + 76)) + (5^4)) \times -(3 - 21)) \\
12925 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 \times -((5 + 43) - 2)) + 1)) \\
12926 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times ((6 - 5) \times 43^2))) \times -1) \\
12927 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + (5 + 4)))) \times (32 - 1)) \\
12928 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 - 6543)) \times (2 \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
12929 &:= (((12^3) - ((4 \times (5 \times 6) - 7)) \times 8) + 9) & 12929 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 - 65) \times 4))) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
12930 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 \times ((4 \times (5 + (67 \times 8))) - 9)))) & 12930 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 \times -((6 - 5) - ((43^2) - 1)))) \\
12931 &:= ((12 + ((3 + 4)^5)) + ((6^7) / - (8 \times 9))) & 12931 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (6 \times -(5 \times (432 - 1)))) \\
12932 &:= ((1 + ((2 - (3 - 4)^5)) \times ((6 + (7 \times 8) - 9))) & 12932 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times ((5 \times -((4 + 3)^2)) + 1)) \\
12933 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -((4 \times -5) - ((6 \times 78) - 9))) & 12933 &:= (9 + (((87 + 6) + (5^4)) \times -(3 - 21))) \\
12934 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (4^5))) + 6789) & 12934 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times -((4 \times (3 \times 2)) + 1))) \\
12935 &:= ((1 - ((2 - ((3 + 4) \times 5) \times 6)) \times ((7 \times 8) + 9)) & 12935 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (4^3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
12936 &:= (1 + (2 - ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 - 78)))) \times 9))) & 12936 &:= (((9 + 87) - ((6^5)/4)) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
12937 &:= (1 \times (((2^{3 \times 4 - 5}) \times 6) - 7) \times (8 + 9))) & 12937 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times ((6 - 5) - (43^2))) - 1)) \\
12938 &:= (1 + (((2^{3 \times 4 - 5}) \times 6) - 7) \times (8 + 9))) & 12938 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times ((6 - 5) - (43^2))) - 1)) \\
12939 &:= (1 \times (((((2 - 34) \times 5) - 6) \times -78) - 9)) & 12939 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (4^3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
12940 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times 3)^4) + (5 - 6))) \times (7 - (8 + 9))) & 12940 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6^5 - 4^3) - 2) \times -1)) \\
12941 &:= (1 \times (((23 - (4^5)) \times -(6 + 7)) - (8 \times 9))) & 12941 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -765) - 43) - 21) \\
12942 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - (5 \times 6)) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)) & 12942 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - 6) \times -((5 \times -((4 \times 3)^2)) + 1)) \\
12943 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3^4) \times (5 + (67 + 8))) - 9))) & 12943 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -(((6 - 5) \times 43^2)) + 1)) \\
12944 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^3) - (4^5)) \times -(6 + 7)) - 8) - 9) & 12944 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6 - 5) \times 43^2)) - 1)) \\
12945 &:= ((12 + 3) \times ((4 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) - 9)) & 12945 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -(((6 - 5) \times 43^2)) - 1)) \\
12946 &:= (1 - (((((2 + 3) \times 45) + 6) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9)) & 12946 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 \times -((6 - 5) - ((43^2) - 1)))) \\
12947 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3 + (4^5)) \times 6)) - (7 \times 89))) & 12947 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 - (6 \times ((5 \times 432) - 1)))) \\
12948 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times 6))) - (7 \times -89)) & 12948 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
12949 &:= ((1 - ((23 \times (4 - 567)) - 8)) - 9) & 12949 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -((6 - 5) + (43^2))) + 1)) \\
12950 &:= ((1 + (2 + 34)) \times (5 + ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) & 12950 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) \times -((4 \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
12951 &:= (((12^3) \times 45) / 6) + ((7 - 8) \times 9)) & 12951 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times ((6 - 5) + (43^2)))) \times -1)) \\
12952 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times (45 \times 6)))) \times -(7 - (8 - 9))) & 12952 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times ((6 \times (54 \times (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\
12953 &:= (1 - ((2^3) + (4 \times (5 \times ((6 - 78) \times 9)))) & 12953 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 \times -((6 - (((5^4) \times 3) - 21)))) \\
12954 &:= ((1 - ((2^3) \times (45 \times 6))) \times -((7 + 8) - 9)) & 12954 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times ((6 - 5) - (43^2))) - 1)) \\
12955 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times 6))) - (78 \times -9)) & 12955 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (6 \times -((5 \times 432) - 1))) \\
12956 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) + (4 \times (5 \times ((6 - 78) \times 9)))) & 12956 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - (7 + 6543)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
12957 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - 5) \times 6) + ((7 + 8) \times -9)) & 12957 &:= ((98 - (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
12958 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) \times 5)) \times (6 - (7 - (8 - 9)))) & 12958 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (((4^3) - 2) \times -1)) \\
12959 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((34 \times 5) - 6) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 12959 &:= (9 - ((8 - ((7 - 6)^5)) \times -((43^2) + 1))) \\
12960 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^3) - (4^5)) \times -(6 + 7)) + 8) - 9) & 12960 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - 6) \times -((5 \times -((4 \times 3)^2 \times 1))) \\
12961 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^3) - (4^5)) \times -(6 + 7)) \times -(8 - 9)) & 12961 &:= (9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 \times ((54 \times (3 + 2)) + 1)))) \\
12962 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times 5)) \times -(6 - (7 - (8 - 9)))) & 12962 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - ((6 \times -(5 \times 432)) - 1)) \\
12963 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 + 4) \times -((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)) & 12963 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (65 + (4 \times 3)))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
12964 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (3 - (4 \times (5 \times ((6 - 78) \times 9)))) & 12964 &:= (98 + (7 \times -((6 + 5) - (43^2 \times 1)))) \\
12965 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) - (4 \times (5 \times ((6 - 78) \times 9)))) & 12965 &:= (98 + ((7 \times -((6 + 5) - (43^2))) + 1)) \\
12966 &:= ((1 + ((2^3) \times (45 \times 6))) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)) & 12966 &:= ((98 - ((7 \times (6 + (5^4))) + 3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
12967 &:= ((((((12^3) \times 45) / -6) - 7) \times (8 - 9)) & 12967 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 \times -((6 - 5) + (43^2 \times 1)))) \\
12968 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times (45 \times 6)))) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) & 12968 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -((6 \times -(54 \times (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\
12969 &:= ((1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5))) \times ((6 \times -7) - 89)) & 12969 &:= (((9 + 8) + (76 \times 5)) - 4) \times (32 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 12970 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5 - 6)) \times -(7 - (8 + 9))) & 12970 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6^5)/ - ((4 \times 3)/2) - 1)) \\
 12971 &:= (1 \times ((2 - (3^4) + (5 \times 6))) \times -(7 \times (8 + 9))) & 12971 &:= (((98 - 7) - ((6^5)/4)) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
 12972 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3^4) + (5 + 6)) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) & 12972 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (6 \times -(((5 + 43) - 2) \times 1))) \\
 12973 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - 5) \times 6) + (7 \times -(8 + 9))) & 12973 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times -(4 + (3 + 21)))) \\
 12974 &:= (12345 + (6 + (7 \times 89))) & 12974 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 \times -((6 - 5) + ((43^2) + 1)))) \\
 12975 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -(4 - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 12975 &:= (((9 + (876 \times 5)) - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 12976 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times 5))) \times (6 - (7 - (8 + 9)))) & 12976 &:= (9 + ((8 - 7) + (6 \times ((5 \times 432) + 1)))) \\
 12977 &:= ((((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times 45))) \times 6) + 7) \times 8) + 9 & 12977 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 - (6 - 5))^4) \times -(3^2) + 1))) \\
 12978 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^3) - (4^5)) \times -(6 + 7)) + 8) + 9) & 12978 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - 6) \times -((5 \times -((4 \times 3)^2) - 1)) \\
 12979 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3^4) + ((5 + 67) \times 89)))) & 12979 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - 4) \times (3 \times 21)))) \\
 12980 &:= (((1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) - (5 - 6)) \times -(7 - (8 + 9))) & 12980 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6^{5-4+3}) + 2) \times -1)) \\
 12981 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(34 - ((56 - 7) \times 89))) & 12981 &:= ((9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 12982 &:= ((-1 + 23) + (4 \times -(5 \times ((6 - 78) \times 9)))) & 12982 &:= ((9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
 12983 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9) & 12983 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 + (6 \times (5 \times 432))) - 1)) \\
 12984 &:= (1 - (((2^3) + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9) & 12984 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) + 2)) - 1)) \\
 12985 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6)))) - (78 \times -9)) & 12985 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) + 2)) - 1)) \\
 12986 &:= ((1 + (234 \times 56)) + (7 \times -(8 + 9))) & 12986 &:= ((9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
 12987 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) \times 6) + ((7 + 8) \times -9) & 12987 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) + 2)) + 1)) \\
 12988 &:= ((1 - ((2 - ((3^4) + (5 \times 6))) \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)) & 12988 &:= (9 - (((8 - (7 - 6)) \times -5 + (43^2))) - 1)) \\
 12989 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 - 78)))) \times 9))) & 12989 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 + 54))) \times -(32 - 1)) \\
 12990 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 - 78)))) \times 9))) & 12990 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -((65 \times -4 \times (3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
 12991 &:= (1 \times -((((2 + 3)^4)/5) \times -((6 + 7) \times 8)) + 9) & 12991 &:= (9 - (8 + (((7 \times (6 - (5^4))) + 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 12992 &:= (1 - (((((2 + 3)^4)/5) \times -((6 + 7) \times 8)) + 9)) & 12992 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) + 2) - 1))) \\
 12993 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 \times (4 \times (5 + (67 \times 8)))) - 9)) & 12993 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) + 2) - 1))) \\
 12994 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(3 \times (4 \times (5 + (67 \times 8)))) - 9)) & 12994 &:= (((9^{8+7-6-5}) - (4^3)) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
 12995 &:= (1 \times (23 \times -((4 \times 56) - 789))) & 12995 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3))) - 21) \\
 12996 &:= ((1 + ((2^3) \times 45)) \times -(6 \times -((7 + 8) - 9))) & 12996 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
 12997 &:= ((1 - (((23 - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) + 8)) - 9) & 12997 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 12998 &:= ((1 - (2 \times 34)) \times -(5 + ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9))) & 12998 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
 12999 &:= (12 - ((3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 - 78)))) \times -9)) & 12999 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 \times -((6 - (5^4)) \times 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
 13000 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) + 5)) \times ((6 \times (7 + 8)) / -9)) & 13000 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 \times -((6 - (5^4)) \times 3)) + (2 - 1))) \\
 13001 &:= (1 \times -((((2^3) + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9)) & 13001 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 \times -((6 - (5^4)) \times 3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 13002 &:= (1 - (((2^3) + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9) & 13002 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
 13003 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) \times 6) + (7 \times -(8 + 9)) & 13003 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) + 2)) + 1)) \\
 13004 &:= ((-123 \times -((4 + (5 + 6)) \times 7)) + 89) & 13004 &:= (9 + (((87 + 65)/4) \times 3^2) - 1)) \\
 13005 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3^4) - 5))) \times ((6 + 7) + (8 \times 9))) & 13005 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 - ((6 + 5^4))) / 3)) / - (2 + 1)) \\
 13006 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 - 78)))) \times -9)) & 13006 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) - (2 - 1)))) \\
 13007 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3 \times (45 \times 6))) + 7) \times -8) + 9) & 13007 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) - (2 - 1)))) \\
 13008 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3 \times (45 \times 6))) + 7) \times -8) + 9) & 13008 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 \times (6 - (5^4))) - 3) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
 13009 &:= (1 \times -((((2 + 3)^4)/5) \times -((6 + 7) \times 8)) - 9) & 13009 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) + 2) - 1))) \\
 13010 &:= (1 - (((((2 + 3)^4)/5) \times -((6 + 7) \times 8)) - 9)) & 13010 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 + 6)) \times (5^4)) / - (3 + 2)) - 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13011 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) + 5) \times -((6 \times (7 + 8))/9)) & 13011 &:= (9 - (((8 - (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times -3) + 21)) \\
13012 &:= (1 - (((((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times - (6 + (7 + 8))) + 9)) & 13012 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) - 2)) - 1)) \\
13013 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - 5) \times 6) - 7) + (8 \times -9)) & 13013 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) - 2)) - 1)) \\
13014 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((((3^4) - (5 + 6)) \times 7) - 8) \times -9)) & 13014 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) - 2)) + 1)) \\
13015 &:= ((1 - (((23 - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) + 8)) + 9) & 13015 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) - 2)) + 1)) \\
13016 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3 \times 45)) \times -(((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9))) & 13016 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 - ((6 + 5)^4)))/(3^2)) + 1)) \\
13017 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + 5) \times 6) + ((7 + 8) \times -9)) & 13017 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times 3)) + (2 - 1))) \\
13018 &:= (1 \times (23 \times - (4 - (5 \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))))) & 13018 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
13019 &:= (1 + (23 \times - (4 - (5 \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))))) & 13019 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\
13020 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + 5)) \times -((6 \times (7 + 8))/ -9)) & 13020 &:= ((98 - (7 \times (6 + ((5^4) + 3)))) \times - (2 + 1)) \\
13021 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 + 4)) \times (5^6)))/(7 + 8) - 9) & 13021 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -((6 + 5) + (43^2))) - 1)) \\
13022 &:= ((1 - (23 \times (4 - 567))) - (8 \times -9)) & 13022 &:= (9 - (8 - ((7 \times ((6 + 5) + (43^2))) + 1))) \\
13023 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 \times -(((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) & 13023 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) - (2 - 1)))) \\
13024 &:= ((1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 + (5^6))))/ - ((7 + 8) - 9)) & 13024 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 76) \times 5) - 4)) \times (32 \times -1)) \\
13025 &:= ((((((12^3) \times 45)/6) - 7) - (8 \times -9)) & 13025 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((7 \times (6 - (5^4))) - 3) \times - (2 + 1))) \\
13026 &:= (((1 - 23) + (4^5)) \times ((6 + 7) \times - (8 - 9))) & 13026 &:= ((9 - 87) \times -((6 + (54 \times 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
13027 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - 5) \times 6) + 7) + (8 \times -9)) & 13027 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times 4)) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
13028 &:= ((((-12 - 3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) - 89) & 13028 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 \times -((6 + 5) + ((43^2) + 1)))) \\
13029 &:= (1 \times -((((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times - (6 + (7 + 8))) - 9) & 13029 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) - 2)) - 1)) \\
13030 &:= (1 - (((((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times - (6 + (7 + 8))) - 9)) & 13030 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 \times -(((6 + 5) + (43^2)) - 1))) \\
13031 &:= ((1 - (((23 - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) - 8)) + 9) & 13031 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) - 2)) + 1)) \\
13032 &:= ((1 + 23) \times -(((4 + (5 \times (6 + 7))) \times -8) + 9)) & 13032 &:= (9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times - (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
13033 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^3) - (4^5)) \times - (6 + 7)) - (8 \times -9)) & 13033 &:= (98 + ((7 \times -(((6 - 5) - (43^2))) - 1)) \\
13034 &:= (1 \times - (2 \times ((3 + 4) \times (5 - ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 13034 &:= (9 - (((8 - (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times -3) - (2 \times 1))) \\
13035 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times -((5 + 6) \times - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 13035 &:= (9 - (((8 - (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times -3) - (2 + 1))) \\
13036 &:= (((1 + (234 \times 56)) - 78) + 9) & 13036 &:= (9 + ((8 + (7 \times ((6 + 5) + (43^2)))) - 1)) \\
13037 &:= ((-1 - (23 \times (4 - 567))) + 89) & 13037 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times ((6 + 5) + (43^2)))) \times -1)) \\
13038 &:= (123 \times (4 + ((5 - (6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 13038 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 \times - (4^3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
13039 &:= ((((((12^3) \times 45)/6) + 7) - (8 \times -9)) & 13039 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((7 + 6) \times - (5 - (43 + 21)))) \\
13040 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times -((56/ -7) - (8 \times 9))) & 13040 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -(((6 - 5) \times 43^2)) + 1)) \\
13041 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times ((4 - (5 + 6)) \times - (78 - 9))) & 13041 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 - 6) - ((5^4) - 3)) \times -21)) \\
13042 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -((3 + 4)^5)) + (6^{7+8-9})) & 13042 &:= (9 - (8 + (((7 - 6) - ((5^4) - 3)) \times 21))) \\
13043 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) \times 6) - 7) + (8 \times -9)) & 13043 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((765 + 4) - 3)) + 21) \\
13044 &:= (12 \times ((3 + (4^5)) - (6 \times (7 - (8 + 9)))))) & 13044 &:= (9 - (87 - (6 \times (((5 + 4)^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
13045 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - 5) \times 6) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & 13045 &:= (((9 + 8) - (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3))/2)) \times -1) \\
13046 &:= (1 - (2 - ((34 \times ((56 \times 7) - 8)) - 9))) & 13046 &:= ((98 - 76) \times -(((5^4) - 32) \times -1)) \\
13047 &:= ((1 - 2) \times ((34 \times -((56 \times 7) - 8)) + 9)) & 13047 &:= (9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6 - ((5^4) + 3)))) \times - (2 + 1))) \\
13048 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) \times - (4 - (5 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) & 13048 &:= (98 - (7 \times -((6 - 5) + (43^2 \times 1)))) \\
13049 &:= (1 + ((2^3) \times - (4 - (5 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) & 13049 &:= ((9 + ((8 - ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3))/2)) \times -1) \\
13050 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^3) - (4^5)) \times - (6 + 7)) + 89) & 13050 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times - (3 \times - (2 - 1))) \\
13051 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^{4+5+6-7}))) + (8 \times -9)) & 13051 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7^6))/ - (5 + 4)) + (32 - 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

13052 := $(1 \times (2 - ((34 - 5) \times ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9))))$
13053 := $(1 + (2 - ((34 - 5) \times ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9))))$
13054 := $(1 \times (2 \times (((3 \times (45 \times 6)) + 7) \times 8) - 9))$
13055 := $(1 + (2 \times (((3 \times (45 \times 6)) + 7) \times 8) - 9))$
13056 := $((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - (5 + 6)) \times ((7 + 8) - 9))$
13057 := $((((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) \times 6) + 7) + (8 \times -9))$
13058 := $(1 \times (2 + (34 \times ((5 \times (67 + 8)) + 9))))$
13059 := $(1 \times (((2 + 3) + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) \times -9))$
13060 := $(1 + (((2 + 3) + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) \times -9))$
13061 := $(1 - ((2 + 3) \times -(4 \times ((5 \times 6) + (7 \times 89)))))$
13062 := $((1 + 2) \times ((3 + 4) \times ((5 - 6) + (7 \times 89))))$
13063 := $(1 \times ((2 \times (((3 \times (45 \times 6)) + 7) \times 8) - 9))$
13064 := $(1 + ((2 \times (((3 \times (45 \times 6)) + 7) \times 8) - 9))$
13065 := $((1 + 2) \times (3 + ((4^{5+6-7}) \times (8 + 9))))$
13066 := $((1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) - 8)) - 9)$
13067 := $((12 - (((3 + 4)^5) - 6) \times 7 + 8) / -9)$
13068 := $((1 - ((2 - (3 - 4))^5)) \times -(6 \times -((7 - 8) \times 9)))$
13069 := $((1 - 2) \times -(((3 + 4)^5) - (6 \times (7 \times 89))))$
13070 := $((1 + (((2 + ((3 + 4)^5) - 6) \times 7) + 8)) / 9)$
13071 := $(1 - ((2 + 3) \times -(4 + (5 \times (6 \times (78 + 9))))))$
13072 := $((1 - 2) - (((3 + 4)^{5-6+7}) + 8) / -9)$
13073 := $((1 - 2) \times (((3 + 4)^{5-6+7}) + 8) / -9)$
13074 := $((1 + 2) \times -(3 + ((4 - (5 + 6)) \times (7 \times 89))))$
13075 := $(1 \times -(2 + ((3 + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))$
13076 := $(1 - (2 + ((3 + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))$
13077 := $((12 - (((3 \times 4) - 5)^6) + (7 \times 8)) / -9)$
13078 := $((1 - (23 + 4)) \times -((5 - 6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9))))$
13079 := $((12 + (((3 + 4)^5) + 6) \times 7 + 8) / 9)$
13080 := $((1 + 2) + ((3 + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) \times -9))$
13081 := $(1 \times ((2 + (((3 \times 4) - 5)^6) + 78)) / 9)$
13082 := $((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - 5) \times 6) + 7 - (8 + 9)$
13083 := $((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - 5) \times 6) + ((7 - 8) \times 9)$
13084 := $((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - 5) \times 6) - 7 + (8 - 9)$
13085 := $((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - 5) \times -6) + 7 \times (8 - 9)$
13086 := $((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - 5) \times 6) - 7 - (8 - 9)$
13087 := $((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + 5) \times 6) + 7 + (8 \times -9)$
13088 := $(1 + (23 \times -(((4 + 5) \times 6) - (7 \times 89))))$
13089 := $(12 + ((3 + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) \times -9))$
13090 := $((1 - 23) \times ((4 - (5 - 6)) \times -(7 \times (8 + 9))))$
13091 := $(1 \times (2 + (3 \times ((4 + (56 \times 78)) - 9))))$
13092 := $(1 \times -(2 \times -((3 \times (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) - 8)) + 9))$

13052 := $(9 + (876 + (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1})))$
13053 := $((9 - ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times ((5^4) - 3))) \times -(2 - 1))$
13054 := $((9 - ((87 + 65) \times 43)) \times (2 \times -1))$
13055 := $((9 - 8) \times (7 \times (((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) / 2) - 1)))$
13056 := $((9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) / 2) - 1)))$
13057 := $(9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6 + (5 \times 4)) \times (3 \times 21))))))$
13058 := $(98 - (((7 - (6 - 5))^4) \times -((3^2) + 1)))$
13059 := $((98 - ((7^6) - (5 \times 4))) / (3 \times -(2 + 1)))$
13060 := $((9 + ((8 - ((7^6) - (5 \times 4))) / (3^2))) \times -1)$
13061 := $((9 - 8) \times (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3)) / 2) - 1)$
13062 := $((9 - 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3)) / 2) - 1)$
13063 := $((9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3)) / -2) - 1)$
13064 := $((9 - 8) - (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3)) / -2) - 1)$
13065 := $((9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 - ((5^4) + 3)))) \times (2 + 1)$
13066 := $((9 - 8) - ((7^6) - 54)) / (3 \times -(2 + 1))$
13067 := $(9 + ((8 - ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3))) / - (2 \times 1)))$
13068 := $((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times (6 - (((5^4) \times 3) - 2))) + 1))$
13069 := $((9 - 8) - ((7 \times (6 - (((5^4) \times 3) - 2))) + 1))$
13070 := $((9 - 8) \times ((7 \times -(6 - (((5^4) \times 3) - 2))) + 1))$
13071 := $((9 - 8) + ((7 \times -(6 - (((5^4) \times 3) - 2))) + 1))$
13072 := $((9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) / 2) - 1)))$
13073 := $((9 + ((8 + (7^6)) / (5 + 4))) + (3 \times -(2 + 1)))$
13074 := $((9 + ((8 + (7^6)) / (5 + 4))) - ((3^2) - 1))$
13075 := $((9 + ((8 + (7^6)) / (5 + 4))) + ((3 \times -2) - 1))$
13076 := $((9 - 8) \times (7 \times -(6 - (((5^4) \times 3) - (2 - 1))))))$
13077 := $((9 - 8) + (7 \times -(6 - (((5^4) \times 3) - (2 - 1))))))$
13078 := $((9 + 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3)) / 2) - 1)$
13079 := $(((9 - 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 \times -(4^3)) + (2 - 1)))$
13080 := $((9 + 8) - (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3)) / -2) - 1)$
13081 := $((9 - 8) \times ((7 \times -(6 - ((5^4) \times 3))) - (2 \times 1)))$
13082 := $(((9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 - ((5^4) \times 3)))) + (2 \times -1))$
13083 := $((9 - 8) + ((7 \times -(6 - ((5^4) \times 3))) - (2 - 1)))$
13084 := $((9 - 8) \times ((7 \times -(6 - ((5^4) \times 3))) + (2 - 1)))$
13085 := $((9 - 8) + ((7 \times -(6 - ((5^4) \times 3))) + (2 - 1)))$
13086 := $(((9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 - ((5^4) \times 3)))) - (2 \times -1))$
13087 := $((9 + 8) + ((7 \times -(6 - (((5^4) \times 3) - 2))) + 1))$
13088 := $((9 + ((8 + (7^6)) / (5 + 4))) - (3 \times -(2 \times 1)))$
13089 := $((9 + ((8 + (7^6)) / (5 + 4))) - ((3 \times -2) - 1))$
13090 := $((9 - 8) \times (7 \times -(6 - (((5^4) \times 3) + (2 - 1))))))$
13091 := $((9 - 8) + (7 \times -(6 - (((5^4) \times 3) + (2 - 1))))))$
13092 := $((9 + ((8 + (7^6)) / (5 + 4))) + ((3^2) + 1))$

$$\begin{aligned}
13093 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 \times (((4+5) - 6)^7) - 8)) + 9))) \\
13094 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (4 + ((56 - 7) \times 89)))))) \\
13095 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -(((4 + (5 + 6)) \times 7) - 8) \times -9)) \\
13096 &:= ((1 + (234 \times 56)) + ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
13097 &:= (((1 + (234 \times 56)) - 7) + (8 - 9)) \\
13098 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - 5) \times 6) + 7) + (8 - 9)) \\
13099 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - 5) \times -6) - 7) \times (8 - 9)) \\
13100 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - 5) \times 6) + 7) - (8 - 9)) \\
13101 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - 5) \times 6) - ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
13102 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - 5) \times 6) - 7) + (8 + 9)) \\
13103 &:= (1 + (((23 - (4^5)) \times -(6 + 7)) + 89)) \\
13104 &:= ((1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times ((5 \times -6) - ((7 - 8) \times 9))) \\
13105 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + 5) \times 6) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
13106 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times -(7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
13107 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7)))) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
13108 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 \times -(4 + (56 \times 78))) + 9)) \\
13109 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3 \times (4 + (56 \times 78)))) - 9)) \\
13110 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times (5 \times -((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
13111 &:= ((1 + ((234 \times 56) + 7)) + (8 - 9)) \\
13112 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) \times 6) + 7) - (8 + 9)) \\
13113 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^{(-4+5) \times 6}))) \times ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
13114 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) \times 6) - 7) + (8 - 9)) \\
13115 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) \times -6) + 7) \times (8 - 9)) \\
13116 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) \times 6) - 7) - (8 - 9)) \\
13117 &:= ((1 - (((2 + (3^{4+5})) \times 6) - (7 \times 8)))/ -9) \\
13118 &:= (1 - (2 + (3 \times (4 - ((56 \times 78) + 9)))))) \\
13119 &:= ((12 + 3) + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times -(7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
13120 &:= ((1 - (((2^3) - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) - 89) \\
13121 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3^{4+5+6-7})) - (8 - 9))) \\
13122 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3^{4+5+6-7})) + 8)) - 9) \\
13123 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^{4+5+6-7}))) \times -(8 - 9)) \\
13124 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^{4+5+6-7}))) - (8 - 9)) \\
13125 &:= ((1 + 2) + (((3^{4+5}) \times 6)/ -((7 - 8) \times 9))) \\
13126 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 \times -(4 + (56 \times 78))) - 9)) \\
13127 &:= ((1 - (((2 - (3^{4+5})) \times 6) - (7 \times 8)))/9) \\
13128 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) \times 6) + 7) + (8 - 9)) \\
13129 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) \times -6) - 7) \times (8 - 9)) \\
13130 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) \times 6) + 7) - (8 - 9)) \\
13131 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^{(-4+5) \times 6}))) \times -((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
13132 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) \times 6) - 7) + (8 + 9)) \\
13133 &:= ((1 + ((23 \times (4 + 567)) + 8)) - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13093 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 \times -(6 - (((5^4) \times 3) - (2 - 1)))))) \\
13094 &:= ((98 - (7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\
13095 &:= ((98 - (7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
13096 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 \times -(6 - (((5^4) \times 3) + 2))) - 1)) \\
13097 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 \times -(6 - (((5^4) \times 3) + 2))) - 1)) \\
13098 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 \times -(6 - (((5^4) \times 3) + 2))) + 1)) \\
13099 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 - (((5^4) \times 3) + 2)))) - 1)) \\
13100 &:= (98 + ((7 \times -((6 - (5^4)) \times 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\
13101 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 \times -(6 - (((5^4) \times 3))) + (2 - 1))) \\
13102 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times (6 - (((5^4) \times 3)))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
13103 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 \times -(6 - (((5^4) \times 3))) + (2 + 1))) \\
13104 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - 6) \times (((5 + 4)^3) - (2 - 1))) \\
13105 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 - (((5^4) \times 3)))) + 21) \\
13106 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - 3)))/ (2 \times -1)) \\
13107 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 \times -(6 - (((5^4) \times 3) + (2 - 1)))))) \\
13108 &:= (((9^{8+7-6-5}) - (4 + 3)) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
13109 &:= ((9 + (((8 + (7 + 6)) - 5)^4))/ -((3 + 2) \times -1)) \\
13110 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times ((5 + (4^3)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
13111 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6) \times -(((5^4) \times -3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
13112 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 + 6)) \times -((5^4) - (3 - 2))) + 1)) \\
13113 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 \times -(6 - (((5^4) \times 3) + 2))) - 1)) \\
13114 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - 3)))/ (2 \times -1)) \\
13115 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 \times -(6 - (((5^4) \times 3) + 2))) + 1)) \\
13116 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (((6 \times ((5 + 4)^3))/ -2) + 1)) \\
13117 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3))/ - (2 + 1)) \\
13118 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6) \times -(((5^4) \times -3) + (2 - 1))) \\
13119 &:= (9 - (((8 - (7 - 6)) \times -(((5^4) \times 3) - 2)) + 1)) \\
13120 &:= (((9^{8+7-6-5}) - (4 - 3)) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
13121 &:= (9 - (((8 \times -7) + 6) - (((5^4) - 3) \times 21))) \\
13122 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - 6) \times -(((5 + 4)^3) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
13123 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 + (6 + 5))^4)/ ((3^2) - 1)))) \\
13124 &:= (((((9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))) - 3)/ - (2 \times -1)) \\
13125 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))/ - (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
13126 &:= (((9 - 8) - (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) + 3)))/ (2 \times -1)) \\
13127 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (5^4))) + ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
13128 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (5^4))) + (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
13129 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (5^4))) + ((3 + 2) \times -1)) \\
13130 &:= (((9^{8+7-6-5}) + 4) \times (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
13131 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (5^4))) + (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
13132 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times ((5^4) \times 3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
13133 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (5^4))) + (3/ - (2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{13134} &:= ((1+2) - ((3 - ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) \times -9)) & \mathbf{13134} &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (5^4))) \times -(3 / - (2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{13135} &:= ((1 + (2 + 34)) \times -(5 \times -((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9)))) & \mathbf{13135} &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (5^4))) - (3 / - (2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{13136} &:= (1 \times (((2^3) - (4^5)) \times -(6 + 7)) - (8 \times 9))) & \mathbf{13136} &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + 3))) / - (2 \times -1)) \\
\mathbf{13137} &:= ((1 - (((2^3) - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) + (8 \times -9)) & \mathbf{13137} &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (5^4))) - (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
\mathbf{13138} &:= (1 + ((2 - (3 \times (45 + 6))) \times -(78 + 9))) & \mathbf{13138} &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (5^4))) + ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
\mathbf{13139} &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - 5) \times 6) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & \mathbf{13139} &:= (((9 - 8)^7 + 6) \times -(((5^4) \times -3) - (2 \times 1))) \\
\mathbf{13140} &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 \times -(4 \times (5 \times ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9)))))) & \mathbf{13140} &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (5^4))) - (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
\mathbf{13141} &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times -(4 - (56 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))))) & \mathbf{13141} &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (5^4))) - ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
\mathbf{13142} &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + 5) \times 6) + (7 - 8)) - 9) & \mathbf{13142} &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) / - (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
\mathbf{13143} &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + 5) \times 6) + ((7 - 8) \times 9)) & \mathbf{13143} &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (5^4))) - (3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{13144} &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + 5) \times 6) - (7 - 8)) - 9) & \mathbf{13144} &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + 3))) / - (2 \times -1)) \\
\mathbf{13145} &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + 5) \times -6) + 7) \times (8 - 9)) & \mathbf{13145} &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7^6)) / (5 + 4))) - (3 \times -21)) \\
\mathbf{13146} &:= ((1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times -((5 \times -6) - ((7 - 8) \times 9))) & \mathbf{13146} &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + (6 \times (((5 + 4)^3) \times (2 + 1)))))) \\
\mathbf{13147} &:= (1 - (2 \times - (3 + (((45 - (6 \times 7))^8) + 9)))) & \mathbf{13147} &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6 + (((5^4) + 3) \times 21))) \\
\mathbf{13148} &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3^{4+5+6-7}) + 8))) + 9) & \mathbf{13148} &:= (987 - (6 - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
\mathbf{13149} &:= (((((12 + 3)^4) / 5) - (6 \times -(7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & \mathbf{13149} &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 - (65 + 4)))) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\
\mathbf{13150} &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times -(5 - ((67 - 8) \times 9))) & \mathbf{13150} &:= ((9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times 4)) \times -(3^2 + 1)) \\
\mathbf{13151} &:= (1 \times -((234 \times -56) - ((7 \times 8) - 9))) & \mathbf{13151} &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - (6543 \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
\mathbf{13152} &:= ((1 + 23) \times -(4 \times -((5 \times (6 + 7)) + (8 \times 9)))) & \mathbf{13152} &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times (5^4))) \times -(3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
\mathbf{13153} &:= ((((-1 - 234) \times -56) - 7) \times -(8 - 9)) & \mathbf{13153} &:= (98 + (7 \times (((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) / 2) - 1))) \\
\mathbf{13154} &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3^4) + 56) \times (7 + 89)))) & \mathbf{13154} &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + (43^2)))) \times -1)) \\
\mathbf{13155} &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) \times -(4 - (5 \times ((67 \times 8) - 9)))))) & \mathbf{13155} &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -((6 \times 5) + (43^2))) - 1)) \\
\mathbf{13156} &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times -(4 - (5 \times ((67 \times 8) - 9)))))) & \mathbf{13156} &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 + 6)) \times -((5^4) + (3 - 2))) - 1)) \\
\mathbf{13157} &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - 5) \times 6) - 7) - (8 \times -9)) & \mathbf{13157} &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + 6)) + (((5^4) - 3) \times 21))) \\
\mathbf{13158} &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + 5) \times 6) + 7) + (8 - 9)) & \mathbf{13158} &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - 6) \times -(((5 + 4)^3) + 2) \times -1)) \\
\mathbf{13159} &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + 5) \times -6) - 7) \times (8 - 9)) & \mathbf{13159} &:= (98 + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3)) / 2) - 1)) \\
\mathbf{13160} &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + 5) \times 6) + (7 - 8)) + 9) & \mathbf{13160} &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 + (6 \times ((5 + 4)^3))) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{13161} &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) - 8) \times -9)) & \mathbf{13161} &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (5^4))) + (3^{2+1})) \\
\mathbf{13162} &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + 5) \times 6) - (7 - 8)) + 9) & \mathbf{13162} &:= ((9 + (((876 \times 5) + 4) \times 3) + 2)) - 1) \\
\mathbf{13163} &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3) - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) + (8 \times -9)) & \mathbf{13163} &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 + ((5^4) \times 3)))) - 21) \\
\mathbf{13164} &:= (1 \times -((2^3) + (4 \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 89)))) & \mathbf{13164} &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(6 + ((5^4) \times 3))) + (2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{13165} &:= (1 - ((2^3) + (4 \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 89)))) & \mathbf{13165} &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(6 + ((5^4) \times 3))) + (2 \times 1))) \\
\mathbf{13166} &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -3) - (4 \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 89)))) & \mathbf{13166} &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times (6 + ((5^4) \times 3)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
\mathbf{13167} &:= (1 + ((2 \times -3) - (4 \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 89)))) & \mathbf{13167} &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -(6 + ((5^4) \times 3))) + (2 - 1))) \\
\mathbf{13168} &:= ((1 - (((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5^6)) / 7) \times 8)) - 9) & \mathbf{13168} &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(6 + ((5^4) \times 3))) - (2 - 1))) \\
\mathbf{13169} &:= (((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) \times 6) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & \mathbf{13169} &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(6 + ((5^4) \times 3))) - (2 \times 1))) \\
\mathbf{13170} &:= (12 - (((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) - 8) \times -9)) & \mathbf{13170} &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times (6 + ((5^4) \times 3)))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
\mathbf{13171} &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - 5) \times 6) + 7) - (8 \times -9)) & \mathbf{13171} &:= (((9 + 8) - (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 3)) / 2)) \times -1) \\
\mathbf{13172} &:= (1 + ((2 - 3) - (4 \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 89)))) & \mathbf{13172} &:= (((-9 \times -8) + ((7 + 6543) \times 2)) \times 1) \\
\mathbf{13173} &:= (1 \times -((234 \times -56) - (78 - 9))) & \mathbf{13173} &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times ((6 + (5^4) - 3))) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{13174} &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times (((4 \times 5) + (6 \times 78)) \times 9)))) & \mathbf{13174} &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 \times -(6 + (((5^4) \times 3) + (2 - 1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13175 &:= (((1+2) - 34) \times (5 \times -((6+7) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
13176 &:= ((1 + ((2 - (3 - 4))^5)) \times (6 \times -((7 - 8) \times 9))) \\
13177 &:= (1 \times ((2+3) - (4 \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 89)))) \\
13178 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -3) + (4 \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 89)))) \\
13179 &:= ((1+2) - (3 \times -(((4 \times 5) + (6 \times 78)) \times 9))) \\
13180 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (((4+5) - 6)^7) + 8))) + 9 \\
13181 &:= (1 - ((2+3) \times -(4 + (56 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
13182 &:= (1 \times - (2 + (((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) + 89))) \\
13183 &:= (1 - (2 + (((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) + 89))) \\
13184 &:= (((12^3) \times ((4^5) + 6)) / - (7 + 8)) / - 9 \\
13185 &:= ((1+2) \times - (3 \times (((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
13186 &:= ((1 - (((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5^6)) / 7) \times 8)) + 9 \\
13187 &:= (((((1+2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) \times 6) - 7) - (8 \times -9)) \\
13188 &:= (((1+2)^{3+4}) + (5+6)) \times ((7+8) - 9) \\
13189 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times - (67 + (8+9)))) \\
13190 &:= (-1 + (234 \times 56)) + (78 + 9) \\
13191 &:= (((1+2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) \times 6) + (78 - 9) \\
13192 &:= ((1 - (((2^3) - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) + 8)) - 9 \\
13193 &:= (1 \times (((2^3) \times -((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8)) + 9)) \\
13194 &:= (1 + (((2^3) \times -((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8)) + 9)) \\
13195 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^{4+5+6-7}))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
13196 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3^4) \times (5 + (6 + 7))) + 8) \times 9))) \\
13197 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3^4) \times (5 + (6 + 7))) + 8) \times 9))) \\
13198 &:= (1 \times - (2 \times - (3 - ((4 - (56 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
13199 &:= (((((1+2)^{3+4}) + 5) \times 6) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
13200 &:= (1 - (2 + (((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
13201 &:= (((((1+2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) \times 6) + 7) - (8 \times -9)) \\
13202 &:= (((1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times ((5 \times -((6 \times 7) - 8)) + 9)) \\
13203 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times -((4 + (5 + 6)) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
13204 &:= (1 + (2 - (((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
13205 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times - (4 + 567)) - (8 \times 9))) \\
13206 &:= (12 - (((3^4) \times (5 + (6 + 7))) + 8) \times -9) \\
13207 &:= ((1 + (((2^3) - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) \times (8 - 9)) \\
13208 &:= ((1 - (((2^3) - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) + (8 - 9)) \\
13209 &:= ((1 - (((2^3) - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) \times - (8 - 9)) \\
13210 &:= ((1 - (((2^3) - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) + 8)) + 9 \\
13211 &:= (((((1+2)^{3+4}) - 5) \times 6) - (7 \times - (8 + 9))) \\
13212 &:= ((1+2) \times - (3 \times - (4 \times (((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9)))) \\
13213 &:= ((12 - ((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
13214 &:= (-12 + ((3 + ((4^5) \times (6 + 7))) - 89)) \\
13215 &:= ((12 + 3) \times - ((4 \times - ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) - 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13175 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 \times - (6 + (((5^4) \times 3) + (2 - 1)))) \\
13176 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - 6) \times (((5 + 4)^3) + (2 + 1))) \\
13177 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + ((43^2) + 1)))) \\
13178 &:= (98 + ((7 \times - (6 - ((5^4) \times 3))) - (2 + 1))) \\
13179 &:= ((98 - (7 \times (6 - ((5^4) \times 3)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
13180 &:= ((9 - 8) \times - ((7 \times - (6 + (((5^4) \times 3) + 2))) + 1)) \\
13181 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times - (6 + (((5^4) \times 3) + 2))) + 1)) \\
13182 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 \times (6 + (((5^4) \times 3) + 2))) + 1)) \\
13183 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 \times (6 + (((5^4) \times 3) + 2))) + 1)) \\
13184 &:= (98 + ((7 \times - (6 - ((5^4) \times 3))) + (2 + 1))) \\
13185 &:= (((9 + 8) + ((7 \times (6 + ((5^4) \times 3))) + 2)) - 1) \\
13186 &:= (((9 + 8) + ((7 \times (6 + ((5^4) \times 3))) + 2)) \times 1) \\
13187 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 3)) / 2) - 1) \\
13188 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 3)) / 2) - 1) \\
13189 &:= ((9 - 8) \times - (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 3)) / - 2) - 1) \\
13190 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 3)) / - 2) - 1) \\
13191 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 \times - (6 + (((5^4) \times 3) + (2 - 1)))) \\
13192 &:= ((9 + 8) \times - ((7 + (6 + 5)) \times -43) - (2 \times 1)) \\
13193 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((76 - (5^4)) \times - (3 + 21))) \\
13194 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times ((5^4) + 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\
13195 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times ((5^4) + 3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
13196 &:= (9 + (((8 + (7 + 6)) \times ((5^4) + 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
13197 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times - (6 + (((5^4) \times 3) + 2))) + 1)) \\
13198 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 + (((5^4) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
13199 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times - (6 + (((5^4) \times 3) + 2))) - 1)) \\
13200 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2) - 1) \\
13201 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6) + (((5^4) + 3) \times 21))) \\
13202 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 \times - (4^3)) - (2 \times 1))) \\
13203 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (76 - (5^4)))) \times - (3 \times - (2 - 1))) \\
13204 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 3)) / 2) - 1) \\
13205 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times - ((5 \times - (4 - 32)) - 1)) \\
13206 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 3)) / - 2) - 1) \\
13207 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (6 - ((5 + 4) \times 32) - 1)) \\
13208 &:= (((9^{8+7-6-5}) + 43) \times - (2 \times -1)) \\
13209 &:= ((98 + (7 + 6)) \times ((5 \times (4 \times (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\
13210 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 - 6) + ((5^4) + 3)) \times 21))) \\
13211 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) + 6) \times - (5 + (4 \times 3))) + 2) \times 1) \\
13212 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times ((4 + 32) \times -1)) \\
13213 &:= (98 - (7 - (6 \times (((5 + 4)^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
13214 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times - ((5 \times 43) - 2)) + 1) \\
13215 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times 3)) - 21)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13216 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) \times -(4 - (((5 \times 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 13216 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times -((5 \times 43) - 2)) - 1) \\
13217 &:= (1 + ((2^3) \times -(4 - (((5 \times 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 13217 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(76 - ((54 \times 32) - 1)))) \\
13218 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3) - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) + 8) - 9) & 13218 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times 3)) \times -(2 - 1)) \\
13219 &:= ((1 - 2) - (3 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) - 89))) & 13219 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((7 \times -(((6 + (5^4)) \times 3) - 2)) + 1)) \\
13220 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (3 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) - 89))) & 13220 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times (((6 + (5^4)) \times 3) - 2))) \times -1) \\
13221 &:= (12 - (((3^4) + (5 \times 6)) \times -(7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 13221 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times ((6 + (5^4)) - 3))) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
13222 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) + 5) \times (6 + (7 + 8))) - 9) & 13222 &:= ((98 - 76) \times ((5^4) - (3 + 21))) \\
13223 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) - 89))) & 13223 &:= (98 - (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) / - (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
13224 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) \times ((4^5) + (6 + (7 \times 89)))))) & 13224 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 + (65 + 43))^2) - 1)) \\
13225 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times -((5 \times -((6 + 7) \times 8)) - 9)) & 13225 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2) \times -1) \\
13226 &:= ((1 - (((2^3) - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) + (8 + 9)) & 13226 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 - 6) + ((5^4) + 3)) \times -21)) \\
13227 &:= (1 \times -((((2 - 3) + (4^5)) \times -(6 + 7)) + (8 \times 9))) & 13227 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) - 3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
13228 &:= ((1 + (((2 - 3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) + (8 \times -9)) & 13228 &:= (((-98 \times -((76 - 5) + (4^3))) - 2) \times 1) \\
13229 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 3) - ((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) - 89))) & 13229 &:= (((-98 \times -((76 - 5) + (4^3))) - 2) + 1) \\
13230 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -((4 \times 5) - (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 13230 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times ((6 + ((5 + 4)^3)) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
13231 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + 5) \times 6) + 7) - (8 \times -9)) & 13231 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + (6 \times 54)) \times (3 + 2)))) \times -1) \\
13232 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) - ((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 \times 9))) & 13232 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 32)) + 1)) \\
13233 &:= (1 - ((2^3) - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 \times 9)))) & 13233 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
13234 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3) - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) - 8) - 9) & 13234 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
13235 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times 3) - (4^5)) \times -(6 + 7)) - (8 - 9)) & 13235 &:= (9 + (((((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + (5 + 4)) / 3)^2) + 1)) \\
13236 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3) - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) + 8) + 9) & 13236 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6 + (5^4)) \times 3) - 2)) + 1)) \\
13237 &:= (1 + (((2 - 3) - (4^5)) \times -(6 + 7)) - 89) & 13237 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -(((6 + (5^4)) \times 3) - 2)) + 1)) \\
13238 &:= (12 + ((3 + ((4^5) \times (6 + 7))) - 89)) & 13238 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
13239 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + 5) \times 6) + (78 + 9)) & 13239 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -(((6 + (5^4)) \times 3) - 2)) - 1)) \\
13240 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 \times 9)))) & 13240 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 + 6)) \times -((5^4) + (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\
13241 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - 3) - ((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 \times 9))) & 13241 &:= (98 - ((7 + (6 \times ((5 + 4)^3)) \times - (2 + 1))) \\
13242 &:= (1 - ((2 - 3) - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 \times 9))) & 13242 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times (6 + (5^4))) - 3) \times - (2 + 1))) \\
13243 &:= (1 \times -((2 + (((3^4) + (5 \times 6)) \times 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) & 13243 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 \times (6 + (5^4))) - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
13244 &:= (1 - ((2 + (((3^4) + (5 \times 6)) \times 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) & 13244 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6 + (5^4)) \times 3) - (2 - 1)))) \\
13245 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) + ((4^5) \times (6 + 7))) - (8 \times 9))) & 13245 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 \times -(((6 + (5^4)) \times 3) - (2 - 1)))) \\
13246 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 + ((4^5) \times (6 + 7))) - (8 \times 9))) & 13246 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 + 6) \times - (5 - (4^{3+2}))) - 1)) \\
13247 &:= ((1 - (((2 + 3) - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) + (8 - 9)) & 13247 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((7 + 6) \times - (5 - (4^{3+2}))) - 1)) \\
13248 &:= ((1 - (((2 + 3) - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) \times -(8 - 9)) & 13248 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times (3 \times - (2 - 1))) \\
13249 &:= ((1 - (((2 + 3) - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) - (8 - 9)) & 13249 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -((6 + (5^4)) \times 3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
13250 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) + (5 \times 6))) \times (7 - (8 + 9))) & 13250 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
13251 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3^4) \times -56) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 13251 &:= (9 - (8 - ((7 \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3)) - (2 - 1)))) \\
13252 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3) - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) - 8) + 9) & 13252 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -((6 + (5^4)) \times 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
13253 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (34 \times 56)) \times -7) + 89)) & 13253 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -((6 + (5^4)) \times 3)) - (2 \times 1))) \\
13254 &:= ((1 - ((23 - 4) \times 5)) \times -(6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) & 13254 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
13255 &:= (((1 - 2) - ((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) - (8 + 9)) & 13255 &:= (9 + (8 + ((7 \times (((6 + (5^4)) \times 3) - 2)) + 1))) \\
13256 &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times -(4 - (5 \times ((67 - 8) \times 9)))))) & 13256 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - 4))) \times ((3^2) - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

13257 := (((1+2)^{3×4-5}) × 6) - ((7+8) × -9)
13258 := (1 + (23 × (4 × ((5 + (6 + 7)) × 8)))) + 9
13259 := (1 - (2 + (3 × (4 - (56 × (7 + (8 × 9)))))))
13260 := ((1 - ((2 × (3⁴)) - 5)) × -((6+7) + (8 × 9)))
13261 := ((12 + ((3 - (4⁵)) × (6 + 7))) × (8 - 9))
13262 := ((-1 + 2) + (((3 × (4 - 56)) + 7) × -89))
13263 := (1 × -((((2 - (3 - 4))⁵) - 6) × -(7 × 8) + 9))
13264 := (1 - (((((2 - (3 - 4))⁵) - 6) × -(7 × 8) + 9)))
13265 := ((1 - (((2 + 3) - (4⁵)) × (6 + 7))) + (8 + 9))
13266 := ((1 + 2) × - (3 × -((4⁵) - ((6 - (7 × 8)) × 9))))
13267 := (((1 + 2)³) - (((4⁵) × -(6 + 7)) + (8 × 9)))
13268 := ((12 - (((3 - (4⁵)) × (6 + 7)) + 8)) - 9)
13269 := ((1 + 2) × ((3 - 4) + (56 × (7 + (8 × 9)))))
13270 := (((1 + 2) + ((3 - (4⁵)) × (6 + 7))) × (8 - 9))
13271 := (((1 - 2) - ((3 - (4⁵)) × (6 + 7))) + (8 - 9))
13272 := (((1 - 2) - ((3 - (4⁵)) × (6 + 7))) × -(8 - 9))
13273 := ((1 - 2) - (((3 - (4⁵)) × (6 + 7)) + (8 - 9)))
13274 := (((1 - 2) + ((3 - (4⁵)) × (6 + 7))) × (8 - 9))
13275 := ((1 + 2) + (((3 - (4⁵)) × -(6 + 7)) + (8 - 9)))
13276 := (1 × (2 - (((3 - (4⁵)) × (6 + 7)) + (8 - 9))))
13277 := (1 × -(2 - (((3 + (4⁵)) × (6 + 7)) - (8 × 9))))
13278 := (1 - (2 - (((3 + (4⁵)) × (6 + 7)) - (8 × 9))))
13279 := ((1 - 2) × (((3 + (4⁵)) × -(6 + 7)) + (8 × 9)))
13280 := (((1 - 2) + (3⁴)) × -(((5 + 6) × -7) - 89))
13281 := ((1 - (((2³) - (4⁵)) × (6 + 7))) - (8 × -9))
13282 := ((1 + (((2 - (3 - 4))⁵) - 6) × (7 × 8)) + 9)
13283 := (((1 + (((2 - 3) + (4⁵)) × (6 + 7))) - 8) - 9)
13284 := ((12 - (((3 - (4⁵)) × (6 + 7)) - 8)) - 9)
13285 := ((12 - ((3 - (4⁵)) × (6 + 7))) × -(8 - 9))
13286 := (((1 - (2 - 3)) - (4⁵)) × -((6 + 7) × -(8 - 9)))
13287 := (((((1 + 2)³⁺⁴) + 5) × 6) - ((7 + 8) × -9))
13288 := (((1 + 23) - ((4⁵) × (6 + 7))) × (8 - 9))
13289 := (((1 - 2) - ((3 - (4⁵)) × (6 + 7))) + (8 + 9))
13290 := (1 + ((23 - ((4⁵) × (6 + 7))) × (8 - 9)))
13291 := ((12 + ((3 + (4⁵)) × (6 + 7))) + (8 × -9))
13292 := (1 × (2 - (((3 - (4⁵)) × (6 + 7)) - (8 + 9))))
13293 := (1 + (2 - (((3 - (4⁵)) × (6 + 7)) - (8 + 9))))
13294 := (1 + ((23 - (4 × (5 × (67 + 8)))) × -9))
13295 := ((1 + 2) - (3 - (((4⁵) × (6 + 7)) - (8 + 9))))
13296 := ((1 - (2 - 3)) × -(((4⁵) × -6) - (7 × (8 × 9))))
13297 := (1 - ((2 - 3) - (((4⁵) × (6 + 7)) - (8 + 9))))

13257 := ((9 - ((8 - (7 × (6 + (5⁴)))) × 3)) + 21)
13258 := ((9 - 8) × -(7 × -(((6 + (5⁴)) × 3) + (2 - 1))))
13259 := ((9 - 8) - (7 × -(((6 + (5⁴)) × 3) + (2 - 1))))
13260 := ((9 - (8 + 7)) × -((((6 + 5) × 4) + 3)² + 1))
13261 := ((9 + 8) - (7 × -(((6 + (5⁴)) × 3) - (2 - 1))))
13262 := (98 - ((7 × -(6 + ((5⁴) × 3))) + (2 + 1)))
13263 := ((9 + 8) + (((7 + 6) × -(5 - (4³⁺²))) - 1))
13264 := ((9 - 8) × -((7 × -(((6 + (5⁴)) × 3) + 2)) + 1))
13265 := ((9 - (8 × (7 × ((6 × 5) + 4)))) × ((3 × -2) - 1))
13266 := ((9 - 8) × -((7 × -(((6 + (5⁴)) × 3) + 2)) - 1))
13267 := ((9 - 8) - ((7 × -(((6 + (5⁴)) × 3) + 2)) - 1))
13268 := ((9 + 8) - (7 × -((6 + (5⁴)) × (3 × (2 - 1)))))
13269 := ((9 + 8) - ((7 × -((6 + (5⁴)) × 3)) - (2 - 1)))
13270 := (((9 + 8) + (7 × ((6 + (5⁴)) × 3))) - (2 × -1))
13271 := (9 + (8 + ((7 × ((6 + (5⁴)) × 3)) + (2 + 1))))
13272 := (98 - (7 × -(6 + (((5⁴) × 3) + (2 - 1))))
13273 := ((9 - 8) - ((7 × -((6 + (5⁴)) × 3)) - 21))
13274 := (9 - ((8 × -((765 + (4³)) × 2)) - 1))
13275 := ((9 + 8) - (7 × -(((6 + (5⁴)) × 3) + (2 - 1))))
13276 := ((-9 - ((8 - (7 × (6⁵)))/4)) - 321)
13277 := ((9 + 8) - (((7 × (6 + (5⁴))) + 3) × -(2 + 1)))
13278 := (98 - ((7 × -(6 + (((5⁴) × 3) + 2))) + 1))
13279 := (((9 - (8 × 7)) + ((6⁵)/4)) × -((3 × -2) - 1))
13280 := ((9 - ((8 × (7 × 6)) + 5)) × (4 × -((3²) + 1)))
13281 := ((9 + 8) - ((7 × -(((6 + (5⁴)) × 3) + 2)) + 1))
13282 := ((9 + ((8 + (7 × (6 + (5⁴)))) × 3)) + (2 × -1))
13283 := (9 - (((8 + (7 × (6 + (5⁴)))) × -3) + (2 - 1)))
13284 := (9 - ((8 + (7 × (6 + (5⁴)))) × -(3 × (2 - 1))))
13285 := (9 - (((8 + (7 × (6 + (5⁴)))) × -3) - (2 - 1)))
13286 := ((9 + ((8 + (7 × (6 + (5⁴)))) × 3)) - (2 × -1))
13287 := (((9 - 8) + (7 × 6)) × -((5 × -((4³) - 2)) + 1))
13288 := (9 - (8 - (((7 × (6⁵))/4) - 321)))
13289 := ((98 - (7 - 6)) × -(((5 + (4³)) × -2) + 1))
13290 := ((9 + 87) + (6 + (((5⁴) + 3) × 21)))
13291 := ((((-98 + (7 × (6 - (5⁴)))) × -3) - 2) × 1)
13292 := (9 - (((87 - 6) × -((54 × 3) + 2)) + 1))
13293 := ((98 - (7 × (6 - (5⁴)))) × -(3 × -(2 - 1)))
13294 := ((9 + 8) × (((7 × 65) - (4³)) × (2 × 1)))
13295 := (((-98 - (7 + 6543)) × -2) - 1)
13296 := ((98 + (7 + 6543)) × (2 × 1))
13297 := (9 - (8 × -(76 - (5 × (4 - 321))))

$$\begin{aligned}
13298 &:= (1 \times -(((2-3) + (4^5)) \times -(6+7)) - (8-9)) \\
13299 &:= (1 - (((2-3) + (4^5)) \times -(6+7)) - (8-9)) \\
13300 &:= ((1 + (((2-3) + (4^5)) \times (6+7))) \times -(8-9)) \\
13301 &:= (((1 + (((2-3) + (4^5)) \times (6+7))) - 8) + 9) \\
13302 &:= (((1+2)^{3+4}) + (5 \times 6)) \times ((7+8) - 9) \\
13303 &:= (1 \times (((2-34 \times (56-7))) \times -8) - 9) \\
13304 &:= (12 - (3 - (((4^5) \times (6+7)) - (8+9)))) \\
13305 &:= ((1+2) - (((3+4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + 8) \times -9) \\
13306 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -3) - ((4^5) \times ((6+7) \times (8-9)))) \\
13307 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times 3) - (4^5)) \times (6+7)) - (8 \times -9)) \\
13308 &:= ((1-2) + ((3 - ((4^5) \times (6+7))) \times (8-9))) \\
13309 &:= ((1-2) \times -((3 - ((4^5) \times (6+7))) \times (8-9))) \\
13310 &:= ((1-2) \times (3 - ((4^5) \times (6+7)) - (8-9))) \\
13311 &:= (1 + ((2-3) + (((4^5) \times (6+7)) + (8-9)))) \\
13312 &:= ((1+2) + ((3 - ((4^5) \times (6+7))) \times (8-9))) \\
13313 &:= ((1+2) - (3 - (((4^5) \times (6+7)) - (8-9)))) \\
13314 &:= ((1 - (2-3)) + ((4^5) \times -((6+7) \times (8-9)))) \\
13315 &:= ((1 - (2-3)) - (((4^5) \times -(6+7)) + (8-9))) \\
13316 &:= (1 \times -(((2-3) + (4^5)) \times -(6+7)) - (8+9)) \\
13317 &:= ((1+2) + (3 + (((4^5) \times (6+7)) + (8-9)))) \\
13318 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -3) + ((4^5) \times ((6+7) \times (8-9)))) \\
13319 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3) + (4^5)) \times (6+7))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
13320 &:= ((1 - (((2+3) - (4^5)) \times (6+7)) - (8 \times -9)) \\
13321 &:= (12 + ((3 - ((4^5) \times (6+7))) \times (8-9))) \\
13322 &:= (1 \times (2 - ((3 - (4 \times (5 + (6 \times 7)))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
13323 &:= (1 + (2 - ((3 - (4 \times (5 + (6 \times 7)))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
13324 &:= (1 \times (((2-3) - (4^5)) \times -(6+7)) + (8-9)) \\
13325 &:= (1 + (((2-3) - (4^5)) \times -(6+7)) + (8-9)) \\
13326 &:= (12 + (3 + (((4^5) \times (6+7)) + (8-9)))) \\
13327 &:= ((1 + (((2+3)^4) - ((5^6) - 7)) \times 8) / -9) \\
13328 &:= (12 + ((3 + ((4^5) \times (6+7))) - (8-9))) \\
13329 &:= ((1+2) \times (3 \times -(4 - ((5+6) \times ((7+8) \times 9)))) \\
13330 &:= (1 \times -((2 + (34 \times (56 \times 7))) \times (8-9))) \\
13331 &:= (1 - ((2 + (34 \times (56 \times 7))) \times (8-9))) \\
13332 &:= (1 \times -((2 - (((3 + (4^5)) \times (6+7)) - (8+9)))) \\
13333 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 + (4^5)) \times (6+7)) - (8+9)))) \\
13334 &:= ((1-2) \times (((3 + (4^5)) \times -(6+7)) + (8+9))) \\
13335 &:= ((1+2) + (3 + (((4^5) \times (6+7)) + (8+9)))) \\
13336 &:= (((1+23) + ((4^5) \times (6+7))) \times -(8-9)) \\
13337 &:= ((1+2) - (((3 + (4^5)) \times -(6+7)) + (8+9))) \\
13338 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times -((4 \times -5) - (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13298 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times (6^5)))) / -4) + 321)) \\
13299 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + (6 \times ((5+4)^3))) \times -(2+1))) \\
13300 &:= (((9+8) - 7) \times (((6+5)^{4-3+2}) - 1)) \\
13301 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 - ((5 + (4 \times 3))^2)) \times -1)) \\
13302 &:= (((9+8) + (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times -(3 \times -(2-1))) \\
13303 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times (5 - (4^{3+2-1}))) \\
13304 &:= ((9 - (8-7)) \times -(65 - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
13305 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times 3)) + 21) \\
13306 &:= ((-9+8) - (7 - ((6 + ((5^4) + 3)) \times 21))) \\
13307 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -((4^3) - (2+1)))) \\
13308 &:= (9 + ((87+6) \times (((5 + (4+3))^2) - 1))) \\
13309 &:= ((-9 \times (87 \times (6 - ((5 \times 4) + 3)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
13310 &:= (((9+8) - 7) \times -(((6+5)^{4-3+2}) \times -1)) \\
13311 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (76 \times 5)) \times 4)) \times (3 \times -(2+1))) \\
13312 &:= (((98+7) - (6-5)) \times -(4 \times -(32 \times 1))) \\
13313 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(7 + ((65+4) \times (3+21)))) \\
13314 &:= (((9-8)^7) \times -((6 + ((5^4) + 3)) \times -21)) \\
13315 &:= (9 - (8 - (7 \times (6 + (((5^4) \times 3) + 21)))) \\
13316 &:= (((-9 \times -876) + 5432) \times 1) \\
13317 &:= (9 + (8 + (76 \times (5 \times ((4+32) - 1)))) \\
13318 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times -(5 \times 43)) + 21) \\
13319 &:= (9 - (((87 \times (6 \times (54-3))) / -2) + 1)) \\
13320 &:= (((9+8) - 7) \times (((6+5)^{4-3+2}) + 1)) \\
13321 &:= ((9-8) \times (7 + ((6 + ((5^4) + 3)) \times 21))) \\
13322 &:= ((9-8) + (7 + ((6 + ((5^4) + 3)) \times 21))) \\
13323 &:= (98 - (((7 + (65+43))^2) \times -1)) \\
13324 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7+6)) \times -((5^4) + (3^2))) - 1)) \\
13325 &:= (((9-8) - (7 \times 6)) \times ((54 \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
13326 &:= (((-98 \times -(76 + (5 \times (4 \times 3)))) - 2) \times 1) \\
13327 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((7 \times -(65 + (43^2))) - 1)) \\
13328 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times (43+2))) + 1)) \\
13329 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times ((43+2) \times 1)))) \\
13330 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times 4)) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\
13331 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times (6 + (((5^4) \times 3) + 21)))) \\
13332 &:= (98 + ((7+6) \times -(5 - ((4^{3+2}) - 1)))) \\
13333 &:= ((-987 + ((6+5)^4)) - 321) \\
13334 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((7-6) \times 5)) \times -((4^{3+2}) + 1))) \\
13335 &:= (((9-8) + (76 \times 5)) \times -((4 \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\
13336 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) - 4)) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
13337 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 \times 43))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
13338 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times -(5 \times 43)) + (2 - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 13339 &:= (((1+2)^3) + ((4^5) \times -((6+7) \times (8-9)))) \\
 13340 &:= (((1+2)^3) - (((4^5) \times -(6+7)) + (8-9))) \\
 13341 &:= (1 \times -(((2+(34 \times 56)) \times -7) - (8-9))) \\
 13342 &:= ((1 + (((2+(34 \times 56)) \times 7) + 8)) - 9) \\
 13343 &:= ((1 + ((2+(34 \times 56)) \times 7)) \times -(8-9)) \\
 13344 &:= (((1-2) - ((3-(4^5)) \times (6+7))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
 13345 &:= ((1 + (((2^3) + (4^5)) \times (6+7))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
 13346 &:= (((12 + ((3+(4^5)) \times (6+7))) - 8) - 9) \\
 13347 &:= ((1+2) \times -(((3^4) \times -56) + (78+9))) \\
 13348 &:= (1 \times -2 - (((3+(4^5)) \times (6+7)) + (8-9))) \\
 13349 &:= (((1-2) + (((3+(4^5)) \times (6+7)) + 8)) - 9) \\
 13350 &:= (((1-2) + ((3+(4^5)) \times (6+7))) \times -(8-9)) \\
 13351 &:= (((1-2) + ((3+(4^5)) \times (6+7))) - (8-9)) \\
 13352 &:= (((1-2) - ((3+(4^5)) \times (6+7))) \times (8-9)) \\
 13353 &:= ((1+2) - (((3+(4^5)) \times -(6+7)) - (8-9))) \\
 13354 &:= (((1+2) + ((3+(4^5)) \times (6+7))) \times -(8-9)) \\
 13355 &:= ((1+2) - (((3+(4^5)) \times -(6+7)) + (8-9))) \\
 13356 &:= (((1+2)^3) - (((4^5) \times -(6+7)) - (8+9))) \\
 13357 &:= ((12 - ((3-(4^5)) \times (6+7))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
 13358 &:= (1 \times ((2 + ((3^4) \times ((5+6) \times (7+8)))) - 9)) \\
 13359 &:= (1 + ((2 + ((3^4) \times ((5+6) \times (7+8)))) - 9)) \\
 13360 &:= (1 \times (((2+3) + (4^5)) \times (6+7)) - (8+9)) \\
 13361 &:= (((1 + (((2+3) + (4^5)) \times (6+7))) - 8) - 9) \\
 13362 &:= ((12 + (((3+(4^5)) \times (6+7)) + 8)) - 9) \\
 13363 &:= ((12 + ((3+(4^5)) \times (6+7))) \times -(8-9)) \\
 13364 &:= (((12 + ((3+(4^5)) \times (6+7))) - 8) + 9) \\
 13365 &:= (((1+2)^{3+4}) \times -((56+7) - 8) / -9) \\
 13366 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times ((5-6) \times (7-89))) \\
 13367 &:= (((1-2) + (((3+(4^5)) \times (6+7)) + 8)) + 9) \\
 13368 &:= ((1 - (2-3)) \times -4 \times -((5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
 13369 &:= ((1 + (2345 \times 6)) + (78 \times -9)) \\
 13370 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3+(4^5)) \times (6+7)) + (8+9)))) \\
 13371 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3+(4^5)) \times (6+7)) + (8+9)))) \\
 13372 &:= ((1 + (((2-3) + (4^5)) \times (6+7))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
 13373 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 3) + (4^5)) \times -(6+7)) + (8+9)) \\
 13374 &:= (((1 + (((2 \times 3) + (4^5)) \times (6+7))) - 8) - 9) \\
 13375 &:= (1 \times ((2+3) \times ((4+(5 \times (67 \times 8))) - 9))) \\
 13376 &:= ((1 - ((2+3) + (4^5)) \times (6+7)) \times (8-9)) \\
 13377 &:= ((1 + (((2+3) + (4^5)) \times (6+7)) + 8) - 9) \\
 13378 &:= ((1 + (((2+3) + (4^5)) \times (6+7))) \times -(8-9)) \\
 13379 &:= (((1 + (((2+3) + (4^5)) \times (6+7))) - 8) + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 13339 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5) \times -((4^3) - 21)) \\
 13340 &:= ((98 - (7 - (6 - 5))) \times (((4 \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\
 13341 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 \times 43))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
 13342 &:= (98 - (7 \times -(((6+(5^4)) \times 3) - (2-1)))) \\
 13343 &:= ((-98 + (((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)) + 2)) - 1) \\
 13344 &:= (98 + (((7+6) \times -(5-(4^{3+2}))) - 1)) \\
 13345 &:= (98 + ((7+6) \times -(5-(4^{3+2} \times 1)))) \\
 13346 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -((6+(5^4)) \times 3)) + (2+1))) \\
 13347 &:= ((98 + (7 \times ((6+(5^4)) \times 3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
 13348 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -((6+(5^4)) \times 3)) + (2-1))) \\
 13349 &:= ((9-8) \times -(7 \times -((6 \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)) - 1))) \\
 13350 &:= (9 - (8 - (7 \times ((6 \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)) - 1)))) \\
 13351 &:= ((98 + (7 \times ((6+(5^4)) \times 3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
 13352 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -((6+(5^4)) \times 3)) - (2+1))) \\
 13353 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (76 \times 5))) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
 13354 &:= ((98 - 76) \times ((5^4) + (3 - 21))) \\
 13355 &:= ((9-8) \times -(((7 \times 6) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)) + 1)) \\
 13356 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 \times 6) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)) - 1))) \\
 13357 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((7 \times 6) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - 2))) \times -1)) \\
 13358 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 \times 6) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)) + 1))) \\
 13359 &:= (9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times -(54 - 321))) \\
 13360 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times -(5 \times 43)) - 21) \\
 13361 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 - 54)))) \times -(32 - 1)) \\
 13362 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -(((6+(5^4)) \times 3) + 2)) + 1)) \\
 13363 &:= ((9-8) \times -(7 \times -((6 \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)) + 1))) \\
 13364 &:= (9 - (8 - (7 \times ((6 \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)) + 1)))) \\
 13365 &:= ((9-8) - ((7+6) \times -(5+(4^{3+2})) - 1)) \\
 13366 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)) - 1)))) \\
 13367 &:= ((-9-8) - (7 \times -(((6^5)/4) - (32 \times 1)))) \\
 13368 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times (4 \times -(3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
 13369 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7-65) + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))) \\
 13370 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -((6+(5^4)) \times 3)) - 21)) \\
 13371 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + (6 + 543)))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 13372 &:= (9 + ((8 + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - 2))) - 1)) \\
 13373 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - 2))) \times -1)) \\
 13374 &:= ((9+8) - (((7 \times 6) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)) - 1)) \\
 13375 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times -43) - 2) \times -1) \\
 13376 &:= (((9-8) - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) \times -(2-1))) \\
 13377 &:= ((9-8) - (((7+6) \times -(5+(4^{3+2}))) + 1)) \\
 13378 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((7+6) \times (5+(4^{3+2})))) \times -1)) \\
 13379 &:= ((9-8) - (((7+6) \times -(5+(4^{3+2}))) - 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13380 &:= ((12 + (((3 + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) + 8)) + 9) \\
13381 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (3 + (4 \times (5 \times (678 - 9)))))) \\
13382 &:= (1 \times (2 - (3 \times (4 + ((5 - 67) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
13383 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 - (((4 \times 5) + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
13384 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
13385 &:= (1 \times -((2 - 3) - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
13386 &:= ((1 - 2) + (3 + (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
13387 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(3 + (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
13388 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - 3) + (4^5)) \times -(6 + 7)) - 89) \\
13389 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times 3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 - 9)) \\
13390 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times 3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 - 9)) \\
13391 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times 3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) \times -(8 - 9)) \\
13392 &:= (((1 + ((2 \times 3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) - 8) + 9) \\
13393 &:= (12 - (3 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
13394 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3) + (4^5)) \times -(6 + 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\
13395 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 \times -(((4 \times 5) + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
13396 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -3) + (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) + 89))) \\
13397 &:= (1 \times (((2 - 3) - (4^5)) \times -(6 + 7)) + (8 \times 9)) \\
13398 &:= (1 + (((2 - 3) - (4^5)) \times -(6 + 7)) + (8 \times 9)) \\
13399 &:= (1 \times (((2^3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\
13400 &:= (((1 + ((2^3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) - 8) - 9) \\
13401 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) + 89))) \\
13402 &:= (1 \times -((2 - 3) - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) + 89))) \\
13403 &:= (1 - ((2 - 3) - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) + 89))) \\
13404 &:= (12 - (3 \times -(((4 \times 5) + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
13405 &:= (1 \times -((23 - (((4^5) + (6 \times 78)) \times 9))) \\
13406 &:= (1 - (23 - (((4^5) + (6 \times 78)) \times 9))) \\
13407 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 \times -(4 - ((5 - 67) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
13408 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times 3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 + 9)) \\
13409 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - (3 \times (4 + 5))) \times (67 \times 8)) - 9)) \\
13410 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4 + 5))) \times (67 \times 8))) + 9) \\
13411 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (((4^5) \times -(6 + 7)) - (8 \times 9))) \\
13412 &:= (1 + (((2 + 3) \times (4 + (5 \times (67 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\
13413 &:= (12 + ((3 - ((4^5) + (6 \times 78))) \times -9)) \\
13414 &:= (1 \times (((2 + (34 \times 56)) \times 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
13415 &:= ((1 - (((2^3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) \times (8 - 9)) \\
13416 &:= ((1 + (((2^3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) + (8 - 9)) \\
13417 &:= ((1 + (((2^3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) \times -(8 - 9)) \\
13418 &:= (((1 + ((2^3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) - 8) + 9) \\
13419 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -((4 \times -5) - ((6 \times 78) + 9))) \\
13420 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) - (((4^5) + (6 \times 78)) \times 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13380 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)) + 1)))) \\
13381 &:= (9 + (8 + ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + (4^{3+2})) - 1)))) \\
13382 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((7 \times -(65 + (43^2))) - 1)) \\
13383 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6^5)/4) - 32)) + 1)) \\
13384 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -(((6^5)/4) - 32)) + 1)) \\
13385 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6^5)/4) - 32)) - 1)) \\
13386 &:= ((98 - (7 - 6)) \times -((5 + (4^3)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
13387 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 - (76 \times 5)) \times 4)) - 3) + (2 \times -1)) \\
13388 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (7 \times -(65 + ((43^2) + 1)))) \\
13389 &:= (9 + ((8 + 7) \times -((6 + 5) - (43 \times 21)))) \\
13390 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + 6) \times -(5 + ((4^{3+2}) + 1)))) \\
13391 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4))) \times -(3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
13392 &:= (9 + ((87 + (6 \times ((5 + 4^3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\
13393 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 + 6) \times -(5 + (4^{3+2}))) + 1)) \\
13394 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((7 + 6) \times (5 + (4^{3+2})))) \times -1)) \\
13395 &:= (9 + (8 + (((7 + 6) \times (5 + (4^{3+2}))) + 1))) \\
13396 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((7 + 6) \times (5 - (4^3))) - 21)) \\
13397 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(65 + (43^2))) + 1)) \\
13398 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5)) \times (43 - (2 - 1))) \\
13399 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times (65 + (43^2)))) \times -1)) \\
13400 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) + 4)) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
13401 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 \times -(((6^5)/4) - (32 \times 1)))) \\
13402 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times -(((6^5)/4) - 32)) - 1)) \\
13403 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7^6))/ - (5 + 4)) - 321)) \\
13404 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times -((6 \times (5 + ((4 \times 3)^2))) - 1))) \\
13405 &:= (9 + ((8 - 76) \times -(5 + ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))))) \\
13406 &:= (9 + ((87 \times -(6 - ((54 \times 3) - 2))) - 1)) \\
13407 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 + 6) \times -(5 + ((4^{3+2}) + 1)))) \\
13408 &:= (9 - ((87 \times (6 - ((54 \times 3) - 2))) - 1)) \\
13409 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times (((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)) - 2))) \times -1) \\
13410 &:= (((9 + 87) - 6) \times -((5 + ((4 \times 3)^2)) \times -1)) \\
13411 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) - 5) \times (4 - 32)) - 1) \\
13412 &:= ((98 - (7 \times (6 \times (54 \times 3)))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
13413 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((765 + (4 \times (3 \times 2))) \times -1)) \\
13414 &:= (9 + ((8 + (7 \times (65 + (43^2)))) - 1)) \\
13415 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times (65 + (43^2)))) \times -1)) \\
13416 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (((5^4) - 3)/2 + 1)) \\
13417 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times (65 - 4))) \times -(32 \times 1))) \\
13418 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 \times (65 - 4))) \times -32) + 1)) \\
13419 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times 6) \times -(5 + ((4 \times 3)^2 \times 1)))) \\
13420 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times 6) \times (5 + ((4 \times 3)^2)) + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13421 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (3^4)) \times -(5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8))) - 9)) \\
13422 &:= (1 + (((2 - (3^4)) \times -(5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8))) - 9)) \\
13423 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -3) + (((4^5) + (6 \times 78)) \times 9))) \\
13424 &:= (1 \times (23 + (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) + 89))) \\
13425 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -(((4 \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times -8) + 9)) \\
13426 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))))))) - 9) \\
13427 &:= (1 \times ((2 - 3) + (((4^5) + (6 \times 78)) \times 9))) \\
13428 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times -4) + ((5 - 67) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
13429 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - (5^6)) \times (7 - 8)) - 9) \\
13430 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times 56)))) \times (7 - (8 + 9))) \\
13431 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - (5^6) - 7) \times (8 - 9)) \\
13432 &:= ((1 - ((2 - 34) \times (5 \times (6 + 78)))) - 9) \\
13433 &:= (1 \times -((((2^3) + (4^5)) \times -(6 + 7)) - (8 + 9))) \\
13434 &:= (1 - (((2^3) + (4^5)) \times -(6 + 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\
13435 &:= ((12 + ((3 + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
13436 &:= (((123 + ((4^5) \times (6 + 7))) - 8) + 9) \\
13437 &:= (1 \times (((2 - 3) - ((4^5) + (6 \times 78))) \times -9)) \\
13438 &:= (1 + (((2 - 3) - ((4^5) + (6 \times 78))) \times -9)) \\
13439 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3^4) - 5))) \times ((6 - 7) \times 89)) \\
13440 &:= ((1 - ((2 + 3) \times 45)) \times -(6 \times -(7 - (8 + 9)))) \\
13441 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times ((4 - ((5 + 6) \times 7)) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
13442 &:= (1 - ((23 \times ((4 - ((5 + 6) \times 7)) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
13443 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))))) + 9)) \\
13444 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -(3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))))) + 9)) \\
13445 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - (5^6) + 7) \times (8 - 9)) \\
13446 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times ((4 - 5) \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
13447 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - (5^6)) \times (7 - 8)) + 9) \\
13448 &:= 123^{(4 \times 5 - 6)/7} \times 8/9 \\
13449 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3^4) \times -(((5 + 6) \times 7) + 89))) \\
13450 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
13451 &:= (12 - ((3 - (4 \times (5 - (6 \times 7)))) \times -89)) \\
13452 &:= (12 \times -((((3 \times (4 \times (5 + 6))) + 7) \times -8) - 9)) \\
13453 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 + ((4^5) + (6 \times 78))) \times 9))) \\
13454 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 + ((4^5) + (6 \times 78))) \times 9))) \\
13455 &:= (((1 + 2) - ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
13456 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -(45 \times (6 + 7))) + (8 - 9))) \\
13457 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 + ((4^5) + (6 \times 78))) \times 9))) \\
13458 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + 56) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)) \\
13459 &:= (1 + (2 \times -((3 \times (4 \times 5)) - 6789))) \\
13460 &:= (12 + (((34 \times 5) - 6) \times -(7 - 89))) \\
13461 &:= (((-1 - (23 \times (45 - 6))) \times -(7 + 8)) - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13421 &:= (((-9 \times -(((8 - (76 \times 5)) \times 4) - 3)) - 2) \times -1) \\
13422 &:= ((9 - (((8 + (7 + 6)) \times 5) \times (4^3))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
13423 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 + 54)))) \times (32 - 1)) \\
13424 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (76 \times 5)) \times 4)) - (32 \times -1)) \\
13425 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)) - 2)) + 1)) \\
13426 &:= (9 - (8 - ((7 \times (((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)) - 2)) - 1))) \\
13427 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times (((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)) - 2))) \times -1)) \\
13428 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) + 3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
13429 &:= (((-98 + 76) \times -(5^4)) - 321) \\
13430 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(7 - ((6 \times (5 + (4 \times 32))) - 1))) \\
13431 &:= ((98 + (7 + 6)) \times -((5 \times -(4 \times (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\
13432 &:= (9 - (((8 - 7) + (6 \times 5)) \times -(432 + 1))) \\
13433 &:= (98 - (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) - 3) \times -21) \\
13434 &:= (9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times (5 + ((4 \times 3)^2)) + 1))) \\
13435 &:= (-9 - (8 + (76 \times ((5 - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
13436 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times -(4^3)) + 21)) \\
13437 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times -(4^3)) + (2 + 1))) \\
13438 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times -(4^3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
13439 &:= (9 + ((8 - (((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)) - 2)) \times -1)) \\
13440 &:= ((98 - (7 \times 6)) \times -(5 \times -(((4 + 3)^2) - 1))) \\
13441 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times ((6 + 54) \times 32))) \times -1)) \\
13442 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) - 3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
13443 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) - 3) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
13444 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) - 3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
13445 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times ((5 \times 43) + 2))) \times -1) \\
13446 &:= (9 \times -((87 \times -6) + (54 \times (3 - 21)))) \\
13447 &:= (98 - (7 \times -((6 \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)) - 1))) \\
13448 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))^2) \times -1)) \\
13449 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 \times 6) - (5 - 43)) \times 21))) \\
13450 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times ((6 - 5) + ((4^3) \times 21))) \\
13451 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 \times 76)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) - 21) \\
13452 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (76 \times -((5 - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
13453 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)) + 2)) + 1)) \\
13454 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) + 3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
13455 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)) + 2)) - 1)) \\
13456 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -(((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)) + 2)) - 1)) \\
13457 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times ((6 + 54) \times 32))) \times -1)) \\
13458 &:= (((9 + 8) + (((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)) + 2)) - 1) \\
13459 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times -(((5^4) + 3) / -2) + 1)) \\
13460 &:= (((9 + 8) + (((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)) + 2)) + 1) \\
13461 &:= (98 - (7 \times -((6 \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)) + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13462 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times 3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 \times 9)) \\
13463 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) \times -(4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))))) + 9) \\
13464 &:= (1 - (((2^3) \times -(4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))))) + 9) \\
13465 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times (67 - 8)))) / -9) \\
13466 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) \times -(4 + ((5 \times (67 \times 8)) + 9)))) \\
13467 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 \times (4 + 56)) + 7) \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
13468 &:= ((1 + (23 \times 45)) \times ((6 + 7) \times -(8 - 9))) \\
13469 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) \times -(4 \times (5 - 678))) + 9)) \\
13470 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -(4 + ((5 + 6) \times (7 - 89)))) \\
13471 &:= (1 \times ((23 - 4) \times -(5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
13472 &:= (((12^3) - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
13473 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -((4 - (5 - 6)) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
13474 &:= (-1 + (2 - ((3 - (4 \times (5 \times (67 + 8)))) \times 9))) \\
13475 &:= ((1 - (2 + 34)) \times -(((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) + 9)) \\
13476 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(3 \times (4 + (5 \times ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9))))) \\
13477 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(3 \times (4 + (5 \times ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9))))) \\
13478 &:= (1 - (23 - (4 \times (5 \times ((67 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
13479 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3^4) - 5) \times (67 - 8)) + 9) \\
13480 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) \times 8))) - 9) \\
13481 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) \times -(4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))))) - 9) \\
13482 &:= (1 - (((2^3) \times -(4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))))) - 9) \\
13483 &:= (1 \times (((23 \times 4) + 5) \times (67 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
13484 &:= (((12^3) + 4) \times 5) - (67 \times -(8 \times 9)) \\
13485 &:= ((12 + 3) \times ((4^5) - (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9))))) \\
13486 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times -(((4 - 567) \times 8) + 9))) \\
13487 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (3 \times (4 - 567))) \times 8) + 9)) \\
13488 &:= (1 \times -((((2^3) + (4^5)) \times -(6 + 7)) - (8 \times 9))) \\
13489 &:= ((1 + (((2^3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
13490 &:= ((1 - ((2 + 3) \times (45 \times 6))) \times (7 - (8 + 9))) \\
13491 &:= ((1 - (2^3 \times 4)) - (((5^6) + 7) / 8) \times -9) \\
13492 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) - (4 \times (5 \times ((67 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
13493 &:= (1 - ((2^3) - (4 \times (5 \times ((67 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
13494 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 + 4567) - (8 \times 9))) \\
13495 &:= (1 \times (((((2 \times 3)^4) + (56 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9)) \\
13496 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + (56 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9) \\
13497 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) \times 8)) + 9)) \\
13498 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) \times 8))) + 9) \\
13499 &:= (((((12^3) + (4 + (5^6))) \times -7) + 8) / -9) \\
13500 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -(4 \times 5)) \times ((6 \times -7) + (8 + 9)) \\
13501 &:= (1 \times -(23 - (4 \times ((5 \times 678) - 9)))) \\
13502 &:= (1 \times -((234 - 5) \times -(67 - 8)) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13462 &:= (98 - ((7 + 6) \times -((5 + (4^{3+2})) - 1))) \\
13463 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times -((5 \times 43) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
13464 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times -((5 \times 43) + 2)) - 1) \\
13465 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 - 65) \times (4 - (32 + 1)))) \\
13466 &:= (9 + (((8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5) + 43))^2 + 1)) \\
13467 &:= (987 - (65 \times -((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
13468 &:= ((98 - 7) \times ((6 - 5) + ((4 + 3) \times 21))) \\
13469 &:= (9 + (8 - (76 \times ((5 - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
13470 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4))) + 3))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
13471 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times (((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)) + 2))) \times -1)) \\
13472 &:= (9 + (8 + ((7 \times (((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)) + 2)) + 1))) \\
13473 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (76 \times 5)) \times 4)) \times -(3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
13474 &:= (98 - (((7 + 6) \times -(5 + (4^{3+2}))) + 1)) \\
13475 &:= (98 - (7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) - (32 + 1)))) \\
13476 &:= (98 - (((7 + 6) \times -(5 + (4^{3+2}))) - 1)) \\
13477 &:= (9876 + (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2 + 1)) \\
13478 &:= (((9 + 8) + ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3))) + 21) \\
13479 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (54 \times 32)))) \times -1) \\
13480 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) - 4) \times ((3^2) - 1)) \\
13481 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (7 - ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) / - (2 \times 1))) \\
13482 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 - ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) / - 2) + 1)) \\
13483 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) - 32)) - 1)) \\
13484 &:= (((-9 \times -((876 + (5^4)) - 3)) + 2) \times 1) \\
13485 &:= (9 - ((8 - (76 \times (5 - (4^3)))) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
13486 &:= (((-98 + ((7 \times (6^5)) / 4) - 3) - 21) \\
13487 &:= ((98 - ((7 \times (((6^5) / 4) - 3)) - 2)) \times -1) \\
13488 &:= (98 - ((7 + 6) \times -(5 + ((4^{3+2}) + 1)))) \\
13489 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 \times -((4^3) + 2)) + 1)) \\
13490 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times -(5 \times (43 + 2))) + 1)) \\
13491 &:= (9 \times -(((8 \times 765) / - 4) + (32 - 1))) \\
13492 &:= ((987 - ((6^5) - 43)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
13493 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (6 - ((5 + 4)^3)))) / - (2 + 1)) \\
13494 &:= ((9 - 87) \times -(65 + (4 \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
13495 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + ((6 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))^2)))) \times -1) \\
13496 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -((7 \times 6) - (54 \times 32))) - 1)) \\
13497 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (54 \times 32)))) \times 1) \\
13498 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(7 - ((65 \times (4 \times 3)) + 21))) \\
13499 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) \times (6 - ((5 + 4)^3)))) / (2 + 1)) \\
13500 &:= (((9 + 87) - 6) \times (5 + (((4 \times 3)^2) + 1))) \\
13501 &:= ((-9 \times -(876 + (5^4))) - ((3^2) - 1)) \\
13502 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times -(((5^4) + 3) / - (2 \times 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 13503 &:= ((1+2) \times ((3+4) \times -(5 + ((6-78) \times 9)))) \\
 13504 &:= ((-1+2) - ((3 \times ((4-567) \times 8)) + 9)) \\
 13505 &:= ((1+(2+34)) \times (5 \times -((6-7) - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 13506 &:= ((1 + (((2^3) + (4^5)) \times (6+7))) + 89) \\
 13507 &:= (1 \times -(2 + ((3 - (4 \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
 13508 &:= (1 - (2 + ((3 - (4 \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
 13509 &:= ((1+2) \times -(3 \times -((4^5) + ((6 \times 78) + 9)))) \\
 13510 &:= ((1 + ((2+34) \times (5 \times (67+8)))) + 9) \\
 13511 &:= (1 \times -((234-5) \times -((6 \times 7) + (8+9)))) \\
 13512 &:= ((1+2) + ((3 - (4 \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8))) \times -9)) \\
 13513 &:= (1 \times (((((2 \times 3)^4) + (56 \times 7)) \times 8) + 9)) \\
 13514 &:= ((1-23) - (4 \times -((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 13515 &:= ((1 + ((2-34) \times 5)) \times -((6+7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 13516 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) - (4 \times ((5 \times 678) - 9)))) \\
 13517 &:= (1 - ((2^3) - (4 \times ((5 \times 678) - 9)))) \\
 13518 &:= ((1 - (23 - 4)) \times (5 - ((6 + 78) \times 9))) \\
 13519 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -3) + (4 \times ((5 \times 678) - 9)))) \\
 13520 &:= ((1 + ((2 - (3 \times (4 - 567))) \times 8)) - 9) \\
 13521 &:= (12 + ((3 - (4 \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8))) \times -9)) \\
 13522 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((3 - ((4 + (5 + 67)) \times 89)))) \\
 13523 &:= ((1 + ((23 + (4^5)) \times (6+7))) - 89) \\
 13524 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times (5 + ((6-7) \times 89))) \\
 13525 &:= (1 \times -((2-3) - (4 \times ((5 \times 678) - 9)))) \\
 13526 &:= (1 - ((2-3) - (4 \times ((5 \times 678) - 9)))) \\
 13527 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times -((4 + ((5-67) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
 13528 &:= ((1 + (23 \times (45 \times (6+7)))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
 13529 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times -((5 - (6 - (7 - 89)))) \\
 13530 &:= (((1-2) - (3^4)) \times ((5 \times -6) - ((7+8) \times 9))) \\
 13531 &:= (1 \times -((2+3) - (4 \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 13532 &:= ((1-2) - (3 - (4 \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 13533 &:= ((1-2) \times (3 - (4 \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 13534 &:= ((1 - (2-3)) \times -(((4^5) \times -6) - (7 \times 89))) \\
 13535 &:= (1 \times ((2-3) + (4 \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 13536 &:= (1 + ((2-3) + (4 \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 13537 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times 567)))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
 13538 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3 \times 45) + 6) \times (7 + 89)))) \\
 13539 &:= (12 - ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times (67 + 8)))) \times -9)) \\
 13540 &:= ((1 + ((23 + (4^5)) \times (6+7))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
 13541 &:= (1 + (2 \times (3 + (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 \times 89)))) \\
 13542 &:= ((1 + (2+34)) \times -((5 \times -(67+8)) + 9)) \\
 13543 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 \times ((4 \times 567) - 8)) - 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 13503 &:= (98 - (7 \times -(65 + ((43^2) + 1)))) \\
 13504 &:= (((9-8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -((4^3) \times -(2-1))) \\
 13505 &:= ((98 - (((7 \times (6^5))/4) - (3+2))) \times -1) \\
 13506 &:= (((9+8) - (7 \times (6 \times 54))) \times (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
 13507 &:= (((-9 \times -(876 + (5^4))) - (3-2)) - 1) \\
 13508 &:= (9 - (((((8+76) - 54^3)/ -2) + 1)) \\
 13509 &:= (9 \times (((8 - (765 - (4+3))) \times -2) + 1)) \\
 13510 &:= ((98 - ((7 \times (6^5))/4)) \times (3/ - (2+1))) \\
 13511 &:= ((-98 + (((7 \times (6^5))/4) + 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
 13512 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times -(4 \times -(3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
 13513 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(7 + ((6 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))^2 \times 1)))) \\
 13514 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 + ((6 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))^2))) - 1)) \\
 13515 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((7 + (6 + 5)) \times -43) - 21)) \\
 13516 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times 654)) \times -3) + 2) \times -1) \\
 13517 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -((6 \times ((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)) - 1))) \\
 13518 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 \times -((6 \times ((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)) - 1))) \\
 13519 &:= ((98 - (((7 \times (6^5))/4) + (3^2))) \times -1) \\
 13520 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times 654)) \times 3) - (2 \times -1)) \\
 13521 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) - (5^4)) \times -(3 + 21)) \\
 13522 &:= ((((-98 - 7) \times -65) - (4^3)) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
 13523 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times 6) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)) + 1)) \\
 13524 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 \times 6) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)) + 1)) \\
 13525 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times 6) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)) - 1)) \\
 13526 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -((4^3) - 2)) - 1)) \\
 13527 &:= (((9 + 8) - (76 \times (5 \times 4))) \times (3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
 13528 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times (((6^5)/4) - (3^2)))) \times -1) \\
 13529 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 + ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))/2) - 1))) \\
 13530 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (5 \times -((4^3) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
 13531 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -((6 \times ((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)) + 1))) \\
 13532 &:= (9 - (8 - (7 \times ((6 \times ((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)) + 1)))) \\
 13533 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - (((5^4) + 3) \times -21)) \\
 13534 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)) - 1)))) \\
 13535 &:= (98 - (((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times -(4^3)) + (2 + 1))) \\
 13536 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 + ((6 + (5 + 4))^3)))/ -2) + 1)) \\
 13537 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (4 + 32)) - 1)) \\
 13538 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6^5)/4) - ((3^2) + 1)))) \\
 13539 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 \times -(((6^5)/4) - ((3^2) + 1)))) \\
 13540 &:= (9 + ((8 + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) + 2))) - 1)) \\
 13541 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) + 2))) \times -1)) \\
 13542 &:= (9 + (8 + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)) + 1))) \\
 13543 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -(4 + (3 \times 21))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13544 &:= (1 - (2^3) - ((4 \times (5 \times 678)) - 9)) & 13544 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) + 4)) \times ((3^2) - 1)) \\
13545 &:= ((1 + (2^{3+4})) \times ((5 \times -6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) & 13545 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -(((6^5)/4) - (3^2))) + 1)) \\
13546 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -3) + ((4 \times (5 \times 678)) - 9))) & 13546 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6^5)/4) - (3^2))) - 1)) \\
13547 &:= (1 \times -(23 \times ((4 + (5 \times 6)) - (7 \times 89)))) & 13547 &:= (9 - (8 - ((7 \times (((6^5)/4) - (3^2))) + 1))) \\
13548 &:= (1 - (23 \times ((4 + (5 \times 6)) - (7 \times 89)))) & 13548 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)) + 1)))) \\
13549 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times ((3^4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) & 13549 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (765 + ((4^3)/(2 \times 1)))) \\
13550 &:= (1 - (((2 \times ((3^4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) & 13550 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times 4)) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
13551 &:= ((12 + 3) - (4 \times -((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 13551 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -(((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)) + 2)) + 1)) \\
13552 &:= (((12^3) - (4 + (5 \times 6))) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) & 13552 &:= (((9 - (8 - 7)) - ((6^5)/4)) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
13553 &:= (1 - ((2 - 3) - ((4 \times (5 \times 678)) - 9))) & 13553 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -(((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)) + 2)) - 1)) \\
13554 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times ((4 \times -5) + (6 \times (78 + 9)))) & 13554 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -((6 - (5 - 43))^2)) - 1)) \\
13555 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times (5 + 6))) + (78 \times -9)) & 13555 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times (((6^5)/4) - ((3^2) + 1)))) \\
13556 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) + (4 \times (5 \times 678))) - 9)) & 13556 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6^5)))/4)) + (3 \times -21)) \\
13557 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 - (4 - 567)) \times -8) + 9)) & 13557 &:= (((9 + 8) - ((7 \times (6^5))/4 \times 3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
13558 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -3) - ((4 \times (5 \times 678)) - 9))) & 13558 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (6^5)))/-4) + 32) \times -1) \\
13559 &:= ((1 - (23 \times 4)) \times ((5 \times -6) - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 13559 &:= ((98 - 7) \times ((6 \times (5 + (4 \times (3 + 2)))) - 1)) \\
13560 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -(4 \times -(5 + ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) & 13560 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 \times -(((6 - (5 - 43))^2) + 1))) \\
13561 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) - ((4 \times (5 \times 678)) + 9))) & 13561 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times -(((6^5)/4) - (3^2))) + 1)) \\
13562 &:= (1 - ((2^3) - ((4 \times (5 \times 678)) + 9))) & 13562 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times (((6^5)/4) - (3^2)))) \times -1)) \\
13563 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 \times (4 \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8))) + 9)) & 13563 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times -(((6^5)/4) - (3^2))) - 1)) \\
13564 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((3 \times 4) - (5 + 6789)))) & 13564 &:= (((-98 - 7) \times 65) + 43) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
13565 &:= (1 \times ((2 + ((34 - 5) \times (6 \times 78))) - 9)) & 13565 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6^5)/4) - (3 \times 2))) + 1)) \\
13566 &:= (1 + ((2 + ((34 - 5) \times (6 \times 78))) - 9)) & 13566 &:= (9 - (8 - ((7 \times (((6^5)/4) - (3 \times 2))) - 1))) \\
13567 &:= (1 \times -(2 + (3 \times (4 - ((567 \times 8) - 9)))) & 13567 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times (((6^5)/4) - (3 \times 2)))) \times -1)) \\
13568 &:= (1 - (2 + (3 \times (4 - ((567 \times 8) - 9)))) & 13568 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -(((6^5)/4) - (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\
13569 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 - ((4 \times (5 \times 678)) + 9))) & 13569 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 \times -((6 - (5 - 43))^2 \times 1))) \\
13570 &:= ((12 + 34) \times -(5 \times -((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9)))) & 13570 &:= (9 - (((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 54))) \times (3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
13571 &:= (1 \times (2 - (3 \times (4 - ((567 \times 8) - 9)))) & 13571 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 \times -((4^3) + 2)) - 1)) \\
13572 &:= (((1 + 2) - (3^4)) \times (((5 + 6) \times -(7 + 8)) - 9)) & 13572 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6^5)/4) - (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\
13573 &:= (1 \times -(23 - (4 \times ((5 \times 678) + 9)))) & 13573 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) - (6^5))/4)) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
13574 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) - 89) & 13574 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times (((6^5)/4) - (3 + 2)))) \times -1)) \\
13575 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 34) \times 5)) \times ((6 + 78) - 9)) & 13575 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -(((6^5)/4) - (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\
13576 &:= (((12^3) \times 4) - (56 \times -(7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 13576 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 \times -(((6 - (5 - 43))^2) + 1))) \\
13577 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) + ((4 \times (5 \times 678)) + 9))) & 13577 &:= (((9 - 8) + ((7 \times (6^5))/4)) + (32 \times -1)) \\
13578 &:= ((1 + (23 \times 4)) \times ((5 + 6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) & 13578 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((76 - 5) \times 4))) \times (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
13579 &:= ((1 + (2 + 34)) \times -(((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times -8) + 9)) & 13579 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times ((4 \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
13580 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -(4 \times (56 + (7 \times 89)))) & 13580 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6^5)/4) - ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
13581 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -((4 \times (5 \times 6)) - (7 \times 89))) & 13581 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 \times -(((6^5)/4) - ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
13582 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((3 + 4) - (5 - 6789)))) & 13582 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times -(((6^5)/4) - (3 \times 2))) + 1)) \\
13583 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3 \times (4 \times 567)) - 8)) + 9)) & 13583 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times (5 + 43)) + (2 - 1))) \\
13584 &:= ((1 + 23) \times -(4 - (5 \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))) & 13584 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times -(((6^5)/4) - (3 \times 2))) - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

13585 := $(1 \times ((23 - 4) \times -((5 + 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))$
13586 := $(1 + ((23 - 4) \times -((5 + 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))$
13587 := $((1 + 2) \times (((3^4) \times 56) + (7 \times (8 - 9))))$
13588 := $(1 \times (2 \times -((3 - 4) \times (5 + 6789))))$
13589 := $(1 \times -(2 - ((34 \times ((56 \times 7) + 8)) - 9)))$
13590 := $((1 - (2 \times ((3^4) - 5))) \times (6 - (7 + 89)))$
13591 := $(((((1 + 2)^3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 \times -9))$
13592 := $((((12^3) + (4 \times 56)) \times 7) + (8 \times -9))$
13593 := $((((1 + 2)^3) - (4 \times 56)) \times -(78 - 9))$
13594 := $(1 \times (((23 + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 + 9)))$
13595 := $((1 + 2) + (((((3^4) - (5^6)) \times 7) / -8) - 9))$
13596 := $(((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - 5) \times 6) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9)))$
13597 := $(1 \times -((2 - 3) - (4 \times ((5 \times 678) + 9))))$
13598 := $((((1 - 23) - (4^5)) \times -((6 + 7) \times -(8 - 9)))$
13599 := $(1 + (2 - (3 \times (4 - ((56 + 7) \times (8 \times 9))))))$
13600 := $(1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -(4 \times (5 + ((67 + 8) \times 9))))))$
13601 := $(1 - ((2 + 3) \times -(4 \times (5 + ((67 + 8) \times 9)))))$
13602 := $((1 + 2) - (((3^{4-5+6}) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9))$
13603 := $(1 \times -((2 + (3 \times (4 - (567 \times 8)))) - 9))$
13604 := $(12 + (((((3^4) - (5^6)) \times 7) / -8) - 9))$
13605 := $((1 + 2) \times (((3 - (4 + 567)) \times -8) - 9))$
13606 := $(1 \times -(2 \times -((3 \times (4 \times 567)) + (8 - 9))))$
13607 := $((1 - (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times 567)))) \times (8 - 9))$
13608 := $(((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) \times -56) / ((7 - 8) \times 9))$
13609 := $((1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times 567)))) \times -(8 - 9))$
13610 := $((1 - ((23 + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) \times (8 - 9))$
13611 := $(12 - (((3^{4-5+6}) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9))$
13612 := $((1 + ((23 + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) \times -(8 - 9))$
13613 := $((1 + 2) + (((((3^4) - (5^6)) \times 7) / -8) + 9))$
13614 := $(1 - (2 - ((3 + 4) \times (((5^6) + 7) / 8) - 9))))$
13615 := $(1 - (2 \times -(3 \times ((4 \times 567) - (8 - 9))))))$
13616 := $((((12^3) + (4 - (5 \times 6))) \times (7 - (8 - 9)))$
13617 := $((1 + (2 \times ((3^4) - 5))) \times -((6 - 7) \times 89))$
13618 := $((1 + 2) - ((3 + 4) \times -(((5^6) + 7) / 8) - 9)))$
13619 := $(1 - (2 - (3 \times (4 + ((56 + 7) \times (8 \times 9))))))$
13620 := $((12 + 3) \times -(4 \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 + 9))))$
13621 := $(1 \times -(2 + (3 \times (4 - ((567 \times 8) + 9))))))$
13622 := $(12 + (((((3^4) - (5^6)) \times 7) / -8) + 9))$
13623 := $(1 + (2 + (3 \times (4 + ((56 + 7) \times (8 \times 9))))))$
13624 := $((((1 + 23) + (4^5)) \times ((6 + 7) \times -(8 - 9)))$
13625 := $(1 \times -(((2^3) \times -((4^5) + 678)) - 9))$

13585 := $((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) - 3)) + (2 \times 1)))$
13586 := $((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) - 3)) + (2 \times 1)))$
13587 := $((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) - 3)) + (2 - 1)))$
13588 := $((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) - 3)) - (2 - 1)))$
13589 := $((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) - 3)) - (2 \times 1)))$
13590 := $((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) - 3)) - (2 \times 1)))$
13591 := $((9 + 8) - ((7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) - (3 + 2))) - 1))$
13592 := $(9 - (((8 + (7 \times (6^5))) / -4) + (3^{2+1})))$
13593 := $((9 + 8) + ((7 \times (6^5)) / 4) + (32 \times -1))$
13594 := $((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) - (3 - (2 - 1))))))$
13595 := $((9 - 8) - (7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) - (3 - (2 - 1))))))$
13596 := $((98 - 76) \times ((5^4) - ((3 \times 2) + 1)))$
13597 := $((9 + 8) - (7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) - ((3 + 2) - 1))))$
13598 := $((9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times (6^5)) / -4) + ((3^2) + 1)))$
13599 := $(9 - (8 - (((7 \times (6^5)) / 4) - ((3^2) + 1))))$
13600 := $((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times -(4 \times -((3^2) + 1)))$
13601 := $((9 - 8) + ((7 \times (6^5)) / 4) - ((3^2) - 1))$
13602 := $((9 - 8) + ((7 \times (6^5)) / 4) + ((3 \times -2) - 1))$
13603 := $((9 - 8) + ((7 \times (6^5)) / 4) + (3 \times -(2 \times 1)))$
13604 := $((9 - 8) + ((7 \times (6^5)) / 4) - 3) + (2 \times -1))$
13605 := $((9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6^5))) / 4) - ((3^2) + 1))$
13606 := $((9 - 8) + ((7 \times (6^5)) / 4) + (3 \times -(2 - 1)))$
13607 := $((9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6^5))) / 4) - ((3^2) - 1))$
13608 := $((9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6^5))) / 4) + ((3 \times -2) - 1))$
13609 := $((9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6^5))) / 4) - ((3^2) + 1))$
13610 := $((9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times (6^5)) / -4) - (3 - (2 - 1))))$
13611 := $((9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6^5))) / 4) - ((3^2) - 1))$
13612 := $((9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6^5))) / 4) + ((3 \times -2) - 1))$
13613 := $((9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6^5))) / 4) + (3 \times -(2 \times 1)))$
13614 := $((9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6^5))) / 4) - 3) + (2 \times -1))$
13615 := $((9 - 8)^7 + ((6^5) / 4) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1))$
13616 := $((9 - (((8 - (7 \times (6^5))) / 4) - 3)) + (2 \times -1))$
13617 := $((9 - 8) + ((7 \times (6^5)) / 4) + ((3^2) - 1))$
13618 := $((9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6^5))) / 4) - 3) - (2 \times -1))$
13619 := $((9 - 8) - (((7 \times (6^5)) / -4) - ((3^2) + 1)))$
13620 := $((9 - (((8 - (7 \times (6^5))) / 4) - 3)) - (2 \times -1))$
13621 := $((9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6^5))) / 4) - (3 \times -(2 \times 1)))$
13622 := $((9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6^5))) / 4) - ((3 \times -2) - 1))$
13623 := $((9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6^5))) / 4) + ((3^2) - 1))$
13624 := $((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4))) \times -((3^2) - 1))$
13625 := $((9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6^5))) / 4) + ((3^2) + 1))$

$$\begin{aligned}
13667 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3^4)) + (5 + 6)) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
13668 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) + (5 + 6)) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
13669 &:= ((1 + 2) + (((3 - ((4 + (5^6)) \times 7)) / -8) - 9)) \\
13670 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times 456)) \times -(7 - (8 + 9))) \\
13671 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3^4) - 5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))) + 9)) \\
13672 &:= (((1 - 2) - ((3 + 4) \times (5^6))) / - (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
13673 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times 5)))) \times (((6 + 7) \times 8) + 9)) \\
13674 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3^4) + 5) \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
13675 &:= (1 \times (((2 + ((3 + 4) \times ((5^6) - 7))) / 8) + 9)) \\
13676 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3^4) + ((5^6) \times 7)) / -8) + 9)) \\
13677 &:= (1 - ((23 \times -(((4 + 5) \times 67) - 8)) + 9)) \\
13678 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) - ((4 - (5^6)) \times 7)) / 8) + 9)) \\
13679 &:= (1 + (((2 + 3) - ((4 - (5^6)) \times 7)) / 8) + 9)) \\
13680 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 + 9)) \\
13681 &:= (12 - (((3 + 4) \times ((5^6) + 7)) / -8) + 9)) \\
13682 &:= (1 \times (2 - (3 \times (456 \times (7 - (8 + 9)))))) \\
13683 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times - (3 - (456 \times (7 + 8)))) + 9)) \\
13684 &:= ((1 + 2) + (((3 - 4) - ((5^6) \times 7)) / -8) + 9)) \\
13685 &:= (12 - (((3^4) + ((5^6) \times 7)) / -8) + 9)) \\
13686 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 345) / 6) \times -(7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
13687 &:= ((1 + ((234 - ((5^6) + 7)) \times 8)) / -9) \\
13688 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -((4^5) + (678 + 9)))) \\
13689 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3^4) - 5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))) - 9)) \\
13690 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 + 4) \times ((5^6) + 7)) / -8) - 9)) \\
13691 &:= (-1 \times (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times -5) + 6789)) \\
13692 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times (((4^5) \times 6) + (78 \times 9))) \\
13693 &:= (1 \times (((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) - 8)) - 9)) \\
13694 &:= (1 + (((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) - 8)) - 9)) \\
13695 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -(((4 \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times -8) - 9)) \\
13696 &:= (1 \times ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 + (6 + (7 + 89)))))) \\
13697 &:= (1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 + (6 + (7 + 89)))))) \\
13698 &:= ((1 + 2) \times - (3 \times -((4^5) - (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
13699 &:= (12 - (((3 + 4) \times ((5^6) + 7)) / -8) - 9)) \\
13700 &:= (1 + ((2 - (3 \times 4567)) \times (8 - 9))) \\
13701 &:= ((1 + ((23 + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) + 89) \\
13702 &:= (((1 - 2) - (3 \times 4567)) \times (8 - 9)) \\
13703 &:= (12 - (((3^4) + ((5^6) \times 7)) / -8) - 9)) \\
13704 &:= (((12^3) - (4 + (5 + 6))) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
13705 &:= (((1 + 23)^{4+5-6}) + (7 \times -(8 + 9))) \\
13706 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) \times -((4 \times (5 + 678)) + 9))) \\
13707 &:= ((1 + 2) \times - (3 - ((4 + ((56 + 7) \times 8)) \times 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13667 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6^5) / 4) + (3 \times 2)))) \times 1) \\
13668 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) + (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\
13669 &:= (9 + (((87 \times (6 - (5 \times (4^3)))) / -2) + 1)) \\
13670 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) + (3^2))) + 1)) \\
13671 &:= (9 - (8 - ((7 \times (((6^5) / 4) + (3^2))) - 1))) \\
13672 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times (((6^5) / 4) + (3^2)))) \times -1)) \\
13673 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) + (3^2))) - 1)) \\
13674 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times -(4^3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
13675 &:= (98 - (((7 \times (6^5)) / -4) + (32 - 1))) \\
13676 &:= ((987 + 65) \times -((4 + 3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
13677 &:= (((9 - 8) - (76 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))) \times - (2 + 1)) \\
13678 &:= ((9 - 8) \times - (7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) + ((3^2) + 1)))) \\
13679 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) + ((3^2) + 1)))) \\
13680 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times (((6 \times 5) + (4 + 3))^2 - 1)) \\
13681 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((76 \times -(5 \times (4 + 32))) - 1)) \\
13682 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 - (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2)) \times -1)) \\
13683 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 - (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2)) \times -1)) \\
13684 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2) + 1)) \\
13685 &:= ((9 + 8) \times - (7 \times -((6 \times 5) + ((4^3) + 21)))) \\
13686 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) - 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
13687 &:= (9 + ((8 + (7 \times (((6^5) / 4) + (3^2)))) - 1)) \\
13688 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2 - 1)) \\
13689 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -(((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2) \times -1)) \\
13690 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2) \times -1)) \\
13691 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2) + 1)) \\
13692 &:= (98 - (7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) - (3 - (2 - 1)))))) \\
13693 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 - (765 + 4))) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\
13694 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) + (3 - (2 - 1)))))) \\
13695 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
13696 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2)) \times -1)) \\
13697 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2)) \times -1)) \\
13698 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2) + 1)) \\
13699 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 - (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2)) \times -1)) \\
13700 &:= (9 + ((8 - 7) + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2) + 1)) \\
13701 &:= (((98 + ((7 \times (6^5)) / 4)) - 3) + (2 \times -1)) \\
13702 &:= ((98 + ((7 \times (6^5)) / 4)) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
13703 &:= ((98 + ((7 \times (6^5)) / 4)) + (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
13704 &:= (98 - (((7 \times (6^5)) / -4) + (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
13705 &:= (((98 + ((7 \times (6^5)) / 4)) - 3) - (2 \times -1)) \\
13706 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4))^{3-2+1})) \\
13707 &:= ((98 + (((7 \times (6^5)) / 4) + 3)) + (2 \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13708 &:= (1 - ((23 + (4 \times (5 \times (67 + 8)))) \times -9)) \\
13709 &:= (1 - (23 \times -((4 \times 5) + (6 \times (7 + 89)))) \\
13710 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3 \times 456)) \times -(7 - (8 + 9))) \\
13711 &:= (1 \times (((2 + (3 \times (4 + 567))) \times 8) - 9)) \\
13712 &:= (((12^3) - ((4 \times 5) - 6)) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
13713 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 + 4) \times -((5 \times 6) + (7 \times 89)))) \\
13714 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times (4 + ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 89)))) \\
13715 &:= (((1 - 2) - ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
13716 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times - (4 - (((5 \times 6) / (7 + 8))^9)) \\
13717 &:= (1 \times - (23 - (4 \times (5 \times (678 + 9)))) \\
13718 &:= (1 - (23 - (4 \times (5 \times (678 + 9)))) \\
13719 &:= ((1 + 2) \times - (3 - (4 \times (5 + (67 \times (8 + 9))))) \\
13720 &:= (1 \times - (2 \times - ((3 + 4) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 89)))) \\
13721 &:= (1 - (2 \times - ((3 + 4) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 89)))) \\
13722 &:= (1 + ((2 + (((34 \times 5) + 6) \times 78)) - 9)) \\
13723 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (67 \times 89))) \\
13724 &:= (((1 - 23) - (45 \times 6)) \times ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
13725 &:= (1 \times (((((2 + 3) - (4 \times 56)) \times 7) + 8) \times -9)) \\
13726 &:= (1 + (((((2 + 3) - (4 \times 56)) \times 7) + 8) \times -9)) \\
13727 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (4 \times (5 + (67 \times (8 + 9))))))) \\
13728 &:= ((1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times ((5 \times (6 - 7)) - (8 + 9))) \\
13729 &:= (1 \times (((2 + (3 \times (4 + 567))) \times 8) + 9)) \\
13730 &:= ((1 - ((234 - 5) \times 6)) \times (7 - (8 + 9))) \\
13731 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 \times - (4 \times (5 + (67 \times (8 + 9))))) \\
13732 &:= (1 \times (((2 - ((3^4) + (5^6))) \times 7) / -8) - 9)) \\
13733 &:= (1 + (((2 - ((3^4) + (5^6))) \times 7) / -8) - 9)) \\
13734 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 \times - (4 - (5 \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))) \\
13735 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 \times -9)) \\
13736 &:= (1 \times - (2 \times - (((3 \times 4) + (56 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
13737 &:= (1 - (2 \times - (((3 \times 4) + (56 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
13738 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 3) - (4 \times - (5 \times (678 + 9)))) \\
13739 &:= (1 \times - (2 - ((3 + 4) \times (((5^6) + 7) / 8) + 9))) \\
13740 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 + 4) \times (((5^6) + 7) / 8) + 9))) \\
13741 &:= ((1 - (23 \times 4)) \times (5 - (67 + 89))) \\
13742 &:= (((1 + 23)^{4+5-6} + 7) - 89) \\
13743 &:= (((12^3) - (4 + 5)) \times - ((6 - 7) \times 8) - 9) \\
13744 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 + 4) \times - (((5^6) + 7) / 8) + 9)) \\
13745 &:= (((1 + 23)^{4+5-6} - 7) + (8 \times -9)) \\
13746 &:= (1 - ((2 \times - (34 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8))) - 9)) \\
13747 &:= (1 \times - (23 - (45 \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))) \\
13748 &:= (1 - (23 - (45 \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13708 &:= (98 - (((7 \times (6^5)) / -4) - (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
13709 &:= ((98 + ((7 \times (6^5)) / 4)) - (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
13710 &:= (98 - (((7 \times (6^5)) / -4) - ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\
13711 &:= ((98 + (((7 \times (6^5)) / 4) + 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
13712 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
13713 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2)) \times -1)) \\
13714 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2) + 1)) \\
13715 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + (6^5)) / 4) \times - ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\
13716 &:= (98 - (((7 \times (6^5)) / -4) - ((3^2) + 1))) \\
13717 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times - ((5 \times -(4^3)) + (2 - 1))) \\
13718 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 \times 654)) \times -3) - (2 - 1))) \\
13719 &:= ((9 + 8) \times - ((7 \times - (6 \times (5 \times 4))) + (32 + 1))) \\
13720 &:= (98 - (7 \times - (((6^5) / 4) + (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
13721 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 \times 654)) \times 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
13722 &:= ((9 - (87 \times (6 + (5^4)))) / - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
13723 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (6 + ((5 + 4)^3)))) / (2 + 1)) \\
13724 &:= ((98 + (7 \times (((6^5) / 4) + 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\
13725 &:= ((98 + (7 \times (((6^5) / 4) + 3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
13726 &:= (98 - ((7 \times - (((6^5) / 4) + 3)) + (2 - 1))) \\
13727 &:= (98 - (7 \times - (((6^5) / 4) + (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
13728 &:= (98 - ((7 \times - (((6^5) / 4) + 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
13729 &:= ((98 + (7 \times (((6^5) / 4) + 3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
13730 &:= ((98 + (7 \times (((6^5) / 4) + 3))) + (2 + 1)) \\
13731 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 654)) \times (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
13732 &:= ((9 - 8) \times - ((7 \times - (654 \times 3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
13733 &:= (98 - (((7 \times (6^5)) / -4) - (3^{2+1}))) \\
13734 &:= (98 - (7 \times - (((6^5) / 4) + ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\
13735 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (5 \times - (4 + (3 \times 21)))) \\
13736 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times - ((6 + 5) - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
13737 &:= (98 - (((7 \times (6^5)) / -4) - (32 - 1))) \\
13738 &:= ((98 + ((7 \times (6^5)) / 4)) - (32 \times -1)) \\
13739 &:= (98 - (((7 \times (6^5)) / -4) - (32 + 1))) \\
13740 &:= (98 - ((7 \times - (((6^5) / 4) + (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\
13741 &:= (98 - (7 \times - (((6^5) / 4) + ((3 + 2) \times 1)))) \\
13742 &:= (98 - ((7 \times - (((6^5) / 4) + (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\
13743 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times - ((4^3) - (2 - 1)))) \\
13744 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times ((654 \times 3) - (2 - 1)))) \\
13745 &:= (9 - (87 - ((6 \times ((5 + 43)^2)) - 1))) \\
13746 &:= ((9 - 87) - (6 \times - ((5 + 43)^2 \times 1))) \\
13747 &:= (98 - ((7 \times - (((6^5) / 4) + (3 \times 2))) + 1)) \\
13748 &:= ((98 + (7 \times (((6^5) / 4) + 3))) + 21)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 13749 &:= ((1+2) - ((34-5) \times -(6 \times (7+(8 \times 9)))))) \\
 13750 &:= ((12-34) \times (5 \times -(6+(7 \times (8+9)))))) \\
 13751 &:= (((1+((2 \times 3)^4)) - (((5^6)+7) \times 8))/ -9) \\
 13752 &:= (((((1+2)^3) + (4^5)) \times (6+7)) + 89) \\
 13753 &:= ((1+(((2 \times 3)^4) \times (5+6))) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
 13754 &:= (1 - (((2 \times ((3^4) \times 5)) + (6-7)) \times -(8+9))) \\
 13755 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((34 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8)) + 9))) \\
 13756 &:= ((1+((2+34) \times 5)) \times -((6+7) - 89)) \\
 13757 &:= ((-12 \times ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times 67)) + 89) \\
 13758 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(((3+(4 \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
 13759 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3+(4 \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
 13760 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -((4^5) - (6 - (78 \times 9)))))) \\
 13761 &:= (((((12^3) - (4+5)) \times -((6-7) \times 8)) + 9) \\
 13762 &:= (1 \times -(2+(3 \times (4+(56 \times (7-89)))))) \\
 13763 &:= (1 - (2+(3 \times (4+(56 \times (7-89)))))) \\
 13764 &:= ((1+2) - (((3^4) \times -(5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8))) + 9)) \\
 13765 &:= (1 \times -((2+3) - (45 \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))) \\
 13766 &:= (1 - ((2+3) - (45 \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))) \\
 13767 &:= (1 \times (((2+(34+5)) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
 13768 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) \times -(4 - (5 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)))))) \\
 13769 &:= (1 + ((2^3) \times -(4 - (5 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)))))) \\
 13770 &:= ((1 - (23 \times (4 \times 5))) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\
 13771 &:= (1 \times ((23+(45 \times 6)) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 13772 &:= ((1+((2+3)^4)) \times -((5 \times (6-7)) - (8+9))) \\
 13773 &:= (12 - (((3^4) \times -(5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8))) + 9)) \\
 13774 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(34 + ((5+6) \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\
 13775 &:= (((((1+2)^{3+4}) + 5) \times 6) - (7 \times -89)) \\
 13776 &:= (12 \times (((34 \times 5) - 6) \times -(7 \times (8-9)))) \\
 13777 &:= (((1+23)^{4+5-6}) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
 13778 &:= (1 \times -((2+(3^4)) \times -(((5+6) \times 7) + 89))) \\
 13779 &:= (1 - ((2+(3^4)) \times -(((5+6) \times 7) + 89))) \\
 13780 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -((4+5) \times 67)) + 89)) \\
 13781 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3^4) \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8))) + 9))) \\
 13782 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3^4) \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8))) + 9))) \\
 13783 &:= ((1-2) \times -(((3+4)^5) - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 13784 &:= (((12^3) - (4 - (5 - 6))) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
 13785 &:= (1 \times -(((2+(34+5)) \times -(6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
 13786 &:= (((1+2) + ((3+4)^5)) + (6 \times -(7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 13787 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times ((3^4) \times 5)) - (6-7)) \times -(8+9))) \\
 13788 &:= (1 - (((2 \times ((3^4) \times 5)) - (6-7)) \times -(8+9))) \\
 13789 &:= ((1-2) - ((3 \times -4567) - 89)) \\
 13790 &:= ((1 - (23 \times (4+56))) \times (7 - (8+9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 13749 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -(((6^5)/4) + (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\
 13750 &:= ((98 - 76) \times -((5^4) \times -(3/(2+1)))) \\
 13751 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times (654 \times 3))) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
 13752 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times (6 + ((5 + 4) \times (3 \times 21)))) \\
 13753 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(7 - (((6 \times 5) + 4) \times (3 + 21)))) \\
 13754 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -((6 \times 5) + (4 \times 32))) + 1)) \\
 13755 &:= (9 - (87 \times -((6 + 5) + ((4 + 3) \times 21)))) \\
 13756 &:= (9 + ((87 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4 \times 32))) + 1)) \\
 13757 &:= (9 - (8 - ((76 \times 543)/(2 + 1)))) \\
 13758 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
 13759 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 + (7 \times 654))) + 3)/(2 + 1)) \\
 13760 &:= (9 - (((8 + (76 \times (5 \times 4))) \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\
 13761 &:= (9 - ((8 + (76 \times (5 \times 4))) \times -(3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 13762 &:= (9 - (((8 + (76 \times (5 \times 4))) \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
 13763 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -((65 - 4) \times 32)) - 1)) \\
 13764 &:= ((98 + (7 + 6)) \times (((5^4)/(3 + 2)) - 1)) \\
 13765 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times 654)) \times -3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 13766 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times 654)) \times -3) + (2 - 1))) \\
 13767 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times 654)) \times -(3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
 13768 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times (6 + (5 \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))) \\
 13769 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + (6^5))/4)) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
 13770 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -(((6^5)/4) + (3^2))) - 1)) \\
 13771 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -7) + (6 \times (((5 + 43)^2) - 1)))) \\
 13772 &:= ((98 - 76) \times -(((5^4) + (3 - 2)) \times -1)) \\
 13773 &:= (((9 + 8) - ((7 + 65) \times (4^3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 13774 &:= ((98 - (7 - 6)) \times -((5 - ((4 + 3) \times 21)))) \\
 13775 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times (5 \times (4 - (32 + 1)))) \\
 13776 &:= (98 - (7 \times -(((6^5)/4) + ((3^2) + 1)))) \\
 13777 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times -((5 + 43)^2 \times 1))) \\
 13778 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6 \times -((5 + 43)^2)) - 1)) \\
 13779 &:= ((98 - 7) + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2) - 1)) \\
 13780 &:= (98 + ((7 - (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2)) \times -1)) \\
 13781 &:= (98 - (7 - (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2) + 1)) \\
 13782 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (6 - (((5 + 43)^2) - 1))) \\
 13783 &:= ((9 - (87 \times (6 \times 5))) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
 13784 &:= ((9 + 87) + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2) - 1)) \\
 13785 &:= ((9 + 87) - (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2) \times -1)) \\
 13786 &:= ((9 + 87) + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2) + 1)) \\
 13787 &:= (98 + (((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4))^{3-2+1})) \\
 13788 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times -((6 - ((5 + 43)^2)) \times -1)) \\
 13789 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (7 - ((654 + 3) \times 21))) \\
 13790 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 - ((654 + 3) \times 21)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13791 &:= (12 - (((3^4) \times -(5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8))) - 9)) & 13791 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - ((654 + 3) \times 21))) \\
13792 &:= (((12^3) - 4) \times (5 - 6)) \times -(7 - (8 - 9)) & 13792 &:= ((9 - (876 - 5)) \times (4 \times -((3 + 2) - 1))) \\
13793 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3 \times ((4 + 5) \times 6)) - 7) \times 89))) & 13793 &:= (98 + ((7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
13794 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times 5)))) \times -((6 \times 7) - (8 \times 9))) & 13794 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (((4^3) + 2) \times -1)) \\
13795 &:= ((12 + ((3 + 4)^5)) + (6 \times -(7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 13795 &:= (98 + (7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)^2) + 1)) \\
13796 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times ((4 + 5) \times 67))) + (8 \times -9)) & 13796 &:= (98 + ((765 - 4) \times -(3 - 21))) \\
13797 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (45 \times -(((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) & 13797 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times (4 - (32 - 1))) \\
13798 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 \times ((4 + 5) \times 6)) - 7) \times -89)) & 13798 &:= (9 - (8 - (7 \times ((654 + 3) \times (2 + 1)))))) \\
13799 &:= (((12^3) + (4 - (5 - (6 - 7)))) \times 8) - 9 & 13799 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (7 \times -((654 \times 3) - (2 - 1)))) \\
13800 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -(4 \times -(5 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)))) & 13800 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -((6 \times -((5 + 43) \times 2)) + 1)) \\
13801 &:= ((1 - (((23 \times 4) - ((5^6) - 7)) \times 8))/9) & 13801 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((7 - (6 + 5)) \times (432 - 1)))) \\
13802 &:= (1 - (23 - (4 \times (((56 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))) & 13802 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 765))/ -4) + 32) \times 1 \\
13803 &:= ((1 + (2^{3+4})) \times (5 + (6 + (7 + 89)))) & 13803 &:= ((9 + (87 + (6 + 5))) \times -((4 \times -32) - 1)) \\
13804 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(((3^4) \times 5) - (6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9))) & 13804 &:= (((9 - 8) + (((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3)) - 21) \\
13805 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3^4) \times 5) - (6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9))) & 13805 &:= (((9 + 8) - (((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3) - 2)) \times -1 \\
13806 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 \times -((4^5) + (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 13806 &:= ((9 + (87 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times -(4 - 3)) - 21)) \\
13807 &:= (12 - (((3 \times ((4 + 5) \times 6)) - 7) \times -89)) & 13807 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 + 6)) \times -((5^4) + 32)) - 1)) \\
13808 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times -(3 \times (4 \times (567 + 8)))) - 9)) & 13808 &:= ((98 + 765) \times -(4 \times -((3 + 2) - 1))) \\
13809 &:= ((1 - (((2 + (3^4)) - ((5^6) - 7)) \times 8))/9) & 13809 &:= (9 + (((8 + (7 \times 6)) - (5^4)) \times -(3 + 21))) \\
13810 &:= ((1 + (23 \times (4 + 56))) \times -(7 - (8 + 9))) & 13810 &:= (-98 - (76 \times -((54 \times 3) + 21))) \\
13811 &:= (((1 + 2) - (((3^4) - ((5^6) - 7)) \times 8))/9) & 13811 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 - (6 \times (((5 + 43)^2) - 1)))) \\
13812 &:= ((12 - (((3^4) - ((5^6) - 7)) \times 8))/9) & 13812 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - (6 \times (((5 + 43)^2) - 1)))) \\
13813 &:= ((((-1 + (2^3))^4) + 5) \times 6) + (7 \times -89)) & 13813 &:= (((-98 + 76) \times -(5^4)) - (3 \times -21)) \\
13814 &:= (((12^3) \times -4) + 5) \times (6 - (7 - (8 - 9))) & 13814 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times ((654 + 3) \times (2 + 1)))))) \\
13815 &:= (((12 + 3)^4) - ((5 \times (6^7))/8))/ -9) & 13815 &:= ((987 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times ((3 + 2) \times -1)) \\
13816 &:= (((1 + 23)^{4+5-6}) - 7) + (8 - 9)) & 13816 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(((7 \times -6) + 54)^3) - 2)) + 1) \\
13817 &:= (((12^3) + (4 - (5 - (6 - 7)))) \times 8) + 9 & 13817 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 - (6 \times ((5 + 43)^2))) \times -1)) \\
13818 &:= (((1 + 23)^{4+5-6}) - 7) - (8 - 9)) & 13818 &:= ((98 - (7^{(6-5) \times 4})) \times (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
13819 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) - (4 \times (((56 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))) & 13819 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) - ((6 \times -((5 + 43)^2)) - 1)) \\
13820 &:= ((1 - 2) - (3 - (4 \times (((56 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))) & 13820 &:= (((9 + 8) + (((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3)) - 21) \\
13821 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (((3^4) \times 5) - (6 - 7))) \times (8 + 9)) & 13821 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3) - (2 + 1))) \\
13822 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times ((456 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) & 13822 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3) - 2) \times -1) \\
13823 &:= (((1 + 23)^{45-6 \times 7}) + (8 - 9)) & 13823 &:= (9 + ((8 - (((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3) - 2)) \times -1) \\
13824 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -(4^5))/(6 - (7 - (8 - 9))) & 13824 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -6) \times (((5 + 43)^2) \times -1) \\
13825 &:= ((1 + ((2 - ((3^4) - ((5^6) + 7))) \times 8))/9) & 13825 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (6 \times -((5 + 43)^2 \times 1))) \\
13826 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5^6))) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 13826 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3) + 2) \times -1) \\
13827 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(3 + (4 \times (((56 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))) & 13827 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3) + 2) \times -1) \\
13828 &:= (((-123 \times -4) - (((5^6) - 7) \times 8))/ -9) & 13828 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
13829 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) - 8)) + 9)) & 13829 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -(654 \times 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\
13830 &:= (1 - (((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) - 8)) + 9)) & 13830 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (((7 \times -6) + 54)^3))) - (2 + 1)) \\
13831 &:= (((1 + 23)^{4+5-6}) + 7) \times -(8 - 9)) & 13831 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (((7 \times -6) + 54)^3))) + (2 \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13832 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -(4 + (5 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)))))) \\
13833 &:= (1 - ((2^3) \times -(4 + (5 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)))))) \\
13834 &:= (((12^3) \times -4) - 5) \times (6 - (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
13835 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((34 - 5) \times ((6 \times 78) + 9)))) \\
13836 &:= (12 \times (((3^4) - (5 - 67)) \times 8) + 9) \\
13837 &:= (1 - (2 - (34 \times ((5 \times 67) + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
13838 &:= ((1 - 23) \times ((4 - 5) \times (6 + (7 \times 89)))) \\
13839 &:= (12 + (3 + (4 \times (((56 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))) \\
13840 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -(4 \times (5 + (678 + 9)))))) \\
13841 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 + 4)^{5-6+7}))) / -(8 + 9)) \\
13842 &:= (1 - (((23 + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\
13843 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3 \times (456 + (7 \times 8)))) \times -9)) \\
13844 &:= ((12^3) - (4 \times -(5 + (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
13845 &:= (1 \times (((23 \times (4 + 5)) + 6) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
13846 &:= (1 + (((23 \times (4 + 5)) + 6) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
13847 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) - 8)) - 9)) \\
13848 &:= (1 - (((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) - 8)) - 9)) \\
13849 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times ((45 + (6 \times 78)) \times 9)))) \\
13850 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times ((45 + (6 \times 78)) \times 9)))) \\
13851 &:= (((1 - 2) - (34 \times 5)) \times -((6 - (7 + 8)) \times -9)) \\
13852 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -((4 + 5) \times 67)) + (8 + 9))) \\
13853 &:= (((1 + (23 \times ((4 + 5) \times 67))) - 8) - 9) \\
13854 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + 5) \times 6) - (78 \times -9)) \\
13855 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times (5 \times -((6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
13856 &:= (((12^3) + 4) \times (5 - 6)) \times -(7 - (8 - 9)) \\
13857 &:= ((1 + (23 \times 4)) \times -((5 \times -6) - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
13858 &:= ((-1 - (((2^3) + (4 \times 5)) \times 6)) \times (7 - 89)) \\
13859 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 34) \times -(5 + (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
13860 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 \times (4 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9))))))) \\
13861 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) \times 6) + 789)))) \\
13862 &:= (((-1 - 234) \times -56) - (78 \times -9)) \\
13863 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 34) - ((5^6) + 7)) \times 8)) / -9) \\
13864 &:= (((12^3) + (4 - (5 - 6))) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
13865 &:= (((12^3) - (4 - (56/7))) \times 8) + 9) \\
13866 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -(((4^5) \times -6) - 789)) \\
13867 &:= ((-1 + ((23 \times ((4 + 5) \times 67)) + 8)) - 9) \\
13868 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -((4 + 5) \times 67)) - (8 - 9))) \\
13869 &:= (((1 + 234) - (((5^6) + 7) \times 8)) / -9) \\
13870 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -((4 + 5) \times 67)) + (8 - 9))) \\
13871 &:= (((1 + 23)^{4+5-6}) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
13872 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 - 5)) - 6) \times -(7 - (8 - 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13832 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) - (6 \times -((5 + 43)^2 \times 1))) \\
13833 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times -(5 + (4^{3+2-1}))) \\
13834 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 - (6 \times ((5 + 43)^2))) \times -1)) \\
13835 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (((7 \times -6) + 54)^3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
13836 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (((7 \times -6) + 54)^3))) + (2 + 1)) \\
13837 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 + (6 \times (((5 + 43)^2) + 1)))) \\
13838 &:= (9 + ((8 + (((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
13839 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3) - 2) \times -1)) \\
13840 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3) - (2 - 1))) \\
13841 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 + 65) \times -((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
13842 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) - (6 \times -(((5 + 43)^2) - 1))) \\
13843 &:= (9 + (8 + (((((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
13844 &:= (9 + (8 + (((((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
13845 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3) + 21)) \\
13846 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times -(4^3)) - (2 \times 1))) \\
13847 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) - (2 + 1))) \\
13848 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 - 5))) \times -(4 \times -(3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
13849 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) - ((6 \times -((5 + 43)^2)) - 1)) \\
13850 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(((7 \times -6) + 54)^3) + 2)) - 1) \\
13851 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times 765)/4)) \times -(3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
13852 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 + 6)) + 5) \times -((4 \times 32) - 1))) \\
13853 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 \times -(((6 \times 5) \times ((4^3) + 2)) - 1))) \\
13854 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 \times -(((6 \times 5) \times ((4^3) + 2)) - 1))) \\
13855 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(7 - (6 \times (5 + (4 \times (32 + 1)))))) \\
13856 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times (((6^5)/4) + (32 + 1)))) \\
13857 &:= ((9 + (8 + 76)) \times -((5 + ((4 \times 3)^2)) \times -1)) \\
13858 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (5 - ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
13859 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times -((4^3) + 2)) + 1)) \\
13860 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times -((4^3) + 2)) + 1)) \\
13861 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times ((4^3) + 2))) \times -1)) \\
13862 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times -((4^3) + 2)) - 1)) \\
13863 &:= (((-9 \times 87) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
13864 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -((6 \times -((5 + (4 \times 3)^2)) + 1)) \\
13865 &:= ((9 + ((87 + 6) \times (5 + ((4 \times 3)^2)))) - 1) \\
13866 &:= ((9 + ((87 + 6) \times (5 + ((4 \times 3)^2)))) \times 1) \\
13867 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 \times -(((6 \times 5) \times ((4^3) + 2)) + 1))) \\
13868 &:= (9 - (8 - (7 \times (((6 \times 5) \times ((4^3) + 2)) + 1)))) \\
13869 &:= (9 \times (8 + (((7 + (65 + 4)) - 3) \times 21))) \\
13870 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times (((6 \times 5) \times ((4^3) + 2)) - 1)))) \\
13871 &:= (((9 + (87 + 6)) - 5) \times (((4 \times 3)^2) - 1)) \\
13872 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 \times -(6 \times (5 \times 4))) + (3 + 21)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13873 &:= (((((12^3) + 4) \times (56/7)) + 8) + 9) \\
13874 &:= (1 \times (2 - (((3 \times 4) - ((5^6) - 7)) \times 8)/9)) \\
13875 &:= (1 + (2 - (((3 \times 4) - ((5^6) - 7)) \times 8)/9)) \\
13876 &:= (1 - (((234 - 56) \times -78) + 9)) \\
13877 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 + (4 \times (5^6))) - (7 \times 8)))) / -9) \\
13878 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3^4) \times -(56 - (7 - 8))) - 9)) \\
13879 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) \times -(((4 \times 56) - 7) \times 8)) + 9)) \\
13880 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (3 - 4)) - ((5^6) - 7)) \times 8) / -9) \\
13881 &:= (1 + (((2 - (3 - 4)) - ((5^6) - 7)) \times 8) / -9) \\
13882 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((4 \times ((5^6) + (7 - 8)))) / 9)) \\
13883 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - (3 - 4)) + ((5^6) - 7) \times 8) / -9)) \\
13884 &:= (1 - (((2 - (3 - 4)) + ((5^6) - 7) \times 8) / -9)) \\
13885 &:= ((-1 + ((23 \times ((4 + 5) \times 67)) + 8)) + 9) \\
13886 &:= (((12^3) + (4 - ((5^6) - 7))) \times (8 - 9)) \\
13887 &:= (1 \times (((2^3) \times (4 - (5^6))) - (7 + 8)) / -9) \\
13888 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times (3 - ((4 \times (5^6)) + (7 - 8)))) / -9)) \\
13889 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times -((3 - 4) \times 5))^6) + 7)) / - (8 \times -9)) \\
13890 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -((4 \times -56) - (78 \times 9))) \\
13891 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3) + ((4 - ((5^6) + 7)) \times 8)) / 9)) \\
13892 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) + ((4 - ((5^6) + 7)) \times 8)) / 9)) \\
13893 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (((3^{4+5}) \times 6) - 7))) / - (8 + 9)) \\
13894 &:= (((12^3) - ((4 + (5^6)) - 7)) \times (8 - 9)) \\
13895 &:= (1 + (((2^3) \times (4 - (5^6))) - 78) / -9) \\
13896 &:= (((12^3) + (4 + 5)) \times ((6 - 78) / -9)) \\
13897 &:= (1 \times (((2^3) \times (((4 \times 56) - 7) \times 8)) + 9)) \\
13898 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 3) - ((4 + ((5^6) + 7)) \times 8)) / 9)) \\
13899 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3) - ((4 + ((5^6) + 7)) \times 8)) / 9)) \\
13900 &:= (((12^3) + (4 - ((5^6) + 7))) \times (8 - 9)) \\
13901 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 + ((4 + ((5^6) + 7)) \times 8)) / 9)) \\
13902 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3 + ((4 + ((5^6) + 7)) \times 8)) / 9)) \\
13903 &:= (((1 + 23)^{4+5-6} + 7) - (8 \times -9)) \\
13904 &:= ((-12 + (34 \times 5)) \times (6 - (7 - 89))) \\
13905 &:= ((12 + 3) \times (((4 + 5) \times ((6 + 7) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
13906 &:= (1 + ((23 - (4 \times ((56 - 7) \times 8))) \times -9)) \\
13907 &:= (12 - (((3 - 4) + ((5^6) + 7) \times 8) / -9)) \\
13908 &:= (((12^3) - (4 + ((5^6) + 7))) \times (8 - 9)) \\
13909 &:= (1 - ((23 - 4) \times -((5 \times 6) + (78 \times 9)))) \\
13910 &:= (((12^3) - (4 + (5^6))) \times (7 - 8) + 9) \\
13911 &:= (12 - ((3 + ((4 + ((5^6) + 7)) \times 8)) / -9)) \\
13912 &:= (1 \times (((23 - 4) + ((5^6) + 7)) \times 8) / 9) \\
13913 &:= (1 + (((23 - 4) + ((5^6) + 7)) \times 8) / 9) \\
13873 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 - 6) \times 5) + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))) \\
13874 &:= (98 - (7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) + (3 + 21)))) \\
13875 &:= ((98 + (7 + 6)) \times -((5^4) / -((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
13876 &:= (9 + ((8 + ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times ((4^3) + 2))) - 1)) \\
13877 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times ((4^3) + 2))) \times -1)) \\
13878 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times -((4^3) + 2)) - 1)) \\
13879 &:= ((-9 \times - (8 - ((7 + 6) \times ((5 - (4^3)) \times 2)))) + 1) \\
13880 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -((6 \times -((5 + (4 \times 3))^2)) - 1)) \\
13881 &:= (9 + ((8 - 76) \times -((5 \times (43 - 2)) - 1))) \\
13882 &:= ((98 - 76) \times -(((5^4) + (3 \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
13883 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - (6 \times (((5 + 43)^2) - 1)))) \\
13884 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times (((6 \times 5) \times ((4^3) + 2)) + 1)))) \\
13885 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times ((6 + 54) \times 3) - 2) + 1) \\
13886 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + (76 \times 5)) \times 4)) \times (3^2)) - 1) \\
13887 &:= ((9 - ((8 + (76 \times 5)) \times 4)) \times (3 \times - (2 + 1))) \\
13888 &:= (9 - ((8 \times - (7 + (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 32)))) + 1)) \\
13889 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 \times -((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
13890 &:= (9 - ((876 - (5 \times 43)) \times -21)) \\
13891 &:= (-9 - (8 - (76 \times ((54 \times 3) + 21)))) \\
13892 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 76) + 5)) \times -((4 \times (3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
13893 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - ((5^4) - 3)))) \times - (2 + 1)) \\
13894 &:= (-98 + (((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times - (3 + 21))) \\
13895 &:= (((9 + 8) + (76 \times 5)) \times -((4 \times - (3^2)) + 1)) \\
13896 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 76) - (5 \times 4))) \times - (3 + 21)) \\
13897 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((76 - (5 \times 4)) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
13898 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times ((654 \times 3) + 21)))) \\
13899 &:= ((-9 \times - (87 + 6)) - (((5^4) - 3) \times -21)) \\
13900 &:= ((9 - ((876 - 5) \times 4)) \times -((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
13901 &:= (98 - (((7 \times 6) + (5 - 4)) \times -321)) \\
13902 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times 6) \times -((5 \times ((4^3) + 2)) + 1))) \\
13903 &:= (9 - (8 - ((7 \times 6) \times ((5 \times ((4^3) + 2)) + 1)))) \\
13904 &:= ((98 - 76) \times ((5^4) + ((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\
13905 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) + 4)) \times - (3^{2+1})) \\
13906 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((7 \times -((6 + 5) - (4 \times 32))) - 1)) \\
13907 &:= (-9 + (8 + (76 \times ((54 \times 3) + 21)))) \\
13908 &:= ((9 - 8) \times - (76 \times -((54 \times 3) + 21))) \\
13909 &:= (98 - (7 - (6 \times (((5 + 43)^2) - 1)))) \\
13910 &:= (-9 - ((87 \times -((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)) - 2)) + 1)) \\
13911 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 \times 6)) - ((5^4) + 3)) \times -21)) \\
13912 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times - (6 + (((5 + (4 \times 3))^2) + 1))) \\
13913 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 765)) + (4 - 3)) \times -2) + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13914 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -3) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 - (78 \times 9)))))) \\
13915 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -3) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 - (78 \times 9)))))) \\
13916 &:= (12 - (((34 \times 5) + 6) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
13917 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (3 \times -(4567 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
13918 &:= (12 + (34 \times -(5 - (6 \times (78 - 9)))))) \\
13919 &:= ((1 - (((23 + 4) + ((5^6) + 7)) \times 8)) / -9) \\
13920 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^4)) \times -(((5 + 6) \times -(7 + 8)) - 9)) \\
13921 &:= (1 \times -((2 - 3) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 - (78 \times 9)))))) \\
13922 &:= (1 - ((2 - 3) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 - (78 \times 9)))))) \\
13923 &:= ((1 - (23 \times 4)) \times (((5 + (6 + 7)) \times -8) - 9)) \\
13924 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times ((5 \times 6) + (7 \times 8)))))) - 9) \\
13925 &:= (((1 + 2) - ((34 + ((5^6) + 7)) \times 8)) / -9) \\
13926 &:= ((1 - 23) \times -(4 - ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
13927 &:= ((1 - (((2 + 34) + ((5^6) + 7)) \times 8)) / -9) \\
13928 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3) + (4 \times 5)) \times (67 \times 8))) - 9) \\
13929 &:= (1 + ((2^3) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 - (78 \times 9)))))) \\
13930 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) \times -(4 - (5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))))) \\
13931 &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times -(4 - (5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))))) \\
13932 &:= ((1 + (2^{3+4})) \times (((5 + 6) - (7 - 8)) \times 9)) \\
13933 &:= (-1 + (2 - (3 \times ((4 - (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\
13934 &:= (1 \times (2 - (3 \times (((4 \times 5) - (67 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
13935 &:= ((1 + ((2^3) \times (4 - ((5^6) + (7 \times 8)))))) / -9) \\
13936 &:= ((1 + (((2 - (3 - 4))^5) + 6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) \\
13937 &:= (((-1 - (23 \times (4 + 5))) \times -67) - (8 - 9)) \\
13938 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times (3 - (4 \times ((5^6) + (7 \times 8)))))) / -9) \\
13939 &:= (1 + ((2 \times (3 - (4 \times ((5^6) + (7 \times 8)))))) / -9) \\
13940 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times 67) + 8) \times 9)) \\
13941 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 - (45 \times (6 + 7))) \times 8) + 9)) \\
13942 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times ((5 \times 6) + (7 \times 8)))))) + 9) \\
13943 &:= (1 \times -(((2^{3+4}) \times -(5 + ((6 + 7) \times 8))) + 9)) \\
13944 &:= (1 - (((2^{3+4}) \times -(5 + ((6 + 7) \times 8))) + 9)) \\
13945 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 3) + (4 \times 5)) \times -(67 \times 8)) - 9) \\
13946 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3) + (4 \times 5)) \times -(67 \times 8)) - 9) \\
13947 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + (4 \times -(5 \times (6 - (78 \times 9)))))) \\
13948 &:= ((12 - 34) \times -((5 + 6) + (7 \times 89))) \\
13949 &:= (((-1 - 234) \times -56) + 789) \\
13950 &:= ((1 + (23 \times 4)) \times -(5 \times -(6 + (7 + (8 + 9)))))) \\
13951 &:= (1 - ((2 - (3 \times ((4 \times 5) - (67 \times 8)))) \times -9)) \\
13952 &:= (1 \times -(((2^{3+4}) \times -((5 \times 6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
13953 &:= ((1 - ((2 - ((3^4) + ((5^6) - 7))) \times 8)) / 9) \\
13954 &:= (1 - (((2 - (3 - 4))^5) + 6) \times -(7 \times 8) - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13914 &:= (98 - (7 - ((6 \times ((5 + 43)^2)) - 1))) \\
13915 &:= (98 + ((7 - (6 \times ((5 + 43)^2))) \times -1)) \\
13916 &:= ((98 - 7) - ((6 \times -((5 + 43)^2)) - 1)) \\
13917 &:= (987 - (6 \times -(5 \times (432 - 1)))) \\
13918 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6^5)))) / 4) + 321) \\
13919 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times 6) \times -((5 \times ((4^3) + 2)) + 1))) \\
13920 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(6 \times -(((5 + (4 \times 3))^2) + 1))) \\
13921 &:= (98 + (((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3) - (2 - 1)) \\
13922 &:= (98 - ((7 + 65) \times -((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
13923 &:= ((98 + 7) - (6 \times -(((5 + 43)^2) - 1))) \\
13924 &:= (98 - (((((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3) + 2) \times -1)) \\
13925 &:= (98 + (((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3) + (2 + 1)) \\
13926 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -(((4^3) + 2) \times -1)) \\
13927 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 765)) - (4 + 3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
13928 &:= (98 + ((7 + (6 \times ((5 + 43)^2))) - 1)) \\
13929 &:= ((98 + 7) - (6 \times -((5 + 43)^2 \times 1))) \\
13930 &:= ((98 + 7) - ((6 \times -((5 + 43)^2)) - 1)) \\
13931 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) + 32)) - 1)) \\
13932 &:= ((9 + ((87 + ((6 \times 5) + (4 - 3)))^2)) - 1) \\
13933 &:= (9 - (((87 + ((6 \times 5) + (4 - 3)))^2) \times -1)) \\
13934 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times (7 + 6)) + 5) \times (4^3))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
13935 &:= (98 + (7 + (6 \times (((5 + 43)^2) + 1)))) \\
13936 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) + (54 \times 32)))) - 1) \\
13937 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) / 4)) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
13938 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 + 6) + (54 \times 32))) - 1)) \\
13939 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) \times 54) - 3) \times -2) + 1) \\
13940 &:= ((98 + ((7 - (6 - 5))^4)) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\
13941 &:= (9 - ((8 \times ((76 + 5) \times 43)) / - (2 \times 1))) \\
13942 &:= (9 - (((8 \times ((76 + 5) \times 43)) / - 2) - 1)) \\
13943 &:= (98 + (((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3) + 21) \\
13944 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) \times -(43 - (2 - 1))) \\
13945 &:= (9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) + ((54 \times 32) + 1)))) \\
13946 &:= (9 + (8 + (((7 \times (6^5)) / 4) + 321))) \\
13947 &:= (9 + (876 + (((5^4) - 3) \times 21))) \\
13948 &:= ((98 - 76) \times -(((5^4) + (3^2)) \times -1)) \\
13949 &:= (9 + ((8 - 76) \times -(5 \times ((43 - 2) \times 1)))) \\
13950 &:= (((9 + 87) - 6) \times -(5 \times -(4 + (3^{2+1})))) \\
13951 &:= (98 - (7 \times -(((6 \times 5) \times ((4^3) + 2)) - 1))) \\
13952 &:= ((9 - (876 + 5)) \times (4 \times -((3 + 2) - 1))) \\
13953 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(7 \times ((6 \times (5 - 43)) - 21)))) \\
13954 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times -(76 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))) + 21))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13955 &:= (((1+2) + (((3^4) + ((5^6) - 7)) \times 8)) / 9) \\
13956 &:= ((12 + (((3^4) + ((5^6) - 7)) \times 8)) / 9) \\
13957 &:= (1 \times -((2 + (3 \times ((45 - 6) \times 7))) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
13958 &:= (((1+2)^3) - (4^5)) \times -((6+7) - (8-9)) \\
13959 &:= (((1+2)^{3+4}) \times 5) - (6 \times -(7 \times (8 \times 9))) \\
13960 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -(((4 \times 56) - 7) \times 8) + 9)) \\
13961 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times (((5+6) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9)) \\
13962 &:= (((1+2) - (3^4)) \times ((5 \times -((6 \times 7) - 8)) - 9)) \\
13963 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(3 \times (4 - ((5 \times (6 \times 78)) - 9)))) \\
13964 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!! - 4!) \times 5! / 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
13965 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times -(5 - ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
13966 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times (4567 + 89)))) \\
13967 &:= (((1-2) + (((3^4) + ((5^6) + 7)) \times 8)) / 9) \\
13968 &:= ((12^3) - (((4^5) + (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times -9)) \\
13969 &:= ((1 + ((2 + ((3^4) + ((5^6) + 7))) \times 8)) / 9) \\
13970 &:= (1 \times -((2+3) \times -(4 + (5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
13971 &:= (1 - ((2+3) \times -(4 + (5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
13972 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (34 \times ((5 \times (6 + 78)) - 9))) \\
13973 &:= (1 - (2 - (34 \times ((5 \times (6 + 78)) - 9))) \\
13974 &:= ((1+2) \times ((3 - ((45 \times 6) + 7)) \times -(8+9))) \\
13975 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -((4 + (5 + 67)) \times 8)) + 9)) \\
13976 &:= (1 - ((23 \times -((4 + (5 + 67)) \times 8)) + 9)) \\
13977 &:= ((1 + ((23 \times 4) + ((5^6) + 7)) \times 8) / 9) \\
13978 &:= (1 + ((23 - ((4 \times (56 \times 7)) + 8)) \times -9)) \\
13979 &:= (-1 - (2 \times -(3 + ((4^5) + (67 \times 89)))) \\
13980 &:= (12 \times ((3 \times -(4 - (56 \times 7))) - (8 - 9))) \\
13981 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (34 \times 5))) \times -((6 \times -7) - (8 - 9))) \\
13982 &:= (((-1 + 2345) \times 6) + 7) - 89 \\
13983 &:= (1 \times -((2345 \times -6) + (78 + 9))) \\
13984 &:= (((12^3) + (4 \times 5)) \times -(6 - 78)) / 9) \\
13985 &:= (12 - (((34 \times 5) - (6 + 7)) \times -89)) \\
13986 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times ((4 \times 5) - (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
13987 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(((3^4) - ((5+6) \times 78)) \times 9)) \\
13988 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 45))) \times ((6 \times 78) / -9)) \\
13989 &:= ((1 + ((2345 \times 6) + 7)) - 89) \\
13990 &:= (((-1 + (2345 \times 6)) - 7) + (8 \times -9)) \\
13991 &:= (1 \times -((2345 \times -6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
13992 &:= ((1 - (23^4)) / -5 \times -((6+7) - (8+9))) \\
13993 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -((4 + (5 + 67)) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
13994 &:= (1 - ((23 \times -((4 + (5 + 67)) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
13995 &:= ((1+2) \times -(3 \times -((4^5) + ((67 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
13996 &:= (-1 + (2 - (((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times 7) - 8) \times 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13955 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) + ((6+5)^4)) - (3-2)) + 1) \\
13956 &:= (-9 - (((8+7) \times 6) + 5) \times -((4+3) \times 21)) \\
13957 &:= ((9+8) \times -((7 \times -((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)) - (2 \times 1))) \\
13958 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (4^3))) - (2 + 1)) \\
13959 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (4^3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
13960 &:= ((9 - ((8 - 76) \times 5)) \times -(4 \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
13961 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -(43 + 21))) \\
13962 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 + 6)) + 5) \times -(4 \times 32)) - 1) \\
13963 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (4^3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
13964 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -(4^3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
13965 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (5^4)))) \times (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
13966 &:= (9876 - (5 - ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\
13967 &:= (9876 + ((5 - (4^{3 \times 2})) \times -1)) \\
13968 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -(6 \times -((5 + 43) \times 2) + 1)) \\
13969 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((76 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
13970 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times (7 + 6)) + 5) \times (4^3))) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
13971 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times 654)) \times -3) + 21 \\
13972 &:= ((987 + (6 + 5)) \times ((4 + 3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
13973 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) + ((6+5)^4)) - 3) + 21) \\
13974 &:= ((9 + (87 + 6)) \times -(((5 + (4^3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
13975 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (76 - 5))) \times ((4 \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
13976 &:= (9 - (((8 + (76 \times 5)) \times -(4 + 32)) + 1)) \\
13977 &:= (9 - ((8 + (76 \times 5)) \times -((4 + 32) \times 1))) \\
13978 &:= (9 - (((8 + (76 \times 5)) \times -(4 + 32)) - 1)) \\
13979 &:= (98 - (7 \times -((654 \times 3) + 21))) \\
13980 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times 3)) - 21)) \\
13981 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times 3)) + 2)) \times -1) \\
13982 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) \times ((6 - (5 - 4))^3))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
13983 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) + 6) \times 54) / -3) - (2 + 1) \\
13984 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times (65 \times 43)) / - (2 + 1))) \\
13985 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((76 \times ((5 + 4) - 32)) + 1))) \\
13986 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times 3) + 2)) + 1) \\
13987 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) + 6) \times -54) + 3) / (2 + 1) \\
13988 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) + 6) \times 54) / -3) - (2 \times -1) \\
13989 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times -(43 - 2)) + 1) \\
13990 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)))) - (2 + 1)) \\
13991 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
13992 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times -(3 + 21))) \\
13993 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times -(3 + 21))) \\
13994 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -((76 \times ((5 + 4) - 32))) + 1)) \\
13995 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
13996 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((76 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))) - (2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13997 &:= (1 \times (2 - (((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\
13998 &:= (1 + (2 - (((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\
13999 &:= (1 + (2 \times -((3 \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times 78)))) + 9)) \\
14000 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^4)) \times -(((5 \times 6) - 7) \times -8) + 9) \\
14001 &:= (1 \times -((2345 \times -6) + (78 - 9))) \\
14002 &:= (((1 + (2345 \times 6)) - 78) + 9) \\
14003 &:= ((1 - (2 \times 34)) \times ((5 \times -(6 \times 7)) - (8 - 9))) \\
14004 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 \times -4) + (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
14005 &:= (1 + (((23 \times (4 - (5 + 67))) + 8) \times -9)) \\
14006 &:= ((1 + ((23 + 4) \times (5 + 6))) \times -((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
14007 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times ((5 - 6) \times (78 + 9))) \\
14008 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times 78)))))) - 9) \\
14009 &:= ((1 + (((2^{3+4}) + (5^6) + 7) \times 8))/9) \\
14010 &:= (1 + (((2 + ((3 - 45) \times 6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9)) \\
14011 &:= (1 - (2 \times -3 \times ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times 78))) - 9))) \\
14012 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (((4 + 56) \times 78) - 9)))) \\
14013 &:= (((12 + 3)^4)/5) - ((6^7)/ - (8 \times 9)) \\
14014 &:= (1 \times ((23 - (4^5)) \times -((6 + 7) - (8 - 9)))) \\
14015 &:= (1 + ((23 - (4^5)) \times -((6 + 7) - (8 - 9)))) \\
14016 &:= (((12^3)/ - (4 + 5)) \times ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\
14017 &:= (1 \times -23 - (((4^5) + (67 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
14018 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times (5 - (6 - (78 + 9)))) \\
14019 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 + 4) - (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
14020 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -4 \times ((5 - 6) + (78 \times 9)))) \\
14021 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) \times -4 \times ((5 - 6) + (78 \times 9)))) \\
14022 &:= (((1 + 2) - 345) \times ((6 \times -7) - (8 - 9))) \\
14023 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((34 + 56) \times 78) - 9)) \\
14024 &:= ((1 + (2345 \times 6)) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
14025 &:= ((1 - (2 - 34)) \times -5 \times -((6 + 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
14026 &:= (1 \times -2 + (3 \times (4 - (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
14027 &:= (1 - (2 + (3 \times (4 - (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
14028 &:= (((1 - 23) + (4^5)) \times ((6 + 7) - (8 - 9))) \\
14029 &:= (1 \times -2 - (3 \times ((4 + 56) \times 78) - 9)) \\
14030 &:= ((12 + 34) \times (((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times -8) + 9)) \\
14031 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 \times -4 - (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
14032 &:= (((12^3) - (4 - (5 \times 6))) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
14033 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - (3 \times (45 \times (6 + 7)))) \times 8) - 9)) \\
14034 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 \times (45 \times (6 + 7)))) \times 8)) + 9) \\
14035 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) - (((4^5) + (67 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
14036 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) - (((4^5) + (67 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
14037 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 - 4) + (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
14038 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times (6 + 78))) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13997 &:= (((-9 \times -((8 + (76 \times 5)) \times 4) + 3)) + 2) \times 1) \\
13998 &:= (9 - ((8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
13999 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
14000 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) \times -4 \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
14001 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times 3)) \times (2 - 1)) \\
14002 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times 3)) - 2) - 1) \\
14003 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times 3)) - 2) \times 1) \\
14004 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times 3)) - 2) + 1) \\
14005 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) - ((6 + 5) \times -4 \times 321)) \\
14006 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (6 - ((5^4) - 321))) \\
14007 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7^6)) \times 5))/(43 - (2 - 1))) \\
14008 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((76 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)) + 2)) + 1)) \\
14009 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((76 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)) + 2))) \times 1) \\
14010 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((76 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)) + 2)) - 1)) \\
14011 &:= (((-9 \times 87) + ((6^5) + (4 \times 3))) \times 2) + 1) \\
14012 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (76 \times 5)) \times -(((4^3)/ - 2) + 1)) \\
14013 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 - ((5^4) \times 3))))/(2 \times -1)) \\
14014 &:= ((98 - 7) \times ((6 + 5) \times -((4 + 3) - 21))) \\
14015 &:= ((((-9 + 87) \times (6 \times 5)) - 4) \times (3 \times 2)) - 1) \\
14016 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times 65)) \times ((4^3)/ - (2 \times 1))) \\
14017 &:= (9 + ((8 - 76) \times -((5 \times (43 - 2)) + 1))) \\
14018 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times 3) - 2)) + 1) \\
14019 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (5^4)))) \times -3 \times -2) - 1) \\
14020 &:= ((98 - ((7 + 6) \times (543 \times 2))) \times -1) \\
14021 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times -((5 \times (43 + 2)) + 1))) \\
14022 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - ((5^4) \times 3))))/(2 \times -1)) \\
14023 &:= (9 - ((87 + (6 + 5)) \times -(((4 \times 3)^2) - 1))) \\
14024 &:= (9 - ((876 \times -((54/3) - 2)) + 1)) \\
14025 &:= ((9 - (8 + 76)) \times (5 - ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
14026 &:= (9 - ((876 \times -((54/3) - 2)) - 1)) \\
14027 &:= (98 - (((7 \times (6^5))/ - 4) - 321)) \\
14028 &:= (-9 - (87 - ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 321)))) \\
14029 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -765) - ((4^{3+2}) \times -1)) \\
14030 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + (6 \times 5)))) \times (43 + (2 + 1))) \\
14031 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (76 \times 5)) \times 4)) - (3 \times -21)) \\
14032 &:= (-9 - (8 - (7 \times (((6^5)/4) + (3 \times 21)))) \\
14033 &:= ((-98 + 7) - ((6 + 5) \times -4 \times 321)) \\
14034 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) \times -((4^3) + 21))) \\
14035 &:= ((-98 \times (7 + 6)) - (((5 + 4)^3) \times -21)) \\
14036 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5)) \times ((43 + 2) - 1)) \\
14037 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 76) + (5 \times (4 \times 3))) \times -21)) \\
14038 &:= (((987 - 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14039 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times 3)^4) + (((5^6) + 7) \times 8))) / -9 & 14039 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -6^{(5+4)/3}) - 2) + 1) \\
14040 &:= (((1 + 2) - (3^4)) \times (5 \times -(6 \times ((7 + 8) - 9)))) & 14040 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times (65 \times -(4 - (32 - 1)))) \\
14041 &:= (1 \times -((2 - 3) - (((4^5) + (67 \times 8)) \times 9))) & 14041 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -6^{(5+4)/3}) + 2) - 1) \\
14042 &:= ((1 - 2) + (3 + (((4^5) + (67 \times 8)) \times 9))) & 14042 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((7 \times -(6 + 5)) + (43 \times 21))) \\
14043 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 - 4) - (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 14043 &:= (987 - (6 - (((5^4) - 3) \times 21))) \\
14044 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -(((4 + 5) \times 67) + 8)) + 9)) & 14044 &:= (((-98 \times -(76 - 5)) + (4^3)) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
14045 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) + (((4^5) + (67 \times 8)) \times 9))) & 14045 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) - ((6 + 5) \times -(4 \times 321))) \\
14046 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 + (((4^5) + (67 \times 8)) \times 9))) & 14046 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times ((65 \times -(4 + 32)) - 1)) \\
14047 &:= (1 \times (((2 + (3 \times (45 \times (6 + 7)))) \times 8) - 9)) & 14047 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) \times ((65 \times 4) - (3^2)))) \times -1) \\
14048 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3 \times (45 \times (6 + 7)))) \times 8)) - 9) & 14048 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (7 \times -(((6^5)/4) + (3 \times 21)))) \\
14049 &:= (1 + ((2^3) + (((4^5) + (67 \times 8)) \times 9))) & 14049 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 \times -(((6^5)/4) + (3 \times 21)))) \\
14050 &:= (1 \times -((2 - (3 \times (4 + (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9))))))) & 14050 &:= (9 - (8 - (7 \times (((6^5)/4) + (3 \times 21)))) \\
14051 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (4 + (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9))))))) & 14051 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) - 4) \times -3) - 2) + 1) \\
14052 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (3 \times -(4 + (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 14052 &:= (((-98 \times -7) - ((6^5) - (4^3))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
14053 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -((4 + ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8))) - 9))) & 14053 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 \times -(5 + (43 + 2))) + 1)) \\
14054 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times (4 + (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9))))))) & 14054 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) - 4) \times -3) + 2) \times 1) \\
14055 &:= (1 + (2 + (3 \times (4 + (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9))))))) & 14055 &:= (987 + (6 + (((5^4) - 3) \times 21))) \\
14056 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(3 \times (4 + (5 \times (6 \times 78)))))) + 9) & 14056 &:= ((98 - (7 \times 6)) \times -(5 - (4^{3+2-1}))) \\
14057 &:= ((((-1 + 2345) \times -6) + 7) \times (8 - 9)) & 14057 &:= (9 - ((8 \times ((7 \times (6^5)) + 4)) / - (32 - 1))) \\
14058 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times 5)) \times (67 - 89)) & 14058 &:= (((98 + 7) - 6) \times -(5 - ((4 + 3) \times 21))) \\
14059 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((34 + 56) \times 78) + 9))) & 14059 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((765 + (4^3)) - 2) \times -1)) \\
14060 &:= ((1 + (2 + 34)) \times (5 \times -((6 + 7) - 89))) & 14060 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times -((5 + ((4 \times 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
14061 &:= ((1 + (2^{3+4})) \times -((5 \times -6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 14061 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -((5 \times -4) + (3 \times 21))) \\
14062 &:= (1 - ((2345 \times -6) - ((7 - 8) \times 9))) & 14062 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(((6 + 54) \times 3) - 2)) \times 1) \\
14063 &:= (((1 + (2345 \times 6)) - (7 - 8)) - 9) & 14063 &:= (-9 - (8 \times -(((7 - (6 - 54)) \times 32) - 1))) \\
14064 &:= (12 - (3 \times -(4 + (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 14064 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -((6 \times -5) - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
14065 &:= (1 \times (((2 + (3 \times (45 \times (6 + 7)))) \times 8) + 9)) & 14065 &:= ((98 - (7 - 6)) \times (5 \times -(4 - (32 + 1)))) \\
14066 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3 \times (45 \times (6 + 7)))) \times 8)) + 9) & 14066 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) \times -((65 \times 4) - (3^2))) - 1)) \\
14067 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))))) / -9 & 14067 &:= (9 \times -(((8 \times 765) / -4) - (32 + 1))) \\
14068 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((3 - (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) - 89)))) & 14068 &:= (((-9 \times (((8 \times (7 + 6)) - (5^4)) \times 3)) + 2) - 1) \\
14069 &:= (1 + (2 \times -((3 - (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) - 89)))) & 14069 &:= (((-98 \times -(7 + 6)) + 5) \times -((4 \times -3) + (2 - 1))) \\
14070 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 - (8 + 9))) & 14070 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 + 6)) + 5) \times -((4 \times 32) + 1))) \\
14071 &:= (1 + (2 \times -((3 \times (4 - ((5 \times (6 \times 78)) + 9)))))) & 14071 &:= (9 - (8 - (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + (3 \times 21))))))) \\
14072 &:= ((((-1 + 2345) \times 6) + 7) - (8 - 9)) & 14072 &:= (987 - ((6543 \times -2) + 1)) \\
14073 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 \times (4 + (5 \times (6 \times 78)))))) - 9) & 14073 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times ((65 \times 4) - (3^2))) + 1))) \\
14074 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(3 \times (4 + (5 \times (6 \times 78)))))) - 9) & 14074 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -(((4^3) - 2) \times -1)) \\
14075 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times (5 + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) & 14075 &:= (((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + 6)) + 5) \times -((4 \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
14076 &:= ((12^3) - (4 \times -(((5 \times 67) + 8) \times 9))) & 14076 &:= ((9 + (87 + 6)) \times -((5 + (4^3)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
14077 &:= ((1 + ((2345 \times 6) + 7)) + (8 - 9)) & 14077 &:= ((98 - (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4)) \times 3)^2))) \times -1) \\
14078 &:= ((1 + (2345 \times 6)) + (7 \times -(8 - 9))) & 14078 &:= ((-987 \times 6) - ((5^4) \times -(32 \times 1))) \\
14079 &:= (1 \times -((2345 \times -6) + ((7 - 8) \times 9))) & 14079 &:= (98 - (((7 \times 65) - 4) \times -(32 - 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14080 &:= (1 - ((2345 \times -6) + ((7 - 8) \times 9))) \\
14081 &:= (((1 + (2345 \times 6)) - (7 - 8)) + 9) \\
14082 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((3 \times (4 + (5 \times (6 \times 78)))) + 9))) \\
14083 &:= (1 \times -(2 + ((3 - (4 \times ((56 - 7) \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
14084 &:= (1 - (2 + ((3 - (4 \times ((56 - 7) \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
14085 &:= ((12 + 3) \times ((4^5) - ((6 + 7) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
14086 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times -567) - 89) \\
14087 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + ((3 - 45) \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8) + 9)) \\
14088 &:= (1 - (((2 + ((3 - 45) \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8) + 9)) \\
14089 &:= (1 \times -(23 - (4 \times ((56 - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
14090 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 + 6))) \times -(7 - (8 + 9))) \\
14091 &:= (-1 + (((234 + 5) \times (67 - 8)) - 9)) \\
14092 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 45))) \times -((6 \times 78) / -9)) \\
14093 &:= (1 \times ((2 - (3 \times ((45 \times 6) + 7))) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
14094 &:= (1 + ((2 - (3 \times ((45 \times 6) + 7))) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
14095 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 34) \times -(56 \times 7)) + (8 + 9))) \\
14096 &:= (((12^3) + (4 + (5 \times 6))) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
14097 &:= (1 \times ((23^4) - (((5^6) + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
14098 &:= ((1 + (23^4)) + (((5^6) + 7) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
14099 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times -(4 \times (5 \times (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))))) \\
14100 &:= (12 \times -(((3^4) - 56) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
14101 &:= (1 \times -((234 + 5) \times -((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9)))) \\
14102 &:= ((1 - 23) \times (4 + (5 \times (6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
14103 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 \times -((4 \times (56 \times 7)) + (8 - 9)))) \\
14104 &:= ((1 - (2 - 345)) \times -((6 \times -7) - (8 - 9))) \\
14105 &:= (((1 + 2) - 34) \times -(5 - ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
14106 &:= (1 - (((2 + ((3 - 45) \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8) - 9)) \\
14107 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) - (4 \times ((56 - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
14108 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -(((4^5) - 6) \times -7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
14109 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))))) / -9) \\
14110 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) + 5)) \times -((6 + 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
14111 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 34) \times -(56 \times 7)) - (8 - 9))) \\
14112 &:= ((1 + ((23 \times 4) + 5)) \times -(6 \times -(7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
14113 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 34) \times -(56 \times 7)) + (8 - 9))) \\
14114 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((3 + (((4^5) - 6) \times 7)) - (8 \times 9)))) \\
14115 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 + (((4^5) - 6) \times 7)) - (8 \times 9)))) \\
14116 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times 7) - 89))) \\
14117 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times 7) - 89))) \\
14118 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 - (((45 \times 6) + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
14119 &:= (1 \times (((2 - ((3 - 45) \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8) - 9)) \\
14120 &:= (1 + (((2 - ((3 - 45) \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8) - 9)) \\
14121 &:= (1 + ((2^3) + (4 \times ((56 - 7) \times (8 \times 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14080 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 + 5) \times -(4 \times (32 \times 1)))) \\
14081 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 - (6 - 54)) \times 32) - 1))) \\
14082 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -(6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))) + 21)) \\
14083 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))) - 2)) \times -1) \\
14084 &:= (((9 + 8) - ((7 + 6) \times 543)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
14085 &:= (9 + ((8 - 76) \times -((5 + (4^3)) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
14086 &:= ((-9 + ((87 \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))) + 2)) - 1) \\
14087 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))) + 2)) \times -1) \\
14088 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 - ((5^4) - 32)) \times -1)) \\
14089 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 - (6 - 54)) \times (32 \times 1)))) \\
14090 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 + 5) \times -(4 \times 32)) - 1)) \\
14091 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times (6 \times 54)) + 3)) / (2 \times -1)) \\
14092 &:= (9 - (8 - (7 \times ((65 - 4) \times (32 + 1)))) \\
14093 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 \times 65) - (4 \times 321))) \\
14094 &:= (9 - (((87 \times (6 \times (5 + 4))) - 3) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
14095 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(765 + (4^3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
14096 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(765 + (4^3))) + (2 + 1)) \\
14097 &:= (((9 - 8) + (76 \times 5)) \times -((4 \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
14098 &:= ((-98 \times 7) - ((6 + 5) \times -((4^3) \times 21))) \\
14099 &:= (((-98 \times (7 + 65)) + (4 + 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
14100 &:= ((9 + (87 \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)))) - (2 + 1)) \\
14101 &:= ((9 + (87 \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
14102 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -(6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))) + (2 - 1))) \\
14103 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 + ((5^4) \times 3)))) / (2 \times -1)) \\
14104 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times (((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2) - 1)) \\
14105 &:= ((9 + (87 \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
14106 &:= ((9 + (87 \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)))) + (2 + 1)) \\
14107 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) \times -(5^4)) - 3) / 21) \\
14108 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 76) + 5) \times (4 - (3^{2+1})))) \\
14109 &:= (987 - (6 \times -(((5 + 4)^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
14110 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 \times -(6 \times (5 \times 4))) + ((3^2) + 1))) \\
14111 &:= ((9 - ((8 - ((7 + 6) \times 543)) \times 2)) \times 1) \\
14112 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2) \times -1)) \\
14113 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(7 + (6 \times (5 \times (4 - (3 \times 21))))))) \\
14114 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(765 + (4^3))) + 21) \\
14115 &:= ((-9 - 876) - ((5^4) \times -(3 + 21))) \\
14116 &:= (((9 - 8) - ((7 + 6) \times 543)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
14117 &:= (((9 - 8) - ((7 + 6) \times (543 \times 2))) \times -1) \\
14118 &:= ((98 + ((7 + 65) \times (4^3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
14119 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((7 + 6) \times (543 \times 2))) \times -1)) \\
14120 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times (((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2) + 1)) \\
14121 &:= (9 \times ((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 54) - 32))) + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14122 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))) - 9) \\
14123 &:= (1 \times (2 - (((3 - 45) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9))) \\
14124 &:= (1 + (2 - (((3 - 45) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9))) \\
14125 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times (5 \times -(6 - (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
14126 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((((3^4) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) \times 8) - 9))) \\
14127 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((((3^4) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) \times 8) - 9))) \\
14128 &:= ((-1 + (((2 + 34) \times (56 \times 7)) + 8)) + 9) \\
14129 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 34) \times -(56 \times 7)) - (8 + 9))) \\
14130 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 \times -(((45 \times 6) + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
14131 &:= (1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times -(6 - (7 + 89)))) \\
14132 &:= (((-1 - ((2 \times 3)^4)) \times -(5 + 6)) + ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
14133 &:= (12 + (((3 - 45) \times -(6 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9)) \\
14134 &:= (((-1 + (2345 \times 6)) - 7) - (8 \times -9)) \\
14135 &:= (1 \times -((2345 \times -6) + (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
14136 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 + (((45 \times 6) + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
14137 &:= ((1 - (2 \times 34)) \times ((5 \times -(6 \times 7)) + (8 - 9))) \\
14138 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7)) - (8 \times 9))) \\
14139 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
14140 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))) + 9) \\
14141 &:= (1 \times -((2 - (3^4)) \times ((5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8)) + 9))) \\
14142 &:= (1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times ((5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8)) + 9))) \\
14143 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (345 \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 - 9)))))) \\
14144 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(((3^4) + (5 \times 67)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
14145 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3^4) + (5 \times 67)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
14146 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times ((4 + (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\
14147 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times ((4 + (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\
14148 &:= ((12 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 \times -((7 + 8) - 9))) \\
14149 &:= (1 \times -((2345 \times -6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
14150 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)))) \\
14151 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)))) \\
14152 &:= (123 - 4)^{5 \times 6 / (7 + 8)} - 9 \\
14153 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((((3^4) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) \times 8) - 9)) \\
14154 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((((3^4) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) \times 8) - 9)) \\
14155 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -3) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + (78 \times 9)))))) \\
14156 &:= ((1 + ((2^3) \times (4^5))) - (67 \times -89)) \\
14157 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times -((4 \times (56 \times 7)) + 8)) + 9)) \\
14158 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) - 6) \times 7)))) - 89) \\
14159 &:= (1 \times ((2 - 3) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + (78 \times 9)))))) \\
14160 &:= (12 - (3 \times -((4 + (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
14161 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3 \times (45 - 6))) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
14162 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((((3^4) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) \times 8) + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14122 &:= (9 - (((87 + (6 + 5)) \times -((4 \times 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
14123 &:= ((((-9 - (87 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) \times -3) + 2) \times 1) \\
14124 &:= ((9 + (87 + (6 + 5))) \times -(4 \times -(32 + 1))) \\
14125 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - ((6 + 5) \times -(4 \times 321))) \\
14126 &:= (-9 - (((8 + ((7 + 6) \times 543)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
14127 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (((76 - 5) \times (4 \times 3)) - 21)) \\
14128 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4))) - (3^2))) + 1) \\
14129 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 + (6 \times 5)) + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))) \\
14130 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 6) + (5 - 4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
14131 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + 6) \times -((543 \times 2) + 1))) \\
14132 &:= ((9 + ((876 + 5) \times 4)) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
14133 &:= ((9 - 876) - ((5^4) \times -(3 + 21))) \\
14134 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((7 + 6) \times (543 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
14135 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((7 + 6) \times (543 \times 2))) \times -1)) \\
14136 &:= ((9 + (8 + 76)) \times (5 + ((4 + 3) \times 21))) \\
14137 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (4 + (3 \times 21))) \\
14138 &:= ((-98 / -7) - ((6 + 5) \times -(4 \times 321))) \\
14139 &:= (9 + ((8 + 7) \times -((6 - (5 \times (4^3))) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
14140 &:= ((98 + (7 \times 6)) \times -(((54 - 3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
14141 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(6 - 543)) / -(2 + 1)) \\
14142 &:= (9 - (((8 + ((7 + 6) \times 543)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
14143 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((7 + 6) \times 543)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
14144 &:= (((9 + 8) - ((7 \times 65) + 4)) \times (32 \times -1)) \\
14145 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -((5 + (4 + 32)) \times -1)) \\
14146 &:= ((98 - 76) \times ((5^4) - (3 - 21))) \\
14147 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times -((4^3) + 2)) + 1)) \\
14148 &:= (9 \times (((8 \times -7) + ((6 \times 543) / 2)) - 1)) \\
14149 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 654) / -3) - 21) \\
14150 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times 6) + (54 \times 32))) + 1)) \\
14151 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + (54 \times 32)))) \times -1) \\
14152 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -((76 + 5) - (43^2))) - 1)) \\
14153 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((76 + 5) - (43^2)))) \times 1) \\
14154 &:= (((9 - 87) - ((6^5) / 4)) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
14155 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times ((5 + ((4 \times 3)^2)) \times -1)) \\
14156 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + 65)) \times -(4 + (3^2))) - 1) \\
14157 &:= (9 - (((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) + 4) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
14158 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4)) \times 3)^2))) \times -1) \\
14159 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + ((6 \times -5 - (4 \times 3))^2)))) \times -1) \\
14160 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 \times -6 - ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) - 1)) \\
14161 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times -6 - ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) \times -1)) \\
14162 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((7 \times -6 - ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2)) \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14163 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((((3^4) \times (5+6)) - 7) \times 8) + 9))) \\
14164 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3 - (4^5))) + 6) \times 7) + 89)) \\
14165 &:= (1 \times ((2+3) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + (78 \times 9)))))) \\
14166 &:= ((1+2) + (3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + (78 \times 9)))))) \\
14167 &:= (((12^3) + ((45+6) - 7)) \times 8) - 9) \\
14168 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times (5 - (6 + (78 + 9)))) \\
14169 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) + 89)) \\
14170 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 3) + (4 \times 5)) \times -((67 \times 8) + 9))) \\
14171 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3) + (4 \times 5)) \times -((67 \times 8) + 9))) \\
14172 &:= (12 \times -(((3+4) \times -56) - 789)) \\
14173 &:= (1 \times -(2 + (3 \times ((4+5) - (6 \times 789)))))) \\
14174 &:= (1 \times -((((2 \times 3)^4) \times -(5+6)) - (7 - 89))) \\
14175 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) - 6) \times 7)))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
14176 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7) + (8 + 9)))) \\
14177 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 3)^4) \times -(5+6)) + (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
14178 &:= (((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times (5+6))) - 7) + (8 \times -9)) \\
14179 &:= (1 \times -((2+3) - (((4 \times (56 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9))) \\
14180 &:= (1 \times ((2+3) \times -(4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8+9))))))) \\
14181 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times (3 - (4^5))) + 6) \times 7)) + (8 \times -9)) \\
14182 &:= (1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) - (5 - 6)) \times (78 + 9))) \\
14183 &:= (1 \times (23 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + (78 \times 9)))))) \\
14184 &:= ((1 + ((2 - (3^4)) \times 5)) \times (6 \times -((7+8) - 9))) \\
14185 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7) + 8)) - 9)) \\
14186 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -(((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7) + 8)) - 9)) \\
14187 &:= (((1+2)^3) - (4 \times -(5 \times (6 + (78 \times 9)))))) \\
14188 &:= (((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times (5+6))) - 78) + 9) \\
14189 &:= (1 \times -((2345 \times -6) - (7 \times (8+9)))) \\
14190 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -3) - (((4 \times (56 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9))) \\
14191 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -3) - (((4 \times (56 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9))) \\
14192 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times (5+6)) + 7) + (8 \times -9)) \\
14193 &:= (1 + ((2^3) + (((4 \times (56 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9))) \\
14194 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times ((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7)) + 8)) - 9) \\
14195 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5^6))) + ((7+8) \times -9)) \\
14196 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((3 \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9))))))) \\
14197 &:= (1 + (2 \times -((3 \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9))))))) \\
14198 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times ((4 - 5) + (6 \times 789)))))) \\
14199 &:= (12 + (3 + (((4 \times (56 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9))) \\
14200 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7) + 89))) \\
14201 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7) + 89))) \\
14202 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times (((4-5) + (67 \times 8)) - 9)) \\
14203 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7) + 8)) + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14163 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 \times -(6 - ((5 \times 4) + 3)))^2) + 1))) \\
14164 &:= ((9 + 8) \times 7)^{6/((5+4)/3)} + 2 + 1 \\
14165 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times ((7+6) \times 5)) + 4) \times 3) + 2)) - 1) \\
14166 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7+6)) - 5) \times -(((4 \times 3)^2) - 1))) \\
14167 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 - (5 \times 4)))) \times (32 - 1)) \\
14168 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6 + (5+4)) \times 3)^2) - 1))) \\
14169 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 \times -(((6 + (5+4)) \times 3)^2) - 1))) \\
14170 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times 6) + (54 \times 32))) - 1)) \\
14171 &:= (9 + (((87 - ((6+5) - 43))^2) + 1)) \\
14172 &:= ((9 - ((8+7) \times ((6+5) \times 43))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
14173 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 654) / -3) + (2 + 1)) \\
14174 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6 + (5+4)) \times 3)^2) + 1))) \\
14175 &:= (9 - (8 - ((7 \times (((6 + (5+4)) \times 3)^2) - 1))) \\
14176 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2)))) - 1) \\
14177 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2)))) \times 1) \\
14178 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 + ((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2)))) - 1)) \\
14179 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -((4^3) + (2 - 1)))) \\
14180 &:= (-9 - (((8+7) \times -((6+5) \times (43 \times 2))) + 1)) \\
14181 &:= ((9 - ((8+7) \times ((6+5) \times (43 \times 2)))) \times -1) \\
14182 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6 + (5+4)) \times 3)^2) + 1))) \\
14183 &:= (9 - (8 - (7 \times (((6 + (5+4)) \times 3)^2) + 1))) \\
14184 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (76 - (5 - 4)))) \times -((3 + 21))) \\
14185 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 \times -(((6 + (5+4)) \times 3)^2) - 1))) \\
14186 &:= (9 + (((8 - ((7 \times 65) - 4)) \times -32) + 1)) \\
14187 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5! - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
14188 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 76)) \times -((5 \times 4) + 3)) - 2) - 1) \\
14189 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - ((6+5) \times (4 \times 321)))) \\
14190 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times -((4^3) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
14191 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times -(((6 + (5+4)) \times 3)^2) + 1))) \\
14192 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times (((6 + (5+4)) \times 3)^2))) \times -1)) \\
14193 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times -(((6 + (5+4)) \times 3)^2) - 1))) \\
14194 &:= (((-98 + 7) \times (6 - (54 \times 3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
14195 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((7 \times (6 + 54)) - 3) \times -2) - 1)) \\
14196 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 \times 6) \times -((5 - ((4+3)^{2+1})))) \\
14197 &:= (9 - (8 + ((7 \times 6) \times (5 - ((4+3)^{2+1})))) \\
14198 &:= (9 - (((8+7) \times -((6+5) \times (43 \times 2))) + 1)) \\
14199 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 \times -(((6 + (5+4)) \times 3)^2) + 1))) \\
14200 &:= (9 - (((8+7) \times -((6+5) \times (43 \times 2))) - 1)) \\
14201 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 321) \\
14202 &:= ((9 + ((8+7) \times ((6 + (5^4) \times 3)))) / -((2 \times -1)) \\
14203 &:= (98 - ((7+6) \times -((543 \times 2) - 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14204 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7) + 8)) + 9)) \\
14205 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3 + (4 + (5 + 6))) \times 789))) \\
14206 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times 7))) - 89) \\
14207 &:= (1 \times -((234 - 5) \times -(6 + (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
14208 &:= (((12^3) \times -(4 + ((5 - 6) \times 78)))/9) \\
14209 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7))) \times (8 - 9)) \\
14210 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times ((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7)) - 8)) - 9) \\
14211 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7))) \times -(8 - 9)) \\
14212 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times ((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7)) + 8)) + 9) \\
14213 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(34 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 - 9)))))) \\
14214 &:= ((1 + ((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -((7 + 8) - 9)) \\
14215 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - ((3 - 45) \times 6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9)) \\
14216 &:= (1 - (((2 - ((3 - 45) \times 6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9)) \\
14217 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) - 6)))) \times (7 \times -(8 - 9))) \\
14218 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7) - 8))) - 9) \\
14219 &:= ((12^3) - ((4 \times -(5^{6+7-8})) + 9)) \\
14220 &:= (12 \times -(3 \times -((4^5) - (6 + (7 \times 89)))))) \\
14221 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) - 8))) - 9)) \\
14222 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) - 8))) - 9)) \\
14223 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times 7))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
14224 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((3 + (((4^5) - 6) \times 7)) - (8 + 9)))) \\
14225 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 + (((4^5) - 6) \times 7)) - (8 + 9)))) \\
14226 &:= (((-12 - 3) \times -((4^5) - (67 + 8))) - 9) \\
14227 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 345) \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 - 9)))) \\
14228 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times ((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7)) - 8)) + 9) \\
14229 &:= ((1 + (23 \times 4)) \times -(((5 + (6 + 7)) \times -8) - 9)) \\
14230 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) - 6) \times 7)))) - (8 + 9)) \\
14231 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times ((4 + 5) + (6 \times 789)))))) \\
14232 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(3 \times (4 \times ((5 \times 6) - (7 \times 89)))))) \\
14233 &:= (((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times (5 + 6))) - 7) - (8 + 9)) \\
14234 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
14235 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
14236 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7) - 8))) + 9) \\
14237 &:= ((12^3) - ((4 \times -(5^{6+7-8})) - 9)) \\
14238 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (34 \times 5))) \times -(6 \times -(7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\
14239 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (3 \times 45)) \times -((6 + 7) \times 8)) + 9)) \\
14240 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) - 8)))) + 9) \\
14241 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) + (8 + 9))) \\
14242 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) + (8 + 9))) \\
14243 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5^6))) - (78 + 9)) \\
14244 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7) - (8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14204 &:= (((((-9 \times 87) - 6) \times 54) / -3) - (2 \times -1)) \\
14205 &:= (((((-9 \times 87) - 6) \times 54) / -3) + (2 + 1)) \\
14206 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times -((7 + 65) - (43^2))) - 1)) \\
14207 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 65) - (43^2)))) \times -1) \\
14208 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -(6 - ((5^4) - (3^{2+1})))) \\
14209 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(7 - (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times (32 + 1)))))) \\
14210 &:= ((98 - ((7^{6-5} \times 4) \times 3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
14211 &:= ((987 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
14212 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (76 \times -(5 - ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))))) \\
14213 &:= (9 + (8 - ((7 \times 6) \times (5 - ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))))) \\
14214 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times -(((6 + 5) \times (43 \times 2)) + 1))) \\
14215 &:= ((98 + ((7 + 6) \times (543 \times 2))) - 1) \\
14216 &:= ((98 + ((7 + 6) \times (543 \times 2))) \times 1) \\
14217 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((7 + 65) - ((43^2) - 1)))) \\
14218 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((6 + 54) \times 3)) - 2) \times 1) \\
14219 &:= (9 - ((87 + (6 + 5)) \times -(((4 \times 3)^2) + 1))) \\
14220 &:= ((9 - (87 \times (6 + 5))) \times ((4 \times -3) - (2 + 1))) \\
14221 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times -43) + 21)) \\
14222 &:= ((-9 + (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times 43)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
14223 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 - 54)))) \times -(32 + 1)) \\
14224 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times 6) - 5)) \times ((4 - 32) \times 1)) \\
14225 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((7 + 65) - (43^2 \times 1)))) \\
14226 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times 43) + 2)) \times -1) \\
14227 &:= ((-9 + (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times 43) + 2)) + 1) \\
14228 &:= (-9 + (8 + (((7 \times 65) + 4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
14229 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) \times -(((4^3) / -2) + 1)) \\
14230 &:= (((9 + 876) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
14231 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 - (65 \times 4)))) \times -(3 \times -2) - 1) \\
14232 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 \times 65)) \times 4)) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
14233 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times -((4^3) + 2)) - 1)) \\
14234 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -((76 - 5) - (43^2))) + 1)) \\
14235 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(654 + 3)) / (2 + 1)) \\
14236 &:= (((-9 - ((8 - 76) \times 5)) \times 43) + (2 + 1)) \\
14237 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) + 6) + ((5 + 4)^3)) \times 2) - 1) \\
14238 &:= ((987 + (6 \times 5)) \times ((4 + 3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
14239 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times -43) + (2 + 1))) \\
14240 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times 43)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
14241 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 \times -(54 - 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\
14242 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times 43)) \times (2 - 1)) \\
14243 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times -43) - (2 - 1)) \\
14244 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times 43)) - (2 \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 14245 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(3 - ((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) + (8 - 9)) \\
 14246 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -(3 - ((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) + (8 - 9)) \\
 14247 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) \times -(8 - 9)) \\
 14248 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) - (8 - 9)) \\
 14249 &:= (((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times (5 + 6))) - 7) + (8 - 9)) \\
 14250 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times -(5 \times -(6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 14251 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5^6) - 7))) + (8 \times -9) \\
 14252 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times (3 - (4^5))) + 6) \times 7)) + (8 - 9)) \\
 14253 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times (3 - (4^5))) + 6) \times -7) - (8 - 9)) \\
 14254 &:= (1 + (((2 \times (3 - (4^5))) + 6) \times -7) - (8 - 9)) \\
 14255 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(34 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) - 8)) + 9) \\
 14256 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times 5)) \times -(6 \times -(7 + 8) - 9)) \\
 14257 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) \times (8 - 9)) \\
 14258 &:= ((1 - 23) - (4 \times -(5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))) \\
 14259 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 + ((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) + (8 - 9)) \\
 14260 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(3 + ((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) + (8 - 9)) \\
 14261 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5^6))) - (78 - 9)) \\
 14262 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7) \times (8 - 9)) \\
 14263 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7) + (8 - 9)) \\
 14264 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7) \times -(8 - 9)) \\
 14265 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5^6))) - ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
 14266 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) + 8))) - 9) \\
 14267 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) \times (((5 \times 6) / (7 + 8)) + 9)) \\
 14268 &:= (((1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times (((5 + 6) \times -(7 + 8)) - 9)) \\
 14269 &:= (1 \times ((23 - 4) \times -(5 - ((6 + 78) \times 9))) \\
 14270 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times (3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 14271 &:= (1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 14272 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))) \\
 14273 &:= (1 - ((2^3) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))) \\
 14274 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(34 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) - 8)) - 9) \\
 14275 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times (3 + ((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) + (8 + 9)) \\
 14276 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 - (7 - 8))) + 9)) \\
 14277 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 - (7 - 8))) + 9)) \\
 14278 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times 7))) - (8 + 9)) \\
 14279 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(34 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - (8 - 9)) \\
 14280 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))) \\
 14281 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7) + (8 + 9)) \\
 14282 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(34 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) + (8 - 9)) \\
 14283 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 - ((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
 14284 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) + 8))) + 9) \\
 14285 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 - (7 - 8))) + 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 14245 &:= (((98 - 7) + ((6^5) / 4)) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
 14246 &:= (9 + (8 + (((7 \times 65) + 4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
 14247 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times 6)) + ((5^4) + 3)) \times -21)) \\
 14248 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times (65 \times 4))) + 321)) \\
 14249 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -(7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) - 32) + 1) \\
 14250 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times -(5 + (((4 \times 3)^2) + 1))) \\
 14251 &:= (9876 - ((5^4) \times -((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\
 14252 &:= ((9 - (8 - (7 + 6))) \times -(5 - ((4^{3+2}) - 1))) \\
 14253 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times ((65 - 4) \times 3)) - 21) \\
 14254 &:= (((-9 - ((8 - 76) \times 5)) \times 43) + 21) \\
 14255 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 321)) \\
 14256 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -(6 \times -((5 \times (4 \times (3 + 2))) - 1))) \\
 14257 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times ((54 \times -(3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
 14258 &:= (98 + (((7 \times -(6 - ((5 \times 4) + 3)))^2) - 1)) \\
 14259 &:= (98 - (((7 \times -(6 - ((5 \times 4) + 3)))^2) \times -1)) \\
 14260 &:= (98 + (((7 \times -(6 - ((5 \times 4) + 3)))^2) + 1)) \\
 14261 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) \times 3)) \times 2) - 1) \\
 14262 &:= ((((-9 \times ((87 \times 6) + 5)) - 4) \times -3) + 21) \\
 14263 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (7 + ((6 + (5 \times 4)) \times (32 \times 1)))) \\
 14264 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 + 6)) - 5) \times -((4 \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\
 14265 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((76 + 5) \times (43 - 21)))) \\
 14266 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 + 6)) - 5) \times -((4 \times 3)^2) - 1)) \\
 14267 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -76) + 5) \times -((4 \times -3) + (2 - 1))) \\
 14268 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -(5 + ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 14269 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 - 65)) + 4) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
 14270 &:= ((9 - (((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5)^4) - 3) / 2)) \times -1) \\
 14271 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 - 43)))) - 21) \\
 14272 &:= (((9 + 8) - ((7 + 6)^{5-4+3})) / (2 \times -1)) \\
 14273 &:= (98 - (7 \times -(((6 + (5 + 4)) \times 3)^2 \times 1)) \\
 14274 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -(((6 + (5 + 4)) \times 3)^2) - 1)) \\
 14275 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 65))) \times -4) - 321) \\
 14276 &:= ((9 - ((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5)^4)) / - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
 14277 &:= (9 - (87 \times -((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
 14278 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)) + 2)) - 1)) \\
 14279 &:= ((((-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) \times 43) + 2) + 1) \\
 14280 &:= (((9 - 8) - ((7 + 6)^{5-4+3})) / (2 \times -1)) \\
 14281 &:= (((9 - 8) + ((7 + 6)^{5-4+3})) / - (2 \times -1)) \\
 14282 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5)) - 4) \times -32) - 1) \\
 14283 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times - (4 - (32 - 1))) \\
 14284 &:= (-9 - (8 - (((76 \times (5 + 4)) - 3) \times 21))) \\
 14285 &:= ((9 + ((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5)^4)) / (3 - (2 - 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14286 &:= (1 - ((2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 - (7 - 8)))) + 9)) & 14286 &:= (((9 + 8) - ((7 \times (6 - (5 - 4)))^3)) / - (2 + 1)) \\
14287 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times ((34 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + 8)) - 9)) & 14287 &:= (9 - (((((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5))^4) - 3) / - 2) + 1)) \\
14288 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((34 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + 8))) - 9) & 14288 &:= (9 - ((8 \times - (7 \times ((65 \times 4) - (3 + 2)))) + 1)) \\
14289 &:= (12 - (3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))))) & 14289 &:= (((9 + 8) + ((7 + 6)^{5-4+3})) / - (2 \times -1)) \\
14290 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7))) - 89) & 14290 &:= ((9 + (((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5))^4) + 3) / 2) - 1) \\
14291 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((34 \times (5 \times (6 + 78))) + 9))) & 14291 &:= ((9 + (((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5))^4) + 3) / 2) \times 1) \\
14292 &:= (1 \times ((2 - ((34 \times (5 + (6 \times 7))) - 8)) \times -9)) & 14292 &:= (9 - (((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5))^4) + 3) / - 2 - 1)) \\
14293 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times 7)) - (8 - 9))) & 14293 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 - 43)))))) + 2) - 1) \\
14294 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times 7)) + 8)) - 9) & 14294 &:= (98 + ((7 \times 6) \times - (5 - ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
14295 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times 7)) + (8 - 9))) & 14295 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times (65 \times 4)) - 32))) \times -1) \\
14296 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times 7)) + (8 - 9))) & 14296 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (7 - (((6 + 5)^4) - 321))) \\
14297 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times 7) - (8 - 9))) & 14297 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((7 - 65) - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
14298 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (34 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) + 8)) + 9) & 14298 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((7 \times (6 - (5 - 4)))^3)) / - (2 + 1))) \\
14299 &:= ((1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - (5^6))) + (78 \times -9)) & 14299 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(((65 - 4) \times 3) - 2)) \times 1) \\
14300 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) \times - (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) & 14300 &:= (9 - (((87 + 6) \times 5) - 4) \times - (32 - 1)) \\
14301 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times 7) + 8)) + 9) & 14301 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) - (2 - 1))) \\
14302 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times 7) + 8)) + 9) & 14302 &:= (9 - (8 - (((76 \times (5 + 4)) - 3) \times 21))) \\
14303 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 3)^4) \times - (5 + 6)) - ((7 \times 8) - 9)) & 14303 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (765 + (4^{3+2})))) \times -1) \\
14304 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times ((5 \times 6) - 7))) + (8 \times -9)) & 14304 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7^{(6-5) \times 4})) \times (3 \times - (2 \times 1))) \\
14305 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((34 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + 8)) - 9)) & 14305 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times (65 \times 4)) - (32 + 1)))) \\
14306 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7)) - (8 \times 9))) & 14306 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times 76) + 5)) \times ((4 \times (3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
14307 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7))) + (8 \times -9)) & 14307 &:= (((-9 \times -87) - (6 \times 5)) \times -((4 \times - (3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
14308 &:= (((1 - (2 - 3)) - (4^5)) \times -((6 + 7) - (8 - 9))) & 14308 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times ((4 - 32) \times 1)) \\
14309 &:= (1 - (2 - (((34 \times (5 + (6 \times 7))) - 8) \times 9))) & 14309 &:= ((9 - ((8 - 76) \times 5)) \times -((43 - 2) \times -1)) \\
14310 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times ((4 - 5) + ((67 - 8) \times 9))) & 14310 &:= ((9 + ((87 - 6) \times (5 - (4^3)))) \times - (2 + 1)) \\
14311 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times 7)) - (8 + 9))) & 14311 &:= ((-9 + (((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5))^4)) - 321) \\
14312 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times 7)) + 8)) + 9) & 14312 &:= ((987 - (((6 + 5)^4) \times 3)) / - (2 + 1)) \\
14313 &:= (1 - (2 \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 - (7 - 8))) - 9))) & 14313 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (65 \times 4)) - 32))) \times 1) \\
14314 &:= (1 - (23 - ((4^5) \times ((6 + 7) - (8 - 9)))))) & 14314 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 \times - (6 \times (5 \times 4))) - (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
14315 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((34 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + (8 + 9)))) & 14315 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + (6 \times (5 + (4^3)))) \times 2)) + 1) \\
14316 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) \times 6) / 7) - 89)) & 14316 &:= (-987 - (6 - (((5 + 4)^3) \times 21))) \\
14317 &:= (1 - (2 \times - (3 + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 789)))))) & 14317 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7! / 6 - 5 + 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
14318 &:= (1 \times - (2 \times - (((3 + (4^5) + 6)) \times 7) - (8 \times 9))) & 14318 &:= (9 + (8 + (((76 \times (5 + 4)) - 3) \times 21))) \\
14319 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) - 6) \times 7)))) - (8 \times -9)) & 14319 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times - (6 \times ((54 \times 3) - (2 + 1)))))) \\
14320 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^4)) \times - ((5 \times - ((6 \times 7) - 8)) - 9)) & 14320 &:= (9 - ((8 \times - (765 + (4^{3+2}))) + 1)) \\
14321 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times 3)^4)) - (((5^6) \times (7 - 8)) + 9)) & 14321 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (765 + (4^{3+2})))) \times 1) \\
14322 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times (6 - (7 - 8)))))) - 9) & 14322 &:= ((9 - 87) + ((6 \times (5 \times 4))^{3-2+1})) \\
14323 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - ((5^6) - 7))) \times - (8 - 9)) & 14323 &:= (9 - (8 - (7 \times (6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 321)))))) \\
14324 &:= (1 \times - (2 \times - ((3 + ((4^5) \times (6 - (7 - 8)))) - 9))) & 14324 &:= (9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + 5) \times (-4 + 3!!) + (2 + 1)!! \\
14325 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times (3 - (4^5))) + 6) \times 7)) - (8 \times -9)) & 14325 &:= ((((-9 \times (87 + 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2) - 1) \\
14326 &:= (1 \times - (2 - ((3 + (4 \times (56 - 7))) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 14326 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 321))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14368 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
14369 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(34 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - 89)) \\
14370 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(((3^4) + (5 + 6)) \times 78) + 9)) \\
14371 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7) + 8)) + 9)) \\
14372 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -(((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7) + 8)) + 9)) \\
14373 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 - ((4 + 5) \times 67)) \times -8) - 9)) \\
14374 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3)^4) \times -((5 \times 6) - 7)) - (8 - 9)) \\
14375 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3)^4) \times -((5 \times 6) - 7)) - (8 - 9)) \\
14376 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times ((5 \times 6) - 7))) \times -(8 - 9)) \\
14377 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5^6))) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
14378 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times ((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7)) - 8)) - 9) \\
14379 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7)) - (8 - 9))) \\
14380 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7)) - (8 - 9))) \\
14381 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 + (4^5)) \times -((6 + 7) - (8 - 9)))) \\
14382 &:= ((1 - (23 - 4)) \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
14383 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 + ((4 + 56) \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
14384 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times 7))) + 89) \\
14385 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7) - 8)) - 9)) \\
14386 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -(((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7) - 8)) - 9)) \\
14387 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3^4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7) \times 8) + 9)) \\
14388 &:= (12 \times (3 + (4 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 89)))) \\
14389 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3^4) \times 5) + 6789))) \\
14390 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3 + ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7)) + (8 \times 9))) \\
14391 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
14392 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times (5 + 6))) - ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
14393 &:= (1 \times (2 - (((3^4) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))) \\
14394 &:= (1 + (2 - (((3^4) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))) \\
14395 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - ((5^6) - 7))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
14396 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times ((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7)) - 8)) + 9) \\
14397 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times (6 - (7 - 8))) + 9))) \\
14398 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -((3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) - (8 + 9))) \\
14399 &:= (1 \times ((2 - 3) + (4 \times (((56 \times 7) + 8) \times 9)))) \\
14400 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^4)) \times -((5 \times -((6 \times ((7 + 8) - 9)))))) \\
14401 &:= (12 - (((((3 + 4)^5) \times 6) / -7) + (8 + 9))) \\
14402 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) - (4 \times -(((56 \times 7) + 8) \times 9))) \\
14403 &:= (((1 + 2) - (((3 + 4)^5) \times 6) / 7) \times (8 - 9)) \\
14404 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3 + (4^5))) + 6) \times -7) + (8 + 9)) \\
14405 &:= ((1 - (2 \times 34)) \times (5 \times -((6 \times 7) - (8 - 9)))) \\
14406 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 + (4 \times (((56 \times 7) + 8) \times 9)))) \\
14407 &:= ((-1 + ((2 - 345) \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 - 9)) \\
14408 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((((3 + 4)^5) \times 6) / -7) - (8 - 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14368 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7^{(6-5)^4})) \times -((3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
14369 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 + 6) + (54 \times (32 + 1)))))) \\
14370 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 + 6)) \times (5 + (4^3)))) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
14371 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + ((7^{(6-5)^4}) \times 3)) \times 2) - 1) \\
14372 &:= (((9 + 8) - ((7^{(6-5)^4}) \times 3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
14373 &:= (9 \times (8 + (7 \times ((65 \times 4) - (32 + 1)))))) \\
14374 &:= (-9 + ((8 - 765) \times -((4 \times (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\
14375 &:= (-9 + (8 \times -((76 - ((5^4) \times 3) - (2 - 1)))))) \\
14376 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 \times 65)) \times 4)) \times ((3^2) - 1)) \\
14377 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times (65 \times 4)) - (3 + 21)))) \\
14378 &:= ((98 - 7) \times -((6 \times -5) - (4 \times (32 \times 1)))) \\
14379 &:= ((9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) + 2))) \times -1) \\
14380 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times ((65 \times 4) - 3))) + 21)) \\
14381 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times ((65 \times 4) - 3))) - 2)) \times -1) \\
14382 &:= (9 \times -((8 \times -7) - (6 \times (5 + (4 \times (3 \times 21)))))) \\
14383 &:= (((9 + 8) - (((7 \times (6 + 5)) + 43^2)) \times -1) \\
14384 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times ((65 \times 4) - 3)) - 2)) + 1)) \\
14385 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 76) \times 5)) \times ((4 \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\
14386 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times ((65 \times 4) - 3)) - 2)) - 1)) \\
14387 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -((5 - ((4 + 3)^2))) - 1) \\
14388 &:= ((9 - (((8 - ((7 - 6)^5)^4) \times 3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
14389 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 43))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
14390 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (((7^{(6-5)^4}) \times -((3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
14391 &:= (9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times -((65 + 43)) + 21)) \\
14392 &:= ((9 - (8 - (7 + 6))) \times ((5 + (4^{3+2})) - 1)) \\
14393 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 - ((6 \times (5 \times 4))^{3-2+1}))) \\
14394 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - ((6 \times (5 \times 4))^{3-2+1}))) \\
14395 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times -((65 - (4^{3+2}))) + 1)) \\
14396 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -((4^3) + 2)) + 1)) \\
14397 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 + 6)) + 5) \times -((4 \times (32 + 1)))))) \\
14398 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times ((65 \times 4) - 3))) + (2 + 1))) \\
14399 &:= ((9 - (8 - 76)) \times -((5 - ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
14400 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7^{(6-5)^4})) \times (3 \times -((2 \times 1))) \\
14401 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 \times (6 + 5)) + 43^2) \times -1)) \\
14402 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 \times ((65 \times 4) - 3))) + 2)) - 1) \\
14403 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((65 \times 4) - 3)))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
14404 &:= (((9 - 8) - ((7^{(6-5)^4}) \times 3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
14405 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7^{(6-5)^4}) \times -((3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
14406 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7^{(6-5)^4}) \times (3 \times 2)) - 1))) \\
14407 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((7^{(6-5)^4}) \times (3 \times 2))) \times -1)) \\
14408 &:= (((9 - 8) + ((7^{(6-5)^4}) \times 3)) \times -((2 \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14409 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times 3)^4) - (5^6))) + (7 + (8 \times 9)) & 14409 &:= (9 - (((8 \times -(7 - (65 - 43)))^2) \times -1)) \\
14410 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 + 4)^5) \times 6) / -7) + (8 - 9)) & 14410 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 - ((6 \times (5 \times 4))^{3-2+1}))) \\
14411 &:= (1 - (2 + (3 \times ((4 \times 5) - (67 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 14411 &:= (98 - (7 - (((6 + 5)^4) - 321))) \\
14412 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times 3)^4) - ((5^6) - 7))) + 89 & 14412 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7^{(6-5) \times 4})) \times -(3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
14413 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) + (8 - 9))) & 14413 &:= ((9 - ((8 + ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) \times 3)) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
14414 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) - 8)) - 9) & 14414 &:= (9 - (((8 - ((7 - 6)^5))^4) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1) \\
14415 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times 7)))) \times -(8 - 9)) & 14415 &:= ((9 + (8 + 76)) \times -(5 \times -(4 + (3^{2+1})))) \\
14416 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times 7)))) - (8 - 9)) & 14416 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times ((65 \times 4) - 3)) + 2)) + 1) \\
14417 &:= ((12 + (((3 + 4)^5) \times 6) / 7) + 8) - 9 & 14417 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 \times (6 + 5)) + 43)^2) \times -1) \\
14418 &:= ((12 + (((3 + 4)^5) \times 6) / 7) \times -(8 - 9)) & 14418 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 76) - 5) \times 4) \times (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
14419 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3 + (4^5))) + 6) \times 7) \times (8 - 9)) & 14419 &:= ((((-9 - 87) \times (6 \times 5)) - 4) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1) \\
14420 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3 + (4^5))) + 6) \times 7) + (8 - 9)) & 14420 &:= ((9 - (8 - (7 + 6))) \times (5 + ((4^{3+2}) + 1))) \\
14421 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3 + (4^5))) + 6) \times 7) \times -(8 - 9)) & 14421 &:= (-987 + ((6 - 54) \times -321)) \\
14422 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + 8)))) - 9 & 14422 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
14423 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3))^4) \times 56) + (78 + 9) & 14423 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times -(((6 \times 5) + (4 - 3))^2)) + 1)) \\
14424 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 + ((4 + ((5 + 6) \times 7)) \times 89)))) & 14424 &:= ((9 + (((8 - ((7 - 6)^5))^4) \times 3)) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
14425 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 + (((4^5) + 6) \times 7)))) \times (8 - 9)) & 14425 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 - 5))) \times -((4 \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
14426 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times (7 \times (8 - 9))))) & 14426 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(((7 \times 6) + 5) - (43^2))) + 1)) \\
14427 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3 + (4^5))) + 6)) \times (7 \times -(8 - 9))) & 14427 &:= (9 \times -(((876 + ((5 + 4)^3)) - 2) \times -1)) \\
14428 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(((3 + ((4^5) + 6) \times 7) - (8 + 9)))) & 14428 &:= (9 - (8 - (((76 \times (5 + 4)) + 3) \times 21))) \\
14429 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3 + ((4^5) + 6) \times 7) - (8 + 9)))) & 14429 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (((6 + 5) \times (4 - 32)) + 1)) \\
14430 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3 + (4 \times ((56 \times 7) + 8))) \times 9))) & 14430 &:= (9 - (((8 + ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) \times 3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
14431 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) + (8 + 9))) & 14431 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) \times 3)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
14432 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) - 8)) + 9) & 14432 &:= (9 + (((8 + ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) \times 3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\
14433 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + 8))) + 9) & 14433 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((7 \times (65 - 4)) - 3) \times -2) - 1) \\
14434 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + 8))) + 9) & 14434 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 \times 65) - 4) \times 32) + 1)) \\
14435 &:= ((12 + (((3 + 4)^5) \times 6) / 7) + 8) + 9 & 14435 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 - (7 \times (6 \times (5 - 43)))))) - 2) + 1) \\
14436 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 \times (4 \times ((56 - 7) \times 8) + 9))) & 14436 &:= ((9 - ((8 + (7^{(6-5) \times 4})) \times 3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
14437 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3 + (4^5))) + 6) \times -7) - (8 + 9)) & 14437 &:= ((987 - (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
14438 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times 7) + (8 \times 9))) & 14438 &:= (-987 - (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
14439 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times 7) + (8 \times 9))) & 14439 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times -(((6 \times 5) + (4 - 3))^2) + 1)) \\
14440 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + 8))) + 9) & 14440 &:= (((9 + 8) + ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) \times 3)) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
14441 &:= (1 + (2 \times (((3^4) - 5) \times (((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9))) & 14441 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(76 + (54 \times (32 \times 1)))) \\
14442 &:= (-12 - ((34 \times (5 + (6 \times 7))) + 8) \times -9) & 14442 &:= ((98 + 76) \times -((5 \times -4) - (3 \times 21))) \\
14443 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times (3 + (((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) + (8 + 9))) & 14443 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) - 5) \times -(4^3)) - 21) \\
14444 &:= (1 + ((2 \times (3 + (((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) + (8 + 9))) & 14444 &:= (9 + (8 + (((76 \times (5 + 4)) + 3) \times 21))) \\
14445 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((34 - 5) \times -(6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 14445 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - 6) \times ((5 + 4) \times -321) \\
14446 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + ((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) - (8 + 9)) & 14446 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times (65 + 4))) \times -(32 - 1)) \\
14447 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times 67))) \times 8) + 9)) & 14447 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) + 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2) + 1) \\
14448 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times ((5 \times 6) - 7))) - (8 \times -9)) & 14448 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 65)) \times ((4 \times -32) - 1)) \\
14449 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times 3)^4) - (5^6)) - (7 \times -(8 + 9))) & 14449 &:= (((9 + 8) + ((7 \times 65) - 4) \times 32)) \times 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14450 &:= ((1 - (23 \times ((4 \times (5 + 6)) - 7))) \times -(8 + 9)) & 14450 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times (((6 - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
14451 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + 8))) - 9)) & 14451 &:= ((9 + (87 \times ((6 + (54 \times 3)) - 2))) \times 1) \\
14452 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + 8))) - 9)) & 14452 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -((6 + (54 \times 3)) - 2)) - 1)) \\
14453 &:= (1 - (2 - (((34 \times (5 + (6 \times 7))) + 8) \times 9))) & 14453 &:= ((98 - (7 - 6)) \times -((5 + ((4 \times 3)^2)) \times -1)) \\
14454 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -(((4^5) + 6) \times -7) - (8 + 9))) & 14454 &:= (((987 - 6) + (5^4)) \times -(3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
14455 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3 + ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7) - 8)) - 9)) & 14455 &:= (((-987 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) / -3) - 21) \\
14456 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(((3 + ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7) - 8)) - 9)) & 14456 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) \times -((65 + (4^3)) \times 2)) + 1)) \\
14457 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((34 \times (5 + (6 \times 7))) + 8) \times -9)) & 14457 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((76 - (54 \times 3)) \times 21))) \\
14458 &:= (1 - (((2 + (34 \times 5)) \times -(6 + 78)) - 9)) & 14458 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) \times -((65 + (4^3)) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
14459 &:= (123 - ((4^5) \times -((6 + 7) - (8 - 9)))) & 14459 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times 5) \times -((4^3) + 21))) \\
14460 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + (8 + 9)))) & 14460 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 + (4 \times 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
14461 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times ((3 + ((4^5) + 6) \times 7)) + (8 - 9))) & 14461 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 65))) \times 4) + (3 \times -21)) \\
14462 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + ((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) + (8 - 9)) & 14462 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7^{(6-5) \times 4})) \times -3) \times 2)) + 1)) \\
14463 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + ((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) \times -(8 - 9)) & 14463 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7^{(6-5) \times 4})) \times -(3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
14464 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + ((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) - (8 - 9)) & 14464 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 + 6)) \times -5 - ((4 \times 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
14465 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5^6))) - ((7 + 8) \times -9)) & 14465 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 + 6)) \times (5 - ((4 \times 3)^2)))) \times 1) \\
14466 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 + 4) - 5) - (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 14466 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 + 6)) \times -5 - ((4 \times 3)^2)) + 1)) \\
14467 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3^4) + 5) \times (6 + 78) + 9))) & 14467 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((765 + (43 \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
14468 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 - ((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) + 89) & 14468 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 65) - 4))) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
14469 &:= (((-1 - 2) + (345 \times 6)) \times (7 \times -(8 - 9))) & 14469 &:= ((98 - 7) \times -(((6 + 54) \times -3) + 21)) \\
14470 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times -(6 + (7 \times 89)))) & 14470 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 + (5 \times 4)))) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
14471 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times ((4 - 5) + (67 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 14471 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 4)) - (32 + 1)) \\
14472 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -4) \times -((5 - 6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) & 14472 &:= ((9 + ((87 \times 6) + 5)) \times -(4 - (32 - 1))) \\
14473 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((345 \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9))) & 14473 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(76 - (((5^4) + 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
14474 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times (4 \times ((56 + 78) \times 9)))) & 14474 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 76) \times -((5 \times 43) - 2)) - 1)) \\
14475 &:= ((12 + 3) \times ((4^5) - ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9)))) & 14475 &:= ((9 + ((8 - 76) \times ((5 \times 43) - 2))) \times -1) \\
14476 &:= ((1 - (23 \times 45)) \times -((6 + 7) - (8 - 9))) & 14476 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + 5) \times -(4 + (3 + 21)))) \\
14477 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (345 \times 6)) \times -7) - (8 - 9))) & 14477 &:= ((((-9 + 87) \times -6) + (5 - 4)) \times -(32 - 1)) \\
14478 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 \times -((4 - 5) - (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 14478 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times 5)) \times ((4 \times 32) - 1)) \\
14479 &:= (1 \times (((2 + (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times 67))) \times 8) - 9)) & 14479 &:= ((987 - (((6^5) - 43) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
14480 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((((3 + 4)^5) \times 6) / 7) + (8 \times 9)))) & 14480 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 76) - 5) \times -(4 \times (3 \times 2))) + 1)) \\
14481 &:= (1 + (2 + (((((3 + 4)^5) \times 6) / 7) + (8 \times 9)))) & 14481 &:= (9 - ((8 \times (7 + (6 + 54))) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
14482 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - (345 \times 6)) \times -7) + 8) - 9) & 14482 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 76) - 5) \times -(4 \times (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\
14483 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 \times ((4 + 5) \times (67 \times 8))) + 9))) & 14483 &:= ((-98 \times -7) - ((654 + 3) \times -21)) \\
14484 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 - (4 - 5)) + (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 14484 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 + (65 \times (4 + (3^2)))) \times -1)) \\
14485 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((34 + (56 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 14485 &:= ((9 - (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times (4 - 32))) \times 1) \\
14486 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) + (8 \times 9))) & 14486 &:= ((9 - (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times (4 - 32))) + 1) \\
14487 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) - (8 \times -9)) & 14487 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + (6 \times 5)) - (43^2)))) \times -1) \\
14488 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((345 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) - 9) & 14488 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (65 \times 4)))) + (3 \times -21)) \\
14489 &:= (1 + ((2 - (345 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 - 9))) & 14489 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times (65 \times 4)) - ((3^2) + 1)))) \\
14490 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times -(5 \times -(6 - (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 14490 &:= ((98 - ((7 \times (6 + 5)) \times (4^3))) \times -(2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14491 &:= (((12^3)/4) + (5^6)) + (78 \times -9) & 14491 &:= (98 - (7 - ((6 \times (5 \times 4))^{3-2+1}))) \\
14492 &:= (1 \times -((2 + (345 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 - 9))) & 14492 &:= (9 + (((8 - 76) \times -((5 \times 43) - 2)) - 1)) \\
14493 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times (3 + (4^5))) + 6) \times 7)) - (8 \times -9)) & 14493 &:= ((9 - ((8 - 76) \times ((5 \times 43) - 2))) \times 1) \\
14494 &:= (((1 + 2) + (345 \times (6 \times 7))) - 8) + 9 & 14494 &:= (9 + (((8 - 76) \times -((5 \times 43) - 2)) + 1)) \\
14495 &:= (-12 + ((345 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) + 9 & 14495 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times -(((65 \times (4^3))/2) + 1))) \\
14496 &:= ((1 - ((2 + 3^4)) - (5 \times -(6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 14496 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 + (5^4)) - (3^{2+1}))) \\
14497 &:= ((1 - ((2 + 3^4) - (5^6))) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 14497 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4)))) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
14498 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) - (8 \times 9))) & 14498 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times (65 \times 4)) - (3^2))) - 1)) \\
14499 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) - (8 \times 9))) & 14499 &:= ((9 - ((87 - 6) \times (5 \times 4))) \times (3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
14500 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 34) - 5) \times (6 \times 78))) - 9) & 14500 &:= (9 - (87 - (((6 + 5)^4) - (3 \times 21)))) \\
14501 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times ((4 + 5) + (67 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 14501 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((76 - 5) \times -(4 \times 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
14502 &:= ((1 + ((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 6)) \times -((7 + 8) - 9)) & 14502 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 + ((5^4) \times (3 + 21)))) \\
14503 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (345 \times 6)) \times -7) - (8 - 9))) & 14503 &:= (98 - (((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) \times -3 \times 2) + 1)) \\
14504 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) - (((6^7)/8) + 9)) & 14504 &:= (98 - ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) \times -(3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
14505 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (345 \times 6)) \times 7)) \times -(8 - 9)) & 14505 &:= (98 - (((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) \times -3 \times 2) - 1)) \\
14506 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((345 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) + 9) & 14506 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (65 \times 4)))) + (3 \times -21)) \\
14507 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times -((5 \times 6) - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 14507 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -(4^3)) - 21) \\
14508 &:= ((1 + (23 \times 4)) \times -(((5 + 6) \times -(7 + 8)) + 9)) & 14508 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7^{(6-5) \times 4})) \times -(3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
14509 &:= (((((12^3)/4) - 5) \times ((6 \times 7) - 8)) - 9) & 14509 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times -(((5 + (4 \times 3))^2) + 1))) \\
14510 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times (3 + (4^5))) + 6) \times 7)) + 89) & 14510 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(6 - (((5 + 4)^3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
14511 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 + 4) \times -((5 + 6) - (78 \times 9)))) & 14511 &:= ((98 - ((7 \times 65) \times (4^3)))/(2 \times -1)) \\
14512 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) \times -(4 - (((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times 9)))) & 14512 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7 + (65 \times (4 - 32)))) - 1)) \\
14513 &:= (1 + ((2^3) \times -(4 - (((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times 9)))) & 14513 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(7 - (6 \times ((5 \times 4) - 32)))))) \\
14514 &:= ((1 - ((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 6)) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)) & 14514 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7 + (65 \times (4 - 32)))) + 1)) \\
14515 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) - 89)) & 14515 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 65))) \times 4) + (3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
14516 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) - 89)) & 14516 &:= ((9 - (8 + 765)) \times ((4 \times -(3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
14517 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 + ((4 + 5) \times 67)) \times -8) + 9)) & 14517 &:= (9 \times -((8 + 7) - (((6 \times 543)/2) - 1))) \\
14518 &:= (1 \times -(((23 \times 4) + (5 \times 6)) \times -(7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 14518 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((7 \times ((6 - (5 - 4))^3)) - 21)) \\
14519 &:= (1 - (((23 \times 4) + (5 \times 6)) \times -(7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 14519 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (65 \times 4)))) + (32 \times -1)) \\
14520 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 - 4)^5)) \times -6 \times -(7 - (8 + 9)))) & 14520 &:= (((9 + 8) - (76 \times 5)) \times (4 \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
14521 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (345 \times 6)) \times -7) - (8 + 9))) & 14521 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((7 + (65 \times (4 - 32)))) - 1)) \\
14522 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) - (((6^7)/8) - 9)) & 14522 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times (65 \times 4)) - (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\
14523 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)))) & 14523 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 \times -(5 + 43)) - 21)) \\
14524 &:= ((-1 - ((234 \times (5 - 67)) - 8)) + 9) & 14524 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 65))) \times ((4 \times 3)/ - (2 + 1))) \\
14525 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 + 89)))) & 14525 &:= (98 - (((76 \times (5 + 4)) + 3) \times -21)) \\
14526 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -((4 \times 5) - ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) & 14526 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 76) - 5) \times 4)) \times -(3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
14527 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (3^4)) \times -((5 \times 6) - 7) \times 8) - 9)) & 14527 &:= (9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 - 432) \times 1))) \\
14528 &:= (1 + (((2 - (3^4)) \times -((5 \times 6) - 7) \times 8) - 9)) & 14528 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -((4^3) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
14529 &:= (1 - ((2 - 34) \times -5 - ((6 \times 78) - 9))) & 14529 &:= ((9 - ((87 + 6) \times (5^4)))/ - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
14530 &:= (1 \times -2 - (3 \times ((4 \times 5) + (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 14530 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(6 - (((5 + 4)^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
14531 &:= (1 - 2 - (3 \times ((4 \times 5) + (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 14531 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4)) + (3 \times -21))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14532 &:= ((1-2) \times (3 \times -((4 \times 5) + (67 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 14532 &:= (9 - (87 - (((6+5)^4) - (32-1)))) \\
14533 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 345)) \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) + 9 & 14533 &:= (((-98 - (76-5)) \times -(43 \times 2)) - 1) \\
14534 &:= (1 \times -((234 \times (567-8))/ -9)) & 14534 &:= (((9-8) + (7 \times 6)) \times -(5 - ((4+3)^{2+1}))) \\
14535 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7))) - (8 \times -9)) & 14535 &:= ((9+8) \times -(((7+65) \times 4) - 3) \times -(2+1)) \\
14536 &:= (1 \times -(((2^{3+4}) + 56) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 14536 &:= (((98+7) - ((6+5)^4)) \times (3/ - (2+1))) \\
14537 &:= (1 - (((2^{3+4}) + 56) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 14537 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (65 \times 4)))) + (32 \times -1)) \\
14538 &:= (1 \times (2 \times - (3 - (4 \times (((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times 9)))) & 14538 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times (65 \times 4))) + (32 - 1))) \\
14539 &:= (1 + (2 \times - (3 - (4 \times (((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times 9)))) & 14539 &:= ((9 + (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times 4)) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
14540 &:= (1 + 2 + 3!! + 4) \times 5 \times (-6 - 7 + 8 + 9) & 14540 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 65)) + 4)) \times -((3+2) - 1)) \\
14541 &:= ((1+2) \times (3 + ((4 \times 5) + (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 14541 &:= (-987 - (((6^5) - (4 \times 3)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
14542 &:= ((1-23) \times -(4 + (((5 \times (6+7)) + 8) \times 9))) & 14542 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (65 \times 4)))) - (3^{2+1})) \\
14543 &:= ((1 + ((23 - (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) \times 8))/ -9) & 14543 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (65 \times 4)) - 3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
14544 &:= (((1-2) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -(6 \times -((7+8) - 9))) & 14544 &:= ((9 - (((8+7) \times (6 \times 54)) - 3)) \times -(2+1)) \\
14545 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (3^4)) \times -(((5 \times 6) - 7) \times 8)) + 9)) & 14545 &:= (((9+87) - ((6+5)^4)) \times (3/ - (2+1))) \\
14546 &:= (1 + (((2 - (3^4)) \times -(((5 \times 6) - 7) \times 8)) + 9)) & 14546 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times (65 \times 4)) - 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
14547 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3 \times 45) + 67) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 14547 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (65 \times 4)) - 3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
14548 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (345 \times 6)) \times -7) + (8 \times 9))) & 14548 &:= (9 - (((87+6) \times 5) + 4) \times -(32-1)) \\
14549 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (345 \times 6)) \times 7)) - (8 \times -9)) & 14549 &:= (((98-7) - (((6+5)^4) - (3-2))) \times -1) \\
14550 &:= ((12+3) \times ((4^5) + (6 \times ((7-8) \times 9)))) & 14550 &:= ((98 - (7-6)) \times (5 + (((4 \times 3)^2) + 1))) \\
14551 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3 + ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7)) - 89)) & 14551 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times (65 \times 4)))) \times (3/ - (2+1))) \\
14552 &:= ((1 - ((2+3) \times ((4-56) \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) & 14552 &:= (((9-8) - (7 \times (65 \times 4))) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
14553 &:= (1 \times -((((((2+3)^4)/5) \times (6+7)) - 8) \times -9)) & 14553 &:= ((9 - ((8+7) \times (((6^5)/4) - 3)))/(2 \times -1)) \\
14554 &:= (1 - ((((((2+3)^4)/5) \times (6+7)) - 8) \times -9)) & 14554 &:= (9 + ((87 - (((6+5)^4) - (3^2))) \times -1)) \\
14555 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -3) - (4 \times (56 \times (7 - (8 \times 9))))) & 14555 &:= (9 - (87 - (((6+5)^4) - ((3^2) - 1)))) \\
14556 &:= (1 - ((2+3) + (4 \times (56 \times (7 - (8 \times 9))))) & 14556 &:= (9 - (87 - (((6+5)^4) - ((3 \times 2) + 1)))) \\
14557 &:= (1 + (2 \times -((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7) - 89)) & 14557 &:= (9 + ((87 - (((6+5)^4) - (3 \times 2))) \times -1)) \\
14558 &:= (1 \times (2 \times - (3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))) & 14558 &:= (((9-87) + ((6+5)^4) - 3) + (2 \times -1)) \\
14559 &:= (1 + (2 \times - (3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))) & 14559 &:= (((9-87) + ((6+5)^4)) - ((3+2) - 1)) \\
14560 &:= (1 - (23 \times - (4 - ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times (8+9)))) & 14560 &:= ((9-87) - (((6+5)^4) - 3) \times -(2-1)) \\
14561 &:= (1 \times ((23 - ((4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) \times 8))/ -9) & 14561 &:= (((9-87) + ((6+5)^4)) - (3 - (2-1))) \\
14562 &:= (((1+2) - ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -((7+8) - 9)) & 14562 &:= ((9 + ((8+7) \times (((6^5)/4) - 3)))/ - (2 \times -1)) \\
14563 &:= (((1 + (2^{3 \times 4 + 5})) - 6)/ - ((7-8) \times 9)) & 14563 &:= (((9-87) + ((6+5)^4) - 3) + (2+1)) \\
14564 &:= ((1 - (2-3)) \times -(((4^5) + 6) \times -7) - (8 \times 9)) & 14564 &:= ((9-87) - (((6+5)^4) + (3-2)) \times -1) \\
14565 &:= ((12+3) \times ((4^5) - ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9))) & 14565 &:= (((9-87) + ((6+5)^4)) + (3 - (2-1))) \\
14566 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -3) + (4 \times (56 \times (7 - (8 \times 9))))) & 14566 &:= ((9-87) - (((6+5)^4) + 3) \times -(2-1)) \\
14567 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -3) + (4 \times (56 \times (7 - (8 \times 9))))) & 14567 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6+5)^4)) - (3^{2+1})) \\
14568 &:= (12 \times -(((3 \times (4^5))/ -6) - (78 \times 9))) & 14568 &:= ((9-87) - (((6+5)^4) + (3+2)) \times -1) \\
14569 &:= (1 \times (((2+3) \times -((4-56) \times (7 \times 8))) + 9)) & 14569 &:= ((9+8) \times ((7 - ((6^5)/4) + (3+2))) \times -1) \\
14570 &:= (1 \times - (2 \times - (3 + (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))) & 14570 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (((6 - ((5^4) + 3))/2) + 1)) \\
14571 &:= (1 - (2 \times - (3 + (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))) & 14571 &:= (((9-87) + ((6+5)^4)) + ((3^2) - 1)) \\
14572 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3 \times (45 \times 6))) + (7-8)) \times -9)) & 14572 &:= ((9-87) - (((6+5)^4) + (3^2)) \times -1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14573 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4 + 5}) + (6 + 78))) / 9) & 14573 &:= (((9 - 87) + ((6 + 5)^4)) + ((3^2) + 1)) \\
14574 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)) & 14574 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6^5)) / 4) - 3)) / (2 \times -1) \\
14575 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4 + 5}) + ((6 + 7) \times 8))) / -9) & 14575 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (65 \times 4)))) - (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
14576 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (345 \times 6)) \times -7) - (8 \times 9))) & 14576 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (65 \times 4)))) - ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
14577 &:= ((1 + (2^{3 \times 4 - 5})) \times (((6 + 7) \times 8) + 9)) & 14577 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6^5)) / 4) + 3)) / (2 \times -1) \\
14578 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) - 9)))))) & 14578 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 \times 65) \times (4^3)) / -2) - 1) \\
14579 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) - 9)))))) & 14579 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times (65 \times 4))) - ((3^2) + 1))) \\
14580 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times ((4 - ((5 + 67) - 8)) \times -9)) & 14580 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - 6) \times -(54^{3-2+1}) \\
14581 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 345) \times 6)) \times (7 \times -(8 - 9))) & 14581 &:= (((9 - 87) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) + 21) \\
14582 &:= (1 \times -(23 \times -(4 - ((5 - (67 + 8)) \times 9)))) & 14582 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) - ((6 + 5)^4) \times 3))) / -2 + 1) \\
14583 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3^4) \times -(5 \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) - 9)))))) & 14583 &:= (((9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6^5)) / 4)) - 3) / -2 \times -1) \\
14584 &:= (1 \times (((23 + (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) \times 8) / 9)) & 14584 &:= (9 - ((8 \times 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) - ((3^2) + 1)))) \\
14585 &:= (1 + (((23 + (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) \times 8) / 9)) & 14585 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6 + 5)^4) - (3^2)) \times -1) \\
14586 &:= (((1 - 2) - ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -((7 + 8) - 9)) & 14586 &:= ((9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6^5)) / 4) + 3)) / -2 \times -1) \\
14587 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + (4 \times -(56 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) & 14587 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4)) + ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
14588 &:= (1 \times (2 + (34 \times ((5 \times (6 + 78)) + 9)))) & 14588 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6 + 5)^4) - (3 \times 2)) \times -1) \\
14589 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3 \times (45 \times 6))) - (7 - 8)) \times -9)) & 14589 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) + (2 \times -1) \\
14590 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^{(-4+5) \times 6}))) \times -(7 - (8 + 9))) & 14590 &:= ((9 + ((8 - 7)^6)) \times -(((5 + 4)^3) \times -2) - 1) \\
14591 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 345) \times -(6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9))) & 14591 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times -(2 - 1)) \\
14592 &:= (12 - ((3^4) \times -(5 \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) - 9)))))) & 14592 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
14593 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + 89)))) & 14593 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) - (2 \times -1) \\
14594 &:= ((1 - 2) + (3 \times -(4 - ((5 + (67 \times 8)) \times 9)))) & 14594 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) + (2 + 1) \\
14595 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(3 \times -(4 - ((5 + (67 \times 8)) \times 9)))) & 14595 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) + (2 \times -1) \\
14596 &:= (1 \times ((234 - 56) \times -(7 - 89))) & 14596 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4)) + (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
14597 &:= (1 + ((234 - 56) \times -(7 - 89))) & 14597 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3) \times -(2 - 1)) \\
14598 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)) & 14598 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 7) \times (((6^5) / 4) + 3))) / (2 \times -1) \\
14599 &:= (1 - (((23 + 4) \times -(5 + (67 \times 8))) + 9)) & 14599 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) - (2 \times -1) \\
14600 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times (567 + (8 + 9))) & 14600 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6 + 5)^4) + (3 \times 2)) \times -1) \\
14601 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4 + 5}) + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) / 9) & 14601 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
14602 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times -(6 + (78 + 9)))) & 14602 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4)) + ((3^2) - 1)) \\
14603 &:= (1 \times ((2 - ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times 6))) \times 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) & 14603 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6 + 5)^4) + (3^2)) \times -1) \\
14604 &:= (1 + ((2 - ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times 6))) \times 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) & 14604 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4)) + ((3^2) + 1)) \\
14605 &:= (1 \times (23 \times -(4 - 567) - (8 \times 9))) & 14605 &:= (((-98 \times ((7 + 6) - (54 \times 3))) + 2) + 1) \\
14606 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(((3 + ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))) & 14606 &:= ((98 - (((7^6) - 5) / 4) - 3) / 2) \times -1) \\
14607 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3 + ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))) & 14607 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6^5) / 4) + 3))) / -2 \times -1) \\
14608 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) + 5)) \times -(6 - (7 - 89))) & 14608 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - (((6 + 5)^4) - (3^{2+1})))) \\
14609 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times (45 + (67 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 14609 &:= (((9 + 87) - (((6 + 5)^4) \times 3)) / -2 + 1) \\
14610 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 - 4) - ((5 + (67 \times 8)) \times 9)) & 14610 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 \times (5 + (4 + 3)))))) \times -(2 \times -1) \\
14611 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!)^4 - 5! \times 6 / (7 + 8 + 9) & 14611 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - (32 - 1) \\
14612 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 + 5)! - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 14612 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 \times 65)) + 4)) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
14613 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 - 4) + (56 \times (78 + 9)))) & 14613 &:= ((9 + (((8 - 7) - ((6 + 5)^4)) / 3)) \times -(2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14614 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3+4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
14615 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3+4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
14616 &:= (((1-2) - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 \times -((7+8) - 9))) \\
14617 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 - 56)))) \times ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
14618 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3+4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
14619 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3+4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
14620 &:= (((1-2) + ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times 6))) \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)) \\
14621 &:= (1 - ((2 + (34 \times 5)) \times -((6+7) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
14622 &:= (1 + (2 + (3 \times (4 + ((5 + (67 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
14623 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4 + 5}) + (67 \times 8))) / -9) \\
14624 &:= (-1 + ((23 + ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8)) \times -9)) \\
14625 &:= ((12 + 3) \times ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
14626 &:= ((1 - (23 \times (4 + 5))) \times -((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
14627 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (4 + (56 \times (78 + 9))))) \\
14628 &:= (12 - (((3+4) \times 5) - 6) \times -(7 \times (8 \times 9))) \\
14629 &:= (-1 - ((2+3) \times -((45 \times 67) - 89))) \\
14630 &:= (1 \times -((2+3) \times -((45 \times 67) - 89))) \\
14631 &:= (12 - (3 \times -(4 + ((5 + (67 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
14632 &:= (((1+2) - 34) \times (5 - ((6 \times 78) + 9))) \\
14633 &:= (((-12 \times -((34 - 5) \times (6 \times 7))) + 8) + 9) \\
14634 &:= ((12 - (((3 \times 4)^5) - (6 \times 7))) / -(8 + 9)) \\
14635 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
14636 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
14637 &:= (((1+2) - ((3 \times 4)^5)) / ((6 - 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\
14638 &:= ((1 - (23 + 4)) \times -(5 + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
14639 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
14640 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
14641 &:= (1 \times ((2 - (((3 \times 4)^5) + 67)) / -(8 + 9)) \\
14642 &:= (1 + ((2 - (((3 \times 4)^5) + 67)) / -(8 + 9)) \\
14643 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 3)^4) - (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times -9) \\
14644 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times -9) \\
14645 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 345) \times (6 \times 7))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
14646 &:= ((1 - ((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 6)) \times -((7 + 8) - 9)) \\
14647 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 345) \times (6 \times 7))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
14648 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!)^4 + (5 + 6 - 7)! - 8 - 9 \\
14649 &:= (12 - ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times 6))) \times -(7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
14650 &:= (-1 - (23 \times -((4 \times 5) - (6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\
14651 &:= ((1 - (23 \times 4)) \times ((5 \times -((6 \times 7) - 8)) + 9)) \\
14652 &:= (12 \times -(3 \times -((4^5) + (6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\
14653 &:= (1 - ((2 + 34) \times -((5 \times 67) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
14654 &:= (1 \times ((2 - (3 \times (4 \times (5 + 67)))) \times -(8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14614 &:= (((9-8)^7) \times (((6+5)^4) - (3^{2+1}))) \\
14615 &:= (((9-8)^7) + ((6+5)^4)) - (3^{2+1}) \\
14616 &:= ((98 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5 + (4^{3+2-1}))) \\
14617 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - ((6+5)^4)) \times (3 / -(2 + 1))) \\
14618 &:= (((9 - (8 - 7)) + ((6+5)^4)) - (32 - 1)) \\
14619 &:= ((9 + ((87 - (6 + 5)) \times (4^3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
14620 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((7 \times (65 - 4)) + 3) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
14621 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6+5)^4)) + (3^{2+1})) \\
14622 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 + ((6+5)^4)) - (3^{2+1}))) \\
14623 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4)))) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
14624 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 - (((6+5)^4) - ((3^2) + 1)))) \\
14625 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 - (((6+5)^4) - (3^2))) \times -1)) \\
14626 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 - (((6+5)^4) - (3^2))) \times -1)) \\
14627 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - (((6+5)^4) - ((3^2) - 1)))) \\
14628 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 - (((6+5)^4) - (3 \times 2))) \times -1)) \\
14629 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 - (((6+5)^4) - (3 \times 2))) \times -1)) \\
14630 &:= (((9 - (8 + 7)) + ((6+5)^4)) - 3) + (2 \times -1) \\
14631 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 - (((6+5)^4) - 3)) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
14632 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + ((6+5)^4)) - ((3^2) + 1) \\
14633 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 - (((6+5)^4) - (3 - 2))) \times -1)) \\
14634 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + ((6+5)^4)) - ((3^2) - 1) \\
14635 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + ((6+5)^4)) + ((3 \times -2) - 1) \\
14636 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + ((6+5)^4)) + (3 \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
14637 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + (((6+5)^4) - 3)) + (2 \times -1) \\
14638 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times (((6+5)^4) - (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
14639 &:= (((9 - (8 - 7)) + ((6+5)^4)) - ((3^2) + 1)) \\
14640 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) - (((6+5)^4) - (3^2)) \times -1) \\
14641 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + (((6+5)^4) - 3)) - (2 \times -1) \\
14642 &:= (((9 - (8 - 7)) + ((6+5)^4)) + ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
14643 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) - (((6+5)^4) - (3 \times 2)) \times -1) \\
14644 &:= (((9 - (8 - 7)) + ((6+5)^4)) - 3) + (2 \times -1) \\
14645 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + ((6+5)^4)) - 3) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
14646 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 + ((6+5)^4)) - 3) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
14647 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + ((6+5)^4)) - (3 - 2)) \times -1)) \\
14648 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + ((6+5)^4)) - (3 \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
14649 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + ((6+5)^4)) - ((3 \times -2) - 1) \\
14650 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 + (5 \times 4)))) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\
14651 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (((6+5)^4) + (3^2)) \times -1) \\
14652 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + ((6+5)^4)) + ((3^2) + 1) \\
14653 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 - (((6+5)^4) + (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
14654 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + (((6+5)^4) + (3 \times 2))) \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14655 &:= ((12+3) \times -(4 - ((5 + ((6+7) \times 8)) \times 9))) & 14655 &:= ((9-8) - ((7 + (((6+5)^4) + (3 \times 2))) \times -1)) \\
14656 &:= (((12^3) - (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) \times (8-9)) & 14656 &:= ((9-8) \times (7 + (((6+5)^4) + (3^2) - 1))) \\
14657 &:= (((((-1 + (2+3)) \times 456) + 7) \times 8) + 9) & 14657 &:= ((9-8) \times -((7 + (((6+5)^4) + (3^2))) \times -1)) \\
14658 &:= ((1 + ((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 6)) \times ((7+8) - 9)) & 14658 &:= ((9-8) - ((7 + (((6+5)^4) + (3^2))) \times -1)) \\
14659 &:= (1 - ((23 + (4^5)) \times -((6+7) - (8-9)))) & 14659 &:= (((9 - (8-7)) + ((6+5)^4)) + ((3^2) + 1)) \\
14660 &:= (1 \times ((2+3) \times -(4 \times (56 - 789)))) & 14660 &:= (((9+8) - 7) - (((6+5)^4) + (3^2)) \times -1)) \\
14661 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times -(((4 + (5 \times (6+7))) \times -8) + 9)) & 14661 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7+6) - (5^4)))) \times (3 \times -(2-1))) \\
14662 &:= ((-1 + ((2+345) \times (6 \times 7))) + 89) & 14662 &:= ((9+8) - (((7 + ((6+5)^4)) - 3) \times -(2-1))) \\
14663 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (34 \times 5))) \times -((6 \times -7) + (8-9))) & 14663 &:= ((9+8) + ((7 + ((6+5)^4)) - (3 - (2-1)))) \\
14664 &:= ((1+23) \times ((4 + ((5+6) \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)) & 14664 &:= ((9+8) - (((7 + ((6+5)^4)) - (3-2)) \times -1)) \\
14665 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(3 \times ((4-56) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))))) & 14665 &:= ((9+8) - ((7 + ((6+5)^4)) \times -(3/(2+1)))) \\
14666 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!)^4 - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 14666 &:= ((9+8) - ((7 + (((6+5)^4) + (3-2))) \times -1)) \\
14667 &:= (-1 - (2 - (((34+5) \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times 9)) & 14667 &:= ((9+8) + (7 + (((6+5)^4) + (3 - (2-1)))))) \\
14668 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((34+5) \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times 9)) & 14668 &:= ((9+8) - ((7 + (((6+5)^4) + 3)) \times -(2-1))) \\
14669 &:= (1 - (2 - (((34+5) \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times 9)) & 14669 &:= ((9+8) + (7 + (((6+5)^4) + ((3+2) - 1)))) \\
14670 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times (5 \times -(6 - (7 + (8+9)))))) & 14670 &:= (((9 + (8+7)) + (((6+5)^4) + 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
14671 &:= (1 \times -((23 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) \times -(8+9))) & 14671 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - ((5^4) \times 3)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
14672 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -((4^5) + (6 \times ((7+8) \times 9)))))) & 14672 &:= ((9+8) + (7 + (((6+5)^4) + ((3 \times 2) + 1)))) \\
14673 &:= (1 - ((2^3) \times -((4^5) + (6 \times ((7+8) \times 9)))))) & 14673 &:= ((9+8) + (7 + (((6+5)^4) + ((3^2) - 1)))) \\
14674 &:= ((12+34) \times -((5 \times -(6 + (7 \times 8))) - 9)) & 14674 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times ((7 \times 6) - ((5^4) \times 3))) - 2)) - 1) \\
14675 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - (5^6))) - 789) & 14675 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times ((7 \times 6) - ((5^4) \times 3))) - 2)) \times 1) \\
14676 &:= (12 \times (((34-56) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9)) & 14676 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times ((7 \times 6) - ((5^4) \times 3))) - 2)) + 1) \\
14677 &:= (((-12 \times (3^4)) + ((5^6) + (7+8))) + 9) & 14677 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (((7+6) - (5^4)) \times 3)) + 2)) \times -1) \\
14678 &:= (((1-2) - (3^4)) \times ((5 \times -((6 \times 7) - 8)) - 9)) & 14678 &:= (9 + ((8-7) + (((6+5)^4) + (3^{2+1})))) \\
14679 &:= ((1+2) \times (3 \times -(4 - (5 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))))) & 14679 &:= (9 - ((8+7) \times -(6 - (54 \times (3-21)))))) \\
14680 &:= (((-1 + 234) \times (56+7)) - (8-9)) & 14680 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times (4 \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
14681 &:= (1 \times (((2^3) - (45 \times 6)) \times -(7 \times 8) + 9)) & 14681 &:= ((9-8) - ((7 + (((6+5)^4) + 32)) \times -1)) \\
14682 &:= (1 + (((2^3) - (45 \times 6)) \times -(7 \times 8) + 9)) & 14682 &:= ((9+8) - (7 - (((6+5)^4) + (32 - 1)))) \\
14683 &:= (123 + (4 \times -(56 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) & 14683 &:= ((9+8) - (7 - (((6+5)^4) + (32 \times 1)))) \\
14684 &:= (-1 - ((2+3) \times -(((4 \times 5) + (6+7)) \times 89))) & 14684 &:= (9 + ((8-7) + (((6+5)^4) + (32 + 1)))) \\
14685 &:= ((12+3) \times -((4 - ((5-6) \times 7)) \times -89)) & 14685 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6+5)^4) - 3)) \times -(2-1)) \\
14686 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times ((45+6) \times (7+89)))))) & 14686 &:= ((-9+8) - (((7 \times 65) + 4) \times -32) + 1)) \\
14687 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times ((45+6) \times (7+89)))))) & 14687 &:= ((9-8) \times -(((7 \times 65) + 4) \times -32) + 1)) \\
14688 &:= (((12^3)/-4) - (5 \times -(6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 14688 &:= ((9 - (8 + (7+6))) \times -(((5 \times (4+3))^2) - 1)) \\
14689 &:= (((12^3)/-4) + (5^6)) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9)) & 14689 &:= (((9+8) + (76 \times 5)) \times -((4 \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
14690 &:= ((1 - (23+4)) \times -(5 \times -(6 - (7 \times (8+9)))))) & 14690 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -((7 \times 6) - (((5^4) \times 3) + 2))) + 1)) \\
14691 &:= (1 + (2 + (3 \times ((45+6) \times (7+89)))))) & 14691 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times (5 - (4^3)))/-2) \times -1) \\
14692 &:= (1 \times -(23 - (45 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) & 14692 &:= ((9+8) + (7 + (((6+5)^4) + (3^{2+1})))) \\
14693 &:= (1 - (23 - (45 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) & 14693 &:= ((9 - (((87 \times 6) + 5) \times 4)) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
14694 &:= (1 \times -(((2+34) - 5) \times -(6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) & 14694 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (((7+6) - (5^4)) \times 3))) - (2+1)) \\
14695 &:= (1 - (((2+34) - 5) \times -(6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) & 14695 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (((7+6) - (5^4)) \times 3))) + (2 \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14696 &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times -(4 - (((5 \times 67) - 8) \times 9)))) \\
14697 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times -(6 - (7 - 89)))) \\
14698 &:= (1 - (23 \times -(4 - ((5 + 6) - 78) \times 9))) \\
14699 &:= (((-1 - 2345) \times -6) - (7 \times -89)) \\
14700 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (((((3 \times 4) - 5)^6) + 7)/8)) - 9)) \\
14701 &:= (1 + ((2 + (((((3 \times 4) - 5)^6) + 7)/8)) - 9)) \\
14702 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + (((((3 + 4)^5) + 6) \times 7)/8) - 9)) \\
14703 &:= (-12 - (3 \times -((4 + 5) \times ((67 \times 8) + 9)))) \\
14704 &:= (-12 - ((((((3 \times 4) - 5)^6) + 7)/ - 8) - 9)) \\
14705 &:= (((1 + 2) + (34 \times 5)) \times ((6 + 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
14706 &:= ((1 + (2^{3+4})) \times -((5 \times -(6 + (7 + 8))) - 9)) \\
14707 &:= (1 \times -(2^3) - (45 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
14708 &:= (1 - (2^3) - (45 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
14709 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -3) + (45 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\
14710 &:= (12 - ((((((3 \times 4) - 5)^6) + 7)/ - 8) + 9)) \\
14711 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) - (45 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\
14712 &:= ((1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - (5 + 6))) \times -(7 + (8 + 9))) \\
14713 &:= (1 + (2^3) \times (((4 \times 56) + 7) \times 8) - 9)) \\
14714 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((((((3 \times 4) - 5)^6) + 7)/8) + 9))) \\
14715 &:= (1 - (2 - ((((((3 \times 4) - 5)^6) + 7)/8) + 9))) \\
14716 &:= ((1 - (23 + 4)) \times -((567 + 8) - 9)) \\
14717 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times ((67 \times 8) + 9)))) \\
14718 &:= (1 + (2 + (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times ((67 \times 8) + 9)))) \\
14719 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((((((3 \times 4) - 5)^6) + 7)/ - 8) - 9)) \\
14720 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^4)) \times -(5 - ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9))) \\
14721 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -3) - (45 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\
14722 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -3) - (45 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\
14723 &:= (1 \times (2^3) + (45 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
14724 &:= (1 + (2^3) + (45 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
14725 &:= (((1 + 2) - 34) \times (5 \times -(((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9))) \\
14726 &:= (((1 + (234 \times (56 + 7))) - 8) - 9) \\
14727 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 - ((4^5) + ((6^7)/(8 \times 9)))) \\
14728 &:= (12 - ((((((3 \times 4) - 5)^6) + 7)/ - 8) - 9)) \\
14729 &:= ((((-12 - 3) \times -((4^5) - (6 \times 7))) + 8) - 9) \\
14730 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 \times ((4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\
14731 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 \times ((4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\
14732 &:= (((-12 \times (3^4)) + ((5^6) + 7)) - (8 \times -9)) \\
14733 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 + ((4 - (5 + 6)) \times (78 \times 9)))) \\
14734 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times ((4^5) + ((6^7)/(8 \times 9)))) \\
14735 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times ((4^5) + ((6^7)/(8 \times 9)))) \\
14736 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) \times -(4 + (((5 \times 67) - 8) \times 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14696 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times (65 \times 4))) \times (3^2 - 1)) \\
14697 &:= (((9 + 8) - (((7^6) - 5)/4)) / - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
14698 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + (((6 + 5)^4) + (32 + 1)))) \\
14699 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (((7 + 6) - (5^4)) \times 3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
14700 &:= ((9 + ((8 - ((7^6) - 5)/4)) / - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
14701 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - (((6 + 5)^4) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)))) \\
14702 &:= ((9 - ((8 + (((7^6) - 5)/4) + 3)) / 2) \times -1) \\
14703 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((((7^6) - 5)/4) - 3) / - 2) + 1)) \\
14704 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((((((7^6) - 5)/4) - 3) / - 2) + 1)) \\
14705 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((((((7^6) - 5)/4) - 3) / - 2) \times 1)) \\
14706 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7^6) - (5 - 4)) / - ((3^2) - 1)) \\
14707 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((((7^6) - 5)/4) + 3) / - (2 \times 1)) \\
14708 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((((7^6) - 5)/4) + 3) / - 2) - 1)) \\
14709 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((((((7^6) - 5)/4) + 3) / - 2) - 1)) \\
14710 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 \times 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
14711 &:= ((9 + (((8 + (7^6)) - 5)/4)) / (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
14712 &:= ((9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times -(((5 \times (4 + 3))^2) + 1)) \\
14713 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
14714 &:= (((9 + 8) + (((7^6) - 5)/4)) / (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
14715 &:= (9 - (((8 + (((7^6) + 5) \times 4)) / - 32) + 1)) \\
14716 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times ((65 \times 4) + 3))) + 21)) \\
14717 &:= (9 - (((8 + (((7^6) + 5) \times 4)) / - 32) - 1)) \\
14718 &:= (((9 - 87) - (((6 + 5)^4) - (3 - 2))) \times -1) \\
14719 &:= (9 - (((8 + (((7^6) - 5)/4) + 3)) / - 2) + 1)) \\
14720 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((((((7^6) - 5)/4) - 3) / - 2) + 1)) \\
14721 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((((((7^6) - 5)/4) - 3) / - 2) \times 1)) \\
14722 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7^6) - (5 + 4)) / - ((3^2) - 1)) \\
14723 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7^6) - (5 - 4)) / - ((3^2) - 1)) \\
14724 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((((((7^6) - 5)/4) + 3) / - 2) \times 1)) \\
14725 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((((((7^6) - 5)/4) + 3) / - 2) - 1)) \\
14726 &:= (98 + ((7 - (((6 + 5)^4) - (3 \times 2))) \times -1)) \\
14727 &:= (((98 - 7) + ((6 + 5)^4) - 3) + (2 \times -1)) \\
14728 &:= (98 - (7 - (((6 + 5)^4) - ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
14729 &:= (98 + ((7 - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
14730 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) \times (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
14731 &:= (((98 - 7) + ((6 + 5)^4) - 3) - (2 \times -1)) \\
14732 &:= (98 + ((7 - ((6 + 5)^4)) \times -3) / (2 + 1))) \\
14733 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - (((6 + 5)^4) + (3^{2+1}))) \\
14734 &:= (98 - (7 - (((6 + 5)^4) + (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
14735 &:= ((98 - 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3) \times -2) - 1)) \\
14736 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 - ((5^4) - (3 + 2))) \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14737 &:= ((-1 + 23) - (45 \times -((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) & 14737 &:= (((98 - 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
14738 &:= (1 \times (23 + (45 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) & 14738 &:= (98 + ((7 - (((6 + 5)^4) + (3 \times 2))) \times -1)) \\
14739 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 \times -((4^5) + ((6^7)/(8 \times 9)))) & 14739 &:= (((9 + 8)^{7-(6-5) \times 4}) \times -(3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
14740 &:= (1 \times -(2 + (3 \times ((4 - (5 + 6)) \times (78 \times 9)))) & 14740 &:= (98 - (((7 + ((6 + 5)^4)) - (3 \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
14741 &:= (1 - (2 + (3 \times ((4 - (5 + 6)) \times (78 \times 9)))) & 14741 &:= ((98 - 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) + (3^2)) \times -1)) \\
14742 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 + 5)) + (6 \times -((7 + 8) \times 9))) & 14742 &:= (98 - (7 - (((6 + 5)^4) + ((3^2) + 1)))) \\
14743 &:= (1 \times -((234 \times -(56 + 7)) + (8 - 9))) & 14743 &:= (98 - (((7 + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
14744 &:= (((1 + (234 \times (56 + 7))) - 8) + 9) & 14744 &:= (98 + ((7 + ((6 + 5)^4)) - (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
14745 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 + ((4^5) + ((6^7)/(8 \times 9)))) & 14745 &:= (98 - (((7 + ((6 + 5)^4)) - (3 - 2)) \times -1)) \\
14746 &:= -(1^2 + 3)^4 + 5^6 - 7 \times 89 & 14746 &:= (98 - ((7 + ((6 + 5)^4)) \times -(3/(2 + 1)))) \\
14747 &:= ((((-12 - 3) \times -((4^5) - (6 \times 7))) + 8) + 9) & 14747 &:= (98 - ((7 + (((6 + 5)^4) + (3 - 2))) \times -1)) \\
14748 &:= (12 - (3 \times -((4^5) + ((6^7)/(8 \times 9)))) & 14748 &:= (((9 + 8)^{7-(6-5) \times 4}) + 3) \times (2 + 1)) \\
14749 &:= (1 \times ((2 - 345) \times -((6 \times 7) - (8 - 9)))) & 14749 &:= (98 - ((7 + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
14750 &:= (1 + ((2 - 345) \times -((6 \times 7) - (8 - 9)))) & 14750 &:= (98 + (7 + (((6 + 5)^4) + ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
14751 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 - ((4 - (5 + 6)) \times (78 \times 9)))) & 14751 &:= (((98 + 7) - 6) \times -((5 + ((4 \times 3)^2)) \times -1)) \\
14752 &:= (1 - (((234 + 5) - 6) \times 7) + 8) \times -9) & 14752 &:= (98 - ((7 + (((6 + 5)^4) + (3 \times 2))) \times -1)) \\
14753 &:= (1 \times -((2 + (3^4)) - ((5^6) - 789))) & 14753 &:= (((98 + (((7^6) - 5)/4) - 3) / - (2 \times -1)) \\
14754 &:= ((1 - 2) + ((3 + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 14754 &:= (98 + (7 + (((6 + 5)^4) + ((3^2) - 1)))) \\
14755 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((3 + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 14755 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) + (2 - 1))) \\
14756 &:= ((123 - 4) \times -((5 + 6) - ((7 + 8) \times 9))) & 14756 &:= ((98 + (((7^6) - 5)/4 + 3)) / - (2 \times -1)) \\
14757 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 34) + 56) \times -(7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 14757 &:= (9 - (876 - ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) - 1))) \\
14758 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 14758 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times 54) - ((3^2) + 1))) \\
14759 &:= (1 - (2 + (3 \times ((4 + 56) \times (7 - 89)))) & 14759 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 7) - 6)^5) - 4) / - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
14760 &:= (((1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times (5 \times -(6 \times ((7 + 8) - 9)))) & 14760 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(6 \times -((5 \times ((4 + 3)^2)) + 1))) \\
14761 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times (5 + 6))) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 14761 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 7) - 6)^5) + 4) / - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
14762 &:= (1 \times -((2 - ((3^{4+5}) \times 6)) / (7 - (8 - 9)))) & 14762 &:= (9 - (((87 + 6) \times 5) - 4) \times -32) - 1) \\
14763 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 + (((4 + 5)^6) + 7)/8))) / - 9) & 14763 &:= ((98 + (7 + 6)) \times -((5 + (4 \times 32)) \times -1)) \\
14764 &:= (1 + 2) \times ((3 + 4)! - 5) - 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 & 14764 &:= (((9 + 87) + ((6 + 5)^4)) + (3^{2+1})) \\
14765 &:= (((((-1 - 2) \times (3^4)) + 5) \times -(6 + (7 \times 8))) + 9) & 14765 &:= (((98 - 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 32)) + 1) \\
14766 &:= ((1 + ((23 \times (4 + 5)) + 6)) \times (78 - 9)) & 14766 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 76) + 5) \times 4)) \times -(3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
14767 &:= (12 + ((3 + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 14767 &:= ((-9 \times 87) - (((6^5) - (4 - 3)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
14768 &:= ((1 + (23 \times (4 + 5))) \times ((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9))) & 14768 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 - (6 + 5)) + (43^2))) + 1)) \\
14769 &:= (1 \times ((23 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7))/8)) \times -9)) & 14769 &:= (9 - ((87 + (((6 + 5)^4) + 32)) \times -1)) \\
14770 &:= (1 + ((23 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7))/8)) \times -9)) & 14770 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 - (6 + 5)) + (43^2))) - 1)) \\
14771 &:= ((-1 + (2345 \times 6)) - (78 \times -9)) & 14771 &:= ((-9 \times 87) - (((6^5) + (4 - 3)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
14772 &:= (12 \times -(((34 \times 5) + 6) \times -7) - (8 - 9)) & 14772 &:= ((98 - ((7^6) + (5^4))) / - ((3^2) - 1)) \\
14773 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 34) + 56) \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)) & 14773 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 \times -(6 - ((5 - (4^3)) \times 2))) - 1)) \\
14774 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) + 5)) \times ((6 - 7) \times 89)) & 14774 &:= ((-987 \times -(6 + (5 + 4))) - (32 - 1)) \\
14775 &:= ((12 + 3) \times (4 + ((5 + ((6 + 7) \times 8)) \times 9))) & 14775 &:= ((9 - (8 + 76)) \times -(5 + ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
14776 &:= (1 - (((234 + (5 \times 6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9)) & 14776 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 - 65) \times 4))) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
14777 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) + ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8)) \times -9)) & 14777 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 - ((6 + 5) \times ((4^3) \times 21))))
\end{aligned}$$

14778 := (1 × −((2 × ((3 × (45 × 6)) + 7)) + 8) × −9))	14778 := ((9 − 8) − (7 − ((6 + 5) × ((4 ³) × 21))))
14779 := (1 − (((2 × ((3 × (45 × 6)) + 7)) + 8) × −9))	14779 := (98 + (7 + (((6 + 5) ⁴) + (32 + 1))))
14780 := ((−12/3) × (((456 + 7) × −8) + 9))	14780 := (((−98 × −7) − (((6 ⁵) − 43) × 2)) × −1)
14781 := (−1 + ((23 − 4) × −((5 + 6) − 789)))	14781 := (((9 − 8) − ((7 × (6 + 5)) × (4 ³))) × −(2 + 1))
14782 := (1 × ((23 − 4) × −((5 + 6) − 789)))	14782 := (((−98 × −76) − (54 + 3)) × −(2 × −1))
14783 := (1 + ((23 − 4) × −((5 + 6) − 789)))	14783 := (((−9 × −8) + 7) + ((6 + 5) ⁴) − (3 × −21))
14784 := (12 × (((34 × 5) + 6) × −(7 × (8 − 9))))	14784 := ((9 + (8 + 7)) × ((6 − ((5 ⁴) − 3)) × −(2 − 1)))
14785 := (1 + ((2 + (3 × (4 − 56))) × −(7 + 89)))	14785 := (9 + (8 × −(((7 − 6) ⁵) − ((43 ²) − 1))))
14786 := (−1 + (((2 + 3) + ((4 − (5 × (6 × 7))) × 8)) × −9))	14786 := (98 − (((7 × 65) + 4) × −(32 × 1)))
14787 := (1 × −(((2 + 34) − 5) × −((6 × 78) + 9)))	14787 := ((9 − ((8 × 7) + 6)) × ((5 + 4) × −(32 − 1)))
14788 := (1 × −(2 − ((34 − 5) × (6 + (7 × (8 × 9)))))	14788 := (9 + ((8 × −(7 + ((6 − (5 ⁴)) × 3))) − 21))
14789 := (1 − (2 − ((34 − 5) × (6 + (7 × (8 × 9)))))	14789 := ((9 + ((8 × (7 + ((6 − (5 ⁴)) × 3))) + 2)) × −1)
14790 := ((12 + 3) × (((4 + 5) − 67) × −(8 + 9)))	14790 := ((9 + ((8 − (76 × 5)) × 4)) × −((3 ²) + 1))
14791 := (((−1 − (2 + 34)) × −((56 × 7) + 8)) − 9)	14791 := ((9 − 8) × −(((7 + 6) − 5) × −(43 ²)) + 1))
14792 := (1 × (2 + ((34 − 5) × (6 + (7 × (8 × 9)))))	14792 := (9 + ((8 × −(((7 − 6) ⁵) − (43 ²))) − 1))
14793 := (1 + (2 + ((34 − 5) × (6 + (7 × (8 × 9)))))	14793 := ((9 − 8) × −(((7 + 6) − 5) × −(43 ²)) − 1))
14794 := (1 − (((234 + (5 × 6)) × −(7 × 8)) − 9))	14794 := (9 − (8 − (((7 + 6) − 5) × (43 ²)) + 1))
14795 := (1 × −((2 ³⁺⁴) − ((5 ⁶) − (78 × 9))))	14795 := (98 − (7 − (((6 + 5) ⁴) + (3 × 21))))
14796 := (((1 + 2) ³) × −4) × ((5 × −(6 + 7)) − (8 × 9))	14796 := (9 + ((87 × −6) + (((5 + 4) ³) × 21)))
14797 := (1 − ((2 + 34) × −((5 × (6 + 78)) − 9)))	14797 := ((−987 × −(6 + (5 + 4))) − ((3 ²) − 1))
14798 := (1 + 2) × (3 + 4 − 5! + 6! × 7) + 8 + 9	14798 := (9 − ((87 × −(6 + ((54 × 3) + 2))) + 1))
14799 := ((1 + 2) × (((3 ⁴) × −(5 − 67)) − 89))	14799 := (9 − (87 × −(((6 × −5) + 43) ²) + 1))
14800 := (1 × −((2 + 34) − ((5 ⁶) − 789)))	14800 := ((9 + (8 × (((7 − 6) ⁵) × (43 ²)))) − 1)
14801 := ((1 + ((2 ³) × 45)) × −((6 × −7) − (8 − 9)))	14801 := (98 − (((((7 ⁶) − 5)/4) − 3)/ − 2) + 1))
14802 := (1 × (2 × ((3 × (4 × ((5 + 6) × (7 × 8)))) + 9)))	14802 := (98 − (((((7 ⁶) − 5)/4) − 3)/ − (2 × 1)))
14803 := (1 × −(2 + ((3 + ((4 − (5 × (6 × 7))) × 8)) × 9)))	14803 := (98 − (((7 ⁶) − (5 + 4))/ − ((3 ²) − 1))
14804 := (1 − (2 + ((3 + ((4 − (5 × (6 × 7))) × 8)) × 9)))	14804 := (98 − (((7 ⁶) − (5 − 4))/ − ((3 ²) − 1))
14805 := ((1 − 2) × −((3 + ((4 − (5 × (6 × 7))) × 8)) × −9))	14805 := (98 − (((((7 ⁶) − 5)/4) + 3)/ − (2 × 1)))
14806 := (1 × −(2 × −((34 × ((5 × (6 × 7)) + 8)) − 9)))	14806 := (9 + ((8 × −(7 + ((6 − (5 ⁴)) × 3))) − (2 + 1)))
14807 := (1 − (2 × −((34 × ((5 × (6 × 7)) + 8)) − 9)))	14807 := ((9 − (8 × (7 + ((6 − (5 ⁴)) × 3)))) + (2 × −1))
14808 := ((1 + 2) + ((3 + ((4 − (5 × (6 × 7))) × 8)) × −9))	14808 := ((9 + (8 + 7)) × −(6 − ((5 ⁴) − (3 − (2 − 1))))
14809 := (1 × (((234 + 5) × (6 + (7 × 8))) − 9))	14809 := (((9 + 8) + (((7 + 6) − 5) × (43 ²))) × 1)
14810 := ((1 − 23) + ((4 − (5 × (6 × 7))) × −(8 × 9)))	14810 := (9 − ((8 × −(((7 − 6) ⁵) + (43 ²))) − 1))
14811 := (((−1 − (2 × (3 × 4))) + (5 ⁶)) − 789)	14811 := ((9 − (8 × (7 + ((6 − (5 ⁴)) × 3)))) − (2 × −1))
14812 := ((12 + 34) × −(5 − ((6 × (7 × 8)) − 9)))	14812 := (((9 − (8 × 7)) + (6 × (5 ⁴))) × ((3 + 2) − 1))
14813 := (((1 − (2 × (3 × 4))) + (5 ⁶)) − 789)	14813 := ((−987 × −(6 + (5 + 4))) + ((3 ²) − 1))
14814 := (12 − (34 − ((5 ⁶) − 789)))	14814 := (((9 + 8) − (7 × (6 × (5 × 4)))) × (3 − 21))
14815 := (1 × ((2 × (34 × ((5 × (6 × 7)) + 8))) − 9))	14815 := ((−987 × −(6 + (5 + 4))) + ((3 ²) + 1))
14816 := ((1 + (2 × (34 × ((5 × (6 × 7)) + 8)))) − 9)	14816 := ((−9 × −8) − (76 × −((5 × 43) − 21)))
14817 := (12 + ((3 + ((4 − (5 × (6 × 7))) × 8)) × −9))	14817 := ((9 + 8) − (((7 + 6) − 5) × −(43 ²) + 1))
14818 := ((1 − 23) + ((4 + (5 ⁶)) − 789))	14818 := ((98 + (76 × 5)) × −(((4 ³)/ − 2) + 1))

$$\begin{aligned}
14819 &:= (1 \times (2 - (3 \times ((4^5) - (67 \times 89)))))) \\
14820 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - 5)) \times (((6 + 7) \times -8) + 9)) \\
14821 &:= (1 - ((23 - 4) \times -(5 \times (67 + 89)))) \\
14822 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times -(3 + 4)) + (5^6)) - 789)) \\
14823 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3+4}) \times 5) - ((6^7) / - (8 \times 9)) \\
14824 &:= (1 + (((2 + 3) \times (4 - (5 \times 67))) + 8) \times -9)) \\
14825 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times ((5 \times -6) + (7 \times 89))) \\
14826 &:= (12 - (((34 + 5) \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) \times -9)) \\
14827 &:= (1 \times (((234 + 5) \times (6 + (7 \times 8))) + 9)) \\
14828 &:= ((1 + ((234 + 5) \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) + 9) \\
14829 &:= ((1 - 2) \times ((3 + 4) - ((5^6) - 789))) \\
14830 &:= ((-1 + (234 \times (56 + 7))) + 89) \\
14831 &:= (1 \times -(234 \times -(56 + 7) - 89)) \\
14832 &:= ((12^3) + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times -(7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
14833 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times (34 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8))) + 9)) \\
14834 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5^6))) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
14835 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times -(5 \times -(6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
14836 &:= ((1 - 2) - ((3 - 4) - ((5^6) - 789))) \\
14837 &:= ((1 + (2 + 34)) \times -(((56 - 7) \times -8) - 9)) \\
14838 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 + 5)) + (6 \times -(7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
14839 &:= (1 + ((2 + (((3 - 4) \times -5)^6)) - 789)) \\
14840 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - 3) \times 4) - ((5^6) - 789))) \\
14841 &:= (1 \times (((2 - 3) + ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8)) \times -9)) \\
14842 &:= (1 + (((2 - 3) + ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8)) \times -9)) \\
14843 &:= (1 + (2 \times ((34 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) + 9))) \\
14844 &:= (1 \times (2 - ((3^4) - ((5^6) - (78 \times 9)))))) \\
14845 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - 56) \times 7) + (8 \times -9)) \\
14846 &:= (((12^3) - (4 + (5 + 6))) \times -78) / -9) \\
14847 &:= ((12 + 3) + ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
14848 &:= (12 - ((3 - 4) \times ((5^6) - 789))) \\
14849 &:= (((((12^3) / 4) + 5) \times ((6 \times 7) - 8)) - 9) \\
14850 &:= (1 + (((2 + 3) - (45 \times 6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9)) \\
14851 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 \times -4) - ((5^6) - 789))) \\
14852 &:= ((-12 / 3) \times (((456 + 7) \times -8) - 9)) \\
14853 &:= (((-1 + 2345) \times 6) + 789) \\
14854 &:= (12 - ((3^4) - ((5^6) - (78 \times 9)))) \\
14855 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times 34) - ((5^6) - (78 \times 9)))) \\
14856 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) - ((4^5) - 6)) \times -(7 + 8)) - 9) \\
14857 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3^4)) \times ((5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8)) + 9))) \\
14858 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times ((5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8)) + 9))) \\
14859 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
14819 &:= ((9 + (((87 \times 6) + 5) \times 4)) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
14820 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times (6 \times -(5 - (4 \times (3 \times 21)))))) \\
14821 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (6 \times (5 - 43))) + 2) - 1) \\
14822 &:= (9 + (8 + (((7 + 6) \times 54) + 3) \times 21))) \\
14823 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((76 - (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
14824 &:= (((98 - 7) - ((6^5) / 4)) \times -(3^2 - 1)) \\
14825 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (((5^4) - 32) \times -1)) \\
14826 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times (65 \times 4)) + 32)) - 1)) \\
14827 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times -(4 - 321))) \\
14828 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - 4))) - 3) - (2 - 1)) \\
14829 &:= (((-987 \times -(6 + (5 + 4))) + 3) + 21) \\
14830 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7 + ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3))) + 21)) \\
14831 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) - ((6 + 5) \times -((4^3) \times 21))) \\
14832 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -(6 \times -(((54 - 3) \times 2) + 1))) \\
14833 &:= ((98 - 7) \times -((6 \times -((5 + 4) \times 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
14834 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -((7 - (6 + 5)) - (43^2))) + 1)) \\
14835 &:= (((9 + 8) + ((7 \times (6 + 5)) \times (4^3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
14836 &:= ((-987 \times -(6 + (5 + 4))) + (32 - 1)) \\
14837 &:= ((-987 \times -(6 + (5 + 4))) - (32 \times -1)) \\
14838 &:= ((-987 \times -(6 + (5 + 4))) + (32 + 1)) \\
14839 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + (((6 - 5) \times 43)^2)))) \times -1) \\
14840 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
14841 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 - 6)) - (5^4)) \times -(3 + 21))) \\
14842 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(((7 - 6) \times 5) + (43^2))) - 1)) \\
14843 &:= ((((-9876 - (5 \times 4)) \times 3) / -2) - 1) \\
14844 &:= ((((-987 + 6) \times -5) + 43) \times (2 + 1)) \\
14845 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 65))) \times 4) + 321) \\
14846 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 - ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 21)))) \\
14847 &:= (((((-9 \times -8) + (7 + 6)) + (5^4)) - 3) \times 21) \\
14848 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times (((6 - (5^4)) \times -3) - (2 - 1))) \\
14849 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 - 65) \times -(4^{3+2-1}))) \\
14850 &:= (((98 + 7) - 6) \times (5 + (((4 \times 3)^2) + 1))) \\
14851 &:= ((-98 \times 7) - (((6^5) - (4 + 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
14852 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times 54) - ((3^2) - 1))) \\
14853 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -765) + ((43^2) - 1)) \\
14854 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -765) - ((43^2) \times -1)) \\
14855 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -765) + ((43^2) + 1)) \\
14856 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times -(3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
14857 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 + 6) - 5) + (43^2))) - 1)) \\
14858 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((76 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)) / - (2 \times 1))) \\
14859 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times -(6 \times (5 \times ((4 \times 3) + 21))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 14860 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 \times 4)) - ((5^6) - 789))) & 14860 &:= (((-98 \times -76) - (54/3)) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
 14861 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 14861 &:= (((((-98 \times (7 \times 65)) + 4)/ -3) - 2) + 1) \\
 14862 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 - ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8)) \times -9)) & 14862 &:= (((((-987 - 6) \times 5) + 4) \times -3) - 21) \\
 14863 &:= ((-1 \times -23) + ((4 + (5^6)) - 789)) & 14863 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 - ((6 \times ((5^4) - 3))/2)))) \times -1) \\
 14864 &:= ((1 + 23) + ((4 + (5^6)) - 789)) & 14864 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times (((6 - (5^4)) \times -3) + (2 - 1))) \\
 14865 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3)^4) - ((5^6) - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 14865 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 - 65) \times -(4^{3+2-1}))) \\
 14866 &:= ((1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - (5^6))) + ((7 + 8) \times -9)) & 14866 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 + ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 21)))) \\
 14867 &:= (((((12^3)/4) + 5) \times ((6 \times 7) - 8)) + 9) & 14867 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5 + 432))) \times 1) \\
 14868 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 \times 4) - 5) \times -(6 + (78 \times 9)))) & 14868 &:= ((9 + (87 \times 6)) \times ((5 - 4) + (3^{2+1}))) \\
 14869 &:= (1 + (((2^3) \times 4) + ((5^6) - 789))) & 14869 &:= (-9 - (((87 \times (6 \times (54 + 3)))/ -2) - 1)) \\
 14870 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((34 + (5^6)) - 789)) & 14870 &:= ((-98/ -7) + ((6 - (5^4)) \times -(3 + 21))) \\
 14871 &:= (12 - ((3 - ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8)) \times -9)) & 14871 &:= ((9 - ((87 + 6) \times ((54 \times 3) - 2))) \times -1) \\
 14872 &:= ((1 - 23) \times -((4 \times -5) - (6 - (78 \times 9)))) & 14872 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 14873 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((34 + (5^6)) - 789)) & 14873 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(76 + (54 \times (32 + 1)))))) \\
 14874 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) - ((4^5) - 6)) \times -(7 + 8)) + 9) & 14874 &:= ((98 + (7 + 6)) \times (5 + ((4 \times 32) + 1))) \\
 14875 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3)^{4+5-6}) \times -(7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 14875 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (7 \times ((6 - 5) + (4 \times (32 - 1))))) \\
 14876 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3)^{4+5-6}) \times -(7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 14876 &:= (9876 - ((5^4) \times -((3^2) - 1))) \\
 14877 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -((4 \times -5) - ((67 - 8) \times 9))) & 14877 &:= ((9 - (87 \times 6)) \times -((5 + (4 \times (3 + (2 + 1))))) \\
 14878 &:= (1 \times -2 - (((((3 + 4)^5) - 67) \times 8)/9)) & 14878 &:= (-98 + (((7 - 6) - (5^4)) \times -(3 + 21))) \\
 14879 &:= (1 - 2 - (((((3 + 4)^5) - 67) \times 8)/9)) & 14879 &:= ((-98 \times 7) - (((6^5) + (4 + 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
 14880 &:= ((1 - ((2 - ((3^4) \times ((5 \times 6) - 7))) \times 8)) - 9) & 14880 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -(((65 + 4) \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\
 14881 &:= (1 \times -23 \times -((4 - 5) - ((6 - 78) \times 9))) & 14881 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((7 + 6) - (((5^4) \times 3) - (2 + 1))))) \\
 14882 &:= ((1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - (5^6))) + (7 \times -(8 + 9))) & 14882 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7 - ((6 \times ((5^4) - 3))/2))) + 1)) \\
 14883 &:= (1 + (2 + (((((3 + 4)^5) - 67) \times 8)/9))) & 14883 &:= (((9 + 8) - (76 \times 5)) \times ((43 - 2) \times -1)) \\
 14884 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 14884 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -((7 + 6) - ((5^4) \times 3))) - 21)) \\
 14885 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 14885 &:= (9 - (((87 \times (6 \times (54 + 3)))/ -2) + 1)) \\
 14886 &:= (1 + (((2 + 3) + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 14886 &:= (9 \times -((((8 \times 7) + 6) \times -5) - ((4^3) \times 21))) \\
 14887 &:= (1 + ((2 + ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 - 78))) \times -9)) & 14887 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times ((65 \times 4) + (3 \times 2)))) \times -1) \\
 14888 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) \times -((4 \times (5 - (6 \times 78))) - 9)) & 14888 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6 \times 5) \times -((4^3) - 2)) - 1)) \\
 14889 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 + 4) \times -(5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 14889 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + (65 \times 4)))) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
 14890 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (34 - ((5^6) - (78 \times 9)))) & 14890 &:= (98 - (((7 + 6) - 5) \times -(43^2 \times 1))) \\
 14891 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) \times 4) - ((5^6) - (78 \times 9)))) & 14891 &:= ((9 - (((8 - (7 - 6)) \times 5) - 4^3))/ (2 \times -1)) \\
 14892 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) \times -(8 + 9)) & 14892 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((7 + 6) \times -(5 + (4^3))) + 21)) \\
 14893 &:= (1 \times -2 - (((3^4) \times ((5 \times 6) - 7) \times 8) - 9)) & 14893 &:= (9 - (((8 + 76) - (5 - 43))^2) \times -1) \\
 14894 &:= (1 - 2 - (((3^4) \times ((5 \times 6) - 7) \times 8) - 9)) & 14894 &:= (9 + (((8 + 76) - (5 - 43))^2) + 1) \\
 14895 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 \times (((4^5) \times (6 + 7))/8) - 9)) & 14895 &:= ((9 + ((8 - 76) \times 5)) \times ((43 + 2) \times -1)) \\
 14896 &:= (1 \times -((23 + 4) - ((5^6) - (78 \times 9)))) & 14896 &:= (98 \times -((7 \times -6) - (5 \times (43 - 21)))) \\
 14897 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - (3^4) \times ((5 \times 6) - 7))) \times 8) - 9) & 14897 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times ((65 \times 4) + (3 \times 2))) - 1))) \\
 14898 &:= ((1 - ((2 - ((3^4) \times ((5 \times 6) - 7))) \times 8)) + 9) & 14898 &:= (98 - (((7 + 6) - 5) \times -((43^2) + 1))) \\
 14899 &:= ((1 - (((2^3) + 45) \times 6)) \times ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & 14899 &:= ((9 + (876 \times (5 + (4 \times 3)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
 14900 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - 56) \times 7) - 8) - 9) & 14900 &:= ((9 + (((8 - (7 - 6)) \times 5) - 4^3))/ - (2 \times -1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14901 & := (12 - (34 - ((5^6) - (78 \times 9)))) \\ 14902 & := (1 \times ((2 - (((3 + 4)^5) - (6 \times 7) \times 8)) / - 9)) \\ 14903 & := (1 + ((2 - (((3 + 4)^5) - (6 \times 7) \times 8)) / - 9)) \\ 14904 & := (((1 + 2)^3) \times -4) \times ((5 \times -(6 \times 7)) + (8 \times 9))) \\ 14905 & := ((1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - (5^6))) - (7 + 89)) \\ 14906 & := (1 \times (2 - ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times ((6 - 78) \times 9)))) \\ 14907 & := (12 - (((3^4) \times -((5 \times 6) - 7) \times 8)) + 9) \\ 14908 & := (1 + (((23 - 45) \times -678) - 9)) \\ 14909 & := (1 \times (((2 \times -(3 + 4)) + (5^6)) - (78 \times 9))) \\ 14910 & := ((12 + 3) \times ((4^5) - (6 + (7 + (8 + 9))))) \\ 14911 & := ((123 + (4^5)) \times ((6 + 7) \times -(8 - 9))) \\ 14912 & := ((1 - 234) \times (((5 + 67) \times 8) / - 9)) \\ 14913 & := ((1 + 2) \times -(3 \times -((4 \times (56 \times 7)) + 89))) \\ 14914 & := ((1 + 2) + (((3 \times -4) + (5^6)) - (78 \times 9))) \\ 14915 & := (1 \times (((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times (((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9))) \\ 14916 & := ((1 + 2) - (((3^4) \times -((5 \times 6) - 7) \times 8)) - 9) \\ 14917 & := (1 + (((23 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times - (7 + 8)) - 9)) \\ 14918 & := (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - 56) \times 7) - 8) + 9) \\ 14919 & := (1 + (((2 - (3 + 4)) + (5^6)) - (78 \times 9))) \\ 14920 & := (((1 - 2) - ((3^4) - (5^6))) + (7 \times -89)) \\ 14921 & := ((1 - (2 - 3)) - (4 - ((5^6) - (78 \times 9)))) \\ 14922 & := ((1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - (5^6))) - (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\ 14923 & := (12 + (((3 \times -4) + (5^6)) - (78 \times 9))) \\ 14924 & := (((1 + 2) - ((3^4) - (5^6))) + (7 \times -89)) \\ 14925 & := (12 - (((3^4) \times -((5 \times 6) - 7) \times 8)) - 9) \\ 14926 & := ((1 + 2) - ((3 - 4) \times ((5^6) - (78 \times 9)))) \\ 14927 & := ((1 + 2) - ((3 - 4) - ((5^6) - (78 \times 9)))) \\ 14928 & := (12 \times (3 - ((4 - ((5 + 6) \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 14929 & := (1 \times (((2 + ((3^4) \times ((5 \times 6) - 7))) \times 8) + 9)) \\ 14930 & := (1 + (((2 + ((3^4) \times ((5 \times 6) - 7))) \times 8) + 9)) \\ 14931 & := ((1 + 2) - (((((3 + 4)^5) - (6 + 7) \times 8) / - 9)) \\ 14932 & := ((1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - ((5^6) - 78))) + 9) \\ 14933 & := (1 \times (((2 \times 3) + 4) + (5^6)) - (78 \times 9)) \\ 14934 & := ((1 - ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -((7 + 8) - 9)) \\ 14935 & := ((1 - ((23 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times (7 + 8))) + 9) \\ 14936 & := ((1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - ((5^6) - (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 14937 & := ((1 - ((2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + (6 - 7))) \times 8)) / 9) \\ 14938 & := ((1 + 2) - ((3 \times -4) - ((5^6) - (78 \times 9)))) \\ 14939 & := (((1 + 2) + (((3 + 4)^5) + (6 - 7) \times 8)) / 9) \\ 14940 & := ((1 + 2) \times -(3 \times -(4 + (((5 \times 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 14941 & := (1 \times -(2 + (((3 - (45 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14901 & := ((9 - (8 \times (((7 - 6) \times 5^4) - 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 14902 & := ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) - ((5^4) \times 3)))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 14903 & := ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) - ((5^4) \times 3)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\ 14904 & := (((9 + (8 + 7)) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 14905 & := ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) - ((5^4) \times -(3 + 21))) \\ 14906 & := (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times ((65 \times 4) + (3 \times 2)))) - 1)) \\ 14907 & := ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) - ((5^4) \times 3)))) - (2 \times -1)) \\ 14908 & := (9 + ((8 \times -(7 + 6) - ((5^4) \times 3))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 14909 & := (9 + ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times ((5^4) - 3)))) / - (2 \times 1))) \\ 14910 & := (9 + (((8 \times (7 - (6 \times ((5^4) - 3)))) / - 2) + 1)) \\ 14911 & := ((((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (65 + 4))) \times 32) - 1) \\ 14912 & := (((9 + 8) - (7 \times (65 + 4))) \times (32 \times -1)) \\ 14913 & := ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 5) - 4))) \times -(3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\ 14914 & := ((-98 \times 7) - (6 \times -(((54 - 3)^2) - 1))) \\ 14915 & := (9 + ((8 \times -7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 321))) \\ 14916 & := ((9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times (((5^4) - 3) \times -2) + 1)) \\ 14917 & := (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 65))) \times -4) + 321) \\ 14918 & := (9 - ((8 \times -(7 - ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3))) + (2 + 1))) \\ 14919 & := ((9 + (8 \times (7 - ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\ 14920 & := ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) / - 2) + 1)) \\ 14921 & := ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) - ((5^4) \times 3) + 2))) \times 1) \\ 14922 & := ((9 + ((8 \times (7 - ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3))) + 2)) - 1) \\ 14923 & := ((9 + ((8 \times (7 - ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3))) + 2)) \times 1) \\ 14924 & := ((9 + ((8 \times (7 - ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3))) + 2)) + 1) \\ 14925 & := ((9 - (8 \times (((7 - 6) + (5^4)) - 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 14926 & := ((9 + 8) \times -((7 \times -((6 - (5 - 4))^3)) - (2 + 1))) \\ 14927 & := ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + (6 + 5)) + (43^2)))) \times -1) \\ 14928 & := ((9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times (((5^4) - 3) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\ 14929 & := (9 + (8 \times -(7 + (6 \times ((5 + 4) - 321)))) \\ 14930 & := (((-98 \times -76) + (5 + (4 \times 3))) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\ 14931 & := ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + ((6 + 5) \times (4^3))) \times -21)) \\ 14932 & := (9 - (8 - ((7 + ((6 + 5) \times (4^3))) \times 21))) \\ 14933 & := ((((-98 \times 76) - (54 / 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\ 14934 & := (9 + ((8 + 7) \times -((6 \times 5) - ((4^{3+2}) + 1)))) \\ 14935 & := ((9 - ((8 + ((7 \times 65) + 4)) \times 32)) \times -1) \\ 14936 & := (9 - ((8 \times -(7 - (((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) - 2))) + 1)) \\ 14937 & := ((9 + (8 \times (7 - (((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) - 2)))) \times 1) \\ 14938 & := (9 - ((8 \times -(7 - (((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) - 2))) - 1)) \\ 14939 & := (((9 + (8 \times ((7^6) - 5))) - 4) / - (3 \times -21)) \\ 14940 & := ((9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times (((5^4) - 3) \times -2) - 1)) \\ 14941 & := (9 + ((8 - 76) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 21)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14983 &:= (1 + (((2+3) \times -4) + (5^6)) - (7 \times 89))) & 14983 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (((7-6) - (5^4)) \times 3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
14984 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -((45 \times (6 \times 7)) - (8+9)))) & 14984 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 6) - 54) \times -32) + 1) \\
14985 &:= (12 - (3 - (((4^5) \times (6+7))/8) \times 9))) & 14985 &:= ((98 + (7+6)) \times (5 \times -(4 - (32-1)))) \\
14986 &:= ((1 + (234 \times ((5+67) - 8))) + 9) & 14986 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (((7-6) - (5^4)) \times 3)) - 2)) - 1) \\
14987 &:= (12 + (3 + (4 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) & 14987 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (((7-6) - (5^4)) \times 3)) - 2)) \times 1) \\
14988 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times -(3+4)) + (5^6)) - (7 \times 89))) & 14988 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (((7-6) - (5^4)) \times 3)) - 2)) + 1) \\
14989 &:= (((((1+2)^{3+4}) - 56) \times 7) - (8 \times -9)) & 14989 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (((7-6) \times 5^4) \times 3)) - 2)) \times -1) \\
14990 &:= ((-1 \times -(2+3)) \times -((45 \times -67) + (8+9))) & 14990 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times ((65+4) \times (32-1)))))) \\
14991 &:= ((1 - (((2+3)^4) - (5^6))) + (7 - (8+9))) & 14991 &:= (9 - (((8+7) \times (6 \times 5)) + 4) \times -(32+1)) \\
14992 &:= ((1 - ((2+3)^4)) - (((5^6) \times (7-8)) + 9)) & 14992 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((((7-6) \times 5^4) \times 3) - 2)) + 1)) \\
14993 &:= (1 \times (((2+3)^4) - ((5^6) - 7)) \times (8-9)) & 14993 &:= ((9-8) \times -(7 - (6 \times ((5^4) \times ((3+2) - 1)))))) \\
14994 &:= (1 + (((2+3)^4) - ((5^6) - 7)) \times (8-9)) & 14994 &:= ((9 - (8+7)) \times (((6 \times (5^4))/3) \times -2) + 1) \\
14995 &:= ((1 - (((2+3)^4) - (5^6))) - ((7+8) - 9)) & 14995 &:= (9 - (8 - (7 \times (((6 \times 5) + 4) \times (3 \times 21)))))) \\
14996 &:= (1 + (23 + (4 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) & 14996 &:= (((9-8)^7) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -((3+2) - 1) \\
14997 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (3+4)) + (5^6)) - (7 \times 89))) & 14997 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7-6) + (5^4)))) \times (3 \times -(2-1))) \\
14998 &:= (1 + (((2 - (3+4)) + (5^6)) - (7 \times 89))) & 14998 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -((7-6) - ((5^4) \times 3))) - (2+1))) \\
14999 &:= (1 \times (((2^3) + (4 \times 5)) \times (67 \times 8)) - 9) & 14999 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7-6) - ((5^4) \times 3)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
15000 &:= (((1+23) - (4^5)) \times ((6 \times (7-8)) - 9)) & 15000 &:= ((9 - (8 + (7+6))) \times ((5^4) \times -(3 - (2-1)))) \\
15001 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (((3+4)^5) + 67)) \times 8))/9) & 15001 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7-6)) + ((5^4) \times (3+21)))) \\
15002 &:= (1 - (((2+3) - 4) - ((5^6) - (7 \times 89)))) & 15002 &:= ((9-8) \times -((7^6) - ((54-3)^{2+1}))) \\
15003 &:= (((1+2)^3) - (((4^5) \times (6+7))/8) \times -9) & 15003 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7-6) - ((5^4) \times 3)))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
15004 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times (3-4)) - ((5^6) - (7 \times 89)))) & 15004 &:= (((9-8)^7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times ((3+2) - 1) \\
15005 &:= (1 - ((2 \times (3-4)) - ((5^6) - (7 \times 89)))) & 15005 &:= (9 + (((8-7) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -((3+2) - 1))) \\
15006 &:= (((1 + ((2+3)^4)) - ((5^6) + 7)) \times (8-9)) & 15006 &:= ((9 - (8+7)) \times (((6 \times (5^4))/3) \times -2) - 1) \\
15007 &:= (1 \times (((2+3)^4) - ((5^6) + 7)) \times (8-9)) & 15007 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (((7-6) \times 5^4) \times 3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
15008 &:= (1 + (((2+3)^4) - ((5^6) + 7)) \times (8-9)) & 15008 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (((7-6) \times 5^4) \times 3)) - (2-1))) \\
15009 &:= (1 \times -(((2+3)^4) - ((5^6) - ((7-8) \times 9)))) & 15009 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + ((6+5)^4)) + 321) \\
15010 &:= ((1 - ((2+3)^4)) - (((5^6) \times (7-8)) - 9)) & 15010 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (((7-6) \times 5^4) \times 3)) + 2)) - 1) \\
15011 &:= ((1 - (((2+3)^4) - (5^6))) - (7 - (8+9))) & 15011 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (((7-6) \times 5^4) \times 3)) + 2)) \times 1) \\
15012 &:= (((((1+2)^3) \times -4) - (5 \times -(6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 15012 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (((7-6) \times 5^4) \times 3)) + 2)) + 1) \\
15013 &:= (((((1+2)^3) \times -4) + (5^6)) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 15013 &:= ((9-8) \times ((7+6) + ((5^4) \times (3+21)))) \\
15014 &:= ((1-2) \times ((3 \times -4) - ((5^6) - (7 \times 89)))) & 15014 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7-6) + ((5^4) \times 3)))) - (2+1)) \\
15015 &:= (12 + ((3 + (((4^5) \times (6+7))/8) \times 9)) & 15015 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7-6) + ((5^4) \times 3)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
15016 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3+4)) - ((5^6) - (7 \times 89)))) & 15016 &:= (((9+8) - 7) + (6 + ((5^4) \times (3+21)))) \\
15017 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) + (4 \times 5)) \times -(67 \times 8)) - 9) & 15017 &:= (9 - (((87+6) \times 5) + 4) \times -(32 \times 1)) \\
15018 &:= (1 - (((2^3) + (4 \times 5)) \times -(67 \times 8)) - 9) & 15018 &:= ((9+8) + ((7-6) + ((5^4) \times (3+21)))) \\
15019 &:= (1 \times (23 \times -(4 - (((5 \times (6+7)) + 8) \times 9)))) & 15019 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7-6) + ((5^4) \times 3)))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
15020 &:= (1 + (23 \times -(4 - (((5 \times (6+7)) + 8) \times 9)))) & 15020 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7-6) + ((5^4) \times 3))) - (2+1))) \\
15021 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times -(6 \times (7+8))) + 9) & 15021 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7-6) - ((5^4) + 3)))) \times -(2+1)) \\
15022 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times -(6 \times (7+8))) + 9) & 15022 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 + (6 \times (5^4)))) - 3))/(2 \times -1) \\
15023 &:= ((2^3) - (((4^5) \times -(6+7)) + (8+9))) & 15023 &:= ((-9+8) - (((7-6) + (5^4)) \times -(3+21)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15024 &:= (1 \times -(((2+3)^4) - (5-6)) \times -(7+(8+9))) & 15024 &:= ((9+8) + (7+(6 \times (5^4) \times ((3+2)-1)))) \\
15025 &:= ((1 - ((2+3)^4) - (5^6)) + (7+(8+9))) & 15025 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7+(6 \times (5^4)))) + 3)) / (2 \times -1)) \\
15026 &:= (12 - ((3 \times -4) - ((5^6) - (7 \times 89)))) & 15026 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 76)) - ((5^4 \times 3/2) \times -1)) \\
15027 &:= (((((1+2)^{3+4}) - (5 \times 6)) \times 7) + (8 \times -9)) & 15027 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (((7-6) \times 5^4))) \times -(3 \times -(2-1))) \\
15028 &:= (((12^3) - ((4-5) \times 6)) \times -78) / -9 & 15028 &:= ((9+8) \times ((7+6) \times ((5+(4^3)) - (2-1)))) \\
15029 &:= ((1 - (23 \times 4)) - (5 \times -(6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15029 &:= (9 - (8 - ((7+(6 \times (5^4))) \times ((3+2)-1)))) \\
15030 &:= (((1 - (23 \times 4)) + (5^6)) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 15030 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (((7-6) + (5^4)) \times 3))) - (2+1)) \\
15031 &:= ((1+2) - (((3^4) \times (5+6)) - 7) \times -(8+9)) & 15031 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (7+(6 \times (5^4)))))) - 3) / -(2 \times -1)) \\
15032 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times 3)^4) - (5^6)) - (78 \times -9)) & 15032 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(((7-6) + (5^4)) \times 3)) + (2-1))) \\
15033 &:= (((1+2)^3) + ((4+(5^6)) - (7 \times 89))) & 15033 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(7+(65 \times (4-(32+1)))))) \\
15034 &:= (1 \times (((2^3) \times 4) + ((5^6) - (7 \times 89))) & 15034 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7+(6 \times (5^4)))) + 3)) / -(2 \times -1)) \\
15035 &:= (1 + (((2^3) \times 4) + ((5^6) - (7 \times 89))) & 15035 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (((7-6) + (5^4)) \times 3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
15036 &:= ((1 - ((2+34) \times 5)) \times -(67+(8+9))) & 15036 &:= ((9 - (8+7)) \times -(6 + ((5^4) \times ((3+2)-1)))) \\
15037 &:= (1 \times -((2+(3^4)) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15037 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (7+(6 \times (5^4)))) / (3 - (2-1)))) \\
15038 &:= (1 \times -((2+(3^4)) - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15038 &:= (((98-7) - (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2)) \times -1) \\
15039 &:= (1 - ((2+(3^4)) - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15039 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times -((4 \times -3) + 21)) \\
15040 &:= ((1-2) \times ((3^4) - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15040 &:= (((9+8) - 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times ((3+2)-1) \\
15041 &:= ((12^3) - (((4^5) \times -(6+7)) + (8-9)) & 15041 &:= ((9+8) - (((7-6) + (5^4)) \times -(3+21))) \\
15042 &:= (((1+2) - (3^4)) - (5 \times -(6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15042 &:= (((9 + (8 \times ((7-6) + (5^4)))) - 3) \times (2+1)) \\
15043 &:= (((1+2) - ((3^4) - (5^6))) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 15043 &:= (9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) - ((5^4) \times (3+21)))) \\
15044 &:= (1 + (2 + (((34 \times 5) + (6-7)) \times 89))) & 15044 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 \times (6-543))) / -2) - 1)) \\
15045 &:= ((1+2) \times -(((3+45) \times 6) + 7) \times -(8+9)) & 15045 &:= ((9+8) - ((7+(6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3+2)-1)) \\
15046 &:= (1 \times -2 - (((3-4) + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9))) & 15046 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 \times (6-543))) / -2) + 1)) \\
15047 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) + ((5^6) + 7) \times 8)) / -9 & 15047 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times ((43-2) \times -1)) \\
15048 &:= ((1 - ((2+3)^4) - (5^6)) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & 15048 &:= (9 - (((8-76) + (5^4)) \times -(3^2+1))) \\
15049 &:= ((1 + ((2^3) \times (45 \times (6 \times 7)))) + (8 \times -9)) & 15049 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (43 - (2+1)))) \\
15050 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3-4) + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9))) & 15050 &:= ((9-87) + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2) - 1) \\
15051 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3-4) + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9))) & 15051 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7-6) + (5^4)))) \times -(3 \times -(2-1))) \\
15052 &:= (12 - ((3^4) - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15052 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 - (6 \times ((5^4) + 3)))) / -2) - 1)) \\
15053 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times -34) + (5^6)) - (7 \times (8 \times 9))) & 15053 &:= (9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times ((5^4) + 3)))) / (2 \times 1))) \\
15054 &:= (((1+2) - (3^4)) \times ((5 \times -(6 \times 7)) + (8+9))) & 15054 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (((7-6) + (5^4)) \times 3))) + 21) \\
15055 &:= (1 \times -(((2-3) + (45 \times 6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9) & 15055 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times -(6 + (5 \times (432-1)))) \\
15056 &:= (1 - (((2-3) + (45 \times 6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9) & 15056 &:= ((9 - (8-7)) \times (6 + (((5^4) \times 3) + (2-1)))) \\
15057 &:= ((12^3) - (((4^5) \times -(6+7)) - (8+9)) & 15057 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((76 \times 5) - 4) \times (3+2)) + 1)) \\
15058 &:= (((12^3) / -4) + (5^6)) + ((7+8) \times -9) & 15058 &:= (9 + (87 + (((6+5)^4) + 321))) \\
15059 &:= (1 \times (2 - (((3+4) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) & 15059 &:= ((9+8) - ((7 \times -6) - ((5^4) \times (3+21)))) \\
15060 &:= (1 + (2 - (((3+4) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) & 15060 &:= ((9 - (8 + (7+6))) \times (((5^4) + 3) \times -2) + 1) \\
15061 &:= (1 \times -23 + ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) & 15061 &:= (((9+8) + (7 \times (6 - (5 \times 432)))) \times -1) \\
15062 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + ((3^4) \times (5+6))) - 7) \times -(8+9)) & 15062 &:= ((9+8) \times -((7 \times -65) - (432-1))) \\
15063 &:= (1 - (((2 + ((3^4) \times (5+6))) - 7) \times -(8+9)) & 15063 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 - (((6 + (5^4)) \times 3) - 2)))) \times -1) \\
15064 &:= (1 + (((2 \times 3) - (45 \times (6 \times 7))) \times -8) - 9) & 15064 &:= ((9 - (8-7)) \times -(((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) / -2) + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15065 &:= (1 + ((2^3) \times ((4 \times (5 + (6 \times 78))) - 9))) & 15065 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times ((65 \times 4) + (3^2))) - 1))) \\
15066 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) \times -(6 + (7 \times 8))) / -9 & 15066 &:= ((9 - 87) - ((6 + (5^4)) \times -(3 + 21))) \\
15067 &:= (((-12 \times -(3 \times 4)) + (5^6)) + (78 \times -9)) & 15067 &:= (98 + (7 + (((6 + 5)^4) + 321))) \\
15068 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((34 \times (56 - 7)) + 8) \times 9))) & 15068 &:= (-9 - (8 + (7 \times (6 - ((5 \times 432) + 1)))))) \\
15069 &:= (12 + (((3 + 4) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times -9)) & 15069 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -((3 + 2) - 1))) \\
15070 &:= ((1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - (5^6))) + (78 - 9)) & 15070 &:= (98 - (76 \times -(5 + ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))))) \\
15071 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) - (45 \times (6 \times 7))) \times -8) - 9)) & 15071 &:= (9 - (((8 \times -7) - 6) - ((5^4) \times (3 + 21)))) \\
15072 &:= (1 + (((2 + 3) - (45 \times (6 \times 7))) \times -8) - 9)) & 15072 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 + (5^4)) - (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
15073 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - 3) + (45 \times 6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9)) & 15073 &:= ((9 + ((87 + 6) \times (54 \times 3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
15074 &:= (((12^3) / -4) + (5^6)) + (7 \times -(8 + 9)) & 15074 &:= (98 + (((7 - 6) - (5^4)) \times -(3 + 21))) \\
15075 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 \times -((4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9))) & 15075 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) + 4)) \times (3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
15076 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3) \times -(45 \times 67)) + (8 - 9))) & 15076 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3)))) - 21) \\
15077 &:= (((1 + ((2 + 3) \times (45 \times 67))) - 8) + 9) & 15077 &:= ((9 + ((87 + 6) \times (54 \times 3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
15078 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -3) - ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))) & 15078 &:= ((9 + ((87 + 6) \times (54 \times 3))) + (2 + 1)) \\
15079 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -3) - ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))) & 15079 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})) \\
15080 &:= ((1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - (5^6))) + (7 + (8 \times 9))) & 15080 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7 - ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3) - 2))) - 1) \\
15081 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) \times -((45 \times 67) - (8 - 9)))) & 15081 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2)) - 1) \\
15082 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - (5 \times 6)) \times 7) - 8) - 9) & 15082 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2) \times -1) \\
15083 &:= ((1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - (5^6))) - (7 - 89)) & 15083 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -7) + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
15084 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 \times -(4 \times (5 + (6 \times (78 - 9)))))) & 15084 &:= ((9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times (((5^4) + 3) \times -2) - 1) \\
15085 &:= ((1 - 2) - (34 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 15085 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((76 \times 5) - 4))) \times -((3 + 2) \times -1)) \\
15086 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) + ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times -9)) & 15086 &:= (9 - (8 + (7 \times (6 - ((5 \times 432) + 1)))))) \\
15087 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 - (45 \times (6 \times 7))) \times -8) - 9)) & 15087 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times 6) + ((5^4) + 3) \times -21)) \\
15088 &:= (((1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times (5 - ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9))) & 15088 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})) \\
15089 &:= ((1 + 2) - (34 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 15089 &:= (9 - (((87 \times (65 \times 4)) / 3) \times -2) \times 1)) \\
15090 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -3) + ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))) & 15090 &:= (9 - (((87 \times (65 \times 4)) / 3) \times -2) - 1) \\
15091 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -3) + ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))) & 15091 &:= (98 - (7 - (6 \times ((5^4) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))))) \\
15092 &:= (1 - (2 + ((3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 78)))) \times 9))) & 15092 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 + 6) + ((5^4) \times 3))) + 21)) \\
15093 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -((4 - 5) - ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) & 15093 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) - 4) \times -3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
15094 &:= ((1 - 23) - (4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 15094 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3)))) - (2 + 1)) \\
15095 &:= (1 \times -((2 - (3 + 4)) \times -(5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 15095 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
15096 &:= (1 - ((2 - (3 + 4)) \times -(5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 15096 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 + (5^4)) - (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
15097 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times -(3 \times 4)) + (5^6)) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15097 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -7) + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 21)))) \\
15098 &:= (((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + (5^6)) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 15098 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3))) - 2)) - 1) \\
15099 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - (5 \times 6)) \times -7) \times (8 - 9)) & 15099 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3))) - 2)) \times 1) \\
15100 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) \times -4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 15100 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3))) - 2)) + 1) \\
15101 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) \times -4) + (5^6)) - (7 \times (8 \times 9))) & 15101 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6 \times -((54 - 3)^2)) + 1)) \\
15102 &:= (1 + (((2 + 3) \times -4) + (5^6)) - (7 \times (8 \times 9))) & 15102 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times (3 - 21)) \\
15103 &:= ((1 - 23) + ((4 + (5^6)) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15103 &:= (((-9 \times -87) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 321) \\
15104 &:= (((1 - 2) - ((3 - (45 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8)) + 9) & 15104 &:= (9 + (8 - ((7 - (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times 321))) \\
15105 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -(((4^5) \times (6 - 7)) + (8 + 9))) & 15105 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2)) \times -1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15106 &:= (((12^3) + (4 + (5 + 6))) \times -78) / -9 & 15106 &:= ((98 - 7) \times -(((6 + (54 \times 3)) - 2) \times -1)) \\
15107 &:= ((1 - 2) + ((3 \times -4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15107 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) - 4) - (3^2)) \times 1) \\
15108 &:= ((1 - 2) + (((3 \times -4) + (5^6)) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15108 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) + ((6 + 5) \times (4^3))) \times -21)) \\
15109 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 \times -4) + (5^6)) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15109 &:= (9 - ((8 \times (7 + (6 \times ((5^4) + 3)))) / - (2 \times 1))) \\
15110 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times 3) + (4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15110 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 + 6) + ((5^4) \times 3))) + (2 + 1))) \\
15111 &:= (1 - ((2 \times 3) + (4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15111 &:= (9 + (((87 \times -6) + (5^{4 \times 3/2})) - 1)) \\
15112 &:= ((1 + 2) + (((3 \times -4) + (5^6)) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15112 &:= ((9 - (87 \times 6)) - ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) \times -1)) \\
15113 &:= (((1 - (2 - 3)) + (45 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) & 15113 &:= ((9 - (87 \times 6)) + ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) + 1)) \\
15114 &:= (((12^3) / -4) + ((5^6) - 7)) + (8 \times -9) & 15114 &:= (9 + ((8 \times ((7 + 6) + ((5^4) \times 3))) + (2 - 1))) \\
15115 &:= (1 \times ((2 - (3 + 4)) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15115 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 + 6) + ((5^4) \times 3))) - (2 \times 1))) \\
15116 &:= (1 + ((2 - (3 + 4)) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15116 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 + 6) + ((5^4) \times 3))) - (2 + 1))) \\
15117 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 + 4) - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15117 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) - 4)) + (32 + 1)) \\
15118 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) - (4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15118 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7 - ((6 + (5^4) \times 3))) + 21)) \\
15119 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) \times -(45 \times (6 \times 7))) - (8 - 9))) & 15119 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times -(6 \times (5 \times (4 \times (3 - 21))))) \\
15120 &:= ((1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - (5^6))) - (7 \times -(8 + 9))) & 15120 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times (6 + (((5^4) + 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
15121 &:= (12 + (((3 \times -4) + (5^6)) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15121 &:= ((9 - 8) \times - (7 - (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2) - 1)) \\
15122 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 - 4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15122 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 - (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2)) \times -1)) \\
15123 &:= (12 - (((3 - 4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times -9) & 15123 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 - (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2)) \times -1)) \\
15124 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 - 4) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15124 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
15125 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 - 4) - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15125 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times -(6 + (5 \times (432 + 1))))) \\
15126 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) + (4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15126 &:= (98 - ((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
15127 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) + ((4 + (5^6)) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15127 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + 6) \times -((5 \times -432) - 1) \\
15128 &:= (((12^3) / -4) + ((5^6) + 7)) + (8 \times -9) & 15128 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((((7 + 6) - 54) \times -3)^2) - 1)) \\
15129 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 - ((45 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9))) & 15129 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((((7 + 6) - 54) \times -3)^2) \times -1) \\
15130 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15130 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times 4))) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\
15131 &:= (1 \times -((2 - (3 \times 4)) - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15131 &:= (9 - (8 - (((((7 + 6) - 54) \times -3)^2) + 1))) \\
15132 &:= (1 - ((2 - (3 \times 4)) - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15132 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 - ((5 + 4)^3)))) \times - (2 + 1)) \\
15133 &:= (12 - ((3 - 4) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15133 &:= (9 + ((876 - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15134 &:= (12 - ((3 - 4) - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15134 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 \times -54) + (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
15135 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 \times -4) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15135 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
15136 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 \times -4) - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15136 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2)) \times -1)) \\
15137 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) \times -(45 \times (6 \times 7))) - (8 + 9))) & 15137 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2)) \times -1)) \\
15138 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 + (45 \times (6 \times 7))) \times -8) + 9) & 15138 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
15139 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8))) / 9 & 15139 &:= (9 - ((8 - 7) \times -((((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
15140 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3) \times -4) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15140 &:= (9 + ((8 - 7) + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
15141 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) \times -4) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15141 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 76) - 5) \times (4^3))) \times - (2 + 1)) \\
15142 &:= (1 + (((2^3) - ((4^5) - 6)) \times - (7 + 8)) - 9) & 15142 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) + 43) - 21) \\
15143 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15143 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times -(6 - ((5 \times 432) - 1)))) \\
15144 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (4 - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15144 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -((6 + (5^4)) \times - (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
15145 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) - (5 \times -(6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15145 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((((7 + 6) - 54) \times -3)^2) - 1)) \\
15146 &:= (((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + (5^6)) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 15146 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((((7 + 6) - 54) \times -3)^2) \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15147 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4) - 5)) \times -((6 \times -(7 + 8)) - 9)) & 15147 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((((7 + 6) - 54) \times -3)^2) + 1)) \\
15148 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) - ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))) & 15148 &:= (9 + (((8 - 765) \times -(4 \times (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\
15149 &:= (1 - ((2^3) - ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))) & 15149 &:= (9 - ((8 - 765) \times -(4 - (3 + 21)))) \\
15150 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -3) + ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))) & 15150 &:= (9 + (((8 - 765) \times -(4 \times (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\
15151 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -3) + ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))) & 15151 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 21)))) \\
15152 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + ((4 + (5^6)) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15152 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6 + (5^4)) \times -3) - (2 - 1))) \\
15153 &:= ((1 - 2) + (34 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15153 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2)) \times -1)) \\
15154 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(34 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15154 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
15155 &:= (-12 - (((34 \times 56) - 7) \times -8) + 9) & 15155 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (76 \times 5))) \times -(4 + (3/(2 + 1)))) \\
15156 &:= (((12^3) - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times -((7 - 8) \times 9)) & 15156 &:= (9 + (((8 + (7 \times 65)) - 4) \times (32 + 1))) \\
15157 &:= ((1 + 2) + (34 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15157 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7654 - 3)) \times 2) - 1) \\
15158 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) - ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times -9)) & 15158 &:= (((98 + (7 + 6)) - 5) \times (((4 \times 3)^2) - 1)) \\
15159 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 3) + (45 \times (6 \times 7))) \times -8) + 9) & 15159 &:= ((9 + (8 + 76)) \times -((54 \times -3) - (2 - 1))) \\
15160 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - (5 + 6)) \times 7) + (8 \times -9)) & 15160 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)))) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
15161 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) + ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))) & 15161 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(6 + (5 \times 432))) + 1)) \\
15162 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 + ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))) & 15162 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 - (6 \times 54)))) \times (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
15163 &:= (1 + ((2 - (3 \times 45)) \times -((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))) & 15163 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times (6 + (5 \times 432)))) \times -1)) \\
15164 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3) \times -(45 \times 67)) - 89)) & 15164 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 - (((6 \times 5)^{(4-3) \times 2}) - 1))) \\
15165 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 \times -(4 - ((5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9)))) & 15165 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) - 4) \times -(3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
15166 &:= (12 + (34 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15166 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) + 4) \times -(3^2) - 1)) \\
15167 &:= (12 + ((34 + (5^6)) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15167 &:= (((-987 \times -6) + (5 \times (43^2))) \times 1) \\
15168 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((34 + (5 \times 6)) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 15168 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -((6 + ((5^4) + (3 - 2))) \times -1)) \\
15169 &:= (((12^3)/ -4) + ((5^6) - 7)) - (8 + 9) & 15169 &:= ((9 - (8 - 76)) \times (5 + ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
15170 &:= (1 + (((2 - ((34 \times 56) - 7)) \times -8) + 9)) & 15170 &:= (9 - (8 - (7 \times (6 + ((5 \times 432) + 1)))) \\
15171 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - (5 \times 6)) \times 7) - (8 \times -9)) & 15171 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times (76 \times 5)) - 4) \times (3 + 2))) \times -1) \\
15172 &:= (1 - ((23 \times -(4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8)))) + 9)) & 15172 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times ((6 + (5 \times 432)) - 1)))) \\
15173 &:= (-12 - (((34 \times 56) - 7) \times -8) - 9) & 15173 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 - ((6 - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times 21))) \\
15174 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 3) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 78)))) \times -9)) & 15174 &:= (9 \times ((8 \times 7) + (((6 \times 543)/2) + 1))) \\
15175 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times -(((5 + 6) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9)) & 15175 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + 4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times -1)) \\
15176 &:= (1 - (((2^3) \times -((45 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) + 9)) & 15176 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6^5)/4)) \times ((3^2) - 1)) \\
15177 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 3) + (45 \times (6 \times 7))) \times -8) - 9) & 15177 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 + ((6 - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times 21))) \\
15178 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3) + (45 \times (6 \times 7))) \times -8) - 9) & 15178 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(((7 \times 6) + 5) + (43^2))) - 1)) \\
15179 &:= (1 \times (23 + ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))) & 15179 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 + (5 \times 432)))) \times -1)) \\
15180 &:= (1 + (23 + ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))) & 15180 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -((5 \times -4) - (3 + 21))) \\
15181 &:= (1 \times -((23 - 4) \times -((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 15181 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((65 \times -4) - (3 \times 21))) \\
15182 &:= (1 - ((23 - 4) \times -((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 15182 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) - (((4^3) - 2) \times -1)) \\
15183 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times -(4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) & 15183 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times ((6 - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times -21)) \\
15184 &:= (((12^3)/ -4) - ((5^6) \times (7 - 8)) + 9) & 15184 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + ((6 - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times -21)) \\
15185 &:= (((12^3)/ -4) + ((5^6) - 7)) + (8 - 9) & 15185 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 - 6) + (((5^4) \times 3) + 21)))) \\
15186 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 + 4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times -9)) & 15186 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 - ((5 + 4)^3)))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
15187 &:= ((1 - (((2 + 3) - ((4^5) - 6)) \times (7 + 8))) - 9) & 15187 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) + 4) - (3 \times -21)) \\
15188 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - (5 \times 6)) \times 7) + 89) & 15188 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -((3 + 2) - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15189 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -34) - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 15189 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 - 65)) + 4) \times -(32 + 1))) \\
15190 &:= (1 \times - (2 + (((3 - 4) - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15190 &:= (((9 - 8) - (76 \times (5 \times 4))) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
15191 &:= (1 - (2 + (((3 - 4) - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15191 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 - ((6 - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times 21))) \\
15192 &:= ((1 - (((2^{3+4}) \times 5) - 6)) \times -(7 + (8 + 9))) & 15192 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times (6 + ((5^4) + (3 - (2 - 1)))))) \\
15193 &:= ((1 + ((2^3) \times (45 \times (6 \times 7)))) - (8 \times -9)) & 15193 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 + ((6 - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times 21))) \\
15194 &:= (1 \times (2 - (((3 - 4) - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15194 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2 \times 1))) \\
15195 &:= (1 + (2 - (((3 - 4) - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15195 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2 + 1))) \\
15196 &:= (((-1 + (234 \times 5)) \times (6 + 7)) + 8) - 9 & 15196 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (7 \times -(6 + (5 \times (432 + 1)))))) \\
15197 &:= ((1 - (234 \times 5)) \times -((6 + 7) \times -(8 - 9))) & 15197 &:= ((98 - 7) \times ((6 + (54 \times 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
15198 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(34 \times -(5 + (6 \times (7 + (8 + 9)))))) & 15198 &:= (9 + (((((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
15199 &:= (((12^3) / -4) + ((5^6) + 7)) + (8 - 9) & 15199 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2 \times 1)) \\
15200 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^4)) - (5 \times -(6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 15200 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2) - 1) \\
15201 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3^4) + (5^6))) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 15201 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times ((4 \times -3) + 21)) \\
15202 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((3^4) + ((5^6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 15202 &:= ((98 - (765 \times (4 \times (3 + 2)))) \times -1) \\
15203 &:= (((12^3) / -4) + ((5^6) - 7)) + (8 + 9) & 15203 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times -((6 + 5) - (4^{3+2}))) - 1)) \\
15204 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) - ((4^5) - 6)) \times -(7 + 8)) + 9) & 15204 &:= (9 + ((8 + 7) \times -((6 + 5) - (4^{3+2} \times 1)))) \\
15205 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3^4) + ((5^6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 15205 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times -((6 + 5) - (4^{3+2}))) + 1)) \\
15206 &:= (((-1 - (234 \times 5)) \times -(6 + 7)) - 8) - 9 & 15206 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 + ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3))) + (2 + 1))) \\
15207 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 + 5)) + ((6 \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9)) & 15207 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
15208 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -((4 \times (5 + (6 \times 78))) + 9))) & 15208 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 \times (65 + 4))) \times -32) - 1)) \\
15209 &:= ((1 - (2 \times 34)) \times ((5 \times -(6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9))) & 15209 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (4 + (3 \times 21))) \\
15210 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 \times -((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) & 15210 &:= ((9 - 87) \times (65 \times -((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
15211 &:= (1 \times -((234 \times -(5 \times (6 + 7))) + (8 - 9))) & 15211 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3)))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
15212 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -4) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 15212 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 + ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3))) - (2 + 1))) \\
15213 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -4) - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 15213 &:= (9 - (((8 + 76) \times 543) / - (2 + 1))) \\
15214 &:= (1 \times - (2 + (((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times (7 + 8)) + 9))) & 15214 &:= (((98 + 7) - ((6^5) - (4^3))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
15215 &:= (1 - (2 + (((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times (7 + 8)) + 9))) & 15215 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((7 \times ((6 - 5) \times (4 \times 32))) - 1)) \\
15216 &:= (((12^3) + 456) \times 7) + (8 \times -9) & 15216 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)))))) - 1) \\
15217 &:= (((12^3) / -4) + ((5^6) + (7 + 8))) + 9 & 15217 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)))) \times 1) \\
15218 &:= (1 \times (2 - (((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times (7 + 8)) + 9))) & 15218 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7 - (6 \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)))) + 1)) \\
15219 &:= (1 + (2 - (((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times (7 + 8)) + 9))) & 15219 &:= (98 - (7 - (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2) - 1)) \\
15220 &:= (1 \times -((23 + 4) \times -567) + 89) & 15220 &:= (98 + ((7 - (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2)) \times -1)) \\
15221 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((34 \times 5) - (6 - 7)) \times 89))) & 15221 &:= (98 - (7 - (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
15222 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3^4) + 5) \times -((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9)))) & 15222 &:= (9 - (((87 + 6) \times 5) - 4) \times -(32 + 1)) \\
15223 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) \times -((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) + 9)) & 15223 &:= ((987 - (6^{5+4-3})) / - (2 + 1)) \\
15224 &:= (1 - (((2^3) \times -((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) + 9)) & 15224 &:= ((9 + 87) + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2) - 1) \\
15225 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 + 5)) + ((6 \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9)) & 15225 &:= ((9 + 87) - (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2) \times -1) \\
15226 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times -((3 \times 45678) / -9)) & 15226 &:= ((9 + 87) + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2) + 1) \\
15227 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - (5 - 6)) \times 7) - 89) & 15227 &:= (98 - (((7 + 6) - 54) \times -3)^2 \times -1) \\
15228 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times 4) - (5 \times -(6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15228 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times -6) + (((5 + 4)^3) \times 21))) \\
15229 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times 4) + (5^6) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9)) & 15229 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + 4) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15230 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3 \times 4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))) \\
15231 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3 \times 4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))) \\
15232 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - (5 + 6)) \times -7) \times (8 - 9)) \\
15233 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - (5 + 6)) \times 7) - (8 - 9)) \\
15234 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (3 \times ((4^5) - (678 \times 9)))) \\
15235 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3^{4-5+6}) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\
15236 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3^{4-5+6}) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\
15237 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 \times -((4^5) - (678 \times 9)))) \\
15238 &:= (1 \times -(23 - (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 + 8)) - 9)) \\
15239 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3^{4-5+6}) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\
15240 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3^{4-5+6}) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\
15241 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) \times -((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
15242 &:= (1 - (((2^3) \times -((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
15243 &:= (1 + (2 \times -3 - (((4^5) \times 67) + 8)/9)) \\
15244 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - (5 - 6)) \times 7) + (8 \times -9)) \\
15245 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 + ((4^5) \times 67)) - 8)))/ -9) \\
15246 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 - 4))^5)) \times -((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9)) \\
15247 &:= (1 \times ((2 - (3^4)) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9)))) \\
15248 &:= (1 + ((2 - (3^4)) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9)))) \\
15249 &:= ((1 + (2^{3+4})) - (5 \times -6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
15250 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) - 6) \times 7) - 8) - 9 \\
15251 &:= (1 \times (2 - ((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times (78 - 9)))) \\
15252 &:= (12 \times -(((3 \times (45 + 6)) + 7) \times -8) + 9) \\
15253 &:= (1 \times -(2 + (3 \times (45 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9))))))) \\
15254 &:= (1 - (2 + (3 \times (45 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9))))))) \\
15255 &:= ((12 + 3) \times ((4 + 5) \times -6 - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
15256 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) \times ((45 \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 + 9)))) \\
15257 &:= ((1 - 23) - (((4^5) - 6) \times -7 + 8) - 9) \\
15258 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -3 - (((4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + 8) \times 9))) \\
15259 &:= (1 + (2 \times -3 - (((4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + 8) \times 9))) \\
15260 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -3 - ((456 - 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
15261 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 - (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 + 8)) - 9)) \\
15262 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((34 \times 5) + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
15263 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) - (((4^5) - 6) \times -7 + 8) + 9) \\
15264 &:= ((12^3) - (4 \times -((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
15265 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (((34 \times 5) + (6 \times 7)) \times -8 \times 9)) \\
15266 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) - 6) \times 7) + (8 - 9)) \\
15267 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) - 6) \times -7) \times (8 - 9)) \\
15268 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) - 6) \times 7) - 8) + 9 \\
15269 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) + (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 + 8)) - 9)) \\
15270 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times 3) - (4^5)) \times -6 - ((7 - 8) \times 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15230 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3)))) + 21) \\
15231 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (((7654 - 3) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15232 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((7 \times -(6 - 5)) + (43 \times 21))) \\
15233 &:= (98 + ((7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
15234 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times (6 - ((5 + 4)^3)))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
15235 &:= (98 + (7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
15236 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times (7 + (6^5)))/ -4) + 321)) \\
15237 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) + 4)) \times -3 \times -(2 + 1)) \\
15238 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times -7) - 6) + (((5 + 4)^3) \times 21))) \\
15239 &:= (-9 + (8 \times -7 - ((6^5)/4) - (32 - 1))) \\
15240 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times (6 + ((5^4) + ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
15241 &:= ((9 + ((87 - ((6^5) - (4^3))) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
15242 &:= (((98 - 7) - ((6^5) - (4^3))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
15243 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (76 \times 5)) \times (43 - 2))) \times -1) \\
15244 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 - 6)) \times -5 \times 43) - 21) \\
15245 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 \times 5))) \times (4 + (3/(2 + 1)))) \\
15246 &:= (((9 + 8) - (76 \times 5)) \times -43 - (2 - 1)) \\
15247 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 7) \times -((65 + ((4^3) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15248 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7^6) - (((5 \times (4^3))^2) + 1))) \\
15249 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7^6) - ((5 \times (4^3))^2)) \times -1)) \\
15250 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7^6) - ((5 \times (4^3))^2)) \times -1)) \\
15251 &:= (9 - (8 - ((7^6) - (((5 \times (4^3))^2) - 1)))) \\
15252 &:= ((9 + (8 + 76)) \times -54 \times -3 - (2 \times 1)) \\
15253 &:= (98 - (7 \times -((6 + (5 \times 432)) - 1))) \\
15254 &:= (((9 + (87 \times 6)) - 5) \times -4 - (32 + 1)) \\
15255 &:= ((987 + (6 \times 5)) \times -4 \times -3 - (2 + 1)) \\
15256 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -((6 \times -((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)) + 1)) \\
15257 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((7 - 65) - ((43^2) - 1)))) \\
15258 &:= (9 + (((87 - ((6^5) - (4^3))) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15259 &:= ((9 - ((87 - ((6^5) - (4^3))) \times 2)) \times 1) \\
15260 &:= ((98 - ((7 \times 6) \times ((5 + 4)^3)))/(2 \times -1)) \\
15261 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (76 \times 5)) \times (43 - 2))) \times 1) \\
15262 &:= (9 + (((8 - (76 \times 5)) \times -43 - 2) + 1)) \\
15263 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) - ((6 + (5^4)) \times -3 + 21)) \\
15264 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -6 \times -((5 \times (4^3)) - (2 \times 1))) \\
15265 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7^6)) - (((5 \times (4^3))^2) + 1)) \\
15266 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7^6) - ((5 \times (4^3))^2)) \times -1)) \\
15267 &:= (9 + ((8 + (7^6)) - (((5 \times (4^3))^2) - 1))) \\
15268 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6 + (((5 + 4)^3) \times 21))) \\
15269 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (765 \times 4)) \times (3 + 2))) \times 1) \\
15270 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 \times 54)))) \times -3 \times -(2 \times 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15312 &:= ((12 - (3^{4+5})) - (((6^7)/ - 8) + 9)) & 15312 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times (6 + ((5^4) + ((3 \times 2) + 1)))) \\
15313 &:= (((1 - 234) + (5^6)) - 7) + (8 \times -9)) & 15313 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) - (6 - (((5 + 4)^3) \times 21))) \\
15314 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + (5 + 6)) \times 7) + (8 \times -9)) & 15314 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7 - ((6 + 54) \times 32))) + 1)) \\
15315 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - (5 - 6)) \times 7) + 8) - 9) & 15315 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)))))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
15316 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - (5 - 6)) \times -7) \times (8 - 9)) & 15316 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 \times -(((6 \times ((5 + 4)^3))/2) + 1))) \\
15317 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - (5 - 6)) \times 7) - (8 - 9)) & 15317 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 \times -(((6 \times ((5 + 4)^3))/2) + 1))) \\
15318 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 - (4^5)) \times -(6 - ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) & 15318 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\
15319 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + (5 - 6)) \times 7) + (8 + 9)) & 15319 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times 3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
15320 &:= (1 \times (2 - ((3^{4+5}) - (((6^7)/8) + 9)))) & 15320 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times ((5 + 4)^3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
15321 &:= (1 + (2 - ((3^{4+5}) - (((6^7)/8) + 9)))) & 15321 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times ((5 + 4)^3))) + (2 + 1)) \\
15322 &:= (1 - (((2 + (34 \times (5 \times 6))) \times -(7 + 8)) + 9)) & 15322 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times 3)) + 2)) - 1) \\
15323 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) + (((4^5) + 678) \times 9))) & 15323 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times 3)) + 2)) \times 1) \\
15324 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 - (((4^5) \times ((6 + 7) - 8)) - 9))) & 15324 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times 3)) + 2)) + 1) \\
15325 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) \times -(4 - ((5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) & 15325 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) + (6 + (((5 + 4)^3) \times 21))) \\
15326 &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times -(4 - ((5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) & 15326 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7654) - 3) \times -2) + 1) \\
15327 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times -(7 + 8)) - 9) & 15327 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 \times 6) \times ((5 + 4)^3))/ - 2) - 1) \\
15328 &:= (((12^3)/ - 4) + (5^6)) - ((7 + 8) \times -9) & 15328 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7654) - 3) \times -2) - 1) \\
15329 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - (5^6))) + ((7 + 8) \times -9)) & 15329 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 + 6) \times 5) + ((43^2) + 1)))) \\
15330 &:= (((1 - (2 - 3)) - (4^5)) \times ((6 \times (7 - 8)) - 9)) & 15330 &:= (((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) + (5^4)))) - 3) \times (2 + 1)) \\
15331 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times ((6 + 7) - 8)) - 9)))) & 15331 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 - 6) + ((5 + 4)^3)) \times -21)) \\
15332 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times ((6 + 7) - 8)) - 9)))) & 15332 &:= (9 + (8 + (((7654 + 3) \times 2) + 1))) \\
15333 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - (5 - 6)) \times 7) + 8) + 9) & 15333 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 \times -(((6 \times ((5 + 4)^3))/2) + 1))) \\
15334 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) + 6) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) & 15334 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((7 \times ((6 - 5) + (4 \times 32))) - 1)) \\
15335 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3^4) + 56) \times (7 \times 8))) + 9)) & 15335 &:= (((-98 \times -7) + ((6 + 5)^4)) + ((3^2) - 1)) \\
15336 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 \times -(((4^5) \times ((6 + 7) - 8)) - 9))) & 15336 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times (6 + ((5^4) + ((3^2) - 1)))) \\
15337 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3) + (4^5)) - 6) \times (7 + 8)) - 9) & 15337 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(7 - (((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)) + (2 + 1)))))) \\
15338 &:= (1 - (23 - ((4^5) \times (6 - ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) & 15338 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7654 + 3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15339 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) - 6) \times 7) - (8 \times -9)) & 15339 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) + (5^4)))) \times -(3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
15340 &:= (1 \times ((2 + ((34 + 5) \times 6)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 15340 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7654 + 3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15341 &:= (1 + ((2 + ((34 + 5) \times 6)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 15341 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times -(4 - (32 + 1))) \\
15342 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times -((6 + 7) - 8)) + 9)) & 15342 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + ((5^4) \times 3)))) - (2 + 1)) \\
15343 &:= (1 - (((234 - 5) \times -67) - (8 - 9))) & 15343 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + ((5^4) \times 3)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
15344 &:= (1 \times -(((234 - 5) \times -67) + (8 - 9))) & 15344 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6 \times 5) \times -(4^3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
15345 &:= ((1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) - ((5 \times (6^7))/ - (8 \times 9))) & 15345 &:= (((98 + 7) - 6) \times -(5 \times -(4 + (3^{2+1})))) \\
15346 &:= (-1 + (2 + (((3 \times (4 + 567)) - 8) \times 9))) & 15346 &:= ((98 + (7^6)) - (((5 \times (4^3))^2) + 1)) \\
15347 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 + ((4^5) + 678)) \times 9))) & 15347 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + ((5^4) \times 3)))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
15348 &:= (12 \times -(((34 - (5 + 6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9)) & 15348 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + ((5^4) \times 3)))) + (2 + 1)) \\
15349 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3 \times 45) - 6) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 15349 &:= (9 - ((8 + (765 \times 4)) \times -(3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
15350 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) + 6) \times 7) + (8 - 9)) & 15350 &:= (((98 + 7) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -(3 - (2 - 1))) \\
15351 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) + 6) \times -7) \times (8 - 9)) & 15351 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 + (4 \times 3)) \times -21)) \\
15352 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) - ((4^5) \times (6 - ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) & 15352 &:= (((9 + 87) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -(3 - (2 - 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15353 &:= (1 - ((2^3) - ((4^5) \times (6 - ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
15354 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) \times ((6 + 7) - 8)))) - 9) \\
15355 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) - ((4^5) \times (6 - ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
15356 &:= ((1 - 2) - (3 - ((4^5) \times (6 - ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
15357 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (3 - ((4^5) \times (6 - ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
15358 &:= (1 \times - (2 + (3 \times ((4^5) \times (67 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
15359 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times -((6 + 7) - 8)) + 9)) \\
15360 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 - ((4^5) \times (6 - ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
15361 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times -((6 + 7) - 8)) + 9)) \\
15362 &:= (1 - (((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times -((6 + 7) - 8)) + 9)) \\
15363 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4^5))) \times ((6 \times (7 - 8)) + 9)) \\
15364 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) + ((4^5) + 678)) \times -9)) \\
15365 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times - (4 + ((5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\
15366 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 + ((4^5) \times (6 - ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
15367 &:= (1 + (2 \times - (3 + ((4 - ((5 + 6) \times 78)) \times 9)))) \\
15368 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) + 6) \times 7) + (8 + 9)) \\
15369 &:= ((((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + (5 + 6)) \times 7) - 8) - 9) \\
15370 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times - (67 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
15371 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 \times ((4^5) \times ((6 + 7) - 8))) + 9)) \\
15372 &:= ((1 + ((2 - (3 - 4))^5)) \times ((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9)) \\
15373 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3) + ((4^5) + 678)) \times -9)) \\
15374 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + (5 - 6)) \times 7) - (8 \times -9)) \\
15375 &:= (1 \times -(((2^{3+4}) - 5) \times - (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
15376 &:= (1 - (((2^{3+4}) - 5) \times - (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
15377 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - (5^6))) - (78 + 9)) \\
15378 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times -((6 + 7) - 8)) + 9)) \\
15379 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times -((6 + 7) - 8)) - 9)) \\
15380 &:= (1 - (((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times -((6 + 7) - 8)) - 9)) \\
15381 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 \times ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
15382 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) \times -4) + (5^6)) + ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
15383 &:= (1 \times (23 + ((4^5) \times (6 - ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
15384 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3^{4-5+6}) \times 7) + 8) \times -9) \\
15385 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - (5^6))) - (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
15386 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + (5 + 6)) \times -7) \times (8 - 9)) \\
15387 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - ((4^5) \times - (6 - ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
15388 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3+4}) - (5 - 6)) \times 7) - (8 \times -9)) \\
15389 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (45 \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
15390 &:= (((1 - (2 - 3)) + (4^5)) \times -((6 \times (7 - 8)) - 9)) \\
15391 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3) + (45 \times 6)) \times - (7 \times 8)) + 9) \\
15392 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) + (45 \times 6)) \times - (7 \times 8)) + 9) \\
15393 &:= (12 - (((3^{4-5+6}) \times 7) + 8) \times -9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15353 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 + ((6^5)/4)) - (32 + 1)))) \\
15354 &:= (9 - ((87 + 6) \times - (5 \times ((4 \times 3) + 21)))) \\
15355 &:= ((9 + ((87 - ((6^5) - (4 + 3))) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
15356 &:= (((98 + 7) - ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
15357 &:= (9 + ((87 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\
15358 &:= ((98 + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5 + 4)^3)))/ - (2 \times -1)) \\
15359 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 + 6)) \times -((5 + 4)^3) + 2)) + 1)) \\
15360 &:= ((9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times (5 \times - (4^{3+2-1}))) \\
15361 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6 - 54) \times -321)) \\
15362 &:= (((9 + 87) - ((6^5) + (4 - 3))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
15363 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) - ((6^5) - 43)) \times - (2 \times 1))) \\
15364 &:= (((98 - 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
15365 &:= ((98 - (7 \times 6)) - (((5 + 4)^3) \times -21)) \\
15366 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times 6) + ((4^5) \times 3))) - 21)) \\
15367 &:= (((98 - 7) + (6 \times 5)) \times -((4 \times -32) + 1)) \\
15368 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times -6) - (((5 + 4)^3) \times 21))) \\
15369 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times ((5 \times -4) - (3^{2+1}))) \\
15370 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times -((5 + (4 \times 3))^2 + 1)) \\
15371 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7))^6) - 543)/(2 + 1)) \\
15372 &:= ((9 + (((87 - (6^5)) \times 4) + 3))/(2 \times -1)) \\
15373 &:= ((9 - ((87 - ((6^5) - (4 + 3))) \times 2)) \times 1) \\
15374 &:= (9 + (((87 - ((6^5) - (4 + 3))) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15375 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - ((3^2) + 1))) \\
15376 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15377 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times - (2 \times 1))) \\
15378 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15379 &:= (9 + ((87 - ((6^5) - 4)) \times - (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
15380 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 \times -((6 \times -5) + 43)^{2+1})) \\
15381 &:= ((9 - (((87 - (6^5)) \times 4) + 3))/ - (2 \times -1)) \\
15382 &:= (((9 - 87) + (6^5)) - (4 + 3)) \times - (2 \times -1)) \\
15383 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times -((6 - 5) + (4^{3+2}))) + 1)) \\
15384 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6 \times 5) \times - (4^3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
15385 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((7 \times (65 + (4^3))) + (2 \times 1))) \\
15386 &:= (9 + (((8 \times -7) + ((6 + 54) \times 3))^2 + 1)) \\
15387 &:= (9 + ((87 - (6^5)) \times (4 - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
15388 &:= ((9 - ((87 - ((6^5) + (4 - 3))) \times 2)) - 1) \\
15389 &:= ((9 - ((87 - ((6^5) + (4 - 3))) \times 2)) \times 1) \\
15390 &:= (9 + (((87 - ((6^5) + (4 - 3))) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15391 &:= (((-9 \times -87) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - (32 + 1)) \\
15392 &:= (9 + ((8 + ((76 + (5 + 43))^2)) - 1)) \\
15393 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((76 + (5 + 43))^2)) \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15394 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(3^4)) + ((5^6) - (78 - 9)))) \\
15395 &:= (((1 - 2) - ((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8))) - 9) \\
15396 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 + (((4^5) \times ((6 + 7) - 8)) + 9))) \\
15397 &:= (((1 + 234) - ((5^6) + 7)) \times (8 - 9)) \\
15398 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) \times -4) + (5^6)) + (7 \times -(8 + 9))) \\
15399 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - ((5^6) + 7))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
15400 &:= (1 \times (((234 - (5^6)) \times (7 - 8)) + 9)) \\
15401 &:= (1 + (((234 - (5^6)) \times (7 - 8)) + 9)) \\
15402 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) \times -(8 + 9)) \\
15403 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) - ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
15404 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) - ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
15405 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -(((4^5) - 6) \times (7 - 8)) - 9) \\
15406 &:= (1 \times -2 + ((3 - ((4 \times 56) - 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
15407 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 + (4^5)) \times (6 - ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
15408 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3 + (4^5)) \times (6 - ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
15409 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) + (45 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9) \\
15410 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 3) + (45 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9) \\
15411 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 + 5)) - (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
15412 &:= (1 \times -((2 + ((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8))) - 9) \\
15413 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) + ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
15414 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 + ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
15415 &:= (((1 - (23 \times 4)) + (5^6)) + (7 \times -(8 + 9))) \\
15416 &:= (1 \times -2 \times -(((34 \times 5) - 6) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
15417 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - (5^6))) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
15418 &:= (1 \times -23 - (((4^5) + 6) \times (7 + 8)) - 9) \\
15419 &:= (1 - (23 - (((4^5) + 6) \times (7 + 8)) - 9)) \\
15420 &:= (12 \times -(3 + (4 \times (5 - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\
15421 &:= (12 - ((3^4) - ((5^6) - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
15422 &:= ((1 - 23) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
15423 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) + 6) \times 7) - (8 \times -9)) \\
15424 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3^4)) - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
15425 &:= (1 \times ((2 - (3 \times (4 + 5))) \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\
15426 &:= (((12^3) - ((4 \times 5) - 6)) \times -((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
15427 &:= (1 \times (2 - ((3^4) - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
15428 &:= (1 + (2 - ((3^4) - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
15429 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3^4) + (5 + 6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9) \\
15430 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) \times -4) + ((5^6) - 78)) - 9) \\
15431 &:= (1 \times (23 + ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
15432 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times -((6 + 7) - 8)) - 9) \\
15433 &:= (1 \times (23 \times ((4 \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8))) - 9)) \\
15434 &:= (1 + (23 \times ((4 \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8))) - 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15394 &:= ((98 - 7) - (6 - (((5 + 4)^3) \times 21))) \\
15395 &:= (9 + ((87 - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -(3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
15396 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times (((6 \times -5) + 43)^{2+1})))) \\
15397 &:= (98 - ((765 \times -(4 \times (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\
15398 &:= (98 + (765 \times -(4 - (3 + 2)))) \\
15399 &:= ((9 + (87 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times -4) - (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
15400 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (((5^4) - (3^2)) \times -1)) \\
15401 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -76) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
15402 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 76)) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times -2) - 1) \\
15403 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) - ((6^5) - (4^3))) \times -2) - 1) \\
15404 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) - ((6^5) - (4^3))) \times (2 \times -1) \\
15405 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) - 4)) + 321) \\
15406 &:= ((98 - 7) + (6 + (((5 + 4)^3) \times 21))) \\
15407 &:= (9 + (((87 \times 6) \times (5 - (4^3))) / -2) - 1) \\
15408 &:= (98 - (((7 \times 6) \times ((5 + 4)^3)) / -2) - 1) \\
15409 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 - ((6^5) - (4^3))) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15410 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((7 - ((6^5) - (4^3))) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15411 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 - ((6^5) - (4^3))) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15412 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((7 - ((6^5) - (4^3))) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15413 &:= (98 - (((7654 + 3) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15414 &:= (98 - (7 \times -(((6 \times ((5 + 4)^3)) / 2) + 1))) \\
15415 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 765) \times 4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times -1)) \\
15416 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -7 - (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times 2) - 1) \\
15417 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 - (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15418 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 - (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15419 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\
15420 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5) - 43) \times -2) - 1) \\
15421 &:= ((-98/7) - ((6 + ((5 + 4)^3)) \times -21)) \\
15422 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)))) - (2 + 1)) \\
15423 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
15424 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
15425 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -(((6^5) - (4^3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
15426 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
15427 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
15428 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((7 - ((6^5) - (4^3))) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15429 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - ((6 + ((5 + 4)^3)) \times 21))) \\
15430 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 + (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
15431 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15432 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 + (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15433 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 + (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\
15434 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) - (6^5)) \times 4) + 3)) / (2 \times -1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15435 &:= ((1+2) \times ((3 \times ((4+(5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8)) + 9)) \\
15436 &:= (((-1+2) \times -34) \times (5 - ((6 \times 78) - 9))) \\
15437 &:= (12 - ((3^4) - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8+9)))) \\
15438 &:= ((1+2) - ((3 + ((4+(5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8)) \times -9)) \\
15439 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(3^4)) + ((5^6) - (7 + (8+9)))) \\
15440 &:= (1 \times (((2-3) + (((4^5) + 6) \times (7+8))) - 9)) \\
15441 &:= (1 + (((2-3) + (((4^5) + 6) \times (7+8))) - 9)) \\
15442 &:= (1 \times (2 \times ((3-4) + ((5+6) \times (78 \times 9)))) \\
15443 &:= ((1 - (2-3)) - (((4^5) + 6) \times -(7+8)) + 9)) \\
15444 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - 5)) \times ((6 \times -(7+8)) - 9)) \\
15445 &:= (1 \times -((2+3) \times -(4 - (5 \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))))) \\
15446 &:= (1 - ((2+3) \times -(4 - (5 \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))))) \\
15447 &:= (((((1+2)^{3+4}) + (5 \times 6)) \times 7) + (8 \times -9)) \\
15448 &:= (1 + (((2 - (3+45)) \times -(6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
15449 &:= (1 \times (2^3) + (((4^5) + 6) \times (7+8) - 9)) \\
15450 &:= (1 + (2^3) + (((4^5) + 6) \times (7+8) - 9)) \\
15451 &:= (((1+2) - ((3^4) - (5^6))) - (7+89)) \\
15452 &:= (((((1+2)^3) \times -4) + ((5^6) + 7)) + (8 \times -9)) \\
15453 &:= (((12^3) \times (4+5)) + ((6 \times -(7+8)) - 9)) \\
15454 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - ((5^6) + 7))) - (8+9)) \\
15455 &:= ((1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) - 5) \times ((6 \times 7) - 8)))/9) \\
15456 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - (5^6))) - (7 - (8-9))) \\
15457 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^4))) - (((5^6) - 7) \times (8-9))) \\
15458 &:= (((((1+2)^{3+4}) + (5+6)) \times 7) - (8 \times -9)) \\
15459 &:= (((1+2) - 34) + (5^6)) + ((7+8) \times -9)) \\
15460 &:= (((1+2) - ((3^4) - (5^6))) - (78+9)) \\
15461 &:= ((1 - (2-3)) - (((4^5) + 6) \times -(7+8)) - 9)) \\
15462 &:= (((12^3) - (4+5)) \times -(6 - (7+8))) - 9) \\
15463 &:= (1 \times -((23+4) - ((5^6) - ((7+8) \times 9)))) \\
15464 &:= (((1-2) - ((3^4) - (5^6))) - (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
15465 &:= ((1+2) + (3 + (((4^5) + 6) \times (7+8)) + 9)) \\
15466 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(3 \times 4)) + (5^6)) - ((7+8) \times 9)) \\
15467 &:= (1 \times (2^3) + (((4^5) + 6) \times (7+8)) + 9)) \\
15468 &:= (((1+2) - ((3^4) - (5^6))) - (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
15469 &:= (((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) - ((5^6) + 7)) \times (8-9)) \\
15470 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - ((5^6) + 7))) + (8-9)) \\
15471 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - ((5^6) + 7))) \times -(8-9)) \\
15472 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - ((5^6) + 7))) - (8-9)) \\
15473 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^4))) - (((5^6) \times (7-8)) - 9)) \\
15474 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) \times 4) - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8+9)))) \\
15475 &:= (1 - (((2^3) \times 4) - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15435 &:= ((9+8) - (7 - (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\
15436 &:= (9 + ((87 \times -(6+5)) + (4^{3 \times 2+1}))) \\
15437 &:= ((9-8) \times -(((7+(6^5)) - (4^3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15438 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7+(6^5)) - (4^3)) \times 2) - 1)) \\
15439 &:= (9 + ((8 - (((7+(6^5)) - (4^3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15440 &:= ((9-8) - (((7+(6^5)) - (4^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15441 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((76+5) + (43^2)) - 1))) \\
15442 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6^5)/4)))) + (3 \times -21)) \\
15443 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) - (6^5)) \times 4) + 3))/ - (2 \times -1)) \\
15444 &:= ((9 - (8+7)) \times (6 \times -((5 \times (43 \times 2)) - 1))) \\
15445 &:= (9 - (((8+7) - ((6^5) - 43)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
15446 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) - (6^5)) \times 4) - 3))/ - (2 \times -1)) \\
15447 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) - ((6^5) - (4-3))) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
15448 &:= ((9 - (8-7)) \times -((6 \times -((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)) + 1)) \\
15449 &:= ((9+8) + (7 + (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\
15450 &:= (((9+8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - ((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\
15451 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) - ((6^5) + (4-3))) \times -2 \times 1)) \\
15452 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times ((6 + ((5+4)^3)) \times (2+1)))) \\
15453 &:= ((9-8) \times (((7 - ((6^5) - 43)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15454 &:= (9 + ((8 + (((7+(6^5)) - (4^3)) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
15455 &:= (9 - ((8 + (((7+(6^5)) - (4^3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15456 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7 - (((6^5)/4) - (3 \times 2)))) - 1)) \\
15457 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times ((65+4) \times 32))) \times -1)) \\
15458 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7 - (((6^5)/4) - (3 \times 2)))) + 1)) \\
15459 &:= ((9-87) - (((6^5) - (4+3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15460 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6^5) + (4-3))) \times -2 \times -1)) \\
15461 &:= (((98+7) - (((6^5) + (4+3)) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
15462 &:= ((9-8) \times -((7 \times -(((6+5) \times 4) + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
15463 &:= ((9-8) - ((7 \times -(((6+5) \times 4) + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
15464 &:= ((9 - (8-7)) \times -((6 \times -((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)) - 1)) \\
15465 &:= ((9-8) - ((7 \times -(((6+5) \times 4) + 3)^2) - 1)) \\
15466 &:= ((9-87) - (((6^5) - 4) \times -3 - (2-1))) \\
15467 &:= (((9-8)^7) \times -(((6^5) - 43) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15468 &:= (((9-8)^7) - (((6^5) - 43) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15469 &:= ((9+8) + ((7 - ((6^5) - 43)) \times -2 \times 1)) \\
15470 &:= ((9-8) \times -7 \times -(((6+5) \times 4) + 3)^2 + 1)) \\
15471 &:= ((9-8) - (7 \times -(((6+5) \times 4) + 3)^2 + 1)) \\
15472 &:= ((9 - (8-7)) \times -(((6^5)/ -4) + ((3^2) + 1))) \\
15473 &:= ((9-87) - (((6^5) \times -((4-3) \times 2)) + 1)) \\
15474 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)))) \times -2 \times -1)) \\
15475 &:= (((9+8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (((5^4) - (3 \times 2)) \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

15476 := $(1 \times (((2 \times -(3+4)) + (5^6)) - ((7+8) \times 9)))$
15477 := $(1 \times -((2 + (3^4)) - ((5^6) + (7 - (8 \times 9)))))$
15478 := $(1 - ((2 + (3^4)) - ((5^6) + (7 - (8 \times 9)))))$
15479 := $((12^3) \times (4+5)) + ((6-7) - (8 \times 9))$
15480 := $((1 - ((2 \times 3^4) - 5)) \times -((6 + (7+8)) - 9))$
15481 := $((1+2) + (((3 \times -4) + (5^6)) - ((7+8) \times 9)))$
15482 := $((1+2) - ((3^4) - ((5^6) + 7))) + (8 \times -9)$
15483 := $((1+2) \times -(((3^4) + (5+6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9)$
15484 := $(12 - (34 - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8+9)))))$
15485 := $((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times -((5 \times -6) + (7 - (8 \times 9))))$
15486 := $((1+2)^3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times -(7+8)) - 9)$
15487 := $((1 - (23 \times 4)) + (5^6)) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)$
15488 := $((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - ((5^6) + 7))) + (8+9))$
15489 := $((1 + (2^{3+4})) - ((5^6) - 7)) \times (8-9)$
15490 := $(12 + (((3 \times -4) + (5^6)) - ((7+8) \times 9)))$
15491 := $(12 - ((3^4) - ((5^6) + (7 - (8 \times 9)))))$
15492 := $(12 \times (3 - (4 \times (5 - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))))$
15493 := $(1 \times (((2 - (3 - 4)) + (5^6)) - ((7+8) \times 9)))$
15494 := $(1 + (((2 - (3 - 4)) + (5^6)) - ((7+8) \times 9)))$
15495 := $(12 - ((3+4) - ((5^6) - ((7+8) \times 9))))$
15496 := $((1-2) - ((3^4) - (5^6))) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)$
15497 := $(1 - (((2 \times 3) + 4) - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8+9)))))$
15498 := $(1 \times -2 \times -(((3^4) + 5) \times (6 \times (7+8)) + 9))$
15499 := $(1 - 2 \times -(((3^4) + 5) \times (6 \times (7+8)) + 9))$
15500 := $((1+2) - ((3^4) - (5^6))) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)$
15501 := $(1 - (((2 + 3^4) - 5) \times -((6 \times 7) - (8+9))))$
15502 := $(1 + (((2 - (3+4)) + (5^6)) - (7 \times (8+9))))$
15503 := $((1 + (2^{3+4})) - ((5^6) + 7)) \times (8-9)$
15504 := $((1 + ((2 \times 3^4) - 5)) \times ((6 + (7+8)) - 9))$
15505 := $((1 - ((2 + 3^4) - (5^6))) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9)))$
15506 := $(12 + (((3 \times -4) + (5^6)) - (7 \times (8+9))))$
15507 := $((1+2) + (((3 + ((4^5) + 6)) \times (7+8)) + 9))$
15508 := $((1+2)^3 \times -4) - ((5^6) \times (7-8) + 9)$
15509 := $((1+2)^3 \times -4) + (5^6) - (7 - (8-9))$
15510 := $((1+2)^3 \times -4) - ((5^6) - 7) \times (8-9)$
15511 := $((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - (5^6))) - ((7 \times -8) + 9))$
15512 := $((1 - (2-3)) + ((4 + (5^6)) - (7 \times (8+9))))$
15513 := $((1+2)^3 - (4 - ((5^6) - ((7+8) \times 9))))$
15514 := $(12 - ((3 \times -4) - ((5^6) - ((7+8) \times 9))))$
15515 := $((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + (5^6)) + ((7+8) \times -9)$
15516 := $((12^3 - 4) \times (5-6)) \times ((7-8) \times 9)$

15476 := $((9 - 87) - (((6^5) + (4 - 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)))$
15477 := $((98 - (7 \times (6 - ((5 + 4)^3)))) \times (2 + 1))$
15478 := $((9 - (8 \times (7 - (((6^5)/4) - 3)))) - (2 + 1))$
15479 := $((9 - (8 \times (7 - (((6^5)/4) - 3)))) + (2 \times -1))$
15480 := $((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5) - (4 \times 3)) \times -2) + 1)$
15481 := $((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5) - (4 \times 3)) \times -2) \times 1)$
15482 := $((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5) - (4 \times 3)) \times -2) - 1)$
15483 := $((9 - (8 \times (7 - (((6^5)/4) - 3)))) - (2 \times -1))$
15484 := $((9 - (8 \times (7 - (((6^5)/4) - 3)))) + (2 + 1))$
15485 := $((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times ((54 \times -3) - (2 - 1)))$
15486 := $((9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 + ((5 + 4)^3)))) \times (2 + 1)$
15487 := $((9 + 8) - (7 \times -(((6 + 5) \times 4) + 3)^2) + 1)$
15488 := $((9 - (8 - 7)) - ((6^5)/4)) \times -((3^2) - 1)$
15489 := $((98 + ((7 - (6^5)) \times 4)) / - (3 - (2 - 1)))$
15490 := $((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5) - (4 + 3)) \times -2) + 1)$
15491 := $(9 - ((8 \times 7) - (((6^5) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 \times 1))))$
15492 := $(9 + ((8 \times -7) + (((6^5) - (4 + 3)) \times 2) + 1))$
15493 := $((9 + (8 \times (7 - ((6^5)/4)))) - (3 \times 2)) \times -1$
15494 := $(9 - ((87 \times -(((6 + 54) \times 3) - 2)) + 1))$
15495 := $((9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6^5)/4)))) - ((3^2) + 1))$
15496 := $((9 - 8) \times ((7 - ((6^5)/4)) \times -((3^2) - 1))$
15497 := $((9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6^5)/4)))) - ((3^2) - 1))$
15498 := $((9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6^5)/4)))) + ((3 \times -2) - 1))$
15499 := $((9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6^5)/4)))) + (3 \times -(2 \times 1)))$
15500 := $((9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6^5)/4))) + 3)) + (2 \times -1))$
15501 := $(9 + ((8 \times -(7 - ((6^5)/4))) - ((3 + 2) - 1)))$
15502 := $((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5) - (4 - 3)) \times -2) + 1)$
15503 := $((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5) - (4 - 3)) \times -2) \times 1)$
15504 := $((9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6^5)/4))) + 3)) - (2 \times -1))$
15505 := $((9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6^5)/4))) - 3)) - (2 + 1))$
15506 := $((9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6^5)/4))) - 3)) + (2 \times -1))$
15507 := $((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5) + (4 - 3)) \times -2) \times 1)$
15508 := $((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5) + (4 - 3)) \times -2) - 1)$
15509 := $(9 + ((8 \times -(7 - ((6^5)/4))) + ((3 + 2) - 1)))$
15510 := $((9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6^5)/4))) - 3)) - (2 \times -1))$
15511 := $((9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6^5)/4)))) - (3 \times -(2 \times 1)))$
15512 := $((9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6^5)/4)))) - ((3 \times -2) - 1))$
15513 := $((9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6^5)/4)))) + ((3^2) - 1))$
15514 := $((9 - 8) + (((7 - ((6^5) - (4 \times 3))) \times -2) - 1))$
15515 := $((9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6^5)/4)))) + ((3^2) + 1))$
15516 := $((9 - 8) + (((7 - ((6^5) - (4 \times 3))) \times -2) + 1))$

$$\begin{aligned}
15517 &:= (12 + (((3-4) + (5^6)) - (7 \times (8+9)))) \\
15518 &:= (((((1+2)^{3+4}) + (5 \times 6)) \times 7) + (8-9)) \\
15519 &:= (((((1+2)^{3+4}) + (5 \times 6)) \times -7) \times (8-9)) \\
15520 &:= (((((1+2)^{3+4}) + (5 \times 6)) \times 7) - (8-9)) \\
15521 &:= (((1+2)^3) + ((4 + (5^6)) - ((7+8) \times 9))) \\
15522 &:= (((12^3) \times (4+5)) + ((6 \times 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\
15523 &:= (((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + (5^6)) - (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
15524 &:= (((((1+2)^3) \times -4) + ((5^6) + 7)) \times -(8-9)) \\
15525 &:= (((((1+2)^3) \times -4) + ((5^6) + 7)) - (8-9)) \\
15526 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times -4) - (((5^6) \times (7-8)) - 9) \\
15527 &:= (((((1+2)^3) \times -4) + (5^6)) - (7 - (8+9))) \\
15528 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times 5) + 6) \times (7 + (8+9))) \\
15529 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - (5^6))) + ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
15530 &:= (12 - ((3 \times -4) - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8+9)))) \\
15531 &:= (((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + (5^6)) + (7 \times -(8+9))) \\
15532 &:= (12 - ((3^4) - ((5^6) - (7 + (8+9)))) \\
15533 &:= (((1-2) - ((3^4) - (5^6))) + (7 - (8+9))) \\
15534 &:= ((1 - (2-3)) + (4 \times -(5 - ((6^7)/(8 \times 9)))) \\
15535 &:= (((1-2) - ((3^4) - (5^6))) - (7 - (8-9))) \\
15536 &:= (((1-2) - (3^4)) - (((5^6) - 7) \times (8-9))) \\
15537 &:= (((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + (5^6)) - ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
15538 &:= (((1-2) + (3^4)) - ((5^6) - 7) \times (8-9)) \\
15539 &:= (((1+2) - ((3^4) - (5^6))) - (7 - (8-9))) \\
15540 &:= (((1+2) - (3^4)) - (((5^6) - 7) \times (8-9))) \\
15541 &:= (((1+2) - ((3^4) - (5^6))) - ((7+8) - 9)) \\
15542 &:= (((12^3) \times (4+5)) + ((6 \times (7+8))/ -9)) \\
15543 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - ((5^6) + 7))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
15544 &:= ((1 - (2-3)) - (4 - ((5^6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
15545 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times (3-4)) - ((5^6) + (7-89)))) \\
15546 &:= (12 + (((3 \times -4) + (5^6)) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
15547 &:= ((12+3) + (4 \times -(5 - ((6^7)/(8 \times 9)))) \\
15548 &:= (((12^3) \times (4+5)) + ((6+7) - (8+9))) \\
15549 &:= ((1+2) - ((3-4) \times ((5^6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
15550 &:= (((1 - (2-3)) - (4 \times (5 - ((6^7)/8))))/9) \\
15551 &:= (((1-2) - ((3^4) - (5^6))) + (7 - (8-9))) \\
15552 &:= (((1-2) - (3^4)) - (((5^6) \times (7-8)) - 9)) \\
15553 &:= (((1+2) - ((3^4) - ((5^6) + 7))) + (8-9)) \\
15554 &:= (((1 - (2-3)) - (4 \times (5 + ((6^7)/8))))/ -9) \\
15555 &:= (((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + (5^6)) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
15556 &:= (((1+2) - (3^4)) - (((5^6) \times (7-8)) - 9)) \\
15557 &:= (((1+2) - ((3^4) - (5^6))) - (7 - (8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15517 &:= ((98 - ((7 + (6^5)) \times 4)) / - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
15518 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5) + (4 + 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
15519 &:= (((9 + (((8+7) - (6^5)) \times 4)) - 3) / (2 \times -1)) \\
15520 &:= ((9-8) \times -(7 - (((6^5) - (4 \times 3)) \times 2) - 1)) \\
15521 &:= ((9-8) \times ((7 - (((6^5) - (4 \times 3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15522 &:= ((9-8) + ((7 - (((6^5) - (4 \times 3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15523 &:= ((9-8) - (7 - (((6^5) - (4 \times 3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\
15524 &:= (9 - (8 + (((7 - ((6^5) - (4 + 3))) \times 2) + 1)) \\
15525 &:= (9 + ((8 + ((7 - ((6^5) - (4 + 3))) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15526 &:= ((9-8) + (((7 - ((6^5) - (4 + 3))) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15527 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 - (((6^5)/4) + 3)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
15528 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5) + (4 \times 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
15529 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5) + (4 \times 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
15530 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) \times 4) + 3)) / - (2 \times -1)) \\
15531 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 - (((6^5)/4) + 3)))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
15532 &:= ((9+8) + (((7 - ((6^5) - (4 \times 3))) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15533 &:= ((9-8) - (7 - (((6^5) - (4 + 3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\
15534 &:= ((9-8) \times ((7 + (((6^5) - (4 \times 3)) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
15535 &:= ((9-8) + ((7 + (((6^5) - (4 \times 3)) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
15536 &:= (((9-8) + (((7 - (6^5)) \times 4) + 3)) / (2 \times -1)) \\
15537 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6^5))) / 4)) - ((3^2) + 1)) \\
15538 &:= ((9+8) + ((7 - (((6^5) - (4 \times 3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15539 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6^5))) / 4)) - ((3^2) - 1)) \\
15540 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6^5))) / 4)) + ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
15541 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6^5))) / 4)) + (3 \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
15542 &:= ((9-8) \times (((7 + (6^5)) - (4 \times 3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
15543 &:= ((9-8) + (((7 + (6^5)) - (4 \times 3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
15544 &:= (((9-8)^7) - ((6^5)/4) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
15545 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6^5))) / 4)) - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
15546 &:= ((9-8) \times -((7 - ((6^5) + 4)) \times (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
15547 &:= ((9-8) \times ((7 - (((6^5) + (4-3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15548 &:= ((9-8) \times (((7 - (((6^5) \times 4) - 3)) / -2) + 1)) \\
15549 &:= ((9-8) + (((7 - (((6^5) \times 4) - 3)) / -2) + 1)) \\
15550 &:= (((9-8)^7) \times (((6^5) - (4-3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
15551 &:= ((9 - (((8-7) + (6^5)) \times 4) + 3)) / (2 \times -1)) \\
15552 &:= ((9 - (8-7)) - (((6^5) - 4) \times -(3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
15553 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6^5))) / 4)) - (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
15554 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6^5))) / 4)) - ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
15555 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6^5))) / 4)) + ((3^2) - 1)) \\
15556 &:= ((9-8) \times -(((7 + (((6^5) \times 4) + 3)) / -2) + 1)) \\
15557 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6^5))) / 4)) + ((3^2) + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15558 &:= (12 - ((3 - 4) \times (5^6 - (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
15559 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + (4 \times -(5 - ((6^7)/(8 \times 9)))))) \\
15560 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -(4 \times -(((5^6) + 7)/8) - 9))) \\
15561 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 \times -4) - ((5^6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
15562 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 - 4) + ((5^6) + (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
15563 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 - 4) \times ((5^6) + (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
15564 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) \times -4) + (5^6)) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
15565 &:= ((12 + 3) + ((4 + (5^6)) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
15566 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 + 5)) + ((6 + 7) - (8 - 9))) \\
15567 &:= (((1 - 2) - ((3^4) - (5^6))) + (7 + (8 + 9))) \\
15568 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 + 5)) + (6 - (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\
15569 &:= ((1 + 2) + (((3 \times -4) + (5^6)) - ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
15570 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4) + ((5^6) + (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
15571 &:= (((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + (5^6)) - (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
15572 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 - (4 \times (5 + ((6^7)/(8 \times 9)))))) \\
15573 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times ((4 + (5^6)) - (7 \times 8)))/ -9)) \\
15574 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 + 4) - ((5^6) - ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
15575 &:= (((1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) + (5^6) + 7) + (8 \times -9)) \\
15576 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) - (4 - ((5^6) - ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
15577 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + ((4 + (5^6)) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
15578 &:= (((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + (5^6)) - (7 + (8 + 9))) \\
15579 &:= ((12 + 3) + (4 + ((5^6) + (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
15580 &:= ((1 + 23) - (4 - ((5^6) + (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
15581 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 - 4) \times ((5^6) - ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
15582 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) \times -4) + (5^6)) + ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
15583 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (4 - ((5^6) + (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
15584 &:= (12 - ((3 \times -4) - ((5^6) + (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
15585 &:= (((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + (5^6) + 7) + (8 \times -9)) \\
15586 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3^4) + (5^6))) + (7 \times -(8 + 9))) \\
15587 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times (3 + 4)) - ((5^6) - (7 + (8 + 9)))))) \\
15588 &:= ((1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) + (((5 \times (6 - 7)) + 8)^9)) \\
15589 &:= ((12 + 3) - (4 - ((5^6) - ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
15590 &:= (((1 - 2) - ((3^4) - (5^6))) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
15591 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + (4 + ((5^6) + (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
15592 &:= (((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + (5^6)) + (7 - (8 + 9))) \\
15593 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) - (((5^6) \times (7 - 8)) + 9)) \\
15594 &:= (1 + (((2 \times -(3 \times 4)) + (5^6)) - (7 - (8 - 9)))) \\
15595 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) - (((5^6) - 7) \times (8 - 9))) \\
15596 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) \times -4) + ((5^6) + 7)) - (8 \times -9)) \\
15597 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 + 4) - ((5^6) - (7 + (8 + 9)))))) \\
15598 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) \times 4) + (5^6)) + ((7 + 8) \times -9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15558 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 + (((6^5) - (4 - 3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15559 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) - (((6^5) \times -((4 - 3) \times 2)) + 1)) \\
15560 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + ((6^5)/4) \times ((3^2) - 1)) \\
15561 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) - (((6^5) \times -((4 - 3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
15562 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 - ((6^5) + (4 \times 3))) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
15563 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 - ((6^5) + (4 \times 3))) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
15564 &:= (((9 - 8) - (((7 + (6^5)) \times 4) - 3))/(2 \times -1)) \\
15565 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 + (6^5)))/4)) - ((3^2) + 1)) \\
15566 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (((6^5) + (4 + 3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15567 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 + (6^5)))/4)) - ((3^2) - 1)) \\
15568 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 + (6^5)))/4)) + ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
15569 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 + (6^5)))/4)) + (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
15570 &:= (((9 + ((8 \times (7 + (6^5)))/4)) - 3) + (2 \times -1)) \\
15571 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (6 - ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) - 1))) \\
15572 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6 - (5^{4 \times 3/2})) \times -1)) \\
15573 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (6 - ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) + 1))) \\
15574 &:= (((9 + ((8 \times (7 + (6^5)))/4)) - 3) - (2 \times -1)) \\
15575 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -(((6^5) + (4 \times 3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15576 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times (7 + (6^5)))/4) + 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
15577 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5) \times 4) + 3))/(2 \times -1)) \\
15578 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (((6^5) + (4 \times 3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15579 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6 - (5 - 4))^{3 \times 2}) + 1)) \\
15580 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times (7 + (6^5)))/4) + 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
15581 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 + (6^5)))/4)) - (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
15582 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 + (6^5)))/4)) - ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
15583 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 + (6^5)))/4)) + ((3^2) - 1)) \\
15584 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6 + (5^{4 \times 3/2})) \times -1)) \\
15585 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 + (6^5)))/4)) + ((3^2) + 1)) \\
15586 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) - (((6^5) + (4 \times 3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15587 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 - (((6^5) + (4 \times 3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\
15588 &:= ((9 + (((8 + 7) + (6^5)) \times 4) + 3))/ - (2 \times -1)) \\
15589 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + ((6^5) + (4 \times 3))) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15590 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 + ((6^5) + (4 \times 3))) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15591 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + ((6^5)/4)) - 3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
15592 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) + (6^5))/4)) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
15593 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -7 - (6 \times (((54 - 3)^2) - 1))) \\
15594 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) + ((6^5) + (4 - 3))) \times 2) + 1)) \\
15595 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + ((6^5)/4)) - 3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
15596 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + ((6^5)/4)) - 3))) + (2 + 1)) \\
15597 &:= (9 - ((8 + (76 \times (5 \times (43 - 2)))) \times -1)) \\
15598 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -7 - (6 \times ((54 - 3)^2) - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15599 &:= (((1+2)^3) - (4 \times -(5 + ((6^7)/(8 \times 9)))) \\
15600 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times (4 \times -(5 \times (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9))))) \\
15601 &:= (((1+2)^3) - (4 - ((5^6) - ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
15602 &:= (12 - ((3 \times -4) - ((5^6) - ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
15603 &:= (((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + (5^6)) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
15604 &:= (((((1+2) - 34) + (5^6)) - 7) + (8 + 9)) \\
15605 &:= ((1+2) - ((3-4) - ((5^6) - (7 + (8+9))))) \\
15606 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times -((4 \times -5) - ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
15607 &:= ((1+2) + ((3 \times -4) + ((5^6) + ((7-8) \times 9)))) \\
15608 &:= (((1-2) - ((3^4) - (5^6))) + ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
15609 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) - (((5^6) + 7) \times (8 - 9))) \\
15610 &:= (((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + (5^6)) + (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
15611 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) - (((5^6) \times (7 - 8)) - 9)) \\
15612 &:= (((1+2) - ((3^4) - (5^6))) + ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
15613 &:= ((1+2) - ((3+4) - ((5^6) - (7 - (8-9))))) \\
15614 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -(((4 \times ((5^6) + 7))/ - 8) + 9)) \\
15615 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 + 5)) + ((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9)) \\
15616 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) - (4 - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 - 9))))) \\
15617 &:= ((1 - (((2 + (3 + 4)) \times (5^6) - 7) - 8)) / - 9) \\
15618 &:= (((1+2) - 34) + ((5^6) + 7)) + (8 + 9) \\
15619 &:= ((1 + (((2 + (3 + 4)) \times (5^6) - 7) + 8)) / 9) \\
15620 &:= ((1+2) - ((3-4) \times ((5^6) - (7 - (8-9))))) \\
15621 &:= ((1+2) \times -((3 \times (4 - (5^6))) / - ((7-8) \times 9))) \\
15622 &:= (((1-2) - ((3^4) - (5^6))) + (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
15623 &:= (12 + (((3+4) - ((5^6) - 7)) \times (8 - 9))) \\
15624 &:= ((1+2) \times (((3 \times (4 + (5^6))) - (7 + 8)) / 9)) \\
15625 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times -(5 \times -(6 + (7 \times (8 + 9))))) \\
15626 &:= (((1-2) + ((3^4) + ((5^6) - 7))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
15627 &:= ((12 + 3) + (((4 - (5^6)) \times (7 - 8)) - 9)) \\
15628 &:= ((1+2) - ((3+4) - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8-9))))) \\
15629 &:= ((1+2) + (((3+4) + (5^6)) - ((7+8) - 9))) \\
15630 &:= ((1+2) \times -((3 \times ((4 + (5^6)) - (7-8))) / - 9)) \\
15631 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) - (((5^6) \times (7 - 8)) + 9)) \\
15632 &:= ((1+2) + (((3 \times 4) + (5^6)) - (7 - (8 - 9)))) \\
15633 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) - (((5^6) - 7) \times (8 - 9))) \\
15634 &:= (((1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) + (5^6)) - ((7 + 8) - 9)) \\
15635 &:= ((1 + ((2^3+4) + (5^6))) + (7 \times -(8 + 9))) \\
15636 &:= ((1+2) \times ((3 \times (4 - ((5^6) + (7 + 8)))) / - 9)) \\
15637 &:= (((12 + 3)^4) - 5) + (((6^7) / - 8) + 9) \\
15638 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) + ((4 + (5^6)) - (7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\
15639 &:= (((1+2)^3) + (((4 - (5^6)) \times (7 - 8)) - 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15599 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) + ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) - 1)) \\
15600 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) - ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) \times -1)) \\
15601 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 \times -6) + ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) + 1))) \\
15602 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) + ((6^5) + (4 - 3))) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
15603 &:= (((98 + 7) + ((6^5) \times 4)) - 3) / - (2 \times -1) \\
15604 &:= (9 - (((87 + ((6^5) \times 4)) - 3) / - 2) - 1) \\
15605 &:= (9 - (((87 + (((6^5) \times 4) + 3)) / - 2) + 1)) \\
15606 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 + ((6^5) + (4 \times 3))) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15607 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6^5) / 4)))) - ((3^2) + 1)) \\
15608 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + ((6^5) / 4)) \times -((3^2) - 1))) \\
15609 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6^5) / 4)))) - ((3^2) - 1)) \\
15610 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6^5) / 4)))) + ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
15611 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6^5) / 4)))) + (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
15612 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6^5) / 4)))) - 3) + (2 \times -1)) \\
15613 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) + ((6 - (5^{4 \times 3/2})) \times -1)) \\
15614 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6^5) / 4)))) + (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
15615 &:= ((98 + ((7 + (6^5)) \times 4)) / (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
15616 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6^5) / 4)))) - 3) - (2 \times -1)) \\
15617 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 - (((6 - (5 - 4))^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\
15618 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 + ((6^5) / 4))) + 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
15619 &:= ((9 - (((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) - 3)) / (2 \times -1)) \\
15620 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - 6) - ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) \times -1) \\
15621 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - 6) + ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) + 1) \\
15622 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 + ((6^5) / 4))) + 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
15623 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6^5) / 4)))) - (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
15624 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6^5) / 4)))) - ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
15625 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6^5) / 4)))) + ((3^2) - 1)) \\
15626 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) - (6 - ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) - 1))) \\
15627 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6^5) / 4)))) + ((3^2) + 1)) \\
15628 &:= (((9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4))) - 3) / - (2 \times -1)) \\
15629 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) + ((6 - (5^{4 \times 3/2})) \times -1)) \\
15630 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times ((6 + (5^{4 \times 3/2})) - 1)) \\
15631 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + ((6 + (5^{4 \times 3/2})) - 1)) \\
15632 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
15633 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
15634 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
15635 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 - ((6 - (5 - 4))^{3 \times 2})) \times -1)) \\
15636 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) + (((6 - (5 - 4))^{3 \times 2}) + 1)) \\
15637 &:= (98 + (((7 - (6^5)) \times -((4 - 3) \times 2)) + 1)) \\
15638 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) + ((6 + (5^{4 \times 3/2})) - 1)) \\
15639 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + (((6^5) / 4) + 3)))) + (2 \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15640 &:= (((1-2) + ((3^4) + ((5^6) + 7))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
15641 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) - (((5^6) \times (7-8) + 9)) \\
15642 &:= (((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + (5^6)) - (7 - (8-9))) \\
15643 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) - (((5^6) - 7) \times (8-9))) \\
15644 &:= ((1+2) - (((3+4) + (5^6)) \times (7-8) - 9)) \\
15645 &:= ((1+2) + (((3+4) + (5^6)) - (7 - (8+9)))) \\
15646 &:= (((1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) + ((5^6) + 7)) + (8 - 9)) \\
15647 &:= (((1+2)^3) - (((4 + (5^6)) \times (7-8) + 9)) \\
15648 &:= (((1+2)^3) + ((4 + (5^6)) - (7 - (8-9)))) \\
15649 &:= (((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + (5^6)) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
15650 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -(((4 \times ((5^6) + 7)) / -8) - 9)) \\
15651 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 - 4) + ((5^6) + (7 + (8 + 9))))) \\
15652 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) \times -4) + (5^6)) - ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
15653 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + (5^6))) + ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
15654 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) \times 4) + ((5^6) - 7)) + (8 \times -9)) \\
15655 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + ((4 - ((5^6) + 7)) \times (8 - 9))) \\
15656 &:= (((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + ((5^6) + 7)) + (8 - 9)) \\
15657 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) - (((5^6) + 7) \times (8 - 9))) \\
15658 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3^4) + (5^6))) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
15659 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) - (((5^6) \times (7 - 8) - 9)) \\
15660 &:= (((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + (5^6)) - (7 - (8 + 9))) \\
15661 &:= (12 - ((3 - 4) \times ((5^6) + (7 + (8 + 9))))) \\
15662 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3^4) + ((5^6) - ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
15663 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - ((4 + ((5^6) + 7)) \times (8 - 9))) \\
15664 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + (4 + ((5^6) + (7 - (8 - 9))))) \\
15665 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (((4 + (5^6)) \times (7 - 8) - 9)) \\
15666 &:= (((1 + 2) - ((3^4) - (5^6))) - (7 \times -(8 + 9))) \\
15667 &:= (((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + (5^6)) + ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
15668 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) \times 4) + ((5^6) + 7)) + (8 \times -9)) \\
15669 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + (5^6))) + (7 \times -(8 + 9))) \\
15670 &:= ((1 + 2) + (34 + ((5^6) + (7 - (8 - 9))))) \\
15671 &:= (12 + ((3^4) + ((5^6) - ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
15672 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (4 - ((5^6) + (7 + (8 + 9))))) \\
15673 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times (3 \times 4)) + ((5^6) + (7 + (8 + 9))))) \\
15674 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 - 4) + ((5^6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
15675 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 - 4) \times ((5^6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
15676 &:= ((1 - 23) + (4 + ((5^6) + (78 - 9)))) \\
15677 &:= (12 - ((3 + 4) - ((5^6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
15678 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) + (4 + ((5^6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
15679 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((3 + 4) + ((5^6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
15680 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + (4 + ((5^6) + (7 + (8 + 9)))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15640 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) + (6 + ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) + 1))) \\
15641 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) - ((6 + (5^{4 \times 3/2})) \times -1)) \\
15642 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) + (6 + ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) + 1))) \\
15643 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + (((6^5) / 4) + 3)))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
15644 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) - (4 - 3))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
15645 &:= (98 + ((7 - (((6^5) + (4 - 3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15646 &:= (98 + (((7 - (((6^5) \times 4) - 3)) / -2) + 1)) \\
15647 &:= ((9 + 87) - (((6^5) \times -((4 - 3) \times 2)) + 1)) \\
15648 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) + (((6 - (5 - 4))^{3 \times 2} - 1)) \\
15649 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) - (((6 - (5 - 4))^{3 \times 2} \times -1)) \\
15650 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + (((6 - (5 - 4))^{3 \times 2} + 1))) \\
15651 &:= ((98 - 7) - (((6^5) + 4) \times -(3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
15652 &:= (98 - (((7 + ((6^5) \times 4) - 3) / -2) \times 1)) \\
15653 &:= (98 - (((7 + ((6^5) \times 4) - 3) / -2) - 1)) \\
15654 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) + ((6 + (5^{4 \times 3/2})) - 1)) \\
15655 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) - ((6 + (5^{4 \times 3/2})) \times -1)) \\
15656 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) + (6 + ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) + 1))) \\
15657 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 \times -((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3))) + (2 + 1))) \\
15658 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) + (6^5)) \times 4) - 3)) / (2 \times -1)) \\
15659 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + (6^5)) - (4 + 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
15660 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(6 \times -(5 + (4^{3+2-1})))) \\
15661 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) + (6^5)) \times 4) + 3)) / (2 \times -1)) \\
15662 &:= (98 - (((7 + (6^5)) - (4 - 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
15663 &:= (98 - (((7 + (6^5)) \times -((4 - 3) \times 2)) + 1)) \\
15664 &:= (98 + ((7 + (6^5)) \times -(4 - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
15665 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 - ((6^5) + (4^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15666 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((7 - ((6^5) + (4^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15667 &:= (((9 + (((8 \times 7) + (6^5)) \times 4) - 3) / -2) \times -1)) \\
15668 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -6) - ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) + 1))) \\
15669 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -6) - ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) + 1))) \\
15670 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + (6^5)) \times 4) + 3)) / -2 \times -1)) \\
15671 &:= (98 - ((7 + (((6^5) + (4 + 3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15672 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15673 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times -2) \times 1)) \\
15674 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15675 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\
15676 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) + ((6^5) + 43)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15677 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) + ((6^5) + 43)) \times -2) \times 1)) \\
15678 &:= (9 \times (((87 \times (6 + 54)) / 3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
15679 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -(((6^5) + (4^3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15680 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times -2) + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15681 &:= (((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + (5^6)) + (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
15682 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4) + ((5^6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
15683 &:= (12 + ((3 - 4) + ((5^6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
15684 &:= (12 - ((3 - 4) \times ((5^6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
15685 &:= (((1 - (2 \times 34)) - ((5^6) - 7)) \times (8 - 9)) \\
15686 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) \times 4) + (5^6)) + ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
15687 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 \times 4) - ((5^6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
15688 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) - (4 - ((5^6) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
15689 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3+4}) + ((5^6) + 7))) + (8 \times 9)) \\
15690 &:= (12 + (((3 \times 4) + (5^6)) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
15691 &:= ((12 + 3) + (4 + ((5^6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
15692 &:= ((1 + 2) + (((3 - 4) + (5^6)) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
15693 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 + 5)) + (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
15694 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -(((4^5) - (6 \times 7)) \times -8) + 9) \\
15695 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (4 - ((5^6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
15696 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^4)) - ((5^6) \times (7 - 8)) + 9) \\
15697 &:= (((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + (5^6)) - ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
15698 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3^4) + ((5^6) - 7))) \times -(8 - 9)) \\
15699 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3^4) + ((5^6) - 7))) - (8 - 9)) \\
15700 &:= ((1 + 2) + (((3 + 4) + (5^6)) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
15701 &:= (12 + (((3 - 4) + (5^6)) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
15702 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3^4) + ((5^6) - 7)) \times (8 - 9))) \\
15703 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + (4 + ((5^6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
15704 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times - (4 \times -(((5^6) + 7)/8) + 9)) \\
15705 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 \times 4) - ((5^6) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
15706 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 - 4) + ((5^6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
15707 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 - 4) \times ((5^6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
15708 &:= (((1 + (23 \times 4)) + ((5^6) + 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\
15709 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + ((5^6) - 7))) + (8 \times 9)) \\
15710 &:= (12 + ((3^4) + ((5^6) - (7 - (8 - 9)))))) \\
15711 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3^4) + ((5^6) + 7))) + (8 - 9)) \\
15712 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3^4) + ((5^6) + 7))) \times -(8 - 9)) \\
15713 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3^4) + ((5^6) + 7))) - (8 - 9)) \\
15714 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^4)) - ((5^6) \times (7 - 8)) - 9) \\
15715 &:= (((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + (5^6)) + ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
15716 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3^4) + ((5^6) - (7 \times (8 - 9)))))) \\
15717 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 + ((4^5) + (6 \times (78 \times 9)))))) \\
15718 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3^4) + (5^6)) \times (7 - 8)) - 9) \\
15719 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 \times 4) - ((5^6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
15720 &:= ((1 - ((23 \times ((4^5) \times 6) + 7)) + 8)) / -9 \\
15721 &:= ((1 - ((2 - ((3 + 4) \times 5)) \times 6)) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15681 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -(((6^5) + (4^3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
15682 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
15683 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) - ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) - 1))) \\
15684 &:= (((9 + 8) - ((7 - ((6^5) + (4^3))) \times 2)) + 1) \\
15685 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) - ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) + 1))) \\
15686 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 + (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
15687 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15688 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 + (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15689 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 + (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\
15690 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 - (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15691 &:= (9 - ((8 \times 7) - (((6 - (5 - 4))^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
15692 &:= (9 - (((87 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4) \times -(3 \times 2) + 1)) \\
15693 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + ((6^5) + (4^3))) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15694 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 + ((6^5) + (4^3))) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15695 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + ((6^5) + (4^3))) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15696 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 + ((6^5) + (4^3))) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15697 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(7 - (((6^5)/4) + (3 + 21)))))) \\
15698 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + ((6^5) + (4 \times 3))) \times -2) - 1) \\
15699 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -654) + 3) \times (2 - 1) \\
15700 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) + ((6^5) + (4^3))) \times -(2 \times -1) \\
15701 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((76 + (5^{4 \times 3/2})) \times -1)) \\
15702 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((76 + (5^{4 \times 3/2})) \times -1)) \\
15703 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 + (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
15704 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 + (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15705 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\
15706 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 + 6)) + 5) \times -((4 \times 3)^2) - 1)) \\
15707 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) - 6) \times ((5 - ((4 \times 3)^2)) \times -1) \\
15708 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + 3)) / -2) + 1) \\
15709 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + 3)) / -2) \times 1) \\
15710 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 + ((6^5) + (4^3))) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15711 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 + ((6^5) + (4^3))) \times -2) \times 1)) \\
15712 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 + ((6^5) + (4^3))) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15713 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) + ((4^3) + 2)) - 1) \\
15714 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\
15715 &:= (98 - (7 - (((6 - (5 - 4))^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\
15716 &:= (98 + ((7 - ((6 - (5 - 4))^{3 \times 2})) \times -1)) \\
15717 &:= ((98 - 7) + (((6 - (5 - 4))^{3 \times 2}) + 1)) \\
15718 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((76 + (5^{4 \times 3/2})) \times -1)) \\
15719 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) + ((6^5) + (4^3))) \times -2) \times 1) \\
15720 &:= ((9 - (((87 + (6^5)) \times 4) - 3)) / (2 \times -1)) \\
15721 &:= ((98 - 7) + ((6 + (5^{4 \times 3/2})) - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15722 &:= ((1+2) - ((3 \times -4) - ((5^6) - (7-89)))) \\
15723 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + (5^6))) - ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
15724 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times 4) - (((5^6) \times (7-8)) + 9)) \\
15725 &:= (((((1+2)^3) \times 4) + ((5^6) - 7)) + (8-9)) \\
15726 &:= (((((1+2)^3) \times -4) - ((5^6) - 7)) \times (8-9)) \\
15727 &:= (((1+2)^3) - (4 - ((5^6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
15728 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^4) + ((5^6) + (7 + (8 + 9)))))) \\
15729 &:= (((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + ((5^6) + 7)) - (8 \times -9)) \\
15730 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -(((4^5) - (6 \times 7)) \times -8) - 9)) \\
15731 &:= (1 - ((2 \times (3 + 4)) - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
15732 &:= (((((12^3)/4) + 5) \times -6) \times -((7 + 8) - 9)) \\
15733 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3^4) + ((5^6) + (7 + (8 + 9)))))) \\
15734 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 3) + 4) - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
15735 &:= (((1+2)^3) + (4 + ((5^6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
15736 &:= ((1 - 2) - ((3 + 4) - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
15737 &:= (((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + (5^6)) - ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
15738 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(34 + ((5^6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
15739 &:= (((((1+2)^3) \times 4) + ((5^6) + 7)) + (8-9)) \\
15740 &:= (((((1+2)^3) \times -4) - ((5^6) + 7)) \times (8-9)) \\
15741 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + (5^6))) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
15742 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times 4) - (((5^6) \times (7-8)) - 9)) \\
15743 &:= (((((1+2)^3) \times 4) + ((5^6) - 7)) + (8+9)) \\
15744 &:= (1 - (((2+3) - 4) - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
15745 &:= ((1 + (2^{3+4})) - (((5^6) \times (7-8)) + 9)) \\
15746 &:= ((1 + ((2+3)^4)) - (5 \times -(6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
15747 &:= ((1 + (((2+3)^4) + (5^6))) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
15748 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3+4}) + ((5^6) - 7))) - (8-9)) \\
15749 &:= (12 - ((3+4) - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
15750 &:= ((1+2) \times ((3-45) \times -(6 + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
15751 &:= ((1+2) - ((3 \times 4) - ((5^6) + ((7+8) \times 9)))) \\
15752 &:= (((1-2) + ((3^4) + (5^6))) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
15753 &:= (1 + (2 - ((3+4) \times (5 \times ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))))) \\
15754 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times 3) + 4) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
15755 &:= (1 + (((2 \times 3) + 4) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
15756 &:= (12 \times (((3 \times (4 - 56)) - 7) \times -8) + 9)) \\
15757 &:= (1 \times -((2 - (3 - 4)) - ((5^6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
15758 &:= (1 - ((2 - (3 - 4)) - ((5^6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
15759 &:= ((1+2) \times -(3 + ((4 - ((5+6) \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
15760 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3+4}) + ((5^6) + 7))) + (8-9)) \\
15761 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3+4}) + ((5^6) + 7))) \times -(8-9)) \\
15762 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3+4}) + ((5^6) + 7))) - (8-9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15722 &:= ((98 - 7) - ((6 + (5^{4 \times 3/2})) \times -1)) \\
15723 &:= ((98 - 7) + (6 + ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) + 1))) \\
15724 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times -6) - (5^{4+3-2+1}))) \\
15725 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times -6) - ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) + 1))) \\
15726 &:= (((98 - 7) + (6^5)) - 4) \times (3 - (2 - 1)) \\
15727 &:= ((9 + 87) - ((6 + (5^{4 \times 3/2})) \times -1)) \\
15728 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) + ((6^5) + (4^3))) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
15729 &:= ((98 + 7) + (((6 - (5 - 4))^{3 \times 2}) - 1)) \\
15730 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 + 5) \times -((4 \times 3)^2) - 1)) \\
15731 &:= (98 + (7 + (((6 - (5 - 4))^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
15732 &:= ((9 + (((87 + (6^5)) \times 4) + 3)) / -(2 \times -1)) \\
15733 &:= ((9 + (((87 + (6^5)) - (4 - 3)) \times 2)) \times 1) \\
15734 &:= ((9 + (((87 + (6^5)) - (4 - 3)) \times 2)) + 1) \\
15735 &:= ((98 + 7) + ((6 + (5^{4 \times 3/2})) - 1)) \\
15736 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + (6^5)) / 4)) \times ((3^2) - 1)) \\
15737 &:= ((98 + 7) + (6 + ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) + 1))) \\
15738 &:= ((9 + ((87 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4)) \times -(3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
15739 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 + 6)) - ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) + 1))) \\
15740 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 + (654 \times 3))) + 21)) \\
15741 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
15742 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3))) + (2 \times 1))) \\
15743 &:= (9 - ((87 + ((6^5) + 4)) \times -(3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
15744 &:= ((9 + 87) \times -((6 \times -((5 + 4) \times 3)) - (2 \times 1))) \\
15745 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (76 + 5))) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
15746 &:= (((9 + 87) + ((6^5) + (4 - 3))) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
15747 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6^5) / (4 \times 3)))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
15748 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times 6) - 5)) \times (((4^3) / -2) + 1)) \\
15749 &:= ((9 + ((87 + ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times 2)) \times 1) \\
15750 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (((5^4) + (3 + 2)) \times -1)) \\
15751 &:= (98 - (((7 + ((6^5) + 43)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15752 &:= (((9 + 87) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
15753 &:= ((9 - (((876 \times (5 + 4)) - 3) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
15754 &:= (98 - (76 \times -((5 \times (43 - 2)) + 1))) \\
15755 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -(((65 - 4) \times 3) - 2)) + 1)) \\
15756 &:= (9 - (((876 \times 54) / -3) + 21)) \\
15757 &:= (((9 - 8) - (76 \times ((5^4) - 3))) / -(2 + 1)) \\
15758 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
15759 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 \times -((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3))) - (2 + 1))) \\
15760 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 + (654 \times 3))) + (2 - 1))) \\
15761 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - (654 \times (3 + 21)))) \\
15762 &:= ((98 + (7 + 6)) \times -(5 - ((4 + 3) \times 21)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15763 &:= ((1 + (2^{3+4})) - (((5^6) \times (7 - 8)) - 9)) & 15763 &:= (98 + (((7 - ((6^5) + (4^3))) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15764 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3+4}) + ((5^6) - (7 - 8)))) + 9) & 15764 &:= ((98 + (7 \times 6)) + ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) - 1)) \\
15765 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + (4^5)) \times -((6 \times (7 - 8)) - 9) & 15765 &:= ((98 + (7 \times 6)) - ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) \times -1)) \\
15766 &:= (1 \times - (2 + (3 \times ((4 - ((5 + 6) \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15766 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -6) - ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) + 1))) \\
15767 &:= (1 - (2 + (3 \times ((4 - ((5 + 6) \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15767 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times (6 \times (54 + 321)))))) \\
15768 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -4) \times -((5 + 6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)) & 15768 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((654 + 3) \times (2 - 1))) \\
15769 &:= (1 \times - (2 - ((3^4) + ((5^6) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) & 15769 &:= (9 - (8 \times - (7 + ((654 \times 3) + (2 - 1)))))) \\
15770 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^4) + ((5^6) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) & 15770 &:= (98 - (7 - (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times 2) - 1)) \\
15771 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 \times -((4 - ((5 + 6) \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15771 &:= (98 + ((7 - (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15772 &:= (12 - ((3 - 4) \times ((5^6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 15772 &:= (98 - (7 - (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\
15773 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3^4) + ((5^6) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) & 15773 &:= (((-9 - (876 \times 54)) / -3) - (2 \times -1)) \\
15774 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3^4) + ((5^6) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) & 15774 &:= ((98 + (76 \times 5)) \times -((4 \times -3) - 21)) \\
15775 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 \times -4) - ((5^6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 15775 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (((5^4) + (3 \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15776 &:= (123 + (4 + ((5^6) + (7 + (8 + 9)))))) & 15776 &:= ((9 + 87) - (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times - (2 \times 1))) \\
15777 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 - ((4 - ((5 + 6) \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15777 &:= ((9 + 87) - (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
15778 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + (5^6))) + (7 - (8 + 9))) & 15778 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5)) \times (((4 + 3)^2) \times -1)) \\
15779 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) - (((5^6) \times (7 - 8)) + 9)) & 15779 &:= (9 - (((876 \times 54) / -3) - (2 \times 1))) \\
15780 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + ((5^6) - 7))) + (8 - 9)) & 15780 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 76)) - (5 - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
15781 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + ((5^6) - 7))) \times - (8 - 9)) & 15781 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times (43 \times - (2 - 1))) \\
15782 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + ((5^6) - 7))) - (8 - 9)) & 15782 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - ((4^{3+2}) + 1)) \\
15783 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (4 - ((5^6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 15783 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + ((4^{3+2}) \times -1)) \\
15784 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3^4) + ((5^6) + 7))) - (8 \times -9)) & 15784 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - ((4^{3+2}) - 1)) \\
15785 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((3^4) + ((5^6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) & 15785 &:= (98 - ((7 + (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15786 &:= (((12^3) - (4 - (5 \times 6))) \times -((7 - 8) \times 9)) & 15786 &:= (98 + (7 + (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\
15787 &:= (1 \times ((23 + 4) + ((5^6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 15787 &:= (98 - (7 - (654 \times (3 + 21)))) \\
15788 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3^4) + ((5^6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) & 15788 &:= (((((-9 \times 87) - 6) \times - (5 \times 4)) + (3^2)) - 1) \\
15789 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times 34) + ((5^6) + (7 + 89)))) & 15789 &:= (((-987 \times (6 - 54)) / 3) - (2 + 1)) \\
15790 &:= (1 \times - (2 \times -(((3^4) - 5) \times ((6 + 7) \times 8)) - 9)) & 15790 &:= (9 + (((8 \times -76) + 5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
15791 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3^4) - 5) \times ((6 + 7) \times 8)) - 9)) & 15791 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - ((4^{3+2}) + 1)) \\
15792 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3^4) \times - (5 \times (6 + 7))) - (8 - 9))) & 15792 &:= (9 - (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) - (4^{3+2})) \times -1)) \\
15793 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) + ((5^6) + 7))) \times (8 - 9)) & 15793 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - ((4^{3+2}) - 1)) \\
15794 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times - (3^4)) - ((5^6) - (7 \times (8 - 9)))))) & 15794 &:= (9 + ((8 \times - (7 - ((6 \times 5) \times ((4^3) + 2)))) + 1)) \\
15795 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) - (((5^6) + 7) \times (8 - 9))) & 15795 &:= (9 + (((876 + 5) - 4) \times - (3 - 21))) \\
15796 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + (5^6))) + (7 - (8 - 9))) & 15796 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((765 - (4 \times 3)) \times -21)) \\
15797 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) - (((5^6) \times (7 - 8)) - 9)) & 15797 &:= ((((-9 - (87 + 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2) + 1) \\
15798 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) \times 4) + ((5^6) - 7)) - (8 \times -9)) & 15798 &:= (98 + ((76 + (5^{4 \times 3/2})) - 1)) \\
15799 &:= (123 + (4 + ((5^6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) & 15799 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5)) \times ((4^3) - (2 + 1))) \\
15800 &:= (12 + ((3^4) + ((5^6) - (7 - 89)))) & 15800 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) + ((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\
15801 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3+4}) + (5^6))) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & 15801 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((76 + (54/3)) \times 21))) \\
15802 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (((3 \times 45) + 6) \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9) & 15802 &:= (9 + ((8 \times - (7 \times (6 - ((5 + 4) \times 32)))) + 1)) \\
15803 &:= (1 - (2 + (((3 - 45) \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9)) & 15803 &:= ((9 - ((87 + ((6^5) + 43)) \times 2)) \times -1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15804 &:= ((1+2) \times (3 + ((45-6) \times ((7+8) \times 9)))) & 15804 &:= (9 - ((8+7) \times -(((6 \times 5) + (4^{3+2})) - 1))) \\
15805 &:= ((1+2) + ((3^4) + ((5^6) + (7+89)))) & 15805 &:= ((9 + (((87+6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
15806 &:= (1 \times (2 - (((3-45) \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9))) & 15806 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (76 \times (5^4))))/3) - 21) \\
15807 &:= ((12 + (3^{4+5})) + ((6^7)/ - (8 \times 9))) & 15807 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) - (6 - (((5+4)^3 \times 21))) \\
15808 &:= ((1 + (23 \times (4+5))) \times -((6+7) - 89)) & 15808 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6^5)/ - 4) - (32 \times 1))) \\
15809 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times (3 - (4^5))) + 67) \times -8) + 9)) & 15809 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(7 + (((6^5)/4) + (3+21)))) \\
15810 &:= (1 + (((2 \times (3 - (4^5))) + 67) \times -8) + 9)) & 15810 &:= ((9 + (87 + 6)) \times -(5 \times -(4 + (3^{2+1})))) \\
15811 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3^4)) - ((5^6) + (7 + (8+9)))))) & 15811 &:= ((98 - (7 - 6)) \times -((54 \times -3) - (2 - 1))) \\
15812 &:= (((((1+2)^3) \times 4) + ((5^6) + 7)) - (8 \times -9)) & 15812 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((765 - (4 \times 3)) \times -21)) \\
15813 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -34) - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8+9)))))) & 15813 &:= (9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 543) \times -2) + 1) \\
15814 &:= (12 + ((3^4) + ((5^6) + (7+89)))) & 15814 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 + 6)) + 5) \times (((4 \times 3)^2) + 1))) \\
15815 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -((4^5) - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9)) & 15815 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) - (654 \times -(3+21))) \\
15816 &:= (12 \times (3 - ((4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9))) & 15816 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(76 \times ((5 \times 4) + (3 \times 2)))) + 1)) \\
15817 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3^4) - 5) \times ((6+7) \times 8)) - 9)) & 15817 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 \times ((5 \times 4) + (3 \times 2)))))) \times 1) \\
15818 &:= (1 \times ((2^{3+4}) + ((5^6) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) & 15818 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times 5) + (4^{3+2})))) - 1) \\
15819 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3+4}) + ((5^6) - 7))) - (8 \times -9)) & 15819 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times 5) + (4^{3+2})))) \times 1) \\
15820 &:= (((((1+2)^3) \times 4) + ((5^6) + 78)) + 9) & 15820 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times 5) + (4^{3+2})))) + 1) \\
15821 &:= (123 + (4 + ((5^6) + (78 - 9)))) & 15821 &:= ((9 + ((87 + ((6^5) + 43)) \times 2)) \times 1) \\
15822 &:= (1 \times -((2 - (((3 + (4 \times 56)) - 7) \times 8)) \times 9)) & 15822 &:= ((98 - (76 \times (5 + 4))) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\
15823 &:= (1 \times -((2 - ((3^4) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 15823 &:= (9 + (((87 + 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) \times 1)) \\
15824 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^4) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 15824 &:= (9 - (((8 + (76 \times (5^4))))/ - 3) + 21)) \\
15825 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((3^4) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 15825 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) + ((3^2) - 1))) \\
15826 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3^4) - 5) \times ((6+7) \times 8)) + 9))) & 15826 &:= (((98 + 76) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
15827 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3^4) - 5) \times ((6+7) \times 8)) + 9))) & 15827 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(7 \times -((6 \times (54 - 32)) + 1))) \\
15828 &:= ((1+2) + ((3^4) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8+9)))))) & 15828 &:= (9 + (((((8+7) \times 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15829 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -34) - ((5^6) + ((7+8) \times 9)))) & 15829 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 54))) \times -((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\
15830 &:= ((-1 + ((2+3) \times ((4 + (56 \times 7)) \times 8)) - 9) & 15830 &:= (9 - (((((8+7) \times 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2) - 1)) \\
15831 &:= (123 + (4 + ((5^6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) & 15831 &:= (9 \times -((8 \times -((7+6) \times (5 \times 4))) + 321)) \\
15832 &:= ((1 + ((2+3) \times ((4 + (56 \times 7)) \times 8)) - 9) & 15832 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6 \times 5) \times -((4^3) + 2)) + 1)) \\
15833 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3+4}) + ((5^6) + 7))) - (8 \times -9)) & 15833 &:= (((9 - 8) - (76 \times (5^4)))/ (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
15834 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 + 5)) - (6 \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) & 15834 &:= ((9 - 87) \times (((6 \times 5) + 4) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
15835 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + (5^6))) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & 15835 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 654))) \times 3) + (2 \times -1)) \\
15836 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -4) - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 15836 &:= (((((-9 - 8) - (76 \times (5^4)))/ - 3) - 2) - 1) \\
15837 &:= (12 + ((3^4) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 15837 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 654))) \times (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
15838 &:= (1 \times -((2 - (((3 + (4 \times 56)) - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15838 &:= (((9 + 8) + (76 \times (5^4))) - 3)/ (2 + 1)) \\
15839 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 + (4 \times 56)) - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15839 &:= (98 + (((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\
15840 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3^4) + (5^6))) - ((7 + 8) \times -9)) & 15840 &:= ((9 - ((87 - 6) \times 5)) \times (4 \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
15841 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((3^4) + ((5^6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 15841 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times (((4^3)/ - 2) + 1)) \\
15842 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3^4) + (56/7)) \times 89)))) & 15842 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (76 \times (5^4))))/3) - (2 + 1)) \\
15843 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3^4) + ((5^6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) & 15843 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (76 \times (5^4))))/3) + (2 \times -1)) \\
15844 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3^4) + ((5^6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) & 15844 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((7 - ((6 + 5) \times 43)) \times -(2 \times 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15845 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 + (456 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
15846 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) + ((4^5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8)) - 9) \\
15847 &:= (1 \times -(23 \times -((4 \times 5) + (678 - 9)))) \\
15848 &:= (123 + (4 + ((5^6) + (7 + 89)))) \\
15849 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 \times 4) + (567 + 8)) \times -9)) \\
15850 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((4 + (56 \times 7)) \times 8))) + 9) \\
15851 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times 5)))) \times -((6 \times -7) - 89)) \\
15852 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3^4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times -9)) \\
15853 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + ((5^6) - 7))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
15854 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3^4)) \times -(56 + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
15855 &:= (-12 - (((3 \times (45 \times (6 + 7))) + 8) \times -9)) \\
15856 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3^4)) - ((5^6) + (78 - 9)))) \\
15857 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + (5^6))) + (78 - 9)) \\
15858 &:= (((12^3) + (4 + (5 \times 6))) \times -((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
15859 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((345 + (67 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
15860 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times (3^4)) + (5 - 6)) \times -((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
15861 &:= (12 - (((3^4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times -9)) \\
15862 &:= (-1 + (((2^3) \times -((4 \times ((5 - 67) \times 8))) - 9)) \\
15863 &:= (123 - (4 - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
15864 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) + ((4^5) + 6)) \times (7 + 8)) + 9) \\
15865 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 \times (45 \times (6 + 7))) + 8) \times 9)) \\
15866 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 \times (45 \times (6 + 7))) + 8) \times 9)) \\
15867 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + (5^6))) + (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
15868 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) \times 4) + (5^6)) - ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
15869 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3^4)) - ((5^6) - (7 - 89)))) \\
15870 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) + ((6 + 7) \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
15871 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 45))) \times ((6 \times -7) - (8 + 9))) \\
15872 &:= (1 \times -((2^{3+4}) \times ((5 + 6) - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
15873 &:= (1 \times ((2 + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
15874 &:= (1 + ((2 + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
15875 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + (5^6))) + (78 + 9)) \\
15876 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 \times 4) - 5) \times -((6 + 78) \times 9))) \\
15877 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 \times ((45 \times (67 - 8)) - 9)))) \\
15878 &:= (1 \times ((23 - ((4^5) - 67)) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
15879 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 + 5)) - ((6 \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9)) \\
15880 &:= (((1 - (2 - 3))^{4 \times 5 - 6}) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
15881 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - 34) \times -((5 - 67) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
15882 &:= (1 - (((2 - 34) \times -((5 - 67) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
15883 &:= ((12 + ((3 + 4)^5)) + ((6 + 7) \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
15884 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + (5^6))) + (7 + 89)) \\
15885 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -(((4 + (56 \times 7)) \times 8) + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15845 &:= (9 - ((8 + (76 \times (5^4)))) / - (3 \times (2 - 1))) \\
15846 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((76 \times (5^4)) + 3)) / - (2 + 1))) \\
15847 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (76 \times (5^4)))) / 3) - (2 \times -1)) \\
15848 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6 \times 5) \times -((4^3) + 2)) - 1)) \\
15849 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((76 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15850 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (((5^4) + (3^2)) \times -1)) \\
15851 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (76 - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
15852 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 + 654) \times 3)) + 21)) \\
15853 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 654) \times 3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
15854 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) + 321))) \\
15855 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6^5) / 4) + 321))) \\
15856 &:= (9 + ((8 \times ((7 + 654) \times 3) - 2)) - 1)) \\
15857 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 + 654) \times 3) - (2 \times 1)))) \\
15858 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times 4)) \times -(3 - 21)) \\
15859 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) - 65) \times -(4 - 321))) \\
15860 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - (76 \times (5^4))) / -3) + 21) \\
15861 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (((76 - 543) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15862 &:= (9 - (((87 + ((6^5) + (4^3))) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15863 &:= (9 - ((87 + ((6^5) + (4^3))) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
15864 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((76 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15865 &:= (((9 + 8) - ((76 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times 1) \\
15866 &:= ((9 - (87 \times 6)) - (5 - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
15867 &:= ((98 + ((76 \times (5^4)) + 3)) / (2 + 1)) \\
15868 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 - (6^5))) / -4) + 321)) \\
15869 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 \times 54))) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
15870 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -(((5 + 43) - 2) \times -1)) \\
15871 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 654) \times 3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
15872 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 + 654) \times 3)) + (2 - 1))) \\
15873 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
15874 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 + 654) \times 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
15875 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 \times (6 + (5 + (4 + 3))))^2) - 1)) \\
15876 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((7 \times (6 + (5 + (4 + 3))))^2) - 1)) \\
15877 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((7 \times (6 + (5 + (4 + 3))))^2)) \times -1)) \\
15878 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 \times (6 + (5 + (4 + 3))))^2) + 1))) \\
15879 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + (6 \times 54)) \times (3 \times 2)))) \times -1) \\
15880 &:= (((9 + 8) + (76 \times 5)) \times -(4 \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
15881 &:= ((987 + (6^{5+4-3})) / (2 + 1)) \\
15882 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -((7 - (65 + 4)) \times 32)) + 1)) \\
15883 &:= (((98 + 7) + ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
15884 &:= (9 - (((((8 \times 7) + 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\
15885 &:= (9 \times -((8 \times 7) + ((65 \times (4 - 32)) - 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15886 &:= (1 - ((2+3) \times -(((4 + (56 \times 7)) \times 8) + 9))) \\
15887 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3 + (4^5))) - 67) \times -8) + 9) \\
15888 &:= (((12^3)/4) \times -(5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8))))/9 \\
15889 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3+4}) + (5^6))) - ((7+8) \times -9)) \\
15890 &:= ((1 - (2+34)) \times (5 - ((6 \times 78) - 9))) \\
15891 &:= (-12 + (3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 789)))) \\
15892 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 789)))) \\
15893 &:= (1 \times (23 \times -(4 - (5 \times (67 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
15894 &:= (1 + (23 \times -(4 - (5 \times (67 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
15895 &:= (1 \times (((((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times 6) - 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\
15896 &:= (1 + (((((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times 6) - 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\
15897 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 + 5)) - ((6 \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\
15898 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -(3 \times ((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times 8))) + 9)) \\
15899 &:= (1 \times ((2 - 3) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 789)))) \\
15900 &:= (12 \times -(3 - (4 \times ((5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\
15901 &:= (1 \times -((2 - 3) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 789)))) \\
15902 &:= (1 - ((2 - 3) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 789)))) \\
15903 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times (4 + (((5 + 67) \times 8) + 9))) \\
15904 &:= ((1 - ((2 + 3) \times 45)) \times -((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
15905 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3 + (4^5))) - 67) \times -8) - 9) \\
15906 &:= ((1 - 23) \times -((4 + 5) + (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
15907 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + (5^6))) - (7 \times -(8 + 9))) \\
15908 &:= (((1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times -(5 + ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9))) \\
15909 &:= (1 + ((2^3) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 789)))) \\
15910 &:= (1 \times -(2 + ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
15911 &:= (1 - (2 + ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
15912 &:= (((12^3)/4) \times -(5 - (6 \times 7))) + (8 \times -9) \\
15913 &:= (((-1 - ((2 \times (3 + (4^5))) - 67)) \times -8) + 9) \\
15914 &:= (1 \times (2 - ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
15915 &:= (1 + (2 - ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
15916 &:= (1 \times -(23 \times -(((4 + 5) \times 67) + 89))) \\
15917 &:= (1 - (23 \times -(((4 + 5) \times 67) + 89))) \\
15918 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 + 4) \times -(56 + (78 \times 9)))) \\
15919 &:= (((-12 \times 34) + (5^6)) - (78 \times -9)) \\
15920 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (45 \times (67 - 8)))) - 9) \\
15921 &:= (1 \times -(((234 - (5 \times 6)) \times -78) - 9)) \\
15922 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3^4)) - ((5^6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
15923 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + (5^6))) - ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
15924 &:= (12 + ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times -((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
15925 &:= ((1 - (23 \times 4)) \times (((5 \times 6) - 7) \times -8) + 9) \\
15926 &:= (1 + ((234 + (5 + 6)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15886 &:= (9 - (((((8 \times 7) + 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2) - 1)) \\
15887 &:= (-98 - (((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times -432) - 1)) \\
15888 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(6 \times -((5 \times ((4^3) + 2)) + 1))) \\
15889 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(((7 - (65 + 4)) \times 32) - 1))) \\
15890 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 65)) \times ((4 \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\
15891 &:= (((-9 + (87 \times (65 - 4))) \times 3) - (2 + 1)) \\
15892 &:= (9 + ((8 + ((7 \times (6 + (5 + (4 + 3))))^2)) - 1)) \\
15893 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((7 \times (6 + (5 + (4 + 3))))^2)) \times -1)) \\
15894 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((7 \times (6 + (5 + (4 + 3))))^2) + 1)) \\
15895 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((76 - 5) \times (4 - 32)))) \times -1) \\
15896 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 + (6^5)))/ -4) - 321)) \\
15897 &:= ((9 + (87 \times (6 + (5 \times 4)))) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
15898 &:= (((9 + (87 + 6)) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
15899 &:= ((9 - ((8 + (76 \times 5)) \times (43 - 2))) \times -1) \\
15900 &:= ((9 - (8 + 76)) \times ((5 \times -43) + (2 + 1))) \\
15901 &:= (((98 + 7) - 6) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
15902 &:= ((-98 - 7) + (6 + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
15903 &:= ((9 + (8 + 76)) \times -((54 + 3) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
15904 &:= (9 + (((8 \times -(7 + 6)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
15905 &:= (((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) \times 1) \\
15906 &:= ((9 - ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5)) \times (((4^3) + 2) \times -1)) \\
15907 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 76) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15908 &:= (9 + (((8 + (7 \times 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15909 &:= ((9 - 87) + (((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15910 &:= (9 + ((87 + ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15911 &:= (9 - ((87 + ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
15912 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + 6) \times -(((5 \times (4 + 3))^2) - 1))) \\
15913 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 + 6) \times -(((5 \times (4 + 3))^2) - 1))) \\
15914 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
15915 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 \times 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15916 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((7 \times 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15917 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 \times 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15918 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((7 \times 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15919 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times -6) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
15920 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times -6) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) + 1))) \\
15921 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(((76 - 5) \times (4 - 32)) - 1))) \\
15922 &:= (9 - (87 - ((6 \times ((5 \times 4)^3))/(2 + 1)))) \\
15923 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(76 - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) - 1))) \\
15924 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((76 - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15925 &:= ((98 - 7) \times ((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3) + 2)) + 1)) \\
15926 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + 6) \times -((5 \times (4 + 3))^2)) - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15927 &:= (((1+2)^3) - (4 \times -(5 \times (6+789)))) & 15927 &:= ((9-8) - (((7+6) \times -((5 \times (4+3))^2)) - 1)) \\
15928 &:= ((1-23) \times -(4 + ((5 + (67+8)) \times 9))) & 15928 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5)/4)) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
15929 &:= (1 \times -(((2+3) \times -((456 \times 7) - 8)) - 9)) & 15929 &:= ((9+8) - ((7+6) \times -((5 \times (4+3))^2) - 1)) \\
15930 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times (6 \times 78)) - 9))) & 15930 &:= (((9+87) - 6) \times ((5 - (4^3)) \times -(2+1))) \\
15931 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times (6 \times 78)) - 9))) & 15931 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -((65 - 4) \times 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
15932 &:= ((1-2) - ((345 - 6) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) & 15932 &:= ((9+8) + (((7 \times 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15933 &:= (((((1+2)^3) \times -4) - 5) \times -(6 + ((7+8) \times 9))) & 15933 &:= ((9+8) + (((7 \times 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
15934 &:= ((1+2) + ((3 + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times 7)) \times -89)) & 15934 &:= ((9+8) + (((7 \times 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15935 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((345 - 6) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) & 15935 &:= (9 - (87 - (((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2) + 1))) \\
15936 &:= (((12^3) \times -(4 - (5 - (6 + 78)))) / -9) & 15936 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) \times -(((4+3)^2) - 1)) \\
15937 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(3 \times (4 \times (5 - (678 - 9))))) & 15937 &:= (((-98 \times 7) - 6) \times -((5 \times 4) + 3)) + 21) \\
15938 &:= (((((12^3)/4) + (5^6)) + (7 \times -(8+9))) & 15938 &:= ((9-8) \times -((7+6) \times -((5 \times (4+3))^2) + 1))) \\
15939 &:= (1 + (234 + ((5^6) + (7 + (8 \times 9))))) & 15939 &:= ((9-8) - ((7+6) \times -((5 \times (4+3))^2) + 1)) \\
15940 &:= (1 \times ((2+3) \times -((4^5) - (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) & 15940 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15941 &:= (1 + ((2+3) \times -((4^5) - (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) & 15941 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
15942 &:= (((12^3) \times (4+5)) + (6 \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 15942 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
15943 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(3 \times (((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times 8) - 9)))) & 15943 &:= ((9 - ((8+7) \times (6 \times 5))) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
15944 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) \times -((4 \times ((5 - 67) \times 8)) - 9))) & 15944 &:= (((-9 \times -(876 + 5)) + 43) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
15945 &:= (1 + ((2^3) \times -((4 \times ((5 - 67) \times 8)) - 9))) & 15945 &:= (98 + (((76 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15946 &:= ((123 - 4) \times ((5 - 6) + ((7+8) \times 9))) & 15946 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
15947 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times (7 \times 89)))) & 15947 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15948 &:= (((12^3) + (4 \times (5+6))) \times -((7-8) \times 9)) & 15948 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
15949 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (3^4)) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8)) - 9)) & 15949 &:= ((9 + (((8 + (7+6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
15950 &:= (1 + (((2 - (3^4)) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8)) - 9)) & 15950 &:= (((9+8) - 7) \times -((6+5) \times -(((4 \times 3)^2) + 1))) \\
15951 &:= (1 + (2 - (((3 - 45) \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times 9)) & 15951 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -((65 - 4) \times 3)) - 21)) \\
15952 &:= (((((1+2)^3) - (4^5)) \times -(6 - (7 - (8+9)))) & 15952 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) \times -1)) \\
15953 &:= ((1 - ((2+3) \times 456)) \times -(7 \times -(8-9))) & 15953 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -7) + ((6 \times ((5 \times 4)^3)) / (2 + 1)))) \\
15954 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 \times (4 + (5 \times ((67 - 8) \times 9))))) & 15954 &:= ((-98 \times 7) - (65 \times -(4^{3+2-1}))) \\
15955 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 \times (4 + (5 \times ((67 - 8) \times 9))))) & 15955 &:= (9 + (8 + ((7+6) \times (((5 \times (4+3))^2) + 1)))) \\
15956 &:= (1 - ((2+3) \times -((456 \times 7) + (8-9)))) & 15956 &:= (((98 - 76) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
15957 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (3 \times 45)) \times (6+7)) - 8) \times -9)) & 15957 &:= ((9-8) \times (((7 \times -6) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
15958 &:= (1 - (((2 + (3 \times 45)) \times (6+7)) - 8) \times -9)) & 15958 &:= (9 + (((8 \times -7) + 6) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
15959 &:= (1 \times -(((2+3) \times -(456 \times 7)) - (8-9))) & 15959 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6 + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
15960 &:= (12 + (((3 - 45) \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times -9)) & 15960 &:= (9 + (((8 \times -7) + 6) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
15961 &:= (((((12^3)/4) + ((5^6) - 7)) - 89) & 15961 &:= (9 - (8 - (76 \times (5 \times (43 - (2 - 1))))) \\
15962 &:= (1 \times (23 \times -((4 \times 5) - (6 \times (7 \times (8+9))))) & 15962 &:= (9 - (((8+7) + (6^5)) \times 43) / -21)) \\
15963 &:= (1 + (23 \times -((4 \times 5) - (6 \times (7 \times (8+9))))) & 15963 &:= ((9+8) \times ((7 \times -(6 + (5 \times (4-32)))) + 1)) \\
15964 &:= ((((-12 \times -34) + (5^6)) - 78) + 9) & 15964 &:= (9 - ((8 \times 7) - ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2) - 1)) \\
15965 &:= (((1+2) - 34) \times -((5+6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 15965 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times 1) \\
15966 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 \times (((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times 78) + 9)))) & 15966 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
15967 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(3^4)) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 15967 &:= (9 + (((8 + (7+6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 15968 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - (5^6))) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
 15969 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3^4) + 5) \times -(6 + (7 \times 8))) + 9) \\
 15970 &:= (((12^3)/4) + ((5^6) - 78)) - 9 \\
 15971 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3!! \times 4! - (5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
 15972 &:= (12 \times (3 + (4 \times ((5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)))) \\
 15973 &:= (((-12 - 3) \times -((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) - 8) - 9 \\
 15974 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times (5 + (6 + (78 + 9)))) \\
 15975 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times 5)) \times ((6 \times -7) + (8 + 9))) \\
 15976 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) \times -(45 \times ((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 15977 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3) \times -(456 \times 7)) - (8 + 9))) \\
 15978 &:= (((12^3)/4) + ((5^6) - 7)) + (8 \times -9) \\
 15979 &:= (1 + (234 + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 15980 &:= ((1 + 234) \times -(((5 + 6) - 7) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
 15981 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 + 4) \times -(5 + ((6 + 78) \times 9))) \\
 15982 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3 \times 4) + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 15983 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 \times 4) + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 15984 &:= (((12^3)/4) \times -(5 - (6 \times 7))) \times -(8 - 9) \\
 15985 &:= ((1 - ((2^3) \times (4^5)) - (6^7)))/(8 + 9) \\
 15986 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3 \times 4) + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 15987 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3 \times 4) + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 15988 &:= (((12^3)/4) + ((5^6) - 78)) + 9 \\
 15989 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 45))) \times -((6 \times -7) - (8 + 9))) \\
 15990 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3^4) - (5 - 6)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9))) \\
 15991 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3) \times -((456 \times 7) + 8)) + 9) \\
 15992 &:= (((12^3)/4) + ((5^6) + 7)) + (8 \times -9) \\
 15993 &:= (1 \times (((2 - 34) \times 56) + (7 + 8)) \times -9) \\
 15994 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times (3 - ((4 \times 5)^{6 \times (7-8)+9}))) \\
 15995 &:= (1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4 \times 5)^{6 \times (7-8)+9}))) \\
 15996 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) - (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
 15997 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 + 4)^5) - (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 15998 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times 45))) \times -(67 - 8)) + 9) \\
 15999 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -(((4 \times 5) + 67) \times 8)) + 9) \\
 16000 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times ((4 \times 5)^{6 \times (7-8)+9})) \\
 16001 &:= (1 \times -((2^{3+4}) - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 16002 &:= (1 - ((2^{3+4}) - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 16003 &:= (1 + (2 \times -((3 \times (4 - ((5 \times (67 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\
 16004 &:= (1 - 2 \times 3!) \times (-4 + 5!) + 6! \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 16005 &:= ((12 + 3) \times ((4^5) + ((6 \times 7) - (8 - 9)))) \\
 16006 &:= (1 \times (2 \times (3 + ((4 \times 5)^{6 \times (7-8)+9}))) \\
 16007 &:= (1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4 \times 5)^{6 \times (7-8)+9}))) \\
 16008 &:= (((12^3) + (4^5)) \times 6) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 15968 &:= (9 + (((8 + (7 + 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
 15969 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) - 1)) \\
 15970 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) \times -1)) \\
 15971 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times 6)) - ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) + 1))) \\
 15972 &:= (((9 - (8 - (7 + 6))) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
 15973 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 + 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
 15974 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 \times 6)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
 15975 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 \times -6) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
 15976 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times 6)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
 15977 &:= ((9 + (((8 - (7 - 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
 15978 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 76) \times -54) - 3) \times -(2 \times -1) \\
 15979 &:= ((((-98 + 7) \times -6) + 5) \times -(4 - (32 + 1))) \\
 15980 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 + (((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2) + 1))) \\
 15981 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 + ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
 15982 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 + ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
 15983 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 + ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
 15984 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times (6 + (5 \times (4 \times (32 + 1)))) \\
 15985 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 432)) \times -1)) \\
 15986 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + 6) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
 15987 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) - (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
 15988 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -(6 - ((5 \times 4)^3))) \times -(2 \times -1) \\
 15989 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times (((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
 15990 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + (((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
 15991 &:= (9 - ((8 - (((7 + 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
 15992 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) - 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2) - 1) \\
 15993 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -6) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times -2) + 1) \\
 15994 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - 6) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times -2) + 1) \\
 15995 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -6) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times -2) - 1) \\
 15996 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - 6) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times -2) - 1) \\
 15997 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 - (((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2) - 1))) \\
 15998 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((7 - 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
 15999 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((7 - 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) \times 1)) \\
 16000 &:= ((9 - (8 - (7 - 6))) \times -(((5 \times 4)^3) \times -2) - 1)) \\
 16001 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) - (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
 16002 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) + ((6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
 16003 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) - (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
 16004 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 - 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
 16005 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times 6) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times -2) + 1) \\
 16006 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + 6) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times -2) + 1) \\
 16007 &:= ((9 + (((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5) \times (4^3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
 16008 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + 6) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times -2) - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16009 &:= ((12 + ((3 + 4)^5)) + (6 \times -((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
16010 &:= (((12^3)/4) + (5^6)) + ((7 \times -8) + 9) \\
16011 &:= (1 + (2 - ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 - (78 \times 9)))) \\
16012 &:= (1 \times -(((234 + 5) \times -67) - (8 - 9))) \\
16013 &:= ((1 + (((234 + 5) \times 67) + 8)) - 9) \\
16014 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 \times -(((45 \times (6 + 7)) + 8) \times 9))) \\
16015 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - 6) - 789 \\
16016 &:= (1 \times -((234 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8)))/ - 9)) \\
16017 &:= (1 - ((234 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8)))/ - 9)) \\
16018 &:= (1 - ((23 \times -(((4 \times 5) + 67) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
16019 &:= (1 \times -((2 + (3^4)) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9)))) \\
16020 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3^4)) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9)))) \\
16021 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) \times -4) + (5^6)) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
16022 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + (6 - 789)))) \\
16023 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3^4) + 5) \times -(6 + (7 \times 8))) - 9) \\
16024 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 + 4)^5) + (6 - 789))) \\
16025 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times -7) + (8 + 9))) \\
16026 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 + 5)) - (6 \times -(7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
16027 &:= (((1 + 2) - 34) \times -((5 + 6) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
16028 &:= (1 - (((2 + 345) - 6) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
16029 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3^4) \times (5 + 6)))) \times ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
16030 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3 \times ((45 \times (6 + 7)) + 8))) \times -9)) \\
16031 &:= (1 \times -(23 \times -(4 + ((5 - (6 - 78)) \times 9)))) \\
16032 &:= (12 \times (3 - ((4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9))) \\
16033 &:= (((12^3)/4) + ((5^6) - 7)) - (8 + 9) \\
16034 &:= 12 \times 34 + 5^6 - (7 - 8)^9 \\
16035 &:= ((12 + 3) \times ((4^5) + (((6 + 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\
16036 &:= (1 \times -(2 + ((3^4) \times ((56 - 78) \times 9)))) \\
16037 &:= (1 \times ((23 \times -4) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
16038 &:= (((1 - (23 \times 4)) + (5^6)) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
16039 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3))^4) \times (56 + 7)) - 89 \\
16040 &:= (1 \times (2 - ((3^4) \times ((56 - 78) \times 9)))) \\
16041 &:= (1 + (2 - ((3^4) \times ((56 - 78) \times 9)))) \\
16042 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times 3) + (4 \times 5)) \times -(6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\
16043 &:= (1 + (((2 \times 3) + (4 \times 5)) \times -(6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\
16044 &:= (12 \times ((3 - (4 \times (5 \times 67))) \times (8 - 9))) \\
16045 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -((4 \times 5) + 678)) + 9)) \\
16046 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 3) \times 45)) \times ((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
16047 &:= (((1 - 2) - ((3^4) - (5^6))) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
16048 &:= (((12^3)/4) - (((5^6) \times (7 - 8)) + 9)) \\
16049 &:= (((12^3)/4) + ((5^6) - 7)) + (8 - 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16009 &:= ((9 + ((8 - 7)^6)) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times -2) + 1) \\
16010 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (6 + ((5 \times 4)^3))) \times (2 \times -1) \\
16011 &:= ((9 + (((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5) \times (4^3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
16012 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16013 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
16014 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + (6 + ((5 \times 4)^3))) \times -(2 \times -1) \\
16015 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (((7 \times 6) + (5^4)) \times 3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
16016 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(((7 \times 6) + (5^4)) \times 3)) + (2 - 1))) \\
16017 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
16018 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 + ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
16019 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (((7 \times 6) + (5^4)) \times 3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
16020 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 + ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
16021 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 + (((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2) + 1))) \\
16022 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 - ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
16023 &:= (9 - (((8 - (7 - 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
16024 &:= (((9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
16025 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
16026 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 + 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
16027 &:= (9 + ((8 - (((7 + 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
16028 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) - 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2) + 1) \\
16029 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) + ((6 + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
16030 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) - ((6 + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
16031 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) + (6 + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
16032 &:= (((9 + 87) + (6 \times ((5 \times 4)^3)))/(2 + 1)) \\
16033 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((7 - (6 \times (5 \times (4 + (3 \times 21))))))) \\
16034 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(((7 \times 6) + (5^4)) \times 3) + 2)) - 1) \\
16035 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + (5^4)))) \times -(3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
16036 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 + ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
16037 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + (((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2) + 1))) \\
16038 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(((7 \times 6) + (5^4)) \times 3)) - 21)) \\
16039 &:= (-9 + (8 \times -(7 - ((65 - 4) \times (32 + 1)))))) \\
16040 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (76 \times -((5 \times 43) - (2 + 1)))) \\
16041 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -6) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
16042 &:= (9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
16043 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -6) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
16044 &:= (9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
16045 &:= (98 - ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times -(432 - 1))) \\
16046 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) - 6) \times -((5 - ((4 + 3) \times 21))) \\
16047 &:= ((987 + (((6^5) \times 4) + 3))/ - (2 \times -1)) \\
16048 &:= ((98 - (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) - 3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
16049 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2) - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16050 &:= (((12^3)/4 - 4) - ((5^6) - 7)) \times (8 - 9) & 16050 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 \times -1) \\
16051 &:= (((1 + 2) - ((3^4) - (5^6))) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 16051 &:= ((9 + (((8 + (7 + 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) \times 1) \\
16052 &:= (((-123 \times -4) + ((5^6) + 7)) + (8 \times -9)) & 16052 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - (5 - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16053 &:= (1 \times ((2 + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6 + 78) \times 9))) & 16053 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + ((5^4) + 3)))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
16054 &:= (1 + ((2 + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6 + 78) \times 9))) & 16054 &:= (9 - (((8 \times -7) + ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
16055 &:= (((1 - 2) + (34 \times 5)) \times -((6 + 7) \times -8) + 9) & 16055 &:= (98 + (((7 \times -6) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
16056 &:= (((12^3)/4 \times -5 - (6 \times 7)) - (8 \times -9)) & 16056 &:= (98 + ((7 \times -6) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
16057 &:= (1 - ((23 - (4 - 5)) \times -(678 - 9))) & 16057 &:= (98 + ((7 \times -6) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
16058 &:= ((123 + (4^5)) \times ((6 + 7) - (8 - 9))) & 16058 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5)) \times -(((4^3) - 2) \times -1)) \\
16059 &:= (((-12 - 3) \times -((4^5) - 6)) + 789) & 16059 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times -6) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
16060 &:= (12 + (34 \times -(5 - ((6 \times 78) + 9)))) & 16060 &:= (9 - (((8 \times -7) + 6) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
16061 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -34) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 16061 &:= (9 + (8 + ((765 - (4 - 3)) \times 21))) \\
16062 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 + 5)) + (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 16062 &:= (9 + (((8 \times -7) \times 6) + 5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
16063 &:= (((12^3)/4) + ((5^6) + 7)) + (8 - 9) & 16063 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times 7) \times -((65 \times 4) + (3^{2+1}))) \\
16064 &:= (((12^3)/4 - 4) - ((5^6) + 7)) \times (8 - 9) & 16064 &:= (-9 + (8 + (765 \times ((4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
16065 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -((4 - (5 - 6)) \times -(7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 16065 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) \times -((4 \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\
16066 &:= (((12^3)/4) - (((5^6) \times (7 - 8)) - 9)) & 16066 &:= (((9 - 87) + ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
16067 &:= (((12^3)/4) + ((5^6) - 7)) + (8 + 9) & 16067 &:= ((-9 + 87) + (((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16068 &:= (12 \times (3 + (4 \times ((5 \times 67) + (8 - 9)))) & 16068 &:= ((9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times (5 - ((4^3) \times 21))) \\
16069 &:= (((-12 - 3) \times 4) + (5^6)) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9)) & 16069 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 - ((5 + 43)^2)))) \times -1) \\
16070 &:= ((1234 + (5^6)) - 789) & 16070 &:= (9 - (((8 \times -7) - 6) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
16071 &:= ((1 - (2 - 34)) \times ((5 - 67) \times -8) - 9) & 16071 &:= (9 - (((8 \times -7) - 6) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
16072 &:= ((1 - 2) - ((34 \times -(5 + (6 \times 78))) + 9)) & 16072 &:= (98 + (((7 + 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3) \times -2) \times 1)) \\
16073 &:= (((12^3)/4 \times -5 - (6 \times 7)) + 89) & 16073 &:= (98 + (((7 + 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16074 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (34 - 5))) \times (6 \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) & 16074 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 - 54)))) \times (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
16075 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times -5 + ((6 - 78) \times 9)) & 16075 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((76 + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
16076 &:= (1 + ((2 + (34 \times (5 + (6 \times 78)))) - 9)) & 16076 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 \times 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3) \times -2) - 1)) \\
16077 &:= (12 - (3 \times -((4^5) \times 6) - 789)) & 16077 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((76 + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
16078 &:= (1 - (((234 + 5) - 6) \times -(78 - 9))) & 16078 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 \times 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16079 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 + 5)) - ((67 \times -8) + 9)) & 16079 &:= (98 + ((7 + ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
16080 &:= ((12 + 3) \times ((4^5) + (6 \times (7 - (8 - 9)))) & 16080 &:= (98 - ((7 + ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
16081 &:= (((12^3)/4) + ((5^6) + 7)) + (8 + 9) & 16081 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(7 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4 - 321)))) \\
16082 &:= ((1 - 23) \times -(((4 - 5) - (6 \times 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) & 16082 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
16083 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3^4) + (56 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 16083 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
16084 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times 67) - 8)) \times -9)) & 16084 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 \times 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16085 &:= (12 - ((34 \times -(5 + (6 \times 78))) + 9)) & 16085 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 \times 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
16086 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(3^4)) + ((5^6) + (7 \times 89)))) & 16086 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
16087 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3 + (4^5))) - (6 \times 7)) \times -8) + 9) & 16087 &:= (9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6 - ((5 + 43)^2)))) \times -1)) \\
16088 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3 + (4^5))) - (6 \times 7)) \times -8) + 9) & 16088 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 - ((5 + 43)^2)))) - 1)) \\
16089 &:= (((1 + 2) + (34 \times 5)) \times (6 + (78 + 9))) & 16089 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 \times 6) + ((5^4) + 3)) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
16090 &:= ((1 - 2) + ((34 \times (5 + (6 \times 78))) + 9)) & 16090 &:= (9 - (((87 - 6) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16091 &:= ((1-2) \times -((34 \times (5 + (6 \times 78))) + 9)) & 16091 &:= (98 - (7 - ((6 \times ((5 \times 4)^3)) / (2 + 1)))) \\
16092 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (((3^4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7)) - 8) \times -9)) & 16092 &:= (98 + (7 - (((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2) + 1))) \\
16093 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (((3^4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7)) - 8) \times -9)) & 16093 &:= (98 - ((7 - ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
16094 &:= (((1 - (2 + 34)) + (5^6)) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 16094 &:= (98 + (7 - (((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2) - 1))) \\
16095 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times (3 \times (4 + (5 \times (67 \times 8)))))) - 9)) & 16095 &:= (98 + (((7 - 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
16096 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) + (6 \times -(7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 16096 &:= ((98 - 7) + ((6 + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
16097 &:= (1 \times ((2 - 34) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16097 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7 + (6 \times 5))) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16098 &:= (1 + ((2 - 34) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16098 &:= ((98 - 7) + (6 + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
16099 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times (6 \times 7)) / 8) - 9)))) & 16099 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times -6) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
16100 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times (6 \times 7)) / 8) - 9)))) & 16100 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 \times 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16101 &:= (1 - (23 \times -(4 \times (56 + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 16101 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 \times 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
16102 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - 6) + (78 \times -9)) & 16102 &:= ((98 - 7) - (((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16103 &:= ((1 - 23) - (4 - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16103 &:= (98 + ((7 - ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
16104 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 \times -(((4^5) \times (6 \times 7)) / 8) - 9)) & 16104 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -((6 + 5) \times -((4^3) - (2 + 1)))) \\
16105 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(3 \times 4)) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16105 &:= (98 + (7 + ((6 \times ((5 \times 4)^3)) / (2 + 1)))) \\
16106 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times (3 + (4^5))) - (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) + 9) & 16106 &:= (((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
16107 &:= (12 - (34 - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16107 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + ((5^4) + 3)))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
16108 &:= (1 - (2 - (((34 - 5) \times 6) + 7) \times 89))) & 16108 &:= ((9 + (((8 + (7 \times 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) - 1) \\
16109 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 34) \times 5)) \times -((6 - 7) \times 89)) & 16109 &:= ((9 + (((8 + (7 \times 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times 1) \\
16110 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 + (((4^5) \times (6 \times 7)) / 8) - 9)) & 16110 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
16111 &:= ((1 - 23) + (4 + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16111 &:= ((98 + 7) - ((6 + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
16112 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((34 - 5) \times 6) + 7) \times -89)) & 16112 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 + 6)) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
16113 &:= (12 - (3 \times -(((4^5) \times (6 \times 7)) / 8) - 9)) & 16113 &:= (9 + (8 \times ((7 + (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times (32 + 1)))) \\
16114 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 + (5 \times (67 \times 8)))))) + 9) & 16114 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 + 6)) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
16115 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times (3 + 4)) - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16115 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
16116 &:= ((1 - 2) + ((3 \times -4) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16116 &:= (98 + ((7 + ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
16117 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((3 \times -4) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16117 &:= (98 - ((7 + ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
16118 &:= (1 \times (2 - (3 \times (4 - (56 \times (7 + 89)))))) & 16118 &:= (98 + (7 + (((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2) + 1))) \\
16119 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times ((4 \times -5) - (6 - (7 \times 89)))) & 16119 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times (3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
16120 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 \times -4) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16120 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 - (65 \times 4)))) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
16121 &:= (1 - ((2^{3+4}) - ((5^6) + (7 \times 89)))) & 16121 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times 6) + 5) \times -((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
16122 &:= (((12^3) / 4) + ((5^6) - 7)) - (8 \times -9)) & 16122 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times -((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
16123 &:= (1 \times (23 \times -(4 - (5 \times (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) & 16123 &:= (98 - (((7 + 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16124 &:= (1 \times ((2 - (3 + 4)) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16124 &:= (98 - (((7 + 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) \times 1)) \\
16125 &:= (1 + ((2 - (3 + 4)) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16125 &:= (98 - (((7 + 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
16126 &:= (1 + (((2 + 3)^4) / 5) \times -6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9)) & 16126 &:= (9876 - ((5^4) \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
16127 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) - (4 - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16127 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 76)) \times -(5 \times 43)) - 2) \times -1) \\
16128 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 - 4) \times -5)^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 16128 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 65)) \times (((4 \times 3)^2) \times -1)) \\
16129 &:= (12 + ((3 \times -4) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16129 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((76 + 54) - 3)^2) \times -1)) \\
16130 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times (4 \times (56 \times (7 + (8 + 9))))))) & 16130 &:= (9 + ((8 - (((76 + 54) - 3)^2)) \times -1)) \\
16131 &:= (1 + (2 + (3 \times (4 \times (56 \times (7 + (8 + 9))))))) & 16131 &:= (9 - (8 - (((76 + 54) - 3)^2) + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16132 &:= ((1+2) - ((3-4) \times ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16133 &:= ((1+2) - ((3-4) - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16134 &:= (12 - ((3+4) - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16135 &:= ((1 - (2-3)) + (4 + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16136 &:= ((1-2) \times -((3+4) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16137 &:= ((1+2) \times (3 + (4 \times (56 \times (7 + (8+9))))) \\
16138 &:= ((1 + (234 \times (((5+6) \times 7) - 8))) - 9) \\
16139 &:= (1 \times -((2 - (3 \times 4)) - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16140 &:= (1 - ((2 - (3 \times 4)) - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16141 &:= ((1-2) \times ((3 \times -4) - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16142 &:= (12 - ((3-4) - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16143 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3+4+5} \times 67)))/ - (8+9)) \\
16144 &:= ((1+2) - ((3 \times -4) - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16145 &:= (1 - (2 - ((34 - (5+6)) \times (78 \times 9)))) \\
16146 &:= ((1 - (23+4)) \times (((5+6) \times 7) - 8) \times -9) \\
16147 &:= ((1 - (2 \times 34)) \times -((5 \times -(6 - (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
16148 &:= ((12+3) + (4 + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16149 &:= (1 \times -(((2+3) \times -4) - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16150 &:= (1 - (((2+3) \times -4) - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16151 &:= (-12 + (34 + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16152 &:= (((1+2)^3) - (4 - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16153 &:= (12 - ((3 \times -4) - ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16154 &:= (((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + (5^6)) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
16155 &:= ((12+3) \times ((4^5) + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
16156 &:= ((1 + (234 \times (((5+6) \times 7) - 8))) + 9) \\
16157 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times (6 \times 7))/8) + 9)))) \\
16158 &:= (1 + (2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times (6 \times 7))/8) + 9)))) \\
16159 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 \times (4 + ((5 \times (67 \times 8)) + 9)))))) \\
16160 &:= (((1+2)^3) + (4 + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16161 &:= (1 - ((2-34) \times -(((5-67) \times 8) - 9))) \\
16162 &:= (((1 - (2-34)) + (5^6)) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
16163 &:= ((-12 \times -(3 \times (456-7))) + (8-9)) \\
16164 &:= ((1 + (((2+3)^4) + (5^6))) - (78+9)) \\
16165 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(3^4)) + ((5^6) + (78 \times 9)))) \\
16166 &:= ((1+2) + (34 + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16167 &:= (12 - (3 \times -(((4^5) \times (6 \times 7))/8) + 9))) \\
16168 &:= (1 + (((2 \times 3) - ((4^5) - 67)) \times -(8+9))) \\
16169 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times ((5-6) - (78 \times 9))) \\
16170 &:= ((12+3) \times ((4^5) - (6 \times ((7-8) \times 9)))) \\
16171 &:= (1 \times (((2+3)^4) + ((5^6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16172 &:= ((1 + (((2+3)^4) + ((5^6) - 7))) + (8 \times -9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16132 &:= (9 - (((((8 \times 7) + 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16133 &:= (9 - (((((8 \times 7) + 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2 \times 1))) \\
16134 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 43)))))) - (2 + 1)) \\
16135 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 43)))))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
16136 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -((7 + 65) \times (4 - 32))) - 1)) \\
16137 &:= (((98 + 7) - 6) \times -((54 \times -3) - (2 - 1))) \\
16138 &:= (((9 + 8) - ((7 + 6) \times ((5^4) - 3))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
16139 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -6) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
16140 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -6) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
16141 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -6) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
16142 &:= (98 - ((765 - (4 - 3)) \times -21)) \\
16143 &:= (9 + (((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times -5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16144 &:= ((9 - (((8 - 76) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) - 1) \\
16145 &:= ((9 - (((8 - 76) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times 1) \\
16146 &:= ((9 - (((8 - 76) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) + 1) \\
16147 &:= ((9 - ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5)) \times -(4 + (3 \times 21))) \\
16148 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times -((43 + 2) - 1)) \\
16149 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 - (6 - 54)) \times 3)) - 21) \\
16150 &:= (((9 - (8 + 76)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
16151 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((76 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16152 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((76 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16153 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((76 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
16154 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((76 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
16155 &:= ((9 + (87 \times 6)) + ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) - 1)) \\
16156 &:= ((9 + (87 \times 6)) - ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) \times -1)) \\
16157 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -6) - ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) + 1))) \\
16158 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 43)))))) + 21) \\
16159 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + 6) \times -(((5^4) - 3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
16160 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 + 6) \times -(((5^4) - 3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
16161 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times (6 \times (5 + 43))) + (2 + 1)))) \\
16162 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(((7 \times 6) + 5) \times 43) - 2)) - 1)) \\
16163 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -((6 + ((5 + 43)^2)) - 1))) \\
16164 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 \times -((6 + ((5 + 43)^2)) - 1))) \\
16165 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((7 + 6) \times ((5^4) - 3))) \times -2 \times 1)) \\
16166 &:= (9 + (((8 - ((7 + 6) \times ((5^4) - 3))) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16167 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((76 + 5) \times -(4 \times 3)) + 21)) \\
16168 &:= (9 + ((8 + ((76 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
16169 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((76 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2 \times 1)) \\
16170 &:= (9 + (8 + (((76 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2) + 1))) \\
16171 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times (6 + ((5 + 43)^2)))) \times -1)) \\
16172 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + 6) \times -(((5^4) - 3) \times (2 \times 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16173 &:= ((1+2) \times -((3 \times -(4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7+8)))))) + 9)) & 16173 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((7+6) \times (((5^4) - 3) \times 2))) \times -1)) \\
16174 &:= ((-1-23) + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times -(7 \times 89))) & 16174 &:= ((9-8) \times ((7 \times -(6 \times 5)) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16175 &:= (12 + (34 + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 16175 &:= ((9-8) + ((7 \times -(6 \times 5)) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16176 &:= ((1+2) + ((3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7+8)))))) \times -9)) & 16176 &:= ((9+8) - ((7+6) \times -(((5^4) - 3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
16177 &:= (1 \times -(23 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times ((7+8) \times 9)))))) & 16177 &:= ((9-8) \times -(7 \times -(6 + (((5+43)^2) + 1)))) \\
16178 &:= (1 - (23 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times ((7+8) \times 9)))))) & 16178 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times 43)) + (2 - 1))) \\
16179 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) - (6+7)) \times 8))) + 9)) & 16179 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times 43))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
16180 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) - (6+7)) \times 8))) + 9)) & 16180 &:= (((9+87) - 6) + ((5 \times 4^3)) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
16181 &:= (1 \times (((2+3)^4) + ((5^6) - (78-9)))) & 16181 &:= (98 - (((7 \times 6) + ((5 \times 4^3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16182 &:= ((1 + (23 \times 4)) \times -(((5+6) \times -(7+8)) - 9)) & 16182 &:= (98 - (((7 \times 6) + ((5 \times 4^3)) \times -2) \times 1)) \\
16183 &:= (-12 - (3 + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 89)))) & 16183 &:= (98 + ((7 \times -(6 - ((5+43)^2))) - 1)) \\
16184 &:= (1 \times (((2+3) - ((4^5) - 67)) \times -(8+9))) & 16184 &:= ((9+8) \times -(7 \times ((6+5) - ((4+3) \times 21)))) \\
16185 &:= (1 \times -((((2 - (3-4))^5) + 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 16185 &:= ((9-8) \times -((7+6) \times -(((5^4) - 3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
16186 &:= (1 - (((2 - (3-4))^5) + 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))) & 16186 &:= (9 - (8 - ((7+6) \times (((5^4) - 3) \times 2) + 1))) \\
16187 &:= (((-1-2) + (((3+4)^5) + 6)) + (7 \times -89)) & 16187 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 + ((5+43)^2)))) \times -1)) \\
16188 &:= ((1+2) \times -(((3^4) - 5) \times -((6-7) + (8 \times 9)))) & 16188 &:= (9 + (8 + ((7 \times (6 + ((5+43)^2))) + 1)) \\
16189 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) - (6+7)) \times 8) + 9))) & 16189 &:= ((9+8) - ((7+6) \times -(((5^4) - 3) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
16190 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times (45 \times 6)))) \times (7 - (8+9))) & 16190 &:= (((9 - (8 \times (7+6))) - ((5 \times 4^3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
16191 &:= (1 - ((2^3) + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 89)))) & 16191 &:= ((9+8) + ((7 \times -(6 \times 5)) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16192 &:= (((12^3)/4) + (5^6)) - ((7+8) \times -9)) & 16192 &:= ((9 - (8-7)) \times (((6 + (5+4)) \times 3)^2 - 1)) \\
16193 &:= (((1+2) + (((3+4)^5) + 6)) + (7 \times -89)) & 16193 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times 43) + 2))) \times 1 \\
16194 &:= ((1 - (2-3)) \times (((4^5) - (6+7)) \times 8) + 9)) & 16194 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times 43) + 2))) + 1 \\
16195 &:= (1 \times ((2 - (3^4)) \times -(5 \times ((6 \times 7) + (8-9)))))) & 16195 &:= (9 - (((87+6) + ((5 \times 4^3)) \times -2) \times 1)) \\
16196 &:= (1 + ((2 - (3^4)) \times -(5 \times ((6 \times 7) + (8-9)))))) & 16196 &:= (9 - (((87+6) + ((5 \times 4^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
16197 &:= (1 \times ((2-3) - ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 89)))) & 16197 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((7+6) \times ((5^4) - 3))) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
16198 &:= (1 + ((2-3) - ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 89)))) & 16198 &:= ((98-7) \times -(((6+54) \times -3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
16199 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times (((34 \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times 8)) - 9)) & 16199 &:= (((-9 - ((8+7) \times 6)) - ((5 \times 4^3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
16200 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times -(4 \times 5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 \times 9)) & 16200 &:= ((9 - (8-7)) \times -(((6 + (5+4)) \times 3)^2 \times -1)) \\
16201 &:= (1 \times -((((2-34) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times (8+9))) & 16201 &:= ((9+8) \times -((7 + ((6+5) \times (43 \times 2))) \times -1)) \\
16202 &:= ((1 - (2-3)) - (4 \times -(5 \times (6 \times ((7+8) \times 9)))))) & 16202 &:= (9 + (8 + ((7+6) \times (((5^4) - 3) \times 2) + 1))) \\
16203 &:= (-12 + (345 \times -((6 \times 7) - 89))) & 16203 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times 54)) - 321) \\
16204 &:= ((1 + (((2+3)^4) + (5^6))) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & 16204 &:= (((9 + (87+6)) + ((5 \times 4^3)) \times -2) \times -1) \\
16205 &:= (1 \times ((2+3) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times ((7+8) \times 9)))))) & 16205 &:= (98 + ((7+6) \times -((5 - (4^3)) \times 21))) \\
16206 &:= ((1+2) + (3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times ((7+8) \times 9)))))) & 16206 &:= (((9+8) - (7 \times 65)) \times ((4 \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
16207 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times (3^{4+5}) - 6) \times 7)) / - (8+9)) & 16207 &:= (((-9 - 876) / 5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
16208 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^4) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16208 &:= ((9 - (8-7)) \times (((6 + (5+4)) \times 3)^2 + 1)) \\
16209 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^4) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16209 &:= (9 + ((8+7) \times -((6+54) \times (3-21)))) \\
16210 &:= ((1-2) \times -((3^4) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16210 &:= (((9+8) - (((7+6) \times (5^4)) - 3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
16211 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3 \times ((4+5) \times 67)) - 8) \times 9))) & 16211 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (76-5))) \times (4 - (32+1))) \\
16212 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times (3^{4+5})) + 6) \times 7) / (8+9)) & 16212 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times (65+4))) \times -(32+1))) \\
16213 &:= ((1+2) + ((3^4) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16213 &:= (9 - (8 - ((765 + (4+3)) \times 21)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16214 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 - 4))^5)) \times -(67 \times -(8 - 9))) \\
16215 &:= (12 + (3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) \\
16216 &:= ((1 - ((2 - ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times 78)) - 9) \\
16217 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((34 \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
16218 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(((34 \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
16219 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times 3)^4) + ((5^6) - (78 \times 9)))) \\
16220 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + (5^6))) + (78 \times -9)) \\
16221 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 - ((4^5) - 67)) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
16222 &:= (12 + ((3^4) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16223 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3 - (4^5))) + (6 + 7)) \times 8) + 9)) \\
16224 &:= ((1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times -((5 \times (6 - (7 - 8))) - 9)) \\
16225 &:= (1 \times -((2 - ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))))) \times 9))) \\
16226 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))))) \times 9)) \\
16227 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times -(4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))))) - 9)) \\
16228 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) \times -4) + ((5^6) + (7 \times 89)))) \\
16229 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))))) \times 9)) \\
16230 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))))) \times 9)) \\
16231 &:= (1 \times -(((234 + 56) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9)) \\
16232 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) - 6)))) \times -(7 - (8 - 9))) \\
16233 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times 78) - 9)) \\
16234 &:= ((1 - ((2 - ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times 78)) + 9) \\
16235 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -(3 + 4)) + ((5^6) + (7 \times 89)))) \\
16236 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times -7) - (8 - 9))) \\
16237 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) \times 4) + (5^6)) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
16238 &:= (1 \times -(23 \times -(4 - ((5 - 6) \times (78 \times 9)))))) \\
16239 &:= (12 - ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))))) \times -9)) \\
16240 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(((3 + 4) - 5)^{6+7}) - (8 \times 9))) \\
16241 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3 + 4) - 5)^{6+7}) - (8 \times 9))) \\
16242 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) - (((5^6) \times (7 - 8)) + 9)) \\
16243 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) + ((5^6) - (7 - 8)))) - 9) \\
16244 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3)^4) + ((5^6) - 7)) \times (8 - 9)) \\
16245 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) + ((5^6) - 7))) - (8 - 9)) \\
16246 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) - (4 - ((5^6) + (7 \times 89)))) \\
16247 &:= (1 + ((2 \times (3 - 4)) + ((5^6) + (7 \times 89)))) \\
16248 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) - 6)))) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
16249 &:= (((1 - (2 - 3))^{4 \times 5 - 6}) + ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
16250 &:= ((1 - (23 + 4)) \times (5 \times -(6 + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
16251 &:= (1 \times ((2 - (3 - 4)) + ((5^6) + (7 \times 89)))) \\
16252 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times -9)) \\
16253 &:= (1 \times -((2 - (3 + 4)) - ((5^6) + (7 \times 89)))) \\
16254 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -(((4 + 5) \times -67) - (8 - 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16214 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times -((4 + 32) - 1))) \\
16215 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -((5 \times -4) - (3^{2+1}))) \\
16216 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 + 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16217 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times (7 + 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times 1) \\
16218 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 + 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
16219 &:= (98 - (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times -((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
16220 &:= (-9 + (((8 - (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) - 3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16221 &:= (9 - (((8 + 765) - (4 - 3)) \times -21)) \\
16222 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 6) + (5 - 4)) \times -32) - 1)) \\
16223 &:= (9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times -5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16224 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 + (5 \times 4))^{3-2+1})) \\
16225 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) + (3 + 21))) \\
16226 &:= (98 + (((76 + 54) - 3)^2) - 1)) \\
16227 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
16228 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2 \times 1))) \\
16229 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2) - 1)) \\
16230 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((5^5) / -4) + 321)) \\
16231 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 43)) + 2)))) \times -1) \\
16232 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 - (65 \times (4 \times 3))) \times -21)) \\
16233 &:= (9 + ((8 - (76 \times (5 + 4))) \times -3) + 21)) \\
16234 &:= (9 - (8 + ((7 - (65 \times (4 \times 3))) \times 21))) \\
16235 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -7 - (((6 \times 5) + (4 - 3))^2) + 1)) \\
16236 &:= (9 + (((8 - (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) - 3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
16237 &:= (9 + ((8 - (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) - 3)) \times -2 \times 1)) \\
16238 &:= (9 + (((8 - (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) - 3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16239 &:= (((9 + 8) - (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) + 3) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
16240 &:= ((98 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 + (4 \times 3))^2) + 1)) \\
16241 &:= ((9 + (8 \times 76)) + ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) - 1)) \\
16242 &:= (((9 - 8) - (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) - 3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
16243 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) - 3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16244 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) - 3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
16245 &:= (9 + ((8 - (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) - 3) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
16246 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) - 3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
16247 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + (((6 + (5 + 4)) \times 3)^2)))) \times -1) \\
16248 &:= (((9 - 8) - ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) \times -3) - (2 - 1)) \\
16249 &:= (98 - (((76 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16250 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + 6) \times -((5^4) \times (3 - (2 - 1)))))) \\
16251 &:= ((9 - (((8 + ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) - 3) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
16252 &:= (((9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) \times (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
16253 &:= (9 - (((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) + 4) \times -32) - 1)) \\
16254 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 54)) \times -3 \times -2 \times 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16255 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (34 \times (5 \times 6))) - 7) \times -8) + 9)) & 16255 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) + 3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16256 &:= ((1 - (((2 + 3)^4) + ((5^6) + 7))) \times (8 - 9)) & 16256 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) + 3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
16257 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3)^4) + ((5^6) + 7)) \times (8 - 9)) & 16257 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) + 3) \times -2) - 1)) \\
16258 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3)^4) + ((5^6) + 7)) \times (8 - 9)) & 16258 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) + 3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
16259 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) + ((5^6) + 7))) - (8 - 9)) & 16259 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) - 65) \times -(4 + 321))) \\
16260 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) - (((5^6) \times (7 - 8)) - 9)) & 16260 &:= (9 + ((8 + (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) - 3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
16261 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) + ((5^6) - (7 - 8)))) + 9) & 16261 &:= (9 - ((8 + (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) - 3) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
16262 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 + 4)) - ((5^6) + (7 \times 89)))) & 16262 &:= (9 + (8 + (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) - 3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
16263 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 \times -4) - ((5^6) + (7 \times 89)))) & 16263 &:= (9 \times -(8 - ((7 - (6 - 54)) \times (32 + 1)))) \\
16264 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (3 - 4))^5) \times 67) - (8 + 9)) & 16264 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 + (((6 + (5 + 4)) \times 3)^2))) + 1)) \\
16265 &:= (((1 - (2 - 3))^{4 \times 5 - 6}) + (7 \times -(8 + 9))) & 16265 &:= (9 + (8 \times (7 + (((6 + (5 + 4)) \times 3)^2 \times 1)))) \\
16266 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(3 - (((4 \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 16266 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 + (((6 + (5 + 4)) \times 3)^2))) - 1)) \\
16267 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(3 - (((4 \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 16267 &:= (9 + (8 + ((7 + 6) \times ((5^4) \times (3 - (2 - 1)))))) \\
16268 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((3 + 4) \times (5 + ((6 + 7) \times 89)))) & 16268 &:= (9 - (((8 + ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) - 3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16269 &:= ((1 - (2 - 34)) \times -((5 + 6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 16269 &:= (9 - (((8 + ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) - 3) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
16270 &:= (1 \times -((2 - 3) - (((4^5) - 67) \times (8 + 9)))) & 16270 &:= (9 - (((8 + ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) - 3) \times -2) - 1)) \\
16271 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) - 6)) - 7) \times -8) + 9) & 16271 &:= (98 - (((7 + 6) \times -(((5^4) - 3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
16272 &:= (1 - (((2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) - 6)) - 7) \times -8) + 9) & 16272 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) + 3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16273 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (34 \times (5 \times 6))) - 7) \times -8) - 9) & 16273 &:= (((9 + 8) + (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) + 3) \times 2)) \times 1) \\
16274 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (34 \times (5 \times 6))) - 7) \times -8) - 9) & 16274 &:= (9 + (8 + (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) + 3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
16275 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) + ((5^6) + (7 + 8)))) + 9) & 16275 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) \times -(3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
16276 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times ((5 \times (6 - (7 - 8))) - 9)) & 16276 &:= ((9 - 87) + ((6 \times -5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16277 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) + (((4^5) - 67) \times (8 + 9)))) & 16277 &:= (((9 + 8) + (76 \times 5)) \times -((43 - 2) \times -1)) \\
16278 &:= (1 \times -((2 - ((3 + 4)^5) - ((67 \times 8) - 9))) & 16278 &:= (9 - (87 \times -(6 + (543 / (2 + 1)))))) \\
16279 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 + 4)^5) - ((67 \times 8) - 9))) & 16279 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 - ((7 \times (65 \times 4)) - 3))) + 2) \times -1) \\
16280 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3 - (4^5))) + 6)) \times -(7 - (8 - 9))) & 16280 &:= (9 - (((8 + (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) + 3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16281 &:= ((1 + (((2 - (3 - 4))^5) \times 67)) + (8 - 9)) & 16281 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 - (6 \times (5 \times 4))) \times (3 - 21)))) \\
16282 &:= ((1 + (((2 - (3 - 4))^5) \times 67)) \times -(8 - 9)) & 16282 &:= (9 - (((8 + (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) + 3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
16283 &:= (1 \times (((((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) - (6^7)) / -(8 + 9))) & 16283 &:= (98 - ((7 + 6) \times -(((5^4) - 3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
16284 &:= (1 + (((((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) - (6^7)) / -(8 + 9))) & 16284 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) - (5 - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16285 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 + 4)^5) - (6 \times (78 + 9)))) & 16285 &:= (98 - ((76 \times -((5 \times 43) - 2)) + 1)) \\
16286 &:= (1 - (2 - ((34 \times 5) + (6 + 7) \times 89))) & 16286 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((7 + 6) \times 5) - ((4^{3 + 2}) - 1))) \\
16287 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times -(6 + (78 \times 9)))) & 16287 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 543))) / -(2 + 1)) \\
16288 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times (3 - ((4^5) - 6))) - 7) \times 8)) - 9) & 16288 &:= (9 + (((8 + (7 + 6)) \times -5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16289 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3) - (4^5)) \times (6 - (7 - (8 + 9)))) & 16289 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(7 - (6 \times (5 - ((4 + 3)^{2 + 1})))))) \\
16290 &:= (((1 - 23) + (4^{(-5 + 6) \times 7})) + (8 \times -9)) & 16290 &:= ((9 + ((87 - 6) \times (5 \times 4))) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\
16291 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times 3^4)) - (((5^6) + 7) / 8) \times -9) & 16291 &:= ((-98 \times -7) - ((6 \times -((54 - 3)^2)) + 1)) \\
16292 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + (5^6))) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 16292 &:= (((-9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times -543) - (2 \times -1)) \\
16293 &:= (1 + (23 + (((4^5) - 67) \times (8 + 9)))) & 16293 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 543))) / (2 + 1)) \\
16294 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 - (8 - 9)))) & 16294 &:= (9 + (((8 \times -(7 + 6)) + 5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16295 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 - (8 - 9)))) & 16295 &:= ((9 - 87) - ((6 + 5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16296 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3 - (4^5))) + 6)) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) & 16296 &:= (9876 - (5 \times -(4 \times 321))) \\
16297 &:= (((1 - (2 - 3))^{4 \times 5 - 6}) - (78 + 9)) & 16297 &:= (((9 - 8) - (76 \times 5)) \times (43 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
16298 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) + (5^6))) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & 16298 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times -6) - 5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
16299 &:= (1 - (((2 - (3 - 4))^5) \times -67) - (8 + 9)) & 16299 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 543)) / - (2 + 1))) \\
16300 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - 6) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9)) & 16300 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) + (3^{2+1}))) \\
16301 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 + (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) - 89)) & 16301 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) - (65 \times -(4 \times (3 \times 21)))) \\
16302 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(((3 - ((4^5) + (6 - 7))) \times 8) + 9))) & 16302 &:= ((9 - 87) \times -((6 - (5 \times 43)) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
16303 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(((3 - ((4^5) + (6 - 7))) \times 8) + 9))) & 16303 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((76 + 5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16304 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) - (4^5)) \times -(6 - (7 - (8 + 9)))))) & 16304 &:= ((9 - (8 + 76)) - (5 - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16305 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3 - ((4^5) - 6))) - 7) \times 8) - 9)) & 16305 &:= ((9 - 87) - ((6 - 5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16306 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times (3 - ((4^5) - 6))) - 7) \times 8)) + 9) & 16306 &:= (((9 + (87 \times 6)) - 5) \times -(((4^3) / -2) + 1)) \\
16307 &:= (1 + (((2 \times -3) + (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) - (8 \times 9))) & 16307 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6 \times -5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16308 &:= (((1 - 2) + (((3 + 4)^5) + 6)) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 16308 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times -6) + 5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
16309 &:= ((12 + ((3 + 4)^5)) - (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 16309 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 \times -5) + (4 - 321))) \\
16310 &:= (1 \times - (2 - (((34 - (5 \times 6))^7) - (8 \times 9)))) & 16310 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times (6 + (5 \times (4 + 321)))) \\
16311 &:= (1 - (2 - (((34 - (5 \times 6))^7) - (8 \times 9)))) & 16311 &:= (((-9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times -543) + 21) \\
16312 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 - ((4^5) + (6 - 7))) \times 8))) - 9) & 16312 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + 65) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16313 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(((3 + 4) - 5)^{6+7})) + (8 \times 9))) & 16313 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((76 - 5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16314 &:= (1 \times ((2 + ((34 - (5 \times 6))^7)) - (8 \times 9))) & 16314 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((76 - 5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16315 &:= (1 + ((2 + ((34 - (5 \times 6))^7)) - (8 \times 9))) & 16315 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + 6) \times -(((5^4) + 3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
16316 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) + ((5^6) - 7))) - (8 \times -9)) & 16316 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 + 6) \times -(((5^4) + 3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
16317 &:= ((1 + 2) \times - (3 - (((4^5) \times 6) - (78 \times 9)))) & 16317 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) \times ((4 \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
16318 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 \times 4) - ((5^6) + (78 \times 9)))) & 16318 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 \times (65 \times 4))) \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\
16319 &:= (((1 - (2 - 3))^{4 \times 5 - 6}) - ((7 \times 8) + 9)) & 16319 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((76 \times -(5 \times 43)) + 21)) \\
16320 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times -((6 + 7) \times 8) + 9)) & 16320 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times (((4 + 3)^2) - 1)) \\
16321 &:= (12 - (3 - ((4^{(-5+6) \times 7}) - (8 \times 9)))) & 16321 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((765 \times (4^3)) / - (2 + 1))) \\
16322 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) - 89 & 16322 &:= (9 + (((8 - ((7 + 6) \times ((5^4) + 3))) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16323 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 \times (4 \times 56)) + 7) \times -8) - 9)) & 16323 &:= (((9 + 8) - (76 \times (5 \times 43))) \times -(2 - 1)) \\
16324 &:= ((1 - 23) \times -((4^5) - (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) & 16324 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times (6 + 5))) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16325 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) - (4 - ((5^6) + (78 \times 9)))) & 16325 &:= (((9 + 8) - ((76 \times (5 \times 43)) + 2)) \times -1) \\
16326 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 - 4) \times -5)^6) + (78 \times 9))) & 16326 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) - (5 - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16327 &:= (((12 + 3) + (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) + (8 \times -9)) & 16327 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + 6) \times -(((5^4) + 3) \times 2)) + 1)) \\
16328 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 - (4^5)))) \times ((6 - 78) / 9)) & 16328 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 + 6) \times -(((5^4) + 3) \times 2)) + 1)) \\
16329 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times (3 - 4)) - ((5^6) + (78 \times 9)))) & 16329 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + 6) \times -(((5^4) + 3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
16330 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3 - ((4^5) + (6 - 7))) \times 8))) + 9) & 16330 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 + 6) \times -(((5^4) + 3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
16331 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 - 4) - ((5^6) + (78 \times 9)))) & 16331 &:= (98 + ((7 - (65 \times (4 \times 3))) \times -21)) \\
16332 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) + (6 \times -(7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 16332 &:= (9 + (8 + ((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) + 3) \times 2) - 1))) \\
16333 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 + 4)^5) - (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) & 16333 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (65 \times -(4 \times (3 \times 21)))) \\
16334 &:= (1 \times - (2 + ((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 - (7 - (8 + 9)))))) & 16334 &:= (9 + (8 + ((765 + (4 \times 3)) \times 21))) \\
16335 &:= (1 - (2 + ((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 - (7 - (8 + 9)))))) & 16335 &:= ((98 - (((7 + 6) - 5) \times 4^3)) / (2 \times -1)) \\
16336 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times (3 - (4^5))) + (6 - 7)) \times 8)) - 9) & 16336 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) + (5 + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16337 &:= (((1 - (2 - 3))^{4 \times 5 - 6}) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & 16337 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6 - 5) \times -(4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16338 &:= ((1 - 2) - ((3 \times -4) - ((5^6) + (78 \times 9)))) & 16338 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 6)) - (5 - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16339 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) + (8 \times -9) & 16339 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((76 \times (5 \times 43)) - 2)) \times -1)) \\
16340 &:= (12 - ((3 - 4) - ((5^6) + (78 \times 9)))) & 16340 &:= (9 - (8 - ((76 \times (5 \times 43)) - (2 - 1)))) \\
16341 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 + 4)) - ((5^6) + (78 \times 9)))) & 16341 &:= (98 - (((((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) - 3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16342 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((34 + 5) \times 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9))) & 16342 &:= (98 - (((((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) - 3) \times -2) \times 1)) \\
16343 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -((3 - ((4^5) - (6 - 7))) \times 8)) - 9)) & 16343 &:= (98 - (((((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) - 3) \times -2) - 1)) \\
16344 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -((3 - ((4^5) - (6 - 7))) \times 8)) - 9)) & 16344 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16345 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3 - (4^5)) \times ((6 - 7) \times 8))) - 9)) & 16345 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times -2) \times 1)) \\
16346 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -((3 - (4^5)) \times ((6 - 7) \times 8))) - 9)) & 16346 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times -2) - 1)) \\
16347 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((34 + 5) \times 6) - 7) \times -(8 \times 9)) & 16347 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 \times -6) + 5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16348 &:= (12 + ((3 - (4^5)) \times -(6 - (7 - (8 + 9)))) & 16348 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((7 \times -6) + 5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16349 &:= ((((-1 + 2345) - 6) \times 7) - 8) - 9 & 16349 &:= (((-9 \times -87) + (((6^5) + (4 + 3)) \times 2)) \times 1) \\
16350 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -(((4^5) + (6 - 7)) \times -8) + 9) & 16350 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times ((5 + (43 + 2)) \times -1)) \\
16351 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3 + 45)) \times -((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) & 16351 &:= (-9 - (8 \times -((7 \times ((65 \times 4) + 32)) + 1))) \\
16352 &:= (((1 - (2 - 3)) - (4^5)) \times -(6 - (7 - (8 + 9)))) & 16352 &:= (9 - (((8 + ((7 + 6) \times ((5^4) + 3))) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16353 &:= (((1 + 2) - ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9))) & 16353 &:= (98 - (((((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) + 3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16354 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times (3 - (4^5))) + (6 - 7)) \times 8)) + 9) & 16354 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times ((6 \times -5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16355 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) & 16355 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + ((6 \times -5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16356 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) & 16356 &:= (9 + ((8 + (76 \times (5 \times 43))) - (2 - 1))) \\
16357 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) \times (8 - 9) & 16357 &:= (9 - ((8 + (76 \times (5 \times 43))) \times -2) - 1)) \\
16358 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + (4 + ((5^6) + (78 \times 9)))) & 16358 &:= (9 - (((8 - (7 - 6)) \times 5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16359 &:= (1 \times (((2^3) \times 4) + ((5^6) + (78 \times 9)))) & 16359 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((76 \times (5 \times 43)) + 2)) \times -1)) \\
16360 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times -9)) & 16360 &:= ((9 - (((8^{(7-6) \times 5}) / 4) - 3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
16361 &:= (((1 - 23) + (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) + (8 - 9)) & 16361 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times 54) - 32)))) \times 1) \\
16362 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 + 5)) - (6 \times -((7 + 8) \times 9))) & 16362 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) + ((6 \times -5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16363 &:= (((1 - 23) + (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) - 8) + 9 & 16363 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times (65 \times (4 + 32)))) \times -1) \\
16364 &:= (1 \times (((2^{3 \times 4}) - 5) \times -((6 + 7) - (8 + 9)))) & 16364 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((7 \times -6) + 5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16365 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times (3 + (((4^5) + (6 - 7)) \times 8))) - 9)) & 16365 &:= ((9 + (87 \times (((6 \times 5) + (4^3)) \times 2))) \times 1) \\
16366 &:= (1 + ((2 \times (3 + (((4^5) + (6 - 7)) \times 8))) - 9)) & 16366 &:= ((9 - ((8^{(7-6) \times 5}) / 4)) \times -3) - (2 - 1)) \\
16367 &:= ((1 - ((2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - 7))) \times 8)) / -9) & 16367 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6 \times -5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16368 &:= (((1 + (2^{3 \times 4}) - 5) \times -((6 + 7) - (8 + 9))) & 16368 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 + 5) \times ((4^3) - (2 \times 1)))) \\
16369 &:= (((12 + 3) - (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) \times (8 - 9)) & 16369 &:= ((9 - (((8^{(7-6) \times 5}) - (4 \times 3)) / 2)) \times -1) \\
16370 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) + (5^6))) - (7 \times -(8 + 9))) & 16370 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (((7 \times 6) + (5 + 4)) \times -321)) \\
16371 &:= (1 - (((2 - (3 - 4))^5) \times -67) - 89) & 16371 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times (65 \times 4))) \times (3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
16372 &:= (1 \times -(((2345 - 6) \times -7) - (8 - 9))) & 16372 &:= ((9 - (((8^{(7-6) \times 5}) / 4) + 3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
16373 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 + (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) - (8 + 9))) & 16373 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -6) - (5 - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
16374 &:= (((1 - (2 - 3))^{4 \times 5 - 6}) + (7 - (8 + 9))) & 16374 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - 6) - (5 - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
16375 &:= (((1 - (2 - 3))^{4 \times 5 - 6}) + ((7 - 8) \times 9)) & 16375 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times 6) / -5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
16376 &:= (((1 - (2 - 3))^{4 \times 5 - 6}) - (7 - (8 - 9))) & 16376 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + 6) - 5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16377 &:= (((1 - (2 - 3))^{4 \times 5 - 6}) - (7 \times -(8 - 9))) & 16377 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times ((5 \times -((4^3) - 2)) + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16378 &:= ((1+2) + (((3-(4-5))^{6-7+8}) - 9)) \\
16379 &:= (1 \times (((2+3) - (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) \times (8-9))) \\
16380 &:= (((1+2) - (3^4)) \times -(5 \times -(6 \times (7 \times (8-9)))) \\
16381 &:= ((-1 - (((2^3) \times 4) - (5^6))) + 789) \\
16382 &:= ((1 - (2-3)) \times -(((4^5) - (6-7)) \times -8) + 9) \\
16383 &:= ((1 - (2^{3 \times 4 - 5})) \times (6 - ((7+8) \times 9))) \\
16384 &:= ((1+2) + ((3 - (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) \times (8-9))) \\
16385 &:= ((1+2) - (3 - ((4^{(-5+6) \times 7}) - (8-9)))) \\
16386 &:= ((1 - (2-3)) \times -(((4^5) + (6-7)) \times -8) - 9) \\
16387 &:= (12 + (((3 - (4-5))^{6-7+8}) - 9)) \\
16388 &:= ((1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times (5 - (6 / ((7+8) - 9)))) \\
16389 &:= ((1+2) + (3 + ((4^{(-5+6) \times 7}) + (8-9)))) \\
16390 &:= ((1+2) - ((3 + (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) \times (8-9))) \\
16391 &:= (((1 - (2-3))^{4 \times 5 - 6}) + (7 \times -(8-9))) \\
16392 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) + (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) \times (8-9))) \\
16393 &:= (((1 - (2-3))^{4 \times 5 - 6}) - ((7-8) \times 9)) \\
16394 &:= (((1+2)^3) + ((4^{(-5+6) \times 7}) - 8) - 9) \\
16395 &:= ((12 + ((34 - (5 \times 6))^7)) + (8-9)) \\
16396 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(3 - (((4^{56/7}) / 8) + 9)))) \\
16397 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) - (6-7)) \times 8))) + 9)) \\
16398 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) - (6-7)) \times 8))) + 9)) \\
16399 &:= (12 - ((3 + (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) \times (8-9))) \\
16400 &:= (((1-2) + (3^4)) \times -(5 \times -((6 \times 7) + (8-9)))) \\
16401 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + 7))) \times 8)) / 9) \\
16402 &:= ((1 - (2-3)) \times -(((4^{56/7}) / -8) - 9)) \\
16403 &:= (((1+2) + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + 7) \times 8)) / 9) \\
16404 &:= ((12 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + 7) \times 8)) / 9) \\
16405 &:= (((1+2)^3) + ((4^5) - (6^7))) / -(8+9) \\
16406 &:= (((1-23) - (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) \times (8-9)) \\
16407 &:= ((1+2) + (3 + ((4^{(-5+6) \times 7}) + (8+9)))) \\
16408 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + 5)) \times -((6+7) - (8+9))) \\
16409 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((3+4) - 5)^{6+7}) + 8) - 9)) \\
16410 &:= (((1+2)^3) + ((4^{(-5+6) \times 7}) + 8) - 9) \\
16411 &:= (((1+2)^3) + (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) \times -(8-9) \\
16412 &:= (((1+2)^3) + ((4^{(-5+6) \times 7}) - 8) + 9) \\
16413 &:= ((12 + ((34 - (5 \times 6))^7)) + (8+9)) \\
16414 &:= (1 - (((2+3) - 4) - ((5^6) + 789))) \\
16415 &:= ((1 - (2+34)) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
16416 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times (3 + (4^5))) + (6-7)) \times 8)) - 9) \\
16417 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) - (5 \times -(6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16378 &:= ((9-8) + ((7 \times -(6-5)) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16379 &:= ((9-8) - ((7 - (6-5)) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16380 &:= (((9-8) - (((7+6) - 5)^4)) \times -((3+2) - 1)) \\
16381 &:= ((9 - (8 - (7 - 6))) - (5 - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16382 &:= (9 + (((8-7) \times -(6+5)) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16383 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times 6)) / 5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16384 &:= (((9-8)^7) - 6) + (5 + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16385 &:= (((9-8)^7) \times 6) - (5 - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16386 &:= (((9-8)^7) + 6) - (5 - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16387 &:= (9 - (((8^{(7-6) \times 5}) - (4 \times 3)) / -(2 \times 1))) \\
16388 &:= (((9 + (8^{(7-6) \times 5})) - (4-3)) / -(2 \times -1)) \\
16389 &:= ((9 + ((8-7)^6)) - (5 - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16390 &:= ((9-8) - (((7-6) \times -5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16391 &:= ((9 - (8 - (7 - 6))) + (5 + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16392 &:= ((9-8) - ((7 \times -(6-5)) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16393 &:= ((9 + (8^{(7-6) \times 5})) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
16394 &:= ((9+8) + ((7 \times -(6-5)) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16395 &:= (((9-8)^7) \times 6) + (5 + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16396 &:= (((9-8)^7) + 6) + (5 + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16397 &:= (((9 + (8+7)) - 6) - (5 - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16398 &:= ((9 + (((8^{(7-6) \times 5}) + (4 \times 3)) / 2)) - 1) \\
16399 &:= ((9 + ((8-7)^6)) + (5 + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16400 &:= (9 - (((8^{(7-6) \times 5}) + (4 \times 3)) / -2) - 1) \\
16401 &:= ((9+8) - (((((76 \times 5) + 4) / 3)^2) \times -1)) \\
16402 &:= ((9 + ((8^{(7-6) \times 5}) / 4)) \times (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
16403 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 \times -((5 \times (4 \times 3)) - 2)) - 1)) \\
16404 &:= ((9+8) - (7 \times -((65 \times (4+32)) + 1))) \\
16405 &:= (9 - ((8 \times (((7+6) - 5)^4) + 3)) / -(2 \times 1)) \\
16406 &:= ((9+8) - (((7-6) \times -5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16407 &:= ((9-8) \times -((7 - (6 \times 5)) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16408 &:= ((9-8) - ((7 - (6 \times 5)) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16409 &:= ((9 + (8+7)) + ((6-5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16410 &:= (987 - (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
16411 &:= (9 - (((8+7) \times 6) / -5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
16412 &:= (987 - (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
16413 &:= (98 - ((7+6) \times -(((5^4) + 3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
16414 &:= (((9-8)^7) \times -((6 \times -5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16415 &:= (((9-8)^7) - ((6 \times -5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16416 &:= (((9 - (8 - (7 - 6)))^5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
16417 &:= ((98 - ((7+6) \times 5)) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16418 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + (5^6))) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 16418 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 + 6)) \times -5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16419 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 \times -((4 + (5 + 67)) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 16419 &:= (9 - (((8 \times -7) + (6 \times 5)) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16420 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - (6 \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 16420 &:= (((9 - 8) + (76 \times 54)) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
16421 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))) & 16421 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times -6) + 5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16422 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times ((5 - (6 - 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) & 16422 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 \times -6) + 5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16423 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((34 \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times 8)) + 9)) & 16423 &:= (((-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times 6)) - ((5^4) \times 3))) + 2) \times -1) \\
16424 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(((34 \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times 8)) + 9)) & 16424 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 - (6 \times 5)) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16425 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times -(((5 \times (6 + 7)) + 8) \times -9)) & 16425 &:= (98 - (((7 + 6) \times -(((5^4) + 3) \times 2)) + 1)) \\
16426 &:= (1 + ((23 - (((4 \times 56) + 7) \times 8)) \times -9)) & 16426 &:= (98 - ((7 + 6) \times -(((5^4) + 3) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
16427 &:= (12 - ((3 - 4) - ((5^6) + 789))) & 16427 &:= (98 - (((7 + 6) \times -(((5^4) + 3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
16428 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + ((4^{(-5+6) \times 7} + 8)) + 9) & 16428 &:= ((98 + (7 + 6)) \times ((5 + ((4 \times 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
16429 &:= ((12 + ((3 + 4)^5)) - (6 \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 16429 &:= (-98 - ((7 + (65 \times (4 \times 3))) \times -21)) \\
16430 &:= (1 \times (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) - (6 - 7)) \times 8) - 9)) & 16430 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times (5 \times -((4^3) - (2 \times 1)))) \\
16431 &:= (((1 - (2 - 3))^{4 \times 5 - 6} - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & 16431 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times -6) - 5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16432 &:= (1 + (((2 \times (3 - (4^5))) - (6 + 7)) \times -8) - 9)) & 16432 &:= (9 - ((8 - ((7 \times 6) + 5)) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16433 &:= (((((12^3) + (4^5)) \times 6) - 7) + (8 \times -9)) & 16433 &:= ((98 + (((7 + 6) - 5) \times 4^3)) / - (2 \times -1)) \\
16434 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times (3 + (4^5))) + (6 - 7)) \times 8)) + 9) & 16434 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (76 \times (5 + 4))) + 3) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
16435 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 + (4^5)) \times -(6 - (7 - (8 + 9))))) & 16435 &:= ((98 - (7 \times 6)) - (5 - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16436 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((34 \times 56) - 78) \times 9))) & 16436 &:= (9 - (((8 \times ((76 \times 54) + 3)) / - 2) + 1)) \\
16437 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (4 - ((5^6) + 789))) & 16437 &:= (9 - ((8 \times ((76 \times 54) + 3)) / - (2 \times 1))) \\
16438 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3 \times 4)) - ((5^6) + 789))) & 16438 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 \times -6) + 5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16439 &:= (1 \times (((2 - 34) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times -(8 + 9)) & 16439 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((7 \times -((6 \times ((5 + 4) - 32))) + 1)) \\
16440 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -(((4^5) \times (6 - 7)) - (8 \times 9))) & 16440 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 76) \times 5)) \times (4 \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
16441 &:= (1 \times -((2 - ((3 + 4) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 78)) + 9)))) & 16441 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((76 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
16442 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (((34 \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times 8))) + 9) & 16442 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((76 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)) + 2)) - 1)) \\
16443 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times ((4 \times -5) + (6 + (7 \times 89)))) & 16443 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 - 65) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16444 &:= (12 - ((3 + (4^5)) \times -(6 - (7 - (8 + 9))))) & 16444 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (7 \times (65 \times 4))) \times (3^2)) + 1)) \\
16445 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + (4 + ((5^6) + 789))) & 16445 &:= (98 + (((7 \times -6) + 5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16446 &:= ((1 - 23) - (((4 \times 5) + (6^7)) / - (8 + 9))) & 16446 &:= ((98 + ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) \times (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
16447 &:= (((((12^3) + (4^5)) \times 6) + 7) + (8 \times -9)) & 16447 &:= (((9 - 8) - (765 \times 43)) / (2 \times -1)) \\
16448 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) - ((4^{(-5+6) \times 7} + (8 \times 9)))) & 16448 &:= (9 - (((8 \times -7) + (6 - 5)) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16449 &:= (((1 - (2 - 3))^{4 \times 5 - 6} + ((7 \times 8) + 9)) & 16449 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + 6) \times -5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16450 &:= (1 + (((2 \times (3 - (4^5))) - (6 + 7)) \times -8) + 9)) & 16450 &:= (9 - ((8 - ((7 + 6) \times 5)) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16451 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) - ((4^{(-5+6) \times 7} + (8 \times 9)))) & 16451 &:= ((((-98 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times -4) - (32 + 1)) \\
16452 &:= ((1 - 2) - (3 - ((4^{(-5+6) \times 7} + (8 \times 9)))) & 16452 &:= (((9 + 8) + (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
16453 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (3 - ((4^{(-5+6) \times 7} + (8 \times 9)))) & 16453 &:= (987 - (((6^5) - 43) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
16454 &:= (1 \times -((2 - (((34 - (5 \times 6))^7) + (8 \times 9)))) & 16454 &:= (((9 - (8 - 7)) + (6 \times 5)) \times (432 + 1)) \\
16455 &:= ((12 + 3) \times ((4^5) - ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9)))) & 16455 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((76 - 5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16456 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 - ((4^{(-5+6) \times 7} + (8 \times 9)))) & 16456 &:= ((9 - (8 - 76)) - (5 - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16457 &:= ((1 + (((2345 + 6) \times 7) + 8)) - 9) & 16457 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) + (65 + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16458 &:= (((1 + 2) - (3^4)) \times ((5 \times -(6 \times 7)) + (8 - 9))) & 16458 &:= (9 - (((8 - 7) \times -65) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16459 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - (3 \times 45)) + (6^7))/ - (8 + 9))) \\
16460 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) - (((4 \times 5) + (6^7))/(8 + 9))) \\
16461 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4^5)) + ((6 \times - (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\
16462 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 + ((4^{(-5+6) \times 7}) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
16463 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times (3 + ((4^5) + 6))) - 7) \times 8) - 9) \\
16464 &:= (1 + (((2 \times (3 + ((4^5) + 6))) - 7) \times 8) - 9) \\
16465 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4^5)) + ((6 \times - (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\
16466 &:= (1 \times -(((23 - (4 + 5)) - (6^7))/(8 + 9))) \\
16467 &:= (1 - (((23 - (4 + 5)) - (6^7))/(8 + 9))) \\
16468 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 - (4 \times (5 + (6 \times 7)))) \times -89)) \\
16469 &:= (1 \times (((2^3) - (45 + (6^7)))/ - (8 + 9))) \\
16470 &:= ((1 - 2) + (3 + (((4 \times 5) + (6^7))/(8 + 9)))) \\
16471 &:= ((1 - 2) \times - (3 + (((4 \times 5) + (6^7))/(8 + 9)))) \\
16472 &:= (1 \times -((2 + ((3^4) + (5 + (6^7)))))/ - (8 + 9)) \\
16473 &:= (1 - ((2 + ((3^4) + (5 + (6^7)))))/ - (8 + 9)) \\
16474 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 + (((4 \times 5) + (6^7))/(8 + 9)))) \\
16475 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((34 - (5 \times 6))^7) + 89))) \\
16476 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - (5 - (6^7))))/ - (8 + 9)) \\
16477 &:= (((1 + 2) + (34 \times 5)) + (6^7))/(8 + 9) \\
16478 &:= (1 \times - (2 - (((3 + 4^5) - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\
16479 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 + 4^5) - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\
16480 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -(((4^5) + 6) \times - (7 - (8 - 9)))) \\
16481 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3 + ((4^5) + 6))) - 7) \times -8) - 9) \\
16482 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3 + ((4^5) + 6))) - 7) \times -8) - 9) \\
16483 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) - (8 \times -9) \\
16484 &:= ((1 - (23 + 4)) \times -((5 + 6) + (7 \times 89))) \\
16485 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times - (4 - ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 89))) \\
16486 &:= (1 \times - (2 \times - (3 + (((4^5) + 6) \times (7 - (8 - 9)))) \\
16487 &:= (1 - (2 \times - (3 + (((4^5) + 6) \times (7 - (8 - 9)))) \\
16488 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3 + (4^5))) + 6)) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
16489 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times - (3^4)) - ((5^6) + (78 \times 9))) \\
16490 &:= (((1 + ((2 - (3^4)) \times 5)) - (6^7))/ - (8 + 9)) \\
16491 &:= (1 \times - (23 \times - ((4 + (5 + 6)) + (78 \times 9))) \\
16492 &:= ((12 + ((3 + 4^5)) + ((6 \times - (7 \times 8)) + 9)) \\
16493 &:= (1 \times - (2 - ((3^4) + ((5^6) + 789))) \\
16494 &:= (((1 - 2) + (((345 \times 6) - 7) \times 8)) - 9) \\
16495 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (((4 \times 5) + (6^7))/ - (8 + 9)) \\
16496 &:= (1 \times (23 + ((4^{(-5+6) \times 7}) + 89))) \\
16497 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times ((4 + ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
16498 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 3) \times 45)) \times - ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9)) \\
16499 &:= (1 \times - (2 - (((3 + 4^5) - ((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16459 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times ((4^3) + 2)) - 1))) \\
16460 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times (65 \times 4))) \times - (3^2)) + 1)) \\
16461 &:= ((9 - 8) \times - ((7 \times - (6 + 5)) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16462 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times - (6 + 5)) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16463 &:= ((-98 / -7) + (65 + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16464 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - ((4 + 3)^{2 + 1})) \\
16465 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((76 + 5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16466 &:= (9 + ((8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5)) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16467 &:= (9 - (876 - (54 \times 321))) \\
16468 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times 65)) \times 43) - 2) + 1) \\
16469 &:= (((9 + 87) - 6) - (5 - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16470 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 6) + (5 + 4)) \times - (32 - 1))) \\
16471 &:= ((98 - 7) \times - (((6 + 54) \times -3) - (2 - 1))) \\
16472 &:= ((9 - (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times 4)) \times - ((3^2) - 1)) \\
16473 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - ((4 + 3)^{2 + 1})) \\
16474 &:= ((98 - 7) - ((6 - 5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16475 &:= (98 + ((7 \times - (6 - 5)) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16476 &:= ((98 - (7 - 6)) - (5 - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16477 &:= (98 + ((7 \times (65 \times (4 + 32))) - 1)) \\
16478 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times - (6 + 5)) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16479 &:= (((9 + 87) - 6) + (5 + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16480 &:= ((9 + 87) - ((6 - 5) \times - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16481 &:= (98 - (((7 - (6 + 5)) \times (4^{3 \times 2})) + 1)) \\
16482 &:= ((9 + (8 + 76)) + (5 + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16483 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times (((5^4) - 3) / - (2 \times 1))) \\
16484 &:= ((-9 \times - (8 + (7 \times (65 \times 4)))) - (32 \times -1)) \\
16485 &:= ((98 + 7) \times - ((6 \times -5) - ((4 \times 32) - 1))) \\
16486 &:= ((98 - (7 - 6)) + (5 + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16487 &:= (98 - (((7 - 6) \times -5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16488 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times -6) - 5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16489 &:= (98 - ((7 \times - (6 - 5)) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16490 &:= ((98 + 7) + ((6 - 5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16491 &:= ((9 + (87 + 6)) + (5 + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16492 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 + 6)) - 5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16493 &:= (9 + ((8 - (76 \times ((5 \times 43) + 2))) \times -1)) \\
16494 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((76 \times - ((5 \times 43) + 2)) - 1)) \\
16495 &:= (((-9 \times - (87 - ((6 \times 5) \times (4^3))) + 2) \times -1) \\
16496 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (76 \times - ((5 \times 43) + (2 + 1)))) \\
16497 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times - ((6 \times 54) + (3^{2 + 1}))) \\
16498 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 + 6)) \times -5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16499 &:= (9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((54 \times (3^2)) - 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16500 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 + 4)^5) - ((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\
16501 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + 89)) \\
16502 &:= (((((12^3) + (4^5)) \times 6) + (7 - 8)) - 9) \\
16503 &:= (1 \times ((2 + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\
16504 &:= (1 + ((2 + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\
16505 &:= (((((12^3) + (4^5)) \times -6) + 7) \times (8 - 9)) \\
16506 &:= (((((12^3) + (4^5)) \times 6) - 7) - (8 - 9)) \\
16507 &:= ((123 + (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) \times -(8 - 9)) \\
16508 &:= (((123 + (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) - 8) + 9) \\
16509 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times -6) - (7 \times 89))) \\
16510 &:= (1 \times ((2 - ((3 - 45) \times 6)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
16511 &:= (1 + ((2 - ((3 - 45) \times 6)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
16512 &:= ((1 + 23) \times ((4 \times -5) + (6 + (78 \times 9)))) \\
16513 &:= ((12 + ((3 + 4)^5)) + (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times -9)) \\
16514 &:= (1 \times -(23 \times -((4^5) - (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))) \\
16515 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 + ((4 - ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
16516 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3 \times (((4 + 5) \times 67) + 8))) \times -9)) \\
16517 &:= (((-12 \times -((3 \times 456) + 7)) + 8) + 9) \\
16518 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (3^4)) \times -(5 \times (6 \times 7))) - (8 \times 9))) \\
16519 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
16520 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) + 6)))) \times -(7 - (8 - 9))) \\
16521 &:= (((((12^3) + (4^5)) \times 6) - ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
16522 &:= (((((12^3) + (4^5)) \times 6) - (7 - 8)) + 9) \\
16523 &:= (1 \times ((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) + (8 - 9)))) \\
16524 &:= (1 + ((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) + (8 - 9)))) \\
16525 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 + 4)^5) - (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
16526 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times (((3 - ((4^5) + (6 + 7))) \times 8) + 9))) \\
16527 &:= (1 - (2 \times (((3 - ((4^5) + (6 + 7))) \times 8) + 9))) \\
16528 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) + (6 \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
16529 &:= (1 + ((2^3) \times -(4 - (5 \times (6 \times (78 - 9)))))) \\
16530 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(34 - ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16531 &:= ((((-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times 5)) \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) - 9) \\
16532 &:= (((-12 \times -(3^4)) + ((5^6) + 7)) + (8 \times -9)) \\
16533 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 - ((4 - ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
16534 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3^4) + (5 + (67 \times 8))) \times -9)) \\
16535 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -((3 - ((4^5) + (6 + 7))) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
16536 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -((3 - ((4^5) + (6 + 7))) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
16537 &:= ((12 + ((3 + 4)^5)) + (6 \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
16538 &:= (1 - (23 \times -(4 - ((5 + 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16539 &:= (((-1 + (2345 + 6)) \times 7) + 89) \\
16540 &:= (1 \times -(2 + (3 \times (4 + ((5 - 67) \times 89))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16500 &:= ((98 + (7 + 6)) + (5 + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16501 &:= (9 + (((87 + 6) - (5^4)) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
16502 &:= (9 - (((8 \times -(7 + 6)) - 5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16503 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) - 4) \times 32)) \times -1) \\
16504 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) - 4) \times -32) - 1)) \\
16505 &:= (98 - ((7 - (6 \times 5)) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16506 &:= (9 \times (((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times 4) + (3 - 21))) \\
16507 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (((7 \times (65 + 4)) + 3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
16508 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5) \times -(4^3) + 2) + 1)) \\
16509 &:= ((9 + 876) + ((5^{4 \times 3 / 2} - 1)) \\
16510 &:= ((9 + 87) - ((6 \times -5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16511 &:= (9 + (876 + ((5^{4 \times 3 / 2} + 1))) \\
16512 &:= ((9 + 87) \times -(((6 \times (54 + 3)) / -2) - 1)) \\
16513 &:= ((-98 \times -((76 \times 5) - 43)) / - (2 \times -1)) \\
16514 &:= (9 - (((8 \times -7) - 65) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16515 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times ((43 + 2) \times -1)) \\
16516 &:= (987 - (((6^5) - (4 \times 3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
16517 &:= ((((-98 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times -4) + (32 + 1)) \\
16518 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 \times 76) + 5)) + 4) \times -3) - 21) \\
16519 &:= (98 - (((7 \times -6) + 5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16520 &:= ((98 + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 - (4^3)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
16521 &:= ((9 + ((8 - 76) \times ((5 + 4)^3))) / - (2 + 1)) \\
16522 &:= (9 - (((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) - 4) \times -32) - 1)) \\
16523 &:= ((-9 + ((87 \times 6) + (5 \times 4))) \times (32 - 1)) \\
16524 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 + 6) - (5^4)) \times -(3^{2 + 1}))) \\
16525 &:= (9 - (8 + (((7 + 6) - (5^4)) \times (3^{2 + 1})))) \\
16526 &:= (987 - (((6^5) - (4 + 3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
16527 &:= ((9 - ((8 - 76) \times ((5 + 4)^3))) / (2 + 1)) \\
16528 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) \times (6 + ((5 + (4 \times 3))^2))) - 1)) \\
16529 &:= (98 - (((7 \times -6) - 5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16530 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -6) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
16531 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -6) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
16532 &:= ((9 + (87 \times 6)) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times -2) - 1)) \\
16533 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times (65 \times 4))) \times -(3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
16534 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times 54) \times -(3^2) + 1)) \\
16535 &:= (-98 - (7 - (65 \times (4^{3 \times 2 - 1})))) \\
16536 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times -(((5^4) - 3) / 2) + 1)) \\
16537 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 + (6 + 5))) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16538 &:= (987 - (((6^5) \times -((4 - 3) \times 2)) + 1)) \\
16539 &:= ((98 + (7 + 6)) \times -((5 + ((4 \times 3)^2)) \times -1)) \\
16540 &:= (987 - (((6^5) \times -((4 - 3) \times 2)) - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16541 &:= (1 \times -((2 + ((3^4) + 56)) \times -(7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 16541 &:= (9 + (8 - (((7 + 6) - (5^4)) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
16542 &:= (1 - ((2 + ((3^4) + 56)) \times -(7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 16542 &:= (987 - (((6^5) + (4 - 3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
16543 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3+4}) + (5^6))) + 789) & 16543 &:= ((98 - (((7 + 6) \times 5) + (4^3)^2)) \times -1) \\
16544 &:= ((1 - (23 \times 45)) \times -(6 - (7 - (8 + 9)))) & 16544 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (((6 + 5) \times (4^3)) / - (2 \times 1))) \\
16545 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -78) - 9)) & 16545 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 + 6) \times ((54 \times 3) - (2 + 1)))))) \\
16546 &:= (1 - (((2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -78) - 9)) & 16546 &:= (-9 - (87 - (((65 + (4^3))^2) + 1))) \\
16547 &:= (1 - (((2345 + 6) \times -7) - 89)) & 16547 &:= (98 - (((7 + 6) \times -5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16548 &:= ((1 + ((2 - (3^4)) \times 5)) \times -(6 \times -(7 \times (8 - 9)))) & 16548 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - ((5^4) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
16549 &:= (((-123 \times 4) + 5) \times -((6 \times 7) - 8)) - 9 & 16549 &:= (((-98 + 7) + ((65 + (4^3))^2)) - 1) \\
16550 &:= (((-12 \times -(3^4)) + (5^6)) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & 16550 &:= ((9 + ((8 - 76) \times 5)) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
16551 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 \times -(((4 \times 56) + 7) \times 8) - 9))) & 16551 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - (4^{3+2-1})) \\
16552 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times (((4 \times 5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 89)))) & 16552 &:= (9 - (((((87 \times 6) - 5) \times (4^3)) / -2) + 1)) \\
16553 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -((3 - ((4^5) + (6 + 7))) \times 8)) + 9)) & 16553 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 \times 6) + 5) \times ((43 + 2) - 1)))) \\
16554 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -((3 - ((4^5) + (6 + 7))) \times 8)) + 9)) & 16554 &:= (9 - (((((87 \times 6) - 5) \times (4^3)) / -2) - 1)) \\
16555 &:= (-1 - (2 + (34 \times (((5 - 67) \times 8) + 9)))) & 16555 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + (4 \times -(3 \times 21))) \\
16556 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times (((4 \times 5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 89)))) & 16556 &:= (((-9 \times -((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times 54)) - 32) \times -1) \\
16557 &:= (1 + (2 + (3 \times (((4 \times 5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 89)))) & 16557 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((7 + 6) \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))) \times -21)) \\
16558 &:= (((-12 \times -(3 \times 4)) + (5^6)) + 789) & 16558 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5))) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
16559 &:= (((12^3) + (4^5)) \times 6) - ((7 \times -8) + 9) & 16559 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) + 1))) \\
16560 &:= ((12^3) + ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times -(8 \times 9))) & 16560 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - (4^{3+2-1})) \\
16561 &:= (((12^3) / 4) + (5^6)) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9)) & 16561 &:= (((-9 - 876) / -5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
16562 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 \times 89)))) & 16562 &:= (987 - (((6^5) + (4 \times 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
16563 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) - (7 \times 89)))) & 16563 &:= (987 - (((6^5) + (4 \times 3)) \times -2 \times 1)) \\
16564 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times -7) - (8 - 9))) & 16564 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) + (4 \times -(3 \times 21))) \\
16565 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 \times 89)))) & 16565 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - ((76 \times -((5 \times 43) + 2)) - 1)) \\
16566 &:= ((1 + (23 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)) & 16566 &:= (((-9 \times -87) - (6 \times 5)) \times (4 - (3 - 21))) \\
16567 &:= (1 \times -(2 + (3 \times ((4 - (5 + 6)) \times 789)))) & 16567 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times -((54 \times (3^2)) + 1))) \\
16568 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -((4 \times (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8))) - 9))) & 16568 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4)))) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
16569 &:= (1 - ((2^3) \times -((4 \times (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8))) - 9))) & 16569 &:= (9 - (8 - (76 \times ((5 \times 43) + (2 + 1)))))) \\
16570 &:= (12 + (34 \times -(5 + (6 \times (7 - 89)))) & 16570 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - 4))) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\
16571 &:= (1 \times (2 - (3 \times ((4 - (5 + 6)) \times 789)))) & 16571 &:= (((-9 \times -((8 - (7 \times 6)) + ((5^4) \times 3))) + 2) \times 1) \\
16572 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 + ((4^5) \times 6)) - (7 \times 89))) & 16572 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times 54) - 3)) + 21) \\
16573 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (3^4)) \times -(5 \times (6 \times 7))) - (8 + 9))) & 16573 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times -2) - 1) \\
16574 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -(((4^5) + (6 + 7)) \times -8) + 9) & 16574 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times -(7 - ((65 \times (4^3)) / 2))) - 1)) \\
16575 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times -(5 \times -((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) & 16575 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 6) - (5 \times 4)) \times -(32 + 1))) \\
16576 &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times -((45 + 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 16576 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5)) \times -((4^3) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
16577 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -((3 - (((4^5) + (6 + 7)) \times 8))) - 9)) & 16577 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7 - (6 \times 5))) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16578 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -((3 - (((4^5) + (6 + 7)) \times 8))) - 9)) & 16578 &:= ((987 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
16579 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3^4) + (56 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9))) & 16579 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(65 \times 4)) - 321) \\
16580 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((3 + (((4^5) + (6 + 7)) \times 8)) - 9))) & 16580 &:= (((-9 \times -((8 + 7) + ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3))) - 2) \times -1) \\
16581 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 + (((4^5) + (6 + 7)) \times 8)) - 9))) & 16581 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -(5 + 43)) + 21)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16582 &:= (((-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6))) \times 7) + 8) - 9) & 16582 &:= ((-9 \times -(87 - 65)) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
16583 &:= ((1 + ((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -(7 \times -(8 - 9))) & 16583 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 + (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)))) + 21) \\
16584 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(3 \times (4 \times ((5 + 6) - (78 \times 9)))))) & 16584 &:= ((98 + (7^{6-5+4})) - 321) \\
16585 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) + ((6 + 7) \times -(8 + 9))) & 16585 &:= (9 - (8 \times (7 - (((65 \times (4^3))/2) - 1)))) \\
16586 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 + 4)^5) - ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) & 16586 &:= ((-987 + ((6 + (5 \times 4)^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
16587 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3 - (4^5))) - (6^7)))/(8 + 9)) & 16587 &:= ((9 - ((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times 4)) \times (3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
16588 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9))))))) & 16588 &:= ((98 + (7 + (6 + 5))) \times (((4 \times 3)^2) - 1)) \\
16589 &:= ((1 + ((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) \times (8 - 9)) & 16589 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times (((5^4) + 3)/ - 2) + 1)) \\
16590 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) + (8 - 9)) & 16590 &:= ((98 + 7) \times -((6 \times -5) - (4 \times (32 \times 1)))) \\
16591 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) \times -(8 - 9)) & 16591 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 \times -(54 + (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\
16592 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - (8 - 9)) & 16592 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7 - ((65 \times (4^3))/2))) - 1)) \\
16593 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3 + ((4^5) + 6))) + 7) \times -8) - 9)) & 16593 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (65 \times -(4^{3+2-1}))) \\
16594 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3 + ((4^5) + 6))) + 7) \times -8) - 9)) & 16594 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(6 \times 5)) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16595 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) + (6 + 7)) \times 8))) + 9)) & 16595 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -(6 \times 5)) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16596 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 \times -4) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16596 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) - 6) \times -(5 - ((43^2) - 1)))) \\
16597 &:= (1 + (((2^3) + (4 \times (5 - (6 \times 78)))) \times -9)) & 16597 &:= (-9 - (((87 - 6) \times -(5 \times (43 - 2))) - 1)) \\
16598 &:= ((12 + ((3 + 4)^5)) + ((6 + 7) \times -(8 + 9))) & 16598 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) + (6 + 5)) \times -43)/ - (2 \times -1)) \\
16599 &:= ((1 - (2 - 34)) \times ((5 - 6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 16599 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 76)) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
16600 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times -5 - (678 - 9)) & 16600 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
16601 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 3) \times -(((4^5) + (6 + 7)) \times 8) + 9) & 16601 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(7 - (((65 \times (4^3))/2) + 1)))) \\
16602 &:= (12 - ((3 + 4) \times -(5 \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) & 16602 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 - (65 \times (4^3))))/ - 2) - 1)) \\
16603 &:= (1 \times -(2 + ((3 - (((4 \times 56) + 7) \times 8)) \times 9))) & 16603 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 - (65 \times (4^3))))/ - (2 \times 1))) \\
16604 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) + (6 + 7)) \times 8) + 9))) & 16604 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) - 6) \times -(5 - (43^2))) - 1)) \\
16605 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) + (6 + 7)) \times 8) + 9))) & 16605 &:= (((9 + ((8 - 7)^6)) - (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\
16606 &:= ((-1 + (((2 + 34) - 5) \times (67 \times 8))) - 9) & 16606 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) - 6) \times -(5 - (43^2))) + 1)) \\
16607 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times -(((345 \times 6) + 7) \times -8) + 9) & 16607 &:= (987 - (6 - ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) + 1))) \\
16608 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) + (8 + 9)) & 16608 &:= ((9 + 87) \times (65 + (4 \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
16609 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 345) \times 6) - 7) \times -8) - 9) & 16609 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((7 + (6 \times (54 \times 3))) - (2 \times 1))) \\
16610 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -(((4^5) + (6 + 7)) \times -8) - 9) & 16610 &:= ((-987 + ((6 + (5 \times 4)^3)) + 21) \\
16611 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 + 4) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16611 &:= (9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16612 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3)! + 4 \times (-5! - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9) & 16612 &:= (987 - (((6 - (5 - 4))^{3 \times 2}) \times -1)) \\
16613 &:= (-12 - (((345 \times 6) + 7) \times -8) - 9) & 16613 &:= (987 + (((6 - (5 - 4))^{3 \times 2}) + 1)) \\
16614 &:= ((1 - (23 + 4)) \times ((56 + (7 + 8)) \times -9)) & 16614 &:= ((9 - 87) \times ((6 \times -(5 \times (4 + 3))) - (2 + 1))) \\
16615 &:= (1 + (234 \times -((5 + (6 + 7)) - 89))) & 16615 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + ((4^3) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
16616 &:= (1 \times (2 \times (3 + (((4^5) + (6 + 7)) \times 8) + 9))) & 16616 &:= ((9 + (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times 4)) \times ((3^2) - 1)) \\
16617 &:= (1 + (2 \times (3 + (((4^5) + (6 + 7)) \times 8) + 9))) & 16617 &:= ((9 + (8 \times 76)) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
16618 &:= (1 \times -(2 + (3 \times (4 - ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))))) & 16618 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -76) - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
16619 &:= (1 - (2 + (3 \times (4 - ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))))) & 16619 &:= (987 + (6 + ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) + 1))) \\
16620 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -(4 \times (5 - (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))))) & 16620 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 - (65 \times (4^3))))/2)) - 1) \\
16621 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) + ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times -9)) & 16621 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 - (65 \times (4^3))))/2)) \times 1) \\
16622 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(((3 + ((4^5) + (6 + 7))) \times 8) - 9)) & 16622 &:= (98 + (((7 + 6) - (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1})))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16623 &:= ((1+2) + (3 \times -(4 - ((5+6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16623 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 - 65) \times 4))) \times (3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
16624 &:= (((12+3) + (4^5)) \times (6 - (7 - (8+9)))) & 16624 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) + ((4^3) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
16625 &:= ((1 - (2 + 34)) \times (5 \times -(((6+7) \times 8) - 9))) & 16625 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times (5 \times -((4 + 32) - 1))) \\
16626 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times -((5 - (6 - 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) & 16626 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(7 - ((6 \times ((54 \times 3) + 2)) + 1))) \\
16627 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -3) + (((4 \times 56) + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 16627 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6) \times -(5 - (4 \times 32)))) \\
16628 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) - (((4 \times 56) + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 16628 &:= (9 - (8 + ((7 + 6) \times (5 - (4 \times 32)))))) \\
16629 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 - 4) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16629 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (65 \times 4)))) + 321) \\
16630 &:= ((12 + ((3 + 4)^5)) + ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times -9)) & 16630 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(65 - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
16631 &:= (((12^3) + (4^5)) \times 6) - (7 \times -(8 + 9)) & 16631 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times ((54 \times 3) - 2)))) \times -1) \\
16632 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times 5)) \times (6 \times -(7 \times (8 - 9)))) & 16632 &:= (((9 + 87) - ((6^5)/4)) \times (3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
16633 &:= (1 \times -((2 - 3) - (((4 \times 56) + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 16633 &:= (((9 - (8 - 7)) - ((65 + (4^3))^2)) \times -1) \\
16634 &:= ((1 - 2) + (3 + (((4 \times 56) + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 16634 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 - ((65 + (4^3))^2)) \times -1)) \\
16635 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 - 4) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16635 &:= ((9 - 87) + ((6 - (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
16636 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (3 + (((4 \times 56) + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 16636 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - (((65 + (4^3))^2) + 1))) \\
16637 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) + (((4 \times 56) + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 16637 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times 4)) - (32 - 1)) \\
16638 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 + (((4 \times 56) + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 16638 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 \times -(5 - (43 + 21)))) \\
16639 &:= (1 \times -((2 + ((3 + (4 \times (5 - (6 \times 78)))) \times 9))) & 16639 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 + (7 \times ((65 \times 4) + 3)))) - 2) \times 1) \\
16640 &:= (1 \times -((2^{(3+45)/6}) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 16640 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -((65 \times (4^3)) / - (2 \times 1))) \\
16641 &:= ((1 + (2^{3+4}))^{5+6+(7-8) \times 9}) & 16641 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -(((65 + (4^3))^2) \times -1)) \\
16642 &:= (1 \times -((2 - (3 \times (4 + ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))))) & 16642 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times (((5^4) + 3) / - (2 \times 1))) \\
16643 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (4 + ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))))) & 16643 &:= (9 + (((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5) + (4^{3 \times 2+1}))) \\
16644 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3^4) - 5) \times ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9)))) & 16644 &:= (9 + (8 - ((7 + 6) \times (5 - (4 \times 32)))))) \\
16645 &:= (1 \times -(23 + (4 \times ((5 - (6 \times 78)) \times 9)))) & 16645 &:= (-9 + ((8 - 765) \times -(4 - (3 - 21)))) \\
16646 &:= (((1 - 2) - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times ((6 \times -7) - (8 - 9))) & 16646 &:= ((-98 + (7^{6-5+4})) + (3 \times -21)) \\
16647 &:= (1 + (2 + (3 \times (4 + ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))))) & 16647 &:= (((9 - (8 + 7)) - ((65 + (4^3))^2)) \times -1) \\
16648 &:= ((1 - ((2 + 345) \times 6)) \times -(7 - (8 - 9))) & 16648 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + ((65 + (4^3))^2)) \times -1)) \\
16649 &:= (1 \times (((2 - 34) \times -(5 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8))) + 9)) & 16649 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 + ((65 + (4^3))^2)) \times -1)) \\
16650 &:= (1 + (((2 - 34) \times -(5 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8))) + 9)) & 16650 &:= ((98 + (7 + 6)) \times (5 + (((4 \times 3)^2) + 1))) \\
16651 &:= (1 - (((2 + (34 \times 56)) - (7 \times 8)) \times -9)) & 16651 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 - ((65 + (4^3))^2)) \times -1)) \\
16652 &:= (1 \times -(23 \times -(4 + ((5 + (67 + 8)) \times 9)))) & 16652 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 - (((65 + (4^3))^2) + 1))) \\
16653 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 + 4) + ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16653 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 7) \times ((6^5) - 4))) / ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
16654 &:= ((1 - 23) \times ((4 - 5) - ((6 + 78) \times 9))) & 16654 &:= (9 + (((876 \times (5 - 43)) / -2) + 1)) \\
16655 &:= (((12^3) + (4 + (5^6))) + (78 \times -9)) & 16655 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (76 - ((5 \times 432) - 1)))) \\
16656 &:= (12 - (3 \times -(4 + ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16656 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times (6 + ((5^4) + (3 \times 21)))) \\
16657 &:= (1 \times -((2 + (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))))) & 16657 &:= (((9 + 8) + (((7 + 6) \times 5) + (4^3)^2)) - 1) \\
16658 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})) + (6 \times -(7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 16658 &:= (9 - ((8 + (((7 + 6) \times 5) + (4^3)^2)) \times -1)) \\
16659 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3 + ((4^5) + (6 + 7))) \times 8) + 9))) & 16659 &:= (((9 + 8) + (((7 + 6) \times 5) + (4^3)^2)) + 1) \\
16660 &:= ((12^3) + (4 \times -(5 - (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) & 16660 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) \times -1)) \\
16661 &:= (1 \times -((2 - (((3 + 4)^5) - (6 \times (7 + (8 + 9)))))) & 16661 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6^5)) - 4)) / ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
16662 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3^{4+5})) + (6 \times -(7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 16662 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - (((4 \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\
16663 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - (8 \times -9)) & 16663 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + (((4 \times 3)^2) \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16664 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times (3 - 4^5))) - (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) - 9) & 16664 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6^5) - (((4 \times 3)^2) - 1)) \\
16665 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) - (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 16665 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 + ((65 + (4^3))^2)) \times -1)) \\
16666 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 + 4)^5) - (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 16666 &:= (((((9 + ((8 - 7)^6))^5) - 4) / -3) / (2 \times -1)) \\
16667 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) - (67 + (8 \times 9)))) & 16667 &:= (987 - (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times - (2 \times 1))) \\
16668 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times -4) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 16668 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 76) + (5 + 4)) \times - (3^{2+1}))) \\
16669 &:= (1 \times ((2 - (3^4)) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 - 9))) & 16669 &:= (9 - (((8 - 76) \times 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2 \times 1))) \\
16670 &:= (1 + ((2 - (3^4)) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 - 9))) & 16670 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) - 4)) \times - (3^2 + 1)) \\
16671 &:= ((12 + (3^{4+5})) + (6 \times - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 16671 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - (((4 \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\
16672 &:= (1 - (23 - (((4^5) - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 16672 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) + (((4 \times 3)^2) \times -1)) \\
16673 &:= ((1 + (((((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times 8)) / 9) & 16673 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - (((4 \times 3)^2) - 1)) \\
16674 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times 3) - (4 \times ((5 - (6 \times 78)) \times 9)))) & 16674 &:= (((9 + 8) + (76 \times 5)) \times (43 - (2 - 1))) \\
16675 &:= ((12 + ((3 + 4)^5)) + (6 \times - (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 16675 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6^5) + (4 \times - (32 + 1))) \\
16676 &:= (1 \times - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + (6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 16676 &:= (((9 - 8) - (76 \times 5)) \times - ((43 + 2) - 1)) \\
16677 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) & 16677 &:= (((98 - 7) - ((6^5) / 4)) \times (3 \times - (2 + 1))) \\
16678 &:= ((12 + ((3 + 4)^5)) - (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) & 16678 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6^5) + ((4 \times -32) - 1)) \\
16679 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (3^4)) \times - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + 89)) & 16679 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6^5) + (4 \times - (32 \times 1))) \\
16680 &:= (1 \times - (2 \times - (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (67 + (8 \times 9)))))) & 16680 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6^5) + ((4 \times -32) + 1)) \\
16681 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times (3 - 4^5))) - (6 \times 7)) \times -8) + 9) & 16681 &:= (9 + (8 \times - (76 - (5 \times (432 \times 1)))))) \\
16682 &:= (1 + (((2 \times (3 - 4^5))) - (6 \times 7)) \times -8) + 9) & 16682 &:= (9 + ((8 \times - (76 - (5 \times 432))) + 1)) \\
16683 &:= (12 + (3 - (4 \times ((5 - (6 \times 78)) \times 9)))) & 16683 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6^5) + (4 \times - (32 - 1))) \\
16684 &:= (1 \times ((2 + ((3 + 4)^5)) - (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 16684 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) + (4 \times - (32 + 1))) \\
16685 &:= (1 + ((2 + ((3 + 4)^5)) - (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 16685 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 \times -5) - (4 + 321))) \\
16686 &:= ((1 - (23 \times (4 + 5))) \times - ((6 - (7 + 8)) \times -9)) & 16686 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times 76) + (5 - 4))) \times (3^{2+1})) \\
16687 &:= (1 \times - ((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times - ((6 \times 7) + (8 - 9))) & 16687 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + ((65 \times (4^3)) / 2)))) \times -1) \\
16688 &:= (1 - ((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times - ((6 \times 7) + (8 - 9))) & 16688 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7^{(6-5) \times 4})) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
16689 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -3) + (((4^5) - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 16689 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + (6 \times 5)))) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
16690 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) - (((4^5) - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 16690 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times - (2 \times -1)) \\
16691 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 + 5)) - (67 \times - (8 + 9))) & 16691 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (76 \times 5)) \times 43)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
16692 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - (6 \times 7)) + (8 \times -9) & 16692 &:= (98 - ((7 \times - (6 \times 5)) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16693 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6 + 7) \times 8)) - 9) & 16693 &:= (9 - ((8 + (76 \times 5)) \times - ((4^3) - 21))) \\
16694 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 - (((4^5) - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 16694 &:= (9 - (((8 + (76 \times 5)) \times -43) - (2 - 1))) \\
16695 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + (4 \times - ((5 - (6 \times 78)) \times 9))) & 16695 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times (5 \times - ((4^3) - (2 - 1)))) \\
16696 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - (6 \times 7)) + (8 \times -9) & 16696 &:= (9 - (((8 + (76 \times 5)) \times -43) - (2 + 1))) \\
16697 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6 + 7) \times 8)) - 9) & 16697 &:= (9 + ((8 \times 7) \times - (6 - ((5^4) - 321)))) \\
16698 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 + 4) \times - (5 \times ((6 \times 78) + 9)))) & 16698 &:= (((9 + 8) - (76 \times 5)) \times - (43 + (2 + 1))) \\
16699 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) + (((4^5) - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 16699 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6^5) + (4 \times - (3^{2+1}))) \\
16700 &:= (1 \times - ((2 \times -3) - (((4^5) - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 16700 &:= ((-9 \times - ((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times 4)) - (32 \times -1)) \\
16701 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -3) - (((4^5) - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 16701 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 - ((6 + 5) \times (4^3)))) \times - (2 + 1)) \\
16702 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) + (((4^5) - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 16702 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) + (4 \times - (3 + 21))) \\
16703 &:= (1 + ((2^3) + (((4^5) - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 16703 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times -5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
16704 &:= ((12^3) - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) / 8) \times -9) & 16704 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times - (6 \times - (5 + ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16705 &:= (((12 + ((3 + 4)^5)) - (6 \times 7)) + (8 \times -9)) & 16705 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(((7 - 65) \times (4 + 32)) + 1))) \\
16706 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3 + 4)^5) - ((6 \times (7 + 8)) + 9)))) & 16706 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 + ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
16707 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) - ((6 \times (7 + 8)) + 9)))) & 16707 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 + ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
16708 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 + 4)^5) - ((6 \times (7 + 8)) + 9))) & 16708 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^{5^5})) + (4 \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
16709 &:= (12 + (3 + (((4^5) - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 16709 &:= ((98 - (7^{6-5+4})) \times (3 / -(2 + 1))) \\
16710 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3 + 4)^5) - (((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9)))) & 16710 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times ((4 \times -3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
16711 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) - (((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9)))) & 16711 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(7 - (6 \times (5 \times ((4 \times 3) + 21)))))) \\
16712 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) - 5) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 \times -9)) & 16712 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4)))) \times ((3^2) - 1)) \\
16713 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 \times -(((4 \times 56) + 7) \times 8) + 9))) & 16713 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
16714 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) - (4 \times (5 - (6 \times 78)))) \times -9)) & 16714 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + ((6 - (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
16715 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) + (((6 + 7) \times -8) + 9)) & 16715 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 76) \times -5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16716 &:= (1 \times (((2 - ((3 + 4)^5)) \times (6 - 7)) - 89)) & 16716 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times 4) + 3)) + 21) \\
16717 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - (6 + 78)) - 9 & 16717 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
16718 &:= ((1 + 23) - (((4^5) - (6 \times 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) & 16718 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2 \times 1))) \\
16719 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(34 - ((56 + 7) \times 89))) & 16719 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2) - 1)) \\
16720 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^4)) \times -((5 \times -(6 \times 7)) - (8 - 9))) & 16720 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + ((43 \times -2) - 1)) \\
16721 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - 6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)) & 16721 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) + ((6 - (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
16722 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - (67 + 8)) - 9 & 16722 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + ((43 \times -2) + 1)) \\
16723 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 + 4)^5) - (67 + (8 + 9)))) & 16723 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 + ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
16724 &:= (1 \times ((2 + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6 + 7) + (8 \times 9)))) & 16724 &:= (9 - (((8 \times -(7 \times 6)) + 5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16725 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - 6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)) & 16725 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((76 + (5^4)) - 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
16726 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - 67) - (8 + 9) & 16726 &:= (-98 - ((76 + (5^4)) \times -(3 + 21))) \\
16727 &:= (1 - ((2 \times 3) - (4 \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 89)))) & 16727 &:= ((9 - (((87 \times 6) + (5 - 4)) \times 32)) \times -1) \\
16728 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) - (4 \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 89)))) & 16728 &:= (9 - (87 - (((6 + 5) - 4)^{3+2} - 1))) \\
16729 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6 - (7 + 8)) \times -9)) & 16729 &:= (9 - (87 - (((6 + 5) - 4)^{3+2} \times 1))) \\
16730 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3 + 4)^5) - ((6 + 78) - 9)))) & 16730 &:= ((9 - 87) + (((6 + 5) - 4)^{3+2} + 1)) \\
16731 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 - ((4 + ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) & 16731 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^{5^5})) + ((43 \times -2) + 1)) \\
16732 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times (45 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))))) - 9) & 16732 &:= (98 + ((7 - ((65 + (4^3))^2)) \times -1)) \\
16733 &:= (((1 - 2) + (((3 + 4)^5) + 6)) - (7 + (8 \times 9))) & 16733 &:= (9 + (((8 - 76) \times -5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16734 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3 + 4)^5) - ((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9)))) & 16734 &:= (9 - (((8 \times -(7 \times 6)) - 5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16735 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - 6) - ((7 \times 8) + 9) & 16735 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - (4 \times -(3 - 21))) \\
16736 &:= (((1 - 23) - (4^5)) \times -(6 - (7 - (8 + 9)))) & 16736 &:= (9 + (87 + (65 \times (4^{3+2-1})))) \\
16737 &:= (((1 + 2) + (((3 + 4)^5) + 6)) - (7 + (8 \times 9))) & 16737 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) + ((6 - (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
16738 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 + 4)^5) \times (6 - 7)) + (8 \times 9)) & 16738 &:= (98 - (((7 + 6) \times 5) \times -(4^{3+2-1}))) \\
16739 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - 6) - ((7 \times 8) + 9) & 16739 &:= (98 - (((((7 + 6) \times 5) + (4^3))^2) \times -1)) \\
16740 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -(((4 \times 5) + ((6 + 7) \times 8)) \times -9)) & 16740 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (6 - (5^4))) \times (3^{2+1}) \\
16741 &:= (((1 - 2) - (((3 + 4)^5) - 67)) \times (8 - 9)) & 16741 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + (((4^3) + 2) \times -1)) \\
16742 &:= ((1 - 23) \times (4 + ((5 - (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9))) & 16742 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - ((4^3) + (2 - 1))) \\
16743 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9)) & 16743 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + ((4^3) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
16744 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times -(5 + ((6 \times (7 + 8)) + 9))) & 16744 &:= ((9 - ((8 - ((7 - 6)^5)^4)) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
16745 &:= (1 - (23 \times -((4 \times 5) + (6 + (78 \times 9)))) & 16745 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + (((4^3) - 2) \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16746 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3+4)^5) - ((6 \times 7) + (8+9)))))) & 16746 &:= (((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) - ((4^3) - (2+1))) \\
16747 &:= (((1-2) + (((3+4)^5) + (6 - (7 \times 8)))) - 9) & 16747 &:= (98 + (7 + (((65 + (4^3))^2) + 1))) \\
16748 &:= (1 \times -((2 + ((3+4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 16748 &:= ((((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) + 4) + (3 \times -21)) \\
16749 &:= (1 - ((2 + ((3+4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 16749 &:= (((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - ((4^3) + 2)) - 1) \\
16750 &:= (1 \times ((2 + ((3+4)^5)) - ((6 \times 7) + (8+9)))) & 16750 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) + 4)) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
16751 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3+4)^5) + (6 \times ((7-8) \times 9)))))) & 16751 &:= (((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - ((4^3) + 2)) + 1) \\
16752 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3+4)^5) + (6 \times ((7-8) \times 9)))))) & 16752 &:= (9 - (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) - (4^3)) \times -(2 - 1)) \\
16753 &:= (((1-2) + ((3+4)^5)) - 6) + ((7 \times -8) + 9) & 16753 &:= (((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - ((4^3) - 2)) - 1) \\
16754 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3+4)^5) - ((6 \times 78)/9)))) & 16754 &:= (9 - (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) - ((4^3) - 2)) \times -1) \\
16755 &:= ((1 + (((2+3)^4) + (5^6))) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 16755 &:= (((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - ((4^3) - 2)) + 1) \\
16756 &:= (1 \times ((2 + ((3+4)^5)) - ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9))) & 16756 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((7 + 6) \times -(5 + (4 \times 321)))) \\
16757 &:= (1 + ((2 + ((3+4)^5)) - ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9))) & 16757 &:= (((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) - (((4+3)^2) + 1)) \\
16758 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3+4)^5) - (6 \times (7 - (8 - 9)))))) & 16758 &:= (((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) + (((4+3)^2) \times -1)) \\
16759 &:= ((12 + ((3+4)^5)) - (6 \times -(7 - (8+9)))) & 16759 &:= (((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) - (((4+3)^2) - 1)) \\
16760 &:= ((12 + (((3+4)^5) + (6 - (7 \times 8)))) - 9) & 16760 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6+5) - 4)^{3+2}) \times -1) \\
16761 &:= (1 \times ((2 + ((3+4)^5)) - (6 \times (7 - (8 - 9)))))) & 16761 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6+5) - 4)^{3+2}) + 1) \\
16762 &:= (1 + ((2 + ((3+4)^5)) - (6 \times (7 - (8 - 9)))))) & 16762 &:= ((((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) - 43) + (2 \times -1)) \\
16763 &:= (((1-2) + ((3+4)^5)) + ((6 \times -7) + (8 - 9))) & 16763 &:= (((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) - ((43+2) - 1)) \\
16764 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3+4)^5) - ((6 \times 7) + (8 - 9)))))) & 16764 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((76 \times -5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16765 &:= (((1-2) + (((3+4)^5) + 6)) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & 16765 &:= (9 - ((8 - (76 \times 5)) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16766 &:= (((1-2) - (((3+4)^5) - (6 \times 7))) \times (8 - 9)) & 16766 &:= ((9 - (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) - ((4^3)/2))) \times -1) \\
16767 &:= (((1+2) + ((3+4)^5)) + ((6 \times -7) + (8 - 9))) & 16767 &:= (((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) + (4 \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
16768 &:= ((1+2) - (((3+4)^5) - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 - 9)) & 16768 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - (((4+3)^2) - 1)) \\
16769 &:= (((1+2) + ((3+4)^5) + 6)) + ((7 \times -8) + 9) & 16769 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(7 + (6 \times (5 + ((4+3)^{2+1})))))) \\
16770 &:= (((1+2) - (3^4)) \times (5 \times -((6 \times 7) - (8 - 9)))) & 16770 &:= (((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) + ((4 \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
16771 &:= ((1-2) \times -(((3+4)^5) - (6 \times ((7+8) - 9)))) & 16771 &:= (((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - 43) + (2 \times -1)) \\
16772 &:= ((12 + ((3+4)^5)) - ((6 \times -7) + 89)) & 16772 &:= (((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) + ((4 \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\
16773 &:= (1 \times ((2 + ((3+4)^5)) - (6 \times ((7+8) - 9)))) & 16773 &:= (9 - (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) - 43) \times -(2 - 1)) \\
16774 &:= (1 + ((2 + ((3+4)^5)) - (6 \times ((7+8) - 9)))) & 16774 &:= (((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - 43) + (2 - 1)) \\
16775 &:= (1 \times (((2 + (3^4)) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) + 9)) & 16775 &:= (((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - 43) - (2 \times -1)) \\
16776 &:= (1 + (((2 + (3^4)) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) + 9)) & 16776 &:= (((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) + (((4^3)/ -2) + 1)) \\
16777 &:= (12 - (((3+4)^5) - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 - 9)) & 16777 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7^{6-5+4})) - (32 - 1)) \\
16778 &:= ((12 + (((3+4)^5) + 6)) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & 16778 &:= (9 - (((8 \times ((7+6) \times 5)) + 4) \times -32) - 1) \\
16779 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times 5)))) \times -(6 + ((7+8) \times 9))) & 16779 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) + ((4 \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
16780 &:= (((1+2) + ((3+4)^5)) + ((6 \times 7) - (8 \times 9))) & 16780 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7^{6-5+4}) - (3^{2+1}))) \\
16781 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3+4)^5) - ((6 \times 7) - (8+9)))))) & 16781 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) + ((4 \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\
16782 &:= (1 \times -((((2 \times 3)^4) - 5) \times -(6+7)) - (8 - 9)) & 16782 &:= (((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) + ((4 \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
16783 &:= (1 - (((((2 \times 3)^4) - 5) \times -(6+7)) - (8 - 9))) & 16783 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - (((6+5) - 4)^{3+2})) \times -1) \\
16784 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) - 5) \times (6+7)) \times -(8 - 9)) & 16784 &:= (((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) - ((4 \times (3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
16785 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) - 5) \times (6+7)) - (8 - 9)) & 16785 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) + (((4^3)/ -2) + 1)) \\
16786 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times 3)^4) + ((5^6) - ((7+8) \times 9)))) & 16786 &:= ((9 - (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) - (4 \times 3))) \times -(2 - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

16787 := $((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + (5^6))) + ((7 + 8) \times -9))$
16788 := $(1 \times (((2 - ((3 + 4)^5)) \times (6 - 7)) - (8 + 9)))$
16789 := $(1 + (((2 - ((3 + 4)^5)) \times (6 - 7)) - (8 + 9)))$
16790 := $((((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - 6) + (7 - (8 + 9)))$
16791 := $((((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) + ((6 \times (7 - 8)) - 9))$
16792 := $((((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - 6) - (7 - (8 - 9)))$
16793 := $((((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - 6) - (7 \times -(8 - 9)))$
16794 := $((((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - (6 + 7)) - (8 - 9))$
16795 := $((1 + 2) - (((((3 + 4)^5) - 6) \times (7 - 8)) + 9))$
16796 := $((((1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) - 5) \times ((6 + 7) \times -(8 - 9)))$
16797 := $((((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - 6) - (7 \times -(8 - 9)))$
16798 := $((((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - (6 + 7)) - (8 - 9))$
16799 := $((1 + 2) - (((3^4) - 5) \times -((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))))$
16800 := $((((1 - 2) + (3^4)) \times (5 \times -(6 \times (7 \times (8 - 9))))))$
16801 := $((1 + 2) + (((3 \times 4) - 5)^{6+7-8} - 9))$
16802 := $(1 \times -(2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + (6 + ((7 - 8) \times 9))))$
16803 := $(1 - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + (6 + ((7 - 8) \times 9))))$
16804 := $((((1 - 2) + (((3 + 4)^5) + 6)) - (7 - (8 - 9)))$
16805 := $((((1 - 2) + (((3 + 4)^5) + 6)) - (7 \times -(8 - 9)))$
16806 := $((((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - 6) + ((7 + 8) - 9))$
16807 := $((((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - 6) + (7 \times -(8 - 9)))$
16808 := $((((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - 6) + (7 - (8 - 9)))$
16809 := $((((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) + ((6 \times (7 - 8)) + 9))$
16810 := $((((1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times (5 \times -((6 \times 7) + (8 - 9))))$
16811 := $((((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - 6) + (7 \times -(8 - 9)))$
16812 := $((((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - (6 - 7)) - (8 - 9))$
16813 := $((1 + 2) - (((((3 + 4)^5) - 6) \times (7 - 8)) - 9))$
16814 := $(1 \times -(2 - (((3 \times 4) - 5)^{6+7-8} + 9)))$
16815 := $(1 - (2 - (((3 \times 4) - 5)^{6+7-8} + 9)))$
16816 := $(1 - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + ((6 \times (7 + 8))/9))))$
16817 := $(1 \times -(2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + ((6 + (7 + 8)) - 9))))$
16818 := $(1 \times -(2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) - (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9))))$
16819 := $((((1 - 2) + (((3 + 4)^5) + 6)) + (7 \times -(8 - 9)))$
16820 := $((((1 - 2) + (((3 + 4)^5) + 6)) + (7 - (8 - 9)))$
16821 := $((((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6 \times (7 - 8)) - 9))$
16822 := $((((1 + 2) + (((3 + 4)^5) + (6 + 7))) + (8 - 9))$
16823 := $((((1 + 2) + (((3 + 4)^5) + 6)) + (7 \times -(8 - 9)))$
16824 := $((((1 + 2) + (((3 + 4)^5) + 6)) + (7 - (8 - 9)))$
16825 := $((1 + 2) - (((((3 + 4)^5) + 6) \times (7 - 8)) - 9))$
16826 := $(1 \times -(((2 + ((3 + 4)^5)) \times (6 - 7)) - (8 + 9)))$
16827 := $(1 - (((2 + ((3 + 4)^5)) \times (6 - 7)) - (8 + 9)))$

16787 := $((((9 + 8) - ((7^{6-5+4}) - 3)) \times -(2 - 1))$
16788 := $(((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + ((4 \times -(3 + 2)) + 1))$
16789 := $((9 + (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) + 4)) - (32 - 1))$
16790 := $((((9 + 8) - (7^{6-5+4})) \times (3 / -(2 + 1)))$
16791 := $((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) + ((4 \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1))$
16792 := $(((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + ((4 \times -3) - (2 + 1)))$
16793 := $(((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - 4) - ((3^2) + 1))$
16794 := $(((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + ((4 + 3) \times -2) + 1))$
16795 := $(((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - 4) - ((3^2) - 1))$
16796 := $(((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - 4) + ((3 \times -2) - 1))$
16797 := $(((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - (4 \times 3)) - (2 \times -1))$
16798 := $((9 - 8) \times -(((7^{6-5+4}) - (3^2)) \times -1))$
16799 := $((9 - 8) - (((7^{6-5+4}) - (3^2)) \times -1))$
16800 := $((((9 - 8) - (7^{(6-5) \times 4})) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1))$
16801 := $(((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + 4) - ((3^2) + 1))$
16802 := $((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - 4) - ((3^2) + 1))$
16803 := $(((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + 4) - ((3^2) - 1))$
16804 := $(((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + 4) + ((3 \times -2) - 1))$
16805 := $(((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + 4) + (3 \times -(2 \times 1))$
16806 := $((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) + ((4 \times -3) + (2 \times 1)))$
16807 := $((9 - 8) - (((7^6)/(5 - (4 \times 3))) + (2 - 1)))$
16808 := $(((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + 4) + (3 \times -(2 - 1))$
16809 := $(((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - 4) - (3 \times -(2 \times 1))$
16810 := $(((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - 4) - ((3 \times -2) - 1))$
16811 := $(((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - 4) + ((3^2) - 1))$
16812 := $((9 + (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) + 4)) - ((3^2) - 1))$
16813 := $(((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - 4) + ((3^2) + 1))$
16814 := $((9 + (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) + 4)) + (3 \times -(2 \times 1)))$
16815 := $((9 - 8) + (7^{6-5+4})) - ((3 \times -2) - 1))$
16816 := $((9 - 8) \times -(((7^{6-5+4}) + (3^2)) \times -1))$
16817 := $(((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + (4 \times 3)) + (2 \times -1))$
16818 := $(((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + 4) - ((3 \times -2) - 1))$
16819 := $(((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + 4) + ((3^2) - 1))$
16820 := $((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - 4) + ((3^2) - 1))$
16821 := $(((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + 4) + ((3^2) + 1))$
16822 := $((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - 4) + ((3^2) + 1))$
16823 := $((9 + (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) + 4)) - (3 \times -(2 - 1)))$
16824 := $((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - (4 \times -(3 - (2 - 1))))$
16825 := $((9 + 8) + ((7^{6-5+4}) + 3)) + (2 \times -1))$
16826 := $((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 \times -(5 \times (4 \times 3))) + (2 \times 1)))$
16827 := $((9 + (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) + 4)) - ((3 \times -2) - 1))$

$$\begin{aligned}
16828 &:= (((1+2) + ((3+4)^5)) - (6-7) + (8+9)) \\
16829 &:= ((12 + ((3+4)^5)) - ((6 \times (7+8)) / -9)) \\
16830 &:= ((1+2) \times -(34 \times -((5 \times 6) + ((7+8) \times 9)))) \\
16831 &:= (((1-2) + ((3+4)^5)) - ((6 \times -7) + (8+9))) \\
16832 &:= ((12 + (((3+4)^5) + 6)) + (7 \times -(8-9))) \\
16833 &:= ((12 + (((3+4)^5) + 6)) + (7 - (8-9))) \\
16834 &:= (12 - (((((3+4)^5) + 6) \times (7-8)) - 9)) \\
16835 &:= (((1+2) + ((3+4)^5)) - ((6 \times -7) + (8+9))) \\
16836 &:= (((((1-2) + ((3+4)^5)) - (6 \times 7)) - (8 \times -9)) \\
16837 &:= ((12 - (((3+4)^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times (8-9)) \\
16838 &:= (1 - (((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 \times 7)) + 89)) \\
16839 &:= ((12^3) - ((45 \times -(6 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9)) \\
16840 &:= (1 \times (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) - 8) / -9)) \\
16841 &:= (1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) - 8) / -9)) \\
16842 &:= ((1+2) - (((3^4) \times ((5 \times 6) - 7)) + 8) \times -9)) \\
16843 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + ((5^6) - 7))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
16844 &:= (((12^3) - 4) - (5 \times -(6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
16845 &:= (((12^3) - (4 - (5^6))) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
16846 &:= (((1+2) - (((3+4)^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times (8-9)) \\
16847 &:= (((((1-2) + ((3+4)^5)) - 6) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
16848 &:= ((1 - ((2+3)^4)) \times ((5 + ((6-7) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
16849 &:= (((1-2) + ((3+4)^5)) - ((6 \times -7) + (8-9))) \\
16850 &:= (((1-2) - (((3+4)^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times (8-9)) \\
16851 &:= (1 \times -((2 + (((3+4)^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times (8-9))) \\
16852 &:= (1 - ((2 + (((3+4)^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times (8-9))) \\
16853 &:= (((1+2) + ((3+4)^5)) - ((6 \times -7) + (8-9))) \\
16854 &:= (((1-2) + ((3+4)^5)) - (6 \times -(7 - (8-9)))) \\
16855 &:= (((1+2) + ((3+4)^5)) - (((6+7) - 8) \times -9)) \\
16856 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) - 5) \times (6+7)) - (8 \times -9)) \\
16857 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + ((5^6) + 7))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
16858 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3+4)^5) + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\
16859 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3+4)^5) + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\
16860 &:= ((1+2) - (((3^4) - (((5^6) + 7) / 8)) \times 9)) \\
16861 &:= (12 - (((3+4)^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times (8-9)) \\
16862 &:= ((12 + (((3+4)^5) + ((6 \times 7) - 8))) + 9) \\
16863 &:= (((1+2) + (((3+4)^5) + 6)) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
16864 &:= (((1+2) + ((3+4)^5)) + (6 \times -((7-8) \times 9))) \\
16865 &:= (((((1-2) + ((3+4)^5)) - 6) + ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
16866 &:= ((1+2) \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times -6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
16867 &:= ((12 + ((3+4)^5)) - (6 \times -(7 - (8-9)))) \\
16868 &:= ((1+2) - (3 - (4 \times (5 + (6 \times (78 \times 9)))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16828 &:= ((9 + (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) + 4)) + ((3^2) - 1)) \\
16829 &:= (((9 + 8) + ((7^{6-5+4}) + 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
16830 &:= ((((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + ((4 \times (3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
16831 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7^{6-5+4})) - ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
16832 &:= ((((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - ((4 \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
16833 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7^{6-5+4}) + (3^2)) \times -1)) \\
16834 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7^{6-5+4})) + ((3^2) + 1)) \\
16835 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5)) \times ((4^3) + (2 - 1))) \\
16836 &:= ((9 + (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) + (4 \times (3 + 2)))) \times 1) \\
16837 &:= ((9 + (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) + (4 \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
16838 &:= ((((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - (((4^3) / -2) + 1)) \\
16839 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) + ((4 \times (3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
16840 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - (4 \times -(3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
16841 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - ((4 \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
16842 &:= ((((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - ((4 \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\
16843 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
16844 &:= ((((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - ((4 \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
16845 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 54)))) \times -((3 + 2) \times -1)) \\
16846 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7^{6-5+4})) - (32 + 1)) \\
16847 &:= ((((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - (4 \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
16848 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - ((4^3) / - (2 \times 1))) \\
16849 &:= ((((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + (43 - (2 - 1))) \\
16850 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) - 4) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\
16851 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - ((4 \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\
16852 &:= ((((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + 43) - (2 \times -1)) \\
16853 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - ((4 \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
16854 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times ((5 \times -(4^3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
16855 &:= ((((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + (((4 + 3)^2) - 1)) \\
16856 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - (4 \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
16857 &:= ((((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + (((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
16858 &:= ((9 + (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) + 43)) - (2 - 1)) \\
16859 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (54 \times 3)))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
16860 &:= ((9 - (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) + ((4^3) - 2))) \times -1) \\
16861 &:= ((9 + (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) + 43)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
16862 &:= ((9 - (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) + (4^3))) \times -(2 - 1)) \\
16863 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) - (6 - ((5^4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
16864 &:= ((9 + (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) + ((4 + 3)^2))) - 1) \\
16865 &:= ((9 + (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) + ((4 + 3)^2))) \times 1) \\
16866 &:= ((9 + (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) + ((4 + 3)^2))) + 1) \\
16867 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) - 6) \times -((5^4) \times 3) - 2) - 1) \\
16868 &:= ((((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + (4^3)) - (2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16869 &:= (((1-2) + ((3+4)^5)) + ((6-(7-8)) \times 9)) \\
16870 &:= (1 + ((2 + ((3+4)^5) - (6 \times (7-(8+9)))))) \\
16871 &:= (((1-2) + ((3^{4+5}) \times 6)) / (7 \times -(8-9))) \\
16872 &:= ((12 + (((3+4)^5) + 6)) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
16873 &:= (((1+2) + ((3+4)^5)) + ((6-(7-8)) \times 9)) \\
16874 &:= (((1-2) + ((3+4)^5)) + (67 - (8-9))) \\
16875 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + (5^6))) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
16876 &:= (1 \times -(2 + (((3+4)^5) + 67)) \times (8-9)) \\
16877 &:= (((1-2) + (((3+4)^5) + 6)) + ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
16878 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3+4)^5) - ((6-7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
16879 &:= (((1-2) + ((3+4)^5)) - 6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)) \\
16880 &:= (((1-2) + (3^4)) \times -((5 \times -(6 \times 7)) + (8-9))) \\
16881 &:= (((1+2) + (((3+4)^5) + 6)) + ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
16882 &:= ((1+2) - (((3+4)^5) \times (6-7)) - (8 \times 9)) \\
16883 &:= (((1+2) + ((3+4)^5)) - 6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)) \\
16884 &:= ((1+2) \times -(3 \times (4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16885 &:= ((((((12+3)^4)/5) + 6) \times -(7+8)) / -9) \\
16886 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3+4)^5) - (6 - (78+9)))) \\
16887 &:= (((1-2) + ((3+4)^5)) + ((6-(7+8)) \times -9)) \\
16888 &:= (((1 - (2-3))^{4 \times 5 - 6}) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
16889 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - (34 \times (5-67))) \times -8) - 9)) \\
16890 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3+4)^5) + ((6+7) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
16891 &:= (((1-2) + (((3+4)^5) + 6)) + (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
16892 &:= ((1-2) \times -(((3+4)^5) + ((6+7) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
16893 &:= (((1+23)^4) - ((5 - ((6^7)/8)) \times -9)) \\
16894 &:= (((1+2) + (((3+4)^5) + 67)) + (8+9)) \\
16895 &:= (((1+2) + (((3+4)^5) + 6)) + (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
16896 &:= ((1-23) \times (((4^5) \times 6) / - (7 - (8-9)))) \\
16897 &:= ((-12 + ((3+4)^5)) + (6 + (7+89))) \\
16898 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + ((5^6) - (7+8)))) - 9) \\
16899 &:= ((12 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times ((6 \times -7) + (8-9))) \\
16900 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) + 5)) \times -((6+7) \times -(8-9))) \\
16901 &:= (((1-2) + ((3+4)^5)) - (((6+7) \times -8) + 9)) \\
16902 &:= ((1+2) \times (((3 \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - 8) \times -9)) \\
16903 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3^4) + ((5+6) \times 78)) \times 9))) \\
16904 &:= ((12 + (((3+4)^5) + 6)) + (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
16905 &:= (((1+2) + ((3+4)^5)) - (((6+7) \times -8) + 9)) \\
16906 &:= ((1-2) \times -(((3+4)^5) + ((6 \times (7+8)) + 9))) \\
16907 &:= (1 \times (((2 - ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -7) - 89)) \\
16908 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3+4)^5) + ((6 \times (7+8)) + 9)))) \\
16909 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3+4)^5) + ((6 \times (7+8)) + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16869 &:= (((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) - (((4^3) - 2) \times -1)) \\
16870 &:= ((9 + ((8 - ((7-6)^5))^4)) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
16871 &:= ((((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) + (4^3)) \times (2-1)) \\
16872 &:= ((((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) + (4^3)) + (2-1)) \\
16873 &:= (((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) - (((4^3) + 2) \times -1)) \\
16874 &:= ((((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) + (4^3)) + (2+1)) \\
16875 &:= ((9-8) - ((7-6) - ((5^4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
16876 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7-6)) + ((5^4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
16877 &:= ((9 - (8-7)) - (6 - ((5^4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
16878 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7-6))^5)) - (((4^3) - 2) \times -1)) \\
16879 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7-6))^5)) + ((4^3) - (2-1))) \\
16880 &:= (9 - (((8 - (7-6))^5) + (4^3)) \times -(2-1)) \\
16881 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7-6))^5)) + ((4^3) + (2-1))) \\
16882 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7-6))^5)) - (((4^3) + 2) \times -1)) \\
16883 &:= ((9 + (((8 - (7-6))^5) + (4^3))) + (2+1)) \\
16884 &:= (98 - (((7^6) / (5 - (4 \times 3))) + 21)) \\
16885 &:= ((9 + ((8-7)^6)) - ((5^4) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
16886 &:= (9 - (((87-6) \times (5^4)) / -3) - (2 \times 1)) \\
16887 &:= (((9+8) + (7^{6-5+4})) - (3 \times -21)) \\
16888 &:= ((9-8) \times ((7+6) + ((5^4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
16889 &:= ((9 - (8-7)) + (6 + ((5^4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
16890 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times -((4 \times -3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
16891 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7-6)) + ((5^4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
16892 &:= (((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) - ((43 \times -2) + 1)) \\
16893 &:= ((9+8) + ((7-6) + ((5^4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
16894 &:= (((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) - ((43 \times -2) - 1)) \\
16895 &:= ((98 + (7^{6-5+4})) - ((3^2) + 1)) \\
16896 &:= ((9 - (8-7)) \times -((6+5) \times -((4^3) \times (2+1)))) \\
16897 &:= ((98 + (7^{6-5+4})) - ((3^2) - 1)) \\
16898 &:= ((98 + (7^{6-5+4})) + ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
16899 &:= ((9-8) \times (((7 + ((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3))^2) - 1)) \\
16900 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 + ((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3))^2) - 1))) \\
16901 &:= ((9-8) - (((7 + ((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3))^2) \times -1)) \\
16902 &:= ((9-8) + (((7 + ((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3))^2) + 1)) \\
16903 &:= ((9-8) - (((7-6) + (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
16904 &:= (98 - (((7^6) / (5 - (4 \times 3))) + (2-1))) \\
16905 &:= ((9 + (8+7)) + (6 + ((5^4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
16906 &:= ((98 + ((7^{6-5+4}) + 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
16907 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times ((5 \times -(4^3)) + (2-1))) \\
16908 &:= ((98 + ((7^{6-5+4}) + 3)) \times (2-1)) \\
16909 &:= ((98 + ((7^{6-5+4}) + 3)) + (2-1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 16910 &:= (1 - (2 + ((3 - ((45 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8)) \times 9))) & 16910 &:= ((98 + ((7^{6-5+4}) + 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
 16911 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times -((45 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8)) + 9)) & 16911 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) - 6) \times -(((5^4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 16912 &:= (1 \times -((((2 \times 3)^4) + 5) \times -(6 + 7)) - (8 - 9)) & 16912 &:= ((98 + (7^{6-5+4})) - ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
 16913 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) - (((5^6) \times (7 - 8)) + 9)) & 16913 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
 16914 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + ((5^6) - 7))) + (8 - 9)) & 16914 &:= (98 - (((7^{6-5+4}) + (3^2)) \times -1)) \\
 16915 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + ((5^6) - 7))) \times -(8 - 9)) & 16915 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - (4 \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
 16916 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + ((5^6) - 7))) - (8 - 9)) & 16916 &:= (9 + ((8 + ((7 + ((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3))^2)) - 1)) \\
 16917 &:= (((-1 - ((2 \times 3)^{4+5-6})) \times -78) - 9) & 16917 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((7 + ((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3))^2)) \times -1)) \\
 16918 &:= (1 \times - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) - (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 16918 &:= (9 + (8 + (((7 + ((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3))^2) + 1))) \\
 16919 &:= ((1 + ((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 6)) \times -(7 \times -(8 - 9))) & 16919 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (((7 \times ((6 + 5) - 4)) - 3)^2))) \times -1) \\
 16920 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6 \times -7) - (8 \times 9))) & 16920 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -(((6 + 5) \times -(4^3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
 16921 &:= ((12 + (((3 + 4)^5) + (6 + 7))) + 89) & 16921 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (43 + 2)) - 1)) \\
 16922 &:= (1 \times ((2 + ((3 + 4)^5)) - (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 16922 &:= (9 + (8 + ((76 + ((5 + 4)^3)) \times 21))) \\
 16923 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16923 &:= ((98 + (7^{6-5+4})) - (3 - 21)) \\
 16924 &:= (1 \times (((2 - ((3^4) \times 5 \times 6)) \times -7) - (8 \times 9))) & 16924 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - (4 \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
 16925 &:= ((1 - ((2 - ((3^4) \times 5 \times 6)) \times 7)) + (8 \times -9)) & 16925 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - (6^5)) \times -((4 - 3) \times 2)) + 1) \\
 16926 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + 5)) \times ((6 + 7) \times -(8 - 9))) & 16926 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7^{(6-5) \times 4})) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
 16927 &:= (1 \times - (2 - ((3^4) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 - 9)))))) & 16927 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(65 \times 4)) + (3^{2+1})) \\
 16928 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + ((5^6) + 7))) + (8 - 9)) & 16928 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times -((4^3) / -(2 \times 1))) \\
 16929 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + ((5^6) + 7))) \times -(8 - 9)) & 16929 &:= (((9 - (8 - (7 - 6))) + (5^4)) \times (3^{2+1})) \\
 16930 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + ((5^6) + 7))) - (8 - 9)) & 16930 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) + 4)) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\
 16931 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) - (((5^6) \times (7 - 8)) - 9)) & 16931 &:= (98 + ((7 \times -6) + ((5^4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
 16932 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3^4) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 - 9)))) & 16932 &:= ((98 + (7^{6-5+4})) + (3^{2+1})) \\
 16933 &:= ((1 - ((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 6)) \times (7 \times -(8 - 9))) & 16933 &:= (98 - (7 \times -(65 \times (4 + (32 + 1)))))) \\
 16934 &:= (1 \times - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) - (6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) & 16934 &:= (9 - (((8 \times -7) + 6) - ((5^4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
 16935 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) - (6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) & 16935 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - (4 \times -(32 \times 1))) \\
 16936 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 + 4)^5) - (6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 16936 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(((7 \times ((6 + 5) - 4)) - 3)^2)) + 1)) \\
 16937 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3^4) \times 5 \times (6 \times 7))) + (8 \times -9)) & 16937 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (43 + 2)) + 1)) \\
 16938 &:= ((1 - (23 - 4)) \times -(5 + ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 16938 &:= ((98 + ((7^{6-5+4}) + 32)) + 1) \\
 16939 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - 6) - ((7 + 8) \times -9)) & 16939 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - (4 \times -(32 + 1))) \\
 16940 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -(4 + ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 16940 &:= ((98 + (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times -(4 \times (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\
 16941 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times 5 \times (6 \times 7))) + (8 \times -9)) & 16941 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times 65) + (4 - 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 16942 &:= ((1 + ((2 - (3^4)) \times 5)) \times ((6 \times -7) + (8 - 9))) & 16942 &:= ((-9 + (((87 \times 65) - 4) \times 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
 16943 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9))) & 16943 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - ((4 \times -32) + 1)) \\
 16944 &:= (1 - (((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9))) & 16944 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -(((6 + 5) \times -(4^3)) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 16945 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times 3)^4) + ((5^6) + (7 + (8 + 9)))))) & 16945 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - ((4 \times -32) - 1)) \\
 16946 &:= (1 \times - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) & 16946 &:= (9 - (((8 \times -7) - 6) - ((5^4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
 16947 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) & 16947 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 76) - 5) \times 4)) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
 16948 &:= ((12 + ((3 + 4)^5)) - (6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9))) & 16948 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - (4 \times -(32 + 1))) \\
 16949 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (4^5)) \times ((6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)) & 16949 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((7 \times 65) + 43) \times -2) - 1) \\
 16950 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + (6 \times (7 + (8 + 9)))))) & 16950 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + (((4 \times 3)^2) - 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16951 &:= (((1+2) + (((3+4)^5) + 6)) - ((7+8) \times -9)) \\
16952 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
16953 &:= ((1 + ((2 + ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times 7)) + (8 \times -9)) \\
16954 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3+4)^5) + (6 \times (7 + (8+9)))))) \\
16955 &:= ((1234 + ((5^6) + 7)) + 89) \\
16956 &:= ((1+2) \times -(((3 \times 4) + ((5+6) \times (7 \times 8))) \times -9)) \\
16957 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((34 \times (5 \times 6)) - 78) \times 9))) \\
16958 &:= ((12 + (((3+4)^5) + 67)) - (8 \times -9)) \\
16959 &:= ((1+2) \times ((3 \times (45 \times (6 \times 7))) - (8+9))) \\
16960 &:= ((12 + (((3+4)^5) + 6)) - ((7+8) \times -9)) \\
16961 &:= (1 \times (((2+3) \times (4 + (5 \times 678))) - 9)) \\
16962 &:= ((1 - ((2+3)^4)) - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times -9)) \\
16963 &:= ((12 + ((3+4)^5)) - (6 \times -(7 + (8+9)))) \\
16964 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 + (45 \times (6 \times 7))) - 8) \times 9))) \\
16965 &:= ((1+2) \times -(3 \times -((45 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) - 9)) \\
16966 &:= ((1 + ((23 + 4) \times (5 - (6 \times 7)))) \times -(8+9)) \\
16967 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3 + (45 \times (6 \times 7))) - 8) \times 9))) \\
16968 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times 3)^4) + ((5^6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
16969 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + (5^6))) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
16970 &:= (1 - ((234 + 5) \times -((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
16971 &:= ((1+2) \times ((3 \times -4) + (5678 - 9))) \\
16972 &:= (((-1 - 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times 7) - 8) - 9) \\
16973 &:= (((-1 + (2^3))^4) + (5 + 6)) \times 7) + 89) \\
16974 &:= ((1 - ((2 + (3^4)) \times 5)) \times ((6 \times -7) - (8 - 9))) \\
16975 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times (56 + (7 \times 89))) \\
16976 &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times -(4 - ((5 \times 678) + 9)))) \\
16977 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3 + (4^5))) + 67) \times -8) - 9)) \\
16978 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3 + (4^5))) + 67) \times -8) - 9)) \\
16979 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3) \times -(4 + (5 \times 678))) - 9)) \\
16980 &:= ((1 - ((2 - ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\
16981 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) \times -(4 \times (((5 + 6) \times 78) - 9)))) \\
16982 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((34 \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) + 9))) \\
16983 &:= (1 + (2 \times -((34 \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) + 9))) \\
16984 &:= ((1 - 23) \times (4 \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9)))) \\
16985 &:= (1 \times -((((2 \times 3)^4) + 5) \times -(6 + 7)) - (8 \times 9))) \\
16986 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times 3)^4) + ((5^6) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
16987 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + ((5^6) - 7))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
16988 &:= (((-1 - 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times 7) + 8) - 9) \\
16989 &:= (((1 + 2) - ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -(7 \times -(8 - 9))) \\
16990 &:= (1 \times -((2 - (((3^4 - 5 + 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
16991 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3^4 - 5 + 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16951 &:= (((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) - (((4 \times 3)^2) \times -1)) \\
16952 &:= (((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) + (((4 \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\
16953 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((7 \times 6) - (5 \times (432 \times 1)))))) \\
16954 &:= (((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) - ((4+3) \times -21)) \\
16955 &:= (((-9 \times ((87 \times 65) - 4))/ -3) + 2) \times 1) \\
16956 &:= (9 - (((876 - 5) - (4^3)) \times -21)) \\
16957 &:= (-9 - ((87 \times -(65 \times (4 - (3 - 2)))) - 1)) \\
16958 &:= ((((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times 5) \times (4^3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
16959 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) + (((4 \times 3)^2) - 1)) \\
16960 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - (((4 \times 3)^2) \times -1)) \\
16961 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) + (((4 \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\
16962 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 65) - 4) \times -(3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
16963 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - ((4+3) \times -21)) \\
16964 &:= ((9 + (((87 \times 65) - 4) \times 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
16965 &:= ((9 + 87) - (6 - ((5^4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
16966 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((((7 - (6 - (5 + 4)))^3) - 2) \times -1)) \\
16967 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (((6 + 54) \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
16968 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -(((6 + 5) \times -(4^3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
16969 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (7 + 65)) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
16970 &:= ((9 - (((87 \times 65) + 4) \times 3) + 2)) \times -1) \\
16971 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 65) - (4 - 3)) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
16972 &:= ((98 - 7) + (6 + ((5^4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
16973 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -(65 \times (4 - (3 - 2)))) + 1)) \\
16974 &:= (98 + ((7 - 6) + ((5^4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
16975 &:= (987 + ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
16976 &:= (987 + (((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
16977 &:= ((9 + 87) + (6 + ((5^4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
16978 &:= (((-9 - ((87 \times 65) - 4)) \times -3) - 2) \times 1) \\
16979 &:= (((-9 - ((87 \times 65) - 4)) \times -3) - 2) + 1) \\
16980 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times ((6 \times -5) + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
16981 &:= (987 + ((6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
16982 &:= (987 - (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
16983 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) \times -((4 \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
16984 &:= ((9 + (((87 \times 65) + 4) \times 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
16985 &:= (((9 + (((87 \times 65) + 4) \times 3)) - 2) + 1) \\
16986 &:= ((98 + 7) + (6 + ((5^4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
16987 &:= (987 - ((6 \times ((5 \times 4)^3))/ - (2 + 1))) \\
16988 &:= ((9 + (((87 \times 65) + 4) \times 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
16989 &:= ((9 + (((87 \times 65) + 4) \times 3) + 2)) + 1) \\
16990 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -7) + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
16991 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 76)) - (5 - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 16992 &:= (((1-2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - (8+9)) \\
 16993 &:= ((1-2) \times -(((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) - (8+9))) \\
 16994 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3^{4-5+6}) - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 16995 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3^{4-5+6}) - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 16996 &:= ((1 - ((2 - ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times 7)) + (8-9)) \\
 16997 &:= ((1 - ((2 - ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times 7)) \times -(8-9)) \\
 16998 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 \times 9))) \\
 16999 &:= (1 - (((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 \times 9))) \\
 17000 &:= (((1+23) - (4^5)) \times ((6-7) \times (8+9))) \\
 17001 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + ((5^6) + 7))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
 17002 &:= ((1+2) - ((3 + (4 \times (5 + (6 \times 7)))) \times -89)) \\
 17003 &:= (((1-2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 \times -(8-9))) \\
 17004 &:= (12 - (((3^{4-5+6}) - 7) \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
 17005 &:= (((12 + ((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - 8) - 9) \\
 17006 &:= ((1 + ((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 \times 7))) - 89) \\
 17007 &:= (((1+2) - ((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) \times (8-9)) \\
 17008 &:= (((1-2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + 8) - 9) \\
 17009 &:= (1 - (2 + ((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8-9))))))) \\
 17010 &:= (((1-2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - (8-9)) \\
 17011 &:= (((1-2) - ((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) \times (8-9)) \\
 17012 &:= (1 \times -((2 + ((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) \times (8-9))) \\
 17013 &:= (1 - ((2 + ((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) \times (8-9))) \\
 17014 &:= (1 \times -((2 + (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 17015 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 17016 &:= (((12^3) + (4^5)) \times 6) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9)) \\
 17017 &:= (((1-2) - ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -(7 \times -(8-9))) \\
 17018 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((34 \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) - 9))) \\
 17019 &:= (1 + (2 \times -((34 \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) - 9))) \\
 17020 &:= (((12^3) + (4 - (5 \times 6))) \times -(7 - (8+9))) \\
 17021 &:= ((12 + (((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + 8)) - 9) \\
 17022 &:= ((12 + ((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) \times -(8-9)) \\
 17023 &:= ((1 + ((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 \times 7))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
 17024 &:= ((1 + ((2 + ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times 7)) + (8-9)) \\
 17025 &:= ((1 + ((2 + ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times 7)) \times -(8-9)) \\
 17026 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(((3 - ((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times 8) - 9))) \\
 17027 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(((3 - ((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times 8) - 9))) \\
 17028 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3^4) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times -7) + (8-9))) \\
 17029 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + (8+9)))) \\
 17030 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + (8+9)))) \\
 17031 &:= (((1+2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 \times -(8-9))) \\
 17032 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 16992 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times (6 \times -((5 - (4^3)) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
 16993 &:= (987 - ((6 + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
 16994 &:= (987 + (6 + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
 16995 &:= ((9 + ((87 \times 65) + (4 - 3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 16996 &:= (9 - (((8 \times -76) + 5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
 16997 &:= (98 + (((7 + ((6 \times (5 \times 4) + 3))^2) - 1)) \\
 16998 &:= (98 - (((7 + ((6 \times (5 \times 4) + 3))^2) \times -1)) \\
 16999 &:= (((((9-8)^7) + 6)^5) - ((4^3) \times -(2+1))) \\
 17000 &:= ((9+8) \times -(((7 - (6 - (5+4)))^3) \times -(2-1))) \\
 17001 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((76 + (5^4)) \times 3) + 21))) \\
 17002 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 6) + (5 + 4)) \times -32) - 1) \\
 17003 &:= (98 - ((76 + ((5 + 4)^3)) \times -21)) \\
 17004 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times ((5 \times -4) - (32 \times 1))) \\
 17005 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times ((5 \times -(4 + 32)) + 1)) \\
 17006 &:= (9 - (((8 \times -76) - 5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
 17007 &:= ((9 + (((87 \times 65) + 4) \times 3)) + 21) \\
 17008 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - ((4^3) \times -(2+1))) \\
 17009 &:= (9 + (((8 - 76) \times 5) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) + 1))) \\
 17010 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 65) + (4 \times 3)) \times -(2+1))) \\
 17011 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 - (7 + 6)) - (5^4)) \times 3)) + 2) - 1) \\
 17012 &:= (-9 + (8 - ((7 - (6 + 54)) \times 321))) \\
 17013 &:= ((9 + ((87 \times 65) + (4 + 3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 17014 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 \times -(5 \times (4 \times 3))) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 17015 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -6) - ((5^4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
 17016 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times -((5 - (4^3)) \times 2)) + 1)) \\
 17017 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (((7 \times 6) - 543) \times -2) - 1) \\
 17018 &:= (-9 + (8 - ((76 - (5^4)) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
 17019 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((76 - (5^4)) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
 17020 &:= (9 - (8 + ((76 - (5^4)) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
 17021 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 - (6 - (5 + 4)))^3)) + 21) \\
 17022 &:= (9 + (((8 - 7)^6) - 54) \times -321) \\
 17023 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (76 \times -((5 \times (43 + 2)) - 1))) \\
 17024 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((76 \times -((5 \times (43 + 2)) - 1))) \\
 17025 &:= ((9 - 8) - (76 \times -((5 \times (43 + 2)) - 1))) \\
 17026 &:= (((9 - (87 \times 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
 17027 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((76 \times -(5 \times (43 + 2))) + 1)) \\
 17028 &:= ((9 - ((87 - 6) \times 5)) \times (43 \times -(2-1))) \\
 17029 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((76 \times -(5 \times (43 + 2))) - 1)) \\
 17030 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 5) + 4))) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
 17031 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
 17032 &:= (9 + (((87 + 6) - (5^4)) \times -32) - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
17033 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9))) \\
17034 &:= (((1 - 23) + (4^5)) \times -((6 - 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\
17035 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 \times (4 + 5678)) - 9))) \\
17036 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) + (4 \times ((5 + (6 \times 78)) \times 9)))) \\
17037 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3^4) \times -(5 - (67 + 8))) + 9)) \\
17038 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -((((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times -8) + 9)) \\
17039 &:= ((12 + (((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + 8)) + 9) \\
17040 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times 3^4) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
17041 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3^4) + (5^6))) - (7 \times -(8 + 9))) \\
17042 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8)))) - 9) \\
17043 &:= ((12 + 3) - (4 \times -((5 + (6 \times 78)) \times 9))) \\
17044 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9))) \\
17045 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9))) \\
17046 &:= (1 \times ((2 - ((34 \times 5) + 67) \times 8)) \times -9) \\
17047 &:= (1 + ((2 - ((34 \times 5) + 67) \times 8)) \times -9) \\
17048 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3+4} - 56) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
17049 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 \times -4) + (5 \times (67 \times (8 + 9))))) \\
17050 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (34 \times 5))) \times (67 - (8 + 9))) \\
17051 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) - ((4^5) - (6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
17052 &:= (((1 - 2) - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -(6 \times -(7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\
17053 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times (3 + (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8))) - 9) \\
17054 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8)))) - 9) \\
17055 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times -(4 \times (5 + (6 \times 78)))) - 9)) \\
17056 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times -7) - (8 - 9))) \\
17057 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3^4) + (5^6))) - ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
17058 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3 \times (4 + 5678)) + 9))) \\
17059 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8))) + 9)) \\
17060 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8))) + 9)) \\
17061 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times 5)))) \times (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
17062 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((34 \times 5) + 67) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
17063 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3^4) - 5))) \times -(((6 + 7) \times 8) + 9)) \\
17064 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3^4) + ((56 + 7) \times 89))) \\
17065 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (((34 \times 5) + 67) \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
17066 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times (67 + 8))))/9)) \\
17067 &:= (((1 + 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))))/9) \\
17068 &:= (1 \times (((2 - ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
17069 &:= ((1 - ((2 - ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times 7)) - (8 \times -9)) \\
17070 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((((3^4) + 5) \times -67) + (8 \times 9))) \\
17071 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times (3 + (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8))) + 9)) \\
17072 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8)))) + 9) \\
17073 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 45))) \times ((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
17033 &:= ((9 - (((87 + 6) - (5^4)) \times 32)) \times 1) \\
17034 &:= (9 + (((87 + 6) - (5^4)) \times -32) + 1) \\
17035 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times (65 - 4)))) \times ((3 + 2) \times -1)) \\
17036 &:= (9 + (8 - ((76 - (5^4)) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
17037 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -((6 + (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
17038 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - ((6 + (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
17039 &:= (((((-98 \times (7 - 65)) - 4) \times 3) - 2) + 1) \\
17040 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times ((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3))) \times -21)) \\
17041 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times ((6 \times (54 - 3)) - 2)) + 1))) \\
17042 &:= (((((-98 \times (7 - 65)) - 4) \times -3) - 2) \times -1) \\
17043 &:= (-9 - (87 \times -((65 \times (4 - (3 - 2))) + 1))) \\
17044 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
17045 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
17046 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times -((7 + 6) \times ((54 \times 3) + 2))) + 1)) \\
17047 &:= (9 + ((8 - 7) + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
17048 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times -((7 + 6) \times ((54 \times 3) + 2))) - 1)) \\
17049 &:= (98 + (76 + ((5^4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
17050 &:= (((9 - (8 + 76)) + (5^4)) \times (32 - 1)) \\
17051 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (((7 \times 6) - 543) \times -2) + 1) \\
17052 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
17053 &:= ((9 + (((87 \times 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times 1) \\
17054 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
17055 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)))) \times (3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
17056 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7^{6-5+4})) + 321) \\
17057 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 + 6) \times ((54 \times 3) + 2)) - 1)) \\
17058 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 - 7) \times 6) + (5^4)) \times 3) + 21) \\
17059 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - (4 \times -(3 \times 21))) \\
17060 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 - 5 + 4! \times (-3! + (2 + 1)!) \\
17061 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
17062 &:= (((9 + (87 \times 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
17063 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + (4^{3+2-1})) \\
17064 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 + 6) \times ((54 \times 3) + 2))) + 1)) \\
17065 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times ((54 \times 3) + 2)))) \times 1) \\
17066 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times ((5 \times -(4^3)) - (2 \times 1))) \\
17067 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times 65) + 43)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
17068 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - (4 \times -(3 \times 21))) \\
17069 &:= (((((-9 - 8) - (76 \times 5)) \times -43) - 2) \times 1) \\
17070 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times -((4 \times 3) + 21))) \\
17071 &:= (((9 + 8) + (76 \times 5)) \times -(43 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
17072 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) + (4^{3+2-1})) \\
17073 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6^5)/4)) \times -(3 \times -(2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
17074 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -(((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times -8) - 9)) \\
17075 &:= (1 - ((2^3) - (((45 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9))) \\
17076 &:= (12 \times -(((3 + 4) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8)) - 9)) \\
17077 &:= (1 \times (((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9))) \\
17078 &:= (((1 + ((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 \times 7))) - 8) - 9) \\
17079 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (3 - (((45 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9))) \\
17080 &:= (1 \times (2 \times (3 + (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) + 9))) \\
17081 &:= (1 + (2 \times (3 + (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) + 9))) \\
17082 &:= ((1 - (23 + 4)) \times (((5 \times (6 + 7)) + 8) \times -9)) \\
17083 &:= (1 \times -((2 - 3) - (((45 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9))) \\
17084 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
17085 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
17086 &:= (1 \times - (2 \times -(((3 + ((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times 8) - 9))) \\
17087 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3 + ((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times 8) - 9))) \\
17088 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))))) \\
17089 &:= (1 \times - (2 + (3 \times ((45 - 678) \times 9)))) \\
17090 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) + (((45 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9))) \\
17091 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times (4 - ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
17092 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - (6 \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
17093 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times - (6 \times 7)) - (8 - 9))) \\
17094 &:= (1 - (((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times - (6 \times 7)) - (8 - 9))) \\
17095 &:= ((1 + ((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 \times 7))) \times - (8 - 9)) \\
17096 &:= (((1 + ((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 \times 7))) - 8) + 9) \\
17097 &:= ((1 + ((2 + ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times 7)) - (8 \times -9)) \\
17098 &:= ((1 - 2) - (((3^4) \times - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) - 89)) \\
17099 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (((3^4) \times - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) - 89)) \\
17100 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 \times - (4 + (5 \times (67 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
17101 &:= ((1 + ((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 6)) \times (7 \times - (8 - 9))) \\
17102 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + 89))) \\
17103 &:= (12 + (3 \times - ((45 - 678) \times 9))) \\
17104 &:= (1 \times (2 + (34 \times ((5 - 6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
17105 &:= (1 + (2 + (34 \times ((5 - 6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
17106 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 + 4) + (5 \times (67 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
17107 &:= (1 \times - (2 - ((3 + ((45 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) \times 9))) \\
17108 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 + ((45 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) \times 9))) \\
17109 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (((45 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) \times -9)) \\
17110 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + (5^6)) + (78 \times -9)) \\
17111 &:= (12 - (((3^4) \times - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) - 89)) \\
17112 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times -9)) \\
17113 &:= (1 - (2 \times - (3 \times (4 \times ((5 + 6) + (78 \times 9)))))) \\
17114 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + ((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times 8))) + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
17074 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((65 \times 4) + 3)) - 21) \\
17075 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + 2)) + 1) \\
17076 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 - (7^6))) + 5) / ((4^3) - 2)) - 1) \\
17077 &:= (9 - ((8 - 76) \times - (5 - (4^{3+2-1})))) \\
17078 &:= ((9 - ((8 + (7 \times ((6 + 5)^4))) / 3) / (2 \times -1)) \\
17079 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (5 - 43))) - 21) \\
17080 &:= ((98 - (7 \times 6)) \times - (5 \times - ((4^3) - (2 + 1)))) \\
17081 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times ((6 + 5)^4))) / (3 \times - (2 \times 1))) \\
17082 &:= (9 - (((8 + 76) + ((5 + 4)^3)) \times -21)) \\
17083 &:= (((9 + 8) - (76 \times (5 \times (43 + 2)))) \times -1) \\
17084 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 + 5)^4))) / - (3 \times - (2 \times 1))) \\
17085 &:= ((9 + 8) \times - ((76 \times - (5 + 4)) - 321)) \\
17086 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + (7 \times ((6 + 5)^4))) / 3) / - 2) - 1) \\
17087 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times ((6 + 5)^4))) / 3) / - (2 \times -1)) \\
17088 &:= (9 - ((8 \times - (7 \times ((65 - 4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1)) \\
17089 &:= (9 + (8 \times - (7 - (((6 \times 5) + 4) \times (3 \times 21)))))) \\
17090 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times - (6 - (5 \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))) \\
17091 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((76 - (5^4)) \times - (32 - 1))) \\
17092 &:= (((-9 - 8) - (76 \times 5)) \times -43) + 21) \\
17093 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + 21) \\
17094 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5)) \times - (((4^3) + 2) \times -1)) \\
17095 &:= (-9 + (8 \times - (7 - (65 \times (((4^3) / 2) + 1)))))) \\
17096 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (76 \times - ((5 \times (43 + 2)) - 1))) \\
17097 &:= (9 - (8 \times - ((7 \times ((65 - 4) \times (3 + 2))) + 1))) \\
17098 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (76 \times (5 \times (43 + 2)))) - 1)) \\
17099 &:= ((9 - 8) \times - ((76 \times - (5 \times (43 + 2))) + 1)) \\
17100 &:= (9 + ((8 + (((7 - 6) \times 5)^4)) \times (3^{2+1}))) \\
17101 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 76) + 5) \times 4)) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
17102 &:= (9 + ((8 \times 7) + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
17103 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 65) + 43) \times - (2 + 1))) \\
17104 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (76 \times - ((5 \times (43 + 2)) + 1))) \\
17105 &:= ((-9 \times - (8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)))) - (32 - 1)) \\
17106 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times - (7 \times (6 \times (54 - 3)))) + 21)) \\
17107 &:= (((-98 + 7) \times - (((6 \times 5) + (4^3)) \times 2)) - 1) \\
17108 &:= ((98 - 7) \times (((6 \times 5) + (4^3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
17109 &:= (9 \times - ((8 \times - (7 - (6 \times (5 - 43)))) - 21)) \\
17110 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times - ((7 \times (6 \times (54 - 3))) - 2)) + 1)) \\
17111 &:= (98 + ((7 - (6 + 54)) \times -321)) \\
17112 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times - (6 - ((5 \times ((4 \times 3)^2)) - 1))) \\
17113 &:= ((9^{8-(7-6) \times 5}) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
17114 &:= ((((-98 - 7) \times (6 + (5 \times (4^3)))) / - 2) - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$17115 := ((1 + (2 \times 3^4))) \times ((5 \times -6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9))$
 $17116 := (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times -9))$
 $17117 := (-1 + ((2 + (34 \times ((5 - 6) \times (7 \times 8)))) \times -9))$
 $17118 := ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 \times (4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - 8) \times -9))$
 $17119 := (1 - ((2 - (34 \times 56)) \times -((7 - 8) \times 9)))$
 $17120 := ((((-1 - 2) - ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -7) + 89)$
 $17121 := ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times -4) - (5 \times (67 \times (8 + 9))))$
 $17122 := (1 \times -(2 \times -(((3 + ((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times 8) + 9)))$
 $17123 := (1 - (2 \times -(((3 + ((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times 8) + 9)))$
 $17124 := (12 \times (3 + (4 \times (((5 + 6) - 7) \times 89))))$
 $17125 := ((12 + ((3 + 4)^5)) - (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times -9))$
 $17126 := (1 + ((2 + (3 \times 45)) \times (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9))))$
 $17127 := (((1 + 2) + (34 \times 5)) \times -((6 \times -(7 + 8)) - 9))$
 $17128 := (1 \times (2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) \times 67)/8) - 9)))$
 $17129 := (1 + (2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) \times 67)/8) - 9)))$
 $17130 := (((12^3) - (4 + (5 + 6))) \times -(7 - (8 + 9)))$
 $17131 := (1 \times -((2 + 3) - ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))$
 $17132 := ((1 - 2) - (3 - ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))$
 $17133 := ((1 - 2) \times (3 - ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))$
 $17134 := ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 + 4)^5) + ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))$
 $17135 := (((12^3) + (4^5)) \times 6) - (7 \times -89)$
 $17136 := ((1 + 2) - (3 - ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))$
 $17137 := (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6 \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9))$
 $17138 := ((1 - 2) + (3 + ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))$
 $17139 := ((1 - 2) \times -(3 + ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))$
 $17140 := (((12^3) - ((4 \times 5) - 6)) \times -(7 - (8 + 9)))$
 $17141 := (1 - (2 \times -((3 + (((4^5) \times 67)/8)) - 9)))$
 $17142 := ((1 + 2) + (3 + ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))$
 $17143 := (((1 + 2) - 34) \times (5 - ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))$
 $17144 := (1 \times -((((2 - 3^4) \times (5^6)) + 7)/(8 \times 9)))$
 $17145 := (1 - (((2 - 3^4) \times (5^6)) + 7)/(8 \times 9))$
 $17146 := ((12 + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6 \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9))$
 $17147 := (1 \times (2 + ((34 \times ((56 + 7) \times 8)) + 9)))$
 $17148 := (1 + (2 + ((34 \times ((56 + 7) \times 8)) + 9)))$
 $17149 := (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) \times 67)/8))) + 9))$
 $17150 := (1 - ((2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) \times 67)/8))) + 9))$
 $17151 := (((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6 \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9))$
 $17152 := (1 - (((2 + 3) \times -(4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 78))) + 9))$
 $17153 := (1 \times -((((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times 6) + 7) \times -(8 + 9))$
 $17154 := (1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times 6) + 7) \times -(8 + 9))$
 $17155 := (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6 \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9))$
 $17156 := ((1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) \times 67)/8)))) + 9)$

$17115 := ((98 + 7) \times -((6 \times -((5 + 4) \times 3)) - (2 - 1)))$
 $17116 := (9 + ((8 + (76 \times (5 \times (43 + 2)))) - 1))$
 $17117 := (9 - ((8 + (76 \times (5 \times (43 + 2)))) \times -1))$
 $17118 := (9 + (8 + ((76 \times (5 \times (43 + 2))) + 1)))$
 $17119 := ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times ((54 \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1))$
 $17120 := ((((-9 - 8) \times -7) - 654) \times (32 \times -1))$
 $17121 := (9 + ((8 - (76 \times 5)) \times -(43 + (2 + 1))))$
 $17122 := (98 - (76 \times -((5 \times (43 + 2)) - 1)))$
 $17123 := ((-9 + (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) + 4)) + 321)$
 $17124 := (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times (6 \times (54 - 3)))) + 21))$
 $17125 := ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (65 - 4)))) \times -((3 + 2) \times -1))$
 $17126 := (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times (65 - 4)))) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1)$
 $17127 := (9 - (((8 + 7) - 6) + (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))$
 $17128 := (98 - (7 - ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3^{2+1}))))$
 $17129 := (9 + (((8 + 7) \times 6) - (5^4)) \times -(32 \times 1))$
 $17130 := (9 + (((8 + 7) \times 6) - (5^4)) \times -32 + 1)$
 $17131 := ((((-9 + 87) \times -6) + 5) \times ((4 \times -(3^2)) - 1))$
 $17132 := (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + 4) + 321)$
 $17133 := ((9 + 87) - ((6 + (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1})))$
 $17134 := ((-9 \times -876) - (5 \times -((43^2) + 1)))$
 $17135 := ((-98 \times -7) + (65 + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})))$
 $17136 := ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6 \times 5) + 4) \times -(3 \times 21)))$
 $17137 := (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times (65 \times 4)) + 321)))$
 $17138 := ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times 5) - (4^3))) - 2) \times -1)$
 $17139 := ((((-9 \times (87 \times (6 + 5))) + 43) \times -2) - 1)$
 $17140 := (9 - ((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times -(4 + (32 + 1))))$
 $17141 := ((9 + (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) + 4)) + 321)$
 $17142 := (98 + (7 + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3^{2+1}))))$
 $17143 := (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times (6 \times (54 - 3)))) + (2 \times 1)))$
 $17144 := (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times (6 \times (54 - 3)))) + (2 - 1)))$
 $17145 := (((9 - 8) + (76 \times 5)) \times -((43 + 2) \times -1))$
 $17146 := (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times (6 \times (54 - 3)))) - (2 - 1)))$
 $17147 := (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times (6 \times (54 - 3)))) - (2 \times 1)))$
 $17148 := (9 - (87 \times -((654/3) - 21)))$
 $17149 := ((9 - 8) \times (765 + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})))$
 $17150 := ((9 + ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) \times -1))$
 $17151 := ((-9 \times -((8 + 7) + ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3))) - 21)$
 $17152 := ((-98 \times -((7 + 6) + (54 \times 3))) - (2 \times -1))$
 $17153 := (9 - (8 \times -(((7 + (6 + 54)) \times 32) - 1)))$
 $17154 := (9 \times -((8 + 7) - (((6 + 54) \times 32) + 1)))$
 $17155 := ((9 + (((8 \times 76) + 5) \times (4 - 32))) \times -1)$
 $17156 := (-9 + (((8 \times 76) + 5) \times -(4 - 32)) + 1)$

$$\begin{aligned}
17157 &:= (1 \times -((2 - (3 \times 45)) \times -(6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 17157 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) - ((5 + 4)^3)))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
17158 &:= (1 - ((2 - (3 \times 45)) \times -(6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 17158 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + (6 \times 5))) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
17159 &:= (1 - (23 \times -((4 \times (5 + 6)) + (78 \times 9)))) & 17159 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) + ((4 + 3)^{2 + 1})) \\
17160 &:= ((1 + 23) - ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times -(7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 17160 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 76) \times 5)) \times -(4 \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
17161 &:= (1 + ((234 + (5 \times 6)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 17161 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 + (6 + 54)) \times (32 \times 1)))) \\
17162 &:= (1 - (((2^{3+4}) \times -(56 + 78)) - 9)) & 17162 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 + (6 + 54)) \times 32)) - 1)) \\
17163 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times -(7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 17163 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + (4 \times 3)))))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
17164 &:= ((12 + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6 \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9)) & 17164 &:= ((9 - (8 - (7 + 6))) \times (((5 \times (4 + 3))^2) + 1)) \\
17165 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 + ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) & 17165 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 76) - 54) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
17166 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3 + ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) & 17166 &:= ((9 + 8) + (765 + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
17167 &:= ((1 + ((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 \times 7))) - (8 \times -9)) & 17167 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) - (5 \times 432)))) \times -1) \\
17168 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -3 + (((4^5) \times 67)/8))) - 9) & 17168 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times -((7 + 6) - (5 \times 432))) + 1)) \\
17169 &:= ((12^3) - (((4^5) + 6) \times -(7 + 8)) + 9) & 17169 &:= ((98 - (7 - 6)) \times ((5 - (4^3)) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
17170 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) \times -(4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 78))) - 9)) & 17170 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 + 5) - ((4 \times 3)^{2 + 1}))) \\
17171 &:= (-1 + (2 - (34 \times ((5 - 6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 17171 &:= (9 + (((87 + 6) - (5 - 43))^2) + 1) \\
17172 &:= (1 \times (2 - (34 \times (((5 - 67) \times 8) - 9)))) & 17172 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times (54 \times -(3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
17173 &:= (1 + (2 - (34 \times (((5 - 67) \times 8) - 9)))) & 17173 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 76) + 5) \times (4 - 32))) \times 1) \\
17174 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (3 \times (4 + 5))) \times -(678 + 9))) & 17174 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 76) + 5) \times -(4 - 32)) + 1) \\
17175 &:= (12 - ((3 + ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) \times -9)) & 17175 &:= (((-9 \times (((8 - 7) \times 6)^5))/ -4) - 321) \\
17176 &:= (1 \times -2 \times -3 + (((4^5) \times 67)/8 + 9))) & 17176 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(76 \times -((5 \times (43 + 2)) + 1))) \\
17177 &:= (1 - (2 \times -3 + (((4^5) \times 67)/8 + 9))) & 17177 &:= ((9 - 8) - (76 \times -((5 \times (43 + 2)) + 1))) \\
17178 &:= (-1 + (2 - ((3 - (4 \times (56 - 7))) \times 89))) & 17178 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 \times 6)) - (((5^4) - 3) \times -21)) \\
17179 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) - (((4^5) - (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 17179 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -((4^3) + 21))) \\
17180 &:= (1 - ((2^3) - (((4^5) - (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 17180 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times 6)) - ((5^4) \times 3))) - 2) + 1) \\
17181 &:= (1 \times (23 \times -((4 + 5) - ((6 + 78) \times 9)))) & 17181 &:= (9 - ((87 - 6) \times -((5 \times 43) - (2 + 1)))) \\
17182 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 - 4))^5)) \times -((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9))) & 17182 &:= (-9 - (8 - (7 \times (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3) \times 21)))) \\
17183 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) - (((4^5) - (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 17183 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 76) - 54) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
17184 &:= (1 - (((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -(6 \times 7)) - 89)) & 17184 &:= (((9 + (87 \times 65)) + (4^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
17185 &:= (1 + (((234 - 5) \times (67 + 8)) + 9)) & 17185 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
17186 &:= (1 \times ((2 - 3) + (((4^5) - (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 17186 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -((7 + 6) - (5 \times 432))) + 1)) \\
17187 &:= (1 + ((2 - 3) + (((4^5) - (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 17187 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (((76 \times 5) - 43) \times (2 + 1))) \\
17188 &:= (1 \times -((2 - 3) - (((4^5) - (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 17188 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7! - 6! - 5) \times 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\
17189 &:= (1 - ((2 - 3) - (((4^5) - (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 17189 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + 7) + (((6 + (5^4)) \times 3) + 2))) - 1) \\
17190 &:= (((12^3) - (4 + 5)) \times -(6 \times (7 + 8))) / -9) & 17190 &:= (9 \times -((8 - 7) - (((6^5)/4) - (32 + 1)))) \\
17191 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 + ((4^5) + (6 - 78))) \times 9))) & 17191 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + 7) + (((6 + (5^4)) \times 3) + 2))) + 1) \\
17192 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) + (((4^5) - (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 17192 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(6 - (5 \times (432 - 1)))) \\
17193 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -3) - (((4^5) - (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 17193 &:= ((9 + 8) - (76 \times -((5 \times (43 + 2)) + 1))) \\
17194 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -3) - (((4^5) - (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) & 17194 &:= ((-98 - (7 \times 6)) - (54 \times -321)) \\
17195 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 34) \times 5)) \times -(((6 + 7) \times -8) + 9)) & 17195 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times (543 / -(2 + 1))) \\
17196 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) + (6 \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 17196 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) - ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3))) - 21) \\
17197 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 + 4)^5) - (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) & 17197 &:= (98 - ((76 \times -(5 \times (43 + 2))) + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 17198 &:= (-1 - (((234 + 5) \times (6 - 78)) + 9)) \\
 17199 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -((4 \times -5) + (6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\
 17200 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^4)) \times -(5 \times -((6 \times 7) - (8 - 9)))) \\
 17201 &:= (-1 - (((2^3) \times 45) + 6) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\
 17202 &:= (12 + (3 + (((4^5) - (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 17203 &:= (1 - (((2^3) \times 45) + 6) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\
 17204 &:= ((1 - 23) \times ((45 - (6 - 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
 17205 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -((4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 78)) + 9))) \\
 17206 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) \times -((4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 78)) + 9))) \\
 17207 &:= (((-1 + ((2^3) \times (45 \times 6))) - 7) \times 8) - 9 \\
 17208 &:= (((12^3) \times ((4 + 5) - (6 - 7))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
 17209 &:= ((12 + ((3 + 4)^5)) + (6 \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 17210 &:= (((12^3) + (4 - (5 + 6))) \times -(7 - (8 + 9))) \\
 17211 &:= (1 + (23 + (((4^5) - (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 17212 &:= (-1 + (((2 - (3^4)) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) - 9)) \\
 17213 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (3^4)) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) - 9)) \\
 17214 &:= (1 + (((2 - (3^4)) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) - 9)) \\
 17215 &:= (1 \times -((((2^3) \times (45 \times 6)) - 7) \times -8) + 9) \\
 17216 &:= (1 - (((((2^3) \times (45 \times 6)) - 7) \times -8) + 9)) \\
 17217 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times -(((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)))) \\
 17218 &:= (1 \times -((2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 - 89)))))) \\
 17219 &:= (1 \times -((2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + (6 \times (78 - 9)))))) \\
 17220 &:= (((1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times -(5 \times -((6 \times (7 \times (8 - 9)))))) \\
 17221 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (((34 \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
 17222 &:= (((12^3) + (4 + (5^6))) + ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
 17223 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3) - (4 \times 56)) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 17224 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((34 \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
 17225 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3) - (45 \times 6)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 17226 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) - (45 \times 6)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 17227 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times -(5 + (6 + (7 + 89)))) \\
 17228 &:= (1 - (2 + (((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times 78) + 9))) \\
 17229 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times -78) - 9)) \\
 17230 &:= (((12^3) - (4 - (5^6))) + (7 \times -(8 + 9))) \\
 17231 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - (3^4)) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) - 9)) \\
 17232 &:= (1 - (((2 - (3^4)) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) - 9)) \\
 17233 &:= (1 \times -((((2^3) \times (45 \times 6)) - 7) \times -8) - 9) \\
 17234 &:= (1 - (((((2^3) \times (45 \times 6)) - 7) \times -8) - 9)) \\
 17235 &:= ((12 + 3) \times (((4^5) + (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 17236 &:= (1 \times -((2 - (((3 + (4^5)) - (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 17237 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 + (4^5)) - (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 17238 &:= (((12^3) + (4 + (5^6))) + (7 \times -(8 + 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 17198 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 76)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
 17199 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3) \times 21))) \\
 17200 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 \times 4)^{3-2+1})) \\
 17201 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times (6 - ((5 \times 4) - 321)))))) \\
 17202 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 - (5 \times (4 \times (3 - 21)))))) \\
 17203 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) - ((6^5) + 43)) \times -2) - 1) \\
 17204 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times -((43 + 2) - 1))) \\
 17205 &:= ((98 + (7 + 6)) \times -(5 \times -(4 + (3^{2+1})))) \\
 17206 &:= ((-98 / -7) \times -((6 \times -(5 \times (43 - 2))) + 1)) \\
 17207 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 76) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
 17208 &:= ((98 + (76 \times 5)) \times -((4 + 32) \times -1)) \\
 17209 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - 6) - (54 \times -321)) \\
 17210 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times (6 + (5 \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))) \\
 17211 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) - ((5 + 4)^3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 17212 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 - (6 + 5)) \times -4321)) \\
 17213 &:= (((-9 \times (87 \times (6 + 5))) + (4 + 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
 17214 &:= (9 - ((87 + 6) \times -(5 \times (4 + (32 + 1)))))) \\
 17215 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) - (6 \times -((5 + 4) \times 321))) \\
 17216 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3) \times 21)))) \\
 17217 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)))) \times -((3 \times -(2 + 1)))) \\
 17218 &:= (((-9 \times -((87 \times (6 + 5))) - 4) \times (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
 17219 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 654) / -3) - (2 + 1)) \\
 17220 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times 6)) - ((5^4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
 17221 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (6 + (54 \times 321))) \\
 17222 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -654) / -((3 \times -(2 - 1)))) \\
 17223 &:= (((98 - 7) - (((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 17224 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 76) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
 17225 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times ((54 \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
 17226 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
 17227 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
 17228 &:= (9 - (((8 + 76) \times -(5 \times (43 - 2))) + 1)) \\
 17229 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 76) \times (5 \times (43 - 2)))) \times 1) \\
 17230 &:= (9 - (((8 + 76) \times -(5 \times (43 - 2))) - 1)) \\
 17231 &:= ((9 - (876 \times (5 - (4^3)))) / (2 + 1)) \\
 17232 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times ((6 - (5 \times 432)) \times -1)) \\
 17233 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((7 + (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times (3 - 21)))))))) \\
 17234 &:= (((9 + (8 \times 76)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
 17235 &:= (9 - (87 \times -(6 \times (5 + (4 + (3 + 21)))))) \\
 17236 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -(6 \times (5 - (4 - 32)))) - 1)) \\
 17237 &:= (9 + ((876 \times (5 - (4^3))) / - (2 + 1))) \\
 17238 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 + 6) \times -(54 + (3 + 21))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 17239 & := (1 \times -(2 + ((345 \times (6 - (7 \times 8))) + 9))) \\
 17240 & := (((12^3) - 4) \times -5) \times (6 - (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
 17241 & := ((1 + 2) - (((3 + (4^5)) - (6 + 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
 17242 & := (-1 + (2 - ((345 \times (6 - (7 \times 8))) + 9))) \\
 17243 & := (1 \times (2 - ((345 \times (6 - (7 \times 8))) + 9))) \\
 17244 & := ((1 + 2) \times -(3 \times -(4 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9))))))) \\
 17245 & := (1 + (((2 \times (3 - ((4^5) - 67))) - 8) \times -9)) \\
 17246 & := (1 - ((2 + ((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times 78)) - 9)) \\
 17247 & := ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times -78) + 9)) \\
 17248 & := ((1 - 23) \times -(4 + (5 \times (67 + 89)))) \\
 17249 & := ((1 + ((2^3) \times 45) + 6) \times -((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
 17250 & := (((12^3) - ((4 + 5) - 6) \times -(7 - (8 + 9))) \\
 17251 & := (-1 + (2 + (345 \times (67 - (8 + 9)))) \\
 17252 & := (1 \times (2 + (345 \times (67 - (8 + 9)))) \\
 17253 & := (((1 + 2)^{3+4}) \times -(56 + (7 + 8)) / -9) \\
 17254 & := (1 - ((23 + 4) \times -(567 + (8 \times 9))) \\
 17255 & := ((1 - (2 + 34)) \times ((5 + 6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 17256 & := (((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) + ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times -9)) \\
 17257 & := ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 + 4)^5) - ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
 17258 & := (1 - ((2 + (345 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\
 17259 & := (123 - ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times -(7 \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 17260 & := (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) + ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times -9)) \\
 17261 & := (1 + ((2 + 3) \times -(4 - (((56 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\
 17262 & := (1 \times (((2 + 34) - (((5^6) + 7) / 8)) \times -9)) \\
 17263 & := (((12^3) \times ((4 + 5) - (6 - 7))) - (8 + 9)) \\
 17264 & := (1 \times -(2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + ((6 \times 78) - 9))) \\
 17265 & := (1 - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + ((6 \times 78) - 9))) \\
 17266 & := (1 \times -(2 \times -((34 + (56 + 7)) \times 89))) \\
 17267 & := (((12^3) - (4 - ((5^6) + 7))) - 89) \\
 17268 & := (1 \times (2 + (((3 + 4)^5) + ((6 \times 78) - 9))) \\
 17269 & := ((12 + ((3 + 4)^5)) + ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times -9)) \\
 17270 & := (((12^3) - (4 - ((5^6) - 7))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
 17271 & := ((1 - 2) \times (((34 \times 56) + (7 + 8)) \times -9)) \\
 17272 & := (1 \times (((2 + 3) + (4^5)) - (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 17273 & := (1 + (((2 + 3) + (4^5)) - (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 17274 & := (1 - (23 \times -((4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) - 89)) \\
 17275 & := ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times -((5 + 6) - (78 \times 9))) \\
 17276 & := (1 \times -(((2^3) + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\
 17277 & := (1 - (((2^3) + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\
 17278 & := (((12^3) + ((4 + (5^6)) - 7)) + (8 \times -9)) \\
 17279 & := (1 \times -(2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9))))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 17239 & := ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 - 32)))))) \times -1 \\
 17240 & := ((9 - (876 - 5)) \times -(4 \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
 17241 & := (9 + (8 \times -((7 - 6) - (5 \times (432 - 1)))) \\
 17242 & := (((-9 + 87) \times (6 + 5)) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
 17243 & := (9 + (8 + (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times (3^{2 + 1}))) \\
 17244 & := (9 + ((87 - (((6^5) / 4) \times 3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 17245 & := (-9 - (((87 - 6) \times -((5 \times 43) - 2)) - 1)) \\
 17246 & := (-9 + ((876 - 5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
 17247 & := ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) + (432 - 1)) \\
 17248 & := ((9 - (8 - 76)) \times -((5 \times -43 + 2) + 1)) \\
 17249 & := (9 - (8 \times -((7 - 6) \times (5 \times (432 - 1)))) \\
 17250 & := ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -((5 + (43 + 2)) \times -1)) \\
 17251 & := (((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) - 654) \times 3)) + 2) \times -1) \\
 17252 & := (9 + ((8 \times -(7 + (6^5))) + (43^{2 + 1})) \\
 17253 & := ((9 - (8 \times (76 + 5))) \times (4 - (32 - 1)) \\
 17254 & := (((-98 - 76) \times -5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
 17255 & := ((9 + 8) \times -(7 \times -(6 - ((5 \times (4 - 32)) + 1)))) \\
 17256 & := ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -((6 \times -(5 \times (4 \times (3 \times 2)))) + 1)) \\
 17257 & := ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 - 32)))) \times 1) \\
 17258 & := (9 + ((8 \times -(7 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 - 32)))) + 1)) \\
 17259 & := ((9 - 8) - (76 - (54 \times 321))) \\
 17260 & := ((98 + 765) \times (4 \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
 17261 & := (9 - (((87 - 6) \times -((5 \times 43) - 2)) + 1)) \\
 17262 & := ((98 + (7 \times (65 \times 4))) \times -(3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
 17263 & := (9 - (((87 - 6) \times -((5 \times 43) - 2)) - 1)) \\
 17264 & := (((9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times -((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 17265 & := ((98 - ((7 + ((6^5) / 4)) \times 3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 17266 & := ((((-9 \times (87 + (6 \times (5^4)))) + 3) / -2) + 1) \\
 17267 & := (-9 - (8 + ((7 - (6 + 5)) \times 4321))) \\
 17268 & := (9 - (((87 \times 6) + (5 - 4)) \times -(32 + 1))) \\
 17269 & := ((-98 \times (7 - ((65 - 4) \times 3))) + 21) \\
 17270 & := ((9 + ((8 - 7)^6)) \times -((54 \times -32) + 1)) \\
 17271 & := (9 - (((87 + 6) + ((5 + 4)^3)) \times -21)) \\
 17272 & := ((9 + 8) \times -(((7 + 6) - 5) \times -((4 \times 32) - 1))) \\
 17273 & := (9 + (8 \times -((7 - 6) - ((5 \times 432) - 1)))) \\
 17274 & := ((9 + 876) + (5 + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
 17275 & := (9 + ((8 - 76) + (54 \times 321))) \\
 17276 & := ((98 - (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times -((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 17277 & := (((-9 + 876) \times (5 \times 4)) + (3 \times -21)) \\
 17278 & := ((-98 + (7 \times 6)) - (54 \times -321)) \\
 17279 & := ((9 - (8 \times ((7 - 6) + (5 \times 432)))) \times -1)
 \end{aligned}$$

17280 := (1 - (2 - (((3 + 4)⁵) + (6 × (7 + (8 × 9)))))) **17280** := ((9 - (8 - (7 - 6))) × -(5 × -((4 × 3)²⁺¹)))
17281 := ((1 - 2) × -(((3 + 4)⁵) + (6 × (7 + (8 × 9)))))) **17281** := ((9 - (8 × ((7 - 6) - (5 × 432)))) × 1)
17282 := (1 × -(2 - (((3 + 4)⁵) + ((6 × 78) + 9)))) **17282** := (9 + ((8 × -((7 - 6) - (5 × 432))) + 1))
17283 := (1 × (2 + (((3 + 4)⁵) + (6 × (7 + (8 × 9)))))) **17283** := ((-9 + 8) + ((7 - (6 + 5)) × -4321))
17284 := (1 + (2 + (((3 + 4)⁵) + (6 × (7 + (8 × 9)))))) **17284** := ((9 - 8) × ((7 - (6 + 5)) × -4321))
17285 := (-123 + ((4⁵) × -((6 - 7) × (8 + 9)))) **17285** := (9 - (8 + ((7 - (6 + 5)) × 4321)))
17286 := (((1 + 2) - ((3⁴) × 5)) × ((6 × -7) + (8 - 9))) **17286** := ((((-9 + 8) - 7) × 6) - (54 × -321))
17287 := (1 × -(2 - (3 × ((4 + (5 × 67)) × (8 + 9)))))) **17287** := ((9 - (8 × 7)) - (6 × -((5 + 4) × 321)))
17288 := ((1 + ((2³) × (45 × 6))) × (7 - (8 - 9))) **17288** := (9 - ((8 × -((7 - 6) × (5 × 432))) + 1))
17289 := ((1 + (2 × ((3⁴) - 5))) × (((6 + 7) × 8) + 9)) **17289** := ((9 + 8) × -(((765 × 4) / -3) + (2 + 1)))
17290 := (((12³) - (4 - 5)) × -(6 × (7 + 8))) / -9 **17290** := ((9 + ((8 - 7)⁶)) × -((54 × -32) - 1))
17291 := (1 × (2 + (3 × ((4 + (5 × 67)) × (8 + 9)))))) **17291** := (((-9 + 8) - (7 × 6)) - (54 × -321))
17292 := (((12³) + (4 + ((5⁶) + 7))) + (8 × -9)) **17292** := (9 - (((8 × 76) + (5 × 43)) × -21))
17293 := ((12 + ((3 + 4)⁵)) - (6 × -(7 + (8 × 9)))) **17293** := ((9 - (8 × 7)) + (6 + (54 × 321)))
17294 := (1 - (2 + (3 × ((4⁵) - 6789)))) **17294** := (((-98/7) × -65) + (4^{3×2+1}))
17295 := ((12 + 3) × ((4⁵) - (6 - ((7 + 8) × 9)))) **17295** := (-9 + ((8 × 7) × -(6 - (5 × ((4³) - (2 - 1))))))
17296 := ((12 + ((3 + 4)⁵)) - ((6 × -78) - 9)) **17296** := (9 - ((8 × -((7 - 6) + (5 × 432))) + 1))
17297 := (((12³) × ((4 + 5) - (6 - 7))) + (8 + 9)) **17297** := (98 - (7 × -(((6 × (5 × 4)) - 3) × 21)))
17298 := ((1 + 2) × (3 + ((4 + (5 × 67)) × (8 + 9)))) **17298** := (9 - ((8 × -((7 - 6) + (5 × 432))) - 1))
17299 := ((1 - ((2 - (3 × 4)) × ((5⁶) - (7 × 8)))) / 9) **17299** := ((((-9 + 8) - 7) × (6⁵)) + (43²⁺¹))
17300 := ((12³) - (4 × -(5 + ((6⁷) / (8 × 9)))))) **17300** := ((((-9 × 8) - 7) × (6 - (5 × (43 + 2)))) - 1)
17301 := ((1 + 2) × -(((3^{(-4+5)×6}) - 7) × -8) + 9)) **17301** := (9 - (((8 × ((7 + 6) × 5)) + 4) × -(32 + 1)))
17302 := (((1 - 2) - (3⁴)) × ((5 × -(6 × 7)) + (8 - 9))) **17302** := (-9 + (((8 + 76) - (5⁴)) × -32) - 1))
17303 := (1 × (((2 - 34) × -(5 + (67 × 8))) - 9)) **17303** := (((98 - 7) + (6 × 5)) × (((4 × 3)²) - 1))
17304 := (((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)⁵) - 6) - (7 × -(8 × 9))) **17304** := ((9 + (8 + 7)) × ((6 - (((5 + 4)³) - 2)) × -1))
17305 := ((1 - 2) × -(((3 + 4)⁵) - (6 - (7 × (8 × 9)))))) **17305** := (9 - (8 × -((7 - 6) + ((5 × 432) + 1))))
17306 := (1 × (((2 + 3) - ((4⁵) + (6 - 7))) × -(8 + 9))) **17306** := ((9 + 8) × (((765 × 4) / 3) - (2 × 1)))
17307 := (((1 + 2)³⁺⁴) - (5 × -(6 × (7 × (8 × 9)))))) **17307** := (9 + (((87 × (6 + 5)) + 4) × -(3 - 21)))
17308 := (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)⁵) - 6) - (7 × -(8 × 9))) **17308** := ((((-9 + 876) × -(5 × 4)) + 32) × -1)
17309 := (((-1 + (2 + 345)) × -(6 - (7 × 8))) + 9) **17309** := (9 - ((8 + (7 × (6 - (5⁴)))) × ((3 + 2) - 1)))
17310 := (1 × (2 × -3 - (((4⁵) - (6 + (7 × 8))) × 9))) **17310** := ((-9 × -((8 + 7) + ((6⁵) / 4))) - 321)
17311 := (1 + (2 × -3 - (((4⁵) - (6 + (7 × 8))) × 9))) **17311** := (-98 - ((765 + (4³)) × -21))
17312 := -1 - 2 + 3!! × 4! + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 **17312** := (9 - (((8 × 7) + 65) × -(((4 × 3)²) - 1)))
17313 := ((1 + 2) × -((34 × -(5 × ((6 × 7) - 8))) + 9)) **17313** := (9 - (8 × -(7 × ((6 × (5 + 43)) + 21))))
17314 := (-1 - (2 - (((3 + 4)⁵) + (6 + (7 × (8 × 9)))))) **17314** := (((-98/7) - 6) - (54 × -321))
17315 := (1 × -(2 - (((3 + 4)⁵) + (6 + (7 × (8 × 9)))))) **17315** := ((-9 × -(8 × (7 + 6))) - (5 - (4^{3×2+1})))
17316 := (1 - (2 - (((3 + 4)⁵) + (6 + (7 × (8 × 9)))))) **17316** := ((9 - 87) × ((6 × 5) - (4 × (3 × 21))))
17317 := ((1 - 2) × -(((3 + 4)⁵) + (6 + (7 × (8 × 9)))))) **17317** := (-9 + ((8 × -(7 - 6)) + (54 × 321)))
17318 := (-1 - (23 × -((45 + 6) + (78 × 9)))) **17318** := ((-9 - (8 - 7)) - (6 - (54 × 321)))
17319 := ((1 + 2) × ((3 × -4) + (5 × ((6 + 7) × 89)))) **17319** := ((9 - ((8 × (76 × (54 + 3))) / 2)) × -1)
17320 := (((1 + 2) + (((3 + 4)⁵) + 6)) - (7 × -(8 × 9))) **17320** := (9 + (((8 + 76) - (5⁴)) × -32) - 1))

$$\begin{aligned}
17321 &:= (1 \times (((2 - 34) \times -(5 + (67 \times 8))) + 9)) \\
17322 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) - (6 + (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\
17323 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) - (6 + (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\
17324 &:= ((1 + ((2 - (3 - 4))^5)) \times ((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
17325 &:= (((12^3) - (4 - ((5^6) - (7 + 8)))) - 9) \\
17326 &:= (1 + (((2^3) - 45) \times -(6 \times 78)) + 9) \\
17327 &:= (1 \times (((((2^3) \times (45 \times 6)) + 7) \times 8) - 9)) \\
17328 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(((3^4) - 5) \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
17329 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3^4) - 5) \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
17330 &:= (1 - ((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 - 9)))) \\
17331 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) + 45) \times -((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
17332 &:= (1 - (((2^3) + 45) \times -((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
17333 &:= (((12^3) + ((4 + (5^6) - 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\
17334 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 \times (((45 \times 6) - (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
17335 &:= (1 - (2 \times ((3 \times 4) - ((5 + 6) \times 789)))) \\
17336 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3 + 4)^5) + ((67 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
17337 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3 + 4)^5) + ((67 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
17338 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 + 4)^5) + ((67 - 8) \times 9))) \\
17339 &:= (((12^3) - (4 - ((5^6) + (7 - 8)))) - 9) \\
17340 &:= (((12^3) - 4) - (((5^6) \times (7 - 8)) + 9)) \\
17341 &:= (((12^3) - (4 - ((5^6) - 7))) + (8 - 9)) \\
17342 &:= (((12^3) - 4) - (((5^6) - 7) \times (8 - 9))) \\
17343 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3^4) - (5^{6-7+8})))) / - 9) \\
17344 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((3 + 4) - ((5 + 6) \times 789)))) \\
17345 &:= (1 \times -((((2^3) \times (45 \times 6)) + 7) \times -8) - 9) \\
17346 &:= (1 - (((((2^3) \times (45 \times 6)) + 7) \times -8) - 9)) \\
17347 &:= (1 \times -((2 + (3^4)) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 - 9)))) \\
17348 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3^4)) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 - 9)))) \\
17349 &:= (((12^3) + ((4 + (5^6)) - (7 - 8))) - 9) \\
17350 &:= (((12^3) + 4) - (((5^6) - 7) \times (8 - 9))) \\
17351 &:= (((12^3) + ((4 + (5^6)) - 7)) - (8 - 9)) \\
17352 &:= (((12^3) \times ((4 + 5) - (6 - 7))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
17353 &:= ((12^3) + ((4 - (5 - 6))^{7+8-9})) \\
17354 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 - (45 \times 6)) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
17355 &:= ((1 - (((2 - (3 \times 4)) \times (5^6)) + (7 \times 8))) / 9) \\
17356 &:= ((1 - 2) - ((3 - (4^5)) \times -((6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
17357 &:= ((1 - 2) \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times -((6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
17358 &:= (((12^3) - 4) - (((5^6) \times (7 - 8)) - 9)) \\
17359 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
17360 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times ((6 + 7) \times 8))) - 9) \\
17361 &:= ((1 + ((2 - (3 \times 4)) \times (5^6))) / ((7 - 8) \times 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
17321 &:= ((9 - (87 \times (6 - (5 \times (43 - 2)))))) - 1) \\
17322 &:= ((9 - (87 \times (6 - (5 \times (43 - 2)))))) \times 1) \\
17323 &:= (9 + ((87 \times -(6 - (5 \times (43 - 2)))) + 1)) \\
17324 &:= (98 - (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
17325 &:= (((98 + 7) - 6) \times -(5 \times -((4 + 32) - 1))) \\
17326 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) \times (6 - (5^4))) + 3)) / (2 \times -1)) \\
17327 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 - (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 321)))) \\
17328 &:= (9 + (((8 \times ((7 \times (6 - (5^4))) + 3)) / - 2) - 1)) \\
17329 &:= (((9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (6 - (5^4)))) - 3) / (2 \times -1)) \\
17330 &:= (9 + (((8 \times ((7 \times (6 - (5^4))) + 3)) / - 2) + 1)) \\
17331 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times ((5 \times -4) - (32 + 1))) \\
17332 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 \times -((6 - (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
17333 &:= (9 - (8 + (7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))))) \\
17334 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -6) \times ((5 + 4) \times -321)) \\
17335 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) \times (6 - (5^4))) + 3)) / - (2 \times -1)) \\
17336 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
17337 &:= (9 + ((8 - 7) \times -(6 - (54 \times 321)))) \\
17338 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) \times (6 - (5^4))) - 3)) / - (2 \times -1)) \\
17339 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -(765 \times 4)) - 3) / (2 + 1)) \\
17340 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((765 \times 4) / (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
17341 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) \times (6 - (5^4))) / - (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
17342 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 + (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 321)))) \\
17343 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
17344 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 - (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 321)))) \\
17345 &:= ((9 - 87) + (((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3))^2) - 1) \\
17346 &:= (9 + ((87 - (((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3))^2)) \times -1)) \\
17347 &:= (9 - (87 - (((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1)) \\
17348 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times (((6 \times -5) + (4^3))^2)) - 1)) \\
17349 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 \times -((6 - (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
17350 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times -((5 + (4 \times 3))^2)) - 1)) \\
17351 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 - 6)) - (54 \times 321))) \\
17352 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
17353 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5)) \times (4 + (3 \times 21))) \\
17354 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 6) + (5 \times 4)) \times -32) - 1) \\
17355 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (765 - 43))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
17356 &:= (98 - (76 - (54 \times 321))) \\
17357 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((765 \times 4) + 3) / - (2 + 1))) \\
17358 &:= (((9 + (87 \times 6)) - 5) \times -((4 \times -3) - 21)) \\
17359 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) - (54 \times -321)) \\
17360 &:= ((98 - (7 \times 6)) \times -(5 \times -((4^3) - (2 \times 1)))) \\
17361 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((((7 \times (6 - (5^4))) - 3) / 2) - 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 17362 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -((4 + (5^{6-7+8}))/ - 9)) \\
 17363 &:= (1 \times - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
 17364 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
 17365 &:= (((12^3) + (4 + ((5^6) + (7 - 8)))) + 9) \\
 17366 &:= (((12^3) + 4) - (((5^6) \times (7 - 8)) - 9)) \\
 17367 &:= (((12^3) + ((4 + (5^6)) - (7 - 8))) + 9) \\
 17368 &:= (1 \times (2 \times (3 + ((4 + (5^{6-7+8}))/ 9)))) \\
 17369 &:= (1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4 + (5^{6-7+8}))/ 9)))) \\
 17370 &:= (((12^3) + (4 + 5)) \times - (6 \times (7 + 8)) / - 9) \\
 17371 &:= (1 + ((2 - ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + 78))) \times - 9)) \\
 17372 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times - ((6 \times - 7) + (8 - 9))) \\
 17373 &:= (((12^3) - (4 - ((5^6) + (7 + 8)))) + 9) \\
 17374 &:= (((1 - (2 - 3)) - (4^5)) \times ((6 - 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 17375 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times - (5 \times - (67 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 17376 &:= (1 \times - (2 \times - (3 + (((4^5) - (67 - 8)) \times 9)))) \\
 17377 &:= (1 \times - (((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times - ((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 17378 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times - ((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 17379 &:= ((1 - (2 \times ((3^4) + (5^{6-7+8})))) / - 9) \\
 17380 &:= ((1 - 23) \times - ((4 \times - 5) + (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
 17381 &:= (((12^3) + (4 + ((5^6) + (7 + 8)))) + 9) \\
 17382 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + (6 \times (7 + 89)))) \\
 17383 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) - (6 + 7)) \times 8) - 9) \\
 17384 &:= (1 - ((2^3) - (((4^5) + (6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 17385 &:= (1 + ((2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times - (7 - 89))) \\
 17386 &:= ((1 - 23) + ((4^5) \times - ((6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 17387 &:= (1 - (2 + ((3 - 45) \times (6 \times (78 - 9)))) \\
 17388 &:= ((1 - ((2 + (3^4)) \times 5)) \times - (6 \times - (7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\
 17389 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times ((6 + 78) \times 9))) \\
 17390 &:= (1 \times - (2 \times (((3 - ((4^5) + 67)) \times 8) + 9))) \\
 17391 &:= (1 - (2 \times (((3 - ((4^5) + 67)) \times 8) + 9))) \\
 17392 &:= (1 \times - ((2 - 3) - (((4^5) + (6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 17393 &:= (1 - ((2 - 3) - (((4^5) + (6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 17394 &:= (1 \times - (((2 \times 3) + (4 \times 5)) \times - (678 - 9))) \\
 17395 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times 3)^4)) - (5 \times - (6 \times (7 \times 89)))) \\
 17396 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) + (((4^5) + (6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 17397 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 + (((4^5) + (6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 17398 &:= ((1 + (23 \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 78)))) + 9) \\
 17399 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times - ((3 - ((4^5) + 67)) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 17400 &:= (1 + ((2 \times - ((3 - ((4^5) + 67)) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 17401 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) - (6 + 7)) \times 8) + 9) \\
 17402 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times - 3) - ((4^5) \times ((6 - 7) \times (8 + 9))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 17362 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (43 \times 2))) - 1) \\
 17363 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (43 \times 2))) \times - 1) \\
 17364 &:= (9 - ((8 \times - (7 - (6^5))) - (43^{2+1}))) \\
 17365 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (6^5))) / 4 - 3) + (2 \times - 1)) \\
 17366 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - ((6^5) / 4))) + 3) - (2 \times - 1)) \\
 17367 &:= (987 - (65 \times - (4 \times (3 \times 21)))) \\
 17368 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times - 65) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
 17369 &:= (9 - ((8 \times 7) \times - ((6 + (5^4)) - 321))) \\
 17370 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) - ((6^5) / 4)) \times - (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 17371 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) - ((6^5) / 4)) \times - (3^2) + 1)) \\
 17372 &:= (987 + ((6 - 5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
 17373 &:= (9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times - ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\
 17374 &:= ((9 + 8) \times - (((765 \times 4) / - 3) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 17375 &:= ((9 - ((876 - 5) \times 4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times - 1)) \\
 17376 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3))^2 - 1)) \\
 17377 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3))^2 \times - 1)) \\
 17378 &:= (9 + ((8 \times - 7) + (((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3))^2 + 1))) \\
 17379 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) - (6^5)) / 4) \times - (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\
 17380 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times - (43 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
 17381 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (43 \times 2))) \times 1) \\
 17382 &:= (((9 + 8) + ((7 - ((6^5) / 4)) \times 3)) \times - (2 + 1)) \\
 17383 &:= (((((-98 \times 7) - 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times - 2) - 1) \\
 17384 &:= ((((-98 \times - 7) + 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times - (2 \times - 1)) \\
 17385 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times ((54 \times - 3) - 21)) \\
 17386 &:= (((-9 \times - ((8 + 7) - ((6^5) / 4) + 3))) + 2) \times - 1) \\
 17387 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + 6)) - (54 \times - 321)) \\
 17388 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (6 \times - (((5 \times 4) + 3) \times 21))) \\
 17389 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (((6^5) / 4) + 3))) + 2) - 1) \\
 17390 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times ((6 + 5) + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 17391 &:= ((9 + (8 + 76)) \times - (5 - ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 17392 &:= (9 - ((8 \times - ((7 + 6) + (5 \times 432))) + 1)) \\
 17393 &:= (9 - ((8 \times - 7) + (6 - (54 \times 321)))) \\
 17394 &:= ((9 - 87) \times (((6 + 5) - 4) \times - 32) + 1) \\
 17395 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times (6 + ((5 \times 43) + 2))) + 1) \\
 17396 &:= ((-9 \times - ((8 + 7) + ((6 \times 5) \times (4^3))) - 2) - 1) \\
 17397 &:= (9 - ((876 - (5 + 43)) \times - 21)) \\
 17398 &:= (((987 + (6^5)) - (4^3)) \times - (2 \times - 1)) \\
 17399 &:= (9 - ((8 \times - 7) - (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 321)))) \\
 17400 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times - (6 \times - (((5 + (4 \times 3))^2 + 1))) \\
 17401 &:= (987 - ((6 \times - 5) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
 17402 &:= ((9 - (8 - 76)) \times - ((5 \times - (43 + 2)) - 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
17403 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -3) - ((4^5) \times ((6-7) \times (8+9)))))) & 17403 &:= (9 - (((87-6) \times -(5 \times 43)) + 21)) \\
17404 &:= ((1-2) - (3 + ((4^5) \times ((6-7) \times (8+9)))))) & 17404 &:= ((9 - (((87-6) \times (5 \times 43)) - 2)) \times -1) \\
17405 &:= ((1-2) \times (3 + ((4^5) \times ((6-7) \times (8+9)))))) & 17405 &:= (((98-7) - (((6^5)/4) \times (3^2))) \times -1) \\
17406 &:= (12 + (3 + (((4^5) + (6-7)) \times (8+9)))) & 17406 &:= (((((9+8) - 7) - ((6^5)/4)) \times (3 \times -(2+1)))) \\
17407 &:= (1 - ((2 + ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times (6+78))) \times -9)) & 17407 &:= (((9+8) - ((7 + ((6 - (5 - 4))^3))^2)) \times -1) \\
17408 &:= (((((1+2)^{3+4}) - (5+6)) \times (7 - (8-9)))) & 17408 &:= (9 - (8 + ((7+6) \times (5 - ((4^3) \times 21)))))) \\
17409 &:= (1 \times -((2-3) + ((4^5) \times ((6-7) \times (8+9)))))) & 17409 &:= (9 - (87 \times -((6 + (5 \times 43)) - 21))) \\
17410 &:= (1 - ((2-3) + ((4^5) \times ((6-7) \times (8+9)))))) & 17410 &:= (9 + (((8765 - 4^3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
17411 &:= (1 + (2 + (34 \times (((5 \times 6) / (7+8))^9)))) & 17411 &:= (9 + ((8765 - 4^3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
17412 &:= (12 \times -(34 - ((5+6) \times ((7+8) \times 9)))) & 17412 &:= (9 - (((8765 - 4^3) \times -2) - 1)) \\
17413 &:= (1 \times ((2+3) - ((4^5) \times ((6-7) \times (8+9)))))) & 17413 &:= ((9 - ((8+76) \times ((5^4) - 3))) / -(2+1)) \\
17414 &:= (((1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - 8) - 9) & 17414 &:= (((((9+8) - 7) - (((6+5) \times (4 \times 3))^2)) \times -1) \\
17415 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -3) + ((4^5) \times ((6-7) \times (8+9)))))) & 17415 &:= ((-9 \times -((8+7) - 6)) - (54 \times -321)) \\
17416 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) - ((4^5) \times ((6-7) \times (8+9)))))) & 17416 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 - (((6+5) \times (4 \times 3))^2) - 1))) \\
17417 &:= (1 + ((2^3) - ((4^5) \times ((6-7) \times (8+9)))))) & 17417 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 - (((6+5) \times (4 \times 3))^2)) \times -1)) \\
17418 &:= (((1+2)^3) - (((4^5) + (6-7)) \times -(8+9))) & 17418 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 - (((6+5) \times (4 \times 3))^2)) \times -1)) \\
17419 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -3) + (((4^5) - (6-7)) \times (8+9)))) & 17419 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - (((6+5) \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1)) \\
17420 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -3) + (((4^5) - (6-7)) \times (8+9)))) & 17420 &:= (9 - ((8 - 765) \times -(4 - (3^{2+1})))) \\
17421 &:= (1 - ((2+3) \times -(4 - (5 \times (6 - (78 \times 9))))) & 17421 &:= (9 - (((87-6) \times -(5 \times 43)) + (2+1))) \\
17422 &:= (((12^3) + ((4 + (5^6)) - 7)) - (8 \times -9)) & 17422 &:= ((9 + ((87-6) \times (5 \times 43))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
17423 &:= ((1 - ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -(7 \times -(8-9))) & 17423 &:= (((((9-8)^7) - (((6+5) \times (4 \times 3))^2)) \times -1) \\
17424 &:= ((1 + ((2^3) \times (((4+5) - 6)^7) - 8)) - 9) & 17424 &:= (((9-8)^7) \times -(((6+5) \times (4 \times 3))^2) \times -1) \\
17425 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^4))) - (((5^6) + 7) / 8) \times -9) & 17425 &:= (((9-8)^7) - (((6+5) \times (4 \times 3))^2) \times -1) \\
17426 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + (5^6))) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 17426 &:= (((9-8)^7) + (((6+5) \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1) \\
17427 &:= ((1-2) + (3 + (((4^5) - (6-7)) \times (8+9)))) & 17427 &:= (9 - (((87-6) \times -(5 \times 43)) - (2+1))) \\
17428 &:= ((1-2) \times -((3 + (((4^5) - (6-7)) \times (8+9)))) & 17428 &:= (9 - (((876-5) \times -(4 \times (3+2))) + 1)) \\
17429 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (3^4)) \times -(5 \times (6 \times 7))) - (8-9))) & 17429 &:= ((9 + ((876-5) \times (4 \times (3+2)))) \times 1) \\
17430 &:= ((1 + (((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + 8)) - 9) & 17430 &:= ((9-8) \times ((7 + (((6+5) \times (4 \times 3))^2)) - 1)) \\
17431 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) \times -(8-9)) & 17431 &:= ((9-8) \times -((7 + (((6+5) \times (4 \times 3))^2)) \times -1)) \\
17432 &:= (((1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - 8) + 9) & 17432 &:= ((9-8) \times -(((7 - ((6^5)/4)) \times (3^2)) + 1)) \\
17433 &:= ((1+2) + ((3+4) \times -(5 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 17433 &:= ((9-8) - (((7 - ((6^5)/4)) \times (3^2)) + 1)) \\
17434 &:= (12 - (3 - (((4^5) - (6-7)) \times (8+9)))) & 17434 &:= ((9-8) \times (((7 - ((6^5)/4)) \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\
17435 &:= (((1+2)^3) + ((4^5) \times -((6-7) \times (8+9)))) & 17435 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((7 - ((6^5)/4)) \times (3^2))) - 1)) \\
17436 &:= (((12^3) + (4 + ((5^6) + 7))) - (8 \times -9)) & 17436 &:= (((9-8) - ((7 - ((6^5)/4)) \times 3)) \times (2+1)) \\
17437 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 \times -(8-9))) & 17437 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times ((5 \times -((4^3) + 2)) + 1)) \\
17438 &:= ((1 - (2-3)) \times (((4^5) + 67) \times 8) - 9) & 17438 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(6 + (5 \times 43))) - 21) \\
17439 &:= (((1+2) + (((3+4)^5) + 6)) - (7 \times -89)) & 17439 &:= (98 + (7 + (6 \times ((5+4) \times 321)))) \\
17440 &:= (12 + (3 + (((4^5) - (6-7)) \times (8+9)))) & 17440 &:= (9 + ((8 + ((7 + ((6 - (5 - 4))^3))^2)) - 1)) \\
17441 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times (5 + (6 + (7 + 89)))) & 17441 &:= ((9+8) - (((7 + ((6 - (5 - 4))^3))^2) \times -1)) \\
17442 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3^4) - 5))) \times -((6 \times -7) - (8 \times 9))) & 17442 &:= (9 + (8 + (((7 + ((6 - (5 - 4))^3))^2) + 1)) \\
17443 &:= (1 \times ((2-3) + (4 \times ((56-7) \times 89)))) & 17443 &:= (((-9 \times -(8+7)) - (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + 2)) \times -1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}17444 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -(((4 \times 5) - 6) \times -(7 \times 89))) \\17445 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3^4) \times -(5 + 67)) + (8 + 9))) \\17446 &:= (1 - ((2 - 3) - (4 \times ((56 - 7) \times 89)))) \\17447 &:= (1 \times -((234 + 5) \times ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9)))) \\17448 &:= ((1 + (((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + 8)) + 9) \\17449 &:= ((1 + 23) - (((4^5) - (6 - 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) \\17450 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 + (4 \times ((56 - 7) \times 89)))) \\17451 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 + 4) \times -((56 \times (7 + 8)) - 9))) \\17452 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (((4^5) - (6 - 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) \\17453 &:= (((1 + 2) - 34) \times -(5 + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\17454 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((3 \times ((4 - 56) \times (7 \times 8))) + 9))) \\17455 &:= (1 + (2 \times -((3 \times ((4 - 56) \times (7 \times 8))) + 9))) \\17456 &:= (1 \times -(((2^{3 \times 4}) \times -5) + (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\17457 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) + (6 \times -(7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\17458 &:= (((1 - 2) - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times ((6 \times -7) + (8 - 9))) \\17459 &:= (((1 + 2) + (((3^{4+5}) - (6 \times 7)) \times 8))/9) \\17460 &:= ((12 + (((3^{4+5}) - (6 \times 7)) \times 8))/9) \\17461 &:= (1 \times -2 + (((3 - (((4 + 5) - 6)^7)) \times 8) + 9))) \\17462 &:= (1 - 2 + (((3 - (((4 + 5) - 6)^7)) \times 8) + 9))) \\17463 &:= (1 + (((2 - 3) + (4 \times (56 \times 78))) - 9)) \\17464 &:= ((1 + (2 + 34)) \times -(5 - ((6 \times 78) + 9))) \\17465 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) - (((4 + 5) - 6)^7)) \times -8) + 9) \\17466 &:= (1 + (((2 + 3) - (((4 + 5) - 6)^7)) \times -8) + 9) \\17467 &:= ((12 + ((3 + 4)^5)) + ((6 - 78) \times -9)) \\17468 &:= (((12^3) - (4 - (5^6))) - (7 \times -(8 + 9))) \\17469 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 \times -4 - (((5^6) + 7)/8) - 9))) \\17470 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -3) - ((4 \times (56 \times 78)) - 9))) \\17471 &:= ((1 - ((23 - 4) \times ((5^6) + 7)))/- (8 + 9)) \\17472 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times 5)) \times (6 \times -(7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\17473 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) - ((4 \times (56 \times 78)) + 9))) \\17474 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -(((4^5) + 67) \times -8) - 9) \\17475 &:= (12 + (((3 - (((4 + 5) - 6)^7)) \times -8) - 9)) \\17476 &:= (((12^3) + (4 + (5^6))) - (7 \times -(8 + 9))) \\17477 &:= ((-12/3) - ((4 \times -(56 \times 78)) - 9)) \\17478 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -4) - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times -9) \\17479 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 + (4^5)) - (6 - 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) \\17480 &:= (1 - (((2^3) \times -((4 + 5) - 6)^7)) + (8 + 9))) \\17481 &:= ((1 + 2) + (((3 \times 4) - (((5^6) + 7)/8)) \times -9)) \\17482 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 + 4)^5) + ((67 + 8) \times 9))) \\17483 &:= (1 \times (2 - (((3 - (((4 + 5) - 6)^7)) \times 8) - 9))) \\17484 &:= (1 + (2 - (((3 - (((4 + 5) - 6)^7)) \times 8) - 9)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}17444 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) - (6 - 5)) \times -(4 - 321))) \\17445 &:= (((9 + 8) - (((7 + 65)/4)^3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\17446 &:= (((-98 + (((7 + (6 + 5))^4)/3))/2) - 1) \\17447 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 + (((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3))^2)) - 1)) \\17448 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5)/4) \times -(3^2)) + 1) \\17449 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 - ((6^5)/4)) \times (3^2)) + 1)) \\17450 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5)/4) \times -(3^2)) - 1) \\17451 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((7 - ((6^5)/4)) \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\17452 &:= (9 - (((8765 - 43) \times -2) + 1)) \\17453 &:= ((9 + ((8765 - 43) \times 2)) \times 1) \\17454 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 - (54 \times 3)))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\17455 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) - ((6^5)/4))) + (32 \times -1)) \\17456 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) - ((6^5)/4))) - (32 - 1)) \\17457 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times -((4 \times -3) - 21)) \\17458 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 \times -6 - ((5^4) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\17459 &:= (9 - (8 + (7 \times (6 - ((5^4) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))))) \\17460 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) - (((6^5)/4) \times 3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\17461 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -6 + (5 \times 43)) - (2 \times -1)) \\17462 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) - (5^4)) \times -(32 - 1)) \\17463 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 32)))) \times -1) \\17464 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times (5^4))) \times -((3 + 2) - 1)) \\17465 &:= ((9 + ((876 - 5) \times 4)) \times -((3 + 2) \times -1)) \\17466 &:= (((9 + 8) - (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))/3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\17467 &:= (-9 + ((8 - 76) \times -(5 + (4 \times (3 \times 21)))) \\17468 &:= ((9 - ((876 \times 5) - 4)) \times -((3 + 2) - 1)) \\17469 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 - 654) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\17470 &:= (9 + (((8 + (76 \times 5)) \times (43 + 2)) + 1)) \\17471 &:= ((-98 - ((76 - (5^4)) \times 32)) + 1) \\17472 &:= ((98 - (7 \times 6)) \times (((5^4) - 3)/2) + 1) \\17473 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times (4 - (3 \times 21)))) \\17474 &:= ((98 + (7 \times 6)) - (54 \times -321)) \\17475 &:= (9 + (8 - (7 \times (6 - ((5^4) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))))) \\17476 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 - (6 \times ((5 + 4)^3))))/2) - 1)) \\17477 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times ((5 + 4)^3))))/2)) \times 1) \\17478 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 - (6 \times ((5 + 4)^3))))/2) + 1)) \\17479 &:= ((-9 + (876 \times (5 \times 4))) + (32 \times -1)) \\17480 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times (6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 32)))) + 1)) \\17481 &:= (9 + ((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5)) \times ((4^3) \times 21))) \\17482 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times (6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 32)))) - 1)) \\17483 &:= (((-9 + (876 \times 5)) \times 4) - 3) - (2 \times -1) \\17484 &:= ((9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times (((5 + 4)^3) \times -2) + 1))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
17485 &:= (1 \times (((2-3) + (45 \times 6)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 17485 &:= (9 + ((8-76) \times -(5 + (4 \times (3 \times 21)))))) \\
17486 &:= (1 + (((2-3) + (45 \times 6)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 17486 &:= (9 + (8 - ((7-654) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
17487 &:= ((1+2) - (3 - (((4+5) - 6)^7) \times 8) - 9)) & 17487 &:= (((9-8)^7) - ((6^5)/4) \times (3 \times -(2+1))) \\
17488 &:= (((1+2)^{3+4}) + (5-6)) \times (7 - (8-9)) & 17488 &:= ((9-8) \times -(7 - (((6^5)/4) \times (3^2)) - 1)) \\
17489 &:= (1 - ((2^3) \times -(((4+5) - 6)^7) + (8-9))) & 17489 &:= ((9-8) \times ((7 - (((6^5)/4) \times (3^2))) \times -1)) \\
17490 &:= (1 - (((2 - (3^{4 \times 5 - 6 - 7})) \times 8) - 9)) & 17490 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times (5 \times -(4^3) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
17491 &:= (1 - ((23-45) \times (6+789))) & 17491 &:= ((9-8) - (7 - (((6^5)/4) \times (3^2)) + 1)) \\
17492 &:= (1 \times (((2+3) + (((4+5) - 6)^7) \times 8) - 9)) & 17492 &:= ((9+8) + ((7 - (((6^5)/4) \times 3)) \times -(2+1))) \\
17493 &:= ((1+2) + ((3 + (((4+5) - 6)^7) \times 8) - 9)) & 17493 &:= ((9-8) \times -(7 \times -(((6 \times 5^4))/3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
17494 &:= (1 - ((2 + ((34 \times (5 \times 6)) + 7)) \times -(8+9)) & 17494 &:= (9 + (((8 - (((7 \times 6) \times 5^4))/3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
17495 &:= ((1 - ((2^3) \times (((4+5) - 6)^7))) \times (8-9)) & 17495 &:= (9 + (((8-7) - ((6^5)/4) \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
17496 &:= ((1 + ((2^3) \times (((4+5) - 6)^7))) + (8-9)) & 17496 &:= ((9-8) - (((7 + (6+5))^4) / - (3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
17497 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) \times -(((4+5) - 6)^7)) + (8-9))) & 17497 &:= ((9-8) \times -((((7 + (6+5))^4) / - (3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
17498 &:= (1 - (((2^3) \times -(((4+5) - 6)^7)) + (8-9))) & 17498 &:= ((9-8) - (((7 + (6+5))^4) / - (3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
17499 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -3) + (((4+5) - 6)^7) \times 8) + 9)) & 17499 &:= ((9-8) \times -((((7 \times 6) \times 5^4)/3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
17500 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -3) + (((4+5) - 6)^7) \times 8) + 9)) & 17500 &:= ((9-8) - (((7 \times 6) \times 5^4)/3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
17501 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3^4) \times 5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8-9))) & 17501 &:= ((9-8) \times -((((7 \times 6) \times 5^4)/3) \times -2) - 1)) \\
17502 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3^4) \times 5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8-9))) & 17502 &:= ((9-8) \times ((7 + (((6^5)/4) \times (3^2))) - 1)) \\
17503 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - (8 \times -9)) & 17503 &:= ((9-8) \times -(7 + (((6^5)/4) \times (3^2))) \times -1)) \\
17504 &:= (((1-2) - (3^4)) - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times -9)) & 17504 &:= ((9-8) - ((7 + (((6^5)/4) \times (3^2))) \times -1)) \\
17505 &:= (1 - ((2^3) \times -(((4+5) - 6)^7) - (8-9))) & 17505 &:= ((9-8) + (7 + (((6^5)/4) \times (3^2)) + 1)) \\
17506 &:= (1 \times -((2-3) - (((4+5) - 6)^7) \times 8) + 9)) & 17506 &:= ((9+8) + ((7 - (((6^5)/4) \times (3^2))) \times -1)) \\
17507 &:= (1 - ((2-3) - (((4+5) - 6)^7) \times 8) + 9)) & 17507 &:= ((9-8) \times -(7 \times -(((6 \times 5^4))/3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
17508 &:= (((1+2) - (3^4)) - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times -9)) & 17508 &:= ((9-8) - (7 \times -(((6 \times 5^4))/3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
17509 &:= (1 \times -((2-3) - (4 \times ((56 \times 78) + 9)))) & 17509 &:= (9 - (((8+76) \times 5^4) / - (3 \times (2-1)))) \\
17510 &:= ((1 - (23 \times (4+5))) \times -((6+7) + (8 \times 9))) & 17510 &:= ((9+8) - (7 \times -((((6 \times 5^4))/3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
17511 &:= ((1+23) - (((4+5) - 6)^7) \times -8) + 9)) & 17511 &:= ((9 + (((8+76) \times 5^4)/3) - (2 \times -1)) \\
17512 &:= (1 \times (2 + (34 \times ((5+6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 17512 &:= ((9+8) - (((7 + (6+5))^4) / - (3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
17513 &:= (1 + (2 + (34 \times ((5+6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 17513 &:= ((9+8) - (((7 + 65)/4)^3) \times -(2+1)) \\
17514 &:= (((1+2)^3) - (((4+5) - 6)^7) \times -8) + 9)) & 17514 &:= ((9+8) - (((7 + (6+5))^4) / - (3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
17515 &:= (((1+2) - 34) \times -(5 \times -(6 - (7 \times (8+9)))))) & 17515 &:= (98 + ((7 - (((6+5) \times (4 \times 3))^2)) \times -1)) \\
17516 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) + (4 \times ((56 \times 78) + 9)))) & 17516 &:= ((9+8) - (((7 \times 6) \times 5^4)/3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
17517 &:= (12 + (((3^{4 \times 5 - 6 - 7})) \times 8) + 9)) & 17517 &:= (9 - ((8 + (((7 \times 6) \times 5^4)/3) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
17518 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -34) + (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9)) & 17518 &:= (9 + (8 + (((7 \times 6) \times 5^4)/3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
17519 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -34) + (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9)) & 17519 &:= ((9+8) + ((7 + (((6^5)/4) \times (3^2))) - 1)) \\
17520 &:= (((1-2) + ((3+4)^5)) - (6 \times -(7 \times (8+9)))) & 17520 &:= ((9+8) - ((7 + (((6^5)/4) \times (3^2))) \times -1)) \\
17521 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (3^{4 \times 5 - 6 - 7})) \times -8) - 9)) & 17521 &:= ((9+8) + (7 + (((6^5)/4) \times (3^2)) + 1)) \\
17522 &:= (1 - (((2 + (3^{4 \times 5 - 6 - 7})) \times -8) - 9)) & 17522 &:= (98 - (((7 + ((6 - (5 - 4))^3))^2) \times -1)) \\
17523 &:= (12 - (((3 + (((4+5) - 6)^7)) \times -8) + 9)) & 17523 &:= ((98 + ((7 + ((6 - (5 - 4))^3))^2) + 1) \\
17524 &:= (((1+2) + ((3+4)^5)) - (6 \times -(7 \times (8+9)))) & 17524 &:= ((9+8) - (7 \times -(((6 \times 5^4))/3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
17525 &:= (1 \times (2 - (((3+4) - ((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9)) & 17525 &:= ((9 + (876 \times (5 \times 4))) - ((3+2) - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 17526 &:= (1 + (2 - ((3 + 4) - ((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9)) \\
 17527 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times 3) - ((4^5) + (6 + 7))) \times -(8 + 9)) \\
 17528 &:= ((1 - 2) - (((3 + ((4 + 5) - 6)^7) \times -8) - 9)) \\
 17529 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (((3 + ((4 + 5) - 6)^7) \times -8) - 9)) \\
 17530 &:= (1 \times -(2 + (((34 - ((5^6) - 7))/8) \times 9)) \\
 17531 &:= (1 - (2 + (((34 - ((5^6) - 7))/8) \times 9)) \\
 17532 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) \times -8) - 9) \\
 17533 &:= (((1 + 2) - ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) / -9) \\
 17534 &:= (1 \times (2 - (((34 - ((5^6) - 7))/8) \times 9)) \\
 17535 &:= ((1 - (2 + ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times 7))) \times 8) / -9) \\
 17536 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3) + (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) \times -8) + 9)) \\
 17537 &:= (1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times -((5 \times (6 + 7)) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 17538 &:= (1 \times (((2^3) - 45) \times -((6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 17539 &:= (1 + (((2^3) - 45) \times -((6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 17540 &:= (((12^3) - (4 - (5 \times 6))) \times -(7 - (8 + 9))) \\
 17541 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 \times -((4 + ((5^6) + 7)/8) - 9))) \\
 17542 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times ((4^5) + (67 \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
 17543 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times ((4^5) + (67 \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
 17544 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 - 9))) \\
 17545 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) + (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) \times 8) + 9)) \\
 17546 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 3) + (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) \times 8)) + 9) \\
 17547 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (3 + (45 \times (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9))))) \\
 17548 &:= (123 - (((4^5) - (6 - 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
 17549 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times ((5 \times -6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 17550 &:= (((1 + 2) - (3^4)) \times (5 \times -(((6 + 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 17551 &:= (1 \times (((2^3) \times (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) + 8) - 9)) \\
 17552 &:= ((1 + ((2^3) \times (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) + 8)) - 9) \\
 17553 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 3) + (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) \times -8) - 9)) \\
 17554 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) \times 4) - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9)) \\
 17555 &:= (1 - (((2^3) \times 4) - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9)) \\
 17556 &:= (12 \times -((3 + 4) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 - 9)))) \\
 17557 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((34 - 5) \times 67) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 17558 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) - (45 \times (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9))))) \\
 17559 &:= (1 + ((2^3) - (45 \times (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9))))) \\
 17560 &:= ((1 - 23) - (4 - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9)) \\
 17561 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 + 4)^5) + ((6 + 78) \times 9))) \\
 17562 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(3 \times 4) + (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9)) \\
 17563 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -(3 \times 4) + (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9)) \\
 17564 &:= (12 - (34 - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9)) \\
 17565 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3 + 4)^5) + ((6 + 78) \times 9))) \\
 17566 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) \times -4 + (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 17526 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) - (2 + 1))) \\
 17527 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) - 2) \times -1) \\
 17528 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) - (2 - 1))) \\
 17529 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
 17530 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + (2 - 1))) \\
 17531 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + 2) \times -1) \\
 17532 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + (2 + 1))) \\
 17533 &:= (9 - ((876 \times -5) \times 4) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 17534 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 + ((6^5)/4) \times 3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 17535 &:= ((98 + 7) \times ((6 + (54 \times 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
 17536 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times (5^4))) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 17537 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + 6) \times -((5 + ((4^3) \times 21)))) \\
 17538 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 + 6) \times -((5 + ((4^3) \times 21)))) \\
 17539 &:= ((9 + (876 \times (5 \times 4))) + ((3^2) + 1)) \\
 17540 &:= ((987 + ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
 17541 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) + (6^5))/4)) \times (3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
 17542 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 \times -(6 + ((5^4) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
 17543 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times ((5 \times -((4^3) + 2)) - 1)) \\
 17544 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times (6 + (5 \times (((4 \times 3)^2) + 1)))) \\
 17545 &:= (((98 - 7) + (6 \times 5)) \times (((4 \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\
 17546 &:= (((9 + 8765) - (4 - 3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 17547 &:= ((9 + ((876 \times (5 \times 4))/3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 17548 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 - (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) - 21))) \\
 17549 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) - 21))) \\
 17550 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -7) + (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + 21))) \\
 17551 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((76 - (5^4)) \times -(32 \times 1))) \\
 17552 &:= (9 - (((8765 + (4 + 3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
 17553 &:= (9 - ((876 \times -5) \times 4) - (3 + 21)) \\
 17554 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 + 6) \times -((5 + ((4^3) \times 21)))) \\
 17555 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) - 21)) \\
 17556 &:= ((98 + (7 \times -(6 - ((5^4) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
 17557 &:= ((98 - (7 - 6)) \times -((543 / - (2 + 1)))) \\
 17558 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + ((6^5)/4)) \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
 17559 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 + ((6^5)/4)) \times (3^2)) - 1)) \\
 17560 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + ((6^5)/4)) \times -((3^2) - 1))) \\
 17561 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 + ((6^5)/4)) \times -((3^2) - 1))) \\
 17562 &:= (((9 - 8) + ((7 + ((6^5)/4)) \times 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 17563 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 + ((6 + (5 \times 4))^3)) - 21)) \\
 17564 &:= (9 - (((8765 + (4 \times 3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
 17565 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 - (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) - 21))) \\
 17566 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 - (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) - (2 + 1))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
17567 &:= (1 + (((2 + 3) \times -4) + (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17567 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) - (2 + 1)))) \\
17568 &:= ((1 - 23) + (4 + (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17568 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) - (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) - 2) \times -1)) \\
17569 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) \times -(((4 + 5) - 6)^7) + 8)) - 9)) & 17569 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) + (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) - (2 - 1))) \\
17570 &:= (1 \times -((((2 + (3 + 4)) \times (5^6)) + 7) / -8) + 9)) & 17570 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 - (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + (2 - 1)))) \\
17571 &:= (1 - (((((2 + (3 + 4)) \times (5^6)) + 7) / -8) + 9)) & 17571 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 - (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + 2)) \times -1)) \\
17572 &:= (1 \times -(23 \times -(4 \times (56 + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) & 17572 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 - (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + 2)) \times -1)) \\
17573 &:= ((1 - 2) + ((3 \times -4) + (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17573 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) - 2) \times -1) \\
17574 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(3 \times -4) + (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9)) & 17574 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -(((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) - 2) \times -1) \\
17575 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 - 4) + (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17575 &:= (9 + ((8 + ((7 + ((6^5)/4)) \times (3^2))) - 1)) \\
17576 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 - 4) + (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17576 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((7 + ((6^5)/4)) \times (3^2))) \times -1)) \\
17577 &:= (1 + (((2 \times 3) + (4 \times 5))^{6 \times (7-8)+9})) & 17577 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
17578 &:= ((1 - 2) - ((3 + 4) - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17578 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -((7 \times (6 - (5 \times (4^3)))))) + 2)) + 1)) \\
17579 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3 - 4) + (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17579 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + 2) \times 1) \\
17580 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3 - 4) + (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17580 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + 2)) + 1) \\
17581 &:= (1 \times ((2 - (3 + 4)) + (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17581 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + ((6 + (5 \times 4))^3)) - 2) \times -1)) \\
17582 &:= (1 \times (((2 - 3) \times 4) + (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17582 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 + ((6 + (5 \times 4))^3)) - 2) \times -1)) \\
17583 &:= (1 + (((2 - 3) \times 4) + (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17583 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + ((6 + (5 \times 4))^3)) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
17584 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) - (4 - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17584 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 + ((6 + (5 \times 4))^3)) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
17585 &:= (1 - (2 - (((((3 - 4) \times -5)^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17585 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + ((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + 2)) \times -1)) \\
17586 &:= ((1 - 2) - ((3 - 4) - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17586 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 + (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + 2)) \times -1)) \\
17587 &:= ((1 - 2) \times ((3 - 4) - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17587 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 - (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + (2 - 1)))) \\
17588 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 - 4) + (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17588 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 - (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + 2)) \times -1)) \\
17589 &:= (1 + (((((2 + (3 + 4)) \times (5^6)) + 7) / 8) + 9)) & 17589 &:= (9 + ((8 - 7) + (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
17590 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - 3) \times 4) - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17590 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) \times -(6 - (5 \times (4^3)))) - (2 + 1))) \\
17591 &:= (1 - (((2 - 3) \times 4) - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17591 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) \times (6 - (5 \times (4^3))))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
17592 &:= ((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4) + (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17592 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -(((6 + ((5 + 4)^3)) - 2) \times -1)) \\
17593 &:= (1 \times -(2 + ((3 - 4) - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17593 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((7 + 6) \times -(5 - (4 + 3)))^{2+1})) \\
17594 &:= (1 - (2 + (((3 - 4) - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17594 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) \times (6 - (5 \times (4^3)))) - (2 - 1))) \\
17595 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -((4 + (5 \times (6 + 7))) \times -(8 + 9))) & 17595 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) \times (6 - (5 \times (4^3)))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
17596 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times 3) + 4) + (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17596 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) \times -(6 - (5 \times (4^3)))) + (2 + 1))) \\
17597 &:= (1 + (((2 \times 3) + 4) + (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17597 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 + ((6 + (5 \times 4))^3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
17598 &:= ((1 - 2) \times ((3 \times -4) - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17598 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 + ((6 + (5 \times 4))^3)) - 2) \times -1)) \\
17599 &:= (12 - ((3 - 4) - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9)) & 17599 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 + ((6 + (5 \times 4))^3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
17600 &:= (((12^3) - (4^5)) \times -((6 \times -7) + (8 + 9))) & 17600 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 + ((6 + (5 \times 4))^3)) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
17601 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 \times -4) - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17601 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + (2 - 1)))) \\
17602 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 + 4)^5) + (6 + 789))) & 17602 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 + (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + 2)) \times -1)) \\
17603 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (((3 + 4)^5) + 6)) + 789) & 17603 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
17604 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times (((5 + 6) - (7 - 8)) \times 9)) & 17604 &:= ((98 + ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times -(4 \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
17605 &:= ((12 + 3) + (4 + (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17605 &:= (98 - (7 \times -((((6 \times (5^4))/3) \times 2) + 1))) \\
17606 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) \times 4) + (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 17606 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 + 6)^{(5+4)/3})) - 21)) \\
17607 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((((3 \times (4 + (5^6))) - 7) / -8) - 9)) & 17607 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 - (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + 21)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 17649 &:= ((1+2) \times -((3 \times -(4 + ((5^6) + 7)/8))) - 9)) \\
 17650 &:= ((1 + (((234 \times 5) + 6) \times (7+8))) + 9) \\
 17651 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3+4) + ((5^6) + 7)/8)) \times 9))) \\
 17652 &:= (((1+2) + ((3^4) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7) + 8))) - 9) \\
 17653 &:= (1 + (23 + (((4^5) + (6+7)) \times (8+9)))) \\
 17654 &:= ((1 - (23 \times 4)) \times -((5 + ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9)))) \\
 17655 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -34) - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) \\
 17656 &:= (((1+2)^3) - (((4^5) + (6+7)) \times -(8+9))) \\
 17657 &:= (1 - ((2^3) \times -((((45 \times 6) + 7) \times 8) - 9))) \\
 17658 &:= ((1 - (23 - 4)) \times ((5 + ((6 + 7) \times 8)) \times -9)) \\
 17659 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 \times ((45 \times 67) - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 17660 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -((4 + ((56 - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 17661 &:= (12 - (((3+4) + ((5^6) + 7)/8)) \times -9)) \\
 17662 &:= ((-1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) - (5^6))/7) \times 8) - 9) \\
 17663 &:= (((12+3) + (4^5)) \times -((6 - 7) \times (8+9))) \\
 17664 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) - (5^6))/7) \times 8) - 9) \\
 17665 &:= (1 \times -((2 - (((3^4) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7) + 8)) + 9))) \\
 17666 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3^4) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7) + 8)) + 9))) \\
 17667 &:= ((1+2) \times -(((3+4) \times -(56 \times (7+8))) - 9)) \\
 17668 &:= (-1 - (2 - ((34 \times (5 \times ((6+7) \times 8))) - 9))) \\
 17669 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3^4) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7) + 8)) + 9))) \\
 17670 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3^4) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7) + 8)) + 9))) \\
 17671 &:= (-1 - ((2 + (34 \times (5+6))) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 17672 &:= (1 \times -((2 + (34 \times (5+6))) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 17673 &:= ((1 + (2^{3+4})) \times -((5 \times -(6+7)) - (8 \times 9))) \\
 17674 &:= ((1+2) - ((34 \times -(5 \times ((6+7) \times 8))) + 9)) \\
 17675 &:= ((1 - (2 + 34)) \times -(((5 - 67) \times -8) + 9)) \\
 17676 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) - 6)) - 78) \times -9)) \\
 17677 &:= (((1+2)^{3+4} + (5^6)) + ((7+8) \times -9)) \\
 17678 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -4) - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9)) \\
 17679 &:= (12 - (((3^4) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7) + 8)) - 9)) \\
 17680 &:= ((1 + (23 \times (4+5))) \times ((6+7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 17681 &:= (1 \times (((((2 \times (3^4)) - (5^6))/7) \times -8) + 9)) \\
 17682 &:= (1 + (((((2 \times (3^4)) - (5^6))/7) \times -8) + 9)) \\
 17683 &:= ((1+2) - ((3 + ((4^5) + (6+7))) \times -(8+9))) \\
 17684 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (45 \times ((6 \times 7) + 89)))))) \\
 17685 &:= ((12 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (((6+7) - 8) \times -9)) \\
 17686 &:= ((1 + (2 + 34)) \times (567 - 89)) \\
 17687 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((34 \times (5 \times ((6+7) \times 8))) + 9))) \\
 17688 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (34 \times (5 \times (6+7)))) \times 8)) - 9) \\
 17689 &:= (1 - ((2^3) - (4 \times (56 \times (7 + (8 \times 9))))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 17649 &:= ((98 + (7 + 6)) \times -((54 \times -3) + (2 + 1))) \\
 17650 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times (((6 \times -(5 - (4 \times 3)))^2) + 1)) \\
 17651 &:= (9 + ((87 + ((6 + (5 \times 4))^3)) - 21)) \\
 17652 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - (654 \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
 17653 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + (6^5)))/ -4) + (32 - 1)) \\
 17654 &:= ((987 + ((6^5) + (4^3))) \times -((2 \times -1))) \\
 17655 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 - (6 - 54)) \times -321)) \\
 17656 &:= (98 - (((7 + ((6^5)/4)) \times -((3^2)) + 1)) \\
 17657 &:= (98 - ((7 + ((6^5)/4)) \times -((3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 17658 &:= (98 - (((7 + ((6^5)/4)) \times -((3^2)) - 1)) \\
 17659 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (654 \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
 17660 &:= (98 + ((7 + ((6 + (5 \times 4))^3)) - 21)) \\
 17661 &:= ((9 - (876 \times (5^4)))/ - (32 - 1)) \\
 17662 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) \times (6 + (5^4))) - 3))/ (2 \times -1)) \\
 17663 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((((7 \times 65) + (4^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
 17664 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times (6 + (((5 + 4)^3) + (2 - 1)))) \\
 17665 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) \times (6 + (5^4))) + 3))/ (2 \times -1)) \\
 17666 &:= ((98 - 7) + (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) - (2 - 1))) \\
 17667 &:= ((98 - 7) - (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) \times -((2 - 1))) \\
 17668 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -((6 + (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
 17669 &:= (9 - (8 - (7 \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
 17670 &:= (98 - (7 - (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 17671 &:= (((9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (6 + (5^4)))) - 3)/ - (2 \times -1)) \\
 17672 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 17673 &:= ((9 + 87) + (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + (2 - 1))) \\
 17674 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) \times (6 + (5^4))) + 3))/ - (2 \times -1)) \\
 17675 &:= (9 + (87 + (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 17676 &:= ((98 - (((7 + 6)^5) + (4 - 3)))/ - 21) \\
 17677 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) \times (6 + (5^4)))/ - (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
 17678 &:= ((9 - ((8 + ((7 + 6)^5)))/ (4 + 3))/ - (2 + 1)) \\
 17679 &:= (98 - (((7 + ((6 + (5 \times 4))^3)) - 2) \times -1)) \\
 17680 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(((7 \times 6) + 5)^{(4-3) \times 2})) + 1)) \\
 17681 &:= (98 - ((7 + ((6 + (5 \times 4))^3)) \times -((2 - 1))) \\
 17682 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(((7 \times 6) + 5)^{(4-3) \times 2})) - 1)) \\
 17683 &:= (98 - ((7 + (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + 2)) \times -1)) \\
 17684 &:= ((9 + ((8 + ((7 + 6)^5)))/ (4 + 3))/ (2 + 1)) \\
 17685 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
 17686 &:= ((98 + (76 \times 5)) \times -((4 \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
 17687 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (((76 + (54 + 3))^2) - 1)) \\
 17688 &:= (9 - (((8 \times ((7 \times (6 + (5^4))) + 3))/ - 2) + 1)) \\
 17689 &:= (9 + (8 \times (((7 \times 6) + 5)^{(4-3) \times 2} + 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
17731 &:= (1 \times ((23 - ((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times -(8 + 9))) & 17731 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((7 \times -6) + ((543 \times 2) - 1))) \\
17732 &:= (1 + ((23 - ((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times -(8 + 9))) & 17732 &:= (((-9 - 876) \times -(5 \times 4) + 32) \times 1) \\
17733 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + ((5^6) - 7)) + (8 \times -9) & 17733 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((76 - 5) \times (4 \times 3))) \times -21)) \\
17734 &:= (1 + (23 \times -(((4 - 56) \times (7 + 8)) + 9))) & 17734 &:= (((9 - 876) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
17735 &:= (((-1 - (((23 \times 4) - (5^6))/7)) \times 8) - 9) & 17735 &:= (((-9 + 876) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2) + 1) \\
17736 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 - (8 - 9)) & 17736 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
17737 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -(((45 \times 6) + 7) \times 8)) - 9) & 17737 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 76) - 54) \times -(32 \times 1))) \\
17738 &:= (1 - (((2^3) \times -(((45 \times 6) + 7) \times 8)) - 9)) & 17738 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 76) - 54) \times -32) - 1) \\
17739 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3+4}) \times -((5 \times (6 + 7)) + 8)) / -9 & 17739 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times 6) \times -(5 + ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))))) \\
17740 &:= (1 - ((23 + 4) \times -(((5 \times (6 + 7)) + 8) \times 9))) & 17740 &:= ((((-98 \times (7 + (6^5)))/ -43) + 2) \times 1) \\
17741 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times -(6 - (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 17741 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 + 65)) - 4) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
17742 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6 + 7) \times -(8 \times 9))) & 17742 &:= (((-987 \times 6) + (5 - 4)) \times -3) - 21) \\
17743 &:= (1 \times -(2 + ((3 + (45 \times 6)) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) & 17743 &:= ((9 - ((876 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
17744 &:= ((1 - (((23 \times 4) - (5^6))/7) \times 8) - 9) & 17744 &:= (((-98 - 7) \times -(((6 - 5) + (4 \times 3))^2)) - 1) \\
17745 &:= ((1 - 2) \times ((3 + (45 \times 6)) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 17745 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(7 + (((6 + 5) \times 4) + 3)^2 + 1))) \\
17746 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6 + 7) \times -(8 \times 9))) & 17746 &:= (((-98 - 7) \times -(((6 - 5) + (4 \times 3))^2)) + 1) \\
17747 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + ((5^6) + 7)) + (8 \times -9) & 17747 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 + 5)) \times 4) \times -(3^2) - 1) \\
17748 &:= (1 + (2 - ((3 + (45 \times 6)) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) & 17748 &:= (9 \times -(8 - ((7 + 654) \times 3) - (2 + 1))) \\
17749 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times -9) & 17749 &:= (98 - (7 - (654 \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
17750 &:= (1 \times (2 - (34 \times (5 - ((67 \times 8) - 9)))))) & 17750 &:= ((((-987 \times 6) + 5) \times -(4 - (3 - 2))) - 1) \\
17751 &:= (1 + (2 - (34 \times (5 - ((67 \times 8) - 9)))))) & 17751 &:= ((98 - (7 - 6)) \times -(54 \times -3) - 21) \\
17752 &:= (123 - (((4^5) + (6 + 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) & 17752 &:= ((98 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
17753 &:= (1 - (2 + (3 \times (45 - (67 \times 89)))))) & 17753 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 + 6)^{(5+4)/3}) + 21))) \\
17754 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 45))) \times -((67 + 8) - 9)) & 17754 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) - 3) \times -21)) \\
17755 &:= ((12 + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((6 + 7) \times -(8 \times 9))) & 17755 &:= (9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times (5 \times -(4 + (3 \times 21))) \\
17756 &:= (1 \times -(23 \times -(4 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9)))))) & 17756 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -(((6 \times 5) + 4) \times (3 \times 2))) + 1)) \\
17757 &:= (1 \times -(((23 - 4) + (((5^6) + 7)/8)) \times -9)) & 17757 &:= (9 \times ((8 - ((7 + 654) \times 3) - 2)) \times -1) \\
17758 &:= (1 - (((23 - 4) + (((5^6) + 7)/8)) \times -9)) & 17758 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -(((6 \times 5) + 4) \times (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\
17759 &:= (1 - ((234 \times (5 + 678))/ -9)) & 17759 &:= (((-98 \times (7 + (6^5)))/ -43) + 21) \\
17760 &:= (12 \times -(((34 \times (56 \times 7)) - 8)/ -9)) & 17760 &:= ((98 + (7 + 6)) \times -(54 \times -3) + (2 \times 1)) \\
17761 &:= (1 \times (((23 \times 4) - (5^6))/7) \times -8) + 9) & 17761 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(7 \times ((6 - 5) \times (4 - 321)))))) \\
17762 &:= (1 + (((23 \times 4) - (5^6))/7) \times -8) + 9) & 17762 &:= (9 - (((876 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
17763 &:= ((1 + (23 \times 4)) \times (56 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) & 17763 &:= (98 + (7 + (654 \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
17764 &:= (1 \times -(2 + (3 \times (((4 \times 5) - 678) \times 9)))) & 17764 &:= ((((-987 \times 6) + (5 - 4)) \times -3) + 2) - 1) \\
17765 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + (5^6)) + ((7 \times -8) + 9) & 17765 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times (5 - ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
17766 &:= (1 - (((2^3) + ((4^5) + (6 + 7))) \times -(8 + 9))) & 17766 &:= (98 - (7 \times -(((6 + (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
17767 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times -((5 \times -6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 17767 &:= ((((-987 \times 6) - (5 - 4)) \times -3) - 2) \times 1) \\
17768 &:= (1 \times (2 - (3 \times (((4 \times 5) - 678) \times 9)))) & 17768 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 76) + 5) \times -(4 - (32 + 1)))) \\
17769 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3 + (4 \times (5^6)))) / -7) + 89)) & 17769 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 \times (6 + ((5^4) + 3)))/2) + 1))) \\
17770 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3 + (4 \times (5^6)))) / -7) + 89)) & 17770 &:= (((9 + 876) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
17771 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! + (4 \times 5 + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 17771 &:= (((-98 + (765 \times 4)) \times (3 \times 2)) - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
17895 &:= ((12+3) \times ((4 \times -((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) + 9)) \\
17896 &:= (1 + (2 - ((34 - 5) \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))))) \\
17897 &:= (1 \times (((2 - 34) \times -(567 - 8)) + 9)) \\
17898 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times -((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
17899 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times -((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
17900 &:= (1 - (2 - ((34 + 5) \times ((6 \times 78) - 9)))) \\
17901 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -((45 - 6) - (78 \times 9))) \\
17902 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((34 + 5) \times -((6 \times 78) - 9))) \\
17903 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + ((34 + (5^6))/7)) \times -8) + 9)) \\
17904 &:= (12 \times - (3 - ((4 \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) - 9))) \\
17905 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (((34 + (5^6))/7) \times -8) - 9)) \\
17906 &:= (1 \times - (2 \times -(((3^4) + 5) \times ((6 + 7) \times 8)) + 9))) \\
17907 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3^4) + 5) \times ((6 + 7) \times 8)) + 9))) \\
17908 &:= (1 + (2 + (((34 + (5^6))/7) \times 8) + 9))) \\
17909 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 34) + ((5^6) + 7)/8) \times -9)) \\
17910 &:= ((1 + ((2 - 34) \times 56)) \times (7 - (8 + 9))) \\
17911 &:= (1 + ((2 - ((345 \times 6) - 78)) \times -9)) \\
17912 &:= (1 \times - (2 \times -((3 \times (45 \times 67)) - 89))) \\
17913 &:= (12 - ((34 + 5) \times -((6 \times 78) - 9))) \\
17914 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3 \times (((4 + 5)^6) + 7)))/89)) \\
17915 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3 \times (((4 + 5)^6) + 7)))/89)) \\
17916 &:= (12 \times - (3 - ((4 \times (56 \times 7)) - (8 \times 9)))) \\
17917 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) + (7 \times - (8 \times 9))) \\
17918 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - (3 \times -((4 + 5) + (67 \times 89)))) \\
17919 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 34) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times - (7 + 8)) - 9)) \\
17920 &:= ((1 - (2 + 34)) \times -(((5 \times 6)/(7 + 8))^9)) \\
17921 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + ((34 + (5^6))/7)) \times -8) - 9)) \\
17922 &:= (1 - (((2 + ((34 + (5^6))/7)) \times -8) - 9)) \\
17923 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!) \times 4! - 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
17924 &:= (-1 - ((234 + 5) \times -((6 + 78) - 9))) \\
17925 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 + (4 + 5)) + (67 \times 89))) \\
17926 &:= ((12^3) + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times - (7 \times 89))) \\
17927 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) \times 6))) + (7 \times - (8 \times 9))) \\
17928 &:= ((12^3) - (4 \times - (5 \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
17929 &:= (1 \times -((234 \times -((5 + 6) \times 7)) + 89)) \\
17930 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3 + (4 \times (5^6))))/7) - (8 \times 9))) \\
17931 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3 + (4 \times (5^6))))/7)) - (8 \times -9)) \\
17932 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3) + (4 \times 56)) \times -78) + 9)) \\
17933 &:= ((((((12^3)/4) - 5) \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) - 9) \\
17934 &:= ((((((12^3)/4) - 5) \times -6) \times - (7 \times - (8 - 9))) \\
17935 &:= ((((((12^3)/4) - 5) \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 - 9)) \\
17936 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3 + (4 \times 56)) \times (7 + (8 \times 9))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
17895 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 6) + (5 \times 4)) \times -(32 + 1))) \\
17896 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(76 + (5 \times 432))) + 1)) \\
17897 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 + (5 \times 432)))) \times 1) \\
17898 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(76 + (5 \times 432))) - 1)) \\
17899 &:= ((((-98 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5) \times -(4^3)) - 21) \\
17900 &:= (9 - (((8 + 76) \times -((5 \times 43) - 2)) + 1)) \\
17901 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 + 6) \times -((5 \times (4 \times 3)) + 21))) \\
17902 &:= (9 - (((8 + 76) \times -((5 \times 43) - 2)) - 1)) \\
17903 &:= (-9 - (8 \times -((7 \times (6 + (((5^4) + 3)/2))) - 1))) \\
17904 &:= (((-98 \times -7) + (6 + 54)) \times (3 + 21)) \\
17905 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(76 + ((5 \times 432) + 1)))) \\
17906 &:= ((-98 / -7) \times -((6 \times -((5 \times 43) - 2)) - 1)) \\
17907 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 \times - (5 \times (4 \times 3))) - 21)) \\
17908 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 76) \times -((5 \times - (4 \times (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\
17909 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times ((5 + (4 \times 3))^2))) \times -1) \\
17910 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
17911 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) \times (6 + (((5^4) + 3)/2)))) \times -1) \\
17912 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) \times - (6 + (((5^4) + 3)/2))) - 1)) \\
17913 &:= (((((-98 \times 7) + 6) \times 5) / -4) + 3) \times 21 \\
17914 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times (5 - ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
17915 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 43)))) \times 2) - 1) \\
17916 &:= (-9 - (8 + ((7 \times (6 \times (5 - 432))) + 1))) \\
17917 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 + 432) \times -1)) \\
17918 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (((7 + 6) \times - (5 - (43 \times 2))) + 1)) \\
17919 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5)/4)) \times (3 \times - (2 + 1))) \\
17920 &:= ((9 - (8 - (7 + 6))) \times - (5 \times - (4^{3+2-1}))) \\
17921 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times (6 + (((5^4) + 3)/2))) - 1))) \\
17922 &:= ((98 + 76) \times -(((54 - 3) \times -2) - 1)) \\
17923 &:= (((((-98 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5) \times -(4^3)) + 2) + 1) \\
17924 &:= (-9 - (8 + (7 \times ((6 \times (5 - 432)) - 1)))) \\
17925 &:= (((((-987 \times 6) - 54) \times -3) - 2) - 1) \\
17926 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times -((5 + (4 \times 3))^2)) + 1)) \\
17927 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times -((5 + 4) \times 32) + 1)) \\
17928 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (6 + (((5^4) + 3)/2)))) - 1) \\
17929 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (6 + (((5^4) + 3)/2)))) \times 1) \\
17930 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) \times - (6 + (((5^4) + 3)/2))) - 1)) \\
17931 &:= (9 - (87 \times - (6 + (5 \times (43 - (2 + 1)))))) \\
17932 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times - (6 \times (5 - 432))) - 1)) \\
17933 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 \times - (6 \times (5 - 432))) - 1)) \\
17934 &:= (9 - (8 + ((7 \times (6 \times (5 - 432))) + 1))) \\
17935 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -((43 \times -2) + 1)) \\
17936 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 - 432)))) - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
17937 &:= ((1+2) \times (3 \times -((4 \times ((5-67) \times 8)) - 9))) \\
17938 &:= (1 - (((23 \times ((4 \times 5) + 67)) - 8) \times -9)) \\
17939 &:= (1 - (2 - ((345 \times (6 \times 78))/9))) \\
17940 &:= (12 \times ((34 - (5 + 6)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
17941 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
17942 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((345 \times (6 \times 78))/9))) \\
17943 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + ((3^4) + (5^6)))/7) \times -8) + 9) \\
17944 &:= (1 - (((2 + ((3^4) + (5^6)))/7) \times -8) + 9) \\
17945 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + (67 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
17946 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (4^5)) \times (6 - (7 + (8 + 9))) \\
17947 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + (5^6)) - ((7 + 8) \times -9) \\
17948 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3 + 4)^5) + (67 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
17949 &:= ((1 + (23 \times 4)) \times -((5 \times -(6 \times 7)) + (8 + 9))) \\
17950 &:= ((1 - ((2^3) \times 45)) \times -(67 - (8 + 9))) \\
17951 &:= ((((((12^3)/4) - 5) \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) + 9) \\
17952 &:= ((1 - 23) \times ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times -(7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
17953 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(34 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))))) \\
17954 &:= (-1 - ((23 - 4) \times -(5 \times ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9)))) \\
17955 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 + 4) \times -((5 + (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9))) \\
17956 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) \times (456 \times 7))/8) \times -9) \\
17957 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times 45) - 6) \times -(7 - 89)) \\
17958 &:= (123 \times -(4 - (5 \times (6 + (7 + (8 + 9)))))) \\
17959 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) - (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 - 89))) \\
17960 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -((4 \times (567 - 8)) + 9))) \\
17961 &:= (1 - ((2^3) \times -((4 \times (567 - 8)) + 9))) \\
17962 &:= ((1 + (((2 + ((3^4) + (5^6)))/7) \times 8)) + 9) \\
17963 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + ((6 + 7) \times 89)))) \\
17964 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 + 4)^5) + ((6 + 7) \times 89))) \\
17965 &:= (-1 + (2 + (((3 + 4)^5) + ((6 + 7) \times 89)))) \\
17966 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3 + 4)^5) + ((6 + 7) \times 89)))) \\
17967 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (34 \times 5))) \times -((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\
17968 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) \times -(4 + (5 \times ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))))) \\
17969 &:= (1 + ((2^3) \times -(4 + (5 \times ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))))) \\
17970 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times -(4 + 5)) - (67 \times 89))) \\
17971 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 + 4! \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
17972 &:= (((12^3) - (4 - (5^6))) - (7 \times -89)) \\
17973 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times -6) - ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
17974 &:= ((1 - 23) \times ((4 \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8)) - 9)) \\
17975 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
17976 &:= (12 \times ((3 + (4 \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8))) - 9)) \\
17977 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 \times 45) + 67) \times 89)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
17937 &:= (9 \times -((8 \times (7 - (65 \times 4))) + (32 - 1))) \\
17938 &:= ((9 + ((87 - (6^5)) \times (4 + 3)))/ - (2 + 1)) \\
17939 &:= (9 + (((87 \times (6 - (5^4)))/ - 3) - 21)) \\
17940 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -((5 \times -4) - (32 \times 1))) \\
17941 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 \times -((6 \times (5 - 432)) - 1))) \\
17942 &:= ((9 + ((87 \times (6 - (5^4)))/3)) \times -(2 - 1)) \\
17943 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + (6^5)))/ - 4) + 321) \\
17944 &:= (((9 + ((87 \times (6 - (5^4)))/3)) - 2) \times -1) \\
17945 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 76) \times (5 - (4^3)))/2)) \times 1) \\
17946 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 76) \times (5 - (4^3)))/ - 2) + 1) \\
17947 &:= ((9 - ((87 + (((6 + 5) \times 4) + 3))^2)) \times -1) \\
17948 &:= ((98 - (7 \times (6^{5-4+3}))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
17949 &:= (((9 + (87 \times (6 - (5^4)))) - 3)/ - (2 + 1)) \\
17950 &:= (9 - (((87 - (6^5)) \times (4 + 3))/(2 + 1))) \\
17951 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 \times -(6 \times ((5 - 432) \times 1)))) \\
17952 &:= (((9 + 8) - 765) \times (4 \times -(3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
17953 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times (6 - (5^4))) + 3))/(2 + 1)) \\
17954 &:= ((9 - (87 \times (6 - (5^4))))/ - (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
17955 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times (6 - (5^4))) - 3))/(2 + 1)) \\
17956 &:= ((((-9 + (87 \times (6 - (5^4))))/3) - 2) \times -1) \\
17957 &:= (9 + (((87 \times (6 - (5^4)))/ - 3) - (2 + 1))) \\
17958 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times (6 - (5^4)))/3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
17959 &:= (9 + (((87 \times (6 - (5^4))) + 3)/ - (2 + 1))) \\
17960 &:= (((9 + 8) - (((7 \times 6) - (5 + 4))^3))/(2 \times -1)) \\
17961 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 54)) - (3 + 21)))) \\
17962 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times (6 - (5^4)))/3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
17963 &:= (9 + (((87 \times (6 - (5^4)))/ - 3) + (2 + 1))) \\
17964 &:= ((9 - ((87 - (6 \times (5 + 4)))^3))/(2 \times -1)) \\
17965 &:= (9 - (((87 + (((6 + 5) \times 4) + 3))^2) \times -1)) \\
17966 &:= (9 + (((87 + (((6 + 5) \times 4) + 3))^2) + 1)) \\
17967 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + ((6^5)/4))) - (32 + 1)) \\
17968 &:= (((9 - 8) - (((7 \times 6) - (5 + 4))^3))/(2 \times -1)) \\
17969 &:= (((9 - 8) + (((7 \times 6) - (5 + 4))^3))/ - (2 \times -1)) \\
17970 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 \times 65)) \times 4)) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\
17971 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 76)) \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))/2) + 1) \\
17972 &:= (((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + ((6^5)/4)) - 3) - 2) + 1) \\
17973 &:= ((9 + ((87 - (6 \times (5 + 4)))^3))/ - (2 \times -1)) \\
17974 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (43 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
17975 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 \times -((4 \times 3)^2)) + 1)) \\
17976 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -(((6 \times (5^4))/ - (3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
17977 &:= (((9 + 8) + (((7 \times 6) - (5 + 4))^3))/ - (2 \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
17978 &:= ((-1+2) \times -(((3 \times 45) + 67) \times -89)) & 17978 &:= (-9 + (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times 4) + 3)^2)) + 1)) \\
17979 &:= (123 + (4 \times -((5 - 67) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 17979 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times 54) + 321) \\
17980 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times (4 - (((56 \times 7) + 8) \times 9)))) & 17980 &:= ((98 + ((7 \times 6) + 5)) \times -(4 \times -(32 - 1))) \\
17981 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 - (((56 \times 7) + 8) \times 9)))) & 17981 &:= (9 + (((87 \times (6 - (5^4)))) / -3) + 21)) \\
17982 &:= (1 \times ((2 - (((3^{4-5+6}) + 7) \times 8)) \times -9)) & 17982 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times ((6 \times 54) - 3))) + (2 + 1))) \\
17983 &:= (1 + ((2 - (((3^{4-5+6}) + 7) \times 8)) \times -9)) & 17983 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times (((4 + 3)^2) \times -1)) \\
17984 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (34 \times ((5 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8)) + 9)))) & 17984 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times ((6 \times 54) - 3))) + (2 - 1))) \\
17985 &:= (1 - (2 - (34 \times ((5 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8)) + 9)))) & 17985 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times (((54 + 3) - 2) \times -1)) \\
17986 &:= (1 + ((2 - ((3 + 4) \times 5)) \times -((67 \times 8) + 9))) & 17986 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times 54) - 3))) + 2)) - 1) \\
17987 &:= (-1 - (2 \times -(3 \times ((45 \times 67) - (8 + 9)))) & 17987 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times 54) - 3)))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
17988 &:= (12 \times ((3 + (4 \times (56 \times 7))) - (8 \times 9))) & 17988 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times 54) - 3))) + 2)) + 1) \\
17989 &:= ((1 + 2) - (34 \times -((5 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8)) + 9))) & 17989 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times ((6^5) - (4^3)))) / - (2 + 1)) \\
17990 &:= (12 - (((3 \times 45) + 67) \times -89)) & 17990 &:= (98 + (7 \times -(6 \times (5 - (432 - 1)))))) \\
17991 &:= (1 \times (((2^3) \times -(45 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) & 17991 &:= (9 \times -(((87 + ((6^5) / 4)) - 32) \times -1)) \\
17992 &:= (1 + (((2^3) \times -(45 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) & 17992 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - 6) \times -((5 \times 4) + (3 \times 2))) \times 1) \\
17993 &:= (((((-123 \times (4^5)) - 6) / -7) + 8) - 9) & 17993 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times ((6 \times 54) - 3)) + (2 - 1)))) \\
17994 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(3 + (4 \times (5 \times ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) & 17994 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times 4) + 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
17995 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(3 + (4 \times (5 \times ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) & 17995 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times -(((5 \times 4) + 3)^2 \times 1))) \\
17996 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 \times 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 17996 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times 4) + 3)^2)) + 1)) \\
17997 &:= ((12^3) - (((4^5) - 67) \times -(8 + 9))) & 17997 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -((65 + 4) \times 3)) + 21)) \\
17998 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3^{4-5+6}) + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 17998 &:= (-9 - ((87 \times -((65 + 4) \times 3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
17999 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3^{4-5+6}) + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 17999 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times -((6 \times (5 - 432)) + 1))) \\
18000 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^4)) \times -(5 \times -(((6 + 7) - 8) \times 9))) & 18000 &:= ((((-9 - 8)^7) - 6) \times (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) \times -1)) \\
18001 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 \times (45 \times 67))) + 89)) & 18001 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times ((6 \times 54) - 3)) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
18002 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(((3 + (4 \times (5^6))) / 7) + (8 \times 9)))) & 18002 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times ((6 \times 54) - 3)) + 2)) - 1)) \\
18003 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3 + (4 \times (5^6))) / 7) + (8 \times 9)))) & 18003 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (((7 + 6) - 543) \times -2) - 1) \\
18004 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times -(((456 - 7) \times 8) + 9))) & 18004 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 + 6)) \times -(((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) - 1))) \\
18005 &:= (1 \times -(2 + 3) \times -(((456 - 7) \times 8) + 9))) & 18005 &:= ((((-9 - 8)^7) - 6) \times -(((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1)) \\
18006 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 - (4 \times (5 \times ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) & 18006 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times ((6 \times 54) - 3))) - 21)) \\
18007 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 - (4 \times (5 \times ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) & 18007 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times -(6 \times (5 - 432)))) + 1)) \\
18008 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -((4 \times 567) - (8 + 9)))) & 18008 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 + 6)) \times -((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2)) - 1)) \\
18009 &:= (((1 + 2) - ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -(78 + 9)) & 18009 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times 6) + (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
18010 &:= ((1 - ((2^3) \times (45 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) + 9) & 18010 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 + 6)) \times -((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2)) + 1)) \\
18011 &:= ((1 - (234 \times (5 + 6))) \times -(7 \times -(8 - 9))) & 18011 &:= ((98 - (7 \times ((6^5) - 43))) / - (2 + 1)) \\
18012 &:= (12 \times (3 + ((4^5) + (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 18012 &:= ((9 - (87 \times (6 + 5))) \times ((4 \times -(3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
18013 &:= (((-1 + 234) \times ((5 + 6) \times 7)) - (8 \times -9)) & 18013 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times -((6 \times (5 - 432)) - 1))) \\
18014 &:= (1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4!) - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 & 18014 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 + 6)) \times -(((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1))) \\
18015 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 - 45) - (67 \times 89))) & 18015 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -((65 + 4) \times 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\
18016 &:= (1 \times ((2 - 34) \times -(5 + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) & 18016 &:= ((9 + (87 \times ((65 + 4) \times 3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
18017 &:= (1 + ((2 - 34) \times -(5 + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) & 18017 &:= (9 + ((87 \times -(6 - ((5 \times 43) - 2))) - 1)) \\
18018 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 - (((4^5) \times 6) - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 18018 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 \times -(6 \times ((5 \times (43 \times 2)) - 1)))) \\
18019 &:= (1 \times -((234 \times -((5 + 6) \times 7)) + (8 - 9))) & 18019 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 \times -(6 \times ((5 \times (43 \times 2)) - 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
18020 &:= (1 \times -((2+3) \times -(4 + ((56 \times 7) + 8) \times 9))) \\
18021 &:= ((1+2) \times (((3 - 4^5) \times -6) - (7 \times (8+9)))) \\
18022 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times (45 + (67 \times 89)))))) \\
18023 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -(((4 \times 5) - 6) \times (7 \times 8))) + 9)) \\
18024 &:= ((1 + (((2+3)^4)/5) \times 6) \times (7 + (8+9))) \\
18025 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - ((7+8) \times 9)))))) \\
18026 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - ((7+8) \times 9)))))) \\
18027 &:= (1 + (2 + (3 \times (45 + (67 \times 89)))))) \\
18028 &:= (((-1 + (234 \times (5+6))) \times 7) + 8) + 9) \\
18029 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - ((7+8) \times 9)))))) \\
18030 &:= (1 + (2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - ((7+8) \times 9)))))) \\
18031 &:= (((-12 - 34) \times -(56 \times 7)) + (8 - 9)) \\
18032 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times ((5 \times -6) + (7 - 89))) \\
18033 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 \times ((45 \times 67) - 8))) + 9)) \\
18034 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(3 \times ((45 \times 67) - 8))) + 9)) \\
18035 &:= (1 \times -((234 \times -((5+6) \times 7)) - (8+9))) \\
18036 &:= ((1+2) \times ((3 + ((4^5) \times 6)) - ((7+8) \times 9))) \\
18037 &:= (1 \times (((2+3) - ((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times -(8+9))) \\
18038 &:= (1 + (((2+3) - ((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times -(8+9))) \\
18039 &:= (12 - (3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) - ((7+8) \times 9)))) \\
18040 &:= (((12^3) + (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) + (8 \times -9)) \\
18041 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -(((4 \times 5) - 6) \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
18042 &:= (1 - ((23 \times -(((4 \times 5) - 6) \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
18043 &:= (1 \times -(2 + ((34 \times (5 - (67 \times 8))) + 9))) \\
18044 &:= (1 - (2 + ((34 \times (5 - (67 \times 8))) + 9))) \\
18045 &:= ((1+2) \times -(((3+4) \times -((5+6) \times 78)) - 9)) \\
18046 &:= (-1 + (2 - ((34 \times (5 - (67 \times 8))) + 9))) \\
18047 &:= (1 \times (2 - ((34 \times (5 - (67 \times 8))) + 9))) \\
18048 &:= (((12^3)/4) \times -((5 + (6 \times 7) \times 8))/ - 9) \\
18049 &:= ((1 + (((2+3)^4) \times (5 \times 6))) + (78 \times -9)) \\
18050 &:= ((1 + ((2^3) \times 45)) \times (67 - (8+9))) \\
18051 &:= (((12^3) - (4 - (5^6))) - (78 \times -9)) \\
18052 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(3 \times ((45 \times 67) - 8))) - 9)) \\
18053 &:= (-1 - (2 \times -((3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))) \\
18054 &:= ((1+2) \times ((3 - ((45+6) \times 7)) \times -(8+9))) \\
18055 &:= (1 + (2 \times -((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times ((67 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
18056 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((3 \times (45 \times 67)) - (8+9)))) \\
18057 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 \times (45 \times 67)) - (8+9)))) \\
18058 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times 4! + 5! + 6! - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
18059 &:= (((12^3) + (4 + (5^6))) - (78 \times -9)) \\
18060 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - 5)) \times -((6+7) - (8-9))) \\
18061 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 \times ((45 \times 67) - 8)) + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
18020 &:= ((9 + (87 \times ((65 + 4) \times 3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
18021 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -((65 + 4) \times 3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
18022 &:= (9 + 8 + 7) \times 6! - 5 + 4! + 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
18023 &:= (-9 - (8 \times -(((7 \times 65) - 4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1)) \\
18024 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -(((6 \times (5^4))/ - (3 + 2)) - 1)) \\
18025 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 \times -((4 \times 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
18026 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 \times 6) + (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
18027 &:= (9 \times -((8 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 43)) + 21)) \\
18028 &:= (((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + (((6^5)/4) + 3))) + 2) - 1) \\
18029 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times -(((5 \times 4) + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
18030 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (((76 \times 5) - 4) \times 3))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
18031 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (((7 \times 65) - 4) \times (3 + 2)))) \times -1) \\
18032 &:= ((98 - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times -(4^3)) - (2 \times 1))) \\
18033 &:= (98 + ((7 \times -(6 \times (5 - 432))) + 1)) \\
18034 &:= (98 - (76 \times -((5 \times 43) + 21))) \\
18035 &:= ((9 + (87 \times (6 - ((5^4) + 3))))/ - (2 + 1)) \\
18036 &:= ((9 + (87 \times (65 + 4))) \times -(3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
18037 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (((7 + 6) - 543) \times -2) + 1) \\
18038 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times ((6^5) - 43)))/ - (2 + 1)) \\
18039 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times (76 - 5)) - 4) \times 32)) \times -1) \\
18040 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times -(((76 \times 5) - 4) \times (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\
18041 &:= ((9 - (87 \times (6 - ((5^4) + 3))))/ (2 + 1)) \\
18042 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) - (5^4)) \times -(32 - 1) \\
18043 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (43 \times 2)))) \times -1) \\
18044 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6^5) - 43)))/ (2 + 1)) \\
18045 &:= (9 \times -((8 \times -(7 \times (6 \times 5))) - (4 + 321))) \\
18046 &:= ((-98/ - 7) \times -((6 \times -(5 \times 43)) + (2 - 1))) \\
18047 &:= (9 + ((87 \times (6 - ((5^4) + 3))))/ - (2 + 1)) \\
18048 &:= (((98 + 7) - (6 + 5)) \times -((4^3) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
18049 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 \times 65) - 4) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1)))) \\
18050 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times ((6^5) - 43)))/ - (2 + 1))) \\
18051 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 76) \times (5 \times 43))) \times -(2 - 1)) \\
18052 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 43)))) \times -2) - 1)) \\
18053 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 43)))) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
18054 &:= ((9 + (87 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times -(4 + 3)) + (2 - 1))) \\
18055 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times 6))) \times -5 - (4^3)) + 2) - 1) \\
18056 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (76 - 5)) - 4) \times -32) + 1) \\
18057 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (76 - 5)) - 4) \times -32 \times 1)) \\
18058 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 43)))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
18059 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(6 \times (5 \times (43 \times 2)))) + 1)) \\
18060 &:= ((98 + (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
18061 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (43 \times 2)))) \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
18062 &:= (((1-2) - (34 \times (5 - (67 \times 8)))) + 9) & 18062 &:= (9 - (8 - ((7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (43 \times 2)))) + 1))) \\
18063 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times -((4 \times (5 \times 6)) - 789)) & 18063 &:= ((9 + ((8+7) \times ((6+5) \times 4))) \times (3^{2+1})) \\
18064 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times (45 \times 67)) - 8))) - 9) & 18064 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (7 \times -(((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3) \times 21))) \\
18065 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3 \times (45 \times 67)) - 8)) + 9)) & 18065 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(7 + (6 \times (54 + 321)))))) \\
18066 &:= ((1+2) \times -(3 - (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 \times (8+9)))))) & 18066 &:= ((9 - 87) - (((6^5) \times (4+3)) / -(2+1))) \\
18067 &:= ((-1+2) \times -(((3+4) \times 5) - 6) \times -(7 \times 89))) & 18067 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 \times -((6 \times (5 \times (43 \times 2))) + 1))) \\
18068 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times 45))) \times -67) - 89) & 18068 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 \times -((6 \times (5 \times (43 \times 2))) + 1))) \\
18069 &:= (1 \times -(2 + ((3 - ((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times (8+9)))) & 18069 &:= ((9 + ((8+76) \times (5 \times 43))) \times (2-1)) \\
18070 &:= (1 - (2 + ((3 - ((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times (8+9)))) & 18070 &:= ((9+8) - (7 \times -((6 \times (5 \times (43 \times 2))) - 1))) \\
18071 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 \times (4^5)) + (67 \times 89)))) & 18071 &:= ((9+8) \times -((7 \times -((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 32)) + 1)) \\
18072 &:= (12 \times (3 \times -((4 \times 5) - (6 \times (78+9)))))) & 18072 &:= ((9 + (((8+76) \times (5 \times 43)) + 2)) + 1) \\
18073 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (34 \times 5))) \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9)) & 18073 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
18074 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 3)^4) - 5) \times -((6+7) - (8-9))) & 18074 &:= (9 - (8 + (((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
18075 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - 5) \times -((6+7) - (8-9))) & 18075 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times 6))) \times -(5 - (4^3))) + 21) \\
18076 &:= ((-12 \times -(3 - (4 \times (5 \times 678)))) / -9) & 18076 &:= (9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (43 \times 2)))) - 1)) \\
18077 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 \times (8+9)))))) & 18077 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (43 \times 2)))) \times -1)) \\
18078 &:= (1 + (2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 \times (8+9)))))) & 18078 &:= ((9+8) - ((7 \times -(6 \times (5 \times (43 \times 2)))) - 1)) \\
18079 &:= (12 - (((3+4) \times 5) - 6) \times -(7 \times 89)) & 18079 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 + (((7 \times 6) + (5^4)) \times 3))) - 2) \times 1) \\
18080 &:= (((1-2) + (3^4)) \times (5 + ((6+7) \times (8+9)))) & 18080 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 54)) - (3^2))) + 1)) \\
18081 &:= ((1+2) \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times -6) + ((7+8) \times 9))) & 18081 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((76+5) \times 4))) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
18082 &:= (1 - ((2345 - (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times -9)) & 18082 &:= (9 + ((8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 54)) - (3^2))) + 1)) \\
18083 &:= (12 + ((3 - ((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times -(8+9))) & 18083 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 76) - ((5^4) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
18084 &:= ((1+2) \times ((3 + ((4^5) \times 6)) - (7 \times (8+9)))) & 18084 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 43)))) \times -2) + 1)) \\
18085 &:= (1 \times (((2 + (3^4)) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) - 9)) & 18085 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 65) - 4))) \times -((3+2) \times -1)) \\
18086 &:= (1 + (((2 + (3^4)) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) - 9)) & 18086 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 43)))) \times -2) - 1)) \\
18087 &:= (12 - (3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) - (7 \times (8+9)))))) & 18087 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - ((5+43)^2)))) \times -1) \\
18088 &:= (((1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) - 5) \times ((6+7) - (8-9))) & 18088 &:= ((98 - (7 \times 6)) \times -((54 \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
18089 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times (45 \times 67)))) \times (8-9)) & 18089 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times ((6 \times 54) - (3-2))) - 1))) \\
18090 &:= (((1+2) - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (((6+7) - 8) \times -9)) & 18090 &:= ((98 - ((7 \times (6^5)) - (4^3))) / -(2+1)) \\
18091 &:= ((1+2) - (34 \times -((5 + (67 \times 8)) - 9))) & 18091 &:= (((((9-8)^7) + 6^5) - (4 \times -321)) \\
18092 &:= (((1 + (2 \times (3 \times (45 \times 67)))) - 8) + 9) & 18092 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times -(6 - ((54-3)^2))) - 1)) \\
18093 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 \times (45 \times 67)) - (8-9)))) & 18093 &:= ((98 + (7+6)) \times -((54 \times -3) - (2-1))) \\
18094 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) - (4 \times 567)) \times -8) - 9) & 18094 &:= (((9+8) + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 43)))) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
18095 &:= (((12^3) + (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) - (8+9)) & 18095 &:= ((98 - (7 \times ((6^5) - (4+3)))) / -(2+1)) \\
18096 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 \times ((45 \times 67) - (8-9)))))) & 18096 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times ((6 \times 54) - (3-2)))) + 1)) \\
18097 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3 \times (45 \times 67)) + 8)) + 9)) & 18097 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6^5) \times (4+3)) / -(2+1))) \\
18098 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -((3 \times (45 \times 67)) + 8)) + 9)) & 18098 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times ((6 \times 54) - (3-2)))) - 1)) \\
18099 &:= (1 \times (((2+3) - (4 \times ((56+7) \times 8))) \times -9)) & 18099 &:= (9 \times -(((8+7) \times (6 + (5 \times (4-32)))) - 1)) \\
18100 &:= ((1-23) - (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times -(8+9))) & 18100 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7-6)^5)) - (4 \times -321)) \\
18101 &:= (1 - ((2^3) - (4 \times ((567 \times 8) - 9)))) & 18101 &:= ((98 - ((7 \times ((6^5) - 4)) - 3)) / -(2+1)) \\
18102 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -3) + (4 \times ((567 \times 8) - 9)))) & 18102 &:= ((98 - (7 \times ((6^5) - 4))) / (3 \times -(2-1))) \\
18103 &:= (1 \times (((2 + (3^4)) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) + 9)) & 18103 &:= ((98 - ((7 \times ((6^5) - 4)) + 3)) / -(2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
18104 &:= (1 + (((2 + (3^4)) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) + 9)) \\
18105 &:= (1 \times (((2^3) + (4 \times 56)) \times 78) + 9)) \\
18106 &:= ((1 - 23) \times ((4 \times -(5 \times (6 \times 7))) + (8 + 9))) \\
18107 &:= (1 \times -((234 \times -(5 + 6) \times 7) - 89)) \\
18108 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 \times -(4 \times ((5 - 6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
18109 &:= (1 \times -((2 - 3) - (4 \times ((567 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
18110 &:= ((1 - 2) - (((3 - (4 \times 567)) \times 8) + 9)) \\
18111 &:= (((12^3) + (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) + (8 - 9)) \\
18112 &:= (((12^3) + (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) \times -(8 - 9)) \\
18113 &:= (((12^3) + (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) - (8 - 9)) \\
18114 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -3) - (4 \times ((567 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
18115 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 \times (45 \times 67)) + 8) - 9)) \\
18116 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times 3) - (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
18117 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -((4 \times -(5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8))) + 9)) \\
18118 &:= ((1 - 2) - (3 - (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
18119 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (3 - (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
18120 &:= (12 \times -(3 - ((4 \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) + 9))) \\
18121 &:= (1 \times ((2 - 3) + (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
18122 &:= (1 + ((2 - 3) + (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
18123 &:= (1 \times -((2 - 3) - (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
18124 &:= ((1 - 2) + (3 + (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
18125 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(3 + (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
18126 &:= ((1 + ((2 - 34) \times 5)) \times ((6 \times -7) - (8 \times 9))) \\
18127 &:= (1 \times (((2 - 34) \times -567) - (8 + 9))) \\
18128 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -3) - (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
18129 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -3) - (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
18130 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) + (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
18131 &:= (1 + ((2^3) + (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
18132 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times -6) + (7 - 89))) \\
18133 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (3 - ((4 \times (567 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
18134 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3)^4) \times -((5 \times 6) + (7 - 8))) - 9)) \\
18135 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3)^4) \times -((5 \times 6) + (7 - 8))) - 9)) \\
18136 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -((4 \times 567) + (8 - 9)))) \\
18137 &:= (12 + (3 + (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
18138 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times 3) - (4 \times ((56 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
18139 &:= (1 \times (((2 - 3) - ((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
18140 &:= (1 + (((2 - 3) - ((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
18141 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times -6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
18142 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 + 89))))) \\
18143 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 + 89)))) \\
18144 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 + 5)) / -6) \times -(7 \times -(8 - 9)) \\
18104 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((76 - 5) \times 4))) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
18105 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 \times -((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 32)) - 1)) \\
18106 &:= ((9 + (((8 + 7) - (6^5)) \times (4 + 3))) / -(2 + 1)) \\
18107 &:= (98 - (((7 \times 6) + (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
18108 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 76) \times 54)) \times -((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
18109 &:= (((98 + 7) - ((6^5) \times (4 + 3))) / -(2 + 1)) \\
18110 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times (6^{5-4+3}))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
18111 &:= ((98 - ((7 \times (6^5)) - (4 - 3))) / -(2 + 1)) \\
18112 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 54)) - (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\
18113 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times (6 + 5)) - 4) \times (32 - 1))) \\
18114 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 54)) - (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\
18115 &:= (((-9 \times - (8 - ((7 \times 6) + 5) \times 43))) + 2) \times -1) \\
18116 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times ((6^5) - (4 \times 3))) / -(2 + 1))) \\
18117 &:= (9 - (8 - ((7 \times ((6^5) - (4 \times 3))) / (2 + 1)))) \\
18118 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) - (6^5)) \times (4 + 3)) / -(2 + 1)) \\
18119 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times (6 \times ((5 \times (43 \times 2)) + 1)))) \\
18120 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 \times ((6^5) - 4))) / 3) - 21) \\
18121 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 54)))) + (32 \times -1)) \\
18122 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times ((6^5) - (4 + 3)))) / -(2 + 1)) \\
18123 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 \times ((6^5) - 4))) / 3) \times -(2 - 1)) \\
18124 &:= (9 + ((87 - ((6^5) \times (4 + 3))) / -(2 + 1)) \\
18125 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (5 \times -(((4 \times 3)^2) + 1))) \\
18126 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
18127 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 54)) - 3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
18128 &:= (9 + (((8 - ((7 \times (6^5)) - 4)) / -3) - 21)) \\
18129 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times ((6^5) - 4))) / (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
18130 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times 6) + 5)) \times ((4 \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\
18131 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 54)) - 3)) - (2 \times 1))) \\
18132 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 54)) - 3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
18133 &:= (9 + (8 + ((7 \times ((6^5) - (4 \times 3))) / (2 + 1)))) \\
18134 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6^5) - 4))) - 3) / (2 + 1) \\
18135 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6^5) - 4))) / -(3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
18136 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 \times 54))) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
18137 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 \times (((6^5) / (4 - (3 - 2))) - 1))) \\
18138 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6^5) / (4 - (3 - 2))) - 1))) \\
18139 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 \times ((6^5) - 4))) / 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
18140 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((7 \times ((6^5) - 4)) - 3)) / -(2 + 1))) \\
18141 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times ((6^5) - 4))) / -(3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
18142 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times (6^{5-4+3}))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
18143 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 \times ((6^5) - 4))) / 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
18144 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 \times (6^5)) / -(4 - (3 - 2))) + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
18145 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times 3)^4)) - ((5 \times (6^7)) / - (8 \times 9))) \\
18146 &:= ((1 + 23) - (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
18147 &:= (1 + (2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 + 89)))))) \\
18148 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) - ((4 \times (567 \times 8)) + 9))) \\
18149 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
18150 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times 3) + (4 \times ((56 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
18151 &:= (1 + ((2 \times 3) + (4 \times ((56 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
18152 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -((4 \times 567) - (8 - 9)))) \\
18153 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 + ((4^5) \times 6)) - (7 + 89))) \\
18154 &:= (1 \times - (2 + (3 \times ((4 - (5 + 67)) \times 89)))) \\
18155 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) - ((4 \times -(567 \times 8)) - 9)) \\
18156 &:= (12 \times -((3 - (4 - (5 + (6 + 7)))) \times -89)) \\
18157 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 45))) \times (67 \times -(8 - 9))) \\
18158 &:= (1 \times ((23 + (4 \times (567 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
18159 &:= ((12 + 3) - (4 \times -((56 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
18160 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^4)) \times -((5 \times -(6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9))) \\
18161 &:= (1 \times (((2 - 34) \times -567) + (8 + 9))) \\
18162 &:= (((12 + 3) - (4^5)) \times (6 - (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
18163 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times (45 \times 67)))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
18164 &:= (1 \times ((234 + 5) \times -((6 + 7) - 89))) \\
18165 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 - ((4 - (5 + 67)) \times 89))) \\
18166 &:= (1 - (((234 + 5) - 6) \times -78) + 9) \\
18167 &:= ((1 - (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) - (6 \times 7) \times 8)) / -9) \\
18168 &:= (12 \times -(((3^4) \times -(5 + 6)) - (7 \times 89))) \\
18169 &:= (1 \times - (2 + (3 \times (45 - (678 \times 9)))))) \\
18170 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 3) + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
18171 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3) + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
18172 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) - (4 \times ((567 \times 8) + 9)))) \\
18173 &:= (1 - ((2^3) - (4 \times ((567 \times 8) + 9)))) \\
18174 &:= ((1 - 234) \times (((5 + 6) \times -7) + (8 - 9))) \\
18175 &:= (((1 - 2) - ((3 + 4)^5)) - (((6^7) / -8) + 9)) \\
18176 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 + ((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
18177 &:= ((1 + 2) \times - (3 - (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 - 89)))) \\
18178 &:= (1 \times (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) - (((6^7) / 8) - 9)))) \\
18179 &:= (1 + (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) - (((6^7) / 8) - 9)))) \\
18180 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -(((6 + 7) - 8) \times -9)) \\
18181 &:= (1 \times - (2 - (3 \times (4 - ((5 - 678) \times 9)))))) \\
18182 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) - (4 \times -((567 \times 8) + 9))) \\
18183 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 - (4^5)) \times 6) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
18184 &:= (((12^3) + (4^{(-5+6) \times 7})) - (8 \times -9)) \\
18185 &:= (12 - ((3 + ((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times -(8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
18145 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times (6^5)) / - (4 - (3 - 2))) - 1)) \\
18146 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 \times (6^5)) / - (4 - (3 - 2))) - 1)) \\
18147 &:= ((9 - ((8 - ((7 \times (6^5)) - 4)) / 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
18148 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times (6^5)) + (4 \times 3)) / - (2 + 1))) \\
18149 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 \times (6^5)) + (4 \times 3)) / - (2 + 1))) \\
18150 &:= (((9 + 8) + ((7 \times (6^5)) + (4 - 3))) / (2 + 1)) \\
18151 &:= ((9 - ((8 - ((7 \times (6^5)) - 4)) / 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
18152 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 \times -(((6^5) / (4 - (3 - 2))) + 1))) \\
18153 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times ((6^5) + 4))) / (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
18154 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6^5) / (4 - (3 - 2))) - 1))) \\
18155 &:= ((9 + ((8 + ((7 \times (6^5)) + 4)) / 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
18156 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((7 + (65 \times 4)) \times ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\
18157 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 \times (6^5)) - (4 \times 3)) / - (2 + 1))) \\
18158 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 54))) + 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
18159 &:= ((9 + ((8 + ((7 \times (6^5)) + 4)) / 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
18160 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 \times (6^5)) / - (4 - (3 - 2))) + 1)) \\
18161 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 54)))) + ((3^2) - 1)) \\
18162 &:= (((9 + ((8 + (7 \times ((6^5) + 4))) / 3)) - 2) - 1) \\
18163 &:= (((9 + ((8 + (7 \times ((6^5) + 4))) / 3)) - 2) \times 1) \\
18164 &:= (((9 + ((8 + (7 \times ((6^5) + 4))) / 3)) - 2) + 1) \\
18165 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 \times (6^5)) + (4 \times 3)) / - (2 + 1))) \\
18166 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6^5) + (4 + 3)))) / (2 + 1)) \\
18167 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times ((6^5) + 4))) / 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
18168 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6^{5-4+3}))) \times 2)) - 1) \\
18169 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6^{5-4+3}))) \times 2)) \times 1) \\
18170 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6^{5-4+3}))) \times 2)) + 1) \\
18171 &:= (((9 + 8) + ((7 \times (6^5)) + (4^3))) / (2 + 1)) \\
18172 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times ((6^5) + (4 + 3)))) / - (2 + 1))) \\
18173 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1) \\
18174 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 54)) + 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\
18175 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (((5 + 4)^3) - 2) \times -1) \\
18176 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((76 - 5) \times -(4^{3+2-1}))) \\
18177 &:= ((98 + ((7 \times (6^5)) + (4 - 3))) / (2 + 1)) \\
18178 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times (6^{5-4+3}))) \times - (2 \times -1)) \\
18179 &:= (((98 + 7) + ((6^5) \times (4 + 3))) / (2 + 1)) \\
18180 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 54)))) + (3^{2+1})) \\
18181 &:= (9 + (8 - ((7 \times (6 - ((54 - 3)^2))) + 1))) \\
18182 &:= ((9 + (((8 + 7) + (6^5)) \times (4 + 3))) / (2 + 1)) \\
18183 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 54)) + (3 \times 2)))) \times -1) \\
18184 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 54)))) + 32) - 1) \\
18185 &:= (((98 + (7 \times ((6^5) + 4))) - 3) / (2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
18186 &:= (1 + (2 + (3 \times (4 - ((5 - 678) \times 9)))))) & 18186 &:= ((98 + (7 \times ((6^5) + 4)))/ - (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
18187 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - 78)) - 9))) & 18187 &:= ((98 + ((7 \times ((6^5) + 4)) + 3))/(2 + 1)) \\
18188 &:= ((12 - ((3 + 4^5)) - (((6^7)/ - 8) + 9)) & 18188 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 65)) - 4) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
18189 &:= ((1 + (2^{3 \times 4 - 5})) \times (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) & 18189 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 \times -(6 - (((54 - 3)^2) + 1)))) \\
18190 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -((4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 + 9)))) & 18190 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times (65 \times 4))) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
18191 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) \times -((4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 + 9)))) & 18191 &:= ((98 + ((7 \times (6^5)) + 43))/(2 + 1)) \\
18192 &:= (12 \times (3 + ((4 \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) + 9))) & 18192 &:= (((9 - 8) - (76 \times 5)) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) - 1)) \\
18193 &:= (((1 - 2) - ((3 + 4^5)) - (((6^7)/ - 8) - 9)) & 18193 &:= ((98 + (7 \times ((6^5) + (4 + 3))))/(2 + 1)) \\
18194 &:= ((1 - 2) - (3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) & 18194 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 54)) + (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
18195 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) & 18195 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times (6 - (5 \times 43))) - 2)) + 1) \\
18196 &:= (1 \times (2 - (((3 + 4^5) - (((6^7)/8) + 9)))) & 18196 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6^5) + (4 \times 3))))/(2 + 1)) \\
18197 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) & 18197 &:= (-9 + (((8 - (7 - 6)) \times ((54 - 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
18198 &:= (1 + (2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) & 18198 &:= ((98 + ((7 \times (6^5)) + (4^3)))/(2 + 1)) \\
18199 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) \times -((4 \times 567) + 8)) + 9)) & 18199 &:= (((-98 - ((7 \times (6^5)) + 4))/ - 3) + 21) \\
18200 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) + 5)) \times -((6 + 7) - (8 - 9))) & 18200 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -(((5 + 4)^3) - (2 - 1))) \\
18201 &:= (1 - ((2 - (3 + 4)) \times -((56 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) & 18201 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 54)) + (3 \times 2)))) \times 1) \\
18202 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3) + (4 \times 567)) \times -8) - 9)) & 18202 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 54)) + (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\
18203 &:= (1 \times (23 + (4 \times ((567 \times 8) + 9)))) & 18203 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 76) \times (5 - ((4^3) \times 2))) - 1) \\
18204 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 + ((4^5) \times 6)) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 18204 &:= ((98 + (7 + 6)) \times -((54 \times -3) - (2 \times 1))) \\
18205 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - 78)) + 9))) & 18205 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times -(((54 - 3)^2) + 1))) \\
18206 &:= ((12 - ((3 + 4^5)) - (((6^7)/ - 8) - 9)) & 18206 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2)) + 1)) \\
18207 &:= (12 - (3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) & 18207 &:= (9 - (8 - ((7 \times (((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2)) - 1))) \\
18208 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -(((4 + 5) - 6)^7) + 89))) & 18208 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
18209 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - 78)) + 9))) & 18209 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -(((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
18210 &:= (1 \times -(((23 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7)) - 8)/ - 9)) & 18210 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + 4)) \times (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
18211 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3)^4) + (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times 9))) & 18211 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 - (65 \times 4)))) - 3) + (2 \times -1)) \\
18212 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times -9)) & 18212 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 - (65 \times 4)))) - 3) - (2 - 1)) \\
18213 &:= ((-123 \times -(4 + ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times 8))) + 9) & 18213 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 7) \times 6) + 5) \times (4^3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
18214 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times 3)^4) + 5) \times ((6 + 7) - (8 - 9))) & 18214 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2) + 1))) \\
18215 &:= (1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + 5) \times ((6 + 7) - (8 - 9))) & 18215 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 \times -(((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2) + 1))) \\
18216 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 + ((45 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 18216 &:= ((9 + ((87 - 6) \times 5)) \times ((43 + 2) - 1)) \\
18217 &:= ((1 + (((2 - (3 - 4))^5) \times (67 + 8))) - 9) & 18217 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times ((6 \times 54) + (3 - 2)))) + 1))) \\
18218 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3 + 45) \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9))) & 18218 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 43)))))) + 2) \times 1) \\
18219 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3 + 45) \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9))) & 18219 &:= (9 + (876 + (54 \times 321))) \\
18220 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -(4 - (56 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) & 18220 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 - (65 \times 4)))) + (3 + 2)) - 1) \\
18221 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) \times -(4 - (56 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) & 18221 &:= (9 - ((87 \times ((6 + 5^4)) - 3))/ - (2 + 1))) \\
18222 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (34 \times (5 + ((67 - 8) \times 9)))))) & 18222 &:= ((9 - ((8 - 765) \times 4)) \times -(3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
18223 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (78 - 9)))))) & 18223 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times -(((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2) + 1))) \\
18224 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (78 - 9)))))) & 18224 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 \times -(((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2 \times 1))) \\
18225 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -((45 + (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times -9)) & 18225 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times -(((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2) - 1)) \\
18226 &:= ((1 - (23 + 4)) \times -((5 - 6) + (78 \times 9))) & 18226 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((76 - 5) + (4^3))^2) \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

18227 := $(1 \times (2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (78 - 9))))))$
18228 := $((1 + 2) \times -(3 - (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 - (8 \times 9))))))$
18229 := $(((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4) \times (5^6)))/((7 + 8) - 9))$
18230 := $(1 - (23 + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (78 \times 9))))$
18231 := $(123 - (4 \times -((567 \times 8) - 9)))$
18232 := $((1 - (2 - 345)) \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9))$
18233 := $(1 \times (((2 - 34) \times -567) + 89))$
18234 := $((1 + 2) \times ((3 + ((4^5) \times 6)) - (78 - 9)))$
18235 := $(1 \times -(2 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 - (8 \times 9))))))$
18236 := $((1 + (((2 - 3^4) \times 5) + 6)) \times ((7 \times -8) + 9))$
18237 := $((1 - 2) \times (3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) + (7 - (8 \times 9))))))$
18238 := $((1 - 23) \times (4 - ((56 - 7) \times (8 + 9))))$
18239 := $(1 \times -(23 \times -(4 - ((5 - 6) \times 789))))$
18240 := $((1 + 2) - (3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) + (7 - (8 \times 9))))))$
18241 := $((1 + (2 + 34)) \times -((5 + 6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9))))$
18242 := $(1 \times (2 \times -(((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times (67 \times 8)) - 9)))$
18243 := $(1 + (2 \times -(((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times (67 \times 8)) - 9)))$
18244 := $((1 + 2) - ((34 - 5) \times -(6 + (7 \times 89))))$
18245 := $(123 - (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times -(8 + 9)))$
18246 := $(1 - ((23 - ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times 7)) \times -89))$
18247 := $((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 \times 6))) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9)))$
18248 := $(1 - ((2 + 3) + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (78 \times 9))))$
18249 := $((1 + 2) \times -((3 + 4) \times -((5 + 6) \times (7 + (8 \times 9))))))$
18250 := $(1 + (((2 + 3) \times 45) + 6) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))$
18251 := $(1 \times ((2 - 3) - ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (78 \times 9))))$
18252 := $((1 + 2) - (3^4)) \times ((5 + (6 + (7 + 8))) \times -9)$
18253 := $(1 \times -((2 - 3) + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (78 \times 9))))$
18254 := $((1 - 2) - ((3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) - (7 \times 8))) + 9))$
18255 := $((1 - 2) \times ((3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) - (7 \times 8))) + 9))$
18256 := $((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times -((5 \times -6) + (7 - 89)))$
18257 := $(1 \times ((2 + 3) - ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (78 \times 9))))$
18258 := $((1 + 2) - ((3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) - (7 \times 8))) + 9))$
18259 := $(1 - ((2 \times -3) + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (78 \times 9))))$
18260 := $((1 - 23) \times ((4 \times -5) - (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9))))$
18261 := $((1 + (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) - 6)))) \times ((7 - 8) \times 9))$
18262 := $((12^3 - 4) \times (5 + 6) + (78 \times -9))$
18263 := $(1 \times (2 + (((34 + 5) \times (6 \times 78)) + 9)))$
18264 := $((1 + 23) \times -(4 + ((5 - (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9)))$
18265 := $(1 - (2 \times -3 \times (4 \times (5 + ((6 + 78) \times 9))))))$
18266 := $-1 + 2 + 3! \times 4^5 + (6! - 7) \times (8 + 9)$
18267 := $(12 - ((3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) - (7 \times 8))) + 9))$

18227 := $(9 - (8 - (((76 - 5) + (4^3))^2) + 1)))$
18228 := $(9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 65)) + 4) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1))$
18229 := $((9 + (((8 \times (7 \times 65)) + 4) \times (3 + 2))) \times 1)$
18230 := $(9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 65)) + 4) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1))$
18231 := $(9 + (8 + (7 \times (((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2) + 1))))$
18232 := $((((-9 \times 87) - 65) \times -43) / -(2 \times -1))$
18233 := $(9 - (((87 - 6) \times -5 \times (43 + 2))) + 1)$
18234 := $(9 \times - (8 - ((7 - (6 \times (5 \times 4))) \times (3 - 21))))$
18235 := $(98 + (7 \times (((6^5) / (4 - (3 - 2)))) - 1))$
18236 := $(9 - (((8 \times (7 \times (654 - 3)))) / -2) + 1)$
18237 := $((9 - (8 \times (765 - 4))) \times (3 \times -(2 - 1)))$
18238 := $(98 - (((7 \times (6^5)) - (4 \times 3)) / -(2 + 1)))$
18239 := $((((-9 + (8 \times (765 - 4))) \times -3) - 2) \times -1)$
18240 := $((9 + 87) - (((6^5) \times (4 + 3)) / -(2 + 1)))$
18241 := $(98 - (((7 \times (6^5)) / -(4 - (3 - 2))) + 1))$
18242 := $(9 - ((8 + (((76 - 5) + (4^3))^2)) \times -1))$
18243 := $(98 - (((7 \times (6^5)) / -(4 - (3 - 2))) - 1))$
18244 := $(((9 - 8) - (7 \times ((6^5) + 43))) / -(2 + 1))$
18245 := $((((-9 \times -(8 + (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times -((43 - 2) \times -1)))$
18246 := $(98 - (((7 \times (6^5)) + (4 \times 3)) / -(2 + 1)))$
18247 := $((-9 - 8) - ((765 - 4) \times -(3 + 21)))$
18248 := $(9 - (((8 \times (76 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))) / -2) + 1))$
18249 := $(98 - (7 \times -(((6^5) / (4 - (3 - 2)))) + 1))$
18250 := $(((9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -(((5 + 4)^3) + (2 - 1)))$
18251 := $(9 + (((87 \times (6 \times 5)) - 4) \times ((3 \times 2) + 1)))$
18252 := $((98 + 76) - 5) \times -(4 \times -(3^{2+1}))$
18253 := $((9 - ((8 \times ((765 - 4) \times 3)) - 2)) \times -1)$
18254 := $((((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) \times -(5 \times 43)) - 21)$
18255 := $((9 - (8 \times ((765 - 4) \times 3))) \times -(2 - 1))$
18256 := $((9 - 8) \times -(7 \times -(6 + (((54 - 3)^2) + 1))))$
18257 := $((9 + 8) - ((76 \times 5) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) - 1)))$
18258 := $((9 + (87 + 6)) \times -((5 \times -(4 + 32)) + 1))$
18259 := $(9 + (8 + (7 \times ((6 + ((54 - 3)^2)) - 1))))$
18260 := $((-9 \times 87) + (((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) - 1))$
18261 := $(9 + ((8 - (76 \times (5 + 4))) \times -(3^{2+1})))$
18262 := $(9 - (((8 \times 7) \times -(6 + (5 \times (4^3)))) + (2 + 1)))$
18263 := $((9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (6 + (5 \times (4^3)))) + (2 \times -1))$
18264 := $(98 + ((7 \times -(6 - ((54 - 3)^2))) + 1))$
18265 := $((9 + ((8 \times (7 \times 65)) + 4)) \times -(3 + 2) \times -1)$
18266 := $((9 + (((8 \times 7) \times (6 + (5 \times (4^3)))) + 2)) - 1)$
18267 := $((9 + (((8 \times 7) \times (6 + (5 \times (4^3)))) + 2)) \times 1)$

$$\begin{aligned}
18268 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((3 \times (45 \times 67)) + 89))) \\
18269 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 \times (45 \times 67)) + 89))) \\
18270 &:= (((1 - 2) - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (((6 + 7) - 8) \times -9)) \\
18271 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 \times 8))) + 9))) \\
18272 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 \times 8))) + 9))) \\
18273 &:= ((1 - 2) \times ((3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) - (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
18274 &:= ((-1 + 23) + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times -(78 \times 9))) \\
18275 &:= (1 \times (23 - ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (78 \times 9)))) \\
18276 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) - (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
18277 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 + (((4^5) + (6 - (7 + 8))) \times 9)))) \\
18278 &:= ((1 - (23 + 4)) \times ((5 - 6) - (78 \times 9))) \\
18279 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) - 6)))) \times -((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
18280 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -((4 \times 567) + (8 + 9)))) \\
18281 &:= (1 - ((2^3) \times -((4 \times 567) + (8 + 9)))) \\
18282 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((3 - (((4^5) + ((6 - 7) \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
18283 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (3^4)) \times 5) + 6) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\
18284 &:= (1 + (((2 - (3^4)) \times 5) + 6) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\
18285 &:= (12 - ((3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) - (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
18286 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) + ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
18287 &:= (1 \times -((((2 + 3) \times 456) + 7) \times -8) + 9) \\
18288 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times -((4^5) - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
18289 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
18290 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
18291 &:= (1 + (2 - (((3^4) - (5 \times 67)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
18292 &:= ((1 - ((23 \times 45) + (6 \times 7))) \times -(8 + 9)) \\
18293 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
18294 &:= (1 + (2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
18295 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 + (((4^5) + ((6 - 7) \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
18296 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) \times 6))) + ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
18297 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 \times (4 - 5)) + (678 \times 9))) \\
18298 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times 678))) - 9) \\
18299 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times 678))) - 9)) \\
18300 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((3 - (((4^5) - (6 - (7 - 8))) \times 9)))) \\
18301 &:= (1 + (2 \times -((3 - (((4^5) - (6 - (7 - 8))) \times 9)))) \\
18302 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) + (7 \times -(8 + 9))) \\
18303 &:= (12 - (3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) - ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
18304 &:= ((1 + (23 \times (4 + 5))) \times (6 - (7 - 89))) \\
18305 &:= (1 \times -((((2 + 3) \times 456) + 7) \times -8) - 9) \\
18306 &:= (((1 + 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times -((7 + 8) - 9)) \\
18307 &:= (1 \times -(2 + (3 \times ((4 - 5) - (678 \times 9)))) \\
18308 &:= (1 - (2 + (3 \times ((4 - 5) - (678 \times 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
18268 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) \times (6 + (5 \times (4^3)))) + 2)) + 1) \\
18269 &:= ((-9 + ((87 \times (6 + (5^4))))/3) - 21) \\
18270 &:= (((9 + 87) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times ((3 + 2) \times -1)) \\
18271 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 \times -(6 \times (5 \times ((43 \times 2) + 1)))) \\
18272 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((765 - 4) \times 3)) + (2 - 1))) \\
18273 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 \times -(6 + (((54 - 3)^2) + 1)))) \\
18274 &:= (98 - ((76 - 5) \times -(4^{3+2-1}))) \\
18275 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (((5 + 4)^3) + 2) \times -1) \\
18276 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((765 - 4) \times 3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
18277 &:= ((9 + (87 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
18278 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -(6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) + (2 - 1))) \\
18279 &:= (9 \times ((8 \times (((76 + 54) - 3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
18280 &:= ((9 + ((87 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) + 2)) - 1) \\
18281 &:= ((9 + (87 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
18282 &:= ((9 + ((87 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) + 2)) + 1) \\
18283 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (((65 \times (4 \times 3))/ -2) + 1)) \\
18284 &:= (((-9 \times -(87 + ((6^5)/4))) + 3) - (2 \times -1)) \\
18285 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -((5 \times -4) - (32 + 1))) \\
18286 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) \times -(6 + (5 \times (4^3)))) - 21)) \\
18287 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times ((6 \times 54) + 3)) - 2))) \times -1) \\
18288 &:= (((9 - 8) + (76 \times 5)) \times (((4 + 3)^2) - 1)) \\
18289 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times 654)) \times -((3 + 2) - 1))) \\
18290 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(((765 - 4) \times 3) + 2)) - 1)) \\
18291 &:= ((98 - 7) \times ((6 \times -(5 \times 4)) + 321)) \\
18292 &:= ((9 - (((87 \times (6 + (5^4))))/3) + 2)) \times -1) \\
18293 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times -(6 - ((5 \times (4 + 3))^2))) - 1)) \\
18294 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 \times 5))) \times -((4 \times 3)/ - (2 \times 1))) \\
18295 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times -(6 - ((5 \times (4 + 3))^2))) + 1)) \\
18296 &:= ((9 - (87 \times (6 + (5^4))))/ (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
18297 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times (6 + (5^4))) + 3))/ - (2 + 1)) \\
18298 &:= (98 - (7 \times -(65 \times (43 - (2 + 1)))) \\
18299 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6^5) + (4^3))))/ (2 + 1)) \\
18300 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times 5) \times -((4^3) - (2 + 1)))) \\
18301 &:= (((9 + (87 \times (6 + (5^4)))) - 3)/ (2 + 1)) \\
18302 &:= ((9 + (87 \times (6 + (5^4))))/ - (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
18303 &:= ((9 + ((87 \times (6 + (5^4))) + 3))/ (2 + 1)) \\
18304 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -(((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2)) + 1)) \\
18305 &:= (98 - (7 \times -(((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2 \times 1))) \\
18306 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -(((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
18307 &:= (9 - (((87 \times (6 + (5^4))) - 3)/ - (2 + 1))) \\
18308 &:= (9 - (((8 \times ((7 \times 654) - 3))/ - 2) + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
18309 &:= ((1+2) + (3 \times -((4-5) \times (678 \times 9)))) & 18309 &:= ((9 + (((87 \times (6 + (5^4))))/3) + 2)) - 1 \\
18310 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) + ((7+8) \times -9)) & 18310 &:= ((9 + (((87 \times (6 + (5^4))))/3) + 2)) \times 1 \\
18311 &:= (1 \times -(23 + ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 89))) & 18311 &:= ((9 + (((87 \times (6 + (5^4))))/3) + 2)) + 1 \\
18312 &:= (1 \times ((2 - (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times -((7+8) - 9))) & 18312 &:= (98 - (7 \times -(((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2) + 1))) \\
18313 &:= (1 + ((2 - (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times -((7+8) - 9))) & 18313 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times (7 + 65)) - 4) \times 32)) \times 1 \\
18314 &:= ((-1 + (((2^3) \times 4) - 5) \times 678) + 9) & 18314 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 + 65)) - 4) \times -32) - 1)) \\
18315 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3 - (4^5))) + 6)) \times ((7-8) \times 9)) & 18315 &:= (((98 - 7) + ((6^5)/4)) \times -(3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
18316 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + (5^6)) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9)) & 18316 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 654)) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
18317 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 \times ((4 + 5) \times 678)) + 9))) & 18317 &:= (-9 + (((8 - (7 \times 65)) \times -(43 - 2)) - 1)) \\
18318 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -3 + (((4^5) - 6) \times ((7-8) \times 9)))) & 18318 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + 4)) \times -(3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
18319 &:= (1 + (2 \times -3 + (((4^5) - 6) \times ((7-8) \times 9)))) & 18319 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times ((6 \times 54) + 3))) + (2 \times 1))) \\
18320 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - 7)) - 89))) & 18320 &:= (9 + (((8 - (765 \times 4)) \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
18321 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - 7)) - 89))) & 18321 &:= ((9 + (8 + 76)) \times (5 + ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
18322 &:= (1 - (((234 - (5 - 6)) \times -78) + 9)) & 18322 &:= (98 + (((76 - 5) + (4^3))^2) - 1)) \\
18323 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) - 7)) + 89)) & 18323 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times ((6 \times 54) + 3))) - (2 \times 1))) \\
18324 &:= (((12^3) \times -((4^5) - 6)) / - (7 + 89)) & 18324 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - 6) \times -(5 - ((4^{3+2}) - 1))) \\
18325 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times -6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 18325 &:= (9 + (((87 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
18326 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) + (7 \times -(8 + 9))) & 18326 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(7 \times ((6 + 5) \times ((4 + 3) - 21)))) \\
18327 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 \times -(((4^5) - 6) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)))) & 18327 &:= (987 + (6 + (54 \times 321))) \\
18328 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -((4 \times (567 + 8)) - 9))) & 18328 &:= (((-98 \times -(7 + ((6 + 54) \times 3))) + 2) \times 1) \\
18329 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) + ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 89))) & 18329 &:= (9 - (((87 \times (6 + (5^4))) / -3) - 21)) \\
18330 &:= (((1 - 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times -((7 + 8) - 9)) & 18330 &:= ((9 - 87) \times (((6 + (5 \times 4)) \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
18331 &:= (1 + ((2 - ((3 + 4) \times 56)) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) & 18331 &:= (((-9 - (87 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -(4 + 3)) - 2) \times 1) \\
18332 &:= (1 + (23 \times -(4 - ((5 + (6 + 78)) \times 9)))) & 18332 &:= (9 - (((8 \times ((7 \times 654) + 3)) / -2) + 1)) \\
18333 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3 - (4^5))) + 6)) \times -((7 - 8) \times 9)) & 18333 &:= ((9 + (87 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -((4 + 3) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
18334 &:= ((1 - (((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6) + 78)) - 9) & 18334 &:= ((98 - ((7 + (6 + 5)) \times (4^{3+2}))) \times -1) \\
18335 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) \times 6))) - 7) - 89 & 18335 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 \times 65)) \times -(43 - 2)) - 1)) \\
18336 &:= (12 - (3 \times -(((4^5) - 6) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)))) & 18336 &:= ((9 + 87) \times -((6 \times -((5 - 4) \times 32)) + 1)) \\
18337 &:= ((((((12^3)/4) + 5) \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) - 9) & 18337 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 \times 65)) \times -(43 - 2)) + 1)) \\
18338 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - 7))) + (8 \times -9)) & 18338 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -((7 + 6) - ((5 + 43)^2))) + 1)) \\
18339 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) + (7 - 89)) & 18339 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 765) - 4) \times 3)) \times -(2 - 1)) \\
18340 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -3) + ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 89))) & 18340 &:= ((98 + (7 \times (6^{5-4+3}))) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
18341 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times -6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 18341 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 765) - 4) \times 3) + 2)) \times -1) \\
18342 &:= (1 + (((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times -6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 18342 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - 6) \times ((5 - (4^{3+2})) \times -1)) \\
18343 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 \times ((4^5) \times 6)) - (78 + 9)))) & 18343 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((7 + 6) \times ((5 \times 4) + (3 \times 21)))) \\
18344 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) \times 6))) - 78) - 9 & 18344 &:= ((9 - ((87 + (6^5)) \times (4 + 3))) / - (2 + 1)) \\
18345 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times -6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9))) & 18345 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 765) + 4)) \times (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
18346 &:= ((1 - 23) + (4 \times -(56 \times (7 - 89)))) & 18346 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -(6 + ((54 - 3)^2))) + 1)) \\
18347 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3 \times ((4^5) \times 6))) - (78 + 9))) & 18347 &:= (98 - (7 \times -(6 + ((54 - 3)^2 \times 1)))) \\
18348 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times -6) + (7 - (8 + 9)))) & 18348 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -(6 + ((54 - 3)^2))) - 1)) \\
18349 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3 \times ((4^5) \times 6)) + 7)) - 89) & 18349 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 \times 765) - 4)) / -3) + 2) - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
18350 &:= (((12^3) + 4) \times (5 + 6)) + (78 \times -9)) \\
18351 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 \times (((4^{5+6-7}) \times 8) - 9))) \\
18352 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) \times 6))) - 7) + (8 \times -9)) \\
18353 &:= ((1 - 2) \times ((3 \times -((4^5) \times 6)) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
18354 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times -6) - (7 - (8 - 9)))) \\
18355 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
18356 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) - ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
18357 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times -6) + (78 + 9))) \\
18358 &:= (1 - (((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times -6) + (78 + 9))) \\
18359 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((34 \times 5) - 6) \times (7 \times 8))) + 9)) \\
18360 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (((6 + 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\
18361 &:= (((12^3) / -4) + 5) \times ((6 \times -7) + (8 - 9)) \\
18362 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) \times 6))) - 78) + 9 \\
18363 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((3 \times ((4^5) \times 6)) - (78 - 9))) \\
18364 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + 7)) - 89)) \\
18365 &:= (12 - ((3 \times -((4^5) \times 6)) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
18366 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) - (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
18367 &:= ((1 - 2) \times ((3 \times -((4^5) \times 6)) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
18368 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 + (4 \times (56 \times (7 - 89)))))) \\
18369 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 + ((4^5) \times 6)) - (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
18370 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 \times ((4^5) \times 6)) + 7)) + (8 \times -9)) \\
18371 &:= ((((((12^3) / 4) + 5) \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) + 9) \\
18372 &:= (12 \times -((3 - 4) - (5 \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))) \\
18373 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
18374 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
18375 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times -6) + (78 - 9))) \\
18376 &:= (1 \times -((2 - ((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 - (7 + (8 + 9)))))) \\
18377 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 + 8)))) - 9) \\
18378 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times -((7 + 8) - 9))) \\
18379 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times -6) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
18380 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) - ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
18381 &:= ((1 - 2) \times ((3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) + 7)) + (8 \times 9))) \\
18382 &:= (((1 + (((2 + 3) \times 4) \times (5^6))) - 7) / (8 + 9)) \\
18383 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + 7))) - (8 \times 9))) \\
18384 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + 7))) - (8 \times 9))) \\
18385 &:= (1 + ((2 - ((3 \times (4^5)) - 6)) \times -((7 + 8) - 9))) \\
18386 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(((34 \times 5) - 6) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) \\
18387 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) - 6))) \times -((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
18388 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times 3^4)) + (((5 \times (6 - 7)) + 8)^9)) \\
18389 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3^4) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 + 9)))))) \\
18390 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((3 \times (4 - ((5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))))) \\
18350 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
18351 &:= (9 \times -((8 \times -7) - ((654 \times 3) + 21))) \\
18352 &:= (9 + (((8 - (765 \times (4 \times 3))) \times -2) - 1)) \\
18353 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times 654)) \times -((3 + 2) - 1))) \\
18354 &:= (98 - (7 \times -((6 + (((54 - 3)^2) + 1)))) \\
18355 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 765) - 4) \times 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
18356 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 765) - 4) \times 3) - (2 - 1)) \\
18357 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -((43 \times -2) - 1)) \\
18358 &:= (((9 - 8) - (765 \times (4 \times 3))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
18359 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 765) - 4) \times 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
18360 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) \times -((4 \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
18361 &:= ((9 + ((87 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4)) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
18362 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 + (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) - 2)) + 1)) \\
18363 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 765) + 4) \times 3)) \times -((2 - 1)) \\
18364 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 432)) - 1)))) \\
18365 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -((6 + (5 \times (43 - 2)))) + 1)) \\
18366 &:= (((9 - 8) + (765 \times 4)) \times -((3 \times -((2 \times 1))) \\
18367 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -((6 + (5 \times (43 - 2)))) - 1)) \\
18368 &:= (98 - (7 \times -((6 \times (5 \times ((43 \times 2) + 1)))))) \\
18369 &:= (9 \times (((8 \times 765) / (4 - (3 - 2))) + 1)) \\
18370 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times (65 \times 4))) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\
18371 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 432)))) \times -1)) \\
18372 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 765) + (4 - 3)) \times -((2 + 1))) \\
18373 &:= ((((-9 - ((8 \times 765) - 4)) \times -3) - 2) \times 1) \\
18374 &:= ((((-9 - ((8 \times 765) - 4)) \times -3) - 2) + 1) \\
18375 &:= ((98 + 7) \times ((6 \times (((5 + 4) \times 3) + 2)) + 1)) \\
18376 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -((6 - (((5 + 43)^2) - 1))) \\
18377 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (((65 \times (4 \times 3)) / -2) - 1)) \\
18378 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((76 \times 5) + 4))) \times (3 \times -((2 \times 1))) \\
18379 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 765) + 4) \times 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
18380 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times (((6 + 5) - (43^2)) \times -1)) \\
18381 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times ((4 \times -3) + (2 - 1))) \\
18382 &:= (((9 + 8) - (((7^6) \times 5) - 4)) / (32 \times -1)) \\
18383 &:= ((9 - (87 \times (6 + ((5^4) + 3)))) / -((2 + 1)) \\
18384 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times ((6 - ((5 + 43)^2)) \times -1)) \\
18385 &:= (9 - ((8 + (765 \times (4 \times 3))) \times -((2 \times 1))) \\
18386 &:= (9 - (((8 + (765 \times (4 \times 3))) \times -2) - 1)) \\
18387 &:= ((9 + (8 \times 765)) \times -((4 - 3) \times -((2 + 1))) \\
18388 &:= (-9 - ((876 \times -((5 \times 4) + (3 - 2))) - 1)) \\
18389 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 + (6 \times 5)))) \times (4^3)) + 21) \\
18390 &:= (((98 + 7) - ((6^5) / 4)) \times -((3^2) + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 18391 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(3 \times (4 - ((5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))))) & 18391 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 54)) + 32))) \times -1) \\ 18392 &:= ((1 - 23) \times (4 \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 - 9)))) & 18392 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(6 - (((5 + 43)^2) + 1))) \\ 18393 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - 7))) - 8) - 9 & 18393 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((765 + 4) - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 18394 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - 7)) - (8 + 9))) & 18394 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(7 - (((6 \times 5) + 4) \times 32) + 1))) \\ 18395 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 + 8)))) + 9) & 18395 &:= (9 - ((87 \times (6 + ((5^4) + 3)))/ - (2 + 1))) \\ 18396 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times -6) + ((7 + 8) - 9))) & 18396 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times ((4 + 32) \times -1)) \\ 18397 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times -6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9))) & 18397 &:= (9 - (8 - (7 \times (6 \times (5 + (432 + 1)))))) \\ 18398 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & 18398 &:= (((-9 - ((8 \times 765) + 4)) \times -3) - 2) + 1) \\ 18399 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3 \times (4^5)) - 6) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)))) & 18399 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times 765) + 4)) \times -(3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\ 18400 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 - (8 + 9))))) & 18400 &:= (((-9 - ((8 \times 765) + 4)) \times -3) + 2) - 1) \\ 18401 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 - (8 + 9))))) & 18401 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 54)) + (32 - 1)))) \\ 18402 &:= (((1 - 2) - ((3 \times (4^5)) - 6)) \times -((7 + 8) - 9)) & 18402 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (543 - 2))) - 1) \\ 18403 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((34 \times (5 + (67 \times 8))) + 9)) & 18403 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (543 - 2))) \times 1) \\ 18404 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 - (8 + 9))))) & 18404 &:= (9 + (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times -(543 - 2)) + 1)) \\ 18405 &:= (1 + (2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 - (8 + 9))))) & 18405 &:= (9 \times -(((87 + 6) \times -(54 - 32)) + 1)) \\ 18406 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 \times ((4^5) \times 6)) - (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 18406 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 \times (654 + 3)))/ - 2) - 1)) \\ 18407 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) \times 6))) - 7) - (8 + 9) & 18407 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (765 \times 4)))/3) \times -2) - 1) \\ 18408 &:= (((1 + 2) - (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - 7))) \times (8 - 9)) & 18408 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times 765) + (4 + 3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 18409 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - 7))) + (8 - 9)) & 18409 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 54)) + 32))) \times 1) \\ 18410 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - 7))) \times -(8 - 9)) & 18410 &:= (((9 + (87 \times 6)) - 5) \times -(4 \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\ 18411 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - 7))) - 8) + 9 & 18411 &:= (987 - (((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3))^2) \times -1)) \\ 18412 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) + ((7 - 8) \times 9)) & 18412 &:= ((987 + (((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3))^2)) + 1) \\ 18413 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6) - (7 \times (8 - 9)))) & 18413 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 + (432 + 1)))))) \\ 18414 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) - (7 \times -(8 - 9))) & 18414 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + (6 + 5)) \times -((4^{3+2}) - 1))) \\ 18415 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) - 7)) + (8 - 9))) & 18415 &:= (9 - (8 - ((7 + (6 + 5)) \times ((4^{3+2}) - 1)))) \\ 18416 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - ((7 + 8) - 9)))) & 18416 &:= (9 - (((8 + (765 \times 4)) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\ 18417 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 + ((4^5) \times 6)) - (7 - (8 - 9)))) & 18417 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (765 \times 4)) \times (3 \times 2))) \times 1) \\ 18418 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 - 8))) - 9))) & 18418 &:= (9 - (((8 + (765 \times 4)) \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\ 18419 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 - 8))) - 9))) & 18419 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (7 \times -((6 \times (5 + 432)) - 1))) \\ 18420 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 + (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 \times (8 - 9)))) & 18420 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (765 + 4)) - 3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 18421 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (3 \times (4^5) \times 6))) \times (7 - 8)) - 9) & 18421 &:= (((-98 \times -(((7 \times 6) + 5) \times 4)) - 3) \times (2 - 1)) \\ 18422 &:= (1 + (((2 - (3 \times (4^5) \times 6))) \times (7 - 8)) - 9) & 18422 &:= (((-98 \times -(((7 \times 6) + 5) \times 4)) - 3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 18423 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) \times 6))) - 7) + (8 - 9) & 18423 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times -((5 + 4) \times (32 + 1)))) \\ 18424 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) \times 6))) - 7) \times -(8 - 9) & 18424 &:= ((98 - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times -((4^3) + 2)) + 1)) \\ 18425 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) \times 6))) - 7) - (8 - 9) & 18425 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((7 - 6) - (((5 + 43)^2) - 1)))) \\ 18426 &:= (((1 - 2) - ((3 \times ((4^5) \times 6)) - 7)) \times (8 - 9)) & 18426 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (765 \times 4)) \times 3)) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\ 18427 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 \times ((4^5) \times 6)) + (7 \times (8 - 9)))) & 18427 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - ((7 \times -(6 \times (5 + 432))) - 1)) \\ 18428 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) + (7 \times -(8 - 9))) & 18428 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(765 - (43^2 \times 1))) \\ 18429 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (4^5))) \times -((6 \times (7 - 8)) + 9)) & 18429 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (765 + 4))) \times (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\ 18430 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) - ((7 - 8) \times 9)) & 18430 &:= ((9 - ((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times 4)) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\ 18431 &:= (1 + (((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times -6) - (7 - (8 + 9)))) & 18431 &:= (9 + (8 + ((7 + (6 + 5)) \times ((4^{3+2}) - 1)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 18432 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times -((4^5) \times 6)) / ((7-8) \times 9)) \\
 18433 &:= (1 \times -((2345 - (6 \times 7)) \times -8) - 9)) \\
 18434 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (3 \times (4^5)))) \times -6) - (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\
 18435 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (4^5))) \times ((6 \times (7 - 8)) + 9)) \\
 18436 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) + ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
 18437 &:= (1 \times - (2 - ((3 \times ((4^5) \times 6)) - (7 \times (8 - 9)))))) \\
 18438 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) - (7 \times -(8 - 9))) \\
 18439 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3 \times ((4^5) \times 6)) + 7)) - (8 - 9)) \\
 18440 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) \times 6))) - ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
 18441 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 \times ((4^5) \times 6)) + 7)) + (8 - 9)) \\
 18442 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 \times ((4^5) \times 6)) + 7)) \times -(8 - 9)) \\
 18443 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 \times ((4^5) \times 6)) + 7)) - (8 - 9)) \\
 18444 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) \times 6))) - ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
 18445 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) \times 6))) - 7) + (8 + 9)) \\
 18446 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + 8)) / -9)) \\
 18447 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) - (7 - 8))) - 9)) \\
 18448 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(3 - ((4^5) \times (6 - (7 + 8)))))) - 9)) \\
 18449 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + ((7 + 8) - 9)))))) \\
 18450 &:= (((1 + 2) - (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + 7))) \times (8 - 9)) \\
 18451 &:= (1 \times (((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6) - (7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\
 18452 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) + (7 \times -(8 - 9))) \\
 18453 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + 7))) - (8 - 9)) \\
 18454 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) - ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
 18455 &:= (1 \times -((2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + 7))) \times (8 - 9))) \\
 18456 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + 7))) \times (8 - 9))) \\
 18457 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) + 7)) + (8 - 9))) \\
 18458 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 + ((4^{5+6-7}) \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
 18459 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 \times ((4^5) \times 6)) + 7)) + (8 + 9)) \\
 18460 &:= (1 \times - (2 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 - (8 + 9)))))) \\
 18461 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 + ((4^{5+6-7}) \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
 18462 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3 + ((4^{5+6-7}) \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
 18463 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - 8) - 9)) \\
 18464 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 - (8 + 9)))))) \\
 18465 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times -6) - (7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\
 18466 &:= (1 \times - (2 - (((3 \times (4^5)) + 6) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)))) \\
 18467 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times -6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 18468 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
 18469 &:= ((1 + (((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6) + (7 + 8))) + 9) \\
 18470 &:= ((1 - 2) \times ((3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) + 7)) - (8 + 9))) \\
 18471 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 \times (4^5)) + 6) \times -((7 + 8) - 9))) \\
 18472 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -((4 \times (567 + 8)) + 9))) \\
 18432 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 + (6 + 5)) \times -(4^{3+2})) + 1)) \\
 18433 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + (6 + 5)) \times -(4^{3+2})) - 1)) \\
 18434 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 + (6 + 5)) \times -(4^{3+2})) - 1)) \\
 18435 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 + 6)) \times (5 - (4^3)))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 18436 &:= (-9 - ((87 \times -((6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3))) + 2)) - 1)) \\
 18437 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times -(543 - (2 - 1)))) \\
 18438 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (765 + 4)) + 3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 18439 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((765 + 4) \times -(3 + 21))) \\
 18440 &:= ((9 + ((8 - 7)^6)) \times ((5 - (43^2)) \times -1)) \\
 18441 &:= (((98 + 7) + ((6^5)/4)) \times -(3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
 18442 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 6) + 54) \times -32) - 1)) \\
 18443 &:= (((-9 \times -(87 + (654 \times 3))) + 2) \times 1) \\
 18444 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times -(5 + ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 18445 &:= (98 - (7 \times -((6 \times (5 + 432)) - 1))) \\
 18446 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times -((765 + 4) \times 3)) + (2 - 1))) \\
 18447 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times -(43 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
 18448 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 + (6 + 5)) \times -(4^{3+2})) + 1)) \\
 18449 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 + 65) \times -(4^{3+2-1}))) \\
 18450 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + (6 + 5)) \times -((4^{3+2}) + 1))) \\
 18451 &:= (9 - (8 - ((7 + (6 + 5)) \times ((4^{3+2}) + 1)))) \\
 18452 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -((6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3))) + 2)) + 1)) \\
 18453 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -(6 \times (5 + 432))) - 1)) \\
 18454 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 6) + 5) \times -((4 + 32) - 1))) \\
 18455 &:= (((9 + ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times 543)) - 2) \times -1) \\
 18456 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (765 + 4)) - 3) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
 18457 &:= (9 + (8 \times (((765 + 4) \times 3) - (2 - 1)))) \\
 18458 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times -(6 \times (5 \times (43 - 2)))) + 1)) \\
 18459 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times -(6 \times (5 \times ((43 - 2) \times 1)))))) \\
 18460 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times -(6 \times (5 \times (43 - 2)))) - 1)) \\
 18461 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 + 2))) \times -1) \\
 18462 &:= (((9 + 8) + (765 \times 4)) \times -(3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
 18463 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((765 + 4) \times 3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
 18464 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((765 + 4) \times 3)) + (2 - 1))) \\
 18465 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((765 + 4) \times 3))) \times (2 - 1)) \\
 18466 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times ((765 + 4) \times 3)) + 2)) - 1) \\
 18467 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 + (6 + 5)) \times -((4^{3+2}) + 1))) \\
 18468 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((76 \times (5 + 4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
 18469 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((76 \times (5 + 4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
 18470 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 - 65) \times 4))) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
 18471 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 \times -(5 + (4^3))) + 21)) \\
 18472 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times ((6 + ((5 + 43)^2)) - 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
18473 &:= (((1+2) + ((3 \times ((4^5) \times 6) + 7)) + 8)) + 9) \\
18474 &:= (((1-2) - ((3 \times (4^5)) + 6)) \times -((7+8) - 9)) \\
18475 &:= (1 \times -((2+3) \times -(((456+7) \times 8) - 9))) \\
18476 &:= (1 - ((2+3) \times -(((456+7) \times 8) - 9))) \\
18477 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) + 6)))) \times ((7-8) \times 9)) \\
18478 &:= (((1-2) + (3 \times ((4^5) \times 6))) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
18479 &:= (((-1+23) \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) + (8-9)) \\
18480 &:= (1 \times -((2 + ((3 \times (4^5)) + 6)) \times -((7+8) - 9))) \\
18481 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 \times ((4^5) \times 6)) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
18482 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3 \times ((4^5) \times 6)) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
18483 &:= ((1-2) \times ((3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) - 7)) - (8 \times 9))) \\
18484 &:= (1 \times -((2 - ((34+5) \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
18485 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times -6) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
18486 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) + ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
18487 &:= (1 \times ((2 - (3 \times 45)) \times -((67 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
18488 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((34+5) \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
18489 &:= (1 + (2 + ((34+5) \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
18490 &:= (1 + (((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times -6) + (78 - 9))) \\
18491 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times -6) - ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
18492 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
18493 &:= (1 \times -((2 - (((345 \times 6) - (7 + 8)) \times 9))) \\
18494 &:= (1 \times -((2 + ((3 - ((4^5) + 67)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
18495 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) + 6)))) \times -((7-8) \times 9)) \\
18496 &:= (((1-2) + (3 \times ((4^5) \times 6))) - 7) - (8 \times -9)) \\
18497 &:= ((1-2) \times ((3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6)) + (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
18498 &:= (1 \times (2 - ((3 - ((4^5) + 67)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
18499 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times -6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
18500 &:= (1 + (((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times -6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
18501 &:= ((1-2) \times ((3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6)) - (78 - 9))) \\
18502 &:= ((1-23) \times -((4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) - (8 - 9))) \\
18503 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 \times ((4^5) \times 6)) + (78 - 9)))) \\
18504 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3 \times ((4^5) \times 6)) + (78 - 9)))) \\
18505 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3 - ((4^5) \times 6))) - 7) + 89) \\
18506 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 + (8 + 9)))))) \\
18507 &:= ((1+2) \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times -6) + (7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\
18508 &:= (1 + (((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times -6) + (78 + 9))) \\
18509 &:= (1 \times (((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
18510 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) + ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
18511 &:= (-1 \times (((2+3) \times -(((456+7) \times 8)) + 9)) \\
18512 &:= (12 - ((3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) - 7)) - 89)) \\
18513 &:= ((1+2) \times -(((3^4) \times 5) - (6 \times 7)) \times -((8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
18473 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 + ((5 \times (4 + 3))^2)))) - 1) \\
18474 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 + ((5 \times (4 + 3))^2)))) \times 1) \\
18475 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times -((6 + ((5 \times (4 + 3))^2)))) - 1)) \\
18476 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times -((4 \times -((32 - 1)))) \\
18477 &:= (9 \times -(((87 - (6 \times 5)) \times -((4 + 32)) - 1)) \\
18478 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -((3 + 2)) - 1)) \\
18479 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
18480 &:= ((98 - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times -((4^3) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
18481 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((765 + 4) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
18482 &:= (987 - (((6^5)/4) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
18483 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (765 + 4))) \times -((3 \times -((2 - 1)))) \\
18484 &:= (987 - (((6^5)/4) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
18485 &:= (9 + (8 + ((76 \times (5 + 4)) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
18486 &:= ((9 - 87) \times (6 - ((5 + 4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
18487 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times -((7 - 6) - (54/3)))^2)) \times -1) \\
18488 &:= (((9 + 8) - ((7 \times -((6 - (5 + 4))^3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
18489 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times ((54 + 3) - 2)))) \times 1) \\
18490 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 \times (6 \times ((54 + 3) - 2)))) - 1)) \\
18491 &:= (((-9 \times (87 \times 6)) - 5) \times -4) - 321) \\
18492 &:= ((9 - (8 - (7 - 6))) \times -((5 \times -((43^2) - 1)) \\
18493 &:= 98 + 765 \times 4! + 3!^2 - 1 \\
18494 &:= (98 - (7 \times -((6 \times (5 + (432 + 1)))))) \\
18495 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 + 65) + (4^3))^2 - 1)) \\
18496 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 + 65) + (4^3))^2 - 1)) \\
18497 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 + 65) + (4^3))^2) \times -1) \\
18498 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((7 + 65) + (4^3))^2 + 1)) \\
18499 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 + (6 + 5))) \times (43^2))) \times 1) \\
18500 &:= ((9 - (8 - (7 - 6))) \times -((5 \times -((43^2) + 1))) \\
18501 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (765 + (4 + 3)))) \times -((2 + 1)) \\
18502 &:= ((9876 - (5^4)) \times (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
18503 &:= ((-98 \times 7) + ((6 - (5^4)) \times -((32 - 1)))) \\
18504 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - 6) \times ((5 + (4^{3+2})) - 1)) \\
18505 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times -((543 + 2) - 1))) \\
18506 &:= (9 + (((8 \times -((7 - 6) - (54/3)))^2) + 1)) \\
18507 &:= (((9 + (8 \times 76)) - (5 \times 4)) \times (32 - 1)) \\
18508 &:= ((9876 - ((5^4) - 3)) \times -((2 \times -1)) \\
18509 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 + (6 + 5))) \times -((43^2) + 1))) \\
18510 &:= ((9 - ((87 + 6) \times (5 \times 4))) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
18511 &:= (-9 - (((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times 4) \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
18512 &:= (98 - ((7 + (6 + 5)) \times -((4^{3+2}) - 1))) \\
18513 &:= (((98 + 7) - 6) \times -((5 - ((4^3) \times (2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 18514 &:= (((1+2) + ((3 \times ((4^5) \times 6)) + 7)) - (8 \times -9)) & 18514 &:= (9 - (((8 - ((7 \times -(6 - (5 + 4)))^3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\
 18515 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times (5 - (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 18515 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times -((4 \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\
 18516 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times -6) + (7 - (8 + 9)))) & 18516 &:= (9 + (((8 - ((7 \times -(6 - (5 + 4)))^3)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
 18517 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 \times ((4^5) \times 6)) + (78 + 9)))) & 18517 &:= (9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 + 5) + 4! \times (-3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\
 18518 &:= (1 \times -((2 + ((3 + 4) \times 56)) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) & 18518 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (6 - ((5 \times 4)^{3-2+1}))) \\
 18519 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times -6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9))) & 18519 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (76 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)))) - 21) \\
 18520 &:= (((((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6) - 7) + 89) & 18520 &:= (((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -(6 - (5 + 4)))^3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
 18521 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 \times ((4^5) \times 6)) + (78 + 9)))) & 18521 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times -(6 - (5 + 4)))^3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
 18522 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times -(7 + 8)) - 9) & 18522 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 \times -(6 - (5 + 4)))^3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
 18523 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times -6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 18523 &:= (9 + ((8 - (((7 \times -(6 - (5 + 4)))^3) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
 18524 &:= (1 - (((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times -6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 18524 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 \times -(6 - (5 + 4)))^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
 18525 &:= ((1 - 2) \times ((3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) + 7)) - (8 \times 9))) & 18525 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 765)) - (4^3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 18526 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 \times ((4^5) \times 6)) + (7 + 89)))) & 18526 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times -((7 + 6) + ((5 + 43)^2)))) + 1)) \\
 18527 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + 7)) + (8 \times 9)))) & 18527 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) + ((5 + 43)^2)))) \times -1) \\
 18528 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + 7)) + (8 \times 9)))) & 18528 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 76) - (5 \times 4))) \times (32 \times -1)) \\
 18529 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^4))) - (5 \times -(6 \times (7 \times 89)))) & 18529 &:= ((9 - ((8 + ((7 \times -(6 - (5 + 4)))^3)) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
 18530 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - 3) + ((4^5) + 67)) \times -(8 + 9))) & 18530 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 + 6))^{(5+4)/3}) \times -2) + 1)) \\
 18531 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)))) & 18531 &:= (98 - (((7 + (6 + 5)) \times -(4^{3+2})) - 1)) \\
 18532 &:= (((1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times -(5 + ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) & 18532 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 + 6))^{(5+4)/3}) \times -2) - 1)) \\
 18533 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (((4^5) \times 6) + 7))) + 89) & 18533 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times -(43 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
 18534 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)) & 18534 &:= (9 - ((87 - (6 \times 5)) \times -(4 + 321))) \\
 18535 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 \times (4 - (5 \times (6 - (7 \times 89))))))) & 18535 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})) \\
 18536 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4 + 5^6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 18536 &:= ((98 - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times -((4^3) + 2)) - 1)) \\
 18537 &:= (12 - ((3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) + 7)) - (8 \times 9))) & 18537 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((765 + (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 18538 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)))) & 18538 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 \times -(6 - (5 + 4)))^3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
 18539 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)))) & 18539 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 \times -(6 - (5 + 4)))^3) \times -2 \times 1)) \\
 18540 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) - (7 \times -(8 + 9))) & 18540 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 \times -(6 - (5 + 4)))^3) \times -2) - 1)) \\
 18541 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -3) + (((4^5) + 67) \times (8 + 9)))) & 18541 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 + (76 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)))) + 2) - 1) \\
 18542 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -3) + (((4^5) + 67) \times (8 + 9)))) & 18542 &:= ((987 + ((6 + (5 \times 4))^3)) - 21) \\
 18543 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 \times -(((4^5) + 6) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)))) & 18543 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 765) \times (4 \times (3 \times 2)))) \times -1) \\
 18544 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (3 - (((4^5) + 67) \times (8 + 9)))) & 18544 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})) \\
 18545 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) + 7)) - 89)) & 18545 &:= ((9 - 8) - (76 \times -((5 \times ((4 + 3)^2)) - 1))) \\
 18546 &:= (((1 - 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times -((7 + 8) - 9)) & 18546 &:= ((9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4))) + 3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
 18547 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 \times (4 + ((5 \times 67) + 8) \times 9)))) & 18547 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((7 - ((6 + 543) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
 18548 &:= (((12^3) + 4) \times (5 + 6)) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9)) & 18548 &:= (9 - (((8 + ((7 \times -(6 - (5 + 4)))^3)) \times -2) - 1)) \\
 18549 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3 + (4^5))) + 6)) \times -((7 - 8) \times 9)) & 18549 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times -(6 \times ((5 \times (43 - 2)) + 1)))) \\
 18550 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) \times 6))) - (7 \times -(8 + 9))) & 18550 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 18551 &:= ((1 - 2) \times ((3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6)) - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 18551 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 + 765) \times 4))/3) \times -2) - 1) \\
 18552 &:= (1 \times -((2 + (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times -((7 + 8) - 9))) & 18552 &:= (9 - (((876 - 5) + (4 \times 3)) \times -21)) \\
 18553 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times -((7 + 8) - 9))) & 18553 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 + 6) + (((5 + 43)^2) + 1)))) \\
 18554 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) \times 6))) - (7 \times -(8 + 9))) & 18554 &:= (98 - ((765 + 4) \times -(3 + 21)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
18555 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6) - ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
18556 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) - ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
18557 &:= ((-1 + (2^3)) \times -(4 - (5 \times ((67 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
18558 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -(((4^5) + (6 - (7 - 8))) \times -9)) \\
18559 &:= (1 - (((2 \times ((34 \times (5 \times 6)) + 7)) + 8) \times -9)) \\
18560 &:= (-1 - (((2 - 3) + (45 \times 6)) \times -((78 - 9))) \\
18561 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - 3) + (45 \times 6)) \times -((78 - 9))) \\
18562 &:= (1 \times -((2^{3+4}) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 89)))) \\
18563 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times -6) - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
18564 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) - (7 \times -(8 + 9))) \\
18565 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -(((456 + 7) \times 8) + 9))) \\
18566 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) \times 6))) - ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
18567 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 - (((4^5) - (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
18568 &:= ((1 - 23) \times (4 \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 - 9)))) \\
18569 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 \times ((4^5) \times 6)) + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
18570 &:= ((1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - 5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\
18571 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
18572 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
18573 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
18574 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\
18575 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\
18576 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
18577 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4 + (56 \times (7 + 8)))) + 9) \\
18578 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\
18579 &:= (1 + (2 + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\
18580 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) - ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
18581 &:= ((-12 \times -((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times 67)) + 89) \\
18582 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) - ((6 - 7) \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
18583 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) - ((6 - 7) \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
18584 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times ((67 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
18585 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) + 6))) \times ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
18586 &:= (((-12 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times -6) - 7) + 89) \\
18587 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times ((67 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
18588 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) - (6 - (7 + 8))) \times 9))) \\
18589 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
18590 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
18591 &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times -((4 \times 5) - (6 \times (7 \times 89)))) \\
18592 &:= (1 \times ((2 - 34) \times -(5 + (6 \times (7 + 89)))) \\
18593 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -(4 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8)) - 9)) \\
18594 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((3 + ((4^5) + 6)) \times ((7 - 8) \times 9))) \\
18595 &:= (1 + (2 \times -((3 + ((4^5) + 6)) \times ((7 - 8) \times 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
18555 &:= ((9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4))) + 3) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
18556 &:= ((98 + (765 \times (4 \times 3))) \times - (2 \times -1)) \\
18557 &:= ((98 - (7 \times (65 \times (43 - 2)))) \times -1) \\
18558 &:= (((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4)))) - 3) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
18559 &:= (-98 + (((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times -32) + 1) \\
18560 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times (((6 - (5^4)) \times -3) - (2 - 1))) \\
18561 &:= ((9 + 8) - (76 \times -((5 \times ((4 + 3)^2)) - 1))) \\
18562 &:= ((987 + ((6 + (5 \times 4))^3)) - (2 - 1)) \\
18563 &:= (987 - (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
18564 &:= (9 + ((8 + 7) \times -(6 - (((5^4) - 3) \times 2) - 1))) \\
18565 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (((6 + 5) \times -(4 + 32)) + 1)) \\
18566 &:= ((987 + (((6 + (5 \times 4))^3) + 2)) + 1) \\
18567 &:= (9 \times -((8 \times -(7 \times 6)) - ((54 \times 32) - 1))) \\
18568 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 + 65)) + 4) \times -32) + 1) \\
18569 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 76)) \times ((5 - (4 + 32)) \times 1)) \\
18570 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times -(3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
18571 &:= (((9 - 8) - (76 \times 5)) \times (((4 + 3)^2) \times -1)) \\
18572 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4))) + 3) \times -2) - 1) \\
18573 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4))) + 3) \times 2)) \times 1) \\
18574 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4))) + 3) \times -2) + 1) \\
18575 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 43))) - 2) + 1) \\
18576 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
18577 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 43))) + 2) - 1) \\
18578 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - (((5^4) - 3) \times 2)))) - 1) \\
18579 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times -((4 \times -3) + (2 - 1))) \\
18580 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times (((6 - (5^4)) \times -3) + (2 - 1))) \\
18581 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 \times (6 - (54 \times 3))) - (2 - 1))) \\
18582 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4))) + 3)) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
18583 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times -32) - 1) \\
18584 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4))) - 3) \times -2) - 1) \\
18585 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 + (6 + 5)) \times ((4 \times 32) + 1))) \\
18586 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4))) - 3) \times -2) + 1) \\
18587 &:= ((((-98 \times (76 \times 5)) + (4^3)) / -2) - 1) \\
18588 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
18589 &:= ((((-98 \times (76 \times 5)) + (4^3)) / -2) + 1) \\
18590 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) - (2 \times 1))) \\
18591 &:= ((((-9 - 87) \times -65) - 43) \times (2 + 1)) \\
18592 &:= (((((-9 - 87) \times 6) - 5) \times (4^3)) / -2) \times 1) \\
18593 &:= (98 + (((7 + 65) + (4^3))^2) - 1) \\
18594 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4))) - 3)) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
18595 &:= (98 + (((7 + 65) + (4^3))^2) + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 18596 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 + ((4^5) + 67)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 18597 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 + ((4^5) + 67)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 18598 &:= ((-1 \times (23 \times 4)) - (5 \times -(6 \times (7 \times 89)))) \\
 18599 &:= (1 \times (((2^{3 \times 4 + 5}) - (6^7)) / -8) - 9) \\
 18600 &:= (1 + (((2^{3 \times 4 + 5}) - (6^7)) / -8) - 9) \\
 18601 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times -(6 + (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 18602 &:= (-12 + ((3 + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 - 89))) \\
 18603 &:= (12 - ((3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) + (7 \times 8))) + 9)) \\
 18604 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 - 4) + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times -89)) \\
 18605 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((34 + 5) \times ((6 \times 78) + 9)))) \\
 18606 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((3 \times ((4 - (56 \times 7)) \times 8)) + 9))) \\
 18607 &:= (1 \times (23 \times ((4 - 5) + (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
 18608 &:= (1 + (23 \times ((4 - 5) + (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
 18609 &:= (-12 - (((345 \times 6) + (7 - 8)) \times -9)) \\
 18610 &:= (12 - ((3 + ((4^5) + 67)) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
 18611 &:= ((1 + (2 + 34)) \times ((5 - 6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 18612 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 \times 8)))) + 9) \\
 18613 &:= (12 - (((3 - 4) + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times -89)) \\
 18614 &:= (((1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times ((5 \times -(6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9))) \\
 18615 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times -6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 18616 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 \times 6))) + ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
 18617 &:= (1 \times (((2^{3 \times 4 + 5}) - (6^7)) / -8) + 9) \\
 18618 &:= (1 + (((2^{3 \times 4 + 5}) - (6^7)) / -8) + 9) \\
 18619 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((345 \times 6) + (7 - 8)) \times 9))) \\
 18620 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) \times -(4 \times (5 - ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
 18621 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3^4) + (5 \times 6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9) \\
 18622 &:= ((1 + (23 \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))) - 9) \\
 18623 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((345 \times 6) + (7 - 8)) \times 9))) \\
 18624 &:= (((12^3) \times -(((4 + (5 + 6)) \times 7) - 8)) / -9) \\
 18625 &:= (1 \times -(2 + 3) - (45 \times (6 \times (78 - 9)))) \\
 18626 &:= ((1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 - (8 \times 9))))) \\
 18627 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 - (8 \times 9))))) \\
 18628 &:= (1 \times -(2 + (345 \times (6 \times ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
 18629 &:= (1 - (2 + (345 \times (6 \times ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
 18630 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 - (8 \times 9))))) \\
 18631 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - (7 \times (8 + 9))) \\
 18632 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 \times 6))) + (7 \times -(8 + 9))) \\
 18633 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times (3 \times ((4 - (56 \times 7)) \times 8))) - 9) \\
 18634 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times ((4 - (56 \times 7)) \times 8)))) + 9) \\
 18635 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) + (45 \times (6 \times (78 - 9)))) \\
 18636 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 + ((4^5) \times 6)) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 18637 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((345 \times 6) - (7 - 8)) \times 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 18596 &:= (((-9 \times -((87 \times 6) - 5)) - 4) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 18597 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 43))) + 21) \\
 18598 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 \times (6 - (54 \times 3))) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 18599 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + (6 \times 54)))) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
 18600 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 - (5 \times 4))))) \times -(3 + 21)) \\
 18601 &:= (9 - ((8 \times 7) \times -(((6 \times 54) + (3^2)) - 1))) \\
 18602 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (((76 \times 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) + 1)) \\
 18603 &:= (9 \times -((87 + 6) - (5 \times (432 \times 1)))) \\
 18604 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (((76 \times 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
 18605 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + (6 \times 5)))) \times ((4^3) - (2 + 1))) \\
 18606 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 765) \times 4)) \times -(3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
 18607 &:= (((-9 \times -((87 \times 6) - 5) \times 4) - 3) + (2 \times -1)) \\
 18608 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 + 6)) - (54 \times -321)) \\
 18609 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((76 - (5 - 4)) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
 18610 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 \times 5) \times -((4^3) - 2)) - 1)) \\
 18611 &:= (((-9 \times -(((87 \times 6) - 5) \times 4) - 3) - (2 \times -1)) \\
 18612 &:= (9 \times ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) + ((43^2) + 1))) \\
 18613 &:= ((((-98 \times (76 \times 5)) + (4 \times 3)) / -2) - 1) \\
 18614 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 65)) \times ((43 - 2) \times -1)) \\
 18615 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 + (((6 \times 5) + 4) \times 32)) \times -1)) \\
 18616 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (76 \times -((5 \times ((4 + 3)^2)) - 1))) \\
 18617 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 + ((65 - 4) \times 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 18618 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - ((7 + (6 + 5)) - 4)) \times 321) \\
 18619 &:= (98 - (((7 \times -(6 - (5 + 4)))^3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
 18620 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (5^4)))) \times -(3 + 2) - 1) \\
 18621 &:= (98 - (((7 \times -(6 - (5 + 4)))^3) \times -2) - 1) \\
 18622 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((76 \times 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
 18623 &:= (((-98 \times -(7 + ((65 - 4) \times 3))) + 2) + 1) \\
 18624 &:= (((9 + (87 + 6)) - 5) \times -((4^3) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
 18625 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 + 6) \times ((5 \times (4 + 32)) - 1)))) \\
 18626 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -((6^{5+4}/3) - 2)) + 1)) \\
 18627 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 6) / (5 + 4)) \times -321)) \\
 18628 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -((6^{5+4}/3) - 2)) - 1)) \\
 18629 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -54) - 3) - (2 \times -1)) \\
 18630 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times ((3 + 2) \times -1)) \\
 18631 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (7 \times -((65 \times (43 - 2)) - 1))) \\
 18632 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((7 + 65) + (4^{3+2})) \times -1)) \\
 18633 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((765 + 4) \times 3) + 21))) \\
 18634 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -54) + 3) + (2 - 1)) \\
 18635 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -54) + 3) - (2 \times -1)) \\
 18636 &:= (9 + ((8 + ((76 \times 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2))) - 1)) \\
 18637 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((76 \times 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2))) \times -1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
18638 &:= (1 - (2 - ((345 \times 6) - (7 - 8) \times 9))) \\
18639 &:= (12 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
18640 &:= ((1 + (23 \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))))) + 9 \\
18641 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((345 \times 6) - (7 - 8) \times 9))) \\
18642 &:= (1 \times (2 \times - (3 - (4 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 78)) - 9)))))) \\
18643 &:= (1 + (2 \times - (3 - (4 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 78)) - 9)))))) \\
18644 &:= (1 \times - ((2 + ((34 + 5) \times 6)) \times - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
18645 &:= (1 - ((2 + ((34 + 5) \times 6)) \times - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
18646 &:= (1 \times - (2 + (((3 - 45) \times 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
18647 &:= (1 - (2 + (((3 - 45) \times 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
18648 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 + (((4^5) \times 6) + (78 - 9)))) \\
18649 &:= (1 \times - (((2 \times 3) + ((4^5) + 67)) \times - (8 + 9))) \\
18650 &:= (1 \times (2 - (((3 - 45) \times 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
18651 &:= (1 + (2 - (((3 - 45) \times 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
18652 &:= (-1 + 23) - (45 \times - (6 \times (78 - 9))) \\
18653 &:= (1 \times - (23 \times ((4 - 5) - (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) \\
18654 &:= (1 - (23 \times ((4 - 5) - (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) \\
18655 &:= ((1 - (23 \times 4)) \times (5 \times - ((6 \times 7) + (8 - 9)))) \\
18656 &:= ((1 - (23^4)) / (5 \times (6 + ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
18657 &:= ((1 + 2) \times - (((3 + (4^5)) - (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times - 9)) \\
18658 &:= (1 \times - (((2^3) \times 4) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\
18659 &:= (1 \times - ((2 - (((3^4) \times 5) - 6)) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
18660 &:= (1 - ((2 - (((3^4) \times 5) - 6)) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
18661 &:= (((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times - (5 \times 6)) + (7 \times - (8 + 9))) \\
18662 &:= ((-1 - 23) - (4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\
18663 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - (78 + 9)) \\
18664 &:= (((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 \times 6))) - 78) - 9) \\
18665 &:= (1 \times - ((2345 - (6 + 7)) \times - 8) - 9) \\
18666 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times - (((4^5) \times 6) + 78)) / - 9 \\
18667 &:= (1 \times - (2 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
18668 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
18669 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (3 \times - (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
18670 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) \times - 4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\
18671 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
18672 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 \times - (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
18673 &:= (1 \times - (2 - ((3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + 78)) + 9))) \\
18674 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + 78)) + 9))) \\
18675 &:= ((1 + 2) \times - (((3^4) + (5 \times 6)) \times - (7 \times 8)) - 9) \\
18676 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times - (3 + 4)) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\
18677 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + 78)) + 9))) \\
18678 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + 78)) + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
18638 &:= (9 + (8 + (((76 \times 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2) + 1))) \\
18639 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4)))) \times (3 \times - (2 + 1))) \\
18640 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times - 32) + 1) \\
18641 &:= ((-98 \times - (7 + ((65 - 4) \times 3))) + 21) \\
18642 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 - ((5^4) + 3)))) \times (2 \times - 1)) \\
18643 &:= (((-9 \times - ((87 \times 6) - 5) \times 4) + 32) - 1) \\
18644 &:= (((-9 \times - 8) + 7) \times - ((65 \times - 4) + (3 + 21))) \\
18645 &:= (((98 + 7) - (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) \times - 1) \\
18646 &:= ((-9 \times (87 - 6)) - ((5^4) \times - (32 - 1))) \\
18647 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)))) / - (2 + 1)) \\
18648 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5)) \times (4 \times - (3 - 21))) \\
18649 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((7 + 65) + ((4^{3+2}) + 1))) \\
18650 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times - (((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) / - 2) + 1)) \\
18651 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 - ((5^4) + 3)) \times 2))) \times - 1) \\
18652 &:= (((-98 \times - (76 \times 5)) + (4^3)) / - (2 \times - 1)) \\
18653 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)))) / (2 + 1)) \\
18654 &:= (9 + ((8 + 7) \times - (((6 - ((5^4) + 3)) \times 2) + 1))) \\
18655 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) + ((43^2) - 1)) \\
18656 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) + 6)^5) - ((43^2) \times - 1)) \\
18657 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 7) \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3))) / - (2 + 1)) \\
18658 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) \times ((6 \times 54) + (3^2))) + 1)) \\
18659 &:= (9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)))) / - (2 + 1))) \\
18660 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times ((6 - ((5^4) + 3)) \times - (2 + 1))) \\
18661 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times - 54) + (32 - 1)) \\
18662 &:= ((9 - 8) \times - (7 \times - ((65 \times (43 - 2)) + 1))) \\
18663 &:= ((9 + (((8 + 7) \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3))) / (2 + 1)) \\
18664 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) + ((43^2) - 1)) \\
18665 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) - ((43^2) \times - 1)) \\
18666 &:= (9 - (87 - (6 \times (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1)))) \\
18667 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times - (3 + 2)) + 1) \\
18668 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times - ((6 - ((5^4) + 3)) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
18669 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3)) / - (2 + 1)) \\
18670 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times (((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) / 2) + 1)) \\
18671 &:= ((9 - 87) - ((6 \times - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\
18672 &:= ((9 - 87) - (6 \times - (5^{4+3/(2+1)}))) \\
18673 &:= ((9 - 87) - ((6 \times - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\
18674 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times - 32) + 1) \\
18675 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times (6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)))) / - (2 + 1)) \\
18676 &:= ((98 - 765) \times ((4 - 32) \times 1)) \\
18677 &:= (((-98 + 765) \times - (4 - 32)) + 1) \\
18678 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - ((5^4) + 3)))) \times - (2 \times - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}18679 &:= (1 \times (((2^3) \times -(4 - (5 \times (6 \times 78)))) - 9)) \\18680 &:= (1 + (((2^3) \times -(4 - (5 \times (6 \times 78)))) - 9)) \\18681 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times -6) + (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\18682 &:= (((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 \times 6))) - 78) + 9) \\18683 &:= (1 \times (((2^3) + ((4^5) + 67)) \times (8 + 9))) \\18684 &:= (1 + (((2^3) + ((4^5) + 67)) \times (8 + 9))) \\18685 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -((4 - 5) + (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\18686 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) + (8 \times -9)) \\18687 &:= (1 + ((2 - 3) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\18688 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) - (4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\18689 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((3 - 4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\18690 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) - 4) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\18691 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) - 4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\18692 &:= ((1 - 2) - (3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) + (78 + 9)))) \\18693 &:= ((1 - (2 \times 34)) \times (((5 \times 6) - (7 - 8)) \times -9)) \\18694 &:= ((1 - (23 + 4)) \times -((5 + (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\18695 &:= (1 - ((2 - 3) \times (4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\18696 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) + (78 + 9)))) \\18697 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 + ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\18698 &:= ((1 - 23) - (4 \times -((5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\18699 &:= (1 \times (((2 - 3) - (45 \times 6)) \times -((78 - 9)))) \\18700 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 + 4) \times -((5 \times (67 \times 8)) - 9))) \\18701 &:= (12 + ((3 - 4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\18702 &:= (((12 + 3) + (4^5)) \times -((6 - (7 + (8 + 9)))))) \\18703 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3)^4) \times -(5 \times 6)) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\18704 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 \times 6))) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\18705 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -((3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 78)))))) - 9)) \\18706 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times -((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\18707 &:= (-1 + (2 \times -((3 \times (4 - (5^{6+7-8}))) + 9))) \\18708 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3^4) \times -((5 + 6) \times 7)) - (8 - 9))) \\18709 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 78)))) - 9))) \\18710 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3) \times -4) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\18711 &:= ((1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5))) \times ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times -9)) \\18712 &:= (1 \times -((2345 - 6) \times -((7 - (8 - 9)))))) \\18713 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (34 \times 5) - 6) \times -((7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\18714 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3^4) \times -((5 + 6) \times 7)) + (8 - 9))) \\18715 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) - (5 \times -((6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\18716 &:= (1 + ((2 - (3 + 4)) \times -((5 + (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\18717 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 - ((4 - 56) \times 7)) \times -((8 + 9)))) \\18718 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 78)))))) - 9) \\18719 &:= (1 \times ((2 - 3) + (4 \times (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9))))))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}18679 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (((7 \times (6 + 5)) - 4) \times 32))) \times -1) \\18680 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 - (((5^4) \times 3) - (2 - 1)))))) \\18681 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times (6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)))) / (2 + 1)) \\18682 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - 6) \times -((5 + 4) \times 3)) - 2) \times 1) \\18683 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1)) \\18684 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times -((6 - ((5 - (4^3)) \times 21)))))) \\18685 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1)) \\18686 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - 6) \times -((5 + 4) \times 3)) + 2) \times 1) \\18687 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times (6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)))) / - (2 + 1))) \\18688 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4)))) + (32 \times -1)) \\18689 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 \times (6 + 5)) - 4) \times 32) - 1)) \\18690 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times ((6 - ((5^4) \times 3)) \times -(2 - 1))) \\18691 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (((76 \times 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) + 1)) \\18692 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (5^4)))) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\18693 &:= ((9 + (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times 4)) \times -((3 \times -((2 + 1)))) \\18694 &:= (((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4))) - 3)) + 2) - 1) \\18695 &:= ((-98 \times 7) + (6 + ((5^4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\18696 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 + 6)) \times (5^4))) \times (3 \times -((2 \times 1))) \\18697 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times -(((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\18698 &:= (((9 + 8) + ((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 + 2))) \times -1) \\18699 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -((65 \times (4 \times 3))) - 21) \\18700 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 - (((5^4) \times 3) + (2 - 1)))) \\18701 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + (76 \times (5 + 4))) \times 3) + 2)) - 1) \\18702 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6 \times -(((5^4) \times (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\18703 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) \times 1) \\18704 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -7) + ((6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 + 2))) + 1))) \\18705 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times -((43 \times 2) + 1))) \\18706 &:= (((((-9 - 87) \times 65) + 4) \times -3) - 2) \times 1) \\18707 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 76) - (((5^4) \times -32) + 1)) \\18708 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (6 - (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\18709 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -7) + (6 \times (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) + 1)))) \\18710 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times ((6 - (((5^4) \times 3) + 2)) \times -1)) \\18711 &:= ((9 - (8 - 76)) \times -((5 + 4) \times -((3^{2+1})))) \\18712 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -((65 \times -((4 + 32)) + 1)) \\18713 &:= ((9 + 8) - (76 \times -((5 \times ((4 + 3)^2)) + 1))) \\18714 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1)) \\18715 &:= (9 - (8 + (((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 + 2)) + 1))) \\18716 &:= (9 + ((8 + ((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 + 2))) \times -1)) \\18717 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\18718 &:= ((98 + ((7 \times -((6 - (5 + 4)))^3)) \times -((2 \times -1)) \\18719 &:= (98 - (((76 \times 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) - 1))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
18720 &:= (((1+2) - (3^4)) \times (5 \times -(6 \times (7 - (8 - 9)))))) & 18720 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -(65 \times -(4 \times (3 \times (2 - 1)))))) \\
18721 &:= (1 \times -((2 - 3) - (4 \times (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9))))) & 18721 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 + 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 32))) - 1))) \\
18722 &:= (1 - ((2 - 3) - (4 \times (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9))))) & 18722 &:= ((9 - ((876 - 5) \times 43)) / (2 \times -1)) \\
18723 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times -6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 18723 &:= ((((-9 - 87) \times 65) - (4 - 3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
18724 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 78)))))) + 9) & 18724 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times 76) + 5)) \times (((4^3) / -2) + 1)) \\
18725 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) + (4 \times (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9))))) & 18725 &:= ((9 + ((8^{(7-6) \times 5}) \times (4 \times 3))) / 21) \\
18726 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 + (4 \times (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9))))) & 18726 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - ((7 \times -(65 \times (43 - 2))) + 1)) \\
18727 &:= (((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 \times 6))) - 7) - (8 + 9)) & 18727 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (65 \times (43 - 2)))) \times 1) \\
18728 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -(4^5)) + (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 18728 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 + 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 32)))) + 1)) \\
18729 &:= (12 - (3 - (4 \times (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9))))) & 18729 &:= (9 + (8 \times -((76 + 54) \times (3 - 21)))) \\
18730 &:= (1 - ((234 \times -(5 + (67 + 8))) - 9)) & 18730 &:= ((9 + ((8 - 7)^6)) \times -(((5^4) \times -3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
18731 &:= (-1 + (2 \times -(3 - ((4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 78))) + 9)))) & 18731 &:= (9 + (8 - (((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 + 2)) + 1))) \\
18732 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times -6) + (7 - 89))) & 18732 &:= ((9 + ((8 - (7 + 6)) \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
18733 &:= (1 - (((2^3) + (4 \times 5)) \times -(678 - 9))) & 18733 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
18734 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times 45) + 67) \times -(8 + 9)) & 18734 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((7 - 65) \times -((4 \times (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\
18735 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times -6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 18735 &:= (((((-9 - 87) \times 65) - 4) \times -3) + 2) + 1) \\
18736 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 78)))))) + 9) & 18736 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - ((7 + 6) \times 54)) \times 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
18737 &:= (((-1 - ((2 + 34) \times (5 \times (6 + 7)))) \times -8) + 9) & 18737 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 - (6 \times (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1)))) \\
18738 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times ((4 \times -5) + (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))) & 18738 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - (6 \times (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1)))) \\
18739 &:= (1 - (((2^3) \times (45 \times 6)) - 78) \times -9) & 18739 &:= ((9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (43 \times 2))) \times -1) \\
18740 &:= (1 \times -((((2 + 3)^4) \times -(5 \times 6)) - (7 - (8 + 9)))) & 18740 &:= ((9 + ((8 - 7)^6)) \times -(((5^4) \times -3) + (2 - 1))) \\
18741 &:= (1 \times -((((2 + 3)^4) \times -(5 \times 6)) - ((7 - 8) \times 9)) & 18741 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -(65 \times (4 \times 3))) + 21) \\
18742 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3)^4) \times -(5 \times 6)) - ((7 - 8) \times 9)) & 18742 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 - ((6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 + 2))) - 1))) \\
18743 &:= (((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 \times 6))) - 7) + (8 - 9)) & 18743 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 - (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) \times -1)) \\
18744 &:= (((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 \times 6))) - 7) \times -(8 - 9)) & 18744 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -6) \times (((5^4) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
18745 &:= (((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 \times 6))) - 7) - (8 - 9)) & 18745 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - 6) \times (((5^4) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
18746 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})) + ((6 + 7) \times -(8 \times 9))) & 18746 &:= ((9 - ((8 - 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 + 2)) \times -1) \\
18747 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (4 \times -(5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 18747 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 7) \times 6) \times (5^4))) / (3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
18748 &:= (1 \times -(2 + (((3 \times 4) \times (5^6)) / (7 - (8 + 9)))) & 18748 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 7) \times 6) \times (5^4)) + 3)) / -(2 + 1)) \\
18749 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9))) & 18749 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times ((6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\
18750 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8)))) \times -9)) & 18750 &:= (((((9 - 8)^7) - 6) \times -(5^4)) \times -(3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
18751 &:= (-1 \times -((2345 \times -((6 - 7) \times 8)) - 9)) & 18751 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -((6 \times -((5^4) \times (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\
18752 &:= (1 \times (2 - (((3 \times 4) \times (5^6)) / (7 - (8 + 9)))) & 18752 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - ((6 \times -((5^4) \times (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\
18753 &:= (1 + (2 - (((3 \times 4) \times (5^6)) / (7 - (8 + 9)))) & 18753 &:= ((9 + (((8 + 7) \times 6) \times (5^4))) / -(3 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
18754 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 + 4) \times -(5 \times (67 \times 8))) + 9)) & 18754 &:= (9 + (((8 - 7) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
18755 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)) & 18755 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - 6) \times (((5^4) \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
18756 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)) & 18756 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -6) \times (((5^4) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1)) \\
18757 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) + (8 - 9)) & 18757 &:= ((9 + (((8 + 7) \times 6) \times (5^4)) / 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
18758 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times -(8 - 9)) & 18758 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 + (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) \times -1)) \\
18759 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) - (8 - 9)) & 18759 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 + ((6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 + 2))) + 1))) \\
18760 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 \times 6))) - ((7 - 8) \times 9)) & 18760 &:= ((9 + ((8 - 7)^6)) \times -(((5^4) \times -3) - (2 - 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

18761 := (((1 + (((2 + 3) ⁴) × (5 × 6))) - 7) + (8 + 9))	18761 := ((9 + (((((8 + 7) × 6) × (5 ⁴))/3) + 2)) × 1)
18762 := ((1 + 2) × -(((3 ⁴) × -((5 + 6) × 7)) - (8 + 9)))	18762 := ((9 + (((((8 + 7) × 6) × (5 ⁴))/3) + 2)) + 1)
18763 := (12 - (((3 + 4) × -(5 × (67 × 8))) + 9))	18763 := ((9 - 8) × (7 + (6 × (((5 ⁴) × (3 + 2)) + 1))))
18764 := (1 - (2 - (3 × (45 × (67 + (8 × 9)))))	18764 := ((9 - 8) + (7 + (6 × (((5 ⁴) × (3 + 2)) + 1))))
18765 := (12 - (((3 ⁴) × 5) - 6) × -((7 × 8) - 9))	18765 := (9 × -((8 × -((7 - (6 - 5)) × 43)) - 21))
18766 := ((1 - 23) × -((4 + ((5 + 6) × 78)) - 9))	18766 := (9 + ((8 - 7) + (6 × (((5 ⁴) × (3 + 2)) + 1))))
18767 := (1 × -(2 - (((3 + 4) × (5 × (67 × 8))) + 9)))	18767 := (((-9 × -8) - (7 × 65)) × (((4 + 3) ²) × -1))
18768 := ((1 + 2) × (34 × -(5 - ((6 + (7 + 8)) × 9))))	18768 := ((9 + 8) + (7 + (6 × (((5 ⁴) × (3 + 2)) - 1))))
18769 := (1 - (2 ³) × -((4 + (5 × 6)) × (78 - 9)))	18769 := (9 + (8 × -(7 × (6 - ((5 × 4) + 321))))
18770 := (((1 - 2) + (3 ⁴)) - (5 × -(6 × (7 × 89))))	18770 := ((9 + ((8 - 7) ⁶)) × -(((5 ⁴) × -3) - (2 × 1)))
18771 := ((((-1 + 2) × 3) ⁴) - (5 × -(6 × (7 × 89))))	18771 := ((-9 + 8) + (76 × -(5 - (4 × (3 × 21))))
18772 := ((1 + 2) - (((3 + 4) × -(5 × (67 × 8))) - 9))	18772 := (((987 + 6) - 5) × -((4 × -(3 + 2)) + 1))
18773 := (1 × (2 + ((3 ⁴) + (5 × (6 × (7 × 89)))))	18773 := ((9 + 8) + ((7 + (6 × ((5 ⁴) × (3 + 2)))) - 1))
18774 := (1 + (2 + ((3 ⁴) + (5 × (6 × (7 × 89)))))	18774 := ((9 + 8) - ((7 + (6 × ((5 ⁴) × (3 + 2)))) × -1))
18775 := ((1 + (((2 + 3) ⁴) × (5 × 6)) + (7 + 8)) + 9)	18775 := ((9 + 8) + (7 + ((6 × ((5 ⁴) × (3 + 2)))) + 1))
18776 := ((-1 + ((2345 - (6 - 7)) × 8)) + 9)	18776 := (9 + ((8 × -76) + ((5 ⁴) × (32 - 1))))
18777 := (12 - (3 × -(45 × (67 + (8 × 9))))	18777 := (9 - (8 × -((7 + (65 × (4 + 32))) - 1))
18778 := (1 × (((2 + 3) + (4 × 56)) × -(7 - 89)))	18778 := (9 - (((87 + (6 × 54))/3) ²) × -1))
18779 := (1 + (((2 + 3) + (4 × 56)) × -(7 - 89)))	18779 := (9 + (((87 + (6 × 54))/3) ²) + 1))
18780 := (1 × ((2 × 3) × -(4 - ((5 ⁶⁺⁷⁻⁸) + 9)))	18780 := ((9 + 8) + (7 + (6 × (((5 ⁴) × (3 + 2)) + 1))))
18781 := (1 + ((2 × 3) × -(4 - ((5 ⁶⁺⁷⁻⁸) + 9)))	18781 := (((-9 × (87 × 6)) - 5) × -4) - (32 - 1))
18782 := (1 + (2 - (((3 - 4) - (5 × (6 × 7))) × 89)))	18782 := ((((-9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) × -5 ⁴) + 32) × 1)
18783 := ((1 + 2) × (((3 - 4 ⁵) × -6) + ((7 + 8) × 9)))	18783 := (9 × -((87 × -(65 - (43 - 2))) + 1))
18784 := ((1 - (2 × (3 × (4 - (56 × (7 × 8)))))) - 9)	18784 := ((9 - 8) × -(((7 + (6 × (5 ⁴))) × -3 + 2)) + 1))
18785 := ((1 - (2 × (3 - 45))) × -((6 + 7) × -(8 + 9)))	18785 := ((9 - 8) - (((7 + (6 × (5 ⁴))) × -3 + 2)) + 1))
18786 := (1 - (((2 + ((3 + 4) × (5 × 67))) × -8) - 9))	18786 := ((9 - 8) × -(((7 + (6 × (5 ⁴))) × -3 + 2)) - 1))
18787 := (1 × -(2 - (3 × (((4 ⁵) × 6) + (7 × (8 + 9)))))	18787 := (9 - (8 - (((7 + (6 × (5 ⁴))) × (3 + 2)) + 1)))
18788 := (1 - (2 - (3 × (((4 ⁵) × 6) + (7 × (8 + 9)))))	18788 := (9 - (((8 + 7) × -(((6 × (5 ⁴))/3) + 2)) + 1))
18789 := (-1 + ((2 + 3) × ((4 × 5) + (6 × (7 × 89))))	18789 := ((9 + ((8 + 7) × (((6 × (5 ⁴))/3) + 2))) × 1)
18790 := ((1 - ((2 - (3 ⁴⁻⁵⁺⁶) × 78)) - 9)	18790 := (9 - (((8 + 7) × -(((6 × (5 ⁴))/3) + 2)) - 1))
18791 := (((12 ³)/ - 4) - 5) × ((6 × -7) + (8 - 9))	18791 := ((9 - ((87 × (6 ⁵))/4))/ (3 × -(2 + 1)))
18792 := ((1 + (((2 + 3) ⁴) × 5) + 6) × ((7 + 8) - 9)	18792 := ((9 + (8 + 7)) × -((65 × -(4 × 3)) - (2 + 1)))
18793 := (-123 + (4 × -(5 - (6 × 789))))	18793 := ((9 + ((87 × (6 ⁵))/4))/ - (3 × -(2 + 1)))
18794 := (1 × (2 - ((34 - 5) × ((6 - 78) × 9)))	18794 := (98 - (76 × -((5 × ((4 + 3) ²)) + 1)))
18795 := ((1 + 2) × -((34 × -(((5 × 6) - 7) × 8)) - 9))	18795 := ((98 + 7) × ((6 - 543)/ - (2 + 1)))
18796 := ((-1 + (((2 + 3) ⁴) × (5 × 6))) - ((7 × -8) + 9))	18796 := ((9 - ((87 × 6) - 5)) × ((4 × -(3 ²)) - 1))
18797 := (1 × -(((2 + 3) ⁴) × -(5 × 6)) - ((7 × 8) - 9))	18797 := (((9 - (8 × 7)) - (6 × ((5 ⁴) × (3 + 2)))) × -1)
18798 := (((1 + 2) - (3 ⁴)) × -((5 × -(6 - (7 × 8))) - 9))	18798 := (((9 + (87 × (6 ^{(5+4)/3}))) - 2) - 1)
18799 := (1 - (2 × -(3 + (4 × ((5 × (6 × 78)) + 9))))	18799 := (((9 + (87 × (6 ^{(5+4)/3}))) - 2) × 1)
18800 := (1 × -(2 + (34 × (5 - ((6 + (7 × 8)) × 9))))	18800 := (((9 + 8) - 7) + (6 × (5 ⁴))) × -((3 + 2) × -1))
18801 := ((1 + 2) × -(3 × -((4 × (5 × ((6 + 7) × 8))) + 9)))	18801 := ((9 + 8) - (((7 + (6 × (5 ⁴))) × -3 + 2)) + 1))

18802 := $(1 + ((2 \times - (3 \times (4 - (56 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9))$
18803 := $((-1 + 2) + (34 \times - (5 - ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))))$
18804 := $(1 \times - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) + (6 + (7 + 8))) \times 9))))$
18805 := $(1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) + (6 + (7 + 8))) \times 9))))$
18806 := $(-1 + (((2 - (3^{4-5+6})) \times -78) + 9))$
18807 := $(1 \times (((2 - (3^{4-5+6})) \times -78) + 9))$
18808 := $(1 + (((2 - (3^{4-5+6})) \times -78) + 9))$
18809 := $(123 - (4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 89))))$
18810 := $((1 - (2 - 34)) \times - (5 \times - ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9))))$
18811 := $(1 - ((2 - ((34 - 5) \times (6 - 78))) \times -9))$
18812 := $(-1 - 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5) + (6! + 7) \times (8 + 9)$
18813 := $(-123 - (((45 \times 6) - 7) \times - (8 \times 9)))$
18814 := $(12 + (34 \times - (5 - ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))))$
18815 := $(1 \times - (((2 + 3)^4 \times - (5 \times 6)) + (7 - (8 \times 9))))$
18816 := $((1 + (((2 + 3)^4 \times (5 \times 6))) - 7) - (8 \times -9))$
18817 := $((1 + 2) - 34) \times (((5 + 6) \times - (7 \times 8)) + 9)$
18818 := $(1 \times - ((23 \times - (4^5)) + (6 \times 789)))$
18819 := $((1 - (23 \times (4 \times 5))) \times ((6 \times -7) - (8 - 9)))$
18820 := $(1 \times - ((2 + 3) \times - (4 \times (5 + ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9))))))$
18821 := $(1 - ((2 + 3) \times - (4 \times (5 + ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9))))))$
18822 := $(1 \times - (2 \times - ((3 \times (4 + (56 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9)))$
18823 := $(1 - (2 \times - ((3 \times (4 + (56 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9)))$
18824 := $(1 \times - ((2^3) \times - (4 + ((5 \times (6 \times 78)) + 9))))$
18825 := $(1 \times (2 + ((3 + 4) \times ((5 \times (67 \times 8)) + 9))))$
18826 := $(1 + (2 + ((3 + 4) \times ((5 \times (67 \times 8)) + 9))))$
18827 := $(((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times - (5 \times 6)) - ((7 \times -8) + 9))$
18828 := $((1 + 2) \times - (3 - (((4^5) \times 6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9))))$
18829 := $(1 \times - (((2 + 3)^4 \times - (5 \times 6)) - (7 + (8 \times 9))))$
18830 := $((1 + (((2 + 3)^4 \times (5 \times 6)) + 7)) - (8 \times -9))$
18831 := $(1 \times - ((2 \times - (3 \times (4 + (56 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9))$
18832 := $(1 - ((2 \times - (3 \times (4 + (56 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9))$
18833 := $((1 + (((2 + 3)^4 \times (5 \times 6))) - 7) + 89)$
18834 := $((1 + 2) \times (((3^4) + 5) \times - ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9))))$
18835 := $(12 - ((3 + 4) \times - ((5 \times (67 \times 8)) + 9)))$
18836 := $(1 \times (2 \times - (34 \times (5 - (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))))$
18837 := $(1 + (2 \times - (34 \times (5 - (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))))$
18838 := $((1 + (((2 + 3)^4 \times (5 \times 6)) + 78)) + 9)$
18839 := $(1 \times (2 + ((3 + (45 \times 6)) \times (78 - 9))))$
18840 := $((1 + (2 \times ((3 + 4) \times 56)) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))$
18841 := $(1 \times - ((2 + (3^4)) \times - ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 + 9))))$
18842 := $(1 - ((2 + (3^4)) \times - ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 + 9))))$

18802 := $((9 + 8) - ((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times - ((3 + 2) \times 1)))$
18803 := $((9 + 8) - (((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times - (3 + 2)) - 1))$
18804 := $((9 - ((8 - (7 + 6)) \times (5^4))) \times - (3 \times - (2 \times 1)))$
18805 := $((((-9 \times (87 \times 6)) + 5) \times -4) + (32 + 1))$
18806 := $((((-9 \times (87 \times 6)) - 5) \times -4) - (3 \times 2)) \times 1$
18807 := $((-98 \times 7) - ((6 \times - ((54 + 3)^2)) + 1))$
18808 := $((-98 \times 7) - (6 \times - ((54 + 3)^2 \times 1)))$
18809 := $(9 - ((8 \times -7) - (6 \times (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1))))$
18810 := $((9 + 8) - 7) \times - (((6^5) / -4) + (3 \times 21))$
18811 := $((((-9 \times (87 \times 6)) - 5) \times -4) - 3) - (2 \times -1))$
18812 := $(98 + (((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times - (3 + 2)) - 1))$
18813 := $(98 + ((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times - ((3 + 2) \times 1)))$
18814 := $(9 - ((8 \times -7) - ((6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 + 2))) - 1)))$
18815 := $(9 - ((8 \times -7) - (6 \times (5^{4+3/(2+1)}))))$
18816 := $(9 + ((8 \times 7) + ((6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 + 2))) + 1)))$
18817 := $(9 - (8 \times - ((7 \times ((6 + (54 \times 3)) \times 2)) - 1)))$
18818 := $((98 - (7 - 6)) \times - ((5 \times -43) + 21))$
18819 := $((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) \times - ((43 - 2) \times -1))$
18820 := $((9 + 8) - 7) \times (6 + (((5^4) \times 3) + (2 - 1)))$
18821 := $(9 - ((8 \times -7) - (6 \times (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) + 1))))$
18822 := $(9 - ((87 \times - (6^{(5+4)/3})) - 21))$
18823 := $(((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 + (5^4)) - 3))) \times 2) + 1)$
18824 := $(9 - (((8 \times 76) - (5 \times 4)) \times -32) + 1)$
18825 := $((9 - (8 + 76)) \times (5 - (4^{3+2-1})))$
18826 := $((9 + (((8 \times 76) - (5 \times 4)) \times 32)) + 1)$
18827 := $((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 543))) / (2 + 1))$
18828 := $(9 \times - (((8 - 76) + (5 \times 432)) \times -1))$
18829 := $(((-98 + 7) \times 6) - ((5^4) \times - (32 - 1)))$
18830 := $((9 + 8) - 7) \times - (((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) / -2) + 1))$
18831 := $((9 - ((8 + 7) \times (((6 + (5^4)) - 3) \times 2))) \times -1)$
18832 := $((((-9 - 8) + (7 \times 65)) \times -43) + 2) \times -1$
18833 := $(9 - ((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 543)) / - (2 + 1)))$
18834 := $(9 - (((8 + 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times - ((3 + 2) \times 1)))$
18835 := $(9 - (((8 + 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times - (3 + 2)) - 1))$
18836 := $((9 + 8) \times (765 + ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))$
18837 := $((9 - (((8 + 7) \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 3))) / - (2 + 1))$
18838 := $(9 - (8 - ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + (4^3)) \times 21))))$
18839 := $(((-98 + 7) \times - ((65 + 4) \times 3)) - (2 \times -1))$
18840 := $((9 + 8) - 7) \times - (((6 + (5^4)) - 3) \times - (2 + 1))$
18841 := $(98 + ((7 - (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) \times -1))$
18842 := $(98 - (7 - ((6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 + 2))) + 1)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
18843 &:= ((1+2) \times -(((3+(4^5)) \times -6) - (7 \times (8+9)))) & 18843 &:= ((9 + (((8+7) \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 3)))/(2+1)) \\
18844 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (3 \times (((4 \times 5) + 678) \times 9)))) & 18844 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (76 \times -(5 - (4 \times (3 \times 21)))))) \\
18845 &:= (((12^3) - 4) \times (5+6)) + (7 \times -(8+9)) & 18845 &:= (9 + ((87 + (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3+2)))) - 1)) \\
18846 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times ((4 \times (5-6)) + (78 \times 9))) & 18846 &:= (((9+87) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3+2)))) \times 1) \\
18847 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (3^4)) \times 5) - 6) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9)) & 18847 &:= (98 - (7 - (6 \times (((5^4) \times (3+2)) + 1)))) \\
18848 &:= (1 + (((2 - (3^4)) \times 5) - 6) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9)) & 18848 &:= (9 - (((8+7) \times -(((6 + (5^4)) - 3) \times 2)) + 1)) \\
18849 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 \times (4 + (56 \times (7 \times 8)))))) - 9) & 18849 &:= ((9 + ((8+7) \times (((6 + (5^4)) - 3) \times 2))) \times 1) \\
18850 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(3 \times (4 + (56 \times (7 \times 8)))))) - 9) & 18850 &:= (9 - (((8+7) \times -(((6 + (5^4)) - 3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
18851 &:= (1 + ((234+56) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 18851 &:= (9 - (8 + ((7 - 65) \times (4 + 321)))) \\
18852 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3^4)) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 89)))) & 18852 &:= (9 + (87 + (6 \times (((5^4) \times (3+2)) + 1)))) \\
18853 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) - (5 \times -(6 \times (7 \times 89)))) & 18853 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 - ((76 + (5^4)) \times 3))) + 2) \times -1) \\
18854 &:= ((1 - 23) \times ((4 \times -(5 \times (6 \times 7))) - (8 + 9))) & 18854 &:= (98 + ((7 + (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3+2)))) - 1)) \\
18855 &:= ((1+2) \times -(3 \times -(((45 \times 6) - 7) \times 8) - 9)) & 18855 &:= (98 - ((7 + (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3+2)))) \times -1)) \\
18856 &:= (1 - (((2345 + (6+7)) \times -8) + 9)) & 18856 &:= ((98 - ((7+6) \times (((5+4)^3) \times 2))) \times -1) \\
18857 &:= (1 - ((2^3) \times -((4 \times 567) + 89))) & 18857 &:= (9 - ((87 + 65) \times -(4 \times (32 - 1)))) \\
18858 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((3 \times (4 + (56 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9))) & 18858 &:= ((9 + ((8+7) \times ((6 + (5^4)) - 3))) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
18859 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 \times (4 + (56 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9))) & 18859 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) + (7+6)) \times 5) \times -(4^3)) - 21) \\
18860 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times 3) + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 - 89))) & 18860 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! - 6!/5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
18861 &:= (1 + (((2 \times 3) + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 - 89))) & 18861 &:= (98 + (7 + (6 \times (((5^4) \times (3+2)) + 1)))) \\
18862 &:= (-1 + (((2 - (345 - 6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9)) & 18862 &:= (9 + ((87 \times -6) + ((5^4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
18863 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (345 - 6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9)) & 18863 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times 7) \times -(6 + ((5 \times ((4^3) + 2)) + 1)))) \\
18864 &:= ((12^3) - ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times -(7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 18864 &:= (9 - ((8+7) \times -(((6 + (5^4)) - 3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
18865 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3 \times ((4 \times 5) + 678))) \times -9)) & 18865 &:= ((9 - (8 - 76)) \times -5 \times -((4+3)^2 \times 1)) \\
18866 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((34 \times 5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 89))) & 18866 &:= (((-987 - 6) \times -5 + ((4+3) \times 2)) - 1) \\
18867 &:= (1 - (2 - (((34 \times 5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 89))) & 18867 &:= (9 - ((8 + (7+6)) \times (5 - (43 \times 21)))) \\
18868 &:= (((((12^3) - 4) \times (5+6)) - 7) - 89) & 18868 &:= (((-987 - 6) \times -5 + ((4+3) \times 2)) + 1) \\
18869 &:= (1 \times -(((2+3)^4) \times -(5 \times 6)) - (7 \times (8+9))) & 18869 &:= ((-9 \times 87) - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3) / - (2 \times 1)) \\
18870 &:= ((1 - (((2+3)^4) + 5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 \times 9))) & 18870 &:= (((9 + (8+7)) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -((3+2) \times -1)) \\
18871 &:= ((1 + ((2+3) \times ((4^5) - ((6^7)/8)))) / -9) & 18871 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) - ((6^5)/4)) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
18872 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})) + (6 \times -((7+8) \times 9))) & 18872 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (((76 + (5^4)) \times 3) + 2))) - 1) \\
18873 &:= ((1+2) \times -((3 + (((4 \times 5) + 67) \times 8)) \times -9)) & 18873 &:= (9 \times -((8 \times 7) + (6 - ((5 \times 432) - 1)))) \\
18874 &:= (1 - (((2345 + (6+7)) \times -8) - 9)) & 18874 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) - (6 - 5)) \times -((4+3)^{2+1}))) \\
18875 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times ((7+8) \times 9)))) & 18875 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 65) \times -43) - 2) \times 1) \\
18876 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times ((7+8) \times 9)))) & 18876 &:= ((9 + ((8+76) \times 5)) \times ((43+2) - 1)) \\
18877 &:= (((((12^3) - 4) \times (5+6)) - 78) - 9) & 18877 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) - 65) \times -(43 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
18878 &:= 1 - 2 + (-3 + 4!) \times ((5! + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9) & 18878 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times -(7^{(6-5) \times 4})) + 321)) \\
18879 &:= (((-12 + ((345 - 6) \times 7)) \times 8) - 9) & 18879 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 - 54)))) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
18880 &:= (1 \times ((2+3) \times -(4 - (5 \times ((6+78) \times 9)))) & 18880 &:= (((9+8) + (7 \times 65)) \times -(4 \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
18881 &:= (1 + ((2+3) \times -(4 - (5 \times ((6+78) \times 9)))) & 18881 &:= (9 - (8 \times -7 \times (((6 + (54 \times 3)) \times 2) + 1))) \\
18882 &:= ((1+2) \times -(3 \times -(((4+5) - 6)^7) - 89)) & 18882 &:= (98 - (((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3+2)) + 1)) \\
18883 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) - (((5^6) + 7)/8) \times -9) & 18883 &:= ((98 + ((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3+2))) \times 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
18884 &:= ((-1 + (((2+3)^4) \times (5 \times 6))) - ((7+8) \times -9)) & 18884 &:= (98 - (((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3+2)) - 1)) \\
18885 &:= (1 \times -(((2+3)^4) \times -(5 \times 6)) - ((7+8) \times 9)) & 18885 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7+65)) - 4) \times -(32+1))) \\
18886 &:= ((1 + (((2+3)^4) \times (5 \times 6))) - ((7+8) \times -9)) & 18886 &:= ((-98 / -7) \times -((6 \times -(5 \times (43+2))) + 1)) \\
18887 &:= ((((-1-2) + (3^{4+5})) - 6) - 789) & 18887 &:= ((9+8) \times -(((7 + (6+543)) \times -2) + 1)) \\
18888 &:= (12 \times -(3 - ((4 \times ((56-7) \times 8)) + 9))) & 18888 &:= (9 - (87 \times -(((65+43) \times 2) + 1))) \\
18889 &:= ((((-1+2) + (3^{4+5})) - 6) - 789) & 18889 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) - ((6^5)/4)) \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
18890 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (6 + 789))) & 18890 &:= (-9 - (((8+76) \times -(5 \times (43+2))) + 1)) \\
18891 &:= ((1+2) \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times -6) - ((7+8) \times 9))) & 18891 &:= ((9 - (((87 \times 6) + 5) \times 4)) \times (3 \times -(2+1))) \\
18892 &:= (1 - (((2+3) \times -(45 \times (6+78))) + 9)) & 18892 &:= (-9 - (((8+76) \times -(5 \times (43+2))) - 1)) \\
18893 &:= (1 \times -(23 + (4 \times (5 - (6 \times 789)))))) & 18893 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times 6) \times ((5 + (4^3)) - 2)) - 1) \\
18894 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 \times (4 + (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 89))))))) & 18894 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times -5) + (432 \times 1))) \\
18895 &:= (1 \times (((((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times -8) - 9)) & 18895 &:= ((-98 \times 7) - ((65 - 4) \times -321)) \\
18896 &:= (1 + (((((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times -8) - 9)) & 18896 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7^{(6-5) \times 4})) + 321)) \\
18897 &:= (((-12 + ((345 - 6) \times 7)) \times 8) + 9) & 18897 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 + (65 \times (4 \times 3))) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
18898 &:= ((1 - 23) \times -(4 + ((5 + (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9))) & 18898 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 65) \times -43) + 21) \\
18899 &:= (((((12^3) - 4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7) + (8 \times -9)) & 18899 &:= ((((-98 - 7) \times -((6 + 54) \times 3)) - 2) + 1) \\
18900 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) \times -4) \times (((5 \times 6) - 7) \times -8) + 9)) & 18900 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times (6 + (((5^4) + 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
18901 &:= ((1 + (23 \times (4 \times 5))) \times -((6 \times -7) - (8 - 9))) & 18901 &:= ((((-98 - 7) \times -((6 + 54) \times 3)) + 2) - 1) \\
18902 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) - 6) \times -78) / -9) & 18902 &:= ((((-98 - 7) \times -((6 + 54) \times 3)) + 2) \times 1) \\
18903 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((34 \times (5 - 67)) + 8) \times 9)) & 18903 &:= ((9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) + (5^4)) \times 32)) \times -1) \\
18904 &:= ((1 - (((2 + 3) \times (4 \times 56)) - 7)) \times -(8 + 9)) & 18904 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 + (6 + 543)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
18905 &:= (-1 - (23 \times -((4 \times (5 \times 6)) + (78 \times 9)))) & 18905 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + (6 + 543)) \times 2)) + 1) \\
18906 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(((3^4) + 56) \times (78 - 9)))) & 18906 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5^4))) - 3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
18907 &:= ((1 + (2 + 34)) \times -((5 \times -((6 + 7) \times 8)) + 9)) & 18907 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times ((4 \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
18908 &:= (1 - (2 + ((3 - (((45 \times 6) - 7) \times 8)) \times 9))) & 18908 &:= (9 - (((8 + 76) \times -(5 \times (43 + 2))) + 1)) \\
18909 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times -(((45 \times 6) - 7) \times 8)) + 9)) & 18909 &:= (9 \times (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times 4) + (32 + 1)) \\
18910 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 3) \times (45 \times (6 + 78)))) + 9) & 18910 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + (6 \times 5)))) \times -(((4^3) - 2) \times -1)) \\
18911 &:= (1 \times (2 - ((3 - (((45 \times 6) - 7) \times 8)) \times 9))) & 18911 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times (76 - (5 - 4)))) \times 32) - 1) \\
18912 &:= ((1 + ((2 - (3^4)) \times 5)) \times (6 \times -(7 - (8 - 9)))) & 18912 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times -(3 - (2 - 1))) \\
18913 &:= (1 \times (((((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times -8) + 9)) & 18913 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times (76 - (5 - 4)))) \times 32) + 1) \\
18914 &:= (1 + (((((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times -8) + 9)) & 18914 &:= (98 \times -(((7 - (6 + 5)) \times 43) - 21)) \\
18915 &:= ((12^3) - (((4^5) - (6 + 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) & 18915 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5^4))) - 3) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
18916 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) \times -(45 + (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) & 18916 &:= (-9 - (((((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5^4))) - 3) \times -2) - 1)) \\
18917 &:= (((((12^3) - 4) \times (5 + 6)) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & 18917 &:= (-98 + (7 + ((6 + 5) \times ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))) \\
18918 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) + (4^5)) \times -(6 - (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 18918 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5^4))) + 3)) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
18919 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 - ((5 - 6) \times 7))) - 89) & 18919 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)) - 2))) \times -1) \\
18920 &:= ((1 - 23) \times (4 \times -(5 \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 - 9)))))) & 18920 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 + (5^4)) \times -3) + (2 - 1))) \\
18921 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3) \times (4 \times 56)) - 7) \times -(8 + 9)) & 18921 &:= (9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) + (5^4)) \times -(32 \times 1))) \\
18922 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) \times (4 \times 56)) - 7) \times -(8 + 9)) & 18922 &:= (9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) + (5^4)) \times -32) - 1) \\
18923 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -3) + (4 \times (5 - (6 \times 789)))))) & 18923 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times (5 - 43)) - 2) + 1) \\
18924 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) + 5)) \times ((6 \times -7) - (8 \times 9))) & 18924 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times -((6 + (((5^4) + 3) \times 2)) - 1))) \\
18925 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 18925 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) - ((5^4) \times -(32 - 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
18926 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) - ((6 + 78) \times 9)))) \\
18927 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -(4 - (5 \times (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
18928 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) \times -(4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
18929 &:= (1 + ((2^3) \times -(4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
18930 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) + 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\
18931 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -3) + (((45 \times 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
18932 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) - (((45 \times 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
18933 &:= (((12^3) + 4) \times (5 + 6)) + (7 \times -(8 + 9)) \\
18934 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 - (4 - 5)) \times (6 \times 789)))) \\
18935 &:= (1 \times -(((2^{3 \times 4}) \times (5 - (6 \times 7)))/8) + 9) \\
18936 &:= (1 - (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times (5 - (6 \times 7)))/8) + 9) \\
18937 &:= (1 \times -((2 - 3) - (((45 \times 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
18938 &:= (1 - ((2 - 3) - (((45 \times 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
18939 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) \times 6))) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
18940 &:= (((((12^3) - 4) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8)) - 9) \\
18941 &:= (1 \times -((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) - 89))) \\
18942 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 + (((45 \times 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
18943 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3^{4-5+6}) \times 78) - 9))) \\
18944 &:= ((1 + (2 + 34)) \times (((5 \times 6)/(7 + 8))^9)) \\
18945 &:= (1 + ((2^3) + (((45 \times 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
18946 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3))^4) - (5 \times -(6 \times (7 \times 89)))) \\
18947 &:= (1 \times ((2 + ((3^{4-5+6}) \times 78)) - 9)) \\
18948 &:= (1 \times (((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
18949 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
18950 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times (56 + (78 \times 9))) \\
18951 &:= (12 + (3 + (((45 \times 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
18952 &:= ((1 + ((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -(7 - (8 - 9))) \\
18953 &:= (1 \times (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times (5 - (6 \times 7)))/ - 8) + 9) \\
18954 &:= (1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times (5 - (6 \times 7)))/ - 8) + 9) \\
18955 &:= (((12^3) - 4) \times (5 + 6)) + ((7 - 8) \times 9) \\
18956 &:= (((((12^3) - 4) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 - 8)) - 9) \\
18957 &:= (((((12^3) - 4) \times -(5 + 6)) + 7) \times (8 - 9)) \\
18958 &:= (((((12^3) - 4) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) - (8 - 9)) \\
18959 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - ((345 - 6) \times 7)) \times 8) + 9)) \\
18960 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3^4) + (5 - 6)) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
18961 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3^{4-5+6}) \times 78) + 9))) \\
18962 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3^{4-5+6}) \times 78) + 9))) \\
18963 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times -(((45 \times 6) - 7) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
18964 &:= (((((12^3) - 4) \times -(5 - ((6 + 7) \times 8)))/9) \\
18965 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3^{4-5+6}) \times 78) + 9))) \\
18966 &:= (1 + (2 + (((3^{4-5+6}) \times 78) + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
18926 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times -(5 - 43)) - 2) \times -1) \\
18927 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((76 + (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
18928 &:= ((98 - (7 \times 6)) \times -(5 - ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
18929 &:= ((9 + ((8 - ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4)^3))) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
18930 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 + (5^4)) \times -(3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
18931 &:= ((((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times -((6 + (5^4)) \times 3)) + 2) - 1) \\
18932 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 + (6 \times 5))) \times -(4^3)) + 21)) \\
18933 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5^4))) - 3) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
18934 &:= (9 + ((8 - 765) \times -((4 \times (3 \times 2)) + 1))) \\
18935 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 + (6 \times 5))) \times (4^3))) \times -(2 - 1)) \\
18936 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)) - 2)) + 1)) \\
18937 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)) - (2 \times 1)))) \\
18938 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times -(6 + (((5^4) + 3) \times 2))) + 1)) \\
18939 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times -((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
18940 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 + (5^4)) \times -3) - (2 - 1))) \\
18941 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + 6) \times -(((5 + 4)^3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
18942 &:= (((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5^4)))) - 3) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
18943 &:= ((-98 \times 7) - (6543 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
18944 &:= (9 - (((((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5^4))) + 3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
18945 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5^4))) + 3) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
18946 &:= (9 + (((8 - ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4)^3))) \times -2) - 1)) \\
18947 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4)^3))) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
18948 &:= ((987 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
18949 &:= (-9 - (87 - (((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) + 1))) \\
18950 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)))) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
18951 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 + (6 \times 5))) \times (4^3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
18952 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 + (6 \times 5))) \times -(4^3)) + (2 - 1))) \\
18953 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + 6) \times -(((5 + 4)^3) \times 2)) + 1)) \\
18954 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 + 6) \times -(((5 + 4)^3) \times 2)) + 1)) \\
18955 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 + (6 \times 5))) \times (4^3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
18956 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 + 6) \times -(((5 + 4)^3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
18957 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times 654)/3)) \times -(2 - 1)) \\
18958 &:= (9 + (8 + ((7 + 6) \times (((5 + 4)^3) \times 2) - 1))) \\
18959 &:= ((9 - (((87 \times 654)/3) + 2)) \times -1) \\
18960 &:= ((9 - (87 \times (6 + 5))) \times -(4 \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
18961 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6 + 5) \times -((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
18962 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7^{6-5} \times 4) - 32)) - 1)) \\
18963 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 54)) \times -((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
18964 &:= (9 - (8 - (7 \times ((65 + (4^3)) \times 21)))) \\
18965 &:= (9 - (87 - (((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) - 1))) \\
18966 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times (5 - ((4^3) - (2 - 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 18967 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4+5}) - (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 18968 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) - (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 18969 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((3^{4+5}) - (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 18970 &:= (((((12^3) - 4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7) + (8 - 9)) \\
 18971 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 18972 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 18973 &:= (((((12^3) + 4) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) + (8 \times -9)) \\
 18974 &:= (((((12^3) - 4) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 - 8)) + 9) \\
 18975 &:= (12 - (((3^{4-5+6}) \times -78) - 9)) \\
 18976 &:= (1 \times -((2 - 34) \times -((5 \times 6) - (7 \times 89)))) \\
 18977 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - ((345 - 6) \times 7)) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 18978 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3^{4+5})) - 6) + (78 \times -9)) \\
 18979 &:= (1 \times (23 + (4 \times (5 + (6 \times 789)))))) \\
 18980 &:= (((1 - 23) - (45 \times 6)) \times -((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
 18981 &:= ((12 + (3^{4+5})) + (6 \times -(7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 18982 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 + 8)) - 9) \\
 18983 &:= (((((12^3) + 4) \times (5 + 6)) - 78) + 9) \\
 18984 &:= (12 \times ((3 + 4) \times (5 + ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 18985 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - ((5 \times (6^7))/8)))/9) \\
 18986 &:= ((1 - 23) \times -((4 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) - 9)) \\
 18987 &:= (((((12^3) + 4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7) + (8 \times -9)) \\
 18988 &:= (((((12^3) - 4) \times (5 + 6)) + (7 + 8)) + 9) \\
 18989 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3^{4+5}) + (6 - (78 \times 9)))))) \\
 18990 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((3 \times ((4 + (56 \times 7)) \times 8)) - 9))) \\
 18991 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 - ((5 - 6) \times 7))) - (8 + 9)) \\
 18992 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -(4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9))))))) \\
 18993 &:= (1 - ((2^3) \times -(4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9))))))) \\
 18994 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4+5}) - (678 + 9)))) \\
 18995 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((345 - 6) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) \\
 18996 &:= (12 \times -(((3 + (4 \times (56 - 7))) \times -8) + 9)) \\
 18997 &:= ((1 - 2) \times ((34 \times -(567 - 8)) + 9)) \\
 18998 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times -((5 - 6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 18999 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3 \times ((4 + (56 \times 7)) \times 8)) + 9)) + 9)) \\
 19000 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 + 8)) + 9) \\
 19001 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) \times 8))/9) \\
 19002 &:= (((-12 + (3^{4+5})) - 678) + 9) \\
 19003 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 \times 8))))/9) \\
 19004 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3^4) + 5) \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 19005 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3^4) + 5) \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 19006 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(((3^4) + 5) \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 19007 &:= (1 \times (((((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times -8) - 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 18967 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + 6) \times -(((5 + 4)^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
 18968 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)) + 2)) - 1)) \\
 18969 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) - (32 - 1)))) \\
 18970 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6^5)/4)) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\
 18971 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((7 + 6) \times (((5 + 4)^3) \times 2))) \times -1)) \\
 18972 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 + 6) \times -(((5 + 4)^3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
 18973 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((7 + 6) - (5^4)) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
 18974 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7 + (6 \times 5))) \times (4^3))) + 21) \\
 18975 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -((54 + 3) - 2) \times -1)) \\
 18976 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (6 + 5)) - 4))) \times -(32 \times -1)) \\
 18977 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 654)/ -3) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 18978 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 654)/ -3) - (2 + 1))) \\
 18979 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4)^3))) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
 18980 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 6) + 5) \times -(4 + 32)) + 1)) \\
 18981 &:= (((9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) \times 54)) \times (3^{2+1})) \\
 18982 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 6) + 5) \times -(4 + 32)) - 1)) \\
 18983 &:= ((((-9 + 87) \times -6) + 5) \times ((43 - 2) \times -1)) \\
 18984 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 + 6) \times -(((5 + 4)^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
 18985 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times ((3 + 2) \times -1)) \\
 18986 &:= ((98 + 765) \times (43 - 21)) \\
 18987 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 + (65 \times 4)) - 3))) - 21) \\
 18988 &:= (((9 + 8) + ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4)^3))) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
 18989 &:= (9 + (8 - (((7 + 6) - (5^4)) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
 18990 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 \times 5) \times -(4^3)) + 21)) \\
 18991 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times -(43 - 2)) + 1)) \\
 18992 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times (43 - 2))) \times 1) \\
 18993 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times (43 - 2))) + 1) \\
 18994 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 76) + 5) \times -(4 + (3^{2+1})))) \\
 18995 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 18996 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) - 1)) \\
 18997 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) \times -1)) \\
 18998 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -7) + (((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) + 1))) \\
 18999 &:= ((9 + (((87 \times 6) + 5) \times (4 \times 3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 19000 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((76 \times 5) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) + 1))) \\
 19001 &:= (9 + (8 \times ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) - (3^{2+1})))) \\
 19002 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 + ((5^4) + 3)))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
 19003 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -(6 \times 5)) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1}))) \\
 19004 &:= (((-9 \times -(((87 \times 6) + 5) \times 4)) + 32) \times 1) \\
 19005 &:= ((98 + 7) \times -(((6 + 54) \times -3) - (2 - 1))) \\
 19006 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 + 6) \times -((54 + 32) \times 1))) \\
 19007 &:= (((987 + 6) - ((5^4) \times 32)) \times -1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
19008 &:= (1 + (((((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times -8) - 9)) \\
19009 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3^4) + 5) \times -((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
19010 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - ((67 + 8) \times 9))) \\
19011 &:= (((((12^3) - 4) \times (5 + 6)) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
19012 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4+5}) - (678 - 9)))) \\
19013 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) - (678 - 9)))) \\
19014 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((3^{4+5}) - (678 - 9))) \\
19015 &:= ((1 - ((2 + (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times (7 \times 8))) / -9) \\
19016 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (678 - 9))) \\
19017 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 \times -(((45 \times 6) - 7) \times 8) + 9)) \\
19018 &:= (12 - (((3^4) + 5) \times -((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
19019 &:= ((1 - (23 \times 4)) \times ((5 \times -(6 \times 7)) - (8 - 9))) \\
19020 &:= (12 \times (3 + ((4^5) + ((6 + (7 \times 8) \times 9)))) \\
19021 &:= (1 \times (23 \times -(4 - ((56 \times (7 + 8)) - 9)))) \\
19022 &:= (1 + (23 \times -(4 - ((56 \times (7 + 8)) - 9)))) \\
19023 &:= (1 \times -(23 - ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 89))) \\
19024 &:= (1 - (23 - ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 89))) \\
19025 &:= (1 \times (((((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times -8) + 9)) \\
19026 &:= (1 + (((((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times -8) + 9)) \\
19027 &:= ((1 - ((2^3) \times 45)) \times -((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\
19028 &:= ((((((12^3) + 4) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8)) - 9) \\
19029 &:= ((((((12^3) - 4) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) - (8 \times -9)) \\
19030 &:= ((1 - 23) \times (4 - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + (8 \times 9))))) \\
19031 &:= (-12 - (3 - ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 89))) \\
19032 &:= ((1 - (23 + 4)) \times ((5 \times -6) - (78 \times 9))) \\
19033 &:= (1 \times -(2 + ((3^4) \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 89)))) \\
19034 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 - 78) \times -9)) \\
19035 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -((4 + 5) \times -(6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
19036 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 - 78) \times -9)) \\
19037 &:= (1 \times (2 - ((3^4) \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 89)))) \\
19038 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
19039 &:= (1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
19040 &:= (1 + ((2 - (3^{4-5+6})) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
19041 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) - ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 89))) \\
19042 &:= ((((((12^3) + 4) \times (5 + 6)) + (7 - 8)) - 9) \\
19043 &:= ((((((12^3) - 4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7) - (8 \times -9)) \\
19044 &:= ((((((12^3) + 4) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 - 8)) - 9) \\
19045 &:= ((((((12^3) + 4) \times -((5 + 6)) + 7) \times (8 - 9)) \\
19046 &:= ((((((12^3) + 4) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) - (8 - 9)) \\
19047 &:= (1 \times -((2 - 3) - ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 89))) \\
19048 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times (4 - (5 \times ((6 \times 78) + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
19008 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (6 \times -(((5 \times 4) + 3)^2) - 1)) \\
19009 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - ((6 + 5) \times -((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
19010 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 + (65 \times 4)) - 3))) + 2) \times 1) \\
19011 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times ((6 + ((5^4) + 3) \times 2))) \times -1) \\
19012 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 76) + 5) \times -(4 + (3^{2+1})))) \\
19013 &:= ((-98 \times -(((7 \times 6) + 5) \times 4) + (3 \times 2)) + 1) \\
19014 &:= (9 - ((8 + ((7 + 6) \times (5 + (4^3)))) \times -21)) \\
19015 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 + ((6 + 5) \times ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))) \\
19016 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 + ((6 + 5) \times ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))) \\
19017 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((76 \times 5) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) + 1))) \\
19018 &:= (9 + ((8 - 7) + ((6 + 5) \times ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))) \\
19019 &:= ((98 - 7) \times ((6 - (5 \times 43)) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
19020 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(6 \times -((5 \times (4^3)) - (2 + 1)))) \\
19021 &:= (9 - ((8 + (76 \times 5)) \times -((4 + 3)^2 \times 1))) \\
19022 &:= (9 - (((8 + (76 \times 5)) \times -((4 + 3)^2) - 1)) \\
19023 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((7 + 6) \times -(54 + 32)) - 1)) \\
19024 &:= ((-9 \times 87) + (((6 - (5^4)) \times -32) - 1)) \\
19025 &:= (98 - ((76 + (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
19026 &:= (9 \times -((8 + ((7 + 6) \times (54 \times 3))) \times -(2 - 1))) \\
19027 &:= (-98 - (765 \times -((4 \times (3 \times 2)) + 1))) \\
19028 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times -((6 + ((5^4) + 3) \times 2)) + 1)) \\
19029 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 + ((5^4) + 3) \times 2))) \times 1) \\
19030 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times -((6 + ((5^4) + 3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
19031 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (76 + ((5 + 43)^2)))) \times -1) \\
19032 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + ((6 + 5) \times ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))) \\
19033 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 - 65) \times (43 - 2)))) \times 1) \\
19034 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) - ((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) \times -1) \\
19035 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + (5 + 4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
19036 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 - (((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) - 1))) \\
19037 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 - ((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) \times -1)) \\
19038 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 - ((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) \times -1)) \\
19039 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - (((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) + 1))) \\
19040 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1) \\
19041 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 - 5))) \times -((4 \times -3) - 21)) \\
19042 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 - 6! + ((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1} \\
19043 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - ((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) \times -1) \\
19044 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + ((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) - 1) \\
19045 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + ((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) \times 1) \\
19046 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + ((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) + 1) \\
19047 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + ((7 + 6) \times (54 \times 3)))) + 21) \\
19048 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - ((5^4) \times -(32 - 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

19049 := (1 - ((2³) × (4 - (5 × ((6 × 78) + 9))))
19050 := (((1 - 2) - (34 × 56)) × (7 - (8 + 9)))
19051 := (1 × ((2 + 3) + ((4 + (5 × (6 × 7))) × 89)))
19052 := (((12³) + 4) × -(5 - ((6 + 7) × 8)))/9
19053 := (1 + ((2 × 3) + ((4 + (5 × (6 × 7))) × 89)))
19054 := (((1 - 2) + (3 × ((4⁵) × 6))) - (7 × -89))
19055 := ((1 + (2 + 34)) × ((5 + 6) + (7 × (8 × 9))))
19056 := (1 × ((2 + (3⁴⁺⁵)) - (6 + (7 × 89))))
19057 := (1 × (2 + ((3 × ((4⁵) × 6)) + (7 × 89)))
19058 := (1 × -(((2 + 3)⁴) - (((5 × (6 - 7)) + 8)⁹)))
19059 := ((1 - ((2 + 3)⁴)) + (((5 × (6 - 7)) + 8)⁹))
19060 := (((((12³) + 4) × (5 + 6)) + (7 - 8)) + 9)
19061 := (((((12³) + 4) × -(5 + 6) × (7 - 8)) + 9)
19062 := (((((12³) + 4) × (5 + 6)) - (7 - 8)) + 9)
19063 := (1 - (((2 × (34 × (5 × 6))) + 78) × -9))
19064 := (1 × -(2 - ((3⁴⁺⁵) + (6 - (7 × 89))))
19065 := ((1 - ((2 - ((3 × (4⁵)) - 6)) × (7 × 8)))/9)
19066 := ((1 - 2) × -((3⁴⁺⁵) + (6 - (7 × 89))))
19067 := (12 - ((3 × -(4⁵) × 6)) - (7 × 89))
19068 := ((1 + ((2 + (3 × (4⁵))) × 6)) - (7 × -89))
19069 := (1 + (2 + ((3⁴⁺⁵) + (6 - (7 × 89))))
19070 := (1 + (23 + ((4 + (5 × (6 × 7))) × 89)))
19071 := (1 × (((2 + 3) + (4 × (5 - (67 × 8)))) × -9))
19072 := (1 × -((2³⁺⁴) × -(5 + (6 × (7 + (8 + 9))))))
19073 := (1 - ((2³⁺⁴) × -(5 + (6 × (7 + (8 + 9))))))
19074 := (1 - (2 - ((3 + 4) × (5 × ((67 × 8) + 9))))
19075 := ((1 - 2) × ((3 + 4) × -(5 × ((67 × 8) + 9))))
19076 := ((12 - (((3 × (4⁵)) - 6) × (7 × 8)))/ -9)
19077 := (((1 + 2) - (((3 × (4⁵)) - 6) × (7 × 8)))/ -9)
19078 := (1 + (2 + ((3 + 4) × (5 × ((67 × 8) + 9))))
19079 := ((1 - ((2 + (((3 × (4⁵)) - 6) × 7)) × 8)) / -9)
19080 := (((12³) × (4 - ((5 - 6) × 7))) - (8 × -9))
19081 := ((1 + (2 × (3 × (456 × 7)))) + (8 × -9))
19082 := ((-12 × -3) - ((4 + (5 × (6 × 7))) × -89))
19083 := (((12³) - 4) × (5 + 6)) - (7 × -(8 + 9))
19084 := -1 + 2 + 3 × ((4 + 5) × 6! - 7 × (8 + 9))
19085 := (((-12 × -((3 + (4 × 56)) × 7)) + 8) + 9)
19086 := (1 × -(2 × -(3 × ((456 × 7) - 8)) - 9))
19087 := (12 - ((3 + 4) × -(5 × ((67 × 8) + 9)))
19088 := ((1 - 2) + ((3 + (4 × (5 - (67 × 8)))) × -9))
19089 := ((1 - 2) × -(3 + (4 × (5 - (67 × 8)))) × -9))

19049 := ((9 + (8 × (76 + ((5 + 43)²)))) × 1)
19050 := ((9 - 8) × ((7 + ((6 × ((5 × 4) + 3))²)) - 1))
19051 := ((9 - 8) × -((7 + ((6 × ((5 × 4) + 3))²)) × -1))
19052 := ((9 - 8) - ((7 + ((6 × ((5 × 4) + 3))²)) × -1))
19053 := ((9 - 8) + (7 + (((6 × ((5 × 4) + 3))²) + 1)))
19054 := (9 - ((8 - 7) × -(((6 × ((5 × 4) + 3))²) + 1)))
19055 := (9 + ((8 - 7) + (((6 × ((5 × 4) + 3))²) + 1)))
19056 := (((9 + 8) + (76 × 5)) × (((4 + 3)²) - 1))
19057 := ((9 + 8) × ((7 × ((6 - (5 - 4)) × 32)) + 1))
19058 := ((-98 / -7) - (((6 × ((5 × 4) + 3))²) × -1))
19059 := (-9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) × (5 + (43 × 21))))
19060 := (((-9 × -(((87 - 6) + (5⁴)) × 3)) - 2) × 1)
19061 := (9 + ((87 × -(6 - (5 × (43 + 2)))) - 1))
19062 := (9 × -((8 × -(7 × 6)) - (54 × (32 + 1))))
19063 := (9 + ((87 × -(6 - (5 × (43 + 2)))) + 1))
19064 := (((-9 - (8 + 76)) × -(5 × (43 - 2))) - 1)
19065 := (98 - ((7 + 6) × -(((5 + 4)³) × 2) + 1))
19066 := (((-9 - (8 + 76)) × -(5 × (43 - 2))) + 1)
19067 := ((9 + 8) + ((7 + ((6 × ((5 × 4) + 3))²)) - 1))
19068 := ((9 + 8) - ((7 + ((6 × ((5 × 4) + 3))²)) × -1))
19069 := ((9 + 8) + (7 + (((6 × ((5 × 4) + 3))²) + 1)))
19070 := (((9 + 8) - 7) × -((6 × -((5 × (4³)) - 2)) + 1))
19071 := (9 - (((87 - 6) + (5⁴)) × -((3²⁺¹)))
19072 := (((9 + 8) - (7^{(6-5)×4})) × -((3²) - 1))
19073 := (9 - (((87 + 6) × -(5 × (43 - 2))) + 1))
19074 := ((9 + (87 + 6)) × -(5 - ((4³) × (2 + 1))))
19075 := (9 - (((87 + 6) × -(5 × (43 - 2))) - 1))
19076 := ((9 - 8) × (76 × -(5 - (4³⁺²⁻¹))))
19077 := ((9 - 8) + (76 × -(5 - (4³⁺²⁻¹))))
19078 := -(9 + 8) × 7 + (6! - 5 - 4) × 3²⁺¹
19079 := (-9 - (8 × -((7 × (((6 + 5) - 4)³) - 2)) - 1))
19080 := (((9 + 8) - 7) × -(6 × -((5 × (4³)) - (2 × 1))))
19081 := ((-9 × -(8 × (((7 + 6) × (5 × 4)) + (3 + 2)))) + 1)
19082 := ((9 - (8 × 7)) × -(6 + ((5 × 4)³⁻²⁺¹)))
19083 := ((-9 × -(((87 - 6) + (5⁴)) × 3)) + 21)
19084 := (9 + ((8 × -76) + (((5 + 4) × 3)²⁺¹)))
19085 := (-9 × 8 + 7 - 6) × 5 + (4! + 3) × (2 + 1)!!
19086 := ((-9 + 87) - ((6 + 5) × -((4 × 3)²⁺¹)))
19087 := ((9 - ((8 × 7) × (((6 + 5) - 4)³) - 2)) × -1)
19088 := ((-9 × (87 - ((65 + 4) × 32))) - 1)
19089 := (9 - ((8 + 7) × -(6 × ((5 × 43) - (2 + 1))))))

$$\begin{aligned}
19090 &:= (1 \times -(23 \times -((4 \times 5) + (6 \times ((7+8) \times 9)))))) \\
19091 &:= (1 - (23 \times -((4 \times 5) + (6 \times ((7+8) \times 9)))))) \\
19092 &:= (1 + (2 - ((3 + (4 \times (5 - (67 \times 8)))) \times 9))) \\
19093 &:= (1 \times -(23 + (4 \times ((5 - (67 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
19094 &:= (1 - (23 + (4 \times ((5 - (67 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
19095 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 \times ((456 \times 7) - 8))) + 9)) \\
19096 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(3 \times ((456 \times 7) - 8))) + 9)) \\
19097 &:= (((1 - 2) + (34 \times 5)) \times (((6+7) \times 8) + 9)) \\
19098 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3 + ((4^5 + 6))) + (7 \times 8)) \times -9)) \\
19099 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3 + ((4^5 + 6))) + (7 \times 8)) \times -9)) \\
19100 &:= ((-12/3) \times (4 + ((5 - (67 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
19101 &:= (12 + ((3 + (4 \times (5 - (67 \times 8)))) \times -9)) \\
19102 &:= (1 - (((234 + (5 + 6)) \times -78) + 9)) \\
19103 &:= ((-1 + (2^3)) \times (4 + (5 \times ((67 \times 8) + 9)))) \\
19104 &:= ((1 - ((2 - ((3+4) \times 5)) \times 6)) \times (7 + 89)) \\
19105 &:= (1 \times -(((2345 + (6 \times 7)) \times -8) - 9)) \\
19106 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})) + (6 \times -(7 + 89))) \\
19107 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 - ((4 + 5) \times (6 + (78 \times 9)))))) \\
19108 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) + (4 \times ((5 - (67 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
19109 &:= (1 - ((2^3) + (4 \times ((5 - (67 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
19110 &:= ((1 - (23 \times 4)) \times -(5 \times -(6 \times (7 \times (8 - 9)))))) \\
19111 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -3) - (4 \times ((5 - (67 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
19112 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) + (4 \times ((5 - (67 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
19113 &:= (1 - ((2^3) \times -(4 + (5 \times ((6 \times 78) + 9)))))) \\
19114 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times (6 + 78)))) / -9)) \\
19115 &:= (1 \times ((2 - 3) - (4 \times ((5 - (67 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
19116 &:= (1 + ((2 - 3) - (4 \times ((5 - (67 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
19117 &:= (((((12^3) + 4) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) - (8 \times -9)) \\
19118 &:= (1 - ((2 - 3) + (4 \times ((5 - (67 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
19119 &:= ((12^3) - (((4^5) + (6 - 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
19120 &:= (1 - (((234 + (5 + 6)) \times -78) - 9)) \\
19121 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) - (4 \times ((5 - (67 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
19122 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 - (4 \times ((5 - (67 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
19123 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4+5}) - ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
19124 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) - ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
19125 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times ((5 - (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times -9)) \\
19126 &:= ((1 - ((2 + 34) \times (5 - (67 \times 8)))) + 9) \\
19127 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -((3 \times (456 \times 7)) - 8)) + 9)) \\
19128 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3^{4+5})) + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times -9)) \\
19129 &:= ((1 + (2 + 34)) \times ((5 + 6) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
19130 &:= (1 + ((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) - 89))) \\
19131 &:= ((((((12^3) + 4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7) - (8 \times -9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
19090 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times -((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)) - 1)) \\
19091 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2)) \times -1) \\
19092 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 76) \times (5 + (4 \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19093 &:= (9 + (8 - (76 \times (5 - (4^{3+2-1})))))) \\
19094 &:= (((-9 + (87 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) \times (3 + 2)) - 1) \\
19095 &:= ((9 - (87 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) \times ((3 + 2) \times -1)) \\
19096 &:= ((98 - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times -4) - 321)) \\
19097 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times (((6 + 5) - 4)^3) - 2)) - 1)) \\
19098 &:= (9 \times ((8 + (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (43 + 2))) - 1)) \\
19099 &:= (98 - (7 - ((6 + 5) \times ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))) \\
19100 &:= ((9 - (8 + 765)) \times ((4 \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
19101 &:= ((((-98 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) - 4) \times -3) - 21) \\
19102 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (-6 + 5!) \times 4! - 32 - 1 \\
19103 &:= (((-9 - 87) \times (6 - (5 \times (43 - 2)))) - 1) \\
19104 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (((6 + 5) - 4)^3) - 2)) - 1) \\
19105 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (((6 + 5) - 4)^3) - 2)) \times 1) \\
19106 &:= (9 - ((8 \times 7) \times -(((6 + 5) - 4)^3) - 2) - 1)) \\
19107 &:= (9 \times -((8 + (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (43 + 2))) \times -1)) \\
19108 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - (((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) - 1))) \\
19109 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - ((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2 \times 1))) \\
19110 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - (((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) + 1))) \\
19111 &:= ((9 - 87) + ((6 - (5^4)) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
19112 &:= ((9876 - (5 \times (4^3))) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
19113 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times (((6 + 5) - 4)^3) - 2)) + 1)) \\
19114 &:= (-9 - (876 - (((5^4) \times 32) - 1))) \\
19115 &:= (((9 + 876) - ((5^4) \times 32)) \times -1) \\
19116 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times ((65 \times -((4 + 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
19117 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - (3 \times 21)))) \\
19118 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(6 + 5)) \times (4 - (3 - 21))) \\
19119 &:= (9 + ((8 + 7) \times -(6 - (5 \times (4^{3+2-1})))))) \\
19120 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6^5) / -4) + (32 \times 1))) \\
19121 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)) + 21))) \\
19122 &:= (9876 - ((5 \times -(43^2)) - 1)) \\
19123 &:= ((-98 \times 7) + (((6 - (5^4)) \times -32) + 1)) \\
19124 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (765 \times -((4 \times (3 \times 2)) + 1))) \\
19125 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 \times ((6 + (5 + 4))^3)) / -21)) \\
19126 &:= (9 - (8 - (765 \times ((4 \times (3 \times 2)) + 1)))) \\
19127 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times (65 \times (43 - (2 - 1)))))) \\
19128 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -((6 \times -(5 + (4 \times 32))) + 1)) \\
19129 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + 5) \times -(4 + (32 + 1)))) \\
19130 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)))) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\
19131 &:= (987 - (((6^5) \times (4 + 3)) / -(2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
19132 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((345 \times 6) + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
19133 &:= ((1 + ((2^3) \times 45)) \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\
19134 &:= (((((12^3) + 4) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) + 89) \\
19135 &:= (1 \times (((((2^3) - 45) \times 6) + 7) \times -89)) \\
19136 &:= ((12^3) + ((4^5) \times -((6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
19137 &:= ((1 - (((2^{3 \times 4}) + 5) \times (6 \times 7)) - 8)) / -9) \\
19138 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((3^{4+5}) - ((67 \times 8) + 9))) \\
19139 &:= ((1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) + 5) \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) / 9) \\
19140 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -(4 \times -((5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)) + 9)))) \\
19141 &:= ((1 - 2) - (34 \times -(5 + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
19142 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (34 \times -(5 + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
19143 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times (4 + (5 \times (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
19144 &:= (1 \times (2 + (34 \times (5 + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
19145 &:= (1 + (2 + (34 \times (5 + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
19146 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 - (4 \times (5 - (67 \times 8)))) \times -9)) \\
19147 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times 6)) - (78 \times -9)) \\
19148 &:= (((((12^3) + 4) \times (5 + 6)) + 7) + 89) \\
19149 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 - ((4 - 567) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
19150 &:= (((12^3) + ((4^5) - 6) \times 7) + (8 \times -9)) \\
19151 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})) + ((67 - 8) \times -9)) \\
19152 &:= (((((1 + 23)^4) \times -5) + (6^7)) / (8 \times -9)) \\
19153 &:= ((12^3) - (((4^5) - (6 - 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
19154 &:= (12 - (34 \times -(5 + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
19155 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 + (45 \times 6)) - 7) \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
19156 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((3^{4+5}) - ((67 \times 8) - 9))) \\
19157 &:= ((-12 \times -(3 + (4 \times 56)) \times 7) + 89) \\
19158 &:= ((1 - (23 \times (4 + 5))) \times -(6 + (78 + 9))) \\
19159 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3^{4+5})) + ((67 \times -8) + 9)) \\
19160 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})) + (6 \times -(78 + 9))) \\
19161 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3 + (4^5))) + (67 + 8)) \times -9)) \\
19162 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3 + (4^5))) + (67 + 8)) \times -9)) \\
19163 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times (78 + 9)))) \\
19164 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times (78 + 9)))) \\
19165 &:= (1 + 2^3) \times (4! + 5) + 6! \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
19166 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times 4! \times (5! + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
19167 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times 6)) + 789) \\
19168 &:= ((12 + (3^{4+5})) + ((67 \times -8) + 9)) \\
19169 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3 \times (456 \times 7))) - (8 + 9))) \\
19170 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times 5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\
19171 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4+5}) - (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
19172 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) - (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
19132 &:= (9 - (876 - (((5^4) \times 32) - 1))) \\
19133 &:= (9 + ((876 - ((5^4) \times 32)) \times -1)) \\
19134 &:= (98 - (7 - (((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) - 1))) \\
19135 &:= (98 + ((7 - ((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2)) \times -1)) \\
19136 &:= ((9 - ((8 - ((7 - 6)^5)^4)) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
19137 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times (6 \times (54 + 3))) - (2 + 1)))) \\
19138 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times -(4 + (32 + 1)))) \\
19139 &:= (9 + ((87 + ((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) - 1)) \\
19140 &:= ((9 + 87) - (((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) \times -1)) \\
19141 &:= (9 + (87 + (((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) + 1))) \\
19142 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((((76 \times 5) - 4) \times -3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
19143 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + (65 \times 4)))) \times (3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
19144 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) - 654) \times -32) - 1) \\
19145 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) - 654) \times -(32 \times 1))) \\
19146 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) - 654) \times -32) + 1) \\
19147 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (((((6 \times 5) + 4)^3) / -2) + 1)) \\
19148 &:= (98 + ((7 + ((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) - 1)) \\
19149 &:= (98 - ((7 + ((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) \times -1)) \\
19150 &:= (98 + (7 + (((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))^2) + 1))) \\
19151 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) - (3 \times 2)))) \times -1) \\
19152 &:= (9 - (((8 + 76) + (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
19153 &:= (9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (54 + 3))) - (2 - 1)))) \\
19154 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + (3 \times -21)) \\
19155 &:= (-98 - (7 - ((6 + 54) \times 321))) \\
19156 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times -43) + 21) \\
19157 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - 5!) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
19158 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times (6 \times (54 + 3)))) + (2 + 1))) \\
19159 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (54 + 3)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
19160 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times (6 \times (54 + 3)))) + (2 - 1))) \\
19161 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((76 - (5 - 43)) \times 21))) \\
19162 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times (6 \times (54 + 3)))) - (2 - 1))) \\
19163 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (54 + 3)))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
19164 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (54 + 3)))) + (2 + 1)) \\
19165 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (7 + ((6 - (5^4)) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19166 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times 6) + 5)) \times ((4 \times -(3^2) - 1)) \\
19167 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7^{(6-5) \times 4}) - 32)) \times -1) \\
19168 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) - (3 \times 2))) + 1)) \\
19169 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) - (3 \times 2)))) \times 1) \\
19170 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) - (3 \times 2)))) + 1) \\
19171 &:= (9 - ((876 - 5) \times -(43 - 21))) \\
19172 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) - 3)) + 21))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
19173 &:= ((1-2) \times -((3^{4+5}) - (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19174 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19175 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19176 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19177 &:= (1 - ((23 + 45) \times -(6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
19178 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -((3 \times (456 \times 7)) + 8)) - 9)) \\
19179 &:= (((1+2)^{3 \times (4+5-6)}) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
19180 &:= (1 - (((2 + (34 + 5)) \times -(6 \times 78)) + 9)) \\
19181 &:= (-1 - (2 \times -((3 \times ((456 \times 7) + 8)) - 9))) \\
19182 &:= (((1+2) + (3 \times 45)) \times (67 + (8 \times 9))) \\
19183 &:= (1 \times (((2 - ((3 + 4)^{5+6-7})) \times -8) - 9)) \\
19184 &:= (((1-2) + ((3^{4+5}) + 6)) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
19185 &:= ((1-2) \times -((3^{4+5}) + (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19186 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -((3 \times (456 \times 7)) + (8 + 9)))) \\
19187 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3^{4+5}) + (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19188 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3^{4+5}) + (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19189 &:= ((1-2) \times -((34 \times 567) - 89)) \\
19190 &:= (((1-2) + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times -(7 - 89))) \\
19191 &:= (1 + (2 - ((34 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 - 89)))))) \\
19192 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -((3 \times ((456 \times 7) + 8))) + 9)) \\
19193 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times (7 - 89)))))) \\
19194 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times (7 - 89)))))) \\
19195 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4-5+6}) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19196 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^{4-5+6}) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19197 &:= ((12 + ((3^{4+5}) + 6)) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
19198 &:= ((1-2) - (((3+4)^{5+6-7}) \times -8) + 9)) \\
19199 &:= ((1-2) \times (((3+4)^{5+6-7}) \times -8) + 9)) \\
19200 &:= (((1-2) + (3^4)) \times -(5 \times -(6 \times (7 - (8 - 9)))))) \\
19201 &:= (1 \times (((2 - ((3 + 4)^{5+6-7})) \times -8) + 9)) \\
19202 &:= (1 + (((2 - ((3 + 4)^{5+6-7})) \times -8) + 9)) \\
19203 &:= ((12 + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times -(7 - 89))) \\
19204 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((34 \times 567) - (8 \times 9)))) \\
19205 &:= (((12^3) + ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) \\
19206 &:= ((1-23) \times (((4 + (5 + 6)) \times 7) - 8) \times -9)) \\
19207 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4+5}) - (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19208 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) - (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19209 &:= (12 - ((3^{4-5+6}) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
19210 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 3) \times 45)) \times ((6 + 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
19211 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19212 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19213 &:= ((1+2) + (34 \times -(5 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
19173 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times ((7^{(6-5)^4}) - 3)) - 2)) \times -1) \\
19174 &:= (98 + (76 \times -(5 - (4^{3+2-1})))) \\
19175 &:= ((-98/7) + ((6 - (5^4)) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
19176 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (6 \times -((5 + (4^3)) - (2 - 1)))) \\
19177 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 76) - (5 + 4)) \times -(32 \times 1))) \\
19178 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 76) - (5 + 4)) \times -32) - 1) \\
19179 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 654) \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
19180 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 \times 5) \times -(4^3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
19181 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) - ((6 + 54) \times -321)) \\
19182 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 + ((6 - (5^4)) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19183 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7^{6+5-4-3}) - 2))) \times -1) \\
19184 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7^{(6-5)^4})) + (32 + 1))) \\
19185 &:= ((9 + (87 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) \times -((3 + 2) \times -1)) \\
19186 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7^{(6-5)^4})) + (32 - 1))) \\
19187 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 76) - ((5 \times -(4^{3 \times 2})) + 1)) \\
19188 &:= ((9 - 87) \times -(6 \times ((5 + (4 + 32)) \times 1))) \\
19189 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
19190 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7^{(6-5)^4}) - 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\
19191 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7^{(6-5)^4}) - 3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
19192 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7^{(6-5)^4}) - 3)) + (2 - 1))) \\
19193 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (7^{(6-5)^4}))) - 3) - 21) \\
19194 &:= (9 + ((8 + 7) \times -(65 - ((4^3) \times 21)))) \\
19195 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7^{(6-5)^4}) - 3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
19196 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7^{(6-5)^4}) - 3)) \times -(2 - 1)) \\
19197 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 - ((6 - (5^4)) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19198 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 - 7)) + ((6 - (5^4)) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
19199 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7^{(6-5)^4}))) \times (3 / -(2 + 1))) \\
19200 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7^{(6-5)^4})) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
19201 &:= ((98 - 7) \times -((6 + (5 \times (43 - 2))) \times -1)) \\
19202 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 7) - (6 - 5)^4) - 3)) / (2 \times -1)) \\
19203 &:= (9 - ((876 - (5 - 43)) \times -21)) \\
19204 &:= (-987 - (((6 + (5^4)) \times -32) + 1)) \\
19205 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 7) - (6 - 5)^4) + 3)) / (2 \times -1)) \\
19206 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) - (5^4)) \times -(32 + 1)) \\
19207 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7^{(6-5)^4})) + ((3^2) + 1))) \\
19208 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7^{(6-5)^4}) \times -((3^2) - 1))) \\
19209 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7^{(6-5)^4}))) - ((3^2) - 1)) \\
19210 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7^{(6-5)^4}))) + ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
19211 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7^{(6-5)^4}))) + (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
19212 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (7^{(6-5)^4}))) - 3) + (2 \times -1)) \\
19213 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7^{(6-5)^4}))) - ((3 + 2) - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
19214 &:= (((((1+2)^{3+4}) + (5 \times 6)) \times -78) / -9) & 19214 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + (3 \times -(2-1))) \\
19215 &:= ((12^3) - (((((4+5) - 6)^7) \times -8) + 9)) & 19215 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7^{6+5-4-3}))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
19216 &:= (1 \times ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 19216 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) - 3) - (2 \times -1)) \\
19217 &:= ((1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - (5 \times -(6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 19217 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) - 3) + (2 + 1)) \\
19218 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5^6))) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 19218 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
19219 &:= (1 \times ((23 \times -(4 - (56 \times (7 + 8)))) - 9)) & 19219 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7^{6+5-4-3}))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
19220 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 + 4)^{5+6-7}) \times -8) - 9)) & 19220 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) - (3 \times -(2-1))) \\
19221 &:= ((1 + (2^{3+4})) \times -((5 \times -6) - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 19221 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
19222 &:= (((12^3) + ((4^5) - 6)) \times -7) \times (8 - 9)) & 19222 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
19223 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (3^4)) \times 5) - 6) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) & 19223 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) - (3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
19224 &:= (1 - (((2 + (3^4)) \times 5) - 6) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) & 19224 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) - ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\
19225 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (3 \times ((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) \times 8)) / 9) & 19225 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + (3^2))) - 1) \\
19226 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times (4 \times ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times 89))))) & 19226 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + (3^2))) \times 1) \\
19227 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) + 6) \times (7 \times 8))) / 9) & 19227 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + (3^2))) + 1) \\
19228 &:= ((12 + (3 \times ((4^5) + 6) \times (7 \times 8))) / 9) & 19228 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 \times 65)) \times 43)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
19229 &:= (12 - (((3 + 4)^{5+6-7}) \times -8) - 9)) & 19229 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 \times 65)) \times 43) + 2)) + 1) \\
19230 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) - (8 \times 9))) & 19230 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 \times 5) \times -(4^3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
19231 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -(4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) + 89)) & 19231 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + 32)) \times -1) \\
19232 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times -9)) & 19232 &:= ((9 - ((8 - (7 \times 65)) \times 43)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
19233 &:= ((12^3) - (((((4+5) - 6)^7) \times -8) - 9)) & 19233 &:= (((9 + (87 \times (6 + (5 \times 43)))) - 2) - 1) \\
19234 &:= ((1 + ((2 + ((3 + 4)^{5+6-7}) \times 8)) + 9) & 19234 &:= ((9 + (87 \times (6 + (5 \times 43)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
19235 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) & 19235 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) - 3) + 21) \\
19236 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) & 19236 &:= (9 - (87 \times -((654/3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
19237 &:= (1 \times ((23 \times -(4 - (56 \times (7 + 8)))) + 9)) & 19237 &:= ((9 + ((87 \times (6 + (5 \times 43))) + 2)) - 1) \\
19238 &:= (1 + ((23 \times -(4 - (56 \times (7 + 8)))) + 9)) & 19238 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
19239 &:= ((1 - ((2 + (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times (7 \times 8))) / -9) & 19239 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + 3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
19240 &:= ((1 - ((23 + 4) \times (5 + 6))) \times -((7 \times 8) + 9)) & 19240 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\
19241 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 45))) \times ((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9))) & 19241 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + 3)) \times (2 - 1)) \\
19242 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 345) \times 6) + (7 \times 8)) \times 9) & 19242 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + 3)) + 2) - 1) \\
19243 &:= (1 + (((2 + 345) \times 6) + (7 \times 8)) \times 9) & 19243 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + 3)) + 2) \times 1) \\
19244 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times -34) \times -((567 + 8) - 9)) & 19244 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + 3)) + 2) + 1) \\
19245 &:= ((12 + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times -9)) & 19245 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) - (6 \times (54 \times 3))) \times -21)) \\
19246 &:= (1 - (((234 - 5) \times -(6 + 78)) - 9)) & 19246 &:= ((-98/7) - ((6 + 54) \times -321)) \\
19247 &:= (1 + (2 + (34 \times ((567 + 8) - 9)))) & 19247 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + (3 \times 2))) \times -1) \\
19248 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -(4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) + (8 \times 9))) & 19248 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7^{(6-5) \times 4}) - (32 - 1))) \\
19249 &:= ((1 + (23 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) + (8 \times -9)) & 19249 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) - (32 \times -1)) \\
19250 &:= ((1 - (2 + 34)) \times -(567 - (8 + 9))) & 19250 &:= ((9 - (8 - 76)) \times -(5 \times -(((4 + 3)^2) + 1))) \\
19251 &:= (((12^3) / -4) + (((5 \times (6 - 7)) + 8)^9)) & 19251 &:= ((9 + (8 + 76)) \times -((5 + (4^3)) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
19252 &:= (1 - (23 \times -((4 + 5) \times (6 + (78 + 9)))) & 19252 &:= (-9 + ((8 - 7) + ((6 + 54) \times 321))) \\
19253 &:= (1 \times -23 + (4 \times (5 - (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 19253 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 - ((6 + 54) \times 321))) \\
19254 &:= (1 - (23 + (4 \times (5 - (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 19254 &:= (9 + ((8 + 7) \times -((6 - 5) - (4 \times 321))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
19255 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 \times 6))) - (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\
19256 &:= (12 - (34 \times -((567 + 8) - 9))) \\
19257 &:= ((12 + (3 \times 45)) \times -((6 \times -7) - 89)) \\
19258 &:= (1 - (((23 + (4 \times 56)) \times -78) + 9)) \\
19259 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((34 \times 567) - (8 + 9)))) \\
19260 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -(((4 + 56) \times 7) + 8) \times 9)) \\
19261 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) \times -(((4 + 56) \times 7) + 8) \times 9)) \\
19262 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (34 \times 567)) - 8) - 9 \\
19263 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (34 \times 567)) - (8 + 9))) \\
19264 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((3 + 4) - (567 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
19265 &:= (1 + (2 \times -((3 + 4) - (567 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
19266 &:= (1 \times -((((2 \times 3)^4) - (5 + 6)) \times -(7 + 8) + 9)) \\
19267 &:= (1 - (((((2 \times 3)^4) - (5 + 6)) \times -(7 + 8)) + 9)) \\
19268 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) + (4 \times (5 - (67 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19269 &:= (1 - ((2^3) + (4 \times (5 - (67 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19270 &:= (((1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times -(5 \times -((6 \times 7) - 89))) \\
19271 &:= (1 \times -((2 + 3) + (4 \times (5 - (67 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19272 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times ((3^4) \times 5)) - 6)) \times -(7 + (8 + 9))) \\
19273 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (3 + (4 \times (5 - (67 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19274 &:= ((12 + 34) \times (5 + (6 \times (78 - 9)))) \\
19275 &:= (1 \times (((23 + (4 \times 56)) \times 78) + 9)) \\
19276 &:= ((1 + 2) - (3 + (4 \times (5 - (67 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19277 &:= (((1 - 2) + (34 \times 567)) \times -(8 - 9)) \\
19278 &:= ((1 - (23 \times (4 \times 5))) \times -(6 \times -(7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\
19279 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^4))) - ((5 \times (6^7)) / -(8 \times 9))) \\
19280 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^4)) \times ((5 \times -(6 - (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
19281 &:= ((12 + (3^{4+5})) + (6 \times -(78 - 9))) \\
19282 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -3) + (4 \times (5 - (67 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19283 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -3) + (4 \times (5 - (67 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19284 &:= (1 \times -((((2 \times 3)^4) - (5 + 6)) \times -(7 + 8) - 9)) \\
19285 &:= (1 - (((((2 \times 3)^4) - (5 + 6)) \times -(7 + 8)) - 9)) \\
19286 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times (4 + (567 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
19287 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 + ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
19288 &:= (1 - (((2345 + 67) \times -8) + 9)) \\
19289 &:= (((12^3) + ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7) - (8 + 9) \\
19290 &:= (((12^3) \times (4 + 5)) - (6 \times -(7 \times 89))) \\
19291 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19292 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19293 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19294 &:= (((12^3) + ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7) - (8 \times -9) \\
19295 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 - (4 - 5)) \times (67 \times (8 \times 9))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
19255 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (54 + 3)) + 2)))) \times -1) \\
19256 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7^{(6-5)} \times 4) + (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\
19257 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7^{(6-5)} \times 4) + (3 + 2)))) \times 1) \\
19258 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7^{(6-5)} \times 4) + (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\
19259 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times (6 + 54))) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
19260 &:= (9 - ((87 + 6) \times -((5 + (4^3)) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
19261 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((76 + 5) \times -((4 + 3) \times 2)) + 1)) \\
19262 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7^{(6-5)} \times 4) + 3)) - 21)) \\
19263 &:= ((9 - (876 \times (54 - 32))) \times -1) \\
19264 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7^{(6-5)} \times 4) + (3 \times 2))) + 1)) \\
19265 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7^{(6-5)} \times 4) + (3 \times 2)))) \times 1) \\
19266 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7^{(6-5)} \times 4) + (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\
19267 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 + ((6 + 54) \times 321))) \\
19268 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 + ((6 + 54) \times 321))) \\
19269 &:= (9 \times (((8 + 76) \times (54 - 3)) / 2) - 1) \\
19270 &:= (9 + ((8 - 7) + ((6 + 54) \times 321))) \\
19271 &:= (((-9 \times -(87 - 6)) - ((5^4) \times 32)) \times -1) \\
19272 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times ((6 \times (54 + 3)) + 2))) + 1)) \\
19273 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(7 \times ((6 \times (54 + 3)) + (2 \times 1)))))) \\
19274 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times ((6 \times (54 + 3)) + 2))) - 1)) \\
19275 &:= ((9 - (8 + 76)) \times -(5 + (4 \times (3 \times 21)))) \\
19276 &:= ((-98 - 7) + (6 + ((5^4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19277 &:= (-98 - (((7 - 6) \times 5^4) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
19278 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) \times (43 - (2 - 1))) \\
19279 &:= ((9 - ((87 + 6) \times ((5^4) - 3))) / -(2 + 1)) \\
19280 &:= ((9 + ((8 - ((7 - 6)^5)^4)) \times ((3^2) - 1)) \\
19281 &:= ((9 + (876 \times (54 - 32))) \times 1) \\
19282 &:= ((9 + ((8 \times 76) + 5)) \times -(((4^3) / -2) + 1)) \\
19283 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times ((4^3) - 2)) + 1) \\
19284 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times -((6 - 5) + (4 \times 321)))) \\
19285 &:= ((9 + ((87 + 6) \times ((5^4) - 3))) / (2 + 1)) \\
19286 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -(7 \times 6)) - ((5^4) \times 32)) \times -1) \\
19287 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times (65 - 4)) + 3) \times -21)) \\
19288 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7^{(6-5)} \times 4) + (3^2))) + 1)) \\
19289 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7^{(6-5)} \times 4) + (3^2)))) \times 1) \\
19290 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7^{(6-5)} \times 4) + (3^2))) - 1)) \\
19291 &:= (9 + (((87 + 6) \times ((5^4) - 3)) / (2 + 1))) \\
19292 &:= (9 - (((((8 \times 7) + 6) \times ((5^4) - 3)) / -2) - 1)) \\
19293 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (76 + ((5 + 4)^3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
19294 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times -6) + ((5^4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19295 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((76 + 5) \times -((4 + 3) \times 2)) - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
19296 &:= (((1+2) - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 \times -(7 - (8 - 9)))) & 19296 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -(6 \times -(5 + ((4 \times 32) + 1)))) \\
19297 &:= (1 \times -(23 \times -((4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + (8 - 9)))) & 19297 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) + ((3^2) + 1)))) \\
19298 &:= (1 - (23 \times -((4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + (8 - 9)))) & 19298 &:= (-9 + ((8 - 76) + ((5^4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19299 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 \times (45 \times 6)) - 7) \times -8) - 9) & 19299 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times -(6 + (5 \times (4^{3+2-1})))) \\
19300 &:= (1 + (23 - (4 \times (5 - (67 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 19300 &:= ((9 - 8) - (76 - ((5^4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19301 &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times -(4 - (56 \times (78 - 9)))) & 19301 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 \times (6! - 5) \times 4 - 3!! \times (2 - 1) \\
19302 &:= (((1 + 2) - (3 \times (4 + ((5^6) \times 7)))) / -(8 + 9)) & 19302 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (6 + ((5^4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19303 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -(4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) + (8 + 9))) & 19303 &:= ((9 - 87) + (6 + ((5^4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19304 &:= (((1 + (23 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - 8) - 9) & 19304 &:= (9 - (((((8 \times 76) - 5) \times (4^3)) / -2) + 1)) \\
19305 &:= (((((12^3) + ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7) + 8) - 9) & 19305 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + (65 \times 4)))) \times -(3 \times -(2 + 1))) \\
19306 &:= (((((12^3) + ((4^5) + 6)) \times -7) \times (8 - 9)) & 19306 &:= (98 - ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) \times -((3^2) - 1))) \\
19307 &:= (((((12^3) + ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7) - (8 - 9)) & 19307 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) - ((6 + 54) \times -321)) \\
19308 &:= (12 - ((3 - (4 - 5)) \times -(67 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 19308 &:= ((((-98 \times -7) + 6) - ((5^4) \times 32)) \times -1) \\
19309 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) - (((4 \times 56) - 7) \times 89))) & 19309 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) - (6^5)) / 4) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
19310 &:= (((12^3) - 4) - (((5^6) + 7) / 8) \times -9) & 19310 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times -((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)) + 1)) \\
19311 &:= (1 \times ((23 \times ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)) & 19311 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times (5 \times 43)) - 2))) \times -1) \\
19312 &:= (1 + ((23 \times ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)) & 19312 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((76 - 5) \times -(4 \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
19313 &:= ((1 - (23 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times -(7 \times -(8 - 9))) & 19313 &:= (((9 - (8 - (7 - 6))) - (5^4)) \times -(32 - 1)) \\
19314 &:= (1 \times -((2 - ((345 \times 6) + 78)) \times 9)) & 19314 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times -((6 \times (5 \times 43)) - (2 + 1)))) \\
19315 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) & 19315 &:= (((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times 6) - ((5^4) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
19316 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) & 19316 &:= (9 + ((8 - 76) + ((5^4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19317 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3^4) + 56) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) & 19317 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 \times -(5 + (4^3))) + (2 + 1))) \\
19318 &:= (((12^3) + 4) - (((5^6) + 7) / 8) \times -9) & 19318 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (7 + 6)) - (5^4)) \times -32) - 1) \\
19319 &:= ((1 - (23 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) \times (8 - 9)) & 19319 &:= ((9 + (((8 + (7 + 6)) - (5^4)) \times 32)) \times -1) \\
19320 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9)) & 19320 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 + ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)))^2) - 1)) \\
19321 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -(4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) + (8 - 9))) & 19321 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 + ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)))^2) \times -1)) \\
19322 &:= (((1 + (23 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - 8) + 9) & 19322 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 + ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)))^2) \times -1)) \\
19323 &:= (((((12^3) + ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7) + 8) + 9) & 19323 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((7 + ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)))^2) + 1)) \\
19324 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) + (4 \times (5 + (67 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 19324 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -(6 \times ((5 \times (4 + 3)) + 2))) - 1)) \\
19325 &:= (1 + ((2^3) + (4 \times (5 + (67 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 19325 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - ((6 + 54) \times 321))) \\
19326 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) - (6 - (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) & 19326 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times 6) + (5^4)) \times 3) + 21) \\
19327 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) - (6 - (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) & 19327 &:= ((9 - (8 - 76)) \times -(5 - (4^{3+2-1}))) \\
19328 &:= (1 \times ((2^{3+4}) \times -(5 - (67 + 89)))) & 19328 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times -((6 \times (5 \times 43)) - 2)) + 1)) \\
19329 &:= (12 - (((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9)) & 19329 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times (76 - 5)) / 4) - 3)^2) - 1) \\
19330 &:= (1 + ((2 + ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times 67)) \times -(8 + 9)) & 19330 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times -((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)) - 1)) \\
19331 &:= (12 + (3 + (4 \times (5 + (67 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 19331 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times (76 - 5)) / 4) - 3)^2) + 1) \\
19332 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times -(((4^5) - (6 - (7 \times 8))) \times -9)) & 19332 &:= ((98 + (76 + 5)) \times -(4 \times -(3^{2+1}))) \\
19333 &:= (-1 + (2 + (((345 \times 6) + 78) \times 9)) & 19333 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 \times -6) + ((5^4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19334 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((345 \times 6) + 78) \times 9)) & 19334 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6 + ((5^4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19335 &:= (1 + (2 + (((345 \times 6) + 78) \times 9)) & 19335 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 - 7)) + 6) \times (5 + (4 \times 321))) \\
19336 &:= ((1 + ((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 6)) \times -(7 - (8 - 9))) & 19336 &:= (9 + (((8 + (7 + 6)) - (5^4)) \times -32) - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
19337 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)))) & 19337 &:= (((9 + 8) + ((7 + ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)))^2)) - 1) \\
19338 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) - (6 - (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) & 19338 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7 + ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)))^2) \times -1)) \\
19339 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) - (6 - (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) & 19339 &:= (9 + (8 + (((7 + ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)))^2) + 1))) \\
19340 &:= (1 + (23 + (4 \times (5 + (67 \times (8 \times 9))))) & 19340 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6^5)/ -4) + ((3^2) + 1))) \\
19341 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3^{4+5})) + ((6 \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9)) & 19341 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 \times 43)))) \times -(2 - 1)) \\
19342 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) + (67 \times -(8 + 9))) & 19342 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 \times 43))) + 2)) - 1) \\
19343 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (4 \times -(5 + (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 19343 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 \times 43))) + 2)) \times -1) \\
19344 &:= (1 \times ((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -(6 \times (7 - (8 - 9)))) & 19344 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7^{(6-5) \times 4})) \times ((3^2) - 1)) \\
19345 &:= (1 + ((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -(6 \times (7 - (8 - 9)))) & 19345 &:= (9 - (8 + (((7 - 6) - (5^4)) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19346 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(34 + (567 \times (8 + 9)))) & 19346 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times -((65 \times 43) - 21))) \\
19347 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(34 + (567 \times (8 + 9)))) & 19347 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 + ((5 + 4)^3)))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
19348 &:= (1 \times ((23 \times -4) + ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) & 19348 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 + (7 \times (6 \times (54 - 3)))))) - 2) \times 1) \\
19349 &:= (1 + ((23 \times -4) + ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) & 19349 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 + (7 \times (6 \times (54 - 3)))))) - 2) + 1) \\
19350 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times -(((5 \times 6) + (7 \times 8)) \times -9)) & 19350 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6^5)/ -4) + (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
19351 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (34 \times 567)) - (8 \times -9)) & 19351 &:= (98 - (7 - ((6 + 54) \times 321))) \\
19352 &:= ((1 - ((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 6)) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) & 19352 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times 65)) \times -((43 - 2) \times -1)) \\
19353 &:= (1 - ((2 + ((34 + 5) \times 6)) \times (7 - 89))) & 19353 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times -((5 + 4) - 321))) \\
19354 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4+5}) - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) & 19354 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 76)) \times (5^4))/ -3) - 21) \\
19355 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) & 19355 &:= ((-98/7) - (6 - ((5^4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19356 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((3^{4+5}) - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) & 19356 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1})) \\
19357 &:= (1 \times -((2 + (3^4)) - ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) & 19357 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 \times 43)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
19358 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3^4)) - ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) & 19358 &:= (((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 \times 43)))) - 2) + 1) \\
19359 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) & 19359 &:= (9 + ((8 + 7) \times -(6 - (54 \times (3 + 21)))))) \\
19360 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7)) \times 8)) - 9) & 19360 &:= (((9 - (8 - 7)) - ((6^5)/4)) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
19361 &:= (1 \times (2 - ((3^4) - ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) & 19361 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 \times 43)))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
19362 &:= (1 + (2 - ((3^4) - ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) & 19362 &:= ((9 - 87) - (((6^5)/4) \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
19363 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times -(67 \times (8 + 9)))) & 19363 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((76 \times -(5 - (4 \times (3 + 2)))) - 1)) \\
19364 &:= (((1 - 2) - (((3^4) \times 5) + 6)) \times ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & 19364 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 \times -(5 + (4^3))) + (2 \times 1))) \\
19365 &:= (1 \times (2 - ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times (67 \times (8 + 9)))) & 19365 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times (65 + 4)))) \times -((3 + 2) \times -1)) \\
19366 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3)^4) \times -((5 \times 6) - (7 - 8))) + 9) & 19366 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times (65 + 4)))) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1) \\
19367 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3)^4) \times -((5 \times 6) - (7 - 8))) + 9) & 19367 &:= ((-98/7) + (6 + ((5^4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19368 &:= ((12 + (3^{4+5})) + ((6 \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9)) & 19368 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 76) - 5) \times 4)) \times ((3^2) - 1)) \\
19369 &:= ((1 - (((2 + 3) \times ((4^5) - (6^7)))/8))/9 & 19369 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5^4) - 3))/(2 \times -1)) \\
19370 &:= ((1 + ((23 + 4) \times (5 + 6))) \times ((7 \times 8) + 9)) & 19370 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 - ((6^5)/4)) \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
19371 &:= (12 - ((3^4) - ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) & 19371 &:= (9 - (8 + ((7 - ((6^5)/4)) \times ((3^2) + 1)))) \\
19372 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -34) + ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) & 19372 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5^4) + 3))/(2 \times -1)) \\
19373 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -34) + ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) & 19373 &:= ((9 - (((87 + 6) \times (5^4) + 3))/ - (2 + 1)) \\
19374 &:= (((1 - 2) + (((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times 8) - 9) & 19374 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times -((6 \times (5 \times 43)) + (2 - 1)))) \\
19375 &:= (((1 + 2) - 34) \times (5 \times -(6 + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 19375 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 - 6) - ((5^4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19376 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})) + (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times -9)) & 19376 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7 - 6)) + ((5^4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19377 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - (((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7)) \times 8) - 9)) & 19377 &:= (((9 + ((87 + 6) \times (5^4))) - 3)/(2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
19378 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7)) \times 8)) + 9) \\
19379 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\
19380 &:= (((1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) - 5) \times -((6 \times (7 - 8)) - 9)) \\
19381 &:= (-1 + (2 + (34 \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9))))) \\
19382 &:= ((1 - 23) \times ((4 \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) - 9)) \\
19383 &:= ((1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5 \times (6^7)))/8))/ - 9) \\
19384 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3)^4) \times -((5 \times 6) - (7 - 8))) - 9)) \\
19385 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3)^4) \times -((5 \times 6) - (7 - 8))) - 9)) \\
19386 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times ((4^5) - (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\
19387 &:= (12 - (((((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times -8) + 9)) \\
19388 &:= (-1 - (23 \times -(((4 + 5) \times 6) + 789))) \\
19389 &:= ((12 + (3^{4+5})) + (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times -9)) \\
19390 &:= (1 - (23 \times -(((4 + 5) \times 6) + 789))) \\
19391 &:= (1 \times -((((2 + ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) - 7) \times -8) + 9)) \\
19392 &:= (1 - (((2 + ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) - 7) \times -8) + 9)) \\
19393 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (((((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times -8) - 9)) \\
19394 &:= (-12 - (34 - ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
19395 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) \times -((4 + 5) - ((6^7)/(8 \times 9)))) \\
19396 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times -8) - 9)) \\
19397 &:= (1 \times -((2 - ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times 67)) \times -((8 + 9))) \\
19398 &:= (1 - ((2 - ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times 67)) \times -((8 + 9))) \\
19399 &:= (123 + (4 \times -((5 - (67 \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
19400 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})) + (6 \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
19401 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times -((34 - 5) \times -((678 - 9))) \\
19402 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((3 - (45 + 67)) \times 89))) \\
19403 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -((4 + (56 \times (7 + 8)))) + 9)) \\
19404 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3^{4+5})) + (6 \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
19405 &:= (12 - (((((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times -8) - 9)) \\
19406 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times ((5 \times -((6 - 7) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
19407 &:= ((1 - (((((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 \times 8)))/ - 9) \\
19408 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -((3 - ((4 + 567) \times (8 + 9))))) \\
19409 &:= ((1 + 2) - (34 - ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
19410 &:= ((1 + (((2 + ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) - 7) \times 8)) + 9) \\
19411 &:= (1 \times -((2 + (((3^4) \times 5) + 6)) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
19412 &:= (1 - ((2 + (((3^4) \times 5) + 6)) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
19413 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3+4} - (5 \times 6)) \times -((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
19414 &:= ((1 - 23) - (4 - ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
19415 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) \times (45 - ((6^7)/8)))/ - 9)) \\
19416 &:= (((1 + 2) - ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -((7 - (8 - 9))) \\
19417 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) - ((5 \times (6^7))/ - (8 \times 9))) \\
19418 &:= (12 - (34 - ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
19378 &:= (((9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5^4))) - 3)/ - (2 \times -1)) \\
19379 &:= ((9 + (((87 + 6) \times (5^4)) + 3))/(2 + 1)) \\
19380 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times -((54 \times (3 \times 2)) - 1))) \\
19381 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5^4)) + 3))/ - (2 \times -1)) \\
19382 &:= ((9 + (((87 + 6) \times (5^4))/3)) + (2 \times -1)) \\
19383 &:= ((98 - 7) \times -((6 \times -((5 \times (4 + 3))) - (2 + 1))) \\
19384 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times -76) + (((5^4) \times 32) + 1))) \\
19385 &:= ((9 + ((8 - 7)^6)) - ((5^4) \times -((32 - 1))) \\
19386 &:= ((9 + (((87 + 6) \times (5^4))/3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
19387 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 - ((6^5)/4)) \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
19388 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times -((6 \times (5 \times 43)) + 2)) + 1)) \\
19389 &:= (9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times (5 \times 43)) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
19390 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) - (6^5))/4)) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\
19391 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) + (6 + ((5^4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19392 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7 - 6)) - ((5^4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19393 &:= (9 - ((8 \times 7) - (((6^5)/4) \times ((3^2) + 1))) \\
19394 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - (7 + 6)) + (5 \times 432))) - 1) \\
19395 &:= (9 - (((87 + 6) + (5^4)) \times -((3^{2+1}))) \\
19396 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - (7 + 6)) + (5 \times 432))) + 1) \\
19397 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((76 \times (5 - (4 \times (3 + 2)))) - 1)) \\
19398 &:= (((9 + 87) - (6 \times ((54 + 3)^2))) \times -1) \\
19399 &:= (((-9 - ((87 + 6) \times (5^4)))/ - 3) + 21) \\
19400 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6^5)/ - 4) + ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\
19401 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 76)) - ((5^4) \times -((32 \times 1))) \\
19402 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -76) + (((5^4) \times 32) + 1))) \\
19403 &:= (((98 - 7) - (6 \times ((54 + 3)^2))) \times -1) \\
19404 &:= ((9 - ((87 - 6) \times 5)) \times (((4 + 3)^2) \times -1)) \\
19405 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) + (6 + ((5^4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19406 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 - 6) + (5^4)) \times -((32 - 1))) \\
19407 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 - 6) + (5^4)) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19408 &:= ((-9 \times 87) - (((6 + (5^4)) \times -32) + 1)) \\
19409 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -((6 + ((5 \times 43) + 2))) + 1)) \\
19410 &:= ((9 - 87) - (6 \times -(((54 + 3)^2) - 1))) \\
19411 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (((65 + 4) \times -((3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
19412 &:= (-98 - ((7 + ((6^5)/4)) \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
19413 &:= (9 \times (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times -54) + 321)) \\
19414 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((7 + (6 \times (5 \times 4))) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
19415 &:= (9 + (((8 - 7)^6) + (5^4)) \times (32 - 1)) \\
19416 &:= (9 + ((87 - (6 \times ((54 + 3)^2))) \times -1)) \\
19417 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -6) - ((5^4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19418 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times ((6^{5-4+3}) - 2)) - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 19419 &:= ((-1-2) + ((34+5) \times -(6-(7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 19420 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 + ((4+567) \times (8+9)))))) \\
 19421 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -(4 + (56 \times (7+8)))) - 9)) \\
 19422 &:= ((1-23) + (4 + ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
 19423 &:= ((-1+2) + ((34+5) \times -(6-(7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 19424 &:= (1 \times ((2-34) \times -(((5+6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
 19425 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times 3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 + ((7-8) \times 9)))) \\
 19426 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -(3+4)) + ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
 19427 &:= ((1-2) + ((3 \times -4) + ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
 19428 &:= ((1-2) \times -((3 \times -4) + ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
 19429 &:= (1 \times -(2 + (((3^4) - ((5 \times (6^7))/8))/9))) \\
 19430 &:= (1 - (2 + (((3^4) - ((5 \times (6^7))/8))/9))) \\
 19431 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3) + 4) - ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
 19432 &:= (((1-2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
 19433 &:= (1 \times (2 - (((3^4) - ((5 \times (6^7))/8))/9))) \\
 19434 &:= (1 + (2 - (((3^4) - ((5 \times (6^7))/8))/9))) \\
 19435 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + (5 - 6)) \times (7 + 8)) + 9) \\
 19436 &:= ((1+2) - ((3+4) - ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
 19437 &:= ((1 - (((2 \times 3)^4 \times 5)) \times -((6 \times (7 - 8)) + 9)) \\
 19438 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) - (4 - ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
 19439 &:= (1 + ((2 \times (3 - 4)) + ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
 19440 &:= (1 - (((2 + (3 + 4)) - ((5 \times (6^7))/8))/9)) \\
 19441 &:= (1 \times (((2 + (3 + 4)) + ((5 \times (6^7))/8))/9)) \\
 19442 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times (3 - 4)) - ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
 19443 &:= (1 - ((2 \times (3 - 4)) - ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
 19444 &:= ((1+2) - ((3-4) - ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
 19445 &:= (1 \times -(((2+3) \times ((4+5) + ((6^7)/8)))/ - 9)) \\
 19446 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) + (4 + ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
 19447 &:= ((1-2) \times -((3+4) + ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
 19448 &:= (((1-2) - ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -(7 - (8 - 9))) \\
 19449 &:= (((12^3) \times -(4+5)) - (((6^7)/ - 8) - 9)) \\
 19450 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times 3) + 4) + ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
 19451 &:= (1 + (((2 \times 3) + 4) + ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
 19452 &:= (((((1+2)^3) \times -4) - ((5 \times (6^7))/8))/ - 9) \\
 19453 &:= (12 - ((3 - 4) - ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
 19454 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times -(3+4)) - ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
 19455 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times 3^4)) \times -(5 \times (6 + ((7-8) \times 9)))) \\
 19456 &:= (1 \times -((2^{3+4}) \times -(56 + (7 + 89)))) \\
 19457 &:= (1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times -(56 + (7 + 89)))) \\
 19458 &:= ((1+2) \times -((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times -(6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
 19459 &:= ((12+3) + (4 + ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 19419 &:= (9 + ((8+7) \times ((6^{5-4+3}) - (2 \times 1)))) \\
 19420 &:= (((9+8) - 7) \times -(((6^5)/ - 4) + (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
 19421 &:= ((9 - (((8+7) \times ((6^5) - 4))/(3 \times 2))) \times -1) \\
 19422 &:= ((9 - (((8+7) \times (6^5))/(4 \times 3))) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
 19423 &:= (9 + (8 + (((7-6) + (5^4)) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
 19424 &:= (((-9 - 87) \times 6) - ((5^4) \times -(32 \times 1))) \\
 19425 &:= ((98 + 7) \times ((6 \times -(5 - (4 + 32))) - 1)) \\
 19426 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - ((6 + (5^4)) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
 19427 &:= (((-9876 + (54 \times 3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
 19428 &:= (9 - (((8+7) \times -(6^{5-4+3})) + 21)) \\
 19429 &:= (((-9876 + (54 \times 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
 19430 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - ((6^5)/4) \times -(3^2) + 1) \\
 19431 &:= ((9+8) \times -(((76 \times 5) + (4 - 3)) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
 19432 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 76) - (5 - 4)) \times -32) + 1) \\
 19433 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 - (((6^5)/4) \times ((3^2) + 1)))) \\
 19434 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - (((6^5)/4) \times ((3^2) + 1)))) \\
 19435 &:= (9 + (8 + (7 \times ((65 \times 43) - 21)))) \\
 19436 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (76 \times 5)) \times -(43 \times -(2 - 1))) \\
 19437 &:= (((9 - (8 - (7 - 6))) + (5^4)) \times (32 - 1)) \\
 19438 &:= (9 - (((8+7) \times ((6^5) - 4)) / -(3 \times 2)) + 1) \\
 19439 &:= (9 - (((8+7) \times ((6^5) - 4)) / -(3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 19440 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -(((6^5)/4) \times -(3^2) + 1)) \\
 19441 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (((6^5)/4) \times -(3^2) + 1)) \\
 19442 &:= (98 + (((7-6) - (5^4)) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
 19443 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + 6)) - (((5^4) \times -32) - 1)) \\
 19444 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 76) \times 5)) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
 19445 &:= (((((-9 \times 87) + 6) \times -5) + 4) \times -(3 + 2) \times -1)) \\
 19446 &:= ((9 + ((8+7) \times (6^{5-4+3}))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 19447 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 + (((6^5)/4) \times ((3^2) + 1)))) \\
 19448 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 + (((6^5)/4) \times ((3^2) + 1)))) \\
 19449 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - 7)^6)) \times -((5 \times -432) - 1)) \\
 19450 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + ((6^5)/4) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\
 19451 &:= ((9 + (((8+7) \times (6^{5-4+3})) + 2)) \times 1) \\
 19452 &:= ((9 + (((8+7) \times (6^{5-4+3})) + 2)) + 1) \\
 19453 &:= (((9+8) + (76 \times 5)) \times -(((4+3)^2) \times -1)) \\
 19454 &:= (-98 - ((7 \times -((65 \times 43) - 2)) - 1)) \\
 19455 &:= ((98 - (((7^6) - (5^4))/3))/ (2 \times -1)) \\
 19456 &:= (-98 - (7 - ((6 + (5^4)) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
 19457 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 + (65 + 4)) \times 32) - 1))) \\
 19458 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times -((6 - ((54 + 3)^2)) \times -1)) \\
 19459 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5)) \times ((4^3) - (2 + 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 19460 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) \times 4) + ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
 19461 &:= (1 + (((2 + 3) \times 4) + ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
 19462 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((3^{4+5}) - ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 19463 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (4 - ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
 19464 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
 19465 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) - ((5 \times (6^7))/ - (8 \times 9))) \\
 19466 &:= (1 \times -((234 + ((5 \times (6^7))/8)) / - 9)) \\
 19467 &:= ((1 + 2) \times - (3 \times -((4^5) + (67 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 19468 &:= (((12^3) - 4) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 \times - (8 \times 9)) \\
 19469 &:= (1 - ((2^3) - (4 \times ((5 + (67 \times 8) \times 9)))) \\
 19470 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -3) + (4 \times ((5 + (67 \times 8) \times 9)))) \\
 19471 &:= (1 \times (((2 - ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times -8) - 9)) \\
 19472 &:= (1 + (((2 - ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times -8) - 9)) \\
 19473 &:= (1 + (((2^3) \times 4) + ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
 19474 &:= ((12 + (3^{4+5})) + ((6 + 7) \times - (8 + 9))) \\
 19475 &:= (1 \times ((2 - 3) + (4 \times ((5 + (67 \times 8) \times 9)))) \\
 19476 &:= (1 + ((2 - 3) + (4 \times ((5 + (67 \times 8) \times 9)))) \\
 19477 &:= ((1 + 2) + (34 + ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9)))) \\
 19478 &:= (1 - ((2 - 3) - (4 \times ((5 + (67 \times 8) \times 9)))) \\
 19479 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^4) - 5)) \times (6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 19480 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -((34 - 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9)) \\
 19481 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times ((5 \times - (6 \times 7)) + 89)) \\
 19482 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 + (4 \times ((5 + (67 \times 8) \times 9)))) \\
 19483 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -3) + (4 \times (56 \times (78 + 9)))) \\
 19484 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) + (4 \times ((5 + (67 \times 8) \times 9)))) \\
 19485 &:= (1 + ((2^3) + (4 \times ((5 + (67 \times 8) \times 9)))) \\
 19486 &:= ((1 - 2) - (((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times -8) + 9) \\
 19487 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times -8) + 9) \\
 19488 &:= (((1 - 2) - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 \times - (7 - (8 - 9)))) \\
 19489 &:= (1 \times (((2 - ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times -8) + 9)) \\
 19490 &:= (1 + (((2 - ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times -8) + 9)) \\
 19491 &:= (12 + (3 + (4 \times ((5 + (67 \times 8) \times 9)))) \\
 19492 &:= (1 \times - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) - ((6 + (7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
 19493 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) - ((6 + (7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
 19494 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times -9)) \\
 19495 &:= (1 \times - ((23 \times -((4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + 8)) + 9)) \\
 19496 &:= (1 - ((23 \times -((4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + 8)) + 9)) \\
 19497 &:= ((1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 \times (6^7)))/8)) / 9) \\
 19498 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -((34 - 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\
 19499 &:= (12 - (((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times -8) + 9) \\
 19500 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times 3^4) + 5)) \times ((6 \times (7 - 8)) - 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 19460 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6^5) / -4) - (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
 19461 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) - 6543)) / - (2 + 1)) \\
 19462 &:= (((9 + (87 \times 6)) - 5) \times -((4 \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
 19463 &:= (-9 - (8 \times -((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) + (32 + 1)))) \\
 19464 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + (((6^5) / 4) \times ((3^2) + 1)))) \\
 19465 &:= ((9 - ((87 + 6) \times ((5^4) + 3))) / - (2 + 1)) \\
 19466 &:= (9 - (((87 + 65) \times -(4 \times 32)) - 1)) \\
 19467 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) \times - (3 \times -21)) \\
 19468 &:= (98 + ((7 - ((6^5) / 4)) \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
 19469 &:= ((98 - ((7 \times (65 \times 43)) + 2)) \times -1) \\
 19470 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6^5) / -4) - (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
 19471 &:= ((9 + ((87 + 6) \times ((5^4) + 3))) / (2 + 1)) \\
 19472 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) + 32)) + 1)) \\
 19473 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) + 32))) \times 1) \\
 19474 &:= ((98 - 7) \times ((6^{(5+4) / 3}) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 19475 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times (5 \times -((43 - 2) \times 1))) \\
 19476 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times ((5^4) + 3)) / 2)) - 1) \\
 19477 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times ((5^4) + 3)) / 2)) \times 1) \\
 19478 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times ((5^4) + 3)) / 2)) + 1) \\
 19479 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times -((6^{5-4+3}) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
 19480 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times -((6^{5-4+3}) + 2)) - 1)) \\
 19481 &:= ((9 - 8) \times - (7 - (6 \times (((54 + 3)^2) - 1)))) \\
 19482 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - (6 \times (((54 + 3)^2) - 1)))) \\
 19483 &:= (9 - (87 - ((6 + (5^4)) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
 19484 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) - (6 \times ((54 + 3)^2))) \times -1) \\
 19485 &:= ((-9 - 87) - ((65 - 4) \times -321)) \\
 19486 &:= ((9 - 8) \times - (7 - ((6 \times ((54 + 3)^2)) - 1))) \\
 19487 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 - (6 \times ((54 + 3)^2))) \times -1)) \\
 19488 &:= ((98 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5 + ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 19489 &:= (9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3)) - 2)) - 1))) \\
 19490 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) + (6^5)) / 4)) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
 19491 &:= (((9^{8+7-6-5}) - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 19492 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((7 \times - (65 \times 43)) + (2 - 1))) \\
 19493 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times ((6 \times ((54 + 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
 19494 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -6) \times (((54 + 3)^2) \times -1)) \\
 19495 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times -((6 \times -((54 + 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
 19496 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - ((6 \times -((54 + 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
 19497 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 76) + (5 - 4)) \times 32)) \times 1) \\
 19498 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 - (6 \times (((54 + 3)^2) - 1)))) \\
 19499 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 - ((6 + 5) \times 4)) \times (32 - 1))) \\
 19500 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times (65 \times -(((4 + 3)^2) + 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
19501 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 + (4 \times (5 + (67 \times 8)))) \times 9))) & 19501 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + (6 \times ((54 + 3)^2))) \times -1)) \\
19502 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 + (4 \times (5 + (67 \times 8)))) \times 9))) & 19502 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 + (6 \times ((54 + 3)^2))) \times -1)) \\
19503 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times -(4 \times (5 + (67 \times 8)))) - 9)) & 19503 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7^6) - (5^4)) / - (3 \times 2) + 1)) \\
19504 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7)) \times 8)) - 9) & 19504 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7^6) - (5^4)) / - (3 \times 2) + 1)) \\
19505 &:= ((1 + 234) \times -(5 - (6 - (7 - 89)))) & 19505 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7^6) - (5^4)) / - (3 \times 2) - 1)) \\
19506 &:= ((12 + (3^{4+5})) + ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times -9)) & 19506 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7^6) - (5^4)) / (3 \times 2) + 1))) \\
19507 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times 8) + 9))) & 19507 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 + (6 \times (((54 + 3)^2) + 1)))) \\
19508 &:= (1 + (2 + (((((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times 8) + 9))) & 19508 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (65 \times (4 \times (3 + 2)))))) - 1 \\
19509 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -34) - ((5 \times (6^7)) / (8 \times 9)))) & 19509 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (65 \times (4 \times (3 + 2)))))) \times 1 \\
19510 &:= (1 + (((2 + ((3 - 45) \times 6)) \times -78) + 9)) & 19510 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 + ((6^5) / 4)) \times -((3^2) + 1))) \\
19511 &:= ((1 - ((2 + 3) \times ((4^5) + (6^7))) / 8) / -9) & 19511 &:= (9 - (8 - ((7 + ((6^5) / 4)) \times ((3^2) + 1)))) \\
19512 &:= (12 \times -(3 \times -((4 \times 5) + (6 \times (78 + 9)))))) & 19512 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + (6 \times (((54 + 3)^2) - 1)))) \\
19513 &:= (1 \times -((23 + (4 \times 56)) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 19513 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(((7 - ((6 + 5)^4)) / (3 \times 2) + 1)))) \\
19514 &:= (1 \times (2 \times (((3 + ((4 - (5 - 6)^7)) / 8) - 9))) & 19514 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -7) + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19515 &:= (1 + (2 \times (((3 + ((4 - (5 - 6)^7)) / 8) - 9))) & 19515 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -6) - ((5^4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19516 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) + 5) \times -(6 - ((7 - 8) \times 9))) & 19516 &:= (9 - (((8 + (((7^6) - (5^4)) / 3)) / -2) + 1)) \\
19517 &:= (12 - (((((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times -8) - 9)) & 19517 &:= (9 - ((8 + (((7^6) - (5^4)) / 3)) / - (2 \times 1))) \\
19518 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((34 \times 5) - 6) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 19518 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 + (6 \times ((54 + 3)^2))) \times -1)) \\
19519 &:= (((1 + 23)^4) + (5 + (6 \times 7))) / (8 + 9) & 19519 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + ((6 \times ((54 + 3)^2)) + 1))) \\
19520 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^4)) - ((5 \times (6^7)) / - (8 \times 9))) & 19520 &:= (((9 - (8 - 7)) + ((6^5) / 4)) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\
19521 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times ((4 + 5) + (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 19521 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7^6) - (5^4)) / - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
19522 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7)) \times 8)) + 9) & 19522 &:= ((9 + 8) - (((7^6) - (5^4)) / - (3 \times 2) - 1)) \\
19523 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3 + ((4 - (5 - 6)^7))) / -8) + 9)) & 19523 &:= (((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 65)) \times 43) + 2) - 1) \\
19524 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3 + ((4 - (5 - 6)^7))) / -8) + 9)) & 19524 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + (6 \times (((54 + 3)^2) + 1)))) \\
19525 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4+5}) - (67 + 89)))) & 19525 &:= (9 + ((8 - 76) \times -(((5 + 4) \times 32) - 1))) \\
19526 &:= ((1 - (23 + 4)) \times (5 - ((6 + 78) \times 9))) & 19526 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -6) - ((5^4) \times 32)) \times -1) \\
19527 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3 \times 45) + 6))) \times (78 - 9)) & 19527 &:= (9 + (8 + ((7 + ((6^5) / 4)) \times ((3^2) + 1)))) \\
19528 &:= ((1 - ((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 6)) \times -(7 - (8 - 9))) & 19528 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (((7 \times (6 + 54)) / 3)^2) \times -1) \\
19529 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8) \times 9)))))) & 19529 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(((7 - ((6 + 5)^4)) / (3 \times 2) - 1)))) \\
19530 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + 5)) \times -((6 \times (7 - 8)) - 9)) & 19530 &:= ((98 - (7 \times (6 \times 54))) \times (3 \times - (2 + 1))) \\
19531 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (3 \times 4)) \times ((5^6) + 7)) / -8) - 9) & 19531 &:= (98 - (7 - (((6^5) / 4) \times ((3^2) + 1)))) \\
19532 &:= (1 + (((2 - (3 \times 4)) \times ((5^6) + 7)) / -8) - 9) & 19532 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((76 \times - (5 + (4 \times (3 \times 21)))))) \\
19533 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 + 4) \times -(5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8) \times 9)))))) & 19533 &:= (9 - (8 - (76 \times (5 + (4 \times (3 \times 21)))))) \\
19534 &:= (-1 + (((2 - (345 + 6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9)) & 19534 &:= (((9 + 8) - (7 \times ((65 \times 43) - 2))) \times -1) \\
19535 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (345 + 6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9)) & 19535 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((7 \times -((65 \times 43) - 2)) - 1)) \\
19536 &:= (1 \times -((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -(6 \times (7 - (8 - 9)))))) & 19536 &:= (9 + (87 + (((6^5) / 4) \times ((3^2) + 1)))) \\
19537 &:= (1 - ((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -(6 \times (7 - (8 - 9)))))) & 19537 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times ((4^3) + 2)) - 1))) \\
19538 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) - (6 \times (7 + (8 + 9)))))) & 19538 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((654 - 3) \times 2))) - 1) \\
19539 &:= (((12 + (3^{4+5})) - 67) - 89) & 19539 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((654 - 3) \times 2))) \times 1) \\
19540 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) \times ((4 \times 5) + ((6^7) / (8 \times 9)))))) & 19540 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6^5) / -4) - ((3^2) + 1))) \\
19541 &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((4 \times 5) + ((6^7) / (8 \times 9)))))) & 19541 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times ((54 + 3)^2))) \times -1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
19542 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times (3 + ((4 - (5 - 6))^7)))/8)) + 9) & 19542 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times -543) + (2 - 1))) \\
19543 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) - (67 + (8 \times 9)))) & 19543 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 65)) \times 43) + 21) \\
19544 &:= ((1 + ((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 6)) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) & 19544 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 + (6 \times 5))) \times -((4^3) + 2)) + 1)) \\
19545 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) + ((6 + 7) \times -(8 \times 9))) & 19545 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (7 + (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
19546 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (67 + (8 \times 9)))) & 19546 &:= (9 - (((8 \times (7 + (6 \times 5))) \times -((4^3) + 2)) - 1)) \\
19547 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (67 + (8 \times 9)))) & 19547 &:= (((98 + 7) - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3)/2) \times -1) \\
19548 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times 4) - ((5 \times (6^7))/ - (8 \times 9)) & 19548 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) - (5^4)))) \times -((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
19549 &:= (1 \times (((2 - (3 \times 4)) \times ((5^6) + 7))/ - 8) + 9) & 19549 &:= (9 + (8 + (76 \times (5 + (4 \times (3 \times 21))))) \\
19550 &:= (1 + (((2 - (3 \times 4)) \times ((5^6) + 7))/ - 8) + 9) & 19550 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (((76 \times 5) + 4) \times 3) - (2 \times 1)) \\
19551 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 + 4) \times -(5 - ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 19551 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -((65 \times 43) - 2)) + 1)) \\
19552 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times ((4 - 56) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) & 19552 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 \times - (5 + (4^3))) - (2 \times 1))) \\
19553 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3^{4+5}) + 6)) + ((7 + 8) \times -9)) & 19553 &:= ((98 + (((7^6) - (5^4))/3))/ - (2 \times -1)) \\
19554 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) + (6 + (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) & 19554 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 - ((6 + (5^4)) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19555 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) + (6 + (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) & 19555 &:= ((9 - 8) - (7 - ((6 + (5^4)) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19556 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3^{4+5}) + (6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 19556 &:= ((-9 \times 87) - ((6 + 5) \times -(43^2 \times 1))) \\
19557 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3^{4+5}) + (6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 19557 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - 6543) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
19558 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((3^{4+5}) - (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 19558 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - ((6 \times ((54 + 3)^2)) - 1))) \\
19559 &:= (123 - (4 - ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9))) & 19559 &:= ((98 - (((7^6) - (5 - 4))/3))/(2 \times -1)) \\
19560 &:= (1 \times -(2 \times -(3 \times (4 \times (5 + (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) & 19560 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - ((6 \times ((54 + 3)^2)) + 1))) \\
19561 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 \times (4 \times (5 + (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) & 19561 &:= (((98 - 7) - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3)/2) \times -1) \\
19562 &:= (1 + (2 + ((34 \times (567 + 8)) + 9))) & 19562 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - ((6 + (5^4)) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
19563 &:= ((-12 + (34 \times ((5 + 67) \times 8))) - 9) & 19563 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(65 \times 43)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
19564 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3 \times (4+5-6)}) + (7 \times -(8 + 9))) & 19564 &:= (9 + ((8 - ((7 \times (65 \times 43)) - 2)) \times -1)) \\
19565 &:= ((1 - (23 \times 4)) \times (5 \times -((6 \times 7) - (8 - 9)))) & 19565 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (76 - 5))) \times ((4 \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\
19566 &:= ((12 + ((3^{4+5}) + 6)) + ((7 + 8) \times -9)) & 19566 &:= (9 \times -((8 + ((76 \times (54 + 3))/2)) \times -1)) \\
19567 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4+5}) - ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))) & 19567 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((((76 \times 5) + 4) \times -3) + (2 - 1))) \\
19568 &:= (1 \times ((2^{3+4}) + ((5 \times (6^7))/(8 \times 9))) & 19568 &:= (9 - (8 - ((7 \times (65 \times 43)) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
19569 &:= ((1 + (2^{3+4})) - ((5 \times (6^7))/ - (8 \times 9))) & 19569 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) - ((6 + (5^4)) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
19570 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((3^{4+5}) + (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 19570 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times ((5 \times -(43 - 2)) - 1)) \\
19571 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9))) & 19571 &:= (9 + ((8 - 7) + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19572 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9))) & 19572 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(7 \times -((65 \times 43) + (2 - 1)))) \\
19573 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3^{4+5})) - (((6 + 7) \times 8) + 9)) & 19573 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times -((4 \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
19574 &:= (1 + (23 \times -(4 - ((5 + (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9)))) & 19574 &:= (9 + ((87 - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3)/2) \times -1)) \\
19575 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -4) + (((5 \times (6 - 7)) + 8)^9) & 19575 &:= (((9^{8-(7-6) \times 5}) - 4) \times (3^{2+1})) \\
19576 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (34 \times (5 + 67))) \times 8) - 9)) & 19576 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) - 4) \times -32) - 1)) \\
19577 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - (34 \times (5 + 67))) \times 8) - 9)) & 19577 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (7 \times ((65 \times 43) + 2))) - 1)) \\
19578 &:= ((1 - ((2 - (34 \times (5 + 67))) \times 8)) + 9) & 19578 &:= ((9 - 87) \times -((65 \times 4) - (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
19579 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4+5}) - (6 + (7 + 89)))) & 19579 &:= (98 - (7 - (6 \times (((54 + 3)^2) - 1)))) \\
19580 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})) - (6 + 7)) - 89) & 19580 &:= (9 + ((8 + (7 \times (65 \times 43))) - (2 \times 1))) \\
19581 &:= (((12 + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times 7)) + (8 \times -9)) & 19581 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -((65 \times 43) + 2)) - 1)) \\
19582 &:= ((12 + (3^{4+5})) - (((6 + 7) \times 8) + 9)) & 19582 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 \times 65) \times -((4^3) - 21)))
\end{aligned}$$

19583 := $(1 \times -(((2 + (3^4) \times 5) \times 6) + 7) \times -8) + 9)$
19584 := $(1 - (((2 + (3^4) \times 5) \times 6) + 7) \times -8) + 9)$
19585 := $((-1 + 2) - ((3 - (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) - 8)) \times 9)$
19586 := $(1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4+5}) - (((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9))))$
19587 := $(1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) - (((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9))))$
19588 := $((1 - 2) \times -((3^{4+5}) - (((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9)))$
19589 := $((1 - 23) - (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) - 8) \times -9)$
19590 := $((12 + 3) \times ((4^5) + (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))))$
19591 := $((1 + 2) + (3^{4+5}) + (((6 + 7) \times -8) + 9))$
19592 := $((1 - (23 \times 4)) + ((5 \times (6 - 7)) + 8)^9)$
19593 := $((1 + 2) + (3^{4+5}) - (6 + 78)) - 9$
19594 := $((1 - 2) \times ((3^{4+5}) \times (6 - 7)) + 89)$
19595 := $(1 \times -((2 + 3) \times -(4 - (5 \times (6 - 789))))$
19596 := $(12 \times (((3 + 4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 \times 8) + 9)$
19597 := $((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5}) - 6) - (7 + (8 \times 9))$
19598 := $((1 - 2) \times -((3^{4+5}) - ((6 + 7) + (8 \times 9))))$
19599 := $((1 - 2) \times -((3^{4+5}) - (67 + (8 + 9))))$
19600 := $(1 \times ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 + 7) + (8 \times 9))))$
19601 := $(1 \times -(((2 + (3^4) \times 5) \times 6) + 7) \times -8) - 9)$
19602 := $(1 - (((2 + (3^4) \times 5) \times 6) + 7) \times -8) - 9)$
19603 := $((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) - ((5 \times (6^7)) / - (8 \times 9)))$
19604 := $(1 - (2^3) - (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) - 8) \times 9)$
19605 := $((1 + 2) - (3^4)) + ((5 \times (6 - 7)) + 8)^9)$
19606 := $(1 + ((2 \times -3) + (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) - 8) \times 9)$
19607 := $((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5}) - 6) - (78 - 9)$
19608 := $((1 + ((2 \times (3^4) \times 5) + 6)) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))$
19609 := $((1 - 2) + ((3^{4+5}) + 6)) - (7 + (8 \times 9))$
19610 := $(1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4+5}) - ((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9))))$
19611 := $((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5}) - 6) - ((7 \times 8) + 9)$
19612 := $(1 \times -((2 - 3) - (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) - 8) \times 9)$
19613 := $(1 - ((2 - 3) - (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) - 8) \times 9)$
19614 := $(1 + (2 + ((3^{4 \times 5 - 6 - 7}) - 8) \times 9))$
19615 := $((1 + 2) + (3^{4+5}) - 6) - ((7 \times 8) + 9)$
19616 := $((1 - (2 \times 34)) + ((5 \times (6 - 7)) + 8)^9)$
19617 := $(1 \times -((2 \times -3) - (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) - 8) \times 9)$
19618 := $(1 - ((2 \times -3) - (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) - 8) \times 9)$
19619 := $((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9)$
19620 := $(12 - (3 - (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) - 8) \times 9)$
19621 := $(1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times (7 - (8 + 9))))$
19622 := $(1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4+5}) - ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9))))$
19623 := $((1 + 2) - (3 \times -(4 \times (5 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))))$

19583 := $(9 - ((87 \times -(((6 - (5 - 4)) \times 3)^2)) + 1))$
19584 := $((9 - 8) + (((7 + 6) - (5^4)) \times -32) - 1)$
19585 := $((9 + (8 + 7)) - ((6 + (5^4)) \times -32) - 1)$
19586 := $(9 - ((8 + (((7 + 6) - (5^4)) \times 32)) - 1))$
19587 := $(9 - (8 - ((7 \times (65 \times 43)) + 21)))$
19588 := $((9 + ((8 - ((7^6) - 5)) / (4 \times 3))) \times (2 \times -1))$
19589 := $((9 + 87) - ((6 \times -((54 + 3)^2)) + 1))$
19590 := $((9 + 87) + (6 \times ((54 + 3)^2))) \times 1$
19591 := $((98 - ((7^6) - 5)) / ((4 \times 3) / - (2 \times 1)))$
19592 := $((98 - ((7^6) + (5 - 4))) / (3 \times - (2 \times 1)))$
19593 := $(98 + (7 + (6 \times ((54 + 3)^2) - 1)))$
19594 := $(9 + (((8 - 76) \times -((5 + 4) \times 32)) + 1))$
19595 := $((9 + 876) - (5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}))) \times -1$
19596 := $((9 + 87) - (6 \times -((54 + 3)^2) + 1))$
19597 := $(9 + (8 + ((7 \times ((65 \times 43) + 2)) + 1)))$
19598 := $(98 + ((7 + (6 \times ((54 + 3)^2))) - 1))$
19599 := $(9 + (((8 + 7) + ((6^5) / 4)) \times ((3^2) + 1)))$
19600 := $(9 - (8 - (((7 \times (6 + 54)) / 3)^2) - 1))$
19601 := $(98 - (((7^6) - (5^4)) / - (3 \times 2)) + 1)$
19602 := $(98 - (((7^6) - (5^4)) / - (3 + (2 + 1))))$
19603 := $((9 + 8) - (((7^6) + (5 \times 4)) / 3)) / (2 \times -1)$
19604 := $(9 + (((8 \times -7) + (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3) / 2) - 1))$
19605 := $(9 - ((8 \times 7) - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3) / (2 \times 1)))$
19606 := $(9 + ((8 \times -7) + (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3) / 2) + 1)$
19607 := $((9 - 8) \times (((7^6) - (5 - 4)) / (3 \times 2)) - 1)$
19608 := $((9 - 8) + (((7^6) - (5 - 4)) / (3 \times 2)) - 1)$
19609 := $((9 - 8) \times -(((7^6) + 5) \times 4) / - (3 + 21))$
19610 := $((9 - 8) \times -(((7^6) + 5) / - ((4 \times 3) / 2)) - 1)$
19611 := $(9 + (((8 - ((7^6) - 5) / 4)) / 3) \times - (2 \times 1))$
19612 := $((9 - 8) + (((7^6) + (5 \times 4)) / 3)) / - (2 \times -1)$
19613 := $((9 - 87) + (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3)) / - (2 \times -1)$
19614 := $(9 + (((8 - ((7^6) - (5 - 4)) / 3)) / - 2) + 1)$
19615 := $(9 + (((8 - ((7^6) - 5)) \times 4) / - (3 + 21)))$
19616 := $((9 + 8) + (((7 \times (6 + 54)) / 3)^2) - 1)$
19617 := $((9 - 8) - ((7^6) + 54)) / (3 \times - (2 \times 1))$
19618 := $((9 + 8) \times -(((76 \times 5) + 4) \times -3) - (2 \times 1))$
19619 := $(9 - ((8 + ((7^6) + (5 + 4))) / - (3 \times 2)) + 1)$
19620 := $((9 - ((8 - ((7^6) - 5) / 4)) / 3) \times - (2 \times -1))$
19621 := $(9 - (((8 + ((7^6) + (5 + 4))) / - (3 \times 2)) - 1))$
19622 := $(9 - (((8 + 7) \times 654) - 3) \times -2) + 1)$
19623 := $((98 + (7^6)) - (5 + 4)) / - (3 \times - (2 \times 1))$

$$\begin{aligned}
19624 &:= ((1-2) \times -((3^{4+5}) - ((6 \times 7) + (8+9)))) & 19624 &:= ((9 - ((8 - ((7^6) - 5))/(4 \times 3))) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
19625 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times -(6 + (7 \times (8+9)))) & 19625 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 76) + 5) \times (4^3)) / -(2 \times 1)) \\
19626 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times -(6 + (7 \times (8+9)))) & 19626 &:= ((98 + ((7^6) + (5+4))) / -(3 \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
19627 &:= (((1+2) + ((3^{4+5}) + 6)) - ((7 \times 8) + 9)) & 19627 &:= (9 + (8 + (((7^6) + 5)/(4 \times 3/2)) + 1)) \\
19628 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4+5}) - ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) & 19628 &:= (((9 + (8+7)) - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3/2)) \times -1) \\
19629 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times -((4 \times -(((5 \times 6) - 7) \times 8)) + 9)) & 19629 &:= (9 - ((8+7) \times -(654 \times (3 - (2-1)))))) \\
19630 &:= (1 \times -((2 - (3 \times 4)) \times (((5^6) + 7)/8 + 9))) & 19630 &:= (9 + (((8 \times -7) - 6) + (((5+4) \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
19631 &:= (1 - ((2 - (3 \times 4)) \times (((5^6) + 7)/8 + 9))) & 19631 &:= (((-9 - ((8+7) \times 654) - 3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
19632 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9))) & 19632 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3)/2)) - 1) \\
19633 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9))) & 19633 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3)/2)) \times 1) \\
19634 &:= (((1-2) + (3^{4+5})) + (6 \times -(7 - (8-9)))) & 19634 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times 7) - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3)/2)) + 1) \\
19635 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3+4))) \times -((5+6) \times -(7 \times (8+9)))) & 19635 &:= ((9+8) \times ((7 \times -6) + ((54+3) \times 2))) \\
19636 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4+5}) - (((6+7) - 8) \times 9)))) & 19636 &:= (9 - (((((8+7) \times 654) + 3) \times -2) - 1)) \\
19637 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times (7 - (8-9)))) & 19637 &:= ((9-8) + (7 + (6543 \times (2+1)))) \\
19638 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times (7 - (8-9)))) & 19638 &:= (9 \times -((876 + (5 \times 43)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
19639 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times (7 \times (8-9)))) & 19639 &:= (9 + ((8-7) + (6543 \times (2+1)))) \\
19640 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times (7 \times (8-9)))) & 19640 &:= (((9 + (8+7)) - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3)/(2 \times -1)) \\
19641 &:= (((1-2) + ((3^{4+5}) + 6)) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & 19641 &:= ((9-8) \times ((7 \times -6) + (((5+4) \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
19642 &:= (((1-2) - ((3^{4+5}) - (6 \times 7))) \times (8-9)) & 19642 &:= (((9+8) - 7) - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3/2)) \times -1) \\
19643 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + ((5^6) - 7))) + (8 \times -9)) & 19643 &:= ((-98 / -7) - (6543 \times -(2+1))) \\
19644 &:= (1 - (((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times 7)) \times (8-9))) & 19644 &:= ((9-8) \times -(7 - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3/2) - 1)) \\
19645 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 \times 7) + (8-9)))) & 19645 &:= ((9-8) \times ((7 - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3/2)) \times -1)) \\
19646 &:= (((1-2) + (3^{4+5})) + (6 \times -((7+8) - 9))) & 19646 &:= ((9-8) + ((7 - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3/2)) \times -1)) \\
19647 &:= (((((1+2)^{3+4}) - 5) \times -(6 - (7+8))) + 9) & 19647 &:= ((9-8) - (7 - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3/2) + 1)) \\
19648 &:= ((1 - (2+34)) + (((5 \times (6-7)) + 8)^9)) & 19648 &:= (((9 - (8-7)) - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3)/(2 \times -1)) \\
19649 &:= (1 + ((2^3) \times -(4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7-89)))))) & 19649 &:= (((9 - (8+7)) + (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3)) / -(2 \times -1)) \\
19650 &:= (((1+2) + (3^{4+5})) + (6 \times -((7+8) - 9))) & 19650 &:= (((9^{8+7-6-5}) - 4) \times 3) - 21) \\
19651 &:= (1 + (2 \times -3 - (((4 \times 5) - 6) \times (78 \times 9)))) & 19651 &:= (((9-8)^7) \times -(((6 \times 5) + 4)^3) / -2 + 1) \\
19652 &:= (((1-2) + ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times 7))) + (8 \times -9)) & 19652 &:= (((9-8)^7) - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3) / -2 + 1) \\
19653 &:= (12 - (((3^{4+5}) - (6 \times 7)) \times (8-9))) & 19653 &:= (((9-8)^7) \times -(((6 \times 5) + 4)^3) / -2 - 1) \\
19654 &:= ((12 + ((3^{4+5}) + 6)) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & 19654 &:= (((9-8)^7) - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3) / -2 - 1) \\
19655 &:= (1 - (2 - (3 \times (((45 - (6 \times 7))^8) - 9)))) & 19655 &:= (((9 - (8+7)) - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3)/(2 \times -1)) \\
19656 &:= (((1+2) + (3^{4+5})) + ((6 \times 7) - (8 \times 9))) & 19656 &:= ((9-8) \times -(7 \times -(((65 - (4 \times 3))^2) - 1))) \\
19657 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + ((5^6) + 7))) + (8 \times -9)) & 19657 &:= ((98 + (((7^6) - (5-4))/3)) / -(2 \times -1)) \\
19658 &:= ((12 - ((3^{4+5}) - (6+7))) \times (8-9)) & 19658 &:= ((9-8) \times ((7 + (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3/2)) - 1)) \\
19659 &:= (((1+2)^{3 \times (4+5-6)} - 7) - (8+9)) & 19659 &:= ((9-8) \times -((7 + (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3/2)) \times -1)) \\
19660 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 \times 7) - (8+9)))) & 19660 &:= ((9-8) - ((7 + (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3/2)) \times -1)) \\
19661 &:= (((1+2) + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 \times 7) - 8) + 9) & 19661 &:= ((9-8) + (7 + (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3/2) + 1)) \\
19662 &:= ((1+2) + (3 + ((45-6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 19662 &:= ((9+8) + ((7 - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3/2)) \times -1)) \\
19663 &:= (1 - (2 \times -3 + (((4 \times 5) - 6) \times (78 \times 9)))) & 19663 &:= ((9+8) - (7 - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3/2) + 1)) \\
19664 &:= (((1-2) + ((3^{4+5}) + 6)) - (7 + (8+9))) & 19664 &:= (((9 + (8+7)) + (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3)) / -(2 \times -1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
19665 &:= (((1-2) + (3^{4+5})) + ((6-7) \times (8+9))) & 19665 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7+6))) \times ((5 + (4^3)) \times -(2+1))) \\
19666 &:= (((1-2) + (3^{4+5})) - 6) + (7 - (8+9)) & 19666 &:= ((98 + 7) - ((6 + (5^4)) \times -(32 - 1))) \\
19667 &:= (((1-2) + (3^{4+5})) + ((6 \times (7-8)) - 9)) & 19667 &:= (9 + (8 + ((7 + 6543) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
19668 &:= (((1-2) + (3^{4+5})) - 6) - (7 - (8-9)) & 19668 &:= (((((9^{8+7-6-5}) - 4) \times 3) - 2) - 1) \\
19669 &:= (((1-2) + (3^{4+5})) - 6) - (7 \times -(8-9)) & 19669 &:= (((((9^{8+7-6-5}) - 4) \times -3) + 2) \times -1) \\
19670 &:= (((1-2) + (3^{4+5})) - (6+7)) - (8-9) & 19670 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + (6^5))/4)) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\
19671 &:= ((1+2) - (((3^{4+5}) - 6) \times (7-8)) + 9) & 19671 &:= (((9^{8+7-6-5}) - 4) \times -(3 \times -(2-1))) \\
19672 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3^{4+5}) + ((6+7) \times (8-9)))) & 19672 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - (((5^4) \times -32) + 1)) \\
19673 &:= (((1+2) + (3^{4+5})) - 6) - (7 \times -(8-9)) & 19673 &:= (((9^{8+7-6-5}) - 4) \times 3) - (2 \times -1) \\
19674 &:= (((1+2)^{3+4} + (5-6)) \times -(7-8) \times 9) & 19674 &:= (((9^{8+7-6-5}) - 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1) \\
19675 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5^6))) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & 19675 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 + (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3)/2)) - 1) \\
19676 &:= (((1+2)^{3 \times (4+5-6)}) - 7) \times -(8-9) & 19676 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 + (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3)/2)) \times -1) \\
19677 &:= (((1+2)^{3 \times (4+5-6)}) - 7) - (8-9) & 19677 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 + (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3)/2 + 1)) \\
19678 &:= (((1-2) + ((3^{4+5}) + 6)) + (7 - (8+9))) & 19678 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - 6) + (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1}) \\
19679 &:= ((1+2) - ((3+4) - (((5 \times (6-7)) + 8)^9))) & 19679 &:= (9 + ((8 + (7 \times ((65 - (4 \times 3))^2))) - 1)) \\
19680 &:= (((1-2) - (3^4)) \times 5 \times -(6 \times (7 - (8-9)))) & 19680 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 7) - 6)^5))/((4 - 3) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
19681 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) - (4 - (((5 \times (6 - 7)) + 8)^9))) & 19681 &:= (9 + (8 + ((7 \times ((65 - (4 \times 3))^2)) + 1))) \\
19682 &:= (((1-2) + (3^{4+5})) - 6) + ((7 + 8) - 9) & 19682 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 - ((6 - 5) \times 4))^3) - 1)) \\
19683 &:= (((1+2)^{3 \times 4}) / -((5 + ((6 - 7) \times 8)) \times 9)) & 19683 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((7 - ((6 - 5) \times 4))^3) - 1)) \\
19684 &:= (((1-2) + (3^{4+5})) - 6) + (7 - (8-9)) & 19684 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7 - 6)) + (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
19685 &:= (((1-2) + (3^{4+5})) + ((6 \times (7-8)) + 9)) & 19685 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) - (6 - (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
19686 &:= (((1+2) + (3^{4+5})) - (6-7)) + (8-9) & 19686 &:= ((9 + (((8 + 7) - 6)^5)) / -((4 - 3) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
19687 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - 3) \times 4) - (((5 \times (6 - 7)) + 8)^9))) & 19687 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) - (6 - (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
19688 &:= (1 - (((2 - 3) \times 4) - (((5 \times (6 - 7)) + 8)^9))) & 19688 &:= (9 - (((((8 + 7) - 6)^5) - (4 \times 3)) / - (2 + 1))) \\
19689 &:= (1 - (((2 + (3^{4+5})) - 6) \times (7-8)) - 9) & 19689 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times 6) + (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1}) \\
19690 &:= (((1+2)^{3 \times (4+5-6)}) + 7) \times -(8-9) & 19690 &:= ((9 + (((8 + 7) - 6)^5) + (4 \times 3)) / (2 + 1)) \\
19691 &:= (((1+2)^{3 \times (4+5-6)}) + 7) - (8-9) & 19691 &:= (((9 - 87) - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3)) / (2 \times -1)) \\
19692 &:= (((1+2)^{3+4} - (5-6)) \times -(7-8) \times 9) & 19692 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times ((5^4) \times 3))) / - (2 \times -1)) \\
19693 &:= ((1+2) + ((3+4) + (((5 \times (6 - 7)) + 8)^9))) & 19693 &:= (((((9^{8+7-6-5}) + 4) \times -3) + 2) \times -1) \\
19694 &:= (((1-2) + ((3^{4+5}) + 6)) + ((7 + 8) - 9)) & 19694 &:= (((((9^{8+7-6-5}) + 4) \times 3) - 2) + 1) \\
19695 &:= (((1-2) + ((3^{4+5}) + 6)) + (7 \times -(8-9))) & 19695 &:= (((9^{8+7-6-5}) + 4) \times -3) \times -(2 - 1) \\
19696 &:= (((1-2) + ((3^{4+5}) + 6)) + (7 - (8-9))) & 19696 &:= (((((9^{8+7-6-5}) + 4) \times 3) + 2) - 1) \\
19697 &:= (((1-2) + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 \times (7-8)) - 9)) & 19697 &:= (((((9^{8+7-6-5}) + 4) \times -3) - 2) \times -1) \\
19698 &:= ((1+2) - ((3 \times -4) - (((5 \times (6 - 7)) + 8)^9))) & 19698 &:= (((((9^{8+7-6-5}) + 4) \times 3) + 2) + 1) \\
19699 &:= (((1+2) + ((3^{4+5}) + 6)) + (7 \times -(8-9))) & 19699 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((7 - ((6 - 5) \times 4))^3) - 1)) \\
19700 &:= (((1+2) + ((3^{4+5}) + 6)) + (7 - (8-9))) & 19700 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 - 6)) - (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
19701 &:= ((1+2) - (((3^{4+5}) + 6) \times (7-8)) - 9) & 19701 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 - 6) + (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
19702 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (3^{4+5})) \times (6-7)) - (8+9))) & 19702 &:= ((9 + ((8 - ((7^6) + (5^4)))/(3 \times 2))) \times -1) \\
19703 &:= (1 - (((2 + (3^{4+5})) \times (6-7)) - (8+9))) & 19703 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(((7 - 65) \times (4 \times (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\
19704 &:= (((1+2) + (3^{4+5})) - (6-7)) + (8+9) & 19704 &:= (((9^{8+7-6-5}) + (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
19705 &:= ((12 + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 \times (7 + 8)) / -9)) & 19705 &:= (98 + (((7^6) - (5 - 4)) / (3 \times 2)) - 1) \\
19706 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (4 - (((5 \times (6 - 7)) + 8)^9))) & 19706 &:= ((9876 - ((5 \times 4) + 3)) \times - (2 \times -1)) \\
19707 &:= (1 \times -((2 \times - (3 \times 4)) - (((5 \times (6 - 7)) + 8)^9))) & 19707 &:= (98 - (((7^6) + 5) \times 4) / - (3 + 21)) \\
19708 &:= (1 - ((2 \times - (3 \times 4)) - (((5 \times (6 - 7)) + 8)^9))) & 19708 &:= (98 - (((7^6) + 5) / - ((4 \times 3) / 2)) - 1) \\
19709 &:= ((12 + ((3^{4+5}) + 6)) + (7 - (8 - 9))) & 19709 &:= (((-98 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times - (4^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
19710 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3^{(-4+5) \times 6}) - (7 - 8)) \times -9)) & 19710 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times -7) + 65^4)) \times - (3 \times - (2 - 1))) \\
19711 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 \times -7) + (8 + 9))) & 19711 &:= ((-9 - 87) + (((6 - 5^4) \times -32) - 1)) \\
19712 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times 7)) - (8 \times -9)) & 19712 &:= ((9 - 8) \times - (7 \times - ((65 \times 43) + 21))) \\
19713 &:= ((1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - (((5^6) \times (7 - 8)) + 9)) & 19713 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) + (6 + (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1})) \\
19714 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + ((5^6) - (7 - 8)))) - 9) & 19714 &:= ((((-9 \times - (8 - 7)) - 6)^{5+4}) + 32) - 1) \\
19715 &:= (1 - (((2^{3 \times 4}) + ((5^6) - 7)) \times (8 - 9))) & 19715 &:= ((((-9 \times (876 \times 5)) - (4 \times 3)) / -2) - 1) \\
19716 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + ((5^6) - 7))) - (8 - 9)) & 19716 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3) / 2) - 1) \\
19717 &:= (1 \times - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times ((7 + 8) - 9)))) & 19717 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3) / (2 \times 1))) \\
19718 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times ((7 + 8) - 9)))) & 19718 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times - ((654 + 3) \times 2)) + 1)) \\
19719 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 + (((45 - (6 \times 7))^8) + 9))) & 19719 &:= ((9 + ((87 - (6 + 5)) \times 4)) \times - (3 \times -21)) \\
19720 &:= ((12 + ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 \times 7) - 8))) - 9) & 19720 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - ((5^4) \times - (32 - 1))) \\
19721 &:= (1 \times (((2 - 34) \times - ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8))) + 9)) & 19721 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((76 + 5) - 4) \times 32)) \times 1) \\
19722 &:= (((1 + 2) - ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times 7))) \times (8 - 9)) & 19722 &:= (9 - ((8 \times - ((76 + 5) - 4) \times 32)) - 1) \\
19723 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})) - 6) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & 19723 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - 6) \times (54 + 3)) / -2) + 1) \\
19724 &:= (1 + ((2 - ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times 7))) \times (8 - 9))) & 19724 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times - ((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)) + 1) \\
19725 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 \times -7) + (8 - 9))) & 19725 &:= ((9 - 8) \times - ((7 \times -6) - (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1})) \\
19726 &:= (((1 - 2) - ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times 7))) \times (8 - 9)) & 19726 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)) + 1) \\
19727 &:= (1 \times - ((2 + ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times 7))) \times (8 - 9))) & 19727 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times - ((4 \times 3)^2)) - 1) \\
19728 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + ((5^6) + 7))) + (8 - 9)) & 19728 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 76) \times 5)) \times - (((4 + 3)^2) - 1)) \\
19729 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + ((5^6) + 7))) \times - (8 - 9)) & 19729 &:= ((9 - 87) + (((6 - 5^4) \times -32) - 1)) \\
19730 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + ((5^6) + 7))) - (8 - 9)) & 19730 &:= (9 + ((87 + ((6 - 5^4) \times 32)) \times -1)) \\
19731 &:= ((1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - (((5^6) \times (7 - 8)) - 9)) & 19731 &:= (987 - (6 \times - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1)) \\
19732 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + ((5^6) - (7 - 8)))) + 9) & 19732 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (76 \times 5))) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
19733 &:= (1 - (23 - (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) + 8) \times 9)) & 19733 &:= (((-98 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times - (4^3)) + 21) \\
19734 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times - (7 - (8 - 9)))) & 19734 &:= ((9 - 87) \times ((65 \times -4) + ((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\
19735 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3^{4+5}) + 6)) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) & 19735 &:= (-9 + ((8 - (((7 - 6) \times 5)^4)) \times - (32 \times 1))) \\
19736 &:= ((1 - 2) \times - ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9))) & 19736 &:= (987 - ((6 \times - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\
19737 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) + 6) \times - ((7 - 8) \times 9)) & 19737 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) \times - (43 \times - (2 - 1))) \\
19738 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) & 19738 &:= (987 - ((6 \times - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\
19739 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) & 19739 &:= (98 + ((7 \times -6) + (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1})) \\
19740 &:= (1 \times (2 \times ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))))) & 19740 &:= ((98 + 7) \times (((6 \times 5) + (4^3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
19741 &:= (1 \times (((2 - 3^4) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) & 19741 &:= (((-987 \times - (6 + 54)) + 3) / (2 + 1)) \\
19742 &:= ((1 + ((2 - 3^4) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) - 9) & 19742 &:= (9 - (((8 \times -7) + 6) - (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
19743 &:= ((1 - 2) \times - ((3^{4+5}) - (6 \times (7 - (8 + 9)))) & 19743 &:= (98 + ((7 - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3) / 2)) \times -1) \\
19744 &:= (1 \times ((23 + (4 + 5)) \times - (6 - (7 \times 89)))) & 19744 &:= (98 - (7 - (((6 \times 5) + 4)^3) / 2) + 1)) \\
19745 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})) + ((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9)) & 19745 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 - 76)) + 5) \times (4^3)) / 2) + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

19746 := ((1 + ((2 ^{3×4}) + ((5 ⁶) + (7 + 8)))) + 9)	19746 := (9 × ((8 × -7) + (6 × (54 + 321))))
19747 := (1 - ((2 - ((3 - ((45 × 6) + 7)) × 8)) × -9))	19747 := (9 + ((87 + (((6 × 5) + 4) ³)/2) - 1))
19748 := (((1 + 2) ^{3×(4+5-6)}) - 7) - (8 × -9))	19748 := (9 - ((87 + (((6 × 5) + 4) ³)/2) × -1))
19749 := (((1 + 2) + (3 ⁴⁺⁵)) + ((6 - (7 - 8)) × 9))	19749 := (9 + (87 + (((6 × 5) + 4) ³)/2 + 1))
19750 := (((1 - 2) + ((3 ⁴⁺⁵) + (67 - 8))) + 9)	19750 := (((9 + 8) - 7) × -(((6 ⁵)/ - 4) - (32 - 1)))
19751 := (1 × -((2 × -34) - (((5 × (6 - 7)) + 8) ⁹)))	19751 := ((-9876 × (5 - (4 + 3))) - (2 - 1))
19752 := ((1 + 23) × -((4 × - (5 × (6 × 7))) + (8 + 9)))	19752 := (((9 + 8) - (7 × (6 × (5 × 4)))) × -(3 + 21))
19753 := (((1 - 2) + ((3 ⁴⁺⁵) + 6)) + ((7 × 8) + 9))	19753 := (9 - (((8 × 76) + (5 + 4)) × -(32 × 1)))
19754 := (1 - (2 - (((3 ^{4×5-6-7}) + 8) × 9)))	19754 := (98 - (7 × -(((65 - (4 × 3)) ²) - 1)))
19755 := (((1 - 2) + (3 ⁴⁺⁵)) - 6) + (7 + (8 × 9))	19755 := (9 × ((8 × 7) + ((65 + 4) × (32 - 1))))
19756 := (1 × -(2 - ((3 × 4) + (5 × (6 × 7))) × 89)))	19756 := (98 + ((7 + (((6 × 5) + 4) ³)/2) - 1))
19757 := (((1 + 2) + ((3 ⁴⁺⁵) + (6 + (7 × 8)))) + 9)	19757 := (98 - ((7 + (((6 × 5) + 4) ³)/2) × -1))
19758 := ((12 + (3 ⁴⁺⁵)) + ((6 - (7 - 8)) × 9))	19758 := (98 + (7 + (((6 × 5) + 4) ³)/2 + 1))
19759 := (((1 + 2) + (3 ⁴⁺⁵)) - 6) + (7 + (8 × 9))	19759 := ((9 - 8) × (76 + (((5 + 4) × 3) ²⁺¹)))
19760 := ((1 + ((2 - (3 ⁴)) × (5 × (6 - (7 × 8)))) + 9)	19760 := ((9 - 8) + (76 + (((5 + 4) × 3) ²⁺¹)))
19761 := (1 × -((2 × -3) - (((4 + 5) - 6) ⁷) + 8) × 9))	19761 := ((9 - 8) × -(((7 ⁶) - (5 ⁴⁺³))/ - 2) + 1))
19762 := (((1 - 2) - (3 ⁴)) × -((5 × -(6 - (7 × 8))) - 9))	19762 := ((9 - 8) - (((7 ⁶) - (5 ⁴⁺³))/ - 2) + 1))
19763 := (((1 - 2) + (3 ⁴)) + (((5 × (6 - 7)) + 8) ⁹))	19763 := (9 + ((8 - (((7 ⁶) - (5 ⁴⁺³))/2) × -1))
19764 := (1 + ((2 ³) + (((4 + 5) - 6) ⁷) + 8) × 9))	19764 := ((9 - 8) - (((7 ⁶) - (5 ⁴⁺³))/ - 2) - 1))
19765 := ((1 - (2 × 34)) × (5 × -((6 × 7) + (8 + 9))))	19765 := (((-9 - (8 × 7)) × -6) - ((5 ⁴) × -(32 - 1)))
19766 := (1 × -((2 ^{3×4}) × -5) + (6 × (7 × (8 + 9))))	19766 := (9 + (((8 - ((7 ⁶) - (5 ⁴⁺³))) / - 2) - 1))
19767 := (((1 - 2) + ((3 ⁴⁺⁵) + 6)) + (7 + (8 × 9))	19767 := (9 + ((8 - ((7 ⁶) - (5 ⁴⁺³))) / - (2 × 1)))
19768 := ((12 + (3 ⁴⁺⁵)) - ((6 - 7) - (8 × 9)))	19768 := (9 + (((8 - ((7 ⁶) - (5 ⁴⁺³))) / - 2) + 1))
19769 := ((1 + ((2 ^{3×4}) + (5 ⁶))) - ((7 × -8) + 9))	19769 := (-9 - (((8 × 7) + 6) × -((5 × (4 ³) - (2 - 1))))
19770 := ((12 + 3) - (((4 + 5) - 6) ⁷) + 8) × -9))	19770 := (((9 + 8) - 7) × -(((6 ⁵)/ - 4) - (32 + 1)))
19771 := (((1 + 2) + ((3 ⁴⁺⁵) + 6)) + (7 + (8 × 9))	19771 := ((9 + 8) × -(76 + ((5 - (4 ³)) × 21)))
19772 := (((1 - 2) + (3 ⁴⁺⁵)) - 6) + (7 + 89))	19772 := (((-9 - 8) × -7) - (((6 × 5) + 4) ³ / - 2) - 1))
19773 := (((1 + 2) ³⁺⁴) - (((5 ⁶) + 7)/8) × -9))	19773 := (9 - ((87 - 6) × -((5 × ((4 + 3) ²)) - 1)))
19774 := (1 - ((2 + ((3 ^{4×5-6-7}) + 8)) × -9))	19774 := (9 - (((8 + (7 ⁶)) - (5 ⁴⁺³))/ - 2) + 1))
19775 := (1 × -((23 × -4) - (((5 × (6 - 7)) + 8) ⁹)))	19775 := (9 - (((8 + (7 ⁶)) - (5 ⁴⁺³))/ - (2 × 1)))
19776 := (((12 ³) × -((4 - 5) + ((6 + 7) × 8))) / - 9)	19776 := ((9 + 8) + (76 + (((5 + 4) × 3) ²⁺¹)))
19777 := (((1 - 2) + (3 ⁴⁺⁵)) - (((6 + 7) × -8) + 9))	19777 := (9 - (8 × -(7 × ((6 × (54 + (3 + 2))) - 1))))
19778 := ((1 - 23) × -((4 ⁵) - (6 + (7 × (8 + 9))))	19778 := ((9 + (((8 × 7) + 6) × 5)) × -(((4 ³) - 2) × -1))
19779 := ((1 + 23) - (((4 + 5) - 6) ⁷) + 8) × -9))	19779 := (9 + (8 + (((7 ⁶) - (5 ⁴⁺³))/(2 × 1))))
19780 := ((12 + ((3 ⁴⁺⁵) + 6)) + (7 + (8 × 9))	19780 := (9 + (8 + (((7 ⁶) - (5 ⁴⁺³))/2) + 1))
19781 := (((1 + 2) + (3 ⁴⁺⁵)) - (((6 + 7) × -8) + 9))	19781 := ((98 + ((7 - ((6 - 5) × 4)) ³)) × 1)
19782 := ((1 + 2) × -((3 × -(((4 + 5) - 6) ⁷) + 8)) - 9))	19782 := ((98 + ((7 - ((6 - 5) × 4)) ³)) + 1)
19783 := ((1 + (2 × (3 × 45))) × -((6 - 7) - (8 × 9))	19783 := ((98 - (((7 - (6 × (5 + 4))) × -3) ²)) × -1)
19784 := (1 × -(((2 ^{3×4}) × -5) - (6 - (78 × 9))))	19784 := (9 + (((8 - (7 - 6)) - (5 ⁴)) × -32) - 1))
19785 := ((1 + 2) - ((3 + (((4 + 5) - 6) ⁷) + 8)) × -9))	19785 := ((9 + 87) + (6 + (((5 + 4) × 3) ²⁺¹)))
19786 := (1 × ((2 ^{3×4}) + ((5 ⁶) - (7 - (8 × 9))))	19786 := (9 + (((8 - (7 - 6)) - (5 ⁴)) × -32) + 1))

$$\begin{aligned}
19787 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + ((5^6) - 7))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
19788 &:= (1 - (((2 + (3^4)) \times 5) + 6) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\
19789 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + ((5^6) + 78))) - 9) \\
19790 &:= ((12 + (3^{4+5})) - (((6 + 7) \times -8) + 9)) \\
19791 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 - (4 \times ((5 \times 6) - 7) \times 8))) \times -9)) \\
19792 &:= (1 + ((23 + 4) \times -(56 - 789))) \\
19793 &:= (1 \times -(((2^{3 \times 4}) \times -5) + (678 + 9))) \\
19794 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4+5}) - (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9))))) \\
19795 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9))))) \\
19796 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9))))) \\
19797 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((3^{4+5}) + ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
19798 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9))))) \\
19799 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9))))) \\
19800 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9))))) \\
19801 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + ((5^6) + 7))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
19802 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3 \times (4+5-6)}) - (7 \times -(8 + 9))) \\
19803 &:= (1 \times -(((2 - ((3 - 45) \times 6)) \times -78) + 9)) \\
19804 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + ((5^6) - 7))) + 89) \\
19805 &:= (1 \times -(((2^{3 \times 4}) \times -5) + ((67 + 8) \times 9))) \\
19806 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4+5}) + (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9))))) \\
19807 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) + (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9))))) \\
19808 &:= ((12 + (3^{4+5})) + (((6 + 7) \times 8) + 9)) \\
19809 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 3) + (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) + 8)) \times -9)) \\
19810 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3) + (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) + 8)) \times -9)) \\
19811 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) - (6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9))))) \\
19812 &:= ((1 + (2^{3+4})) + (((5 \times (6 - 7)) + 8)^9)) \\
19813 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 \times 7) + 89)))) \\
19814 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -(4^5)) + (6 \times (7 \times 89)))) \\
19815 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3^{4+5})) - 6) - ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
19816 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((34 \times (5 \times (6 + 7))) - 8) \times 9))) \\
19817 &:= (1 - (2 - (((34 \times (5 \times (6 + 7))) - 8) \times 9))) \\
19818 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3 \times (4+5-6)}) - ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
19819 &:= (-1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) + (67 + (8 \times 9))))) \\
19820 &:= ((12 + ((3^{4+5}) + 6)) - (7 \times -(8 + 9))) \\
19821 &:= (1 + (2 + (((34 \times (5 \times (6 + 7))) - 8) \times 9))) \\
19822 &:= (1 \times -(((23 \times (45 + 6)) - 7) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
19823 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3^{4+5}) + 6)) - ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
19824 &:= (12 \times -(3 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) / 8) - 9)) \\
19825 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times (7 + (8 + 9))))) \\
19826 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3^{4+5}) + (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))))) \\
19827 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3^{4+5}) + (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
19787 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) - (2 - 1)))) \\
19788 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (7 + (((6 \times -5) + (4^3))^2) + 1)) \\
19789 &:= ((9 - (8 - 76)) \times (5 + (4 \times (3 \times 21)))) \\
19790 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 \times 5) \times -((4^3) + 2)) + 1)) \\
19791 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5) + 4) \times -(3 \times 21)) \\
19792 &:= ((9876 + (5 \times 4)) \times (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
19793 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(((7 - 65) \times 43) + 21))) \\
19794 &:= ((98 + 7) + (6 + (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1})) \\
19795 &:= (9 + (8 + (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
19796 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 + 6)) - (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1})) \\
19797 &:= ((9 + (87 \times (65 \times (4 + 3)))) / -(2 \times -1)) \\
19798 &:= ((9876 + ((5 \times 4) + 3)) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
19799 &:= ((-98 \times ((7 + 6) - (5 \times 43))) + (2 + 1)) \\
19800 &:= ((9 - ((87 - 6) \times 5)) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
19801 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 + ((6 - (5^4)) \times 32)) \times -1)) \\
19802 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 + ((6 - (5^4)) \times 32)) \times -1)) \\
19803 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 + ((6 - (5^4)) \times 32)) - 1)) \\
19804 &:= (-98 - (((7 \times 6) + (5 \times 4)) \times -321)) \\
19805 &:= ((((-9 - 87) \times (6 - (5^4))) / 3) - 2) - 1) \\
19806 &:= ((9876 + ((5 + 4) \times 3)) \times -(2 \times -1)) \\
19807 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times (((6 - (5^4)) \times -32) - 1)) \\
19808 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times -((3 + 2) - 1))) \\
19809 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (76 + 5))) \times (((4^3) / -2) + 1)) \\
19810 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 \times 5) \times -((4^3) + 2)) - 1)) \\
19811 &:= (((98 + (7^6)) - (5^{4+3})) / -(2 \times -1)) \\
19812 &:= (((9^{8+7-6-5}) + 43) \times (2 + 1)) \\
19813 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) \times (5 - (4^3)))) + 2)) \times -1) \\
19814 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (7 - (((6 - (5^4)) \times 32) + 1))) \\
19815 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -((7 - ((6 - (5^4)) \times 32)) \times -1)) \\
19816 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 - ((6 - (5^4)) \times 32)) \times -1)) \\
19817 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 - (((6 - (5^4)) \times 32) - 1))) \\
19818 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 + ((6 - (5^4)) \times 32)) \times -1)) \\
19819 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 + ((6 - (5^4)) \times 32)) - 1)) \\
19820 &:= 9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5 + (4! + 3)^{2+1} \\
19821 &:= ((-98 / -7) + (((6 - (5^4)) \times -32) - 1)) \\
19822 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times -(3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
19823 &:= (98 - ((7 \times -6) - (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1})) \\
19824 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times 65)) \times (43 - (2 - 1))) \\
19825 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + (6 \times 5)))) \times ((4^3) + (2 - 1))) \\
19826 &:= ((9 - (876 - 5)) \times -((4 \times (3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
19827 &:= (9 \times ((8 \times -((7 \times 6) - (5 \times (4^3)))) - 21))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 19828 &:= (1 - (((2 - ((3 + 4) \times 5)) \times 67) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 19829 &:= (1 \times -(2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 19830 &:= (1 - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5) + (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 19831 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -(((3 + 4)^5) + (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 19832 &:= (1 \times -(((2^{3 \times 4}) \times -5) - ((6 - 78) \times 9))) \\
 19833 &:= (1 \times -((((2^3) \times 45) - 6) \times -(7 \times 8) - 9)) \\
 19834 &:= ((1 + (((2 + (3^4)) \times 5) + 6)) \times -((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
 19835 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times -(4 + ((5 + 6) \times 78))) - 9)) \\
 19836 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 \times -((((4 + 5) - 6)^7) + (8 + 9)))) \\
 19837 &:= (1 - (2 \times -((3 + ((4^5) + (67 + 8))) \times 9))) \\
 19838 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3^{4+5}) + 67)) + 89) \\
 19839 &:= ((12 + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times -(7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 19840 &:= (1 \times ((2^{3 \times 4}) + ((5^6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 19841 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5^6))) - (7 \times -(8 + 9))) \\
 19842 &:= ((1 - (((2^3) - 45) \times (67 \times 8))) + 9) \\
 19843 &:= ((12 + ((3 + 4)^5)) - (6 \times -(7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 19844 &:= ((12 - 34) \times -((5 + 6) \times -(7 - 89))) \\
 19845 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 + 4) - 56) \times -((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 19846 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3^4))) + (((5 \times (6 - 7)) + 8)^9)) \\
 19847 &:= (1 \times (((2^3) - ((4 \times 56) + 7)) \times -89)) \\
 19848 &:= ((1 + 23) \times -(4 - ((56 \times (7 + 8)) - 9))) \\
 19849 &:= (1 \times (23 \times -(4 - (((5 + 6) \times 78) + 9)))) \\
 19850 &:= ((12^3) - (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
 19851 &:= (1 \times -(((2^{3 \times 4}) \times -5) + (6 + (7 \times 89)))) \\
 19852 &:= (((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) - 6) + (7 \times -89)) \\
 19853 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (34 \times -(567 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 19854 &:= (1 \times ((2 - ((3 + ((45 - 6) \times 7)) \times 8)) \times -9)) \\
 19855 &:= (1 + ((2 - ((3 + ((45 - 6) \times 7)) \times 8)) \times -9)) \\
 19856 &:= ((1 + (((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times 8) - 9) \\
 19857 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5^6))) - ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\
 19858 &:= (1 \times (2 + (34 \times (567 + (8 + 9)))))) \\
 19859 &:= (1 + (2 + (34 \times (567 + (8 + 9)))))) \\
 19860 &:= (12 \times -(((34 + 5) \times -(6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9))) \\
 19861 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!^4 - 5) + 6! \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 19862 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 34)) \times 567) + 8) + 9) \\
 19863 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 \times -((((45 \times 6) + 7) \times 8) - 9))) \\
 19864 &:= (((12^3) - (4 + 5)) \times -((6 + 7) \times 8)) / -9) \\
 19865 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6))) - 7) \times 8) + 9) \\
 19866 &:= ((1 + (2^{3+4})) \times -((5 \times -(6 + 7)) - 89)) \\
 19867 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 3!^4 - 5 + 6! \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 19868 &:= (12 - (34 \times -(567 + (8 + 9))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 19828 &:= (9 - (((((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5) \times -(4^3)) + 21)) \\
 19829 &:= (((-987 - 6) \times -(5 \times 4)) - (32 - 1)) \\
 19830 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) \times -(5 - (4^3))) - (2 + 1))) \\
 19831 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) \times (5 - (4^3)))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
 19832 &:= ((9 + ((87 \times 6) + 5)) \times -((4 \times -(3^2)) - 1)) \\
 19833 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 - (((6 - (5^4)) \times 32) - 1))) \\
 19834 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -(7 \times (6 \times (54 + (3 + 2)))))) - 1)) \\
 19835 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) \times (5 - (4^3)))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
 19836 &:= (9 + (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) \times -(5 - (4^3))) + (2 + 1))) \\
 19837 &:= (9 - (8 - (76 \times (5 + (4^{3+2-1})))))) \\
 19838 &:= ((98 - 7) \times -(654 / -(3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
 19839 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -(76 - (((5^4) - 3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
 19840 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) - (6 - (5^4))) \times -(32 \times -1)) \\
 19841 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times (4 + (3 \times 21)))))) \\
 19842 &:= (9 + ((87 \times -(6 \times (5 - 43))) - (2 + 1))) \\
 19843 &:= (9 + ((87 \times -(6 \times (5 - 43))) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 19844 &:= (9 - ((87 \times -((65 \times 4) - 32)) + 1)) \\
 19845 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) \times ((43 + 2) \times -1)) \\
 19846 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5) \times (4^3))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 19847 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5) \times (4^3))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
 19848 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -((6 \times -((5 + (4^3)) \times 2)) + 1)) \\
 19849 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) + 4) \times 32)) \times 1) \\
 19850 &:= (((9 + 8) + (76 \times 5)) \times (((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
 19851 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5) \times (4^3))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
 19852 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5) \times -(4^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 19853 &:= (9 - (((87 - 6) \times 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) + 1)) \\
 19854 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) \times (5 - (4^3)))) + 21) \\
 19855 &:= (9 - (((87 - 6) \times 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
 19856 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((76 - (((5^4) - 3) \times 2)) \times -1)) \\
 19857 &:= (9 + (8 \times -(((7 \times 6) \times (5 - (4^3))) - (2 + 1)))) \\
 19858 &:= (((-987 - 6) \times -(5 \times 4)) - 3) + (2 - 1)) \\
 19859 &:= (98 - (((7^6) - (5^{4+3})) / -2) + 1)) \\
 19860 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times -(6 \times -((5 \times ((4^3) + 2)) + 1))) \\
 19861 &:= (98 - (((7^6) - (5^{4+3})) / -2) - 1)) \\
 19862 &:= (((-987 - 6) \times -(5 \times 4)) + (3 - 2)) + 1) \\
 19863 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 - 7)) \times -(((65 + 4) \times -32) + 1)) \\
 19864 &:= (((9 + 8) - (((7 - (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times -3)^2)) \times -1) \\
 19865 &:= (((-98 \times -7) - (6 - 5)) \times -(4 - (32 + 1))) \\
 19866 &:= (9 + ((87 \times -(6 \times (5 - 43)))) + 21)) \\
 19867 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - 4)) - 321) \\
 19868 &:= (((-987 - 6) \times -(5 \times 4)) + (3^2)) - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 19869 &:= (((-12 - 3) \times (4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))))) + 9) \\
 19870 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3 + 45) \times (6 \times (78 - 9)))))) \\
 19871 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times -9)) \\
 19872 &:= ((1 - ((2 + (3^4)) \times 5)) \times (6 \times -(7 - (8 - 9)))) \\
 19873 &:= (1 \times -(((234 \times 5) + (6 - 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
 19874 &:= ((1 + (((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times 8) + 9) \\
 19875 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times -9)) \\
 19876 &:= (1 + ((2 - (3 \times (4 + 5))) \times -(6 + 789))) \\
 19877 &:= ((123 + (4 \times 5)) \times (67 + (8 \times 9))) \\
 19878 &:= (123 - (((((4 + 5) - 6)^7) + 8) \times -9)) \\
 19879 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (((4 \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times 8)) - 9) \\
 19880 &:= ((1 - (2 + 34)) \times -(567 - (8 - 9))) \\
 19881 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 \times 45) + 6) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 19882 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) \times -((45 + 6) \times 78)) + 9)) \\
 19883 &:= (-1 + (2 \times -(3 - (45 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))))) \\
 19884 &:= ((12 + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times -9)) \\
 19885 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(3 - (45 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))))) \\
 19886 &:= (1 \times 2^{3!} \times 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
 19887 &:= ((-12 \times -((34 \times (56 - 7)) - 8)) - 9) \\
 19888 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) \times -(4 + (5 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9))))))) \\
 19889 &:= (1 + ((2^3) \times -(4 + (5 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9))))))) \\
 19890 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9))))) \\
 19891 &:= (-1 + (2 + ((34 + 5) \times (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
 19892 &:= (1 \times (2 + (34 \times (((5 + 67) \times 8) + 9)))) \\
 19893 &:= (1 + (2 + (34 \times (((5 + 67) \times 8) + 9)))) \\
 19894 &:= (-1 + (23 \times -(4 - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + (8 \times 9))))) \\
 19895 &:= ((1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) + ((5 \times (6^7))/8)))/ -9) \\
 19896 &:= (12 \times ((3 + (((4^5) \times (6 + 7))/8)) - 9)) \\
 19897 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 + (45 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))))) \\
 19898 &:= (-1 - (((((2 \times 3)^4) + (5 \times 6)) \times -(7 + 8)) - 9)) \\
 19899 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times -(((4 + 5) - 6)^7)) - (8 \times 9))) \\
 19900 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) \times -((45 + 6) \times 78)) - 9)) \\
 19901 &:= (-1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 19902 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 19903 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 19904 &:= (1 \times -((2 - 34) \times ((5 - 6) + (7 \times 89)))) \\
 19905 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) + (6 \times -(7 + 89))) \\
 19906 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 19907 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 19908 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3 \times -(4 \times (5 - ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
 19909 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) + (6 \times -(7 + 89)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 19869 &:= ((98 + (7 + 6)) \times -((5 \times -(4 + 32)) + 1)) \\
 19870 &:= (9 - (((((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5) \times -(4^3)) - 21)) \\
 19871 &:= (-98 + (((((7 - 6) - (5^4)) \times -32) + 1)) \\
 19872 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -((6 \times -((5 + (4^3)) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
 19873 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) + ((6 - (5^4)) \times (32 \times 1)))) \\
 19874 &:= (9 - (((8 \times -7) + ((6 - (5^4)) \times 32)) - 1)) \\
 19875 &:= (((9^{8+7-6-5}) + (4^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 19876 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -76) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)))) \\
 19877 &:= (-9 - (8 + ((7 - 65) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))) \\
 19878 &:= ((((-987 - 6) \times -(5 \times 4)) - 3) + 21) \\
 19879 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 - ((6 \times (5^4))/3)) \times 2))) \times -1) \\
 19880 &:= (((9 - 8) - (((7 - (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times -3)^2)) \times -1) \\
 19881 &:= ((9 - 8) \times -(((7 - (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times -3)^2) \times -1) \\
 19882 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 - (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times -3)^2) \times -1) \\
 19883 &:= (9 - (8 - (((7 - (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times -3)^2) + 1)) \\
 19884 &:= ((((-987 - 6) \times -(5 \times 4)) + 3) + 21) \\
 19885 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times ((54 \times -(3^2)) + 1)) \\
 19886 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -76) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\
 19887 &:= ((-9 + 87) + (((6 - (5^4)) \times -32) + 1)) \\
 19888 &:= (((((-9 + 87) \times 6) - 5) \times 43) - 21) \\
 19889 &:= (((98 + (7 + 6)) - ((5^4) \times 32)) \times -1) \\
 19890 &:= ((9 - 87) \times ((65 \times -4) + ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
 19891 &:= (9 + (((8 + (76 + (54 + 3)))^2) + 1)) \\
 19892 &:= ((((-987 - 6) \times -(5 \times 4)) - (32 \times -1)) \\
 19893 &:= ((((-987 - 6) \times -(5 \times 4)) + (32 + 1)) \\
 19894 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 - 65) \times -((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 19895 &:= (9 - (8 + ((7 - 65) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))) \\
 19896 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -((7 - ((6 \times (5^4))/3)) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
 19897 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((7 - (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times -3)^2) - 1)) \\
 19898 &:= (9 - ((8 + (((7 - (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times -3)^2)) \times -1) \\
 19899 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((7 - (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times -3)^2) + 1)) \\
 19900 &:= (98 - ((7 + ((6 - (5^4)) \times 32)) - 1)) \\
 19901 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (((7 \times 6) + (5 \times 4)) \times -32)) \\
 19902 &:= ((9 + (8 + 76)) \times -((5 \times -43) + (2 - 1))) \\
 19903 &:= (((98 - (7 - 6)) - ((5^4) \times 32)) \times -1) \\
 19904 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) - (((5^4) \times -32) + 1)) \\
 19905 &:= (((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) + ((5^4) \times 32)) \times 1) \\
 19906 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6 \times (5^4))/3)))) \times -((2 \times -1)) \\
 19907 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7^6)) - (54^3))/(2 \times -1) \\
 19908 &:= (((9 - 8) - ((7^6) - (54^3)))/ - (2 \times -1)) \\
 19909 &:= ((-9 - 87) + ((6 + ((5^4) \times 32)) - 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
19910 &:= (1 \times (2 - ((3 - 45) \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19911 &:= (1 + (2 - ((3 - 45) \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
19912 &:= ((1 - ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -(7 - (8 - 9))) \\
19913 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(((3^4) - 5) \times ((6 \times 7) + 89)))) \\
19914 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))))) \\
19915 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))))) \\
19916 &:= ((12 + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 + 7) \times -(8 + 9))) \\
19917 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 \times -(((45 \times 6) + 7) \times 8) + 9)) \\
19918 &:= ((1 + 234) + (((5 \times (6 - 7)) + 8)^9)) \\
19919 &:= (1 \times (2 - ((3 - (((45 \times 6) + 7) \times 8) \times 9))) \\
19920 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) \times (4 \times -(5 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
19921 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) - 45) \times -(6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
19922 &:= (1 \times -(((2^{3 \times 4}) \times -5) + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
19923 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times -9)) \\
19924 &:= (1 \times -(2 - ((3^4) \times ((5 \times 67) - 89)))) \\
19925 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^4) \times ((5 \times 67) - 89)))) \\
19926 &:= ((12^{3-4+5}) + (6 \times -((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
19927 &:= (-1 + (2 - ((3^{4-5+6}) \times (7 - 89)))) \\
19928 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
19929 &:= (12 + ((3 - (((45 \times 6) + 7) \times 8)) \times -9)) \\
19930 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(3 - ((45 + 67) \times 89)))) \\
19931 &:= (1 + (2 \times -(3 - ((45 + 67) \times 89)))) \\
19932 &:= (12 \times -(((3 + (4 \times 56)) \times -7) - (8 \times 9))) \\
19933 &:= (((1 + 2) - 34) \times (5 + ((6 - 78) \times 9))) \\
19934 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 34)) \times 567) + 89) \\
19935 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(3 - (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
19936 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) + ((67 \times -8) - 9)) \\
19937 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) - (5 - 67)) \times -89)) \\
19938 &:= (1 \times (2 \times -(3 - (((4^5) + (6 + 78)) \times 9))) \\
19939 &:= (1 \times -(2 + 3) - (((45 \times 6) + 7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
19940 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) - (((45 \times 6) + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
19941 &:= (1 \times (23 \times (((4 \times (5 + 6)) + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
19942 &:= (1 + (23 \times (((4 \times (5 + 6)) + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
19943 &:= (1 \times ((2 - 3) + (((45 \times 6) + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
19944 &:= (1 + ((2 - 3) + (((45 \times 6) + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
19945 &:= (1 \times -((2 - 3) - (((45 \times 6) + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
19946 &:= (1 \times (2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
19947 &:= (1 + (2 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
19948 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) + ((67 \times -8) + 9)) \\
19949 &:= (1 \times -(((2^{3 \times 4}) \times -5) + ((67 - 8) \times 9))) \\
19950 &:= ((12 + 3) \times ((4^5) + (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
19910 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5)/4)) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
19911 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 - 65) \times -((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
19912 &:= (98 + (7 - (((6 - (5^4)) \times 32) + 1))) \\
19913 &:= (98 - ((7 - ((6 - (5^4)) \times 32)) \times -1)) \\
19914 &:= (98 + (7 - (((6 - (5^4)) \times 32) - 1))) \\
19915 &:= ((9 - 87) - (6 - (((5^4) \times 32) - 1))) \\
19916 &:= (((9 + 8) - ((7^6) - (54^3))) / - (2 \times -1)) \\
19917 &:= ((9 - 87) - (6 - (((5^4) \times 32) + 1))) \\
19918 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times 43)) \times (2 - 1)) \\
19919 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times -43) - (2 - 1))) \\
19920 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times 43)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
19921 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times -43) - (2 + 1))) \\
19922 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times ((7 - 65) \times 43)) + 21)) \\
19923 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (765 + (4^3)))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
19924 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (((7 \times 6) - ((5^4) + 3)) \times -(2 \times 1))) \\
19925 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((76 - ((5^4) \times 32)) \times -1)) \\
19926 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (54 \times -(3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
19927 &:= ((9 - 87) + ((6 + ((5^4) \times 32)) - 1)) \\
19928 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 - (5 \times (43 \times 2))) \times -1)) \\
19929 &:= ((9 - 87) + (6 + (((5^4) \times 32) + 1))) \\
19930 &:= ((((-9 + 87) \times 6) - 5) \times 43) + 21 \\
19931 &:= (9 + 8! + 7 + 6 - 5! \times 4) / (3! / (2 + 1)) \\
19932 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 - 6) - (5^4)))) \times -((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
19933 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times (76 + 5)) + 4)) \times (32 - 1)) \\
19934 &:= (98 - (76 \times -(5 + (4^{3+2-1})))) \\
19935 &:= (9 - ((87 - 6) \times -((5 \times ((4 + 3)^2)) + 1))) \\
19936 &:= (((9 - (8 - (7 - 6))) - (5^4)) \times (32 \times -1)) \\
19937 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times ((6 \times 54) + 32)) - 1))) \\
19938 &:= ((((-9 + 876) \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)) - 2) - 1) \\
19939 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times -43) - 21)) \\
19940 &:= ((9 + 8) - (76 - (((5^4) \times 32) - 1))) \\
19941 &:= (9 - (((8 - 76) + ((5^4) \times 32)) \times -1)) \\
19942 &:= (9 + ((8 - 76) + (((5^4) \times 32) + 1))) \\
19943 &:= (((-9 + 876) \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)) - (2 \times -1)) \\
19944 &:= ((9 + (8 + 7)) \times -(((6 + (5 \times 4)) \times -32) + 1)) \\
19945 &:= (9 - (8 \times -(7 \times ((6 \times 54) + (32 \times 1))))) \\
19946 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - (6 - (((5^4) \times 32) - 1))) \\
19947 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times ((5 \times -(4 \times 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
19948 &:= (9 + (((8 \times -7) - 6) + (((5^4) \times 32) + 1))) \\
19949 &:= (((9 + (87 \times 6)) - (5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}))) \times -1) \\
19950 &:= ((9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times (5 \times -(43 - (2 - 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
19951 &:= (1 - (2 \times -(3 + (((4^5) + (6 + 78)) \times 9)))) & 19951 &:= (((9 + 8) + (((7 - 6) - (5^4)) \times 32)) \times -1) \\
19952 &:= (1 \times -((2^3) \times -(4 - (5 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 19952 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7 - (((6 \times (5^4))/3) \times 2))) - 1)) \\
19953 &:= (1 - ((2^3) \times -(4 - (5 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 19953 &:= (9 - (8 \times -((7 \times ((6 \times 54) + 32)) + 1))) \\
19954 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) + ((67 \times -8) + 9)) & 19954 &:= (9 + ((8 \times -(7 - (((6 \times (5^4))/3) \times 2))) + 1)) \\
19955 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times (45 + 6)))) \times ((7 \times 8) + 9)) & 19955 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) - ((5^4) \times 32)) \times -1) \\
19956 &:= (12 - (3 \times -(((4^5) \times 6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 19956 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 7) \times ((6 + 5)^{4-3+2}))) \times -1) \\
19957 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) + (6 \times -(78 + 9))) & 19957 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 \times -6) + ((5^4) \times 32)) - 1)) \\
19958 &:= (1 \times -(((2^{3 \times 4}) \times -5) + (6 \times (78 + 9)))) & 19958 &:= ((9 + 8) \times -((7 \times -(6 + (54 \times 3))) + (2 \times 1))) \\
19959 &:= ((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) + (6 \times -(78 + 9))) & 19959 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6 + ((5^4) \times 32)) \times -1)) \\
19960 &:= (1 \times -2 - (((34 \times (5 \times (6 + 7))) + 8) \times 9)) & 19960 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6 + (((5^4) \times 32) + 1))) \\
19961 &:= (1 - (2 - (((34 \times (5 \times (6 + 7))) + 8) \times 9)) & 19961 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 - 65) \times 43))) \times (2 - 1)) \\
19962 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 \times -45) + 6789)) & 19962 &:= ((9 - (87 \times 6)) - (5 \times -((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\
19963 &:= (1 \times -2 - ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) & 19963 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 - 65) \times 43))) - (2 \times -1)) \\
19964 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) & 19964 &:= ((9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5)) \times (((4^3) - 2) \times -1)) \\
19965 &:= ((1 - 2) \times -((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) & 19965 &:= (-9 - (((87 + 6) \times -5) \times 43) + 21)) \\
19966 &:= ((-1 + 23) - (((45 \times 6) + 7) \times -(8 \times 9))) & 19966 &:= (9 + (((87 \times -6) + (5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1)) \\
19967 &:= (1 \times -((((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times -8) + 9) & 19967 &:= (9 + ((87 \times -6) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
19968 &:= (1 - (((((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times -8) + 9)) & 19968 &:= (((98 + 7) - (6 - 5)) \times -((4^3) \times -(2 + 1))) \\
19969 &:= (1 \times -2 - ((3 + (((45 \times 6) + 7) \times 8)) \times 9)) & 19969 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 - 6) - (5^4)) \times -32) + 1)) \\
19970 &:= (1 \times -(((2^{3 \times 4}) \times -5) + (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 19970 &:= (9 - ((8 + (((7 - 6) - (5^4)) \times 32)) - 1)) \\
19971 &:= (((1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) - 6) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 19971 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 - (6 \times 54)) \times -(3 \times 21))) \\
19972 &:= (-1 + (2 + ((3 + (((45 \times 6) + 7) \times 8)) \times 9)) & 19972 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times ((5 \times (4^3) + 2))) - 1) \\
19973 &:= (1 \times (2 + ((3 + (((45 \times 6) + 7) \times 8)) \times 9)) & 19973 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times ((5 \times (4^3) + 2))) \times 1) \\
19974 &:= (1 + (2 + ((3 + (((45 \times 6) + 7) \times 8)) \times 9)) & 19974 &:= ((9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times ((5 \times (4^3) + 2))) + 1) \\
19975 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times -((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times -(8 + 9))) & 19975 &:= ((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times (5 + ((4^3) + 2))) - 1)) \\
19976 &:= ((1 - 23) \times (4 \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 + 9)))) & 19976 &:= ((9 - (((8 + (7 \times 6))/5)^4) - 3) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
19977 &:= ((12 + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times -((7 \times 8) - 9))) & 19977 &:= ((9 - (8 \times ((7 - 65) \times 43) - 2)) \times 1) \\
19978 &:= (1 \times -2 + (3 \times (4 - (56 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 19978 &:= ((98 + (((7 - (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times -3)^2) - 1) \\
19979 &:= (1 - (2 + (3 \times (4 - (56 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 19979 &:= (98 - (((7 - (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times -3)^2) \times -1)) \\
19980 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -((4 + ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times 8)) \times -9)) & 19980 &:= ((98 + (((7 - (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times -3)^2) + 1) \\
19981 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times -(4 - (56 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 19981 &:= ((-98/7) - (6 - (((5^4) \times 32) + 1))) \\
19982 &:= (1 \times -(((2^{3 \times 4}) \times -5) - (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 19982 &:= ((9 - (((8 + (7 \times 6))/5)^4)) \times -(3 - (2 - 1))) \\
19983 &:= ((1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + 6)) + (7 \times -(8 \times 9))) & 19983 &:= (9 - (((87 + 6) \times -5) \times 43) + 21)) \\
19984 &:= (-1 - (((((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times -8) - 9)) & 19984 &:= (9 + (8 - (((7 - 6) - (5^4)) \times 32) + 1)) \\
19985 &:= (1 \times -((((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times -8) - 9) & 19985 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((7 - 6) - (5^4)) \times -32) \times 1)) \\
19986 &:= (1 - (((((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times -8) - 9)) & 19986 &:= (9 + (8 - (((7 - 6) - (5^4)) \times 32) - 1)) \\
19987 &:= (1 \times -2 - ((3^{4+5}) + (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) & 19987 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) - (6 - (((5^4) \times 32) - 1))) \\
19988 &:= (1 - (2 - ((3^{4+5}) + (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) & 19988 &:= ((9 - (((8 + (7 \times 6))/5)^4) + 3) \times (2 \times -1)) \\
19989 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + 3) + (((45 \times 6) + 7) \times 8)) \times -9)) & 19989 &:= (9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6 + 5)^{4-3+2}) + 1))) \\
19990 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) + (((45 \times 6) + 7) \times 8)) \times -9)) & 19990 &:= ((98 - (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times -1)) \\
19991 &:= (1 \times -((((2 \times 3) + 4)^5) / -((6 + 7) - 8) + 9) & 19991 &:= ((-98/7) + ((6 + ((5^4) \times 32)) - 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
\mathbf{19992} := (((1+2) + (3^{4+5})) - (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times -9)) & \mathbf{19992} := ((9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6 \times (5^4))/3) \times -2) + 1)) \\
\mathbf{19993} := (1 - (2 \times -(3 \times (4 \times ((56 - 7) \times (8 + 9)))))) & \mathbf{19993} := (((((9 - 8)^7) \times -6) - (((5^4) \times -32) + 1)) \\
\mathbf{19994} := 1 \times 2 + 3! \times 4 \times (56 - 7) \times (8 + 9) & \mathbf{19994} := (((((9 - 8)^7) - 6) - (((5^4) \times -32) + 1)) \\
\mathbf{19995} := ((12 + 3) \times ((4 \times -(5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9)) & \mathbf{19995} := (((((9 - 8)^7) - 6) \times (((5 \times 4)^3) / -2) + 1)) \\
\mathbf{19996} := (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (-4! + (-5 + 6) \times 7! - 8 - 9) & \mathbf{19996} := ((9 - (8 \times ((7 - 6) + (5^4)))) \times -((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
\mathbf{19997} := (-1 + (2 \times -(3 - ((4^5) + (6 \times (7 + 8)))) \times 9))) & \mathbf{19997} := ((-9 \times -8) - (76 - (((5^4) \times 32) + 1))) \\
\mathbf{19998} := ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times -6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & \mathbf{19998} := ((9 - 8) \times -((7 - 6) - (((5^4) \times 32) - 1))) \\
\mathbf{19999} := (1 + ((2 - ((345 - 67) \times 8)) \times -9)) & \mathbf{19999} := ((9 - 8) - ((7 - 6) - (((5^4) \times 32) - 1))) \\
\mathbf{20000} := (1 \times (((2 \times 3) + 4^5) / - (67 - (8 \times 9))) & \mathbf{20000} := (((((9 - 8)^7) - 6) \times (((5 \times 4)^3) / - (2 \times 1)))
\end{array}$$

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